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O'ZBEKISTON DAVLAT JAHON TILLARI UNIVERSITETI
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ZAMONAVIY KO'P MADANIYATLI MAKONDA MUTAXASSISLIK TA'LIMI VA KASBIY TA'LIM MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIIY-AMALIY ANJUMAN

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MADANIYATLI MAKONDA
MUTAXASSISLIK TA‘LIMI VA
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mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman to‘plami

Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

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MATERIALLARI TO'PLAMI

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COLLECTION OF MATERIALS
from the international scientific and practical conference
**SPECIALIZED AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION IN
THE CONTEXT OF THE MODERN MULTICULTURAL
SPACE**

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

СБОРНИК МАТЕРИАЛОВ
международной научно-практической конференции
**ПРОФИЛЬНОЕ И ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЕ
ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННОГО
ПОЛИКУЛЬТУРНОГО ПРОСТРАНСТВА**

Ташкент, Узбекистан

Zamonaviy ko‘p madaniyatli makonda mutaxassislik ta‘limi va kasbiy ta‘lim /
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Ushbu to‘plamga 2025-yil 13-fevralda O‘zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti ikkinchi ingliz tili fakulteti O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti, Ingliz tili integrallashgan kursi kafedralari tomonidan o‘tkazilgan “Zamonaviy ko‘p madaniyatli makonda mutaxassislik ta‘limi va kasbiy ta‘lim” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari kiritilgan.

Maqola va tezislarning mazmuni, uslubi va imlosiga, keltirilgan ma‘lumotlarga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas‘ul.

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Ushbu to‘plam O‘zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti Kengashining 2025-yil 28-fevraldagi 7-son qarori bilan nashrga tavsiya etilgan.

ONLINE TEACHING PERSPECTIVES AND PREFERENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: *This article deals with the perspectives of online teaching, setting clear objectives, selecting appropriate materials, taking into account the learners' availability.*

Key words: *online learning, learning objectives, synchronous, asynchronous learning, course content, interaction.*

Learning online has multiple and relevant opportunities for both the teacher and the learner. The array of teaching/learning options, the readily available preparation and delivery of curriculum and resources, and the relevance to contemporary information and presentation formats capture opportunities for educators and educational needs.

Choosing the method of learning for students will depend on a number factors such as learning objectives, course content, the way teachers deliver their training/teaching and students' availability. When there is a choice between two formats of online or distance learning my own preference would go to hybrid learning model which unites both formats: asynchronous and synchronous.

Asynchronous learning doesn't require real-time and immediate interaction it can give our students some time for digesting suggested materials and learning them thoroughly. In asynchronous model students will deal with available content first which they may access any time suitable for their schedule. Moreover, asynchronous learning will help to engage students into a wide variety of instructional interactions and tasks which students may do independently or in collaboration. In my view, this learning format can be applied mostly to teacher-student and student-student modes of interactions.

Asynchronous learning supplemented with synchronous learning tools such as zoom conferences, educational video conferences, interactive webinars, online discussions, chats and lectures etc. will bring a variety to learning online benefitting both teachers and students of live interactions. A combination of both formats will offer flexibility needed to reach different students with varied schedules and available resources.

Before applying a blend of asynchronous and synchronous learning to our students as a teacher we should do a lot of planning and appropriate delivery of the course content. To my view, simple tasks, processes and standardized procedures will work best with teacher-student and student-student lines of communication. In asynchronous learning process students will learn how to be dependent on their peers or group mates and be capable of solving simple virtual class problems. On the contrary, more complex processes such as open discussions, Q&A, problem solving etc. should be organized in the presence of teacher i.e., during synchronous learning. From my personal standpoint, majority of modes of interactions will suit synchronous learning context which are just the matter of careful organization.

How does writing objectives connect with preparing for multilevel classes?

In writing objectives, we have to take into consideration the level of students, their interests, learner preferences. Differentiated instruction means providing multiple choice of tasks for learners' preference. The objective here to involve learners and provide with tasks that are of their interest and capacity. Some students are good at writing tasks, while others have ability to crafting or performing in action.

How does writing objectives connect with Universal Design for Learning (UDL)?

Writing objectives are closely connected with Universal Design for Learning (UDL) as we bear in mind Why, What and How of learning as an educator.

a) In Why of learning students practice "Sustaining effort and Persistence", namely "Heighten salience of goals and objective" in designing communicative tasks on Grammar.

b) In What of learning learners choose Comprehension-activate or supply background knowledge. Students design communicative tasks based on their background knowledge, thus activating and consolidating them.

c) In How of learning learners try Executive functions-support planning and strategy development.

How does writing objectives connect with language teaching?

Summarizing the readings given in this site, <https://www.colorincolorado.org/article/language-objectives-key-effective-content-area-instruction-english-learners> in writing objectives the following elements are crucial as we teach the content with the help of the language:

1. the key words of the topic or we call it metalanguage to use academic language in oral or written presentation or report, to comprehend the context;

2. language structures to construct appropriate content;
3. language skills to integrate and reinforce;
4. language strategies to better acquiring and managing the tasks.

How does writing objectives connect with theories of learning?

In writing objectives an instructor should be aware of the theories of learning:

1. appropriate action verb;
2. specific and measurable outcome;
3. learner-friendly instructions that are easy to follow and fulfill.

As a conclusion it can be assumed that online teaching demands a great deal of dedication in setting clear objectives, delivery of curriculum, course content, relevant resources, contemporary information, learner involvement, learner-friendly instructions, specific measurable outcome.

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CODE-SWITCHING AS A COGNITIVE AND PRAGMATIC STRATEGY IN BILINGUAL AND MULTILINGUAL COMMUNITIES

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Abstract: *Code-switching, the alternation between two or more languages within a conversation, is a fundamental phenomenon in bilingual and multilingual communication. This paper explores the role of code-switching in facilitating discourse, managing sociocultural identity, and optimizing cognitive efficiency. While traditionally analyzed through sociolinguistic perspectives, recent research highlights its cognitive and pragmatic significance. This paper explores how code-switching serves as a discourse strategy, enhances cognitive flexibility, and reflects sociocultural identity. Using a cross-linguistic approach, we analyze data from diverse linguistic communities to examine patterns of code-switching and their communicative functions. The study integrates insights from psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, and corpus-based research to reveal the underlying mechanisms driving this phenomenon. Findings suggest that code-switching is not merely a linguistic constraint but an adaptive strategy that enhances interaction and cognitive processing.*

Keywords: *Code-switching, bilingualism, multilingualism, cognitive linguistics, sociolinguistics, discourse strategies, psycholinguistics, cross-linguistic influence.*

Bilingual and multilingual speakers frequently alternate between languages within a single conversation, a phenomenon known as code-switching. Traditionally viewed as an irregular linguistic behavior, recent studies suggest that code-switching is a systematic and rule-governed strategy with cognitive and pragmatic advantages. Code-switching is often a marker of identity and cultural alignment in multilingual communities (Gumperz, 1982; Myers-Scotton, 1993). This paper explores the role of code-switching in communication, focusing on its cognitive functions, discourse strategies, and sociocultural implications.

Code-switching has been widely studied in sociolinguistics as a means of identity expression and group belonging. According to Myers-Scotton's (1993) *Markedness Model*, speakers switch languages to align with social norms and to negotiate power dynamics in conversations. For instance, bilingual speakers often shift to a high-prestige language in formal settings while using a colloquial variety in casual interactions. Recent studies have demonstrated that code-switching enhances pragmatic efficiency by allowing speakers to access linguistic resources unavailable in a single language. Speakers use code-switching to align with social groups, mark

solidarity, or create linguistic boundaries. In multilingual societies, language choice reflects cultural identity and power relations (Myers-Scotton, 1993).

From a cognitive perspective, bilinguals engage in code-switching as a form of mental flexibility, allowing them to activate and inhibit linguistic systems based on contextual demands (Green & Wei, 2014).

From a pragmatic perspective, code-switching serves discourse functions such as emphasis, clarification, or humor (Auer, 1998). In multilingual communities, switching between languages allows speakers to express emotions more accurately and adapt their speech to different interlocutors (Poplack, 1980). Scholars from various linguistic disciplines have examined code-switching to understand its cognitive implications, discourse functions, and social motivations. Linguists have categorized code-switching into different types based on its structural and functional properties:

Types of code-switching	Definition and usage	Examples
Inter-sentential code-switching	Occurs at sentence boundaries, where one sentence is in one language and the next in another (Poplack, 1980). This type of code-switching is mostly used between fluent bilingual speakers.	<i>Esli khochesh- uznat` podrobno pro nashu organizatsiiu, join our team!</i> <i>I'm going to sleep now. Yaxshi dam oling.</i>
Intra-sentential code-switching	Occurs within a single sentence, often requiring bilingual proficiency to maintain grammatical consistency (Muysken, 2000).	<i>Haven't done your homework, Nega?</i> <i>Why not, davajte pouzhinaem vmeste.</i>
Situational code-switching	Speakers switch languages based on changes in social setting (situational) like switching to a more professional tone in a meeting compared to a casual conversation with colleagues. (Blom & Gumperz, 1972).	<i>Znaesh- nam nuzhno topic specific vocabulary составить</i> <i>English language testing system ni kòrib chiqishimiz kerak ekan.</i>
Metaphorical code-switching	Speakers switch languages based on to convey specific social or emotional meanings (metaphorical)	<i>This is a real khoroshaia vozmozhnost-</i>

	like using a more authoritative tone to emphasize a point or switching to a more personal dialect to build rapport. (Blom & Gumperz, 1972).	<i>It is slegka difficult</i>
Tag-Switching	Involves inserting a word or phrase from another language without affecting the syntactic structure (Romaine, 1995).	<i>What a crisp day, tak ved-/ ne tak li? Are yu going to the US? Rostanmi?</i>

Sociolinguistic and pragmatic approaches

Code-switching has been widely studied in sociolinguistics as a means of identity expression and group belonging. According to Myers-Scotton's *Markedness Model*, speakers switch languages to align with social norms and to negotiate power dynamics in conversations. For instance, bilingual speakers often shift to a high-prestige language in formal settings while using a colloquial variety in casual interactions. From a pragmatic perspective, code-switching serves discourse functions such as emphasis, clarification, or humor. Code-switching is often used to improve discourse coherence and compensate for lexical gaps. Bilingual speakers may switch to a more expressive language to better convey meaning, emotion, or cultural references (Auer, 1998). In multilingual communities, switching between languages allows speakers to express emotions more accurately and adapt their speech to different interlocutors (Poplack, 1980).

Code-switching often serves as a strategic linguistic tool to create humor, highlight irony, or emphasize particular ideas. By alternating between languages, speakers can exploit contrasts in tone, meaning, or cultural associations to achieve rhetorical impact. This deliberate shift in language choice may enhance comedic timing, add a layer of sarcasm, or make a statement more engaging and memorable. The use of different linguistic codes allows speakers to play with meaning, shifting between formal and informal registers or evoking cultural references that resonate with specific audiences (Gardner-Chloros, 2009).

The practice of code-switching also plays a crucial role in signaling social identity and group affiliation. By switching between languages or dialects, speakers can assert their membership in a particular social or cultural group, reinforcing solidarity with in-group members while simultaneously distinguishing themselves from outsiders. This linguistic strategy helps navigate social boundaries, strengthen interpersonal relationships, and establish a sense of belonging. At the same time,

code-switching can serve as a means of distancing oneself from certain social groups, either by adopting a more formal or prestigious variety of a language or by deliberately avoiding specific linguistic markers associated with another group (Gumperz, 1982).

From my own perspective, code-switching is a natural and spontaneous phenomenon which occurs while communicating with bilingual or multilingual speakers in order to:

- clarify some key points of the conversation;
- show off the lexicon and expertise of knowledge of several foreign languages;
- express a sense of humour that is trendy and hide language incompetency at present.

As far as I am concerned, there are many potential merits of switching from one language into another, nevertheless it can provide with some demerits such as misunderstandings, challenges, stigmatization and linguistic discrimination during a speech. Following chart illustrates the data in terms of advantages of code-switching:

Psycholinguistic experiments further reveal that bilinguals process code-switched utterances faster when the switch aligns with syntactic boundaries, supporting the hypothesis that cognitive processing of code-switching follows structured patterns.

Code-switching is far more than an incidental feature of bilingual speech; it is a sophisticated linguistic and cognitive strategy that allows multilingual speakers to navigate complex communicative, social, and cognitive demands. While traditionally studied from a sociolinguistic perspective, recent research highlights its role in cognitive flexibility, discourse coherence, and identity negotiation. The phenomenon

follows systematic patterns influenced by grammatical structures, sociocultural norms, and cognitive processing constraints. Rather than being a sign of language deficiency, code-switching reflects bilinguals' adaptive language control and resourcefulness in communication. It enables speakers to optimize their expressive range, emphasize key ideas, and maintain fluid interaction across diverse contexts. Empirical studies show that code-switching enhances cognitive flexibility and strengthens executive control mechanisms, positioning bilinguals at an advantage in tasks requiring attentional control and problem-solving.

Future research should further explore the neurolinguistic mechanisms underlying code-switching and its long-term effects on language processing and bilingual cognition. Additionally, cross-cultural studies can offer deeper insights into how different linguistic communities use code-switching as a dynamic and meaningful element of multilingual communication. By recognizing its functional and strategic nature, we can better appreciate the cognitive and social advantages of bilingualism and multilingualism in an increasingly interconnected world.

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TALABALARNING RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYADAN ELEKTRON FOYDALANISHDADASTURIY -METODIK TA'MINOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar shiddat bilan rivojlanib boryapti va har bir sohada zamon bilan hamqadam odimlashni taqozo etadi. Masalan, sun'iy intellekt texnologiyacini joriy etish soliq to'lashdan bo'yin tovlash holatlarini aniqlash, firibgarliklarni oldini olish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va takporlanuvchi jarayonlarni avtomatlashtirish hamda shaffoflikni oshirishda qo'l kelsa, katta hajmli ma'lumotlar — Big data esa soliq organlariga kelib tushadigan katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni saqlash, qayta ishlash, tushumlarni yanada yaxshiroq bashorat qilish hamda to'lovchilar va soliq organlari o'rtasidagi hujjat almashinuvini yaxshilash imkoniyatini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli texnologiya, elektron tizim, axborot tizimlari, sun'iy intellekt, ta'lim tizimi, innovatsion metodlar, o'quv jarayoni, o'qitish, tadqiq qilish, rivojlantirish.

Аннотация: Сегодня цифровые технологии стремительно развиваются и требуют идти в ногу со временем во всех сферах. Например, внедрение технологии искусственного интеллекта помогает выявлять случаи уклонения от уплаты налогов, предотвращать мошенничество, анализировать данные и автоматизировать существующие процессы, повышать прозрачность, а большие данные – Большие данные дают возможность хранить и обрабатывать большие объемы данных, поступающих в налоговые органы, лучше прогнозировать доходы, улучшать обмен документами между налогоплательщиками и налоговыми органами.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые технологии, электронная система, информационные системы, искусственный интеллект, образовательная система, инновационные методы, образовательный процесс, обучение, исследования, разработки.

Annotation: Today, digital technologies are developing rapidly and require keeping up with the times in every field. For example, the introduction of artificial intelligence technology helps to detect tax evasion, prevent fraud, analyze data and automate tax processes, and increase transparency, while Big Data allows tax authorities to store and process large amounts of data, better predict revenues, and improve document exchange between payers and tax authorities.

Raqamli texnologiyalar hayotimizga shunchalik singib ketdiki, bugungi kunda nafaqat kundalik faoliyatimiz, balki ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sohalar rivojini ham ularsiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Tabiiyki, boshqa sohalarda bo'lgani singari kabi raqamli texnologiyalarni soliq ma'murchiligida joriy etish ham uning faoliyatini tubdan o'zgartirmoqda. Bu nafaqat soliq to'lovchilar va soliq organlari o'rtasidagi

munosabatlar bilan bog'liq bo'lib qolmay, balki deklaratsiyalarni taqdim etishdan tortib, to soliqlarni to'lash va ma'lumotlarni saqlash usullarigacha ham yangilikliklar kirityapti.

Asosiy qism xususan, tizimda yagona elektron platformani yaratish orqali ma'lumotlarni kiritish, to'plash, shakllantirish, tahlil qilishning zamonaviy uslubi yo'lga qo'yildi. Buning natijasida soliq hisobotlarini topshirish jarayoni 5-7 barobarga qisqardi. Ayni kezda 112 guruh va 1348 tovar va xizmatlar sinfidan iborat bo'lgan O'zbekiston Respublikasi tovarlar va xizmatlarning yagona elektron tasniflagichi uchun veb-portal joriy qilingan. Mahsulotlar va xizmatlar identifikatsiya kodlari yordamida 900 mingdan ortiq elektron hisob-fakturalar yaratilgan. Raqamli texnologiyalar taraqqiy etgan asrda eng muhim omil bu ma'lumotlar hisoblanadi. Ularni to'plab, o'rganishlar asosida xulosalar chiqarishda Big Data texnologiyasining ahamiyati katta.

Undan ko'pincha salmoqli ma'lumotlarning prognozli tahlillariga yoki ma'lumotlardan qiymat chiqarib olishning boshqa usullariga murojaat qilishda ham foydalaniladi. Big Data texnologiyalaridan olinadigan daromadlar yildan yilga o'sib bormoqda. U 2019-yilda 189,1 milliard dollarni tashkil etgan bo'lsa, 2022-yilda 274,3 milliard dollarga etishi kutilmoqda. AQSH, Avstraliya kabi mamlakatlarda katta hajmli ma'lumotlar texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish va moliyalashtirish bo'yicha maxsus davlat dasturlari ishlab chiqilgan.

Ma'lumotlarga ko'ra 2015-2016-yillarda Moliya vazirligining g'aznachilik departamenti va Davlat soliq qo'mitasi bilan hamkorlikda byudjetdan tashqari mablag'larni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri Moliya vazirligi g'aznachiligiga tushirishni yo'lga qo'yish maqsadida ma'lumotlar markazi serverlarining bir qismi yangilagan, biroq mazkur elektron qurilmalar bugungi kunga kelib ancha eskirgan.

Raqamli ta'lim tizimini yuksalishiga Wi-Fi zonalar IT parklar ochilishi katta xizmat qiladi. Ta'lim beruvchilarni raqamli texnologiyalar bilan ishlash qobiliyatini o'stirish va internet orqali turli ochiq kurslar tashkil etish imkoniyati tug'iladi. Bu esa o'z navbatida ta'lim beruvchilarni o'z ustida ko'proq ishlashi va raqobat tufayli ta'lim sifatini yanada ortishiga xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari raqamli texnologiyalar yana sun'iy intellekt texnologiyasini joriy etish soliq to'lashdan bo'yin tovlash holatlarini aniqlash, firibgarliklarni oldini olish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va takrorlanuvchi jarayonlarni avtomatlashtirish hamda shaffoflikni oshirishda qo'l kelsa, katta hajmli ma'lumotlar — Big data esa soliq organlariga kelib tushadigan katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni saqlash, qayta ishlash, tushumlarni yanada yaxshiroq

bashorat qilish hamda to'lovchilar va soliq organlari o'rtasidagi hujjat almashinuvini yaxshilash imkoniyatini beradi.

Raqamli texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirish insoniyat tarixidagi boshqa innovatsiyalarga qaraganda tezroq sodir bo'lmoqda: bor-yo'g'i yigirma yil ichida raqamli texnologiyalar rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar aholisining qariyb 50 foizini qamrab olishga va ularning yordami bilan jamiyatlarni o'zgartirishga muvaffaq bo'ldi.

Ta'lim sohasida virtual o'quv muhiti va masofaviy ta'limning ta'minlanishi talabalarga boshqa imkoniyatga ega bo'lmagan dasturlarda qatnashish imkonini berdi. Bundan tashqari, blokcheynga asoslangan tizimlardan foydalanish orqali davlat xizmatlaridan foydalanish qulay bo'ladi, ularni ta'minlovchi institutlar mas'uliyatini oshiradi va sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish natijasida jarayonlar kamroq byurokratik bo'ladi. Katta ma'lumotlar, shuningdek, yanada moslashuvchan va aniq siyosat va dasturlarga olib kelishi mumkin. Quyida raqamli texnologiyalarni bazilariga to'xtalib o'tamiz: bulutili texnologiyalar –internet foydalanuvchisiga on-layn xizmat sifatida kompyuter resurslarini taqdim etiladigan ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash texnologiyalaridir.

Talabalarda kasbiy kompetentligini va kasbiy moslasha ola bilishi, o'zlashtirgan bilimlarini kasbiy faoliyatida qo'llay olishi va ish beruvchining talablariga moslasha olishini rivojlantirish zarur. Kasbiy kompetentlik – mutaxassis tomonidan kasbiy faoliyatni amalga oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarning egallanishi va ularni amalda yuqori darajada qo'llay olinishi. Kasbiy kompetentlik mutaxassis tomonidan alohida bilim, malakalarning egallanishini emas, balki har bir mustaqil yo'nalish bo'yicha integrativ bilimlar va harakatlarning o'zlashtirilishini nazarda tutadi.

Shuningdek, kompetensiya mutaxassislik bilimlarini doimo boyitib borishni, yangi axborotlarni o'rganishni, muhim ijtimoiy talablarni anglay olishni, yangi ma'lumotlarni izlab topish, ularni qayta ishlash va o'z faoliyatida qo'llay bilishni taqozo etadi. Masofaviy ta'limda talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirishga imkor beradigan masofaviy ta'lim tizimlarni ko'rib chiqaylik.

Onlayn ta'lim sohasidagi eng yirik konsalting agentligining malumotlariga ko'ra dunyoda 800 dan ortiq masofaviy ta'lim tizimi mavjud. Masofaviy ta'lim tizimini juda ko'p kriteriyalar asosida tahlil qilishimiz mumkin va ular odatda sub'ektivdir. Biz xozircha ikki yo'nalishga ajratib chiqaylik:

Bepul foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan masofaviy ta'lim uchun eng yaxshi platformalar barcha ishtirokchilar, savol haqida o'ylab, to'rtta plitalardan biriga ishora qiladilar. Keyin fikr almashish, bahs-munozaralar olib boriladi. Har qanday ishtirokchi ishonchli dalillar ta'siri ostida pozitsiyani erkin o'zgartirishi mumkin. Natijalar sarhisob qilinadi.

Masofaviy ta'lim shakllaridan foydalanish talabning shaxsiyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi, u o'zi-o'zida rivojlanishni ko'radi, o'qituvchi ham buni ko'radi. Talabning rivojlanishi uchun qo'shimcha imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Xulosa. Masofaviy ta'limda tahsil olayotgan talabalarning bilim darajasi albatta DTS talablariga javob beradigan bo'lishi, an'anaviy ta'limda qatnab o'qiyotgan talabalardan kam bo'lmasligi kerak. Shuning uchun masofaviy ta'limni zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalardan, dasturiy ta'lim vositalardan, mobil ilovalardan, turli platformalardan unumli foydalangan holda tashkil qilish, shu bilan birga nafaqat ta'lim balki tarbiyalab borish har bir o'qituvchining oldiga qo'yilgan asosiy vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Masofaviy ta'lim jarayonida ham talabalarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, masofaviy ta'limda tahsil olgan talabning keyinchalik o'z ishiga bo'lgan munosabati va kasbiy kompetentligiga qarab, oliy ta'lim muassasasiga baho beriladi. Shuning uchun ushbu mavzu dolzarb deya e'tirof etishimiz mumkin.

Raqamli texnologiyalar - narsalar interneti (Internet of Things, IoT). Raqamli axborotga asoslangan asosiy texnologiyalardan biri bu narsalar internetidir. Ko'pgina maishiy texnikaning elektr tarmog'iga ulanganligi odatiy holdir, lekin asta-sekin jismoniy dunyoning tobora ko'proq ob'ektlari Internetga ulanadi, bu esa ma'lumot to'plash va hatto ushbu ob'ektlarni masofadan turib boshqarish imkonini beradi. Darhaqiqat, Internetda ob'ekt va tashqi dunyoning turli parametrlarini o'z ichiga olgan va Internet orqali ob'ektni boshqarish imkonini beruvchi jismoniy ob'ektning virtual nusxasi paydo bo'ladi. Narsalar internetiga misol qilib, kinoteatrdagi proyektor kabi qurilma texnik qo'llab-quvvatlash xizmatiga aniqlangan nosozlik va rejadan tashqari ta'mirlash doirasida almashtirilishi kerak bo'lgan ehtiyot qismlar ro'yxati haqida signal yuboradi.

Raqamli texnologiyalar - kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR). Eng istiqbolli - bu virtual dunyodan real dunyoga ob'ektlarni qo'shish imkonini beruvchi to'ldirilgan reallik texnologiyasi. Tasavvur qiling-a, ko'chada yurib, atrofingizdagi narsalar va odamlar haqida qo'shimcha ma'lumotni ko'rasiz. Kengaytirilgan haqiqat misollari allaqachon mavjud va faol qo'llanilmoqda, ba'zi istiroxat bog'larida siz jismoniy dunyodagi

ob'ekt va virtual dunyo o'rtasidagi aloqalarni ko'rsatadigan belgilarni allaqachon ko'rishingiz mumkin.

Raqamli texnologiyalar - virtual haqiqat (Virtual haqiqat, VR). Insonning virtual haqiqatda bo'lishiga imkon beruvchi texnik qurilmalarning paydo bo'lishi ushbu texnologiyani ko'ngilochar sohada talabga aylantirdi. Virtual haqiqatning dubulg'alari va kostyumlari, ixtisoslashtirilgan xonalar sizga noma'lum dunyoga kirishga imkon beradi, bu sizning barcha harakatlaringiz virtual olamdan javob berish uchun dasturlashtirilgan, bu sizga o'zingizni 100% ga cho'mish imkonini beradi.

Ta'lim sohasida VR o'quvchilarning bilim olish uslubini o'zgartiradi. Sinf xonalarida VR dan foydalanish o'quvchilarga bilimlarni yaxshiroq o'zlashtirish va qiyin tushunchalarni tasavvur qilish orqali o'rganishga yordam beradi. Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkinki raqamli texnologiyalarni turli sohalarga nafaqat ta'lim tizimiga joriy etilishi mamlakat ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilishda katta rol o'ynaydi. Zamonaviy ta'limni tashkil etish va ta'lim samaradorligini ortishiga xizmat qiladi.

Ta'lim tizimining hozirgi holati noan'anaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarining roli ortib borayotgani bilan tavsiflanadi. Ta'lim oluvchi tomonidan ularning yordami bilan bilimlarni o'zlashtirish an'anaviy texnologiyalarga qaraganda ancha tezdir. Ushbu texnologiyalar bilimlarni rivojlantirish, egallash va tarqatish xarakterini o'zgartiradi, o'rganilayotgan fanlarning mazmunini chuqurlashtirish va kengaytirish, uni tezda yangilash, samaraliroq o'qitish usullarini qo'llash, shuningdek, har bir kishi uchun ta'lim olish imkoniyatini sezilarli darajada kengaytirish imkonini beradi.

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INTENSIFIERS IN ENGLISH: FUNCTIONAL-STYLISTIC AND GRAMMATICAL ASPECTS

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Annotation: This article offers a summary of English intensifiers utilized in blogs. The blogs are analyzed through the lens of functional stylistics, highlighting features of colloquial and journalistic styles present in the Guardian newspaper's blogs. The techniques for enhancing the utterance and its components at the levels of word formation, morphology, and syntax are examined. The models of intensifier formation are defined: prefixation and stem addition. The numerical proportion of intensifier words categorized by parts of speech is identified: pronouns - 7%, verbs - 8%, adjectives - 15%, adverbs - 70%. In the structure of sentences, the compound nominal predicate shows the most common occurrence of intensifiers.

Key words: syntactic functions, parts of speech, intensifying meaning, functional styles, blogs, intensifiers, intensification.

Lately, the advancement of communication tools, worldwide information networks, and their accessibility has created genuinely boundless opportunities for interaction: almost anyone, regardless of social status, with Internet access can connect with others in diverse situations. The existence and communication of the largest segments of the population in the new information and communication landscape significantly influence the evolution and alteration of functional varieties of language. It appears that currently we are observing the onset of a stylistic breakthrough.

Blog, forum, chat - an unfinished listing of newly developed methods of communication that necessitate understanding in linguistic aspects. Examining the intensifying structures found in blogs helps us gain insight into the unique characteristics of literary language use in specific communication contexts among our contemporaries. Consequently, the importance of the article stems from socio-economic influences and the difficulties within linguistic science.

A blog serves as a notebook for the author's ideas, or more accurately, as a diary, as the entries are preserved automatically in chronological sequence. The term "blog" is actually a combination of two words: web (internet) and log (a record of occurrences). Blog writers direct their pieces—such as notes, thoughts, and factual presentations—towards a diverse audience that can share their opinions on what they have read. A blog serves as a community of shared interests as well as a venue for

discussions. The writer of a blog engages with his audience, debates with them, and explores the subjects brought up. Consequently, the primary piece of the blog is inundated with comments: feedback, viewpoints, critiques, and emotional displays of agreement or dissent.

The blog is conversational and engaging: the author and readers have ongoing, direct, and responsive communication. The blog serves as an instance of an interactive text, which has not been thoroughly examined in linguistics thus far. The blog's social character is evident, primarily, in its attraction to a diverse audience, meaning individuals from various social groups, tiers, and classes. Moreover, the blog is produced by individuals of a specific social standing, having a certain degree of education, culture, and particular interests in a specific field. Consequently, the discourse of bloggers and the format of blogs are influenced by social factors.

From a linguistic perspective, the style of blogs does not exist as an entirely distinct functional style; rather, it is a blend of multiple functional styles that interact, closely intertwined and intermingling with one another. The primary blog post and its accompanying comments, viewed as a cohesive text, lack a strong stylistic coherence. Although the primary article may be composed in one particular style, the tone of the comments on it can vary significantly from the register established by the article's author.

The quantity and, consequently, the substance of functional styles in linguistics have not been clearly established yet. Inquiries regarding the informal style continue to be contentious. The colloquial style is frequently compared to the written style. It appears that colloquial style is viewed as a spoken form of the language used in daily interactions. Communication through contemporary technological means demonstrates the truth of the notion that functional styles appear in both spoken and written forms of language. It is important to recognize that the depiction of everyday spoken language of characters in literature is not representative of colloquial style; rather, it serves to develop the characters' images, while communication conditioned by technical aspects in real time is essentially a dialogue, a conversation presented in writing.

Here is an example of text from the Blogs section of the Guardian newspaper. First, the headline attracts attention: Other cyclists are the scariest thing when you're on a bike? That's nonsense, set in a large font. Next comes the subheading, presented in a smaller font, but nevertheless attracting attention: An anonymous article in the Guardian on antisocial cyclists is contradictory, over-hyped and over-simplistic. The

headline not only introduces the topic, but also gives an unambiguous assessment of the material under discussion. The subheading contains a link to the article that prompted the blogger to express his opinion and reflects his emotional negative reaction.

In general, Guardian bloggers use their headlines to convey the main idea of the rest of the story: If something's famous, you don't need to tell people; if you need to tell people something's famous, it isn't. This allows them to attract the attention of the audience and convey the main idea in case the rest of the story is not read to the end.

But the most important thing is that blogs are written with the aim of getting feedback from readers, provoking controversy, and engaging in dialogue. The dialogic nature of blogs most closely resembles the conversational style. The main text of a blog and the texts of comments to it are structurally and semantically interconnected. For example, in the comments to a blog on the topic of Trial of GM plants to help fight heart disease given go-ahead, the statement I just think that GM will solve any of the issues of the current system gives rise to the response: Don't think.

Dialogic unities are also represented by question-question forms: Did god not make genetic scientists? - But would you accept that the patent of seeds is morally wrong, and has clouded the discussion on GM foods?; agreement accompanied by lexical repetition: That's figuratively amazing! - Ha - yes, that's the one! A new comment expressing disagreement often begins with a generally accepted formula of politeness: Apologies, I shouldn't have said machine harvesting; Yes, but I'm not suggesting that they change their mode of production or growth model within the current system. The blog's main idea is overgrown with additions, introduced by phrases such as "As an extension, This is the point being missed", which signal a change in the direction of the conversation.

Intensity in linguistics has not yet established a distinct status: it is linked to a specific expression of the categories of quantity, evaluation, and expressiveness. The broadest definitions of nouns and verbs are referred to as intensifiers. Nonetheless, all scholars agree that intensity appears at various linguistic levels: phonetic (intonation), lexical, and grammatical (morphological and syntactic).

Intensifier words in English are formed by affixation and addition of two bases. Prefixes that form intensifier words are: super-, over-, sub-, sur-, under- (over-hyped and over-simplistic, underpaid, surpass, subconscious, superman). The intensifying or weakening meaning is contained in the prefixes themselves.

The intensity of the quantity of a feature, object, action is expressed by:

1) the degree of comparison of adjectives: The world will be four times richer, more productive, more globalised and more highly educated. The wider economic effects were probably bigger; Doing something also makes you feel better and hence likely to do more. Intensification is carried out through a comparative assessment of the manifestation of quantity;

2) adverbs: It's the shortest way of saying «I know you may already know this, but I'm saying it again because it supports my point» - intensification through a superlative assessment of the manifestation of quantity; We're too interested in critics - intensification using an adverb of the degree too.

In quantitative terms, the intensifier words are distributed as follows: the pronoun accounts for 7%, the verb - 8%, the adjective - 15%. The leading position is occupied by the adverb - 70%.

The most common intensifier phrases are adverb + adjective (25%) and adverb + adverb (75%).

In the sentence structure, intensifiers perform various functions. In the blogs we reviewed, the most frequent use of intensifiers is found:

1) in a compound nominal predicate: The statistics are very clear (linking verb + adverb-intensifier + adjective); Cyclists are very rarely an actual danger to others, even for example when they weave across red lights (linking verb + adverb-intensifier + adverb of frequency + adjective + noun);

2) in a compound nominal predicate with homogeneous members of the nominal part: They're just less noticed, even normalized (linking verb + intensifying adverb + comparative adverb + past participle, additive adverb + past participle);

3) in complements: There is no certainty at all that the information revolution of the past 20 years will cascade down into ever more highly productive and value-creating industries;

4) in circumstances: Exactly. We have the technology to live in a far better world than we do.

The intensifying function is performed by the word order in a sentence. Changing the direct word order leads to the allocation of individual members of the sentence. Thus, shifting the subject to the end of the sentence and the complement to the beginning contributes to their intensification: Are quite the spectacle, all those couture shows!; Absolutely no desire to go back I have.

The intensifying effect is also achieved by rearranging the predicate or part of the compound predicate to the frontal position: Really serious are the impacts of climate change.

Separating the adverbial modifiers of time, degree, and manner of action from the predicate, moving them to a position unusual for the direct word order intensifies the meanings contained in them: Well did they play... in 1990... Rearranging adverbs and postpositions to the beginning of the sentence intensifies the predicate: Up are going the prices.

The use of special constructions without changing the word order can also intensify individual members of the sentence. Such constructions include sentences with the formal subject there, combined with a verb, a noun, and an attributive clause following them: There's two curiosities to this piece, which has been pretty widely-read. This example contains the colloquial form there's (a singular verb) combined with a plural noun.

Thus, the intensification of a statement or its part is achieved in various ways. Since blog texts are presented in written form, only punctuation marks and graphic design speak about their intonation (phonetic) design, then intensifiers are considered in grammatical and word-formation perspectives.

Word-formation models of modern English allow giving words an intensifying or deintensifying meaning using the prefixes super-, over-, sub-, sur-, under-; as well as by adding adjectives and adverbs that have an intensifying meaning to the bases of other nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs.

Changing the grammatical forms of words makes it possible to intensify the action (aspect-tense forms of the verb, using the analytical form with do instead of the synthetic one in Simple Present and Past; degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs intensify the features of objects and actions). Numerous adverbs act as intensifiers of action, both in individual use and in combination with other adverbs.

The intensifying meaning of the nominal part of the utterance is given by pronouns (reflexive and emphatic, indefinite), various classes of adverbs (intensifiers of degree, interrogative, attributive adverbs, adverbs of manner, frequency), various classes of adjectives.

In syntactic structures, words with intensifying properties perform various functions: predicate, part of a compound nominal predicate, subject, object, definition, circumstance. Constructions with a changed word order, introductory it and there give the effect of intensifying individual parts of the utterance.

Numerous examples of the use of intensifiers in blog texts indicate the implementation of the emotive, voluntative and phatic functions of language. The study of linguistic indicators leads to the conclusion that the research material - the texts of blogs of the English newspaper Guardian - represent a combination of two functional styles: journalistic and colloquial.

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QORIY IJODIDA DIDAKTIK MAVZU

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada *Qo'qon* adabiy muhiti vakillaridan biri bo'lgan *Qoriy* ijodiga mansub didaktik ruhda yozilgan *g'azallaridan* biri tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'z: *Qoriy, g'azal, an'ana, didaktika, ijtimoiylik.*

Qoriy lirik merosining asosiy qismini *g'azal* janri tashkil etadi. Shoir *g'azallarining* aksariyati diniy-ma'rifiy, ishqiy hamda qisman ijtimoiy mavzularda bitilgan. "Jam' bo'lg'on *g'unchalar, guldek parishon o'lmangiz*" misrasi bilan boshlanuvchi mazkur *g'azali* ham ijtimoiy mavzudagi *g'azallari* sirasiga kiradi. *G'azal* 10 baytdan iborat bo'lib, tuzilishiga ko'ra yakpora *g'azallaridan* biri sanaladi. *Qoriyning* ushbu *g'azalida* tasvirlangan mavzu chuqur va nihoyatda keng qamrovli, desak bo'ladi. Chunki, shoir she'rdagi insoniy munosabatlar, hayotiy masalalar, insonning tashvish va quvonchlari, orzu va intilishlari, his va tuyg'ulari haqidagi tushunchalarni birlashtirib, umumlashtirib beradi. Adabiyotshunos olim Aziz Qayumov "Qo'qon adabiy muhiti mintaqaning boshqa adabiy muhitlaridan bir necha xususiyatlari bilan farq qiladi, uchinchidan, zullisonaynlik an'anasi hukm surgan *Qo'qon* adabiy muhitida adabiy ta'sir va bahramandlik shu darajada yuqori bo'lganki, hatto bir shoirning ijodida o'z-o'zidan ta'sirlanish, bir tilda hosil qilgan adabiy tajribani boshqa tildagi ijodda ham qo'llash holatlari juda ko'p kuzatiladi"¹- degan fikrlarini *Qo'qon* adabiy muhiti shoirlaridan biri bo'lgan *Qoriy* ijodiga ham taalluqli deyish mumkin. Zero, *Qoriy* o'zbek va tojik tillarida birday ijod qilgan. *Qoriy g'azallarida* salafaridan ijodiy oziqlangan va ulardan o'ziga xos uslubda samarali foydalangan. Jumladan, mazkur *g'azalida* pand-nasihati ustivorligini shoirdagi qadimgi turkiy adabiyot an'alaridan bahramandlikni, an'anani ko'ramiz. "An'ana-she'riyatdagi uzviy silsilaviy hodisa va ma'lum bir tarixiy davrni o'tagan amaliy tajribalar natijasi. Mumtoz adabiyotimiz namoyandalari orasida bu bosqichni o'tamagan, salafari boy merosidan uzilib qolgan biror bir ijodkorni uchrata olmaymiz. Ammo ijodiy tasvirdan yuzaga kelgan har qanday o'xshash obraz, tasvir, *g'oyada* o'ziga xoslik yangilik singdirilgan bo'ladi. Yani, novatorlik an'ananing tadrijiy takomilidir"². Malumki, qadimgi turkiy adabiyot mahsuli bo'lgan asarlarda

¹Qayumov A. Amiriyy-Qo'qon adabiy muhitining asoschisi. // "Amiriyy va Qo'qon adabiy muhiti" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. - Tamaddun, 2017. - B.9

²Qobilova Z. Badiiy ijodda tasvir va izdoshlik. (Amiriyy she'riyati misolida). Monografiya. - T.: TURON-IQBOL. 2021. B.43

didaktik ruh ustivorlik qiladi. Qoriy tomonidan yaratilgan ushbu g'azalda qadimgi tukiy adbiyotning an'analari davom ettirilgan desak, mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Turkiy adabiyot vakillaridan bo'lgan Yusuf Xos Hojib, Ahmad Yugnakiy, Ahmad Yssaviy o'z asarlarida kishini o'tkinchi dunyo havaslariga berilmaslikka, hamjihatlikka, do'stlikka, hayotni qadriga yetishga undovchi misralar yozib qoldirgani adabiyot ahliga yaxshi ma'lum. Qoriyning ushbu g'azalida didaktika ijtimoiy mazmun bilan qorishiq holda beriladi. Bu holat adabiyotshunoslikda XX asr boshlari Qo'qon adabiy muhiti adabiyoti vakillari ijodining ham o'ziga xos jihatlaridan biri sifatida baholanadi. G'azalning birinchi bayti quyidagicha;

Jam' bo'lg'on g'unchalar, guldek parishon o'lmangiz,
Andalibi xushnavo bo'lg'on gulafshon bo'lmangiz.

Mazkur baytda istiora qo'llanilgan. Istiora-(arabcha so'z bo'lib, vaqtincha omonatga, oriyatga olmoq) - mumtoz adabiyotdagi she'riy san'at, bir so'z shaklini vaqtincha omonatga olib, boshqa, ya'ni ko'chma ma'noda ishlatish. Istiorada so'zni o'z ma'nosidan boshqa ma'noda ishlatish o'xshashlik amalga oshiriladi³. Shoir "g'unchalar" deb zamondoshlariga murojaat qiladi. Ularni gunchadek jam bo'lishga chaqiradi. Ochilgan gul kabi (tashbehni qo'llab) har tarafga tarqab ketmang, deya zorlanadi. Gul, bulbul bo'ston, gulafshon, g'uncha kabi so'zlarni bir baytga jamlab tanosub deb atalgan badiiy tasvir vositasini qo'llaydi. Keyingi baytda esa olamni jonlantirib yashildan libos kiydiradi va uni tomashagohga aylantirgan shoir odamlarni tabiat go'zalligidan zavqlanishga chaqiradi. Odamlarni gulgun ochilishi ya'ni tabiat go'zalligidan zavq olishini, osmonda bir safda qator tizilib turgan yulduzlardek jam bo'lishlarini istaydi:

Sabzadin olam tamoshogoh, sayri bog' uchun,
Ochiling gul-gul davomat dog'i xirmon o'lmangiz.
Do'stlar, go'yo banotun-na'sh bo'stonlar aro,
Lola bargidek parishon, dillari qon o'lmangiz.

Shoir do'stlarga murojaat qilib, ularni tabiat qo'yniga chaqiradi. Kishilarni tabiat go'zalligidan bahramand bo'lishga, bir-birlari bilan inoq, do'st bo'lishga, tarqoq bo'lmaslikka da'vat qiladi. Lola barglarining to'kilishi uni doim xavotirga solib, dilini vayron qiladi. Siz ham lola bargidek bo'lmang,-deya ularni hamjihatlikka undaydi. Navbatdagi baytda shoir olamni visol bog'iga qiyoslaydi:

³Quronov D va b. Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. T.: -AKADEMNASHR, 2010. B. 124

Vasl bog'i sabzu xurram gullar ochilgan kabi,
Sochilib haryon judolikdin pushaymon o'lmangiz.

Visol bog'i tabiatning bu sahovatidan shod. Bu shodlikni ifodalashda yana jonlantirishga murojaat qiladi. Gul ochilgach, har tarafga sochilib ketadi, yaproqlari to'kiladi. Siz ana shu gul bargidek parishon bo'lmang, deya ularni sergaklikka undaydi. G'azalning yettinchi, sakkizinchi, to'qqizinchi, o'ninchi baytlarida shoir tashbehdan mahorat bilan foydalanadi. Do'stlarni tarqalib ketishini nozaninlarning yoyilgan sochlariga qiyoslasa:

Oshnolik rutbasi bo'lsin musallam sizlarga,
Nozaninlar zulfidek haryona larzon o'lmangiz.

bir o'rinda bo'ston ichida suman va sarvga oshiqqan bulbulga mengzaydi:

Sayri gulzor aylagan bulbul kabi bo'ston aro
Betamoshoyi suman, besarvu rayhon o'lmangiz.

Shoir lolani visolga yeta olmaganidan ko'ksida dog' borligidan har tarafga yoyilib ketishini otni qamchi bilan urganda alam bilan turli tomonga qarab qochish tasviri bilan muqoyasa qiladi:

Iftiroqi vaslidin ko'ksi qarodur lolani,
Qamchi urgan raxshdek haryona javlon o'lmangiz.

G'azalning maqta'sida yo'lingizdan adashmay to'g'ri Farg'onaga kelsangiz (yo'lingiz Farg'onaga tushsa), Qoriyning bo'stonidan (she'rlaridan) bahramand bo'ling, deya murojaat qiladi:

Sayr etib obi ravondek kelsangiz Farg'onaga,
Qorining bo'stonidin g'ayriga mehmon o'lmangiz.

Modomiki, fikr badiiy adabiyotda adbiy ta'sir haqida borar ekan, turkiy xalqlar adabiyotida ilk bor aruz vaznida yaratilgan adib Yusuf Xos Hojibning "Qutadg'u bilig" asaridan tortib, Qo'qon adabiy muhitining yirik vakili Qoriy ijodida ham didaktikaning ustivorligini ko'ramiz. Adabiyotshunos olim A. Hojiahmedov "Mumtoz shoirlarimiz she'riyatida "hayot va jamiyat, inson va muhabbat, shoir taqdiri, hijron alamlari haqidagi teran falsafiy mushohadalar vazmin, salobatli vaznlar vositasida ifodalansa, mahbuba tavsifi, oshiqning ehtirosli kechinmalari yengilroq, jozibador ohangdagi baytlarda mujassamlashtiriladi, vafo va sadoqat tantanasi esa sho'x va o'ynoqi ritmga asoslangan misralarda tarannum etiladi", -deydi. Bu fikrlar Qoriy asarlariga ham tegishli deb bilamiz. Chunki, shoir asarlarida muallif aytganidek hayot va jamiyat masalasi ham Vatan tasviri ham, tabiatdan zavqlanish

ham, ma'shuqaning go'zalligi hamda befavoligi, oshiqqa qilgan jabr-u sitamlari ham o'z ifodasini topgan.

THE CURRENT CHALLENGES OF TEACHING ESP

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Abstract: *The simple mastering of the four skills (reading, writing, listening and speaking) and the acquisition of general grammar and vocabulary may not be enough in some circumstances. ESP focuses on the specific needs of the learners, concentrating more on language in context and on the students' need to acquire a set of professional skills and particular job-related functions. This paper, consequently, focuses on identifying the current challenges that teachers and students may encounter in the process of teaching and learning English for Specific Purposes.*

Key words: *English for Specific Purposes, vocabulary, authentic materials, ESL learning contexts and a multi-disciplinary approach.*

Introduction

Some general considerations on ESP As any other kind of language teaching, English for Specific Purposes is first and foremost based on the process of learning, a process which nevertheless addresses the needs of certain communities of learners, namely individuals interested in acquiring some professional skills and performing jobrelated practices. Due to its oriented focus, ESP exhibits some characteristics that differentiate it from ESL (English as a Second Language) or EGP (English for General Purposes). First, it is language in context, this fact requiring real life learning situations, scenarios that tent to replicate the specific working or professional settings the ESP students might be related to or interested in. Instead of focusing on general grammar, vocabulary and language structures, this teaching – learning intercourse stresses the importance of practicing the necessary skills one would mostly employ in their future fields of activity. In comparison with the ESL learning contexts, the ESP students' motivational levels should thus be enhanced by their knowledge of the subject matter, their interest in the field fuelling their active participation in English classes. ESP “assesses needs and integrates motivation, subject matter and content for the teaching of relevant skills” [1]. Since its emergence in the late 1960s, ESP has undergone a constant process of development, defining its scope, improving methodology, shaping its objectives and orientations, and enlarging the number of course books designed to serve its purposes. Its emergence, however, was the direct result of a three-directional process [2] which began immediately after the Second World War and had as a starting point a boom in science, technology and economic

activities at an international level. This fact triggered off the emergence of a community of people tied by their interest in learning English, not for the mere pleasure of knowing it, but for its utility and efficiency in handling specific job-related practices. The second reason underlining the advent of ESP was a revolution in linguistics which shifted specialists' attitudes and attention towards real communicational language opportunities and contexts, rather than focusing on the old-fashioned formalist view on language.

Towards a definition of ESP Various attempts have been made at sketching out, as comprehensively as possible, a definition of this complex subject. In their book *Developments in English for Specific Purposes: A multi-disciplinary approach*, Tony Dudley-Evans and Maggie Jo St John [3] define ESP in terms of absolute and variable characteristics. Absolute traits or features, as the authors claim, include: ESP being designed to meet the specific needs of the learners; it making use of the underlying methodology and activities of the disciplines it serves; ESP being centered on the language, skills, discourse and genres that are thought to be relevant to the above mentioned activities. Variable characteristics, in addition to the previously enumerated ones, emphasise the likelihood of: ESP being related to or designed for specific disciplines; it using a different methodology from that of general English, in specific teaching situations; ESP being designed for adult learners, either at a tertiary level institution or in a professional work situation, without excluding the possibility of being used by learners at secondary school levels; ESP being aimed at intermediate or advanced students, the basic knowledge of the language system being important but not compulsory, the course having the possibility to be tailored to beginners, too. This definition suggests that ESP, instead of being a restrictive, narrowing field of study is actually a permissive, flexible one, having influenced the entire process of English teaching. Even EGP teachers nowadays are likely to be influenced by ESP methods and techniques when they choose to design their syllabi starting from learner needs analyses or to use English in real communication contexts, instead of focusing on grammar or vocabulary related activities [4], [5]. The distinction between EGP and ESP offers us a better understanding of the latter's traits. Thus, while EGP has as an ultimate purpose education in general, ESP is mostly centred on training. The former is usually in the position of predicting with difficulty the very needs of the learners, whereas the latter is meant to be employed in specific professional contexts [6]. In trying to capture the essence of ESP, Hutchinson and Waters give a short but detailed account of it, underlining the fact that it has to be perceived as an approach,

and not as a product. “ESP is not a particular kind of language or methodology, nor does it consist of a particular type of teaching material. Understood properly, it is an approach to language learning, which is based on learner need.”[2] 3. Current challenges in teaching ESP 3.1. Course design One of the greatest challenges of teaching any subject is the course design. Due to the fact that the ESP students have their objectives well-defined from the very beginning, these being directly related to their practical, job-related or professionally oriented needs, the choices the teachers have to make in order to design a course should not, theoretically, be so complicated. The reality, however, is different. According to David Carver [7], [8], an ESP course should be based on three elements; first, it has to offer authentic materials, then it requires a purpose-related orientation, which means that a reasonable simulacrum of reality in which practitioners have the possibility to get involved into communicative tasks that replicate real situations is mandatory, and last but not least, it should be defined by self direction, i.e. learners are to become active users. In order to cover all the areas that might play an essential role in the process of course elaboration, the ESP teacher should be ready to ask some questions and gather information in the field so as to create an important database for further developments. The inquiries to be made are: Why do the students need to learn? Who is going to take part in the process (teachers, students, sponsors, experts in the field)? Where is the learning process going to take place? Does the location provide any potential or impose limitations? When is it set to take place? Is there a time limit to be taken into consideration? What does the student need to learn? What aspects of the language would be more appropriate under the given circumstances? How will the learning be achieved, i.e. what theoretical background will be chosen to fuel the methodology that is meant to be used? [2]

Conclusions

In comparison with teaching EGP, teaching ESP usually poses a lot more challenges. Focusing on the specific needs of the learners, concentrating more on language in context and on the students' need to acquire a set of professional skills and particular job-related functions, ESP remains a major testing experience for every teacher in charge of it. [2]. The emphasis on learners' wants and interests, and learning autonomy does not diminish the role of the teachers; on the contrary they need to subject themselves to a continuous process of adaptation and evaluation in order to meet the requirements imposed by the subject they are teaching. They need to design courses keeping in mind the nature of the particular target and learning

situations they are to deal with, at the same time juggling professionally with the requirements imposed by working with large heterogeneous classes.

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USING MNEMONICS FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TECHNIQUES FOR REMEMBERING PRESENTATION MATERIAL

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Annotation: *Language learning can be a daunting task, particularly for those who struggle with retaining new vocabulary and grammar rules. This article discusses the effectiveness of incorporating mnemonic devices and memory techniques to enhance language learning and speech delivery. It explores various mnemonic strategies, such as the memory palace technique and visualization, along with the importance of repetition and engaging multiple senses in the memorization process. Additionally, the article emphasizes the significance of understanding the material, practicing regularly, and seeking feedback from others to improve speech delivery. Overall, it provides valuable insights and practical tips for language learners aiming to enhance their memory and communication skills.*

Annotatsiya: *Til o'rganish qiyin vazifa bo'lishi mumkin, ayniqsa yangi lug'at va grammatika qoidalarini eslab qolish bilan kurashayotganlar uchun. Ushbu maqola tilni o'rganish va nutqni yetkazib berishni yaxshilash uchun mnemonik qurilmalar va xotira usullarini o'z ichiga olish samaradorligini muhokama qiladi. U xotira saroyi texnikasi va vizualizatsiya kabi turli xil mnemonik strategiyalarni, shuningdek takrorlash va yodlash jarayonida bir nechta hislarni jalb qilishning ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, maqola nutqni yaxshilash uchun materialni tushunish, muntazam ravishda mashq qilish va boshqalardan fikr-mulohazalarni izlash muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Umuman olganda, u til o'rganuvchilar uchun qimmatli tushunchalar va amaliy maslahatlar beradi, ularning xotirasi va muloqot qobiliyatlarini oshirishga qaratilgan.*

Аннотация: *Изучение языка может оказаться непростой задачей, особенно для тех, кому сложно запомнить новый словарный запас и грамматические правила. В этой статье обсуждается эффективность использования мнемонических устройств и методов запоминания для улучшения изучения языка и речи. В нем исследуются различные мнемонические стратегии, такие как техника дворца памяти и визуализация, а также важность повторения и задействования нескольких чувств в процессе запоминания. Кроме того, в статье подчеркивается важность понимания материала, регулярной практики и получения обратной связи от других для улучшения речи. В целом, он предоставляет ценную информацию и практические советы для изучающих язык, стремящихся улучшить свою память и коммуникативные навыки.*

Learning a new language can be a daunting task, especially for those who do not naturally excel in this area. Many learners find it difficult to retain new vocabulary and grammar rules, making the process overwhelming. However, using mnemonics and memory techniques can greatly improve the language learning experience. Mnemonics are memory aids that link new information to existing knowledge, which is particularly helpful for memorizing vocabulary. For example, learners can create

mental images that connect new words to familiar objects, making it easier to recall the words when needed.

The Origins and Role of Mnemonics: Mnemonics have been a part of memory improvement techniques since ancient times. The term "mnemonic" comes from the Greek word Mnemosyne, the goddess of memory. These techniques date back to at least 500 B.C. Memory is crucial in learning vocabulary and grammar, involving both short-term and long-term memory. Short-term memory holds information temporarily but processes it quickly, while long-term memory has unlimited capacity but is slower. The goal of language learning is to transfer information from short-term to long-term memory.

Using Mnemonics in Language Learning: Mnemonics are effective instructional strategies that enhance memory by connecting new information to existing knowledge. This makes it easier to retain new material for longer periods and retrieve it when needed. In language learning, mnemonics often use imagery or grouping techniques to link new words to previously learned information.

Historical Context and Techniques: According to legend, the Greek poet Simonides of Ceos developed a memory technique after using spatial memory to identify victims of a building collapse. This method, known today as the "memory palace" or house memorization technique, involves visualizing a familiar place and associating specific locations within it with key points to remember. Ancient Greek and Roman orators used a similar method called the "loci" method to remember lengthy speeches and lists.

Practical Application of Memory Techniques: To use the loci system, visualize a familiar route or place and mentally walk through it, assigning key points of your presentation to specific landmarks. This technique helps you recall each point effortlessly by mentally navigating through the familiar space. Breaking down speech content into manageable sections also aids memory, allowing flexibility in rearranging or shortening the talk.

Developing Proficiency with Memory Tools: Regular practice with these memory techniques can improve recall abilities, leading to more natural and fluid presentations. Understanding and internalizing the material, rather than just memorizing it, is crucial. Visualizing speech content using mental imagery or mind mapping can also enhance memory, as can repetition through various forms like reciting, writing, or recording the speech.

Additional Memory Aids: Using mnemonics and acronyms can further facilitate memorization. Creating memorable acronyms or associations helps retain information. Visual aids like slides or props serve as reminders during presentations. Engaging multiple senses—reading aloud, visualizing, writing by hand—reinforces memory. Seeking feedback from others by rehearsing in front of an audience helps refine the speech and strengthen memory.

Effective Speech Delivery: When delivering your speech, focus on conveying your message with passion and enthusiasm. Being genuinely invested in your topic makes it easier to remember because you are sharing something meaningful, not just reciting words.

Conclusion: Remembering a speech can be challenging but manageable. By using memory techniques such as the memory palace, visualization, mnemonics, and sensory engagement, you can deliver your speech with confidence. Consistent practice and passionate delivery are key to making a lasting impact on your audience. Incorporating mnemonic devices and memory techniques not only enhances language learning but also improves the ability to remember and deliver speeches effectively. Regular practice, utilizing various resources, and setting specific goals can significantly improve language skills and presentation abilities.

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OPTIMIZING MEMORY RETENTION IN FLT: THE ROLE OF FLASHCARD COMPETITIONS AND VISUAL CUES

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Annotation. *In foreign language teaching (FLT), ensuring long-term retention of key terminology and concepts is a critical challenge. Traditional rote memorization methods often fail to engage students effectively, leading to passive learning and low retention rates. This article presents an innovative technique that integrates paper-based flashcards with visual cues and gamified competitions to enhance memory recall. The method consists of two structured games: a team-based matching activity and an individual competition that encourages active retrieval practice. Over the course of the semester, this technique showed significant improvement in student recall and engagement. By combining principles of retrieval practice, spaced repetition, and gamification, this approach increases student motivation, fosters active recall, and improves long-term retention. The study explores the theoretical foundations of this technique, its practical implementation in FLT courses, student feedback, and potential future developments.*

Keywords: *foreign language teaching (flt), flashcards in flt, memory retention techniques, active recall, gamification in education, visual learning strategies, collaborative learning, competitive learning, educational flashcard games, lexical competence, student engagement, assessment techniques, formative assessment, paper-based learning tools, icon-based learning, vocabulary acquisition, final exam preparation, fl teaching methodologies, innovative teaching techniques, interactive learning methods.*

The effectiveness of foreign language teaching depends not only on exposure to linguistic input but also on learners' ability to retain and recall information efficiently. Traditional memorization techniques, such as repetitive reading and passive review, often result in short-term retention with minimal long-term benefits. However, research in cognitive psychology and pedagogy suggests that active recall, visual learning, and gamification can significantly enhance memory retention.

This article introduces a structured flashcard-based retrieval technique designed to help students internalize key terminology in FLT through a combination of visual cues, team-based collaboration, and competitive recall games. Implemented over the course of a semester, the method led to measurable improvements in student performance, increasing both their knowledge retention and engagement.

Retrieval practice is a highly effective memory technique that involves actively recalling information rather than passively reviewing it. Research by Roediger & Karpicke (2006) demonstrates that frequent testing and retrieval-based activities enhance long-term retention more effectively than repeated exposure to study

material. Flashcards, especially when used in structured recall exercises, encourage students to actively retrieve information, strengthening neural connections associated with memory.

Visual aids have long been recognized as powerful tools for learning. According to Paivio's Dual Coding Theory (1971), information that is both verbally and visually encoded is more likely to be retained. To leverage this effect, each flashcard includes an icon or image, allowing students to create a mental link between the term, its definition, and a visual representation. This multisensory learning approach makes abstract concepts easier to remember.

Gamification—the use of game elements in education—has been proven to increase motivation, engagement, and cognitive effort (Deterding et al., 2011). By integrating competitive mini-games into FLT terminology practice, this technique transforms memorization into a dynamic, interactive, and enjoyable learning experience.

The foundation of this technique is a set of 150 paper-based flashcards, each featuring:

- A term related to FLT methodology
- A concise definition
- A visual icon or image sourced from picture dictionaries, photos, and Google images

Unlike digital flashcards, these tangible cards allow for physical interaction, making them ideal for in-class activities.

The method consists of two structured learning games that encourage both collaborative and individual retrieval practice.

Students work in teams to match the term, definition, and icon correctly.

This collaborative phase allows for peer learning and discussion, reinforcing understanding.

Students participate in an individual competition, structured in three rounds:

1. Each student draws a ticket with a term.
2. If they can immediately recall the definition, they earn a point.
3. If they fail to recall, they sit down, prepare for the term, and attempt again in the next round—but without earning a point.
4. Students who accumulate three points receive an “A” grade, providing strong motivation for participation.

This structured system balances pressure with opportunity, encouraging students to actively retrieve and reinforce their knowledge over time.

-Early in the semester, the technique was used occasionally to introduce students to the method.

-By the end of the semester, it was implemented in every lesson, ensuring students were fully prepared for their final exam.

-This approach aligns with Ebbinghaus's Forgetting Curve, reinforcing concepts at increasing intervals to strengthen retention.

-At the beginning of the semester:

-Most students struggled to recall the terminology.

-Matching terms, definitions, and icons was challenging in the early stages.

By the end of the semester:

-Students demonstrated substantial improvement, correctly recalling more than half of the terms.

-Faster recall and greater accuracy were observed during individual competitions.

-Students responded positively to the technique, noting that:

-The games made learning fun and engaging rather than stressful.

-The visual icons helped them remember complex terminology more easily.

-The competitive element increased motivation to participate actively.

-The structured repetition helped them feel confident by the time of the final exam.

While direct exam performance data was not collected for this study, qualitative observations suggest that students retained more information compared to traditional study methods. The shift from passive memorization to active recall played a key role in knowledge retention and exam preparedness.

To enhance the effectiveness of this technique in future semesters, potential improvements include:

-Expanding the flashcard set to cover more advanced terminology.

-Introducing digital versions of the flashcards (e.g., Quizlet, Anki) for additional self-study.

-Adding new game variations to keep the competitions dynamic.

-Collecting quantitative data on student performance to measure retention rates.

These refinements would further solidify the technique as a highly effective retrieval-based learning strategy in FLT.

The integration of flashcard-based retrieval, visual cues, and gamified competitions offers an innovative and effective method for optimizing memory retention in FLT. By combining active recall, collaborative learning, and motivational game elements, this technique not only improves knowledge retention but also enhances classroom engagement.

Observed results indicate that students who initially struggled with recall showed marked improvement over time, supporting the efficacy of this approach. Future research could explore quantitative performance comparisons and adaptations for different language-learning contexts.

By making learning both structured and interactive, this technique represents a promising advancement in foreign language pedagogy, merging cognitive science principles with practical, engaging teaching methodologies.

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MIFOLOGIYANI O'RGANGAN INGLIZ OLIMLARI ENGLISH SCHOLARS WHO STUDIED MYTHOLOGY

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola adabiyotshunoslikdagi eng muhim masalalardan birini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Mifologiyani o'rgangan ingliz olimlari va ularning asarlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Bundan tashqari, ularning mifologiya sohasiga qo'shgan xissalari haqida ham ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mifologiya genezisi, Ser Jorj Frezer, Endryu Leng, Edward Burnett Tylor, Robert Graves, Maksvell Myuller, Zamonaviy yondashuvlar.

KIRISH

Mifologiya insoniyat tarixidagi eng qadimiy va boy madaniy qatlamlardan biri bo'lib, u xalq e'tiqodlari, dunyoqarashi va tarixini o'rganishga imkon beradi. Bu sohada ingliz olimlarining hissasi alohida o'ringa ega, chunki ular mifologiyani nafaqat ilmiy nuqtai nazardan o'rgangan, balki uni keng ommaga yetkazishda ham katta rol o'ynaganlar. Ushbu maqolada mifologiyani o'rgangan mashhur ingliz olimlari va ularning tadqiqotlari haqida so'z yuritamiz.

ASOSIY QISM

Ingliz olimlari jahon mifologiyasini o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynagan. Ularning tadqiqotlari nafaqat G'arb, balki Sharq mifologiyasini ham qamrab olgan. Bu maqolada eng mashhur ingliz mifologiya tadqiqotchilarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Ser James George Frazer mifologiya sohasidagi eng taniqli ingliz olimlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Uning "Oltin Shox" (The Golden Bough) asari jahon mifologiyasi tadqiqotlarida tub burilish yasadi. Bu asar 12 jilddan iborat bo'lib, unda turli xalqlarning afsonalari, urf-odatlari va diniy marosimlari tahlil qilingan. Frazer o'z tadqiqotlarida qadimgi odamlarning magik tafakkuri va diniy tasavvurlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ochib berdi. U birinchilardan bo'lib mifologiyani antropologik nuqtai nazardan o'rgandi.

Edward Burnett Tylor zamonaviy antropologiyaning asoschileridan biri sifatida tanilgan. Uning "Ibtidoiy madaniyat" (Primitive Culture) asari mifologiya va din o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tushunishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tylor "animizm" tushunchasini fanga kiritdi va ibtidoiy jamiyatlardagi diniy tasavvurlarning rivojlanishini tadqiq etdi. U din va mifologiyani asta-sekin rivojlanadigan bosqichli

tizim sifatida ko'rgan. Uning nazariyasiga ko'ra, mifologiya ilk e'tiqodlarning qoldig'i bo'lib, u asta-sekin murakkab dinlarga aylangan.

Robert Graves yunon va kelt mifologiyasini chuqur o'rgangan olim sifatida mashhur. Uning "Yunon miflari" (The Greek Myths) kitobi bu sohadagi eng muhim manbalardan biri hisoblanadi. Graves miflarni tarixiy va psixologik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qildi. Graves miflarni shunchaki fantastik hikoyalar emas, balki qadimgi jamiyatlarning falsafasi, diniy e'tiqodi va siyosiy tuzilishining aks etishi deb tushuntirgan. Uning uslubi XX asr mifologiyasini tadqiq etishda katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Andrew Lang folklor va mifologiya sohasida keng qamrovli tadqiqotlar olib borgan. U "rang-barang ertaklar to'plami" (Coloured Fairy Books) seriyasini nashr etib, turli xalqlarning og'zaki ijodini ingliz tiliga tarjima qildi. Lang miflarning kelib chiqishi haqidagi nazariyani rivojlantirdi. U miflarni insonlarning irratsional his-tuyg'ulari, qo'rquvlari va umidlariga asoslangan holda tushuntirgan. Leng mifologiyaning rivojlanishini evolyutsion bosqichlar orqali tushuntiradi va uni insonlarning psixologik rivojlanishining ajralmas qismi deb hisoblaydi.

Maksvell Myuller fikricha, mifologiya qadimgi insonlarning tabiat hodisalarini tasvirlash uchun ishlatgan ramziy ifodalari va metaforalardan kelib chiqqan. Masalan, miflar quyosh, oy, yomg'ir kabi hodisalarni shaxsiylashtirib, xudolarga aylantirgan. Myuller buni "kasallangan til" deb atagan, ya'ni tildagi metaforalar vaqt o'tishi bilan noto'g'ri tushunilib, mifologik hikoyalar shakliga kirgan.

Hozirgi kunda ham ko'plab ingliz olimlari mifologiya sohasida tadqiqotlar olib bormoqdalar. Ular zamonaviy texnologiyalar va yangi metodologik yondashuvlardan foydalangan holda qadimgi miflarni o'rganishda davom etmoqdalar.

XULOSA

Ingliz olimlari mifologiya fanini rivojlantirishda beqiyos hissa qo'shganlar. Ularning tadqiqotlari orqali insoniyatning mifologik tushunchalari, qadimiy e'tiqodlar va marosimlar haqida ko'plab ma'lumotlar kashf qilingan. Bu olimlarning asarlari nafaqat ilmiy doiralarda, balki keng omma orasida ham o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmay kelmoqda. Mifologiyani o'rganish orqali insoniyatning madaniy va ruhiy merosi haqida yanada chuqurroq tushunchaga ega bo'lishimiz mumkin.

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TIBBIYOT TALABALARI UCHUN PSIXOLINGVISTIK YONDASHUV ASOSIDA NUTQ MADANIYATINI O'RGATISH

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda tibbiyot talabalari uchun psixolingvistik yondashuv asosida nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy tibbiy ta'lim jarayonida kasbiy muloqotning samaradorligini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda shifokor va bemor o'rtasidagi lingvistik hamkorlik, nutqiy kompetensiyalar va psixolingvistik omillar tahlil qilinadi. Olingan natijalar nutq madaniyatini o'rgatishda samarali metodlar ishlab chiqish va tibbiyot talabalari uchun muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berishga asos bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: psixolingvistika, nutq madaniyati, tibbiy muloqot, lingvistik kompetensiya, bemor-shifokor munosabatlari, tibbiyot talabalari.

KIRISH: Tibbiyot sohasida samarali muloqot bemorlar bilan to'g'ri aloqa o'rnatish va tibbiy xizmat sifatini oshirish uchun muhim hisoblanadi. Shifokorlarning nutq madaniyati nafaqat bemorning ishonchini qozonishda, balki tibbiy xatolarni kamaytirishda ham katta rol o'ynaydi. Psixolingvistika shifokorlarning nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish uchun samarali vosita bo'lib, u lingvistik va psixologik omillarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu maqola tibbiyot talabalari uchun psixolingvistik yondashuv asosida nutq madaniyatini shakllantirish metodlarini ko'rib chiqadi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI: Tibbiy lingvistika va psixolingvistika bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shifokorlarning kasbiy nutqi va kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish zaruriyatini ta'kidlaydi. Chomsky (1965) nutq kompetensiyasi va ijro kompetensiyasini farqlab, shifokorlarning lingvistik bilimlarini amaliy qo'llay olish ko'nikmalariga urg'u bergan. Vygotsky (1978) esa muloqot jarayonida ijtimoiy omillarning ahamiyatini ko'rsatib, bemor bilan shifokor o'rtasidagi dialogda kontekstning muhimligini ta'kidlagan. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlarda esa (Johnson & Brown, 2020) tibbiy ta'limda interfaol yondashuv va texnologiyalar orqali nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish metodlari o'rganilgan.

O'zbek olimlarining tadqiqotlari ham ushbu yo'nalishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Karimov (2018) tibbiyot talabalari uchun psixolingvistik tamoyillarni tibbiy ta'limga integratsiyalash orqali samarali kasbiy muloqotni shakllantirish mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Saidova (2021) esa tibbiy muassasalarda shifokorlarning

nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish uchun rolli o'yinlar va real hayotiy holatlar asosida treninglar o'tkazish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Yuldashev (2019) tibbiyotda nutqiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda sotsiolingvistik omillarning rolini o'rganib, bemor-shifokor muloqotida lingvistik moslashuvchanlik muhimligini asoslaydi.

Ushbu tadqiqotlar natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, psixolingvistika, tibbiy axloq va kommunikatsiya fanlarini o'zaro bog'liq holda o'rganish shifokorlar uchun samarali muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, tadqiqot natijalari shifokorlar uchun lingvistik moslashuvchanlik va empatiya asosidagi kommunikativ modelni shakllantirish muhimligini ko'rsatmoqda.

TADQIQOT METODI: Tadqiqot davomida tibbiyot talabalari o'rtasida kasbiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini o'rganish uchun kuzatuv, so'rovnoma va eksperimental metodlar qo'llanildi. Shuningdek, lingvistik tahlil va diskurs tahlili usullari yordamida shifokor-bemor muloqoti tahlil qilindi. Tajriba jarayonida nutqiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish uchun psixolingvistik mashqlar va interfaol treninglar tashkil etildi.

ASOSIY MUHOKAMALAR VA NATIJALAR: Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, tibbiyot talabalari o'rtasida nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishda psixolingvistik yondashuv samarali vosita hisoblanadi. Eksperiment ishtirokchilari lingvistik jihatdan aniqroq ifoda qilish, bemor bilan empatik muloqot o'rnatish va so'zlashuv strukturasi bo'yicha yuqori natijalar ko'rsatdi. Shuningdek, tibbiy terminlarni to'g'ri ishlatish va bemorlarning hissiy holatini hisobga olish talabalarning muloqot qobiliyatlarini oshirishga yordam berdi.

XULOSA: Psixolingvistik yondashuv asosida nutq madaniyatini o'rgatish tibbiyot talabalari uchun kasbiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Tadqiqot natijalari nutqiy treninglar, interfaol mashg'ulotlar va tibbiy diskurs tahlili yordamida shifokorlarning muloqot samaradorligini oshirish mumkinligini tasdiqladi. Kelajakda tibbiyot ta'limi tizimida lingvistik va psixolingvistik metodlarni yanada kengroq qo'llash tavsiya etiladi.

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ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA PSIXOLOGIK XAVFSIZLIK KONSEPSIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada raqamli dunyoning zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonidagi muammolar va ularning yechimi sifatida psixologik xavfsizlik konsepsiyasining qoidalari hamda shaxsning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda shaxsiy makon hududlarining ta'siri yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: psixologik xavfsizlik konsepsiyasi, psixologik zo'ravonlik, shaxsiy makon, xavfsizlik tamoyillari.

Annotation: The article highlights the problems in the modern educational process of the digital world and the rules of the concept of psychological security as their solution, as well as the influence of personal space areas in ensuring the safety of the individual.

Keywords: concept of psychological security, psychological violence, personal space, principles of security.

Tez taraqqiy etayotgan raqamli dunyoda inson uchun ta'lim-tarbiya suv va havo kabi eng muhim ehtiyoj hisoblanadi. Chunki insoniyatni hayvonot dunyosidan ajratib turuvchi jihat uning bilimi, xulq-atvori va tarbiyasidir. Bugungi kunda yosh avlodni katta hayotga tayyorlab beruvchi maktablarga berilgan e'tibor har qachongidan yuqori. Prezidentimiz Sh.M.Mirziyoyev ta'kidlaganidek, "Maktab ta'limida poydevorni bugundan mustahkam qo'yishimiz kerak. Chunki biz ko'p vaqt yo'qotganmiz". So'nggi yillarda o'tkazilgan islohotlar natijasida ta'lim muassasalarining moddiy-texnik bazasi yaxshilanmoqda, pedagog xodimlarning ilmiy salohiyati uzviy ravishda oshirilib borilmoqda. Shu o'rinda e'tibor qaratishimiz kerak bo'lgan jihat – maktablarda turli hildagi zo'ravonliklarning uchrab turishidir. Zo'ravonlikning turli ko'rinishi mavjud bo'lib, ular ichida psixologik zo'ravonlik eng ko'p uchraydi. Kattalar va bola o'rtasidagi munosabatlarda zo'ravonlik yuz berishi bolaning huquqlari, erkinliklari va fazilatlarini e'tiborsiz qoldirishga olib keladi, natijada bolalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi aloqalar buziladi. Shuningdek, shaxsiy, aqliy, irodaviy, kommunikativ, xulq-atvor va hissiy rivojlanishda bo'shliqlarni vujudga keladi. Ushbu mezonlardan kamida bittasining mavjudligi insonning butun

rivojlanishiga va faoliyat samaradorligiga ta'sir qiladi. Shunday ekan, maktablar nafaqat bilim maskani, balki bola uchun har tomonlama xavfsiz hudud bo'lishi kerak. Yuqoridagi muammolarning yechimi sifatida psixologik xavfsizlik konsepsiyasi ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, u ta'lim jarayonidagi barcha ishtirokchilarning ruhiy va jismoniy salomatligini ta'minlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Ta'lim jarayonida psixologik xavfsizligi konsepsiyasining asosiy jihatlari quyidagilar:

1. Ta'lim – bu inson “ishlab chiqaradigan” soha. Bu shuni anglatadiki, ta'lim muassasasi murakkab mahsulotni, ya'ni o'zini o'zi amalga oshiradigan shaxsning shaxsiyatini ishlab chiqaradi. Shuning uchun, bu sohada shaxsga zarar yetkazadigan barcha xavflarni bartaraf etish, xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning texnologiya va usullarini yaratish kerak.

2. Psixologik xavfsizlikka bo'ladigan tahdidlar. Ta'lim jarayonidagi asosiy xavf psixikaga shikast yetishi natijada shaxsning shakllanishi va rivojlanishida to'siqlarning paydo bo'lishidir. Bunda asosiy e'tibor to'siqlarni yaratayotgan sabablarga qarshi kurashni qamrab oladi.

3. Ta'lim muhiti - ijtimoiylashuv ehtiyojlarini qondiradigan makon. Ta'lim jarayoni bolaga faqatgina ilm-fanni emas, jamiyatning qonun-qoidalarini, ijtimoiylashuv va jamiyatda o'z o'rnini topish yo'llarini ham o'rgatishi lozim.

Ta'limda xavfsizlik muammolari mavzusida ilmiy izlanishlar olib borgan psixolog I.A.Bayeva ta'lim jarayonining psixologik xavfsizligi ko'rsatkichlarini quyidagicha ta'riflab o'tgan:

1. Ta'lim jarayoni insonga ijtimoiy normalar va qadriyatlarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

2. Ta'lim jarayoni odamlar bilan muloqot qilish va o'zaro munosabatlarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni qondiradi.

3. Ta'lim jarayonida psixologik zo'ravonlikdan himoyalanganlik darajasi shaxsning o'z manfaatlarini himoya qilishiga zamin yaratadi.

Psixologik xavfsizlikni yaratadigan subyektlar oila, maktab, qo'shimcha ta'lim markazlari o'qituvchilari bo'lishi mumkin. Bola o'z qadriyatlarini, qarashlarini o'qituvchilar, tengdoshlar va qarindoshlar bilan muloqotda shakllantiradi va o'z munosabatlar tizimini yaratadi. Shunday qilib, ijtimoiylashuv jarayonida boshqalarga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lishga yordam beradigan usullardan foydalanish muhimdir. Psixologik xavfsiz ta'lim muhitini yaratishda quyidagi prinsiplarga tayanish tavsiya etiladi:

A) Oldindan tuzilgan va aniq vazifalar belgilangan rivojlanish rejasiga tayanish prinsipi, uning asosiy maqsadi shaxsni har tomonlama yetuk qilib rivojlantirish, hayot faoliyatining intellektual, ma'naviy, jismoniy va ijtimoiy sohalarga tayyorlashdir.

B) Ta'lim jarayonining har bir ishtirokchisini psixologik himoya qilish prinsipi. Ushbu prinsipning maqsadi o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar uchun psixologik bosim va zo'ravonliklardan holi sharoit yaratishni nazarda tutadi. Bunda o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini inobatga olish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

C) Psixologik va ijtimoiy mahoratni rivojlantirish prinsipi. Prinsipning mohiyati o'quvchilarda olingan nazariy bilimlarni amaliyotga tadbiq qilishga yo'naltirishdan iborat. Jumladan, ijtimoiylashuv jarayonida xavfsiz munosabatlarni o'rgatadigan trening va dasturlarni o'tkazish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Ta'lim jarayonida psixologik xavfsizlik hissini yaratish insonning fazoviy-makon munosabatlari bilan bog'liq hisoblanadi. Inson o'zini xavfsiz va himoyalangan his qilishi uchun shaxsiy makoniga ega bo'lishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi va bu uning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshiradi. Psixologiya fanida shaxsiy makon to'rtta hududga ajratiladi:

1. Samimiy(intim) hudud, uning uzunligi 15-45 sm oralig'ida, ya'ni cho'zilgan qo'ldan kamroq masofada bo'ladi. Ushbu hududga kirishga ota-ona, turmush o'rtoq, farzandlar va yaqin do'stlarga ruxsat beriladi. Agar kimdir ushbu hududga beruxsat kirsam, u holda odam bezovtalanadi va xavotirga tushadi. Natijada, unda himoyalalanishga ehtiyoj vujudga keladi, yoki, aksincha, teskari reaksiya bildirib, agressiv harakat qilishi mumkin.

2. Shaxsiy hudud, uning uzunligi o'rtacha 50 sm dan 1,5 mertgacha bo'ladi va u do'stlar, sinfdoshlar, hamkasblar, qo'shnilar bilan aloqa qilish uchun mo'ljallangan. Ushbu hududda ish, karera va shaxsiy hayot mavzularida muloqot qilish maqsadga muvofiq.

3. 1,5 metrdan 4 metrgacha masofa ijtimoiy hudud deb ataladi. Bu hududda begona odamlar bilan muloqot qilish qulay, chunki ijtimoiy zonada odam o'zini psixologik va axloqiy jihatdan xavfsizlik his qiladi. Ushbu hududni buzish butunlay boshqacha reaksiya keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

4. Ommaviy hudud 4 metr masofadan boshlanadi va u odamlar auditoriyasi bilan muloqot qilish uchun zarur. Misol uchun yig'ilishlar, ma'ruzalar, treninglar va seminarlar o'tkazish ushbu hududda amalga oshiriladi.

Shaxsiy makon nazariyasi 1963-yil Edvard Xoll tomonidan "Proksemika" atamasi bilan ishlab chiqilgan. Nazariyada keltirilgan raqamlar har bir inson uchun

alohida ahamiyatga ega, shuning uchun u o'zgarishi mumkin. Har kim o'z makonining chegaralarini o'ziga xos tarzda, kimdir psixologik, kimdir jismoniy yo'llar bilan belgilaydi hamda himoya qiladi. Ushbu chegaralarni buzish turli xil stresslarga, ba'zan, jismoniy reaksiyalarga olib keladi. Ta'lim muassasasida o'quvchilarda psixologik muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin bo'lgan omillar to'g'risida pedagogika fanlari doktori A.A.Ostapenko xulosalarini quyidagicha asoslaydi:

1. Auditoriyada o'qitish tizimining tartibga solinmaganligi sababli o'quvchi kerakli xonani izlash uchun ko'p vaqt sarf qilsa, u o'zini begonadek his qiladi. Auditoriya va xonalarning nomi, raqamlari aniq ko'rsatilgan bo'lsa, o'quvchilar ushbu joyga ishonishlari ancha osonlashadi.

2. Ta'lim muassasida joylashgan kiyim almashtirish xonasi, yuvinish xonasi, hojatxonalarda tozalik va gigiyena qoidalariga amal qilinmasligi o'quvchilarning o'zlarini begona va keraksiz his qilishlariga olib keladi.

3. Parallel sinflarni yonma yon joylashtirish raqobatbardoshlikka va sinflar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar darajasining pasayishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Shunday qilib, psixologik xavfsizlik ta'lim jarayonida ishtirok etuvchilarning ruhiy salomatligini saqlash va rivojlantirishda muhim jihati hisoblanadi. Psixologik xavfsizlik deb, o'zaro munosabatlarda psixologik zo'ravonlikdan xoli bo'lgan, ishonchli va xavfsiz muloqotga hissa qo'shadigan, atrof-muhitning salbiy ta'siridan ximoyalangan, jarayonda ishtirok etuvchilarning ruhiy salomatligini ta'minlaydigan ta'lim muhitining holatiga aytiladi. Shuningdek, shaxsning psixologik xavfsizligi tashqi muhit bilan birgalikdagina rivojlanishning barqaror modelini tashkil qiladi. Ta'lim muassasalari esa jamiyatning ijtimoiy instituti sifatida xavfsizlik subyekti hisoblanadi. Ta'lim muhitida shaxsning psixologik xavfsizligini o'rganishning ahamiyati shundan iboratki, ta'lim muassasasi nafaqat ta'lim va tarbiya orqali, balki rivojlanish muammolarini hal qilish orqali ham o'zining xususiy xavfsizlik tizimini kuchaytirib boradi.

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O'QUVCHILAR VA TALABALAR UCHUN RAQAMLI SAVODXONLIK: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu ishda o'quvchilar va talabalar uchun raqamli savodxonlikning ahamiyati, asosiy muammolari va ularni hal etish yo'llari tahlil qilingan. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonida muhim o'rin tutib, ularning to'g'ri qo'llanilishi ta'lim sifati va kasbiy rivojlanishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotda internet xavfsizligi, axborot madaniyati va raqamli ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish muammolari ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, raqamli savodxonlikni oshirish uchun ta'lim tizimiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish va pedagoglar malakasini oshirish bo'yicha takliflar berilgan. Ish natijalari raqamli savodxonlikning ta'lim va mehnat bozoridagi o'rni muhimligini ko'rsatib, uning rivojlanishi jamiyatning axborot texnologiyalariga moslashishiga xizmat qilishini tasdiqlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli savodxonlik, zamonaviy ta'lim, internet xavfsizligi, axborot madaniyati, raqamli texnologiyalar, ta'lim sifati, o'quvchilar, talabalar, pedagoglar malakasi, innovatsion ta'lim.*

Raqamli savodxonlik zamonaviy jamiyatda muhim tushunchalardan biri bo'lib, texnologiyalar bilan samarali ishlash, axborotni tahlil qilish va raqamli muhitda xavfsiz harakat qilish ko'nikmalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bugungi kunda o'quvchilar va talabalar turli texnologik vositalar – kompyuterlar, smartfonlar, internet platformalari va sun'iy intellekt tizimlari bilan muntazam muloqotda bo'lishadi. Shu sababli, ularning raqamli savodxonligi nafaqat ta'lim jarayoni, balki kundalik hayot uchun ham zaruriy omil hisoblanadi.

Raqamli savodxonlikning ahamiyati shundaki, u o'quvchilarga va talabalariga mustaqil o'rganish, axborotni tez va samarali topish hamda undan to'g'ri foydalanish imkonini beradi. An'anaviy ta'lim jarayonlaridan farqli o'laroq, zamonaviy ta'lim platformalari o'quvchilarga interaktiv o'quv materiallarini o'zlashtirish, ilmiy izlanish olib borish va raqamli resurslar yordamida mustaqil ta'lim olish imkoniyatini taqdim etadi. Bu esa ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali va innovatsion qilishga xizmat qiladi.

Shuningdek, raqamli savodxonlik kiberxavfsizlik qoidalarini tushunish va ularga rioya qilishda ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. O'quvchilar va talabalar internetdan foydalanish davomida shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish, soxta ma'lumotlarni

ajratish va zararli dasturlardan ehtiyot bo'lish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishlari lozim. Raqamli tafakkurni rivojlantirish orqali ularning tahliliy fikrlash qobiliyatlari ortadi, bu esa ularga turli axborot oqimlari ichidan eng ishonchlisini tanlashda yordam beradi.

Bugungi globallashuv sharoitida raqamli savodxonlik zamonaviy ta'limning ajralmas qismiga aylanmoqda. Uni rivojlantirish nafaqat o'quvchilar va talabalar, balki pedagoglar, ota-onalar va ta'lim muassasalari uchun ham muhim vazifa hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, ta'lim tizimida raqamli kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilishi zarur. Bu nafaqat ta'lim sifatini oshirish, balki kelajak avlodning texnologik taraqqiyotga moslashuvchanligini ta'minlash uchun ham muhimdir.

Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonida keng qo'llanilishiga qaramay, o'quvchilar va talabalar uchun bir qator muammolarni ham keltirib chiqaradi. Eng katta muammolardan biri – internet xavfsizligiga yetarlicha e'tibor berilmasligidir. O'quvchilar va talabalar shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish bo'yicha yetarli bilimga ega bo'lmagani sababli, kiberhujumlar va zararli dasturlarning qurboniga aylanish ehtimoli yuqori bo'lib qolmoqda. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda yolg'on axborot va soxta yangiliklarning ko'payishi yoshlarning ishonchli manbalarni tanlashda qiynalishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Boshqa muhim muammo – axborotni to'g'ri saralash va ishonchli manbalar bilan ishlash ko'nikmalarining yetishmovchiligidir. Internetda mavjud bo'lgan ma'lumotlarning ko'pligi ularni saralash va tahlil qilish zaruratini keltirib chiqaradi. Ko'pchilik o'quvchilar va talabalar esa birinchi duch kelgan ma'lumotdan foydalanadi, uni tekshirib ko'rmaydi. Bu esa noto'g'ri axborotni tarqatish yoki ilmiy izlanishlar olib borishda noaniqliklarga sabab bo'lishi mumkin.

Raqamli texnologiyalarning haddan tashqari ko'p ishlatilishi ham o'quv jarayoniga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ko'pchilik o'quvchilar va talabalar darslar davomida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga berilib ketishi, vaqtni samarasiz sarflashi yoki o'yinlarga mukkasidan ketishi natijasida o'qishga e'tiborini yo'qotishi mumkin. Shuningdek, uzoq vaqt ekranga tikilish ko'z salomatligiga zarar yetkazadi va jismoniy faollikning kamayishiga olib keladi. Bu esa sog'liq bilan bog'liq muammolarni yuzaga keltiradi.

Yana bir muammo – raqamli tafakkurning sustligi va amaliy ko'nikmalarning yetishmovchiligidir. Aksariyat yoshlar zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalana olsa ham, ularni to'g'ri ishlatish, dasturlash yoki ma'lumotlarni chuqur tahlil qilish

bo'yicha yetarli bilimga ega emas. Bu esa kelajakda raqamli muhitda muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun to'siq bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli, ta'lim jarayonida faqat texnologiyalardan foydalanish emas, balki ularni samarali boshqarish ko'nikmalarini ham rivojlantirish muhimdir.

O'quvchilar va talabalar duch kelayotgan muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun ta'lim tizimida raqamli savodxonlikni oshirishga qaratilgan maxsus kurslar va treninglar o'tkazish zarur. Bu orqali yoshlar axborotdan to'g'ri foydalanish, raqamli muhitda xavfsiz ishlash va zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda samarali ta'lim olish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishlari mumkin.

Raqamli savodxonlikni rivojlantirish uchun, avvalo, ta'lim tizimiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish zarur. Maktab va universitetlarda raqamli texnologiyalar bilan ishlash bo'yicha maxsus kurslar tashkil etish, o'quvchilar va talabalarni internetdan to'g'ri foydalanishga o'rgatish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu kurslar nafaqat kompyuter va internetdan foydalanish asoslarini, balki ishonchli axborot manbalarini tanlash, kiberxavfsizlik qoidalariga rioya qilish va raqamli etikani tushunishni ham qamrab olishi kerak.

Bundan tashqari, o'quvchilarning amaliy ko'nikmalarini oshirish maqsadida interaktiv ta'lim usullaridan foydalanish lozim. Virtual laboratoriyalar, onlayn simulyatorlar va raqamli ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanish orqali talabalar nazariy bilimlarini real hayotda qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Masalan, dasturlash asoslari, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va sun'iy intellekt bilan ishlash kabi fanlarni o'rgatish kelajakda ularning raqamli ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

Raqamli savodxonlikni rivojlantirishda ota-onalar va o'qituvchilarning roli ham juda muhimdir. Ular bolalarga raqamli dunyoda xavfsiz harakat qilishni o'rgatishlari, ularning internetdagi faolligini nazorat qilishlari va ularni foydali onlayn resurslarga yo'naltirishlari kerak. Shu bilan birga, pedagoglar zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish bo'yicha muntazam malaka oshirib borishlari, innovatsion ta'lim metodlarini o'zlashtirishlari zarur.

Shuningdek, davlat miqyosida raqamli ta'lim dasturlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maktab va oliy o'quv yurtlarida bepul raqamli ta'lim kurslarini joriy etish, zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan jihozlangan sinflarni tashkil qilish va talabalar uchun maxsus onlayn platformalarni yaratish bu borada samarali yechim bo'lishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, davlat organlari va xususiy sektor hamkorligida innovatsion ta'lim loyihalarini rivojlantirish orqali o'quvchilar va talabalar uchun yangi imkoniyatlar yaratish lozim.

Umuman olganda, raqamli savodxonlikni oshirish uchun ta'lim tizimiga kompleks yondashuv talab etiladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish, o'quvchilarga amaliy ko'nikmalar berish, pedagoglarni malakasini oshirish va davlat miqyosida qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali raqamli savodxonlik darajasini oshirish mumkin. Bu esa kelajak avlodning texnologiyalar bilan samarali ishlashiga va raqamli dunyoda muvaffaqiyatli faoliyat yuritishiga imkon yaratadi.

Raqamli savodxonlik nafaqat shaxsiy rivojlanish, balki ta'lim sifati va kasbiy faoliyat uchun ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Zamonaviy dunyoda ko'plab kasblar texnologiyalar bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, raqamli ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lmagan insonlar mehnat bozorida raqobatlasha olmaydi. Shu sababli, ta'lim jarayonida raqamli savodxonlikni rivojlantirish nafaqat nazariy bilimlarni, balki amaliy ko'nikmalarni ham shakllantirishni talab qiladi.

Bugungi kunda aksariyat kasblarda kompyuter texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanish talab etiladi. Muhandislik, tibbiyot, biznes, marketing va hatto san'at sohalarida ham raqamli texnologiyalar keng qo'llaniladi. O'quvchilar va talabalar dasturlash, data tahlili, onlayn platformalar bilan ishlash va avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlardan foydalanish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lsalar, kelajakda yanada muvaffaqiyatli kasbiy faoliyat yuritishlari mumkin. Bu esa mehnat bozorida ularning talabgir mutaxassisga aylanishiga yordam beradi.

Shuningdek, raqamli savodxonlik ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi. Onlayn ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanish, elektron kutubxonalar va masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlari orqali o'quvchilar va talabalar o'z bilimlarini yanada boyitishlari mumkin. Masalan, turli xil kurslar va sertifikat dasturlarida qatnashish orqali yoshlar o'z mutaxassisliklari bo'yicha chuqur bilimlarga ega bo'lishadi. Bundan tashqari, raqamli vositalar orqali ta'lim jarayonini interaktiv va qiziqarli qilish mumkin, bu esa o'quvchilarning darslarga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi.

Raqamli savodxonlik nafaqat an'anaviy ta'lim jarayonida, balki uzluksiz ta'limda ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. Hozirgi kunda mutaxassislar doimiy ravishda o'z bilim va ko'nikmalarini oshirib borishlari kerak. Internet va onlayn ta'lim platformalari orqali yangi texnologiyalar va sohadagi eng so'nggi tendensiyalar haqida bilib olish imkoniyati mavjud. Bu esa mutaxassislarning o'z sohasida doimiy ravishda yetakchi bo'lib qolishlariga yordam beradi.

Umuman olganda, raqamli savodxonlikning ta'lim sifati va kasbiy rivojlanishdagi roli beqiyosdir. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish orqali o'quvchilar va talabalar nafaqat o'z bilim

darajasini oshiradilar, balki kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyatlarida ham muvaffaqiyatga erishadilar. Shu boisdan, raqamli savodxonlikni o'rganish va uni ta'lim tizimiga keng joriy etish bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

Raqamli savodxonlikni oshirish uchun, eng avvalo, ta'lim tizimiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarni chuqur joriy etish lozim. Maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida raqamli ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan maxsus dasturlar ishlab chiqilishi kerak. Bunday dasturlar kompyuter savodxonligi, internet xavfsizligi, sun'iy intellekt asoslari va dasturlashni o'z ichiga olishi maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, o'quv dasturlarining amaliy jihatlariga e'tibor qaratish orqali talabalar nafaqat nazariy bilimga ega bo'lishlari, balki ularni hayotda qo'llashni ham o'rganishlari lozim.

O'qituvchilar va pedagog kadrlarning malakasini oshirish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida pedagoglar faqat an'anaviy usullar bilan cheklanmasliklari, balki interaktiv darslarni tashkil qilish uchun turli raqamli resurslardan foydalanishlari zarur. Shu sababli, o'qituvchilar uchun doimiy ravishda raqamli ta'lim bo'yicha maxsus seminar va treninglar o'tkazilishi kerak. Bu ularning yangi texnologiyalarga tez moslashishiga va o'quvchilarga yanada samarali ta'lim berishiga yordam beradi.

Bundan tashqari, o'quvchilar va talabalar orasida mustaqil o'rganish va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish madaniyatini shakllantirish lozim. Onlayn kurslar, bepul ta'lim platformalari va ilmiy resurslardan foydalangan holda, ular o'z bilimlarini doimiy ravishda oshirib borishlari mumkin. Masalan, Coursera, Udemy, Khan Academy, Codecademy kabi platformalar orqali turli sohalarda bilim olish imkoniyati mavjud. Shuningdek, davlat miqyosida bepul ta'lim dasturlarini tashkil qilish va ularga keng ommani jalb etish ham raqamli savodxonlik darajasining oshishiga katta hissa qo'shadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, raqamli savodxonlikni oshirish uchun keng ko'lamli strategik yondashuv zarur. Ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiya qilish, pedagoglar malakasini oshirish, o'quvchilarni mustaqil o'rganishga rag'batlantirish va davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash kabi choralar kelajakda jamiyatning texnologiyalar bilan samarali ishlashiga va innovatsion rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Shu bois, raqamli savodxonlikni rivojlantirish bugungi kunda eng muhim ustuvor yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM MUHITINI YARATISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etish, o'quvchilarning bilim olishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish va pedagoglarning ish faoliyatini takomillashtirish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, raqamli ta'lim infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish, o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligini oshirish va gibrid ta'lim usullarini joriy etish muhim ekani ta'kidlanadi. Maqolada innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish jarayonidagi asosiy muammolar va ularning yechimlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli ta'lim, innovatsion ta'lim muhiti, texnologik infratuzilma, gibrid ta'lim, raqamli savodxonlik.

Raqamli texnologiyalar zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining ajralmas qismiga aylanib bormoqda. Ular ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali va interaktiv qilishga xizmat qiladi. Innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish uchun axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanish talab etiladi. Ushbu texnologiyalar o'quvchilarga mustaqil bilim olish, kerakli resurslarga tezkor kirish va interaktiv ta'lim usullaridan foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Elektron ta'lim resurslari, masofaviy o'qitish platformalari va virtual laboratoriyalar o'quv jarayonini an'anaviy ta'lim usullari bilan uyg'unlashtirib, uni yanada boyitishga yordam beradi. Masalan, sun'iy intellekt asosida ishlovchi ta'lim tizimlari o'quvchilarning bilim darajasiga mos ravishda materiallarni taqdim etadi va individual yondashuvni ta'minlaydi. Shu sababli, raqamli texnologiyalarni to'g'ri integratsiya qilish ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, interaktiv ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish orqali o'quvchilarning bilim olish jarayoniga qiziqishi ortadi. Vizual va interaktiv materiallar orqali murakkab mavzularni o'zlashtirish osonlashadi. Shu bilan birga, o'qituvchilar ham zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim jarayonini boshqarish va baholash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Bularning barchasi raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishning muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhiti zamonaviy o'quv jarayonining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, u ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'limning har bir bosqichida yangi imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi. Avvalo, bunday muhit o'quvchilarga o'z bilim darajasiga mos tarzda ta'lim olish imkonini beradi. Masalan, onlayn kurslar, interaktiv o'quv materiallari va sun'iy intellekt yordamida shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv rejalarini yaratish orqali har bir o'quvchining ehtiyojlari inobatga olinadi.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhitining eng muhim afzalliklaridan biri – ta'lim jarayonining moslashuvchanligi va qulayligi hisoblanadi. An'anaviy ta'lim shakllaridan farqli o'laroq, raqamli ta'lim platformalari o'quvchilarga istalgan joyda va istalgan vaqtda o'rganish imkonini beradi. Bu ayniqsa masofaviy ta'lim tizimi orqali o'qiyotgan talabalar va o'quvchilar uchun juda muhimdir. Bunday yondashuv nafaqat ta'lim sifatini oshiradi, balki bilim olish jarayonini ham osonlashtiradi.

Bundan tashqari, innovatsion ta'lim muhitida interaktiv texnologiyalar va vizual materiallar keng qo'llaniladi. Virtual laboratoriyalar, simulyatsiyalar va o'yinlashtirilgan o'quv usullari orqali murakkab mavzularni yanada tushunarli qilish mumkin. Masalan, kimyo yoki fizika fanlarida tajribalarni virtual laboratoriyalar orqali bajarish o'quvchilarning amaliy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Shu sababli, raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish bugungi kunda eng muhim vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishda sun'iy intellekt va raqamli texnologiyalar muhim rol o'ynaydi. Sun'iy intellekt asosida ishlovchi ta'lim tizimlari o'quvchilarning bilim darajasini tahlil qilib, ularga individual ta'lim yo'nalishini taklif etadi. Bunday tizimlar o'quvchilarning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlashga yordam beradi hamda ularga mos keladigan o'quv materiallarini tavsiya qiladi. Natijada, har bir o'quvchi o'z ehtiyojlariga mos holda ta'lim olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Bundan tashqari, raqamli ta'lim muhitida virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat texnologiyalari ham keng qo'llanilmoqda. Ushbu texnologiyalar orqali o'quvchilar an'anaviy dars jarayonlaridan farqli ravishda, o'rganayotgan mavzularni amaliy tajribalar orqali o'zlashtirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Masalan, tarix darslarida virtual haqiqat texnologiyalari yordamida tarixiy joylarni sayr qilish yoki biologiya fanida inson tanasining tuzilishini 3D formatda ko'rish o'quvchilarning mavzuni chuqurroq tushunishiga yordam beradi.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhitining yana bir muhim jihati – avtomatlashtirilgan baholash tizimlaridir. An'anaviy baholash tizimlari ko'pincha ko'p vaqt talab qiladi va subyektiv bo'lishi mumkin. Raqamli ta'lim tizimlarida esa sun'iy intellekt yordamida testlar, yozma ishlar va boshqa baholash usullari avtomatik ravishda tahlil qilinadi. Bu esa nafaqat o'qituvchilarning ishini yengillashtiradi, balki baholash jarayonining shaffofligini ta'minlaydi. Shu sababli, innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishda sun'iy intellekt va ilg'or texnologiyalar muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishda o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchilar nafaqat an'anaviy bilim beruvchilar, balki texnologiyalar yordamida ta'limni boshqaruvchi murabbiylar sifatida ham faoliyat yuritishlari kerak. Shuning uchun o'qituvchilarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan ishlashga o'rgatish va ularning raqamli kompetensiyalarini oshirish muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Raqamli ta'lim muhitini samarali tashkil etish uchun o'qituvchilar turli interaktiv platformalar, onlayn ta'lim tizimlari va elektron resurslardan foydalana olishlari lozim. Masalan, zamonaviy LMS (Learning Management System) tizimlari orqali dars materiallarini tayyorlash, o'quvchilar bilan doimiy aloqa o'rnatish va baholash jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Bunday tizimlardan samarali foydalanish o'qituvchilarga o'quv jarayonini individual yondashuv asosida tashkil etishga yordam beradi.

Bundan tashqari, o'qituvchilarning o'z ustida ishlashi va yangi innovatsion texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirishi ta'lim sifati uchun juda muhimdir. Ular doimiy ravishda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'rganishlari va o'quv jarayoniga integratsiya qilishlari lozim. Raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan darslarni tashkil etish o'qituvchilarga o'quvchilar bilan samarali ishlash va ularning ta'limga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish imkonini beradi. Shu sababli, innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirishda o'qituvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyalarini oshirish muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi.

Innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishda muammolar va ularni hal qilish yo'llari alohida e'tibor talab qiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning keng joriy etilishi bilan bog'liq eng katta muammolardan biri – texnik infratuzilmaning yetarlicha rivojlanmagani hisoblanadi. Aksariyat ta'lim muassasalarida yuqori tezlikdagi internet, zamonaviy kompyuterlar va boshqa raqamli qurilmalar yetishmaydi. Bu esa raqamli ta'lim jarayonining to'liq samarali ishlashiga to'sqinlik qiladi. Mazkur

muammoni hal qilish uchun ta'lim muassasalarini zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan ta'minlash va internet infratuzilmasini kengaytirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Bundan tashqari, raqamli ta'limga o'tish jarayonida o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligini oshirish zarur. Ko'pgina o'quvchilar raqamli resurslardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha yetarli ko'nikmaga ega emaslar. Shu bois, ularning texnologiyalar bilan ishlash bo'yicha bilim va malakalarini oshirish uchun maxsus treninglar va kurslar tashkil etilishi kerak. Xuddi shunday, o'qituvchilarning ham innovatsion texnologiyalarni to'g'ri qo'llay olishlari ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Yana bir muammo – raqamli ta'limning inson omilidan uzoqlashib borishi va o'quvchilarning real ijtimoiy muloqotdan chetlanishidir. Ko'pchilik onlayn ta'lim jarayonida jonli muloqot va o'qituvchi-mentor ko'magining yetishmovchiligidan shikoyat qiladi. Buni hal qilish uchun raqamli ta'limning an'anaviy dars shakllari bilan uyg'unlashgan gibrid tizimini joriy etish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bu yondashuv orqali o'quvchilar ham raqamli resurslardan foydalana oladilar, ham o'qituvchilar bilan bevosita muloqot qilish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Shuningdek, raqamli ta'lim muhitida axborot xavfsizligi va shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish masalalari ham muhim o'rin tutadi. Ko'pgina onlayn platformalar o'quvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini to'plash va saqlash bilan bog'liq xavflarni o'z ichiga oladi. Shu sababli, ta'lim muassasalari maxfiylik siyosatini kuchaytirishi, xavfsiz platformalardan foydalanishi va o'quvchilarni kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha xabardor qilishi lozim.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish jarayonida bir qator muammolar mavjud bo'lsa-da, ularni tizimli va rejalashtirilgan holda hal qilish orqali samarali ta'lim tizimini yaratish mumkin. Raqamli infratuzilmani rivojlantirish, pedagog va o'quvchilarni raqamli savodxonlik bo'yicha o'qitish hamda xavfsiz va interaktiv ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish bu boradagi asosiy yechimlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish bugungi kunda ta'lim sohasining eng dolzarb masalalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirish, o'quvchilarning bilim olishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish va pedagoglarning ish samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Raqamli ta'lim platformalari, sun'iy intellekt, interaktiv darsliklar va virtual laboratoriyalar kabi vositalardan foydalanish o'quv jarayonini yanada samarali qilishga yordam beradi.

Shu bilan birga, innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratishda bir qator muammolar ham mavjud. Ta'lim muassasalarida texnologik infratuzilmaning yetarli emasligi, o'qituvchilarning raqamli savodxonligi pastligi va o'quvchilarning texnologiyalardan to'g'ri foydalana olmasligi bu jarayonga to'sqinlik qilmoqda. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun davlat miqyosida texnologik modernizatsiya ishlarini olib borish, pedagoglarni maxsus treninglar orqali tayyorlash va o'quvchilarga raqamli savodxonlik bo'yicha qo'shimcha ta'lim berish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Shuningdek, raqamli ta'lim muhitida inson omili va jonli muloqotni saqlab qolish muhim. Gibrid ta'lim tizimidan foydalanish, ya'ni an'anaviy va raqamli ta'lim usullarini uyg'unlashtirish, ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Buning natijasida o'quvchilar texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish bilan birga, real muloqot qilish va jamoaviy ishlash ko'nikmalarini ham shakllantirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish kelajak ta'lim tizimining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalardan to'g'ri va samarali foydalanish orqali ta'lim jarayonini yanada takomillashtirish, o'quvchilarni kelajakka tayyorlash va ta'lim sifatini oshirish mumkin. Bu esa jamiyatning intellektual va ilmiy salohiyatini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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TA'LIMDA SIMVOLIZMNI O'QITISH ORQALI O'QUVCHILARDA ADABIYOTGA MUHABBAT UYG'OTISH.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola maktablarda simvollarni o'rgatishning ahamiyatini, bu orqali o'quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash va adabiy tahlil ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish usullarini tadqiq etadi. Simvol – muhim badiiy vosita bo'lib, o'quvchilarga matnlardagi chuqur ma'nolarni tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Bu usul g'oyalar, madaniy kontekstlar va insoniy his tuyg'u va tajribalarni to'liqroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Maqolada ramzlarni o'quvchilarga yaqin misollar orqali tanishtirish, mos matnlarni tanlash va ijodiy mashg'ulotlar orqali jalb qilish usullari keltirilgan. Shuningdek, ramziy ma'noni hayotiy kontekstlarga bog'lash, tanqidiy va tahliliy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish va o'quvchilarni baholash orqali bilimlarini tekshirish usullari haqida so'z yuritiladi. Muammo va qiyinchiliklarni hal qilish bo'yicha amaliy yechimlarni taklif etiladi. Ta'limda simvolizmni o'rni haqida ilmiy ish olib brogan oz'bek va ingliz olimlari keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ramz, simvol, adabiy tahlil, tanqidiy fikrlash, o'qitish mashg'ulotlari, ta'lim, adabiyot, o'quvchilarni jalb qilish, ijodiy mashg'ulotlar, madaniy asar.

Ingliz adabiyotda simvolizm atamasi o'quvchilarda badiiy matnni tahlil qilishga, murakkab yashirin ma'noni tushunishga va adabiy bilimlarini kengaytirishga asos bo'luvchi kuchli vositadir. O'quvchilarga ramz va simvollarni o'qitish orqali ularning mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish mumkin. Bundan tashqari ularni jamoa bo'lib ishlash va amaliyotda birgalikda izlanish kabi muvaffaqiyatli natijalarga erishish mumkin. Simvolizm ta'lim jarayonida nafaqat adabiyot, san'at fanlari, balki boshqa tarix, falsafa, biologiya kabi fanlarni o'qitilishda ham asos hisoblanadi. Ta'lim sohasida simvolizmning afzalliklari ko'p. Masalan, simvolizm hissiyot va intuitiv ma'nolarni tushunishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bu esa o'quvchilarni nafaqat intellektual, balki emotsional jihatdan ham rivojlantiradi. Ba'zi mavzularni tushuntirishda ramzlardan foydalanish mavzuni osonroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Masalan, kimyo darslarida atom yoki molekula strukturasi ramzlar orqali tushuntiriladi. Simvolizm orqali o'quvchilarni real hayotdagi abstrakt tushunchalarni anglashga tayyorlash mumkin. Masalan, matematika yoki fizika darslarida abstrakt tushunchalarni tasvirlash uchun ramzlardan foydalanish.

Ramz va timsollarni tushungan o'quvchi matnni shunchaki o'qish bilan cheklanib qolmaydi balki undagi murakkab ma'no, hissiyot va fikrlarni o'z tilida tarjima va tahlil qiladi. Demak o'quvchi simvol orqali yashirin ma'noni topishi,

voqea rivojini avvaldan tahmin qilishi va mavhum ma'nalarni tahlil qilishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari adabiyot va badiiy asarni o'qish orqali o'quvchilar tarixiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy – siyosiy vaziyatlarni qiyoslab o'rganadi. (Eagleton, T. 1996).

Demak simvolizmni o'quvchilarga o'rgatishda biz asosan ularning yoshi va qiziqishiga mos asarni tanlay olishimiz kerak. Tanlangan asar ularning mantiqiy va tahliliy fikrlashiga yordam beradigan, yorqin misollarga boy bo'lishi kerak. Masalan ingliz adabiyotining mashxur asarlaridan, “Buyuk Getsbi” (“The Great Gatsby” by F. Scott Fitzgerald) asarida *yashil nur, doctor Eklburgning ko'zi*, “To Kill a Mockingbird” by Harper Lee (Mayna qushining o'ldirilishi”) asarida *yovvayi qush*, “The Scarlet Letter” by Nathaniel Hawthorne (Alvon harflar) asarida *qizil A harfi*, Robert Frostning qisqa hikoya va she'rlar to'plami "The Road Not Taken" (Tanlanmagan yo'l) asarida *bo'lingan yo'l* kabi o'ziga xos ma'no beruvchi simvollar berilgan. Shuni ham yodda tutish kerakki, asar tanlashda o'quvchining milliy qadryatlari, mahalliy adabiyotdagi qaysi mavzularga bilan tanishib chiqqanligiga ham e'tibor berish kerak. Chunki o'quvchi ramzlarni o'zining bilim va dunyoqarashi bilan tahlil qiladi.

Demak simvolizmni talabalarga o'qitmoqchi ekanmiz, birinchi navbatda dars jarayonida simvol nima ekanligini tushuntirish lozim. Simvol (ramz, timsol) bu ko'pincha mavhum, abstrakt narsalarni yoki tushunchani ifodalovchi atama. Va bunga oddiy hayotimizdan misollar keltiramiz, masalan, *yurak* shaklidagi belgi har doim sevgi va mehrni ifodalaydi, yoki *kabutar* tinchlik ramzi hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari o'quvchilar uchun tanish bo'lgan multfilm va kinolardan ham foydalanish mumkin. Masalan “Qirol sher” multfilmidagi *quyosh nuri tushgan hududlar* normal hayotni va aksincha Skar egalik qilgan *qo'rqinchli hudud* esa buzg'unchilik va o'limni ramzi sifatida keltirilgan. Ushbu misollar simvol haqida tushunchaga ega bo'lish uchun qulay va ularning turli kontekstlardagi rolini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Keyingi navbat o'quvchilarda tahlil qilish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishga. Buning uchun dars jarayonida o'qish uchun qisqa hikoya yoki she'r beriladi va quyidagi kabi savollar beriladi:

Berilgan asarda qanday ramz yoki simvollar berilgan?

What is the symbol in this story?

Ushbu simvollar nimani anglatadi?

What does it represent?

Berilgan simvollarning asar g'oyasi bilan qanday bog'liqligi bor?

How does this symbol relate to the themes of the text?

Asar muallifi ushbu simvolni qanday o'rinlarda qo'llagan?

How does the author develop the symbol throughout the narrative?

O'quvchilarni ushbu savollarga javoblarini e'tiborga olish va simvollarni ma'nosini yechishda mantiqiy va tahliliy fikrlashlariga yordam berish zarur.

Simvollarning turli talqinlari bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa o'quvchilarga har xil fikrlarni qabul qilish va ularga tanqidiy yondashish imkonini beradi. Masalan, biologiya darsida evolyutsiya jarayonini tasvirlaydigan diagrammalarni ramziy tahlil qilish orqali o'quvchilar mavzuni chuqurroq tushunadi. Ayrim vaziyatlarda simvolizm o'quvchilarga ko'rinadigan narsalarning ortida yashiringan chuqur ma'nolarni tushunishga yordam beradi. (Lye, J. 1996).

O'quvchi va talabalarni simvolizm va ramzlarni tahlil qilishlarida ijodiy fikrlashga ham yo'naltirish zarur. Buning uchun quyidagi mashg'ulotlardan foydalanish mumkin:

Simvollarni tezkorlik bilan topish mashqi. Bunda o'quvchilarga turli xil janrdagi qisqa hikoyalar, she'rlar va media materiallaridan foydalanib simvollarni kim tez va aniq topish topshirig'i beriladi. Va o'quvchilar sinchkovlik bilan turli xil simvollarni topishadi.

O'zingiz simvol yarating mashqi: demak mashq nomidan ma'lumki talabalar o'zlari qandaydur simvol yaratadilar, masalan, do'stlikni, mardlikni, tinchlikni yoki muhim bir g'oyani ifodalovchi bo'lishi mumkin. O'quvchilar o'zlari tayyorlagan ramzlarini auditoriyada namoyish qiladilar va uning asl mohiyatini tushuntiradilar.

Simvollar daftarini tutish: bunda o'quvchilar biror daftar tutadilar va unga hayotida, o'qigan asarlarida yoki ko'rgan filmlarida uchratgan simvollarni yozib boradilar. Vaqti-vaqti bilan bir-birining qaydlarini o'qib o'zaro fikr almashib boradilar.

Ushbu mashg'ulotlar orqali o'quvchilar simvol va ramzlar faqat adabiyotda emas balki hayotning boshqa jabhalarida ya'ni musiqa, san'at, kino-filmlar, gerb va bayroqlarda ham bo'lishi mumkinligini o'rganadilar. Simvollarni turli o'rinlarda turli ma'nolarni berishini tushunadilar. Mashg'ulotlar orqali o'quvchilarda simvollar haqida ko'nikma hosil bo'lganidan so'ng, ularning bilimlarini joriy va yakuniy nazorat savollari bilan baholash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bunda ularga turli xil savollar, testlar, asarlardan parchalar, tanqidiy va tahliliy insho yozishlari uchun savollar berish mumkin va bu orqali ularning mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashlarini baholanadi.

Lekin bugungi kunda simvolizmni o'qitishda qiyinchiliklar ham bor. Ba'zi o'quvchilar matndan ramz va simvollarni ajrata olmasligi, ularning yashirin ma'nosini aniqlay olmasligi mumkin. Simvollar mavhum va noaniq bo'lishi, har bir ramzning turli talqini bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa o'quvchilarni chalkashtirib qo'yishi mumkin. Simvolizmning ko'p darajali hususiyatlari ba'zan murakkab bo'lib, uni tushunish uchun o'quvchilardan chuqur bilim talab qilinadi. Bunda ularga mavhum tushunchalarni aniqlashda sodda misollar berish, matnga asoslangan savollar bilan ularda mantiqiy fikrlash ko'nikmasini oshirishga yordam berish kerak. Shuni unutmaslik kerakki, o'quvchilar erkin fikrlashida ularning bergan javoblarini eshitish, qo'llab quvvatlash va sabr bilan kamchiliklar ustida ishlash zarur.

Simvolizmning boshqa fanlar bilan ham uzviy bog'liqdir. Masalan *adabiyot* darslarida simvolizm she'riy asarlar va romanlarni tahlil qilishda asosiy o'rinni egallaydi. *Tarix* darslarida madaniy yodgorliklar va san'at asarlaridagi ramzlar orqali o'quvchilarga o'tmishdagi jamiyatlar haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Misol uchun Misr mumtoz san'atidagi quyosh va xudolarni ifodalovchi ramzlarni olishimiz mumkin. *San'at* darslarida ham tasviriy san'at asarlarining tahlilida simvolizm muhim rol o'ynaydi. *Biologiya* darslarida ramzlardan foydalanish murakkab tushunchalarni soddalashtirishda yordam beradi. Misol uchun DNKning ikki zanjirli spiral shakli ramz sifatida biologik axborot saqlashni ifodalaydi. *Diniy ramzlarni* tushuntirish orqali o'quvchilarni madaniy va ma'naviy qadriyatlar bilan tanishtirish mumkin. Masalan Islom madaniyatida oy va yulduz ramzining o'ziga xos ma'nosi bor.

O'zbek adabiyotida simvolizm va uning ta'limdagi o'rni borasida bir qancha tadqiqotlar olib borilgan. Masalan, **Aziza Qayumova** o'zbek mumtoz adabiyotida ramzlar va ularning tarbiyaviy jihatlari bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borgan. Navoiyning tasavvufiy she'riyatida ramzlarning ma'naviy va tarbiyaviy o'rnini o'rgangan. O'quvchilarga ramziy obrazlar orqali axloqiy saboqlarni yetkazish usullarini tadqiq qilgan.

Olim Sharafiddinov (tahallusi Ayn) o'zbek adabiyotida obraz va ramzlar nazariyasi bo'yicha bir qancha ishlarni amalga oshirgan. Olim Sharafiddinov Cho'lpon va Qodiriy asarlarida ramzlarning tahlil qilgan. Ramzlarning tarbiyaviy va tanqidiy fikrlashni shakllantirishdagi o'rnini o'rgangan.

Naim Karimov o'zbek jadid adabiyotini o'rganish bo'yicha yetakchi mutaxassis hisoblanadi. Jadidlar ijodida ramzlar va ularning milliy uyg'onish g'oyalarini ifodalashdagi ahamiyatini tadqiq qilgan. Adabiyot orqali madaniy qadriyatlarni tushuntirishda ramzlardan foydalanishni o'rgangan.

Sirojiddin Ahmedov modernizm va simvolizmning o'zbek adabiyotidagi o'rni haqida ilmiy maqolalar muallifi. Ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarga simvolizm orqali mavhum tushunchalarni etkazish usullari haqida izlanishlar olib borgan.

Erkin Vohidov she'riyat va ramzlar nazariyasi bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borgan. Vohidov ramziy obrazlar orqali o'quvchilarga vatanparvarlik, insoniylik va madaniy qadriyatlarni singdirish masalalariga e'tibor qaratgan.

Maqsuda Akbarova (pedagogika va adabiyot metodikasi sohasida mutaxassis) o'rta maktab adabiyot darslarida ramzlarni tushuntirish va ulardan tarbiyaviy vosita sifatida foydalanish bo'yicha ishlar olib borgan. Simvollar orqali o'quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash va adabiy tahlil ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish usullarini o'rgangan.

Ta'limda simvolizm mavzusida jahon miqyosida ham ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilgan. **Susanne Langer** (1895–1985) "Philosophy in a New Key" (1942). Langer o'z asarida simvollarning inson tafakkuri va madaniyatidagi o'rnini tahlil qiladi. U san'at, til va musiqaning ramziy tabiati haqida chuqur mulohazalar yuritib, ta'lim jarayonida ramzlarning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Jerome Bruner (1915–2016) "Acts of Meaning" (1990). Bruner ta'lim va psixologiya sohasida simvollarning ahamiyatini o'rgangan. U insonning bilim olish jarayonida hikoyalar va ramzlarning rolini tahlil qilib, ta'limda simvolizmning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Kieran Egan (1942–2022): "The Educated Mind: How Cognitive Tools Shape Our Understanding" (1997). Egan ta'lim jarayonida ramzlar va hikoyalar orqali bilim berish usullarini o'rganib, ramziy fikrlashning o'quvchilarning tushunish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishdagi rolini tahlil qiladi.

Xulosa qiladigan bo'lsak, simvolizmni o'qitish o'quvchilarda nafaqat adabiyotni sevishni balki, mantiqiy- tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantiradi. Ustozlar turli xil asarlar va qiziqarli mashg'ulotlar orqali simvolizmni ham o'quv rejasining bir qismiga aylantirishlari mumkin. Buning natijasida o'quvchilar adabiy asarlardagi boy ma'noga ega simvollarni sevib o'rganadilar va kitoblarni o'qib o'zgacha fikr va mulohazalar ola boshlaydilar.

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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Current interconnected and globalized world, education must adapt to the demands of multiculturalism to foster inclusive, equitable and high-quality learning environments. Proper and professional education in a multicultural space requires a balanced approach that integrates cultural diversity, global competencies and inclusive pedagogical strategies. This article explores the theoretical and practical dimensions of education in a multicultural setting, focusing on the role of teachers, curriculum design, technological integration, and policies that promote equity and social cohesion. The study also examines challenges such as cultural biases, linguistic barriers and disparities in educational access while proposing solutions to enhance professionalism and inclusivity in modern education.

The rapid expansion of globalization and migration has resulted in an increasingly multicultural educational environment. Schools, universities, and professional training institutions are now home to students from diverse ethnic, linguistic and cultural backgrounds. This shift requires educational systems to adapt to the needs of multicultural learners while maintaining high standards of professionalism and inclusivity. Professional education in a multicultural space must provide students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to thrive in diverse societies. This involves addressing cultural differences, language diversity, and educational equity. The purpose of this article is to explore the theoretical framework, methodologies and best practices that contribute to a successful educational system in a multicultural context.

Multiculturalism in education refers to an approach that acknowledges, values, and integrates diverse cultural perspectives in teaching and learning. According to Banks (2015), multicultural education seeks to promote equal educational opportunities and foster social justice by addressing biases, stereotypes, and systemic barriers in traditional education.

Key principles of multicultural education include:

- Cultural awareness: Recognizing and respecting diverse cultural identities.
- Equity in education: Ensuring equal access to resources, opportunities, and high-quality teaching.

- Inclusion and representation: Incorporating diverse perspectives into the curriculum.
- Critical thinking and global citizenship: Encouraging students to engage with different worldviews and perspectives.

The Role of Professional Education in a Multicultural Space:

Professional education focuses on developing specialized skills and competencies for specific career paths. In a multicultural space, professional education must address:

- Cultural competence: Preparing professionals to work in diverse environments.
- Language proficiency: Enhancing multilingual communication skills.
- Intercultural communication: Teaching students to navigate cultural differences in professional settings.

Educational theorists such as Vygotsky (1978) and Freire (1970) emphasize the importance of cultural and social context in learning, highlighting the need for educational frameworks that reflect the realities of a multicultural society.

Challenges in Multicultural Education:

Despite its benefits, multicultural education faces several challenges that must be addressed for effective implementation. Language diversity presents challenges in communication, comprehension, and assessment. Students from non-native language backgrounds may struggle with academic language proficiency, impacting their learning outcomes. To overcome linguistic barriers, educators must implement bilingual education, translation technologies, and inclusive teaching strategies.

Cultural Bias and Stereotypes:

Implicit biases and stereotypes in educational materials and teaching methods can marginalize students from certain cultural backgrounds. Addressing these biases requires:

- Diversifying curricula to include multiple cultural perspectives.
- Teacher training programs focused on cultural sensitivity and anti-bias education.
- Encouraging intercultural dialogues to promote mutual understanding.

Socioeconomic disparities affect access to quality education in multicultural settings. Factors such as funding gaps, digital divides, and discriminatory practices contribute to educational inequality. Policies promoting equitable resource allocation,

scholarships for disadvantaged groups, and digital inclusion initiatives can help bridge these gaps.

Curriculum Design for Multicultural Education:

An inclusive curriculum should reflect diverse cultures, histories, and perspectives.

Key strategies include:

- Integrating multicultural literature, history, and case studies.
- Teaching critical thinking and media literacy to analyze cultural representations.

- Encouraging project-based learning that incorporates global perspectives.

Teachers play a crucial role in fostering an inclusive learning environment.

Professional development programs should focus on:

- Culturally responsive teaching methodologies.
- Conflict resolution and intercultural communication skills.
- Technology integration for multilingual and diverse classrooms.

Technology and Digital Learning in Multicultural Education:

Technological advancements can enhance multicultural education by providing:

- Online learning platforms that offer multilingual courses.
- AI-based language translation tools to support non-native speakers.
- Virtual exchange programs connecting students from different cultural backgrounds.

Educational institutions must implement policies that promote equity and inclusion, such as:

- Affirmative action programs to support marginalized groups.
- Cultural sensitivity training for educators and administrators.
- Inclusive assessment methods that consider linguistic and cultural differences.

Governments and institutions should:

- Invest in teacher training programs focused on diversity and inclusion.
- Ensure equitable access to digital learning resources.
- Promote cross-cultural understanding through policy frameworks.

Conclusion

Proper and professional education in a multicultural space is essential for fostering inclusive, equitable, and high-quality learning environments. By integrating cultural competence, language support, and inclusive curricula, educators can create meaningful learning experiences that prepare students for global citizenship.

Overcoming challenges such as linguistic barriers, cultural biases, and educational disparities requires collaborative efforts between educators, policymakers, and technological innovators. Future education models should embrace AI-driven personalization, global collaboration, and policy reforms to ensure that multicultural education remains adaptive, effective, and accessible to all. This research emphasizes that proper education in a multicultural space must go beyond basic inclusivity to actively incorporate cultural intelligence, equity-driven policies, and digital innovations.

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TEACHING LISTENING THROUGH COLLABORATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: *The purpose of this scientific study is to investigate a collaborative approach to teaching listening comprehension that is especially designed for students learning English as a foreign language (EFL). It looks at listening comprehension skills, their role in the development of communicative competence, learning difficulties faced by students, and top-down and bottom-up teaching processes suggested by foreign researchers. By observing how students listen in class, it helps university EFL students develop their listening skills and assesses how this approach work.*

Keywords: *listening skill, collaborative approach, EFL students.*

One of the most crucial abilities for learning a new language is listening. Learners almost always use this ability to respond, converse, and even answer the phone. They also use it to listen to English songs, view English movies or music on the radio, and give and receive voice messages in English on social media. These examples demonstrate how important listening is for facilitating interpersonal communication. When students build an English-speaking environment for themselves, it improves not only their listening skills but all of them. As a receptive form of speech activity, listening's primary objective is to receive relevant information. The productive speech activities of speaking and writing usually receive more focus in English classes than hearing, which is a receptive speech activity. However, if we understand the speech perception process of a foreign language and the skills required to understand a particular phrase, we can argue that listening correctly aids in the development of a language in a variety of ways. It requires EFL teachers to understand systematic ways to introduce new subjects and apply these ways to meet instructional objectives.

Therefore, this study was carried out to look into how listening techniques can be used to teach listening to high school EFL students. Particularly, the study explores listening strategies typically deployed by EFL teachers to teach listening skills for university students in EFL classrooms.

In addition to providing conceptual definitions, this review offers scholarly perspectives on listening and the application of listening techniques in the classroom.

Listening assists with lexical and grammatical structure and can be used to master speaking, reading, and writing. Successful foreign language acquisition

requires the ability to listen, and voice speaking should be utilized to further strengthen ear-based speech comprehension[4;57-60].

When attentive listeners engage with any form of spoken communication, various processes operate on multiple levels at the same time to create an understanding of the incoming dialogue. 1. The higher-level processes (top-down) are influenced by the listener's expectations and knowledge regarding the context, the subject matter, the type of text, and the broader world. 2. The lower-level processes (bottom-up) are activated by the sounds, words, and phrases that the listener hears as they work to interpret speech and assign significance.

According to Anderson, the acoustic signal contains limited cues for the meanings it holds; therefore, the listener must rely on their knowledge of the language to identify meaningful sound units, discern syllable boundaries, and recognize words. • In the parsing phase, the listener utilizes the decoded words and phrases to create meaningful units, which are then retained in short-term memory. In the utilization stage, the listener probes long-term memory for concepts that correspond to the new information; comprehension occurs when a connection is established between existing and new information. As language proficiency improves, listeners become more effective and can engage in multiple activities at once. Generally, the top-down approach promotes the use of resources that lead to authentic learning, while the bottom-up approach begins with language materials through an analytical and descriptive method. Skilled educators, equipped with the right professional experience, will blend both methods according to their students' needs. Evaluating the needs and desires of students can occur during the course planning or while executing a lesson (always considering the students' characteristics) and with active involvement from the students. This approach enhances students' autonomy and accountability regarding their own success and participation in the lesson[1].

1. The act of listening comprehension involves three primary schema: linguistic schemata, formal schemata, and content schemata. Linguistic schema pertains to a listener's knowledge of language elements, such as phonemes, vocabulary, phrases, paragraphs, sentence structures, grammar, and cohesive elements, which are essential for understanding the text. The linguistic stage represents the initial phase of the listening process, where the listener concentrates on the meanings of words, phonemes, pronunciations, and syntax.

2. Formal schema pertains to the understanding of organizational types and rhetorical structures within a discourse. It encompasses the awareness of various genres, along with the differing layouts of fables, basic stories, scientific documents, news articles, poetry, and other forms. Formal schemata is characterized as abstract, encoded, internalized, coherent patterns of media-linguistic and textual organization that shape listeners' expectations as they strive to comprehend a meaningful piece of language.

3. Content schema relates to the knowledge specific to the subject matter of the text, including systems of factual information, values, and cultural norms. Language transcends merely combining vocabulary, grammar, and sentence structures; it also serves as a vehicle for conveying diverse levels of culture.

The content schemata aid the understanding of readers as they help in predicting, selecting relevant information, and in the resolving ambiguities of a particular text. "In Schema Theory research, this kind of formal schematic knowledge is often distinguished from what is called content schematic knowledge which is said to be background information on the subject and relevant social cultural information. The failure of a learner to activate an appropriate schema during the course of learning may result in varying degrees of non-comprehension[2]. They also think that, "this failure to activate an appropriate schema may either result from the speaker having provided insufficient clues in the text for the listener to employ a bottom-up processing mechanism to trigger schemata the listener may possess, or the fact that the listener does not possess the appropriate schema which is assumed would be provided by the author and, hence, does not understand the material. In both situations there is a gap between what the speaker expects the listener to be able to do in order to make sense of the text and what the listener is actually capable of doing. The point is that, the appropriate schemata must be and is assumed to be present, and therefore attentions is processes to it when a text is being read."

Construction hypothesis, be that as it may, is the realization of the characteristics of pattern. It implies that a content as it were gives bearings for audience members or perusers as to how they ought to recover or develop meaning from their possess, already obtained information. Pattern hypothesis emphasizes that tuning in isn't a straightforward one-way stream of data to the brain after a sound is listened, but an intelligently prepare of two-way communication amid which the listener's foundation information plays an important role. Audience members don't tune in word for word, but or maybe utilize their foundation information, and different techniques such as

foreseeing and affirming to develop meaning from the text. In other words, tuning in may be a meaning-making handle including an interaction between the audience and the content. According to D.Braun, the approach is theoretically good reasonable positions, assumptions, thoughts, concepts, beliefs about nature of the language learning, used in pedagogical environment in the classroom. From the point of view the scholars, И.А.Колесниковой, О.А.Долгиной, approach to learning is the implementation of the leading, home-nating the idea of learning in practice in the form of a specific strategy and using one or another teaching method[5].

According to researchers, Johnson described it as an educational use of small groups to achieve shared goals and provide the students' working together and support teamwork skills. Cooperative learning approach is a technique that enables the students' learning a subject within a group. In addition, Barth and Demirates point that "it is completing a given task by all the members in the group". According to Baykara, cooperative learning method is one of the teaching methods that have been the subject of numerous researches and have gained importance in Turkey recently[3].

As the cooperative learning method maximizes the motivation of learners in the process of learning, it allows individual talents of the learners to get to the foreground and allows them for self-learning; it facilitates increasing the self-confidence of the learner and developing a positive attitude towards other members of the group. The teacher's role in collaborative learning is to emulate an instructor and facilitator of effective class teaching. In contrast, the role of target groups is to promote autonomous and reflective learners. Teachers are only involved in the collaborative learning process to foster convenient circumstances. They monitor the groups to get learners of all proficiency levels to participate in differentiated instruction [6].

In conclusion. Teachers should support their students to work collaboratively. The study demonstrated in both its theoretical and practical aspects that cooperative learning positively affects the listening skills of English language learners and the high effect between cooperative learning and listening skills. The research also highlighted the importance of this study by concentrating on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in developing learning skills, especially listening skills. The research reached a set of fundamental results, the content schemata helps the understanding of listeners as they help in predicting, selecting relevant information, and in the resolving ambiguities of a particular text. If students do tasks

collaboratively, they are able to enhance their listening comprehension skill in foreign language.

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RETRAINING OF ENGINEERING FIELD PERSONNEL

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Annotation: *this article highlights the important role that emotions play in engineering activities, the management of emotions, and explores the specifications of emotions. In addition, the article reflects on the essence of emotions and their importance in human life, and discusses the positive and negative aspects of emotions show by engineers in organizing activities.*

Keywords: *engineer, emotions, empathy, respect, stress, resilience, emotional intelligence.*

Introduction: in the preparation of qualified engineering and technical personnel with higher education in our country, the practice of such urgent tasks as creating a new system for training personnel using a national plan, development of a special program, dual education system in higher and secondary educational institutions for this area is important in the preparation of both engineering and technical personnel in the direction of Because the practical use of alternative energy sources is seen as the most important factor in the sustainable development of the economy and the increase in the competitiveness of qualified personnel[1]. As you know, the social, economic reforms carried out in the system of professional education necessitate the further improvement of the process of providing the labor market with competitive qualified personnel. The result of the reforms carried out in the field of Professional education is that a completely new system of education was introduced, harmonized with the international standard classifier. Also, at present, systematic reforms are being implemented on the formation of the integration of educational content, science and development on the basis of a dual educational system. Also, the training of qualified personnel of higher educational institutions is characterized not only by qualitative changes in the process of the educational system, but also by the fact that it is mutually exclusive with the spheres of production, as well as the development of personnel competence [2,3].

Dual education " professional training of students in professional areas it can be described as pedagogical activity that ensures the formation of individual knowledge and skills" [4].

In this case, the main role is played by direct practice. L.V. Sidakova recognizes that the dual education system is "an educational system that implies the combination

of the educational institution's educational activities with the activities of production enterprises” [5].

The dual education system of specialist training can be viewed as “an educational system of higher professional education aimed at training specialists who will have a clearly coordinated, required level of qualification in a particular profession in the field of employer production enterprises.” Also, theoretical training of the dual education system in educational institutions, when a deeper analysis of domestic and foreign literature is seen, practice-based can be tasted as an educational model that can be carried out at production enterprises. Dual education is a form of training of personnel that combines theoretical training in an educational institution (30% - 40%) of the training time) and practical training at a production enterprise (60%-70%) of the training time). The basic principle of the Dual education system is equal responsibility of educational institutions and production enterprises for the quality of training of personnel [6].

The Dual education system meets the interests of all parties involved in IT – production enterprises and organizations, students, the state: -for a production enterprise-it is the training of personnel for itself, the search and selection of workers, it is an opportunity to reduce costs for their retraining and adaptation; -for students-it lies in the fact that graduates adapt to the conditions of real production enterprises and are more likely to successfully get a job at production enterprises in their specialty after graduation; -the state, which effectively solves the issue of training qualified personnel for the entire economy, also sees. In Dual education, the University and the enterprise develop a special curriculum for the student, this is organically combined with the program of work in the specialty. Engineering is generally regarded as a field driven by logic, intelligence, and technical courage. However, under the surface lies an important, but often overlooked factor—emotions. Emotions play a crucial role in shaping the experiences, decisions and interactions of engineering personnel. This article focuses on how emotions affect the activities of engineering professionals, their impact on problem solving, teamwork, productivity, and overall well-being. Research in psychology and organizational behavior has highlighted the profound impact of emotions on human knowledge and behavior. Although research on emotions in engineering is relatively sparse, the evidence that arises suggests that the emotional states of engineers significantly affect their performance and interaction. For example, emotions such as frustration or excitement can affect problem-solving approaches and levels of creativity. In addition, emotions

play a decisive role in the dynamics of teamwork, affect cooperation, communication and conflict resolution within engineering groups. A mixed method approach can be used to understand the role of emotions in the activities of engineering personnel [7].

Surveys and interviews can be conducted to collect quantitative and qualitative data on the emotional experiences of Engineers, their impact on work and the mechanisms used. In addition, observational studies in engineering work environments can provide valuable insights into how emotions manifest and influence different tasks and interactions. In the activities of engineering personnel, the roller of emotions is often overlooked, but can significantly affect their effectiveness and results. Although engineering is often seen as a purely technical field, emotions play a crucial role in various aspects of an engineer's work: problem solving: engineers often face complex problems that require innovative solutions. Positive emotions such as curiosity, passion, and passion can encourage engineers to explore unconventional ideas and approaches. On the other hand, negative emotions such as frustration or anxiety can hinder creativity and hinder the ability to solve problems. Teamwork and collaboration: engineering projects typically involve multi-disciplinary teams working together towards a common goal. Emotions such as trust, empathy, and respect are crucial to effective communication and cooperation within communities. Positive relationships between team members can increase productivity and lead to better project outcomes. Teamwork and collaboration are decisive aspects of engineering projects, especially given the multidisciplinary nature of such efforts. Here's why emotions such as trust, empathy and respect are so important: trust forms the basis of any successful team. When team members trust each other, they are more likely to share Open thoughts, admit mistakes, and rely on the experience of their birdies. This enhances the sense of psychological security in the community, where people feel comfortable taking risks and being vulnerable. Empathy: empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others. In a team setting, empathy helps team members relate to each other's prospects, experiences, and problems. It encourages active listening and promotes a supportive environment in which people feel valued and understood. Respect: respect is essential to maintain a positive relationship in the team. When team members respect each other's opinions, contributions, and boundaries, they create an inclusive and collaborative environment. Respectful communication encourages constructive feedback, healthy conflict resolution, and effective decision-making. By fostering trust, empathy and respect in engineering communities, organizations can use the diverse talents and

perspectives of their members to solve complex problems and achieve their goals more effectively. In addition, positive relationships between team members can contribute to high morale, increased job satisfaction, and ultimately better project outcomes. Emotions can affect the decision-making process of Engineers [8]. For example, fear of failure or unwillingness to take risks can lead to conservative decision-making, while overconfidence can lead to the neglect of potential design risks or flaws. When making important decisions, it is important that engineers are aware of their feelings and biases. Engineers often work closely with clients or stakeholders to understand their needs and requirements. Emotions such as empathy and patience are essential to build relationships with clients and ensure their satisfaction. In addition, managing emotions such as frustration or frustration in the face of criticism or difficult clients is essential to maintaining professionalism. Work environment and stress management: the engineering profession can be demanding and stressful, especially when faced with tight deadlines or budget constraints. Emotions such as resilience, optimism, and self-awareness are important for overcoming stress and maintaining mental well-being. Employers can also play a role by promoting a hands-on work environment and providing resources for stress management and emotional handling. Emotions play an important role in various aspects of engineer work, including problem solving, teamwork, decision making, customer interactions, and stress management. By effectively understanding and managing their emotions, engineers can increase their performance, productivity, and overall job satisfaction. The findings highlight the importance of emotion recognition and management in engineering settings. Emotional intelligence development strategies such as intelligence practices, empathy building exercises, and stress management techniques can improve the well-being and performance of Engineers. In addition, the development of a supportive work culture that recognizes and satisfies emotional needs can create a favorable environment for innovation and cooperation in engineering groups. In conclusion, emotions have a huge impact on the activities of engineering personnel, affect problem solving, teamwork, productivity and well-being. By recognizing and accepting the roller of emotions, engineering organizations can open new avenues to improve performance and create a more inclusive and supportive work environment. Moving forward, teaching emotional intelligence and promoting a culture of psychological security give engineers the opportunity to positively apply their emotions, encourage innovation and success in engineering. Longitudinal studies in future studies can further examine

the long-term effects of emotions on engineering performance and well-being, informing the development of tailored interventions and best practices for emotion management in an engineering setting. In addition, interdisciplinary collaboration between engineering and psychology can enrich our understanding of the complex interrelationships between emotions, cognition, and behavior in professional.

Conclusion: Thus, it is possible to draw the following conclusions on the process of transition to a dual education system:- while maintaining the level of theoretical training that institutions of Higher Education provide for the implementation of the requirements of the state educational standard of Education, significantly strengthens the practical component of the educational process;- production enterprises help to solve the problem of training specialists who are fully ready for activities. Increases the professional mobility and competitiveness of graduate students in the labor market;-the relationship between the activities of higher educational institutions and production enterprises is strengthened. Thanks to the Dual education system, it will be possible to achieve real training efficiency to meet the specific needs of production.

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USING COLLABORATIVE LEARNING TO ENHANCE CRITICAL THINKING AND CREATIVITY

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Annotation: *This article outlines how collaborative learning can be an effective method for developing both critical thinking and creativity in students. It discusses the theory behind collaborative learning, its benefits for cognitive and creative development, and strategies for implementation.*

Key words: *Collaborative Learning, Critical Thinking, Creativity, Problem-Solving, Peer Learning, Group Work, Interdisciplinary Collaboration, Debate, Brainstorming, Project-Based Learning.*

In today's educational landscape, fostering critical thinking and creativity is essential for students to thrive in both academic and real-world settings. Collaborative learning, an instructional approach where students work together to solve problems and achieve learning objectives, has proven to be a powerful tool for nurturing these skills. This article explores how collaborative learning can enhance critical thinking and creativity, providing students with the opportunity to engage in meaningful dialogue, exchange diverse ideas, and develop complex solutions to problems.

Collaborative learning involves students working together in pairs or small groups to accomplish specific tasks, projects, or discussions. It encourages interaction, communication, and cooperation among peers, which is fundamentally different from the traditional, teacher-centered approach to learning. The core principle of collaborative learning is the idea that learning is a social process, where students not only acquire knowledge but also actively contribute to the learning of others.

Enhancing Critical Thinking through Collaborative Learning

Critical thinking refers to the ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information to make informed decisions. Collaborative learning promotes critical thinking in several ways:

1. **Exposure to Diverse Perspectives:** When students collaborate, they are exposed to different viewpoints, which challenges their assumptions and broadens

their understanding of the subject matter. This exposure encourages them to critically evaluate their own beliefs and ideas.

2. Engaging in Constructive Debate: Collaborative learning often involves discussion and debate, which fosters an environment where students learn to articulate their reasoning, ask probing questions, and defend their ideas. This back-and-forth exchange promotes deeper cognitive processing and the development of more nuanced perspectives.

3. Collaborative Problem-Solving: Working together to solve complex problems requires students to break down the problem into manageable parts, analyze information, and propose solutions. This process promotes higher-order thinking skills, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation, which are key components of critical thinking.

Fostering Creativity through Collaborative Learning

Creativity is the ability to generate new and innovative ideas, solutions, or approaches. Collaborative learning enhances creativity by:

1. Sharing and Combining Ideas: When students work in groups, they pool their knowledge, experiences, and creative ideas. The synergy of different ideas leads to more original solutions that would not have been possible through individual effort alone. This collective brainstorming sparks creativity.

2. Encouraging Risk-Taking: In a supportive collaborative environment, students feel more comfortable taking risks with their ideas without fear of judgment. This freedom to experiment and explore new concepts nurtures creative thinking and innovation.

3. Cross-Disciplinary Thinking: Collaborative learning often involves students from diverse backgrounds, disciplines, or areas of expertise. This interdisciplinary collaboration encourages students to think outside the box, apply knowledge from different fields, and develop creative solutions to problems.

Practical Strategies for Implementing Collaborative Learning

To effectively use collaborative learning to enhance critical thinking and creativity, educators can employ the following strategies:

1. Group Discussions and Debates: Facilitate structured group discussions where students must critically analyze a topic or debate a specific issue. This helps develop their argumentation skills and promotes critical thinking.

2. Project-Based Learning: Encourage students to work on long-term projects that require collaborative problem-solving. These projects can integrate various

subjects and challenge students to think critically and creatively to achieve their goals.

3. Peer Review and Feedback: Incorporate peer review into collaborative learning activities, where students provide constructive feedback to each other. This process encourages critical evaluation and fosters a creative exchange of ideas.

4. Role-Playing and Simulations: Engage students in role-playing exercises or simulations that require them to think critically and creatively. These activities encourage them to consider different perspectives and come up with creative solutions to problems.

Challenges of Collaborative Learning

While collaborative learning has numerous benefits, it also presents some challenges. These include:

1. Uneven Participation: In some groups, not all students may actively contribute, which can hinder the learning process. It's essential for instructors to monitor group dynamics and ensure equal participation.

2. Group Conflict: Differences in opinion or working styles may lead to conflict within groups. Educators must guide students in conflict resolution techniques to ensure productive collaboration.

3. Assessment Difficulties: Evaluating individual contributions in a group setting can be challenging. Instructors need to design assessments that measure both individual and group performance.

Collaborative learning is a valuable pedagogical approach that fosters critical thinking and creativity by encouraging interaction, debate, and shared problem-solving. By creating an environment where students actively engage with each other's ideas and perspectives, educators can help students develop the skills necessary for success in the 21st century. Although challenges exist, the benefits of collaborative learning in enhancing critical thinking and creativity far outweigh the drawbacks, making it an essential tool in modern education.

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THE ROLE OF PARALLEL CORPUS IN TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Annotation: *the concepts of the corpus and its parallel corpus link, as well as its structure, types, tokens, lemmas, and stemming, are all covered in this article on corpus linguistics. The study of the current linguistic possibilities in Uzbek, the identification of problematic linguistic aspects, the development of electronic dictionaries, the improvement of the efficiency of contemporary information technology in language learning, automatic translation, search, and computer analysis are the areas of theoretical and practical significance of the corpus today. In order to solve problems, a corpus of language in particular fields must be developed.*

Key words: *Corpus, corpus linguistics, parallel corpus, translation corpus, comparable corpus, segmentation, machine translation, tokenization, lemmatization, stemization.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the global problems of the 21st century is the national nature of natural languages is to preserve. Electronic corpora of world languages to NLP and language technologies in creation and development has become an urgent task to consistently conduct research on.¹ Scientific and practical research conducted in the field of foreign corpus linguistics not only for the representatives of the corpus who deal with words, but also for the nation proved to be a necessary and necessary point for development.

The policy to establish a national corpus of the Uzbek language has become one of the most significant challenges. Specifically, to raise the Uzbek language's status in society and internationally, an electronic national corpus of the language that contains all scientific, theoretical, and practical information about the language should be created; the Uzbek language should be made widely known and given a respectable place in the Internet world information network; Uzbek software applications should be developed; and computer programs that teach the Uzbek language should be implemented on a large scale. Two significant issues facing linguistics are the development of computer programs for editing texts in the Uzbek language. In practice, many researches are being conducted in this regard. Corpus Linguistics of Russian and English languages in various fields V. Zakharov, A. Sedov, A. Baranov, R. Potapova, V. Rikov, U. Francis, N. Leontyeva, V. Martin, S. Kubler, A. Lawrence, E. Etwell, S. Hunston, L. Boizou, McKenney, J. Grafmiller, J. Grieva, N. Groom, S.

¹ Abduraxmonova N. O'zbek tili elektron korpusining kompyuter modellari (monografiya) /Toshkent: Muharrir, 2021, 202 b

Hansson² scientific research in the field of corpus studies (corpus linguistics) in Turkology was carried out by foreign scientists such as K.MMcAulif, M.Malberg, P.Milin, A.Murakami, R.Peich, A.Schembri, P.Thompson, B.Winter, G.Lynch. Aksan, Deniz, Zeyrek, Kemal Oflazer, Umut Uzge on the Turkish language; Yusup Aibaidulla, Kim-Teng Lua on the Uighur language; I.A. Buskunbaeva, Z. Sirazitdinov on the Bashkir language; Sheymovich on the Khakaz language, J. Suleymanov, A. Gatiatullin, O. Nevzorova, R. Gilmullin, B. Hakimov on the Tatar language; The works of scientists such as L. Kubedinova on the Crimean Tatar language and Salchak on the Tuva language are noteworthy³. Uzbek scientists B. Mengliyev, Sh. Shahobiddinova, Z. Kholmanova, S. Karimov, N. Abdurakhmonova, L. Raupova, Sh. Hamroyeva, M. Abjalova, G. Toirova, G. Ikromova, J. Djumabayeva, G. Ergasheva, A. Eshmuminov have done scientific work. The concept of the national corpus of the Uzbek language is being developed by a team of scientists headed by B. Mengliyev⁴.

The corpus is an electronic treasure that gathers all the big and small power of the language. There are different standards for writing a corpus of texts. Sort the corpora into the types of the given base (oral, written), the language of the text translations (Russian, German, Turkish...), the parallelism of the text translation (bilingual, trilingual), the style (colloquial, artistic, official, scientific, journalistic), the base (open, closed), geographical location (only one country and belonging). A corpus is a set of spoken and written texts stored in a computer database. The time when the materials collected in the corpus were written, which style they belong to, and which source they belong to, will also be explained in detail. Depending on his interests, the user can refer to artistic, scientific, official or journalistic texts. This is especially useful in language learning. It is very useful for pedagogues to quickly give tasks to students to strengthen their knowledge during the course of school education. The corpus is a systematized library with a very wide scope and a high level of importance which is easy to use, saves a lot of time. It differs from other programs in terms of electronic search engine. The user can locate all variations of the given term in various contexts by using corpus search. It displays its alternatives and location in the lexicon with clarity. It can identify the range of words that can be combined, as well as the word's denotative and con

² Abdurakhmonova N. Kompyuter lingvistikasi (darslik) / Globe edit publishing, 2020, 395 b.

³ Abdurakhmonova N. Kompyuter lingvistikasi (darslik) / Globe edit publishing, 2020, 395 b.

⁴ Abduraxmonova N. O'zbek tili elektron korpusining kompyuter modellari (monografiya) / Toshkent: Muharrir, 2021, 202 b.

notative meanings. It explains the statistics or frequency of word usage in a writer's writing. It is a sign of modern development that can reflect the state of use of this word in which period. The electronic corpus of the Uzbek language was implemented within the project "Creating an electronic corpus of artistic works on the topic of family, neighborhood and gender equality" No. JHBL-20 of the Neighborhood and Family Research Institute⁵. This electronic case has been created using world experience.

Parallel corpus as a new type of linguistic resources

Since it may hold a lot of essential information, the autonomous portion of the electronic body's parallel body is significant. Structured parallel corpora are multilingual corpora that have been carefully designed for side-by-side comparison in the field of machine translation. In contrastive linguistics and translation studies, parallel corpora are essential. Easy-to-use concordancers make it possible to access a large number of parallel corpora, which greatly facilitates the research of cross-linguistic phenomena.

Regarding the parallel corpus, Anarbayev Orzubek

Rakhmanovich states: "The parallel corpus is an important reality for the current era, when intercultural communication is widespread." Parallel corpora will allow for the identification of universals across various linguistic contexts and cultural backgrounds, as well as particular linguistic mentalities, such as realia and lacunar units. Through parallel corpora, it will be possible to identify universals in different language environments and cultures, as well as specific mental characteristics of languages, realia and lacunar units. The corpus of parallel texts also serves for the development of automatic translation, ensures the development of computer lexicography." With the help of corpus of parallel texts, concordance programs are developed and it is possible to create dictionaries of various specializations. The reflection of time is reflected in the vocabulary of the language. It "grows" constantly. The window that clearly shows the richness of the language is its dictionary. The large number of vocabulary content is considered a factor that increases its value. In both translation studies and contrastive linguistics, multilingual corpora have recently been used to study translation phenomena, translation changes or translation features, as well as contrastive differences between them. One such case is the Anglo-German CroCo case. The corpus includes English and German originals and their translations into German and English. Thus, it can be used as both

⁵ Abdurahmonova N. O'zbek tili elektron korpusining kompyuter modellari (avtoreferat). Toshkent: OOO` AKTIV PRINT`, 2021, 72 b.

a comparable and a parallel corpus. There are eight different genres for each translation approach, and each segment has a minimum of ten texts totaling 31,250 words. There are roughly a million words in the CroCo Corpus. Additionally, 2000 word samples from 17 genres are included in an unregistered neutral corpus for German and English. As a result, the body is composed of parallel and similar parts. These genres include textbooks, scientific and popular literature, political articles, artistic texts (fiction), business communications, prepared speeches, travel brochures, and websites (WEB). In order to handle increasingly complicated searches, such as those that work on several annotation and alignment layers, and to apply Java-based annotation tools to the corpus, it has its own application programming interface (API). They were chosen because of their relevance to the study of translation features in the English-German language pair. The world linguistic scene has motivated that the creation of parallel corpora is the main issue in Uzbek linguistics as well. The process of automatic normalization of texts is related to morphological analysis, in which the methods of tokenization, lemmatization, and stemmization are used.

- Tokenization** - speech units in natural language are separated into grammatical meanings in a separate way, word forms are determined.

- Lemmas** - the first part of word forms, that is, their appearance in the dictionary is determined. Words are divided into bases and suffixes and are made into morphemes.

- Stemming** - the root part of the word is determined.

The corpus contains keywords that are relevant to the parallel corpus. Key words are used many times and represent the main meaning. They are formed by dividing the text into parts, including units that do not have an independent meaning in a separate set, and removing them from the table of units classified as keywords. Extracting key words from the text in parallel corpora makes our work easier.

CONCLUSION

Today, the case has become a work tool that saves time and labor. Corpus-based language learning, parsing based on the theory of dependence, FST technology in corpus morphological analysis, programming and linguistic teaching of national corpus creation, morphological and semantic analyzer of corpus, creation of neuro technologies based on parallel corpora of machine translation, formation of educational corpus of Uzbek language⁶... are being conducted. Parallel corpora are

⁶ Uzbek corpus

useful not only in linguistics, but also in translation studies, bilingual lexicography, and in areas where it is necessary to compare languages. One of the advantages of the electronic corpus is that it is possible to observe word changes, historicism, neologism, expansion and narrowing of meaning, emergence of new phraseology in the language. The continuous introduction and placement of news in the language corpora, which is an electronic resource that shows the process of inter-period language enrichment, eases human labor. It takes a lot of effort and money to include the changes that occur in the language over the years in the book-form dictionaries. And the corpus provides an opportunity to solve this problem in a short period of time, at no cost. The expected result of parallel corpora is the complete automation of the text, through which it can be used not only in translation, but also for machine translation. Currently, we are in the process of creating a machine translation technology that is implemented statistically as a direct result of human activity in the future. By creating a translation memory, it helps to develop the neural technology of machine translation on a linguistic basis for statistical translation technology like Google. Another important aspect of parallel corpora is that they put an end to translation nonsense. It is still a problem that there are many mistakes in the translation made on the Internet, that words are turned into words that have nothing to do with the translation of the text. The main goal of creating a parallel corpus is to develop effective and correct translation methods. A translation quality improvement is achieved through a parallel corpus.

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RAQAMLI TA'LIM MUHITIDA TALABALARGA “MEDIASAVODXONLIK VA FAKTCHEKING” FANINI O'QITISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada, raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalar uchun “Mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking” fanini o'qitishning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu fan talabalarni axborotni tahlil qilish, ishonchli manbalardan foydalanish va noto'g'ri axborotni aniqlashga o'rgatishga qaratilgan. Maqola fanning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va uning talabalarni tanqidiy fikrlashga undashi haqidagi fikrlarni keltiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Axborot xavfsizlik, mediasavodxonlik, faktcheking, ta'lim, dezinformatsiya, feyk, manipulyatsiya.

Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar va internetning tez rivojlanishi natijasida axborot oqimi va uning tarqalishi beqiyos darajada ortdi. Shu jumladan, turli manbalardan olingan *axborotning aniqligi va ishonchliligi* masalasi dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bu esa, ayniqsa, talabalar va yoshlar uchun axborotning to'g'ri tahlil qilinishi, xatoliklar va manipulyatsiyalarni aniqlashda mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking ko'nikmalarini egallash zaruratini taqazo etadi. Raqamli ta'lim muhitida bu ko'nikmalarni o'rgatish talabalar uchun nafaqat akademik muvaffaqiyatni, balki ularning ijtimoiy mas'uliyatini oshiradi. Axborotning tez tarqalishi va uning ta'siri kengayishi bilan, mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking fanining ta'limda o'rni yanada ortmoqda. Shuningdek, ushbu fan talabalarni noto'g'ri ma'lumotlarni aniqlash va tasniflashga o'rgatish orqali, ularni tanqidiy fikrlash va axborotga mas'uliyat bilan yondashishga undaydi. Bu esa, ularning nafaqat o'qish jarayonida, balki kundalik hayotda ham foydalidir. Shu bois, “**Mediasavodxonlik va Faktcheking**” fanini o'qitish bugungi ta'lim muhitida eng muhim masalalardan biri sifatida nomoyon bo'lmoqda.

Mediasavodxonlik — bu media manbalarini tahlil qilish, baholash, tanqidiy yondashish va ular bilan ishlash ko'nikmalaridir. Mediasavodxonlik insonlarni axborotni tahlil qilishda ya'ni uni to'g'ri talqin qilishda va manbalarni tekshirishda yordam beradi¹. Mediasavodxonlikni oshirishda ta'limning yetakchi vosita sifatida ahamiyati juda katta. Ta'lim, ayniqsa, yoshlar va talabalar orasida mediasavodxonlikni rivojlantirishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi². Bu jarayonda ta'limning

¹ A. Neag, Ç. Bozdağ, and K. Leurs. Media literacy education for diverse societies. Encyclopedia of Communication. 2022. P 23.

² R. Hobbs. Media literacy in action: Questioning the media. 2024. Page 15.

turli shakllari va metodlari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Rivojlangan davlatlarda, ayniqsa, **Yevropa** va **Shimoliy Amerika** davlatlarida, mediasavodxonlik ta'lim tizimining muhim qismi sifatida tan olinadi. O'quv dasturlarida bu fan alohida yo'nalish sifatida kiritilgan yoki boshqa fanlar bilan integratsiyalashgan. Masalan, **Buyuk Britaniyada** media va axborot texnologiyalari (ICT) ta'limining bir qismi sifatida mediasavodxonlikni o'qitish amaliyoti keng tarqalgan³. Shu bilan birga, o'quvchilarga soxta yangiliklar va manipulyatsiyalangan axborotdan xabardor bo'lishga yordam beradigan materiallar beriladi. Turli davlatlarda, ayniqsa, soxta yangiliklar va manipulyatsiyalangan ma'lumotlar tobora keng tarqalib bormoqda. Shuning uchun, mediasavodxonlikni o'qitishning asosiy vazifalaridan biri o'quvchilarga va talabalarga yolg'on axborotlarni tanib olish va undan saqlanishni o'rgatishdir. Masalan, **Germaniya** va **Finlyandiya** kabi davlatlar, talabalar va o'quvchilarga raqamli media vositalarida tahlil qilish, soxta ma'lumotlarni aniqlash va tarmoqda mas'uliyatli axborot almashish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan maxsus dasturlarni amalga oshirmoqda.

Mediasavodxonlikni *interaktiv ta'lim metodlari* yordamida o'rgatishda ilg'or tajribalarni joriy qilmoqda. Bu metodlar orqali talabalar media kontentini yaratish, bloglar, videolar yoki boshqa axborot materiallarini ishlab chiqish jarayonida o'z fikrlarini bayon qilishni o'rganadilar⁴. Masalan, **Kanada** va **Skandinaviya** davlatlarida o'quvchilarga raqamli vositalar yordamida o'zlarini ifodalash imkoniyatlari yaratiladi, shu bilan birga ularni axborot yaratishda va tarqatishda mas'uliyatli bo'lishga undaydi.

Bugungi kunda talaba-yoshlarning axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishda **“Mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking”** fani O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti shuningdek, pedagogikaga ixtisoslashgan OTM yo'nalishlarida mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish nuqtaiy nazaridan ta'lim berib kelinmoqda. Mazkur fanni o'qitishda quyidagi kamchiliklar ko'zga tashlanmoqda:

1. Hozirgi kunda mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking fanini o'qitish uchun o'qituvchilarning yetarli malakaga ega emasligi muammo hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina o'qituvchilar ushbu sohada yetarli tajribaga ega emas yoki axborot tahlilini samarali o'rgatish uchun zarur pedagogik usullarni qo'llay olmaydi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy media vositalari va raqamli texnologiyalarni o'qitishda samarali qo'llashni biladigan

³ S. Arsyad and A. S. Villia. Exploring the Effect of Digital Literacy Skill and Learning Style of Students on Their Meta-Cognitive Strategies in Listening. *International Journal of Instruction*, 2022. Page 23-28.

⁴ A.B. Rinekso, R.S. Rodliyah, and I. Pertiwi. Digital literacy practices in tertiary education: A case of EFL postgraduate students. *Studies in English Language*, 2021. P 77.

mutaxassislarning yetishmasligi ham ta'lim sifati uchun salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

2. **“Mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking”** fanini o'qitishda nazariy bilimlarga ko'proq e'tibor qaratilmoqda, ammo amaliy mashg'ulotlar va real hayotda axborot tahlil qilish tajribasi etishmaydi. Talabalar real voqealar va yangiliklarni tahlil qilish, soxta axborotlarni aniqlash bo'yicha amaliy mashg'ulotlar o'tkazish orqali ko'proq o'rganishlari lozim. Amaliyotlar orqali bu ko'nikmalarni mustahkamlash zarur.

3. Mediasavodxonlik va faktchekingga oid yetarli va sifati o'quv resurslari (*darsliklar, qo'llanmalar, onlayn materiallar*) hali mavjud emas. O'zbekiston sharoitida talabalar va o'qituvchilar bu fanlarni o'rganishda ko'plab cheklolarga duch kelmoqda. Xususan, sohaga oid yangi va zamonaviy manbalar, interaktiv materiallar yetishmaydi, bu esa o'qitish sifatiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Bugungi kunda **“Mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking”** fanining O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti va pedagogikaga ixtisoslashgan oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qitilishi ahamiyatli bo'lsa-da, ayrim kamchiliklar ham mavjud. Bu kamchiliklar o'qituvchilarning malakasining yetarli bo'lmasligi, amaliy mashg'ulotlarning cheklanganligi, o'quv resurslarining yetishmasligi, talabalar orasida qiziqishning pastligi va axborot texnologiyalarining tez o'zgarishiga moslashishdagi qiyinchiliklar bilan bog'liqdir. Biroq, ushbu kamchiliklarga qarshi samarali choralar ko'rilsa, **“Mediasavodxonlik va faktcheking”** fanining ta'lim jarayonidagi roli ortadi. O'qituvchilarni malakali qilish, amaliy mashg'ulotlar sonini ko'paytirish, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanish va talabalar uchun bu fanlarning amaliy ahamiyatini tushuntirish orqali bu fanlardan olingan bilimlar kundalik hayot va professional faoliyatda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, axborot madaniyatini shakllantirish va soxta axborotlarga qarshi kurashishda talabalar va yoshlar o'rtasida mediasavodxonlikni oshirish nafaqat ularning akademik muvaffaqiyatlarini, balki jamiyatdagi axborot oqimlarini ongli va tanqidiy ravishda qabul qilish qobiliyatini ham rivojlantiradi. Bu esa o'z navbatida jamiyatning axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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2. R. Hobbs. Media literacy in action: Questioning the media. 2024.

3. S. Arsyad and A. S. Villia. Exploring the Effect of Digital Literacy Skill and Learning Style of Students on Their Meta-Cognitive Strategies in Listening. *International Journal of Instruction*, 2022.
4. A.B. Rinekso, R.S. Rodliyah, and I. Pertiwi. Digital literacy practices in tertiary education: A case of EFL postgraduate students. *Studies in English Language*, 2021.

BADIIY MATNDA FRAZEOLOGIZMLAR BAHO IFODALASH VOSITASI SIFATIDA QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada frazeologizmlarning badiiy matnda baho ifodalash vositasi sifatidagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Mirmuhsinning "Ilon o'chi" asaridan olingan misollar orqali frazeologizmlarning qahramonlar xarakterini ochish, voqealarga baho berish va muallifning munosabatini ifodalashdagi funksional xususiyatlari ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Frazeologizmlar, baho ifodalash, badiiy matn, obrazlilik, ekspressivlik, "Ilon o'chi".

Badiiy matnda muallif va qahramonlar tomonidan voqealar va shaxslar haqidagi baho ko'pincha frazeologizmlar yordamida ifodalanadi. Frazeologizm- (yunoncha phrasis-ifoda, jumla, logos-sotuzilishiga ko'ra so'z birikmasiga, gapga teng, semantik jihatdan bir butun, umumlashgan ma'no anglatadigan, nutqqa tayyor holda kiritiladigan lug'aviy birlik (masalan, tomdan tarashatushganday— to'satdan, qo'qqisdan) [1,364]. Frazeologizmlar badiiy tasvir vositasi sifatida nafaqat voqealarni jonlantiradi, balki ularni baholashga, muallifning yoki qahramonlarning shaxsiy munosabatini ifodalashga ham xizmat qiladi. Frazeologizmlar badiiylik mohiyatini yaqqol ochib beruvchi unsur sanaladi." Frazeologizmlar badiiy adabiyotda obrazli va ta'sirchan vosita sifatida qo'llaniladi" [2,54].

Mirmuhsinning "Ilon o'chi" asarida frazeologizmlar orqali voqealarga va qahramonlarga ijobiy yoki salbiy baho berilgan holatlarni ko'rish mumkin.

Frazeologizmlar nafaqat, badiiy matnda, balki, qisman publitsistika, ilmiy-ommabop matnlarda qo'llanadi. Yozuvchi badiiy matnda frazeologizmlardan quyidagi maqsadlarda foydalanadi:

1. Biror voqea va hodisani obrazli, ta'sirli ifodalash uchun;

Masalan: tili uzun, ilonni yog'ini yalagan, dunyoni suv bossa, uning to'pig'a ham chiqmaydi.

2. Turli holatlarni baholash uchun; frazeologizmlar salbiy yoki ijobiy bahoga ega.

Masalan: Uning ko'zlari olayib o'rnidan turolmay qoldi.

3. Badiiy matnda emotsionallikni ifodalash uchun;

Masalan: Xudoga shukr, ko'ngli joyiga tushdi.

4. Nutqda ekspressivlikni ifodalash uchun;
“Ekspressiya” soʻzi aslida lotincha soʻz boʻlib, "kuchaytirilgan; ifodali, tasviriy“, - degan maʼnoni anglatadi. Nutqning taʼsirchanlik xususiyatini ifodalaydi.

5. Badiiy matnda satira va yumor hosil qilish uchun: yumor va satira vositalari asardagi qahramon nutqini, uning soʻzlash ohangidagi yumoristik yoki satirik ishorani taʼkidlash vositasi boʻlib xizmat qiladi [3,40].

Misol: Birovning daydi sigiri, birovning **shaytonga dars beradigan** echkisi zum oʻtmay ekin oralab ketadi [3,40].

1. Frazeologizmlar orqali ijobiy baho ifodalash.

Baʼzi frazeologik birliklar yordamida muallif yoki qahramonlar boshqalarni maqtash yoki ularning ijobiy sifatlarini koʻrsatadi.

“Habib oʻrtogʻing uddaburon, **yulduzni benarvon uradi**, - dedi Sharbatxon aya oʻgʻlini yoniga olib, - doʻxtir boʻlaman deb yoshligidan bu ishga kirishgan” [4,81].

Bu yerda *yulduzni benarvon uradi* frazeologizmi Habibning chaqqonligi va uddaburonligini taʼriflash uchun ishlatilgan. Sharbatxon ayaning bu iborasi orqali qahramonga ijobiy baho beriladi.

2. Frazeologizmlar orqali salbiy baho ifodalash.

Frazeologizmlar koʻpincha salbiy baho berishda, yaʼni qahramonlarning salbiy sifatlarini yoki nojoʻya xatti-harakatlarini koʻrsatishda ham ishlatiladi.

“Pul chiqadigan joyda Fatxulloxon boʻzrayib turaverardi, pulni koʻrsa, **sichqonni poylagan mushukdek** qotib qolardi” [4,77].

Bu frazeologizm Fatxulloxonning pulga nisbatan haddan tashqari ehtirosini va ochkoʻzligini ifodalash uchun ishlatilgan. Sichqonni poylagan mushukdek iborasi uning pul oldidagi oʻzini tutish qiyofasiga salbiy baho beradi.

“Koʻrinishdan loʻmbillagan, **qoʻy ogʻzidan choʻp olmagan** Pati oʻziga yetguncha ogʻir. Universamdagilar sohibchangal deyishadi. Keyingi paytlarda bu ayniqsa avj oldi. **Besh qoʻlini barobar ogʻziga tiqqanga** oʻxshardi” [4,85].

Ushbu iboralar Pati xarakterining tashqi koʻrinishidan farqli ravishda ichki ochkoʻzligini va ogʻir feʼlini ifodalaydi. *Qoʻy ogʻzidan choʻp olmagan* iborasi tashqi begunoh koʻrinishni bildirsa, *besh qoʻlini barobar ogʻziga tiqqanga oʻxshardi* frazeologizmi uning ochkoʻzligini kuchli salbiy baho bilan ifodalaydi.

3. Frazeologizmlar yordamida voqealarga baho berish.

Frazeologik birliklar nafaqat qahramonlarga, balki voqealarga baho berishda ham ishlatiladi. Bunday iboralar voqealarning ahamiyatini, ularning taʼsirini koʻrsatishda muhim rol oʻynaydi.

“1966-yilgi zilzila katta musibat bo‘ldi. Miyonxo‘ja amakining fikricha, 37-yilu 41-yillarda Toshkent farzandlari **tutday to‘kildi**” [4,77].

Tutday to‘kildi frazeologizmi Toshkentdagi falokat va yo‘qotishlarni ta‘riflash uchun ishlatilgan. Bu ibora voqealarning ko‘lamini va dahshatini ifodalovchi kuchli baho vositasi hisoblanadi.

“O‘n kun deganda daragi chiqqan, shalpayib, **dami chiqqan koptokdek** shalpaygan singlisini Pati Urganchdan olib kelgan edi” [4,83].

Bu frazeologizm singlisining holdan toyganini va jismoniy holda juda charchaganini ko‘rsatadi. *Shalpayib, dami chiqqan koptokdek* iborasi voqea ta‘sirini oshirib, holatga salbiy baho beradi.

4. Frazeologizmlar orqali muallifning yoki qahramonlarning munosabatini ifodalash.

Frazeologizmlar yordamida muallif yoki qahramonlarning boshqa shaxslar yoki voqealarga bo‘lgan shaxsiy munosabati ifodalanadi. Bu holatda frazeologik birliklar baho vositasi sifatida ishlaydi.

“Hushyor bo‘lish kerak! Frontda razvedkachi bo‘lganman, debsiz tarjimai holingizda. Nahotki, izingizdan tushgan yaramasni bilmasangiz! **Ko‘zingizni shira bosib qoldimikan**” [4,61]?

Ko‘zingizni shira bosib qoldimikan frazeologizmi beparvolik yoki e‘tiborsizlikka tanqidiy baho berishda ishlatilgan. Bu ibora qahramonning ehtiyotsizligi yoki loqaydligiga nisbatan salbiy munosabatni bildiradi.

Frazeologizmlar badiiy matnda muhim baho ifodalash vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ular yordamida muallif va qahramonlar boshqa shaxslar, voqealar yoki holatlarga ijobiy yoki salbiy baho beradi. Mirmuhsinning “Ilon o‘chi” asarida frazeologik birliklar orqali qahramonlarning xarakteri va voqealar ta‘sirchan tarzda yoritilgan. Bunday iboralar asarning obrazlilikini oshirib, o‘quvchini matn mazmuniga yanada chuqurroq jalb qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati.

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FORMATION OF CULTURAL TOLERANCE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

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Annotation. *In the modern era of globalization, fostering cultural tolerance in preschool children is essential for developing open-mindedness, empathy, and respect for diverse traditions. One of the most effective ways to achieve this is through foreign language learning, which naturally introduces young learners to different cultures. The integration of digital educational resources, including interactive applications, multimedia storytelling, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR), has significantly enhanced this process. These tools provide immersive and engaging learning experiences that help children develop a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity. This article explores the role of digital educational resources in promoting cultural tolerance through early foreign language learning, analyzing their benefits, challenges, and the need for high-quality, authentic content. The findings suggest that a combination of digital tools and real-world multicultural experiences is the most effective approach for fostering cultural awareness in preschool education.*

Key words. *Cultural tolerance, preschool education, foreign language learning, digital educational resources, interactive learning, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), multimedia storytelling, global citizenship, multicultural education.*

Аннотация. *В современную эпоху глобализации воспитание культурной толерантности у детей дошкольного возраста имеет важное значение для развития открытости, сочувствия и уважения к разнообразным традициям. Одним из наиболее эффективных способов добиться этого является изучение иностранного языка, которое естественным образом знакомит молодых учащихся с различными культурами. Интеграция цифровых образовательных ресурсов, включая интерактивные приложения, мультимедийные повествования, виртуальную реальность (VR) и дополненную реальность (AR), значительно улучшила этот процесс. Эти инструменты обеспечивают захватывающий и увлекательный опыт обучения, который помогает детям глубже оценить культурное разнообразие. В этой статье исследуется роль цифровых образовательных ресурсов в продвижении культурной толерантности посредством раннего изучения иностранного языка, анализируются их преимущества, проблемы и потребность в высококачественном, аутентичном контенте. Результаты показывают, что сочетание цифровых инструментов и реального мультикультурного опыта является наиболее эффективным подходом к повышению культурной осведомленности в дошкольном образовании.*

Ключевые слова. *Культурная толерантность, дошкольное образование, изучение иностранных языков, цифровые образовательные ресурсы, интерактивное обучение, виртуальная реальность (VR), дополненная реальность (AR), мультимедийное повествование, глобальное гражданство, поликультурное образование.*

Izoh. *Zamonaviy globallashuv davrida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda madaniy bag'rikenglikni tarbiyalash ochiq fikrlashni, hamdardlik va turli an'analarga hurmatni*

rivojlantirish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bunga erishishning eng samarali usullaridan biri yosh o'quvchilarni turli madaniyatlar bilan tanishtiruvchi xorijiy tillarni o'rganishdir. Raqamli ta'lim resurslari, jumladan, interaktiv ilovalar, multimediali hikoyalar, virtual haqiqat (VR) va to'ldirilgan reallik (AR) integratsiyasi bu jarayonni sezilarli darajada oshirdi. Ushbu vositalar bolalarda madaniy xilma-xillikni chuqurroq anglashlariga yordam beradigan chuqur va qiziqarli o'rganish tajribasini taqdim etadi. Ushbu maqolada raqamli ta'lim resurslarining chet tillarini erta o'rganish orqali madaniy bag'rikenglikni targ'ib qilishdagi roli, ularning afzalliklari, muammolari va yuqori sifatli, haqiqiy kontentga bo'lgan ehtiyoj tahlil qilinadi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli vositalar va real dunyo ko'p madaniyatli tajribalar kombinatsiyasi maktabgacha ta'limda madaniy ongni rivojlantirishning eng samarali usuli hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar. Madaniy bag'rikenglik, maktabgacha ta'lim, chet tillarini o'rganish, raqamli ta'lim resurslari, interaktiv ta'lim, virtual haqiqat (VR), kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR), multimedia hikoyalari, global fuqarolik, ko'p madaniyatli ta'lim.

In the modern world, where globalization has created an interconnected society, the importance of cultural tolerance has grown significantly. Teaching cultural tolerance to preschool children is essential for fostering open-mindedness, empathy, and respect for diverse traditions. One of the most effective ways to instill these values is through foreign language learning, which naturally introduces children to different cultures. With the advancement of technology, digital educational resources have become powerful tools in making this learning process more engaging, interactive, and effective. Foreign language learning at an early age not only enhances cognitive development but also provides an excellent opportunity to introduce cultural awareness and sensitivity. The formation of cultural tolerance in preschool children through foreign language learning and digital educational resources has been widely studied in early childhood education, cognitive development, and technology-enhanced learning. This literature review explores key findings in these areas, focusing on the role of language acquisition in cultural awareness, the impact of digital resources on learning experiences, and the effectiveness of interactive and immersive technologies in fostering cultural tolerance. Research has consistently shown that learning a foreign language at an early age fosters cognitive flexibility, social adaptability, and cultural awareness [1]. Bialystok (2018) highlights that bilingual and multilingual children tend to develop a deeper understanding of cultural differences, as language is inherently tied to traditions, social norms, and worldviews [2]. Early language learning exposes children to linguistic diversity, making them more receptive to different ways of thinking and communicating. Additionally, studies indicate that young learners who engage with foreign languages are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of empathy and cross-cultural understanding, as they become familiar with the customs

and traditions of others through linguistic exposure [3]. Moreover, cultural tolerance is strengthened when language learning includes contextualized experiences that go beyond vocabulary and grammar. According to Kramersch (2020), language serves as both a communicative tool and a cultural medium, shaping children's perceptions of other communities [4]. This suggests that language learning should integrate cultural elements, such as storytelling, music, and folklore, to help preschoolers develop a more holistic understanding of different cultures. Such approaches have been shown to reduce biases and stereotypes, as children are exposed to diverse perspectives in a natural and engaging way [5].

Studies have shown that children who learn a second language from a young age tend to develop a greater appreciation for different cultures and demonstrate higher levels of empathy toward people from diverse backgrounds [1]. This is because language is deeply tied to cultural identity, and exposure to different languages naturally introduces learners to traditions, customs, and worldviews beyond their own. When preschoolers engage with a new language, they simultaneously absorb cultural elements that shape their understanding of global diversity. The integration of digital educational resources into foreign language instruction has further revolutionized the way young children are exposed to different cultures. Digital tools such as interactive applications, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), animated storytelling, and multimedia platforms provide immersive experiences that make learning both enjoyable and effective [2]. Language-learning apps, for instance, often include culturally relevant content, such as traditional songs, folktales, and everyday dialogues, allowing children to familiarize themselves with diverse lifestyles and social norms in an engaging manner. Additionally, animated videos featuring characters from different cultural backgrounds help normalize diversity and promote a sense of inclusivity.

Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies offer even more profound cultural immersion by enabling children to "visit" foreign countries, explore historical landmarks, and interact with digital representations of people from various cultures [3]. Such experiences allow preschoolers to develop a sense of connection with other cultures, fostering cultural empathy and reducing biases. For example, a child learning French might use VR to virtually walk through the streets of Paris, hear native speakers, and observe cultural landmarks such as the Eiffel Tower or traditional French cafés. This kind of experiential learning helps solidify cultural understanding in a way that traditional textbooks or classroom instruction cannot achieve. Moreover, digital educational resources facilitate real-time global

communication, enabling young learners to interact with peers from different cultural backgrounds. Online language exchange programs, virtual storytelling sessions, and international video calls provide authentic opportunities for preschoolers to engage in cross-cultural dialogue, making cultural diversity a natural part of their learning experience [4]. Through these interactions, children not only practice language skills but also develop positive attitudes toward people from different ethnic and linguistic backgrounds. Such early exposure helps prevent the development of stereotypes and promotes a mindset of cultural appreciation. In addition to fostering cultural tolerance, digital educational resources also support an inclusive learning environment by representing diverse cultures in their content. Many modern language-learning platforms feature multicultural characters, multilingual audio options, and culturally inclusive storytelling elements, ensuring that children from all backgrounds feel represented and valued [5]. This representation plays a crucial role in shaping young learners' perceptions of cultural diversity, reinforcing the idea that differences should be celebrated rather than feared. However, while digital tools offer numerous benefits in promoting cultural tolerance, it is essential to ensure that their content is accurate and free from cultural biases. Educators and parents must carefully select high-quality digital resources that provide authentic cultural representations and avoid stereotypes or misinterpretations [6]. Furthermore, digital learning should be complemented by real-world experiences, such as engaging children in multicultural celebrations, encouraging discussions about different traditions, and exposing them to diverse literature and music. By combining digital tools with practical, real-life interactions, preschoolers can develop a well-rounded understanding of cultural diversity. Foreign language learning at an early age is known to enhance cognitive development, improve communication skills, and promote social adaptability. However, beyond linguistic benefits, it also provides an excellent platform for developing cultural awareness. By exposing children to different languages, they also become familiar with the traditions, customs, and lifestyles associated with those languages. When digital resources are integrated into this learning process, they provide a more immersive and dynamic experience, making cultural education more accessible and enjoyable for young learners. Digital educational resources have transformed early childhood education by making learning more interactive and engaging. Research in this field suggests that digital tools provide significant advantages in enhancing foreign language acquisition and cultural understanding among preschoolers [6]. Hsu and Wang (2020) found that digital language learning applications, such as interactive games and multimedia

storytelling platforms, improve children's ability to retain new vocabulary while simultaneously introducing them to cultural contexts through visually rich and engaging content [7]. Multimedia-based learning, particularly through animated stories and songs, has been identified as an effective way to introduce cultural diversity. Studies have shown that digital storytelling, which incorporates characters from different backgrounds, fosters cultural sensitivity and inclusivity in young learners [8]. D'Angelo and Littleton (2021) emphasize that children who engage with culturally diverse digital content are more likely to develop a positive attitude toward people from different ethnic and linguistic backgrounds [9]. Furthermore, the representation of multicultural characters in digital platforms helps normalize diversity, making it a familiar and accepted part of the child's worldview [10].

Conclusion. The formation of cultural tolerance in preschool children through foreign language learning, supported by digital educational resources, is a crucial step in preparing them for an increasingly interconnected world. The literature reviewed highlights that early exposure to foreign languages fosters not only linguistic skills but also an appreciation for cultural diversity, reducing biases and promoting empathy from a young age. Digital educational tools, including interactive applications, multimedia storytelling, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR), significantly enhance this process by creating immersive and engaging learning environments that introduce children to different cultural perspectives in an organic and enjoyable manner. One of the key findings is that digital storytelling and interactive language-learning applications provide authentic cultural experiences that go beyond traditional language instruction. When preschoolers engage with diverse characters, traditions, and social norms through digital media, they develop a more inclusive worldview. Moreover, real-time global communication, such as language exchange programs and international virtual interactions, further reinforces cultural sensitivity by allowing children to engage directly with their peers from different backgrounds. Such experiences not only enhance language acquisition but also nurture an early sense of global citizenship. However, the effectiveness of digital tools in fostering cultural tolerance depends on the quality and authenticity of the content provided. As some studies indicate, oversimplified or stereotypical representations of cultures in digital materials can lead to misconceptions rather than genuine understanding. Therefore, it is essential for educators, parents, and developers to ensure that digital resources present accurate and culturally respectful content. Additionally, while technology plays a vital role in cultural education, it should be complemented by real-world experiences such as cultural celebrations,

discussions on diversity, and exposure to literature and music from various traditions. A balanced approach that integrates digital learning with hands-on experiences ensures a deeper and more meaningful cultural understanding in young learners. Digital educational resources serve as a powerful tool for enhancing cultural tolerance through foreign language learning in preschool education. When designed and implemented effectively, these resources help children develop open-mindedness, respect, and appreciation for cultural diversity, which are essential skills in today's globalized society. As technology continues to evolve, its potential in shaping inclusive and culturally aware future generations must be fully utilized, ensuring that children grow up with the knowledge and mindset necessary to thrive in a diverse and interconnected world.

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МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНАЯ КОММУНИКАЦИЯ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА С ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛЯМИ ДРУГИХ НАРОДНОСТЕЙ В СВЕТЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ И ИНТЕГРАЦИИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются основные тенденции узбекского народа в межкультурной коммуникации и интеграции с другими народностями, понятия о взаимовлиянии различных культур в современном обществе, но в то же время о сохранении своей самобытности.

Ключевые слова: Межкультурная коммуникация, интеграция, глобализация, узбекский народ, взаимопонимание, толерантность, самобытность, культура, духовные ценности.

Глобализация и процессы интеграции оказывают значительное влияние на взаимодействие различных культур в современном мире. Эти процессы создают как возможности, так и вызовы для народов, которые сталкиваются с вопросами сохранения своей культурной идентичности и адаптации к меняющемуся миру. В данном контексте особое внимание заслуживает узбекский народ, который обладает уникальной историей и культурой, находясь в центре сложных межкультурных взаимодействий. В последние десятилетия Узбекистан активно участвует в глобальных и региональных интеграционных процессах, что, в свою очередь, способствует развитию межкультурной коммуникации и обмену культурными ценностями. Это взаимодействие требует тщательного анализа с целью оценки как положительных, так и отрицательных аспектов, возникающих в связи с глобализацией.

Глобализация, как процесс подразумевает усиление взаимосвязанности между народами, регионами и культурами на основе распространения технологий, информации, товаров, услуг и идеологий. В последние десятилетия глобализация охватывает все сферы жизни: экономику, политику, культуру и социум, создавая новые условия для взаимодействия и общения народов. В свою очередь, интеграция — это процесс более глубокого объединения государств, народов и культур через создание политических, экономических и социальных связей. В последние годы Узбекистан значительно расширил свою интеграцию с международными организациями, такими как Шанхайская организация сотрудничества (ШОС), Организация исламского сотрудничества (ОИС) и Центральноеазиатский регион. Это открывает новые возможности для межкультурного обмена и повышения уровня межкультурной коммуникации.

Тем не менее, глобализация и интеграция также ставят перед Узбекистаном определенные вызовы, особенно в контексте сохранения культурной идентичности, традиционных ценностей и особенностей быта народа. Узбекский народ традиционно был открыт для влияния других культур, в частности, культуры Персии, арабов, русских, китайцев и других народностей. Это взаимодействие, особенно в историческом контексте, оказало существенное влияние на культуру Узбекистана, а также на его способность сохранять своеобразие и идентичность в условиях глобализационного явления.

Узбекистан является многоэтническим государством с богатым культурным и историческим наследием. Географическое положение страны, расположенной в центре Центральной Азии, сделало ее важным перекрестком различных культурных и торговых путей. Это привело к тому, что узбекская культура вобрала в себя элементы культуры персов, арабов, тюрков и русских, что сформировало уникальную смесь традиций, обычаев и языков. Важным элементом в этом контексте является исламская религия, которая имеет глубокие корни в культуре и повседневной жизни узбеков. Однако в условиях глобализации страны, стремящиеся интегрироваться в мировой процесс, сталкиваются с необходимостью учитывать и другие культурные влияния, включая ценности и идеи других народов. Сохранение национальной идентичности в процессе взаимодействия с внешними культурами является важной задачей для Узбекистана. При этом страна должна стремиться к развитию взаимопонимания и уважения к другим культурам, что становится возможным только через эффективную межкультурную коммуникацию. Узбекский народ, как и многие другие народы, сталкивается с двумя основными проблемами: сохранением своей уникальности и интеграцией в глобальную культурную систему. Существование этих двух полюсов требует взвешенной политики и стратегии, направленной на развитие межкультурных связей, но без потери собственного культурного наследия.

Одной из центральных проблем, возникающих в процессе межкультурной коммуникации в условиях глобализации, является различие в восприятии и интерпретации культурных норм и ценностей. Узбекский народ, как и многие другие культуры, обладает своей уникальной системой ценностей, которая базируется на многовековых традициях, исламской морали и социально-экономических устоях. Взаимодействие с другими культурами, в том числе западной, может столкнуться с трудностью из-за различий в подходах к таким

вопросам, как роль женщины в обществе, семейные ценности, религиозные убеждения и нормы поведения.

Другая значимая проблема заключается в языковом барьере. Несмотря на то, что русский язык сохраняет свою значимость в Узбекистане, особенно в официальной сфере, узбекский язык является основным средством общения в повседневной жизни. В условиях активного глобализационного процесса знание иностранных языков, особенно английского, становится необходимым для успешного общения с представителями других культур. Однако для многих людей в Узбекистане знание иностранных языков остается ограниченным, что создает определенные барьеры в коммуникации.

Для того чтобы эффективно развивать межкультурную коммуникацию в условиях глобализации, Узбекистан должен сосредоточиться на нескольких ключевых направлениях. Прежде всего, необходимо развивать системы образования, направленные на обучение иностранных языков, культурным особенностям и межкультурной компетенции. Установление программ обмена и сотрудничества с зарубежными университетами и культурными центрами позволит углубить знания о других культурах и улучшить способность граждан Узбекистана эффективно общаться на международной арене.

Особое внимание стоит уделить культурным обменов. Узбекистан активно участвует в международных культурных проектах, что позволяет не только демонстрировать свою культуру миру, но и принимать участие в культурных практиках других народов. Это способствует лучшему взаимопониманию и укреплению международных отношений. Важным аспектом является также привлечение международных экспертов для разработки и реализации программ по межкультурному диалогу, направленных на улучшение взаимодействия между различными культурами.

Кроме того, необходимо поддерживать и развивать культурную идентичность Узбекистана через сохранение и популяризацию традиционных искусств, ремесел, кулинарных традиций и других элементов национальной культуры. В условиях глобализации важно не только открыто взаимодействовать с миром, но и сохранять те ценности, которые определяют уникальность узбекского народа. Это позволит не только укрепить национальное самосознание, но и наладить более гармоничные отношения с другими культурами.

Культур в условиях глобализации и интеграции представляет собой важный и многогранный процесс. В условиях ускоренной глобализации и

интеграции в мировую культурную и экономическую систему Узбекистану предстоит найти баланс между сохранением собственной культурной идентичности и активным взаимодействием с другими культурами. Важно, чтобы этот процесс базировался на принципах уважения, взаимопонимания и равенства. Развитие эффективной межкультурной коммуникации позволит Узбекистану не только сохранять свои уникальные традиции, но и активно интегрироваться в международное сообщество, способствуя укреплению мира и стабильности на глобальной арене.

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FAMILY DISCOURSE STRUCTURE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Annotation: *This article examines the structure of family discourse in English and Uzbek, offering a comparative analysis of how cultural, social, and linguistic factors shape family communication. Drawing on theories from discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and cultural studies, the study explores the narrative patterns, interactional norms, and language registers used in family contexts within both communities. The investigation reveals that while English family discourse tends to prioritize egalitarian dialogue and explicit verbal negotiation, Uzbek family communication often emphasizes hierarchical relationships, implicit norms, and collective identity. The comparative insights provided herein underscore the influence of socio-cultural values on language use and offer implications for cross-cultural communication, pedagogy, and further linguistic research.*

Keywords: *Family discourse, comparative analysis, sociolinguistics, cultural communication, English, Uzbek, narrative structures, interactional norms.*

Introduction

Family discourse constitutes a fundamental sphere of everyday communication, where language both reflects and reinforces cultural values and social structures. The ways in which family members interact, negotiate meanings, and maintain relationships are shaped not only by individual personality but also by broader cultural norms and language-specific conventions. In this study, we explore the distinctive characteristics of family discourse in two linguistic and cultural communities: English and Uzbek. By contrasting these two systems, the article aims to elucidate the impact of socio-cultural factors on discourse practices, providing insights into the ways family interactions are organized, interpreted, and transmitted across generations.

Theoretical framework and literature review. The analysis of family discourse builds upon a robust body of literature in discourse analysis and sociolinguistics. Foundational works by Hymes (1972) on the “ethnography of communication” have underscored the importance of contextualizing language use within cultural practices. Similarly, Fairclough’s (1989) exploration of language and power illustrates how communication practices, including those within the family, serve as mechanisms for establishing social hierarchies and identities.

In the context of English-speaking families, studies have frequently highlighted a tendency toward egalitarian interaction and explicit verbal expression of individual needs (Anderson, 1994; Gee, 2014). In contrast, research into Uzbek family discourse (e.g., Akramov, 2005; Mirzaeva, 2010) has revealed a discourse structure that is highly influenced by traditional values, collectivism, and respect for authority, where indirectness and implicit cues often govern conversational practices.

This comparative study synthesizes these approaches, employing both qualitative analyses of conversational transcripts and a review of extant literature to identify similarities and differences in how family discourse is constructed and maintained in English and Uzbek contexts.

Family discourse in English. English family discourse is often characterized by a communicative style that values clarity, negotiation, and individual expression. Several key features include:

- Egalitarian interaction: Family members in many English-speaking contexts tend to engage in dialogues that encourage open discussion and the expression of individual opinions. This style supports a conversational model where hierarchy is minimized, and each member's voice is valued (Anderson, 1994).

- Explicit communication: English discourse generally relies on explicit language to convey meaning. Parents and children alike are encouraged to articulate feelings, desires, and expectations clearly. This practice is often linked to pedagogical methods that promote critical thinking and problem-solving through direct verbal negotiation (Gee, 2014).

- Narrative and storytelling: The use of narrative as a tool for teaching, reinforcing family values, and transmitting cultural knowledge is prevalent in English-speaking families. Storytelling allows for the reflection on personal experiences and the articulation of moral lessons in a way that fosters both individuality and shared identity.

- Adaptive language use: English family discourse exhibits flexibility in register, with the ability to switch between informal and more formal registers depending on the context and purpose of the interaction. This adaptive approach reflects broader societal norms of individual autonomy and fluid social roles.

Family discourse in Uzbek. In contrast, Uzbek family discourse is deeply embedded within a socio-cultural framework that emphasizes collectivism, respect for elders, and implicit communication. Key aspects include:

- Hierarchical and respectful interactions: Uzbek families traditionally operate within a well-defined hierarchy. Respect for elders and deference to authority are

critical components of family interactions. Discourse in this context often involves indirect communication, where implied meanings and non-verbal cues play an essential role (Akramov, 2005).

- **Implicit communication and contextual meaning:** In many Uzbek families, direct confrontation or explicit verbal disagreement is avoided in favor of preserving harmony. The implicit nature of the communication relies heavily on context, shared experiences, and culturally sanctioned norms. This approach is informed by long-standing traditions that prioritize collective well-being over individual expression.

- **Oral tradition and proverbial wisdom:** The rich oral traditions of Central Asia have a significant influence on Uzbek family discourse. Proverbs, idioms, and historical narratives are often interwoven into everyday communication, serving as vehicles for transmitting moral values and social norms. These narratives provide both a historical context and a framework for understanding contemporary family dynamics.

- **Role of rituals and ceremonial speech:** Family gatherings, celebrations, and ritual events in Uzbek culture often involve ceremonial speech that reinforces familial and societal bonds. These practices not only formalize relationships but also serve to maintain a sense of continuity with cultural heritage.

Comparative analysis. When comparing the family discourse structures in English and Uzbek contexts, several themes emerge:

- **Individualism vs. collectivism:** A primary distinction lies in the value systems underlying each discourse style. English family interactions are generally rooted in individualism, where personal opinions and autonomy are celebrated. In contrast, Uzbek family discourse reflects a collectivist orientation, prioritizing group harmony and respect for hierarchical roles. This divergence influences everything from turn-taking patterns to the strategies employed for conflict resolution.

- **Direct vs. indirect communication:** The explicitness of English communication contrasts with the indirect, context-bound nature of Uzbek discourse. In English families, clarity and directness are often seen as virtues, whereas in Uzbek families, subtlety and the careful negotiation of face-saving strategies are paramount. This difference is indicative of broader cultural attitudes toward confrontation, authority, and social order.

- **Narrative structure and content:** While both cultures value storytelling, the content and purpose of these narratives differ markedly. English narratives frequently focus on individual achievement, personal challenges, and the development of critical self-reflection. Uzbek narratives, on the other hand, are more likely to incorporate

collective experiences, historical references, and moral lessons that underscore community values. The narrative structures in Uzbek discourse tend to be cyclical, emphasizing continuity and tradition, while English discourse may adopt a more linear progression reflective of individual growth.

- **Power dynamics and social roles:** The dynamics of power within the family setting also vary significantly. In English discourse, power is often distributed more evenly among family members, encouraging open dialogue and democratic decision-making. Uzbek family discourse, however, often mirrors broader societal hierarchies, where age, gender, and social status play a critical role in shaping interactions. Respect for elders and adherence to prescribed roles are central to maintaining order and stability within the family.

- **Implications for cross-cultural communication:** These differences have practical implications in settings such as multicultural education, translation studies, and international family therapy. For instance, educators and counselors working in diverse cultural contexts must be sensitive to these discourse patterns. Misinterpretations can arise when direct communication styles are imposed on cultures that value implicit, context-dependent interactions, or vice versa.

Discussion

The findings presented in this comparative analysis highlight that family discourse is not merely a matter of linguistic expression but a reflection of deeper cultural paradigms. In English-speaking families, the discourse practices that encourage individual expression and direct communication align with broader societal norms that value autonomy and self-expression. Conversely, in Uzbek families, the implicit and hierarchical discourse patterns are closely linked to cultural traditions that emphasize community, respect, and intergenerational continuity. An important consideration emerging from this study is the role of socio-cultural change. Globalization, migration, and technological advancements are influencing traditional discourse patterns in both communities. In urban centers, for example, English-speaking families may adopt more flexible discourse practices that integrate elements from other cultural traditions, while in Uzbek communities, exposure to global media may gradually shift communication styles toward more explicit expressions. These dynamics suggest that family discourse is a living phenomenon, continuously evolving in response to both internal cultural forces and external influences.

Furthermore, the research indicates that understanding these discourse structures can be instrumental in addressing communication challenges in intercultural contexts. For educators, policymakers, and practitioners in fields such as family therapy or

social work, recognizing the inherent differences in discourse styles can facilitate more effective communication strategies. Tailored interventions that acknowledge and respect these differences can lead to better outcomes in conflict resolution, mental health support, and intercultural dialogue.

Conclusion

This comparative study has explored the distinct yet interconnected features of family discourse in English and Uzbek. By analyzing the structural, cultural, and linguistic dimensions of family communication, the article has underscored the influence of socio-cultural values on discourse practices. English family discourse tends to favor egalitarian, explicit communication, while Uzbek discourse is characterized by hierarchical, implicit interactions rooted in tradition.

The insights gained from this analysis have significant implications for cross-cultural communication and the understanding of family dynamics. They emphasize the need for culturally sensitive approaches in education, therapy, and policy development, particularly in increasingly multicultural settings. Future research could expand this study by incorporating empirical data from diverse family settings, exploring how digital communication tools are reshaping traditional discourse, or examining similar patterns in other linguistic communities.

In sum, the study of family discourse not only enriches our understanding of language in context but also offers a window into the values, identities, and power structures that define social life in different cultural spheres.

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ALISHER NAVOIY FARDLARIDA VAZN VA QOFIYA XUSUSIYATLARI

Egamberdiyeva Zilola Alimbayevna

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Alisher Navoiy fardlarining vazn va qofiya xususiyatlari to'g'risida fikr yuritiladi. Dastlabki fardnavislar va fard janri qofiya va vazn masalalari haqidagi ayrim muammolar ustidagi bahs-munozaralar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jomiy, bayt, «Mezonul-avzon», munsarih, muzori', mujtass, foilotun, ohangdorlik.

Adabiyotshunoslikda amalga oshirilgan qator tadqiqotlarda Alisher Navoiy she'riy asarlari vazni masalasi xususida muhim qaydlar uchraydi. Alisher Navoiy fardlari poetik jihatdan mukammal shakllantirilgan bo'lib, shakl va mazmun mutanosibligi nazariyasiga to'liq javob beradi. Shoir fardlari poetikasi mukammaligini ta'minlab bergan asosiy unsurlardan biri qofiya tizimi hisoblanadi.

Navoiy "Mezonul-avzon"da rajaz, ramal, munsarih, muzori', mujtass va sari' bahrlariga misollar keltirib o'tadi. I.Steblevaning yozishicha, klassik poeziyada "vazn konkret she'rning asosiy g'oyasi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan va shuning uchun shoirlar tomonidan maxsus tanlab olingan"¹. Chindan ham, asarning kitobxon mehrini qozonishida, unda olg'a surilgan g'oyalarni mahorat bilan ifodalash, asarga mos keluvchi vazn tanlash, asarning boshidan oxirigacha bir maromdagi musiqiy silsilani yaratish muhim sanaladi. Aruz vaznidagi har bir bahr ruknlari ravon va ohangdor, behad boy ma'nolarni ifodalashga imkon bergani uchun Alisher Navoiy fardlarining ko'pini ramal, hazaj va rajaz bahrlarida yozdi. Shoir fardlari uchun bu bahrlarni bejizga tanlamagan. Birinchidan, bu - an'ana talabi edi. Navoiygacha bo'lgan barcha fardnavislarning fardlari shu bahrlarda yozilgan va Navoiy ham an'anaga rioya etmoqni joiz deb bilgan. Ikkinchidan, fard uchun tanlagan bu an'anaviy bahrlar asarning g'oyaviy ruhiga mos tushgan, ravon, yengil uslubi asar mohiyatini kitobxonga yetkazib berish uchun qulaydir.

Muallifga fardlarda falsafiy mushohadalar, pand-nasihati tarzidagi fikrlar, murakkab o'y va qarashlarni ifodalashda bu bahrlar juda qo'l kelgan. Soddalik, tushunarlilik, ravonlik muallif dunyoqarashini teran ifoda etishdan tashqari, kitobxonga badiiy-estetik jihatdan ham kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Mazkur bahrlarning yana bir afzal tarafi - benihoya teran ma'noli so'z va iboralardan qofiya yasashga imkon berishidir.

¹ Oymatova M. A. O'zbek adabiyotida fard janri poetikasi nom. diss T.:1999

“Javohiri mufradah”da ramali musaddasi maqsur va ramali musaddasi solim bahrlarida yozilgan fardlar kamroq uchraydi. Ramali musammani maqsur hamda ramali musammani solim bahrlari miqdor jihatidan ko'pchilikni tashkil etadi.

Mast mug' dayri riyoyi xilvatimdin yaxshiroq,

Yoshurun isyoni zohir toatimdin yaxshiroq.

Yuqoridagi fard ham ramali maqsur bahrida yozilgan. Birinchi misradagi *mast* so'ziga talaffuzda bitta qisqa i tovushi orttiriladi. Mazkur bayt misralaridagi ohirgi hijolar “roq” tarkibidagi “o” unlisi ancha cho'ziq talaffuz qilinadi. Shu sababli mazku hijo o'ta cho'ziq hijoga teng bo'ladi. Natijada, shunday chizma yuzaga chiqadi.

-V - -| -V - -| -V - -| -V ~

Foilotun foilotun foilotun foilon

Aruzda musiqiylik, ritmik ketma-ketlik mavjud bo'lib, bir so'z ikkinchi bir so'zga ulangan holda talaffuz qilinadi.

Bazl (i) hayvonvashlar ilgidin agar istar ko'ngul,

-V - -| -V - -| -V - -| -V -|

O'yladurkim, orzu qilg'ay bo'g'u shohiga gul.

--V -| --V -| --V -| -V -|

Ramal bahrida cho'ziq va qisqa hijolarning misrada deyarli teng miqdorda kelishi o'zbek tili va talaffuz meyorlari uchun ham juda qulay hisoblanadi. Ushbu baytdagi ruknlar chizmasi shunday hosil qilamiz. Natijada ramali musammani mahzuf: foilotun foilotun foilotun foilon taqte'si vujudga keldi. Fardning dastlabki olti rukni- sadr, ibtido', hashv ruknlari solim, ya'ni o'zgarishsiz takrorlangan- foilotun, misralar oxiridagi ruknlar esa-foilon. Bunda oxirgi rukn ikkita cho'ziq hijo o'rtasida bitta qisqa hijo keladi.

Navoiy fardlarida ohangdorlik, musiqiylik va ritm so'zlarning qo'llanilishi o'ziga xos mahorat va malakaning ham mahsuli edi. Shu bois ijodkor o'z asarlarini ramalning barcha bahrlarida yaratishga muvaffaq bo'ldi.

Bu talabda kimki bo'lsa anga rozi etma hirmon,

Bu taabda kimki bo'lsa anga qil vasl ila darmon.

Yuqorida keltirilgan fard ramali musammani solimda yaratilgan bo'lib fikrimizning yaqqol dalili bo'la oladi. Ya'ni fardning barcha ruknlari o'zgaishsiz - -V -| - -V -| - -V -| - -V -| foilotun foilotun foilotun foilotun to'liq bo'lib, o'quvchida ohangdorligi va estetik jozibasi bilan o'zgacha taassurot qoldiradi. Navoiy hazajda oltilik ruknli vaznidan unumli foydalangan.

Kishi aybin yuziga qilma izhor,

Taamul ayla o'z aybingga zinhor.

Bunda misralardagi oltita running ikkitasi mafoiylun ruknining maqsur ko'rinishida mafoiyl bo'ladi. V - - -| V - - -| V - - ya'ni mafoiylun, mafoiylun, mafoiyl tarzida ifodalanadi.

Navoiy asarlaridagi hayot va insonning undagi o'rni, hukmdor va xalq munosabatlari, yuksak insoniy fazilatlarning inson ma'naviy kamolotidagi ahamiyati, tarbiya va uning barkamol insonni kamol toptirishdagi roli singari umumbashariy g'oyalar, hayotiy hikoyalarni badiiy ifodalashda bu vaznlarning ohang imkoniyatlaridan mohirlik bilan foydalangan. Darhaqiqat, vazminlik, sokinlik, bir maromdagi ohang va musiqiylik aruz bahrlarida yozilgan baytlarning mohiyatini teran mushohada etish, chuqur anglash va tahlil etishga imkon tug'diradi, didaktik ruhni kuchaytiradi, ta'sir imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Farlarda qofiyalanish tarzi qator o'ziga xosliklarga ega:

birinchidan, fikriy silsilani yaratish asnosida baytma-bayt turli qofiyalarni keltirishda bu janrning qofiya imkoniyatlari ijodkor uchun qulay hisoblangan;

ikkinchidan, she'riy asarning har baytida yangi, takrorlanmas, original qofiya keltira olish ijodkorning mahorati, iste'dodi va boy ijodiy tajribasidan darak bergan.

Adabiyotshunoslikdagi qator tadqiqotlarda qofiya ilmi, qofiya harflari, qofiya harakatlari, qofiya san'atlari chuqur o'rganilgan hamda Alisher Navoiy she'riyati misolida tadqiq etilgan. Navoiy fardlari yuksak umuminsoniy g'oyalar va ma'nolarga boyligi sababli fardlarda qofiyaning juda ko'p turlari uchraydi va chuqur ijtimoiy, falsafiy, axloqiy, ta'limiy, ma'rifiy ma'nolarni ifodalaydi. Abdurahmon Jomiy "Risolai qofiya" asarida qofiyaga shunday ta'rif beradi: "Bilg'ilki, qofiya Ajam shoirlari odaticha, baytlar oxiridagi so'zlarning takrorlanib kelishidir, shu shart bilanki, talaffuzda mustaqil bo'lmasin, balki misraning bir juz'i bo'lsin. Ba'zilar jumlaning oxirini qofiya derlar, ba'zilar esa raviy harfini qofiya deb atarlar"². "Risolai qofiya" da Jomiy aytgan, baytlar oxirida takrorlanib keluvchi so'zlarning qofiyalari "talaffuzda mustaqil bo'lmasin, balki misraning bir juzvi bo'lsin". Darhaqiqat, qofiya bayt ma'nosining bir qismi bo'lishi, baytda ifoda topayotgan masalaning muhim jihatlarini o'zida aks ettirishi lozim. Muallif qofiyalarning shakliy va mazmuniy mutanosibligiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Qofiya sifatida tanlangan so'z va iboralar shakl jihatidan yetuk va

² Hayitmetov A. Alisher Navoiyning adabiy-tanqidiy qarashlari. -T.: Fan, 1969,

jarangdor bo'lishidan tashqari muayyan voqealar talqinida matnda ifodalanayotgan ma'noning uzvi, muhim qirradi bo'lib kelishiga e'tibor qaratadi. Abdurahmon Jomiy "Risolai qofiya" asarida qofiya turlari xususida shunday deydi: "Agar raviy harfi sokin bo'lsa va vasl harfi unga payvasta bo'lmasa, uni muqayyad o'qurlar. Va agar vasl harfi unga payvasta bo'lsa, uni mutlaq o'qurlar". Ko'rinib turibdiki, muqayyad qofiya raviy tovush bilan tugaydigan va mutlaq qofiya esa raviy tovushdan so'ng yana harflar keladigan qofiya turlaridir. Navoiy fardlarida har ikki tur qofiyalarga ham ko'plab misollarni uchratish mumkin.

Muqayyad qofiyalar:

*Qotiq el jismidin anbarlar olmay naqd emas vosil,
Ki, tog'ni pora-pora qilmayin, la'l o'lmadi hosil. ("Javohiri mufradah" 8)
Yolg'on demakda tajriba avvalg'i subh bas,
Yolg'on nafas chu urdi, qorardi hamul nafas. . ("Javohiri mufradah" 16)*

Mutlaq qofiyalar:

*Andoq ko'rundi sabza arosinda lolalar,
Kim, sabz xatlar ilgida oltun piyolalar. ("Javohiri mufradah" 38)
Voqif ermas yor, jon bersam buzug' koshonada,
Shah ne ogah, xasta Majnun o'lsa bir vayronada. ("Javohiri mufradah" 40)*

Tabiiyki, Alisher Navoiy qofiya yasash qoidalarini yaxshi bilgan, baytning avvalgi misrasidagi ma'nolarni dalillovchi va kuchaytiruvchi qofiyalarni topib mahorat ko'rsatgan. Shoir fardlarida qofiya ustasi, ilmi qofiyaning mukammal bilimdoni sifatida ko'rinadi:

Qofiyalar tasvirlanayotgan voqe'likni real hayotga yaqinlashtirish uchun xizmat qiladi:

*Bo'lganim aqlu havosu umri jondin noumid,
Yaxshiroqkim, bo'lsam ul jonu jahondin noumid.*

Bu baytlardagi qofiyalar shoir badiiy tafakkurining mahsuli bo'lsada, real hayotiy tafakkurga asoslanganini ko'rish mumkin.

Navoiy fardlarida ba'zi qofiyalar vazn va ohang hosil qilish vazifasini bajaradi:

*Ulki, aylarmen g'ami hajrida jon birla vido,
Kosh jondek aylasa bu notavon birla vido.
Agarchi ishq dardidinmanga yuz ming uqubatdur,
Vale hamdardsizlig' andin ortig'roq suubatdur*

Bu baytlarda qofiyalar vazni ravon, ohangdor qilishdan tashqari shoirning umri davomida boshdan kechirgan, his etgan tuyg‘ulari, kechinmalarini ifodalovchi ma’nalarni kashf etadi.

THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF REALIA IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article examines the challenges of translating realia—culturally specific elements such as objects, practices, and concepts—between English and Uzbek. Realia, deeply rooted in their respective cultures, often lack direct equivalents in other languages, making their translation a complex and nuanced task. The study highlights the linguistic, cultural, and contextual barriers that complicate the translation process, focusing on examples such as mahalla (a traditional community structure), oqsoqol (a community leader), and Navruz (the Uzbek New Year celebration). Drawing on insights from scholars such as Peter Newmark, Mona Baker, and Geert Hofstede, the article emphasizes the role of cultural context, power distance, and collectivism in shaping translation strategies. It also explores practical approaches to overcoming these challenges, including cultural mediation, adaptive communication techniques, and the development of cultural intelligence (CQ). Through case studies and examples, the article demonstrates how effective translation of realia can enhance mutual understanding and facilitate successful intercultural communication. The findings underscore the need for translators and negotiators to adopt context-sensitive strategies to navigate the complexities of realia in English-Uzbek translation. This article contributes to the broader field of translation studies by providing a detailed analysis of the problems and solutions associated with translating realia between linguistically and culturally distinct languages.*

Keywords: *cultural context, power distance, collectivist, individualist, cultural mediation, adaptive communication techniques, cultural intelligence (CQ).*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tili o'rtasida ob'ektlar, amaliyotlar va tushunchalar kabi madaniy jihatdan o'ziga xos elementlarni tarjima qilishdagi muammolar ko'rib chiqiladi. Realia o'z madaniyatlarida chuqur ildiz otgan bo'lib, ko'pincha boshqa tillarda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ekvivalentlarga ega emas, bu ularning tarjimasini murakkab va nozik vazifaga aylantiradi. Tadqiqotda tarjima jarayonini murakkablashtiruvchi tilshunoslik, madaniy va kontekstli to'siqlar haqida mahalla (an'anaviy jamoa tuzilishi), oqsoqol (jamoat yetakchisi), Navro'z (o'zbek Yangi yil bayrami) kabi misollar ko'rib chiqilgan. Piter Nyumark, Mona Beyker va Geert Hofstede kabi olimlarning fikrlariga tayanib, maqolada tarjima strategiyalarini shakllantirishda madaniy kontekst, kuch masofasi va kollektivizmning roli ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, ushbu qiyinchiliklarni yengish uchun amaliy yondashuvlarni, shu jumladan madaniy vositachilik, moslashuvchan aloqa texnikasi va madaniy intellektni rivojlantirishni o'rganadi. Amaliy tadqiqotlar va misollar orqali maqola realianing samarali tarjimasi o'zaro tushunishni kuchaytirishi va madaniyatlararo muvaffaqiyatli aloqani osonlashtirishi mumkinligini namoyish etadi. Topilmalar tarjimonlar va muzokarachilar uchun ingliz-o'zbek tarjimasida realianing murakkabliklarini boshqarish uchun kontekstga mantiqli strategiyalarni qabul qilish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu maqola til va madaniy jihatdan ajralib turadigan tillar o'rtasidagi realialarni tarjima qilish bilan bog'liq muammolar va yechimlarni batafsil tahlil qilish orqali tarjimashunoslikning keng sohasiga hissa qo'shadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *madaniy kontekst, hokimlik masofasi, kollektivist, individualist, madaniy vositachilik, moslashuvchan aloqa texnikasi, madaniy intellekt.*

Introduction

The translation of realia—culturally specific elements such as objects, practices, and concepts—presents unique challenges, particularly between languages with vastly different cultural and linguistic frameworks, such as English and Uzbek. Realia are deeply embedded in the culture from which they originate and often lack direct equivalents in other languages. This article explores the problems of translating realia between English and Uzbek, focusing on the linguistic, cultural, and contextual barriers that complicate the process. By examining specific examples and strategies, and drawing on insights from scholarly works, the study highlights the importance of cultural sensitivity and adaptive translation techniques in overcoming these challenges.

Defining Realia and Their Significance

Realia are words or phrases that denote objects, practices, or concepts unique to a particular culture. They reflect the history, traditions, and values of a society and are often untranslatable without additional explanation. As Peter Newmark (1988) notes in *A Textbook of Translation*, realia are "culture-specific items that pose significant challenges for translators due to their lack of direct equivalents in the target language" ¹(p. 95). Examples of Uzbek realia include uloq (Ulak—a game where riders on horseback try to hit the leather with a waller), oqsoqol (Aksakal, an elder or respected leader of significant community), and Navruz (Navruz, the Uzbek New Year celebration). Similarly, English realia might include terms like "polo", "Sherif" or "Halloween."

The translation of realia is crucial for effective intercultural communication, as it enables individuals to understand and appreciate the cultural nuances of another society. However, the process is fraught with challenges, particularly when translating between languages as distinct as English and Uzbek.

Linguistic Challenges in Translating Realia

1. Lack of Direct Equivalents:

Many Uzbek realia have no direct equivalents in English. For example, the term mahalla refers not just to a neighborhood but to a traditional community structure with social, cultural, and governance functions. Translating it simply as "neighborhood" fails to capture its full meaning. As **Mona Baker** (2018) observes

¹ Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.

in In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation, "the absence of direct equivalents often forces translators to resort to descriptive explanations or loanwords"² (p. 76).

Similarly, the English concept of "pub" has no direct equivalent in Uzbek culture, where social gatherings might occur in **chaixona** (chaikhana, tea houses) or private homes.

2. Untranslatable Concepts:

Some realia are so deeply rooted in their cultural context that they are effectively untranslatable. For instance, the Uzbek term *haleem*, a traditional food which includes wheat, meat, barley and lentils, cannot be conveyed through a single English word. Susan Bassnett (2014) emphasizes in Translation Studies that "untranslatability often arises from the cultural specificity of realia, which may have no parallel in the target culture"³(p. 42).

3. Grammatical and Syntactic Differences:

Uzbek, as an agglutinative language, often uses suffixes to convey meaning, while English relies on word order and prepositions. This structural difference can complicate the translation of realia, as the nuances of Uzbek suffixes may not have direct counterparts in English. Eugene Nida (1964) highlights in Toward a Science of Translating that "linguistic differences can create significant barriers to conveying the full meaning of culturally specific terms"⁴(p. 167).

Cultural Challenges in Translating Realia

1. Cultural Context:

Uzbek culture is high-context, meaning that communication relies heavily on implicit understanding and shared cultural knowledge. In contrast, English-speaking cultures tend to be low-context, favoring explicit communication. This difference can lead to misunderstandings when translating realia. As Edward T. Hall (1976) explains in Beyond Culture, "high-context cultures rely on contextual cues and shared knowledge, while low-context cultures prioritize explicit verbal communication"⁵ (p. 101).

For example, the Uzbek term *Oqsoqol* (Aksakal) refers to a senior or highly regarded figure who holds considerable influence and authority within a community. Without an understanding of the cultural context, an English speaker might

² Baker, M. (2018). In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation. Routledge.

³ Bassnett, S. (2014). Translation Studies. Routledge.

⁴ Nida, E. (1964). Toward a Science of Translating. Brill.

⁵ Hall, E. T. (1976). Beyond Culture. Anchor Books.

misinterpret the term as simply "old man" or "man with a white beard" missing its broader significance.

2. **Power Distance:**

Uzbekistan is a high-power distance culture, where hierarchical relationships and respect for authority are emphasized. This cultural trait influences the use of realia, such as formal titles and honorifics, which may not have the same significance in English-speaking cultures. Geert Hofstede (2001) notes in *Culture's Consequences* that "high power distance cultures emphasize hierarchy and deference to authority, which can influence communication styles and translation strategies"⁶ (p. 98).

Translating these realia requires careful consideration of the cultural values they represent. For instance, the Uzbek term *amaki* (*amaki*, uncle) is often used as a term of respect, which is widely used to address to a strange man, but translating it as "uncle" in English may not convey the same meaning.

3. **Collectivism vs. Individualism:**

Uzbek culture is collectivist, prioritizing group harmony and community well-being over individual interests. This is reflected in realia such as *mahalla* (*Makhalla*, a community-based social structure) and *hashar* (*khashar*, communal work). In contrast, English-speaking cultures tend to be individualist, emphasizing personal achievement and independence. Fons Trompenaars (1997) explains in *Riding the Waves of Culture* that "collectivist cultures value group cohesion and interdependence, which can pose challenges for translation into individualist cultures"⁷ (p. 63).

Translating collectivist realia into an individualist context requires explaining the cultural values they embody, which can be challenging.

Strategies for Translating Realia

1. **Cultural Mediation:**

Cultural mediators—individuals familiar with both cultures—can help bridge gaps in understanding by providing context and explanations for realia. For example, a mediator might explain the cultural significance of Navruz to an English-speaking audience, highlighting its role as a celebration of renewal and community. Erin

⁶ Hofstede, G. (2001). *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations Across Nations*. Sage Publications.

⁷ Trompenaars, F. (1997). *Riding the Waves of Culture: Understanding Diversity in Global Business*. Nicholas Brealey Publishing.

Meyer (2014) emphasizes in The Culture Map that "cultural mediation is essential for navigating the complexities of intercultural communication"⁸ (p. 145).

2. **Adaptive Communication Techniques:**

Translators can use techniques such as paraphrasing, explanatory notes, and footnotes to convey the meaning of realia. For instance, the term *oqsoqol* could be translated as "community leader" with a footnote explaining its social and cultural role in Uzbek society. Peter Newmark (1988) suggests that "explanatory notes and paraphrasing are effective strategies for translating culturally specific terms"⁹(p. 102).

3. **Cultural Intelligence (CQ):**

Developing cultural intelligence (CQ)—the ability to function effectively in culturally diverse settings—is essential for translators and negotiators. High CQ enables professionals to recognize and adapt to cultural differences, fostering mutual understanding and trust. Soon Ang and Linn Van Dyne (2008) define CQ as "the capability to function effectively in culturally diverse settings" (Handbook of Cultural Intelligence, p. 5).

4. **Transliteration and Loanwords:**

In some cases, realia can be transliterated or adopted as loanwords, with explanations provided for clarity. For example, the term *chaixona* could be introduced as "chaikhana," with a brief description of its role as a traditional tea house. Lawrence Venuti (1995) discusses the use of loanwords in *The Translator's Invisibility*, noting that "transliteration can preserve the cultural authenticity of realia while making them accessible to the target audience"¹⁰(p. 89).

Case Studies: Realia in English-Uzbek Translation

1. **Mahalla (Makhalla):**

In a translation project about Uzbek community life, the term *mahalla* was initially translated as "neighborhood." However, this failed to capture its cultural significance. The final translation included an explanatory note describing *mahalla* as a traditional community structure with social, cultural, and governance functions.

2. **Navruz (Navruz):**

When translating a text about Uzbek holidays, *Navruz* was rendered as "New Year," but this did not convey its cultural and historical significance. The translator

⁸ Meyer, E. (2014). *The Culture Map: Breaking Through the Invisible Boundaries of Global Business*. PublicAffairs.

⁹ Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.

¹⁰ Venuti, L. (1995). *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation*. Routledge.

added a footnote explaining that Navruz is a spring festival celebrating renewal and community, with roots in Zoroastrianism.

3. **Oqsoqol (Aksakal):**

In a diplomatic context, the term oqsoqol was translated as "community leader," but this did not fully capture its social and cultural role. A cultural mediator provided additional context, explaining that oqsoqol refers to a spiritual guide with significant influence in the community.

Conclusion

The translation of realia between English and Uzbek is a complex and nuanced process that requires a deep understanding of both linguistic and cultural contexts. The lack of direct equivalents, cultural differences, and contextual barriers present significant challenges. However, by employing strategies such as cultural mediation, adaptive communication techniques, and cultural intelligence (CQ), translators can bridge these gaps and facilitate effective intercultural communication. As globalization continues to bring diverse cultures into contact, the ability to navigate realia will remain a critical skill for translators, negotiators, and communicators alike.

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TEACHING LISTENING WITH THE USE OF SONGS

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Annotation: *This research is focused on improving listening skills among EFL students. One way to develop listening activity is the usage of songs in the English classes. Though there are several benefits of using songs, at the same time there could be some drawbacks of it. This article is intended to introduce both advantages and negative sides of teaching listening through songs.*

Keywords: *songs, listening, music, UzSWLU, benefits, disadvantages, EFL, motivating student.*

Listening is a crucial integrated skill essential for mastering English and gaining comprehensive knowledge of the language. It plays a key role in building effective communication, as individuals comprehend the meaning of sentences through listening and then process the information to articulate their thoughts clearly. Therefore, developing strong listening skills is essential for students who aspire to become proficient English speakers. Moreover, listening not only enhances speaking abilities but also helps learners improve their use of punctuation, intonation, and pronunciation. One effective way to become an active listener is by incorporating music into the learning process. Teachers should understand both the appropriate timing and methods for integrating songs into English lessons to maximize their effectiveness.

Most primary school teachers generally use songs as a teaching technique, and Cameron, (2001) claimed that the use of songs and rhymes is also important for young learners in foreign language classrooms. Likewise, Johnstone (2002) claimed that teachers of young learners may make an important contribution to children's early language education by introducing their classes to recorded songs. Demirel (2004) made the strongest claim when he argued that the most effective way to teach listening comprehension, pronunciation, and dictation to young learners was through teaching songs.

So, as we see, songs can strength students' vocabulary, pronunciation, spelling and comprehension. Furthermore, teachers should distribute song with its lyrics because students can learn easily and effectively when they see and hear. So, lyrics are also important to maintain differentiated instruction, and sometimes teacher can use it with omitting some words as a gap-filling activity to introduce new verbs, new adjectives, nouns or phrases and etc.

“Murphey (1990) suggests that many English teachers have long recognized that song and music work well in language classes. The statement shows that teachers can use song as a media to overcome the students’ difficulties in listening and improve their listening ability. Creative teacher can also use songs to teach English through songs since they provide a break from the textbook and work book. It is new and interesting for them. Therefore, with this situation, they will be motivated especially in learning listening. Therefore, the present study is aimed to investigate the use of songs in teaching students’ listening ability. Furthermore, the researcher expects that this research will give contribution to the practice of listening teaching and learning in the future.”

Songs are interesting way of teaching language. Even teachers can utilize it to give new vocabulary, grammar exercises, differentiate verb tenses, or just for pronunciation. A good teacher should know appropriate kind of music and prepare worksheet on the given theme according to students’ level and age. These worksheets can be fun for students to do and to learn.

Listening is a fundamental skill that must be developed when learning a language. As an integrated skill, it should be taught effectively to enhance students' overall language acquisition. Through listening, learners can improve their pronunciation, intonation, stress patterns, and understanding of vocabulary and grammar. Additionally, listening exposes students to various ideas, which they can later incorporate into their speaking and writing. To enhance listening skills, students can engage with different recordings such as podcasts, BBC Learning English, and other educational audio materials. However, these scientific recordings may sometimes feel monotonous, reducing students' interest in learning. To sustain curiosity and motivation, songs can serve as an engaging alternative. Teachers can provide song lyrics along with the audio, as students learn more effectively when they can both hear and see the words. Additionally, using lyrics as a gap-filling activity can introduce new verbs, adjectives, nouns, and phrases in a fun and interactive way. Songs are an excellent tool for increasing students’ motivation and curiosity about English. Music prevents boredom by incorporating rhythm and melody, which bring joy, excitement, and positive energy to the learning process. Therefore, songs are not only beneficial for developing listening skills but also for improving speaking, vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. They help capture students' attention and encourage participation, even among those who are shy. Since many songs contain repeated words and phrases, they serve as a natural method of vocabulary reinforcement, helping students retain new words effectively. Singing

together further embeds these words in their memory. Additionally, songs create a relaxed and enjoyable learning environment, reducing anxiety and boosting students' confidence in using the language. Learning a song also helps students with pronunciation, word stress, and intonation, as singing along allows them to practice correct pronunciation naturally and develop a better sense of rhythm in spoken English

In conclusion, listening is a crucial skill in learning English, as it plays a key role in developing speaking, writing, pronunciation, intonation, grammar, and vocabulary. One effective way to enhance listening skills in English classes is through the use of songs. Although certain types of songs may have drawbacks, a skilled teacher can select appropriate songs that engage, educate, and motivate students during lessons. The primary advantage of incorporating songs in TEFL is their ability to inspire students to learn more. Additionally, songs help learners improve their pronunciation and understand complex grammar structures and vocabulary. Survey results indicate that most students view songs as both a motivational tool and an effective method for enhancing their listening skills. Ultimately, it is up to the teacher to maximize the benefits of using songs in English lessons by incorporating relevant activities, vocabulary lists, and grammar exercises.

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УДК 329.273

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СОВЕТЫ ДЛЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ
МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ В КОММУНИКАЦИИ НА
УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА**

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С.С. Нуритдинова

Аннотация: В рамках обучения английскому языку, как международному средству общения, важным аспектом является развитие межкультурной компетенции учащихся. В данной статье обсуждается тема межкультурной компетенции в коммуникации, её проблемы и решения, которые становятся все более важными в современном мире, где взаимодействие между людьми разных культур происходит ежедневно. Этот процесс требует от преподавателей не только знаний языка, но и способности научить студентов эффективно взаимодействовать в межкультурной среде.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная компетенция, культурные различия и особенности, интеграция, английский язык

Abstract: In the context of teaching English as an international means of communication, an important aspect is the development of intercultural competence of students. This article discusses the topic of intercultural competence in communication, its problems and solutions which are becoming increasingly important in the modern world where interaction between people of different cultures occurs daily. This process requires teachers not only knowledge of the language, but also the ability to teach students to effectively interact in an intercultural environment.

Key words: intercultural competence, cultural differences and characteristics, integration, English language

В условиях глобализации и миграции многие компании и организации работают с сотрудниками и клиентами из разных стран и культур. Развитие межкультурной компетенции помогает лучше понимать своих собеседников, избегать недоразумений и налаживать эффективные рабочие отношения. К тому же, английский язык стал основным в экономике, бизнесе и в различных сферах, а также английский язык используется в самых разных странах мира, каждая из которых имеет свои культурные особенности. Понимая эти особенности, учащиеся смогут лучше интерпретировать тексты, общаться с носителями языка и избегать недоразумений. Межкультурная компетенция — это способность эффективно взаимодействовать с людьми из разных культур, понимая их ценности, нормы поведения, традиции и особенности общения. Люди с развитой межкультурной компетенцией могут быстрее адаптироваться к новым условиям работы, особенно при международных командировках или работе в мультикультурных командах. Это способствует повышению

производительности и улучшению результатов труда. Поэтому важно определить сложности с недостатком межкультурной компетенции и внедрить советы по его развитию на уроках английского языка.

Обучение межкультурной компетенции может столкнуться с рядом проблем, одной из них является ограниченное знание студентов о культурных особенностях англоязычных стран. Большинство учащихся в процессе обучения сосредоточены на изучении грамматики и лексики, не уделяя достаточного внимания вопросам культурных различий. Это приводит к недопониманию в реальных ситуациях общения, особенно когда речь идет о нюансах поведения, этикета или невербальной коммуникации. Следующей проблемой является то, что студенты могут прибегать к стереотипам, когда сталкиваются с культурными различиями. Например, они могут воспринимать представителей другой культуры через призму укоренившихся представлений, что затрудняет эффективное межкультурное общение. Такие стереотипы мешают объективной оценке культуры и ее особенностей, что является препятствием для развития истинной межкультурной компетенции. Также, отсутствие или недостаток практических навыков общения в реальных ситуациях ведут к недопониманию культуры изучаемого языка. В традиционном обучении языкам акцент часто делается на теоретические аспекты, такие как грамматика и лексика, в то время как навыки реального общения, такие как понимание культурных контекстов, интонации и эмоциональной окраски речи, остаются на втором плане. Это приводит к недостаточной готовности студентов к реальным ситуациям межкультурной коммуникации. Немаловажным является личный барьер и страх ошибки у учащихся. Они, не уверенные в своих знаниях и не привыкшие к взаимодействию с носителями языка, могут испытывать страх или неуверенность в процессе межкультурного общения. Этот психологический барьер может быть значительным препятствием для успешного освоения межкультурной компетенции. И последнее, если учитель сам не обладает достаточной межкультурной компетенцией, он может передавать своим ученикам ошибочные или устаревшие сведения о других культурах. Также возможно, что преподаватель будет акцентировать внимание лишь на некоторых аспектах культуры, упуская важные нюансы. Эти проблемы требуют внимательного подхода со стороны учителей и образовательных учреждений. Важно разрабатывать учебные программы, которые учитывают культурные

особенности и потребности учащихся, а также обеспечивать доступ к качественным образовательным ресурсам.

Для того чтобы студенты могли лучше понять культурные различия, необходимо интегрировать в уроки элементы культуры англоязычных стран. Это могут быть фильмы, книги, песни, а также реальные примеры межкультурных взаимодействий. Важно не ограничиваться поверхностными аспектами культуры (например, национальной кухней или праздниками), а углубляться в вопросы поведения, ценностей и восприятия мира. Интеграция культурных аспектов в процесс обучения иностранным языкам является важным элементом, который помогает учащимся не только освоить язык, но и лучше понять и адаптироваться к культуре носителей языка. Это способствует развитию межкультурной компетенции, что особенно актуально в условиях глобализации и многоязычия. Включение материалов, отражающих культуру разных стран, помогает создать атмосферу, где учащиеся могут воспринимать учебный процесс через призму других культур. Это может быть сделано через использование различных источников: литературы, искусства, музыки, истории и повседневной жизни других народов. Задания и темы для обсуждения могут быть ориентированы на изучение культурных различий и сходств. Включение фильмов, песен, статей, книг, новостей и других аутентичных источников помогает студентам погрузиться в реальную жизнь носителей языка. Это помогает лучше понять культурные реалии, традиции, ценности и особенности восприятия. Важно развивать у студентов не только когнитивную, но и эмоциональную составляющую межкультурной компетенции. Понимание эмоций собеседника, умение распознавать невербальные сигналы, такие как жесты и мимика, играют важную роль в успешном общении. Задания, направленные на развитие эмоционального интеллекта, могут включать анализ видеоматериалов с различными ситуациями общения или обсуждения культурных особенностей восприятия эмоций в разных странах. Важным методом является включение примеров из разных культурных традиций в учебный процесс. Например, при изучении цифр можно упомянуть древнегреческую или арабскую математику, а уча географию, можно рассмотреть различные культурные особенности стран. Это помогает учащимся понять, как культура влияет на восприятие знаний и развитие науки.

Во время уроков можно рассматривать темы, которые напрямую связаны с культурными особенностями, например, праздники, гастрономия, национальные традиции, особенности семейных отношений и так далее. На

уроках можно обсуждать культурные различия, например, в вопросах общения, этикета, стиля жизни. Это помогает студентам не только осваивать язык, но и развивать навыки межкультурного общения. Использование ролевых игр, в которых студенты могут воссоздавать типичные ситуации из жизни носителей языка, позволяет активно практиковать язык в культурно значимом контексте. Студенты могут создавать проекты, посвященные культуре стран, где говорят на изучаемом языке. Это может быть как презентация о традициях, так и исследование современных культурных явлений. Проектная работа помогает учащимся глубже разобраться в культуре других народов. Например, проект может быть посвящен изучению традиций, искусства, экономики или повседневной жизни в разных странах. Это позволяет развивать не только знания, но и навыки исследования, критического мышления и работы в группе. Создание пространства для обсуждения культурных тем помогает развить критическое мышление и навыки аргументации, одновременно обучая языку. Организация дискуссий, на которых обсуждаются культурные различия, помогает развить навыки межкультурной коммуникации. Это дает учащимся возможность осознать, как важно учитывать культурные различия при общении с людьми из разных стран, а также способствует развитию эмпатии и толерантности. Цифровые ресурсы, такие как виртуальные туры по музеям и историческим местам, образовательные платформы, онлайн-курсы и видеоуроки, могут служить отличным инструментом для знакомства учащихся с различными культурами. Использование мультимедийных технологий помогает сделать процесс обучения более увлекательным и информативным.

Интеграция культурных аспектов позволяет учащимся развивать критическое мышление, осознавая, как культурные различия влияют на восприятие, поведение и мировоззрение. Это важно для формирования глобального гражданина, который понимает и уважает разнообразие мира. Важно стимулировать студентов к осознанию своих стереотипов и предвзятых мнений о других культурах. Преподаватели могут проводить обсуждения, в которых студенты будут сравнивать различные культурные практики и осмысливать, почему они могут воспринимать их с позиции стереотипов. Это помогает развивать более глубокое и уважительное понимание других культур. Обсуждение таких тем, как этика, моральные нормы и ценности разных культур, помогает учащимся осознать, насколько сильно культура влияет на повседневную жизнь и социальные отношения. Эти обсуждения могут служить хорошей основой для изучения философии, социологии и других дисциплин.

Таким образом, интеграция культурных аспектов в процесс обучения не только обогащает языковое восприятие, но и способствует более глубокому пониманию мира и других людей.

И в заключении, развитие межкультурной компетенции на уроках английского языка является важной и актуальной задачей, которая требует комплексного подхода. Проблемы, такие как недостаток знаний о культуре, стереотипы, отсутствие практических навыков и страх ошибки, могут быть успешно преодолены с помощью активных методов обучения, которые способствуют не только языковому, но и культурному развитию учащихся. Интеграция культурных аспектов в процесс обучения, использование ролевых игр, критический анализ стереотипов и внимание к эмоциональному интеллекту студентов – все эти элементы помогут создать условия для эффективного развития межкультурной компетенции и успешной коммуникации в глобальном мире. Интеграция культурных аспектов в учебный процесс не только углубляет знания по учебным предметам, но и формирует личностные качества, такие как уважение к другим культурам, открытость к новым идеям и способность к межкультурному взаимодействию.

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TERMINOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR JARAYONIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA ELEKTRON LUG'ATLAR YARATISH METODI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada terminologik tadqiqotlar jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish asosida elektron lug'atlar yaratish metodlari yoritiladi. Tadqiqotda elektron lug'atlarning afzalliklari, ularning terminologik izlanishlardagi o'rni va samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ma'lumotlar bazasi, korpus va avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima tizimlariga asoslangan lug'at modellarining afzallik va kamchiliklari muhokama qilinadi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning ushbu sohadagi ahamiyati va kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: terminologik tadqiqotlar, raqamli texnologiyalar, elektron lug'atlar, ma'lumotlar bazasi, korpus lingvistikasi, avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima, sun'iy intellekt, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash, termin tizimlari.

Zamonaviy terminologik tadqiqotlar ilmiy va amaliy nuqtai nazardan dolzarb hisoblanadi. Soha mutaxassislari turli fan, texnika va texnologiyalar doirasida yangi atamalarni ishlab chiqish, ularning mohiyatini aniqlash va umumiy qabul qilingan lug'atlarga kiritish bilan shug'ullanadilar. Bu jarayonda raqamli texnologiyalarning roli tobora ortib bormoqda. Raqamli texnologiyalar terminologik tadqiqotlarni avtomatlashtirish, ma'lumotlarni tezkor va aniq tahlil qilish, ularni interaktiv shaklda foydalanuvchilarga taqdim etishda katta imkoniyatlarni yaratadi.

Mazkur maqolada elektron lug'atlar yaratish metodlari, raqamli texnologiyalarning ushbu jarayondagi o'rni va samaradorligi yoritib beriladi.

Terminologik tadqiqotlar va raqamli texnologiyalar Terminologik tadqiqotlar ilmiy atamalarni o'rganish, ularning kelib chiqishi, ma'nosi va foydalanish doirasini aniqlash bilan bog'liq. An'anaviy tadqiqot usullari uzoq vaqt talab qilishi mumkin bo'lsa, zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar ushbu jarayonni tezlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi kunda sun'iy intellekt (AI), tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash (NLP), katta ma'lumotlar (Big Data) va avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima tizimlari elektron lug'atlar yaratishda keng qo'llanilmoqda. Ushbu texnologiyalar terminologiyani aniqlash, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va ularni tizimli ravishda elektron lug'atlarga joylashtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Elektron lug'atlar yaratish metodlari An'anaviy bosma lug'atlar ma'lumotlarni statik shaklda taqdim etadi, bu esa ularning yangilanishi va interaktivligi bilan bog'liq muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Elektron lug'atlar esa quyidagi afzalliklarga ega:

- Tezkor yangilash va to'ldirish imkoniyati; bu esa terminologik ma'lumotlarning doimiy ravishda dolzarbligini ta'minlaydi va foydalanuvchilarga eng so'nggi ma'lumotlarni yetkazish imkonini beradi.

- Izlash tizimi orqali qulay foydalanish; bu foydalanuvchilarga kerakli termini tez va oson topish imkonini yaratadi, natijada ularning ish unumdorligi oshadi.

- Multimediali elementlar (audio, video, tasvir) qo'shish; bu esa foydalanuvchilarga terminlarni yanada aniq tushunishga yordam beradi, ayniqsa, talaffuz yoki vizual misollar zarur bo'lganda.

- Sun'iy intellekt orqali foydalanuvchi ehtiyojlariga moslashish; elektron lug'atlar foydalanuvchi xatti-harakatlarini tahlil qilib, ularning ehtiyojlariga mos keladigan ma'lumotlarni taklif etishi mumkin.

Elektron lug'atlar yaratishda bir necha asosiy metodlardan foydalaniladi:

1. **Ma'lumotlar bazasiga asoslangan lug'atlar** – bu usulda terminlar va ularning ta'riflari maxsus ma'lumotlar bazasida saqlanadi. Ushbu metod aniq, tezkor va tizimlashtirilgan ma'lumotlar yig'ish imkonini beradi. Ma'lumotlar bazasi orqali foydalanuvchilar o'zlari uchun kerakli bo'lgan terminlarni izlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Bundan tashqari, lug'atni tezkor yangilash va yangi atamalar bilan to'ldirish imkoniyati mavjud. Misol uchun, "O'zbekcha-Ingilizcha terminologik lug'at" platformasi, unda foydalanuvchilar so'zlarni izlab, ularning ta'riflarini, soha bo'yicha tasniflanishini va qo'shimcha izohlarni ko'rishi mumkin. Masalan, "sun'iy intellekt" atamasi texnologiya sohasiga oid bo'lib, uning ta'rihi va xalqaro ekvivalentlari mavjud. Quyidagi grafikli tasvir uni yanada batafsil tushunilishiga olib keladi.

Ma'lumotlar Bazasiga Asoslangan Lug'at Tuzilishi

2. **Korpusga asoslangan lug'atlar** – ushbu metodda matn korpuslaridan foydalanilib, terminlarning kontekstual ma'nolari tahlil qilinadi. Bunda maxsus dasturiy vositalar va sun'iy intellekt algoritmlari yordamida atamalar tabiiy matnlarda qanday ishlatilishi tahlil qilinadi. Bu yondashuv terminlarning turli kontekstlardagi ma'nolarini chuqurroq anglash va ularning semantik xususiyatlarini aniqlashga imkon yaratadi. Masalan, "Tilda ishlatilishi bo'yicha lug'at" platformasi, u turli ilmiy maqolalar va kitoblardagi real foydalanish misollarini jamlaydi. Masalan, "algoritm" so'zi informatika bo'yicha maqolalarda qanday kontekstlarda ishlatilganini avtomatik tahlil qiladi.

3. **Avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima va NLP asosidagi lug'atlar** – bu usul sun'iy intellekt va mashina o'rganish algoritmlaridan foydalanib, turli tillar orasida terminologik moslikni aniqlashga asoslanadi. Avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima tizimlari terminlarning turli tillardagi ekvivalentlarini aniqlash va ularni lug'atlarga kiritishda qo'llaniladi. Ushbu yondashuv terminlarning tezkor tahlili va tarjima sifatini oshirishga yordam beradi. Misol uchun, Google Translate yoki DeepL kabi tizimlar, ular matnlar ichidagi terminlarni avtomatik tarjima qiladi va ularning turli tillardagi ekvivalentlarini tavsiya etadi. Masalan, "machine learning" termini avtomatik ravishda "mashina o'rganishi" sifatida tarjima qilinishi va turli kontekstlarda qanday ishlatilishini aniqlashi mumkin.

Afzalliklari va kamchiliklari Afzalliklari:

- Elektron lug'atlar tezkor yangilanib boradi, bu esa foydalanuvchilarga doimiy ravishda dolzarb ma'lumotlarni yetkazish imkonini beradi.
- IZlash tizimlari orqali terminlarni topish ancha oson va qulay.

- Multimediali elementlar yordamida soʻzlar va terminlar yanada tushunarli va koʻrgazmali boʻladi.

- Sunʼiy intellekt asosida foydalanuvchilarning qidiruv tarixiga moslashish imkoniyati mavjud.

- Turli tillar uchun avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima va moslashtirish tizimlari mavjud.

Kamchiliklari:

- Elektron lugʻatlar internet yoki dasturiy taʼminotga bogʻliq boʻlishi mumkin, bu esa foydalanish imkoniyatlarini cheklashi mumkin.

- Sunʼiy intellekt asosidagi tarjima va NLP tizimlari baʼzan xatolarga yoʻl qoʻyishi mumkin, bu esa maʼlumotlarning aniqligiga taʼsir qiladi.

- Raqamli lugʻatlarni yaratish va doimiy ravishda yangilab borish katta resurs va vaqt talab qiladi.

- Baʼzi foydalanuvchilar anʼanaviy bosma lugʻatlarga koʻnikkan boʻlishi mumkin, shuning uchun elektron lugʻatlarga oʻtish qiyin boʻlishi mumkin.

Xulosa Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida elektron lugʻatlar yaratish terminologik tadqiqotlarning samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi. Elektron lugʻatlar yangilanadigan, foydalanuvchilarga qulay va turli texnologiyalar bilan integratsiya qilinadigan vosita sifatida ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kelajakda bu sohada sunʼiy intellekt va mashina oʻrganish texnologiyalaridan kengroq foydalanish ushbu tizimlarni yanada takomillashtirish imkonini beradi.

Shuningdek, elektron lugʻatlar nafaqat lingvistik tadqiqotlar uchun, balki taʼlim jarayonida ham samarali qoʻllanilishi mumkin. Ular oʻquvchilarning til oʻrganish jarayonini tezlashtirish, soha mutaxassislariga esa terminlarni chuqurroq tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Raqamli lugʻatlar, ayniqsa, ilmiy-texnikaviy sohalarda tez oʻzgarib boruvchi terminologiyani samarali boshqarish va foydalanuvchilarni aniq hamda ishonchli maʼlumotlar bilan taʼminlash uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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SHAXSGA YO'NALTIRILGAN YONDASHUV ASOSIDA CHET TILINI O'QITISHNING INTERFAOL METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola chet tilini o'qitishda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvning asosiy hususiyatlari hamda imkoniyatlari keng yoritilib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Interfaol metod, yondashuv, konstruksionizm, motivatsiya.

Bugungi globallashuv davrida chet tillarni bilish nafaqat shaxsiy muvaffaqiyatning mezonini, balki zamonaviy mutaxassisning kasbiy raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlovchi asosiy ko'nikmalardan biri hisoblanadi. Xalqaro aloqalarning kengayishi va texnologik taraqqiyot xorijiy tillarni o'rganishga bo'lgan talabni sezilarli darajada oshirdi. Ayniqsa, oliy ta'lim muassasalari (OTM) talabalari uchun chet tilini bilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki ular kelgusida o'z kasbiy faoliyatida xorijiy tillardagi axborot va bilimlardan foydalanishlari lozim. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida o'qitishning interfaol metodlari bo'yicha bir qator olimlar va ta'lim mutaxassislari ilmiy ishlar olib borgan. Ushbu metodlarni ta'lim jarayoniga tadbiq etish va ularni rivojlantirish borasida quyidagi muhim tadqiqotchilar va ularning ishlari e'tiborga loyiqdir:

Lev Vygotskiyning shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonida "Yaqin rivojlanish zonasi" nazariyasi interfaol metodlarni qo'llashda muhim asos bo'lib, unda talabalar o'rtasida o'zaro muloqot va faol hamkorlikning o'rganish jarayonini rivojlantirishda samarali ta'siri aks ettirilgan. Amerikalik pedagog John Dewey shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'limning nazariyasini rivojlantirib, interfaol metodlar asosida o'qitishda tajriba va faol ishtirokning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi va ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirishga qaratilgan metodlarni ilgari suradi. Uning "Tajriba orqali o'rganish" tamoyili shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitishning asoslaridan biridir. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim tizimida Carl Rogersning pedagogik yondashuvlar ham katta o'rin egallaydi. Uning "Ijobiy o'qituvchi va o'quvchi munosabatlari" haqidagi tadqiqotida o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlariga mos keladigan o'qitish usullariga to'xtalib, shaxsning ichki motivatsiyasini va o'rganishdagi qiziqishlarini asosiy e'tibor markaziga qo'yadi. Braziliyalik pedagog Paulo Freire interfaol o'qitish metodlarini o'zining "Pedagogiya of the Oppressed" asarida o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish, ular bilan muammoli

vaziyatlar orqali ishlashda ahamiyatli ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. Freire o'qitish jarayonida talabalar va o'qituvchilar o'rtasida tenglik va o'zaro hurmatni yaratish, shuningdek, o'quvchilarga o'z fikrlarini ifodalash imkoniyatini berish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Amerika psixologi va pedagogi Jerome Bruner o'qitishda interfaol metodlarni qo'llashni rivojlantirib, "konstruksionizm" nazariyasini ishlab chiqqan. Brunerning yondashuvi shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'limning asosini tashkil qiladi, chunki u o'quvchilarni bilimni yaratishda faol ishtirok etishga undaydi. Uning ishlarida o'quvchilarga bilimni faqat tayyor shaklda berish emas, balki ularni mustaqil ravishda bilishni kashf qilishga yo'naltirishning ahamiyati ko'rsatilgan.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida o'qitishning interfaol metodlari bo'yicha O'zbekistonda ham bir qancha olimlar ilmiy ishlar olib borgan. Ular o'z tadqiqotlarida interfaol metodlarni shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim tizimida qo'llashning samaradorligini o'rganib, ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlarni joriy etishga yordam berganlar.

M. M. Mirzaev shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish jarayonida interfaol metodlarning ahamiyatini o'rganib, o'quvchilarni faol ishtirok etishga undashning pedagogik zaruratini, interfaol metodlarning motivatsiya va qiziqishni oshirishda muhim o'rin tutishini qayd etadi. Sh. S. Azizov ta'limda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan metodlarni qo'llashni innovatsion yondashuv sifatida ko'rsatgan va bu jarayonda interfaol metodlarni qo'llash orqali o'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlashini rivojlantirish mumkinligini ta'kidlagan. M. A. To'laganov esa shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitish tizimida interfaol metodlarni qo'llash bo'yicha ko'plab tavsiyalar ishlab chiqqan. U o'quvchilarni jamiyatga moslashish uchun interfaol yondashuvlar orqali bilimlarni amaliyotda qo'llashga o'rgatishni maqsad qilgan. B. B. Keldibekov pedagogik jarayonlarda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan interfaol metodlar orqali o'quvchilarni o'z bilimlarini amaliyotda qo'llashga va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirishni taklif etgan. N.F.Davletov ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlarning rolini ko'rsatgan, u shaxsga yo'naltirilgan o'qitishda o'quvchilarning o'zaro faoliyatini qo'llashning pedagogik asoslarini ishlab chiqqan.

Demak, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida o'qitishning interfaol metodlari — bu ta'lim jarayonida har bir talabaning individual ehtiyojlari, qobiliyatlari va o'qish usullarini inobatga olib, o'qitishni interaktiv, qiziqarli va samarali qilishga yo'naltirilgan metodlar to'plamidir. Bu metodlar talabalar o'quv jarayonida faol ishtirok etishlarini ta'minlab, ularning fikrlash qobiliyatlarini

rivojlantirish, bilimlarni mustahkamlash va kasbiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Interfaol metodlarning asosiy xususiyatlari quyidagilar:

Faollik	Interfaol metodlar o'quvchilarning o'quv jarayonida passiv ishtirokidan voz kechib, ularni faol ishtirokchiga aylantiradi. Bu metodlar talabalarni dars davomida faollikka chaqiradi, ular faqat tinglovchi emas, balki fikr bildiruvchi, savollar beruvchi va muhokama qiluvchi bo'lishadi.
Muammoli vaziyatlar	Interfaol metodlar ko'pincha muammoli vaziyatlar orqali o'rganishni taklif etadi. Bunday vaziyatlarda talabalar o'z bilimlarini amalda qo'llab, muammoni hal qilishga harakat qiladilar. Bu metod o'quvchilarda mustaqil fikrlash va ijodkorlikni rivojlantiradi.
Tanqidiy fikrlash	Interfaol metodlar talabalarni tanqidiy fikrlashga, o'z fikrlarini baholashga va boshqalar bilan munozara qilishga undaydi. O'quvchilar har bir vaziyatga turli nuqtai nazardan qarashni o'rganadilar.
Praktik qo'llanish	Interfaol metodlar nazariy bilimlarni amaliyotga tatbiq etishni ta'minlaydi. O'quvchilar o'rganilgan materialni real hayotda qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishadi, bu esa ularning bilimlarini mustahkamlaydi va yodda saqlashni osonlashtiradi.
Refleksiya	O'quvchilarga o'z-o'zini baholash, yutuqlarini va xatolarini tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Bu jarayon o'quvchilarning o'z bilim va qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Yuqoridagi jadvaldan ko'rinadiki, interfaol metodlar mashg'ulot davomida talabalarni faollikka chaqiradi, muammoli vaziyatlarda mustaqil fikrlash va ijodkorlikni rivojlantiradi, tanqidiy fikrlashga, o'z fikrlarini baholashga va boshqalar bilan munozara qilishga undaydi.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan interfaol metodlarning afzalliklari:

- *Motivatsiyani oshirish:* Interfaol metodlar talabalarning darsga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi va ularga faollik beradi;
- *Ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlash:* Talabalar fikrlarini erkin ifodalash, yangi g'oyalarni ilgari surish orqali ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradilar;
- *Real muammolarni hal qilish:* Amaliy mashqlar va simulyatsiya yordamida talabalar real muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatini shakllantiradilar;

➤ *Mustaqil fikrlash va o'zini baholash*: Har bir talaba darsda faol qatnashib, o'z bilim va ko'nikmalarini o'z-o'zini baholash orqali mustahkamlaydi.

Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida interfaol metodlar qo'llanishi o'quv jarayonini talabalar uchun qulay, samarali va qiziqarli qilishga yordam beradi. Bu metodlar talabalarning faolligini oshiradi, ularning fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi va o'qituvchi bilan talabalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni mustahkamlaydi. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan interfaol metodlar yordamida talabalarning bilimlari amaliy ko'nikmalar bilan boyitilib, ular real hayotda chet tilini qo'llashga tayyorlanadi. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida o'qitishning interfaol metodlarini ta'lim jarayoniga singdirish – bu o'quvchilarni faollikka, mustaqil fikrlashga va o'z bilimlarini amaliyotda qo'llashga yo'naltirilgan muhim pedagogik jarayon hisoblanadi. Ushbu metodlar o'quvchilarni shaxs sifatida rivojlantirishga, ularning qiziqishlari, ehtiyojlari va qobiliyatlariga mos o'qitish tizimini tashkil etishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvga mos interfaol metodlar o'quvchilarni faollikka, ijodiy fikrlashga, va mustaqil qaror qabul qilishga undaydi. Bu metodlar o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlarini qondirishga yordam beradi va ularning o'qish jarayonidagi qatnashishini maksimal darajaga oshiradi. Har bir metod shaxsning o'zini ifodalashga va shaxsiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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**RAQAMLI TA'LIM MUHITIDA PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYA
TA'LIM YO'NALISHI TALABALARINING MAS'ULIYAT
KO'NIKMALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MAZMUNI**

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***Annotatsiya.** Mazkur maqolada raqamli ta'lim muhitida “Pedagogika” va “Psixologiya” ta'lim yo'nalishlari talabalarining mas'uliyat ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish mazmuni yoritilgan. Pedagogika” va “Psixologiya” ta'lim yo'nalishlari talabalarining raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalar mas'uliyat ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish mazmuni o'quv rejalari, o'quv dasturlari, mustaqil ta'lim va pedagogik amaliyot kabi me'yoriy hujjatlari asosida tahlil etilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** mas'uliyat ko'nikmalari, o'quv rejalari, o'quv dasturlari, mustaqil ta'lim va pedagogik amaliyot.*

Talabalar mas'uliyat ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish mazmuni – bu talabalarning o'z-o'zini boshqarish, o'qish jarayoniga mas'uliyat bilan yondashish, vaqtni samarali boshqarish va o'z yutuqlarini va kamchiliklarini tahlil qilish kabi ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan faoliyatlar va jarayonlarning umumiy tushunchasidir. Raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalarning mas'uliyat ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish mazmuni turli bosqichlardan iborat bo'lib, uning har bir bosqichi talabaning mustaqil o'qish va o'z-o'zini boshqarishdagi qobiliyatlarini yanada rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7].

“Pedagogika” va “Psixologiya” ta'lim yo'nalishlari talabalarining raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalar mas'uliyat ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish mazmuni o'quv rejalari, o'quv dasturlari, mustaqil ta'lim va pedagogik amaliyot kabi me'yoriy hujjatlari asosida aniqlashtirildi. 60110100-Pedagogika ta'lim yo'nalishi majburiy fanlariga umumiy yuklama hajmiga 4300 soat, auditoriya o'quv soatlariga 1980 soat, mustaqil ta'limga 2340 soat ajratilgan bo'lib, quyidagi ixtisoslik fanlari o'qitiladi (1-jadvalga qarang):

1-jadval.

60110100-Pedagogika ta'lim yo'nalishi majburiy fanlari

№	Fanlar	Umumiy soat	Auditoriya mashg'ulotlari				Mustaqil ta'lim
			Jami	Ma'ruza	Seminar	Amaliy	
1.	Umumiy psixologiya	300	120	60	60		180
2.	Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi	330	136	60	76		194

3.	Milliy tarbiya asoslari	180	74	36	30	14	106
4.	Mutaxassislikka kirish	300	120	60	60		180
5.	Xalq pedagogikasi	240	120	60	60		120
6.	Inklyuziv ta'lim. Gospital pedagogika	120	60	30	16	14	60
7.	Ijtimoiy pedagogika	270	120	60	60		150
8.	Yunogogika	120	60	20	40		60
9.	Ta'lim menejmenti	120	60	20	40		60
10.	Oila pedagogikasi	240	120	40	80		120
11.	Pedagogik diagnostika va korreksiya	270	120	60	60		150
12.	Pedagogik mahorat	120	60	30	30		60
13.	Tarbiya fanini o'qitish metodikasi	240	120	60	60		120
14.	Komparativistik pedagogika	120	60	30	30		60
15.	Uzluksiz ta'limdagi tendensiyalar va zamonaviy yondashuvlar	150	60	24	36		90
16.	Kreativ pedagogika	330	150	40	110		180
17.	Pedagogik texnologiya	180	90	40	50		90

60110100-Pedagogika ta'lim yo'nalishida tanlov fanlarga 1800 soat ajratilgan bo'lib, 3-4-bosqichlarda "Elektron pedagogika", "Pedagogika fani metodologiyasi", "Pedagogik androgogika", "Ijtimoiy psixologiya", "Pedagogik valeologiya", "Pedagogik aksiologogika", "Pedagogik kompetentlik", "Tyutorlik faoliyati asoslari",

“Tarbiyaviy ish texnologiyalari”, “Pedagogik konfliktologiya”, “Pedagogik innovatika”, “Rivojlanish psixologiyasi va pedagogik psixologiya”, “Pedagogika va psixologiya fanlarini o`qitish metodikasi”, “Gender pedagogikasi va psixologiyasi”, “Pedagogik akmeologiya”, “Muzei pedagogikasi”, “Artpedagogika”, “Pedagogik kvalimetriya”, “Testologiya”, “Oila psixologiyasi va psixoterapiyasi”, “Bolalar pedagogikasi”, “Tarbiyada kouch trening”, “Iqtidorli bolalarni o`qitish texnologiyasi”, “Pedagogik riskologiya”, “Pedagogik prognostika”, “Neyropedagogika”, “Pedagogik sinergetika” kabi fanlari o`qitilmoqda. Yuqorida qayd etilgan fanlardan kelib chiqib, 1-2-bosqich talabalari tadqiqot ob`yekti deb tanladik, 60110100-Pedagogika ta`lim yo`nalishining 1-2-bosqichlarida majburiy fanlarga quyidagicha kreditlar ajratilib, o`qitiladi (2-jadvalga qarang):

2-jadval.

1-2-bosqich majburiy fanlarining kreditlari

№	Majburiy fanlar	1-semestr	2-semestr
1.	Umumiy psixologiya	6	4
2.	Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi	6	5
3.	Milliy tarbiya asoslari	6	
4.	Mutaxassislikka kirish	6	4

60310300-Psixologiya ta`lim yo`nalishi majburiy fanlariga umumiy yuklama hajmiga 4920 soat, auditoriya o`quv soatlariga 2160 soat, mustaqil ta`limga 2760 soat ajratilgan bo`lib, quyidagi ixtisoslik fanlari o`qitiladi (3-jadvalga qarang):

3-jadval.

60310300-Psixologiya ta`lim yo`nalishi majburiy fanlari

№	Fanlar	Umumi y soat	Auditoriya mashg`ulotlari				Mustaqil ta`lim	
			Jam i	Ma`ruza	Laborotoriy a	Seminar		Amaliy
1.	Mutaxassislikka kirish	180	60	30		30		120
2.	Umumiy psixologiya	720	300	120		180		420
3.	Eksperimental psixologiya	480	210	104	106			270
4.	Rivojlanish psixologiyasi va differensial psixologiya	300	120	60		60		180
5.	Psixologik	180	90	44			46	90

	ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash metodlari va texnologiyalari							
6.	Umumiy psixodiagnostika	300	120	60			60	180
7.	Sotsial psixologiya	360	150	60			90	210
8.	Psixologik konsultasiya va psixokorreksiya	180	90	44			46	90
9.	Umumiy pedagogika	180	60	30		30		120
10.	Psixologik trening asoslari	120	60	30		30		60
11.	Pedagogik psixologiya va psixologiyaning o`qitish metodikasi	180	60	30		30		120
12.	Klinik psixologiya	180	90	44		46		90
13.	Yuridik psixologiya	120	60	30		30		60
14.	Oila psixologiyasi	120	60	30		30		60
15.	Mehnat va muhandislik psixologiyasi	120	60	30		30		60
16.	Psixologiya tarixi	180	60	30		30		120

60310300-Psixologiya ta'lim yo`nalishida tanlov fanlarga 1800 soat ajratilgan bo`lib, "Psixogenetika", "Psixozanaliz", "Ta'lim muassasalarida psixologik xizmat", "O`qituvchi psixologiyasi", "Etnopsixologiya", "Psixologik salomatlik", "Aratorlik va imidj psixologiyasi", "Tashkiliy psixologiya", "Profayling", "Ta'sir psixologiyasi", "Iqtisodiy psixologiyasi", "Yollsh va networking (aloqa o`rnatish psixologiyasi)", "Neyropsixologiya", "Ekstremal vaziyatlarda psixologik xizmat",

“Boshqaruv va ijtimoiy sohalarda psixologik xizmat”, “Sport psixologiyasi”, “Xulqi og`ishgan bolalar psixologiyasi”, “Psixolingvistika” kabi fanlari o`qitilmoqda.

Yuqorida qayd etilgan fanlardan kelib chiqib, 1-2-bosqich talabalari tadqiqot ob'yekti deb tanladik, 60310300-Psixologiya ta'lim yo`nalishining 1-2-bosqichlarida majburiy fanlarga quyidagicha kreditlar ajratilib, o`qitiladi (4-jadvalga qarang):

4-jadval.

1-2-bosqich majburiy fanlarining kreditlari

№	Majburiy fanlar	1-semestr	2-semestr
1.	Mutaxassislikka kirish	6	
2.	Umumiy psixologiya	8	4
3.	Eksperimental psixologiya		6
4.	Rivojlanish psixologiyasi va differensial psixologiya		6

Kunduzgi ta'lim shaklida tahsil oluvchi talabalarining 4+2 tartibdagi malakaviy amaliyoti 3-8 semestrlarda amalga oshiriladi. Bunda haftaning 4 kunida nazariy va amaliy ta'lim, 2 kunda amaliyot o`tkaziladi [1].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, talabalarining o'z-o'zini boshqarish, vaqtni samarali boshqarish, ijodkorlik, mustaqil fikrlash, jamoaviy ishda ishtirok etish, texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish va ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni anglash kabi ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishni ta'minlaydi. Bu ko'nikmalar talabalarining raqamli ta'lim muhitida muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishi uchun zarur bo'lgan asosiy omillardir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro`yxati:

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СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ДЕЗИНФОРМАЦИИ НА СЕМЕЙНЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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***Аннотация:** Выделяя социальные философские аспекты воздействия дезинформации семейные отношения как субстанцию семейного бытия, автор адекватным методом их исследования считает интегративный подход, включающий в себя онтологический, аксиологический и феноменологический аспекты.*

***Ключевые слова:** Дезинформация, семья, брак, семейная жизнь, семейные отношения.*

Показательной характеристикой трансформационных процессов в обществе являются изменения в семейных отношениях. В условиях глобализации наблюдается массовый выход женщин на рынок труда, что способствует расширению возможностей выбора жизненных стратегий. Эта тенденция оценивается неоднозначно. Некоторые ученые полагают, что это новый поворот в семейно-гендерных отношениях, который наиболее соответствует современной ситуации и отражает многообразие гендерно-ролевых отношений между мужчинами и женщинами. По моему мнению У других авторов наблюдается явный отход от семейных традиций, замена их конкуренцией за достижение индивидуального успеха и карьерного роста.

В современном научном знании существует ряд концепций, характеризующих особенности семьи в контексте социальных трансформаций. Согласно теории Т. Парсонса, семья должна основываться на равноправных отношениях и единстве супружеских ролей. Ее основные функции должны быть связаны с поддержанием определенных норм семейной жизни, интеграцией культурных традиций, регулированием взаимоотношений, обеспечением условий для социализации детей «в духе этой культурной традиции».

Отстаивая функционалистский подход к изучению семьи, Т. Парсонс считает, что «разумно» возлагать на каждого партнера те функции, которые соответствуют биологическим различиям между мужчинами и женщинами. Например, ученый связывает роль женщины в семье с воспитанием детей, реализацией так называемого «экспрессивного лидерства»; Роль мужчины — обеспечивать жену и детей и осуществлять «инструментальное лидерство». Исследователь настаивает на том, что такое разделение рационально, поскольку

муж и жена в семье обязаны выполнять функции, дополняющие друг друга и способствующие объединению членов семьи.

Дезинформация как вид лжи всегда занимала особое место в сознании людей и общественной жизни, изучалась в религиозных учениях и была предметом изучения ряда наук: философии, этики, логики, психологии, педагогики, юридических наук. Это связано с тем, что ложь в той или иной форме встречается на всех этапах развития цивилизации и во всех сферах человеческой деятельности и отношений — от межличностных и межгрупповых до межгосударственных — и оказывает существенное влияние на все уровни социального взаимодействия.

В современной общественно-политической и экономической жизни Узбекистана дезинформация часто используется в манипулятивных технологиях как инструмент воздействия на групповое и индивидуальное сознание. Прикладной аспект исследования дезинформации заключается в том, что выявление эмпирических показателей, фиксирующих ее проявления в поведении человека, является условием эффективной организации практической деятельности и разработки инструментария диагностики и профилактики лжи у конкретных субъектов в различных социальных ситуациях и сферах профессиональной деятельности.

Супружеские отношения, безусловно, являются определяющим (системообразующим) звеном в структуре семейных отношений. Их биологической основой являются межполовые отношения, а социальной основой — брак как социально регламентированный союз мужчины и женщины, создаваемый с целью образования семьи и продолжения рода. Существует также духовная основа брака, которая включает в себя взаимную симпатию, любовь, привязанность, общие идеалы и ценности супругов и т. д. Нередко духовная составляющая сводится либо к биологической основе (например, когда любовь трактуется как проявление полового инстинкта), либо к социально-формальной составляющей брачных отношений (подобный взгляд часто встречается и в юридических определениях брачных отношений, когда их духовная составляющая выносится за скобки и сводится, например, только к юридической ответственности супругов). Однако с философской точки зрения невозможно игнорировать духовное содержание супружеской жизни, на что особое внимание обращал русский философ В.В. Розанов. Естественной предпосылкой возникновения устойчивых межполовых отношений в супружеской паре послужили особенности человека как биологического вида и,

в частности, длительный период беспомощности младенцев, нуждающихся в заботе со стороны обоих родителей. Культурной предпосылкой установления супружеских отношений является необходимость социального регулирования и упорядочения межполовых отношений. Первоначально брачный союз закрепляется традицией, а затем и законом, превращаясь в важный социальный институт.

Таким образом, можно выделить природные, социальные и духовные детерминанты, определяющие семейные отношения как универсальную социальную ценность. Под природными детерминантами следует понимать биологические потребности в продолжении рода, интимном общении, заботе о беспомощных детях и стариках и т. д. Все это определяется необходимостью физического воспроизводства человека и имеет первостепенное жизненное значение. Получается, что биологическая целесообразность выступает естественной предпосылкой существования семейных отношений как универсальной социальной ценности.

Социальные детерминанты связаны с необходимостью создания условий для нормального существования и функционирования человека в обществе, его оптимального сосуществования с другими людьми. В основе этого лежит социальная потребность в регулировании и нормализации межполовых и межпоколенных отношений, в подчинении биологических проявлений человеческой деятельности общепринятым правилам. Наконец, духовными детерминантами, определяющими семейные отношения как универсальную ценность общества, являются потребности в духовном воспроизводстве личности. Как известно, в системе семейных отношений формирование внутренних структур личности происходит на основе их интериоризации. Таким образом, семейные отношения обладают особым смыслообразующим свойством и поэтому предъявляются особые требования к их качественному состоянию. То есть для оптимального формирования личности важно, чтобы они не просто существовали, а были гармоничными и целостными. В этом их духовный и ценностный смысл.

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THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *Critical thinking refers to the individuals' ability to think and make correct decisions independently. Nowadays enhancing critical thinking in learners is considered one of the foreign language teachers' tasks due to its high position in foreign language classrooms. The article analysis the importance of critical thinking skills and it's main characteristics in language teaching.*

Key words: *creativity, collaboration, knowledge, abilities, skills, generalize, compare, abstract, reflexively, capacity, argumentation.*

The president of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev has put a great deal of emphasis on the importance of learning foreign languages for the country's development during his presidency. He urged to improve the process of teaching foreign languages and increasing the level of language training of teachers: «In today's world, the high-ranking places are occupied by people who can speak several foreign languages. A specialist who does not speak any foreign languages cannot achieve a great success in his or her profession».¹

There are so many essential skills for students to succeed in both their education and workplace. Among them, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration and communicational skills make the biggest impact on the performance of students. Educational institutions should form a holistic system of universal knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as independent activity and personal responsibility of students. The difficulty of learning English is also attributed to the fact that it is essential to create facilities for the formation of English-language communicative competence which is the internal readiness and ability to carry out a verbal communication. Therefore, it is necessary to give students not only knowledge in the field of language, but also to develop critical thinking skills in schoolchildren and university students, such as independence in obtaining and using new knowledge, which are the features of the development of critical thinking. Students must be able to generalize, compare, abstract, analyze and evaluate. All of which not only lead to a better acquisition of knowledge and general development of adolescents, but will also help them to deal with challenging problems and work in a creative way.

There are a number of definitions of the term «critical thinking» in the literature, but not all of them agree with each other. O. Mednikova writes that critical thinking

¹<http://www.gazeta-nv.uz/news2023/4/15/mirziyoyev-digita/>

is «the ability to reflexively evaluate facts, events, processes affecting the positions and interests of social forces, which assumes a clear and precise definition of one's position both to the put forward theories and to their practical actions»². «Critical thinking is the search for common sense: how to judge objectively and act logically, taking into account both your point of view and other opinions, the ability to abandon your own prejudices. It is intelligent, reflective thinking focused on deciding what to believe and what to do»³. Critical thinking is defined by the authors of the technology as follows: «Thinking critically means showing curiosity and using research methods, asking questions and systematically searching for answers. It means developing a point of view on a certain issue and the ability to defend this point of view with logical and compelling arguments. Critical thinking involves paying attention to your opponent's arguments and logical comprehension of them». This definition includes many aspects, but we must remember that critical thinking is not just a separate skill, but a combination of many different skills. D. Kluster considers critical thinking to be highly independent; social thinking, which begins with asking questions and understanding the problems that need to be solved; critical thinking, in his opinion, strives for convincing argumentation. The center, its main content is a statement (idea), which is supported by a number of arguments, each of which, in turn, is supported by evidence. Under all the named elements of argumentation there is a foundation - a starting point, which is common to the speaker or writer and his audience and which provides the basis for the entire argumentation⁴. With all the variety of definitions of critical thinking, one can see a similar meaning in them. We consider critical thinking means evaluative, reflective, independent thinking and a critical thinker is almost impossible to manipulate. Undoubtedly, critical thinkers can find their own solutions to the problems and back them up with strong arguments, able to resist even the printed word, the power of tradition and the opinion of the majority. E.S. Korolkova notes that «questions act as the leading means of developing critical thinking»⁵.

From our point of view, critical thinking, in broad terms, refers to a deeper level of thought that extends beyond just obtaining information. It is mainly concerned

²Mednikova, O.N. Technology for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing as a means of developing reflective activity of students // Bulletin of the Tomsk State University. un-ta. – 2015. – No. 6 (15). – pp. 17-20.

³ Zaire-Bek, S.I. Development of critical thinking in the classroom: a manual for teachers / S.I. Zaire-Bek, I.V. Mushtavinskaya. – M.: Education, 2004. – 175 p.

⁴Kluster, D. What is critical thinking / D. Kluster // Change. – 2001. – No. 4. – P. 36-37.

⁵Novikova, Yu., Grevtseva G.Ya. Development of critical thinking of students in the process of cognitive independent activity / Bulletin of the Chelyabinsk State Pedagogical University. – 2015. – No. 5. – pp. 47-52.

with the capacity to engage in reflective and independent thinking; it is about being an active rather than a passive learner. It's about learning how to think rather than what to think. This concept demands a care and critical approach to any object of cognitive interest.

A person who thinks critically has the following qualities: readiness to plan, ability to move away from stereotypes, perseverance, flexibility, originality of thinking. **Signs of critical thinking**⁶:

- critical thinking is independent thinking;
- information is the starting point, not the end point of critical thinking;
- critical thinking begins with asking questions and understanding the problems which should be solved;
- critical thinking strives for convincing argumentation.
- critical thinking is social thinking⁷.

According to the following ideas, succinctly defined, critical thinking is the intellectual exercise of methodically examining, analyzing, and evaluating information gathered from observation, experience, reflection, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. It involves structured questioning, fact-checking, and deep analysis to define authentic, well-rounded understanding, decisions or solutions. Thus, there are some characteristics of critical thinking and characteristics of a critically thinking person:

Characteristics of critical thinking:

1. Critical thinking is a type of thinking that helps a person find his or her own priorities in their personal, professional and social life, and also relate them to today's standards.
2. Critical thinking involves taking individual responsibility for the choices made.
3. Critical thinking is a complex process that allows us to develop a culture of «dialogue» in shared activities.
4. Critical thinking increases the level of culture of individual work with information, develops the ability to analyze and draw independent conclusions, predict the consequences of decisions and also helps to be responsible for them.
5. Critical thinking is an active and entertaining learning process.

Characteristics of a critically thinking person:

⁶Kluster, D. What is critical thinking / D. Kluster // Change. – 2001. – No. 4. – P. 36–37.

⁷ Dewey, J. (1933). How we think. A restatement of the relation of reflective thinking to the educative process (Rev. ed.), Boston, MA: D. C. Heath.

- they tend to be open-minded.
- they have the ability to defend one's opinion.
- they can also evaluate and analyze information.
- they obtain information from different sources.
- they see situations as a whole and clearly define a problem and find ways to solve it⁸.

Critical thinking is intricately connected to logic and reasoning. It is about being able to differentiate reliable information from fake one, discerning truth, fiction, and relevance. It involves systematic problem-solving, forecasting potential scenarios, and making educated predictions.

Critical thinking involves several key skills at its core such as problem-solving, analysis, creative thinking, interpretation, evaluation, and reasoning. These are not only acquired but honed over time, guided by a set of dispositions or attitudes that include a readiness to reconsider, openness to new ideas, being organized and systematic, mindful of the need for accuracy and fairness, and being proactive rather than reactive.

Last but not least, developing critical thinking also builds intellectual self-reliance and promotes intellectual humility. It can help to cultivate creativity by encouraging thinking 'outside the box' and nurture intellectual courage by enabling informed risk-taking. It should, therefore, be reasonable to say that critical thinking deserves recognition as a cornerstone for the development of human cognition and problem-solving abilities.

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⁸ Ennis, R. H. (1991). Critical thinking: A streamlined conception. Teaching Philosophy, 14(1), 5-24.

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES AT UNIVERSITY: MAIN ISSUES

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Abstract: *Teaching English for academic purposes (EAP) has long been an issue for discussion. On the basis of the analysis of the works of Russian and international scientists devoted to the given theme the article discusses the main gaps in teaching EAP to students that may potentially cause trouble when they start presenting the results of their scientific activity in the future.*

Key words: *English for academic purposes, linguistic component, metalinguistic component, gaps in teaching.*

Nowadays, research and science can truly be called international, which is by no means a drawback. Research results can be accessed globally, and international research teams are a common phenomenon. Undoubtedly, science has benefited from the chance to share knowledge, achievements, and establish international collaborations. Such changes boost the scientific development and result in practical outcome.

Although globalization in science seems to be a positive phenomenon. it is closely associated with certain problems. One of them is the problem of the so-called common linguistic code. Such code is a necessity in terms of making international communication possible. Traditionally, English has acquired the role of such a common code in the academic discourse, i.e., for historical reasons, English is used as lingua franca in science. Irina Korotkina states that, in this respect, the discussion around the English language focuses more on the practical issues [1]. Thus, if the English language is accepted as a universal linguistic code of scientific research, academic English loses its national affiliation. Moreover, it becomes a separate variant of the language, which has its own stylistic, organizational, and linguistic rules.

There are a lot of definitions of English for academic purposes [2; 3; 4]. All of them reflect some basic characters differentiating it from other variants of English, however they seem to be incomplete.

Here we present our own definition, combining the most essential ideas. English for academic purposes (herein after EAP) is a type of English for specific purposes that people need to communicate, study and conduct research in the academic English-medium context, i.e., in the international scientific environment. In this

respect, teaching EAP focuses primarily on developing the respective skills facilitating the students' study and research activities [5].

Any language manifests itself only in the process of communication. Communication in the academic context comprises heterogenous academic situations and pursues certain “situation-bound” purposes. Irina Korotkina emphasizes that communicational goals can be achieved only in case the speakers have the general knowledge of English, use specific terms and collocations characteristic of the English language scientific discourse and apply the so-called “publication conventions”, such as text organization or reference style described by Flowerdew [6; 1]. Therefore, we can conclude that EAP does not only require the acquisition of a linguistic component, but the development of metalinguistic skills as well. The need for such skills becomes the most obvious when organizing one's research results and submitting them to the scientific community. So, EAP has two main components: the pure linguistic one and the metalinguistic one, the acquisition of which is needed to reach one's communicative goals in this sphere.

Thus, the use of English as the language of international scientific and academic communication has benefited the scientific community a lot, but at the same time it has become a great challenge for non-English speaking communities in terms of teaching. English has long been studied at universities in Russia, however nowadays, its use in international events and as a working language of international scientific projects is widely fostered.

Students participate in a lot of international, all-Russian and local conferences where English is the main working language, they are encouraged to publish their proceedings and articles in English and participate in a number of English-based educational programs. This tendency is highlighted by the fact that most Russian universities include English-medium activities of staff members and students in their strategic plans. For example, according to the development strategy of Altai State University for 2017-2021, the mission is to train highly-qualified specialists having the world-class professional competences. They should be able to compete globally and present the results of their research internationally, to participate in the processes of interregional and international integration. The most talented students should be supported and encouraged to participate in different international conferences and internships, while the university provides them with any possible support. On the whole, the strategy stresses the importance of the specific educational modules forming “over-professional” universal competences, one of which is the ability to use EAP fluently [7].

The goal of the administration is praiseworthy. Still, the English-language teachers come across a great problem. It is not usually associated with the acquisition of the EAP linguistic component. Nowadays, successful young students usually have a good command of English and try to develop academic English skills while studying. They are flexible and can adapt to the needs of the modern world. However, Irina Korotkina underlines that the problem does not lie only in the scope of the language itself (the linguistic component of EAP). The papers of Russian authors are often rejected by international journals due to the style of writing [1]. So usually, the issue is the lack of knowledge in the sphere of international publication conventions, as traditionally, they differ from the Russian ones. In this regard, the EAP metalinguistic component is worth considering in the educational process.

The analysis of the main problems that the students face when they try to submit their papers to any international platforms showed the following linguistic and metalinguistic gaps (or so-called “by- academic” topics) that need covering within the program along with general grammar rules, basic and academic vocabulary: 1. Spoken and academic clichés used by the scientific community. It may not seem to be a problem, but even such a simple phrase as “Мы хотим выразить благодарность...” can cause difficulty while translating. Editors do not want complex phrases like “We want to express gratitude...” and require simpler ones like “We what to thank...” instead. 2. Active listening. This very important academic skill is neglected during the classes, however, it is essential while communicating orally. The success of communication may depend on the way the listeners perceive your reaction: if they see you are not engaged in active listening, they may consider you are not interested in collaboration. 3. Paying and receiving relevant compliments. This skill is often underestimated in the educational process, however, simple “Thank you” is not often enough. An academic should know the conventions of paying compliments to organizers, listeners,

collaborators, as well as know the appropriate responses and situation where to use them. 4. Establishing collaborations. The Russian tradition is not very welcoming to team work and collaborations in general. More often, Russian scientists are individualists. However, the entrance into the international scientific arena requires certain team work skills as well as the knowledge of specific cliches and responses to use while working in a team. 5. Creating a presentation. Nobody doubts that this skill is essential. However, still not everybody knows that presentation organization rules differ across cultural traditions. In order to perform successfully on the international arena, one needs to accept and follow these rules. For example, in the EAP tradition,

it is a must to provide affiliations and contacts in the last slide of the presentation, which is not usually done in the Russian tradition. 6. Organizing a scientific paper. This aspect is a real challenge to Russian speakers. It may seem surprising that a lot of papers are rejected not due to the fact of poor language and grammatical errors (although it might also be an issue), but due to the wrong organization of the paper parts. The traditional structure of the Russian manuscripts differs from the IMRAD format accepted by the international journals, so the students should be flexible and should know how to conform to the rules and not to stick to the habitual way.

So, the enumerated issues call for special attention and should be addressed during the classes. Teachers should pay special attention to them and include some practical tasks that drill these skills. Otherwise, learning the language will lack a vital component leading to certain problems in the future.

In conclusion, we would once more emphasize that the use of English as a common linguistic code by the international scientific community is a given. So, training highly qualified professionals is impossible without paying attention to the students' linguistic competences. Teaching EAP requires special attention to its two main components: linguistic and metalinguistic. Only such approach can give students an opportunity to correct the style of their papers, submit them internationally, to overcome a language barrier, develop their speaking academic skills, and, thus, to perform successfully in the international arena.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE NARRATIVE STORY CHAIN TECHNIQUE IN VOCABULARY TEACHING

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Annotation: *Vocabulary acquisition is one of the fundamental elements of language learning, directly affecting learners' ability to communicate effectively. This thesis examines the importance of the Narrative Story Chain (NSC) technique in vocabulary teaching, focusing on its role in enhancing vocabulary retention and student engagement. The NSC technique allows learners to collaboratively create stories, embedding new vocabulary in a meaningful context. The study highlights the effectiveness of this method in fostering long-term vocabulary acquisition compared to traditional rote memorization. Through a review of theoretical frameworks and empirical studies, the research demonstrates that storytelling-based vocabulary instruction significantly improves language learning outcomes. The findings suggest that implementing the NSC technique can make vocabulary learning more engaging, contextualized, and effective for learners at various proficiency levels.*

Keywords: *vocabulary teaching, Narrative Story Chain, storytelling, language acquisition, student engagement.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezis so'z boyligini o'rgatishda Narrativ Hikoya Zanjiri (NHZ) texnikasining ahamiyatini o'rganib, uning lug'at yodlash va o'quvchilarning darsga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirishdagi rolini tahlil qiladi. NHZ texnikasi o'quvchilarga hikoyalarni birgalikda yaratish imkonini beradi va yangi so'zlarni mazmunli kontekstda qo'llashga yordam beradi. Tadqiqot natijalari ushbu usulning so'zlarni uzoq muddat eslab qolishda an'anaviy yodlash usullariga nisbatan samaraliroq ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Nazariy manbalar va empirik tadqiqotlar asosida NSC texnikasi til o'rganish jarayonini sezilarli darajada yaxshilashi aniqlangan. Tadqiqot xulosalariga ko'ra, ushbu texnikaning tatbiqi o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini yanada qiziqarli, kontekstga asoslangan va samarali tarzda rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *so'z boyligini o'rgatish, Narrativ Hikoya Zanjiri, hikoya yaratish, til o'zlashtirish, o'quvchilarning faolligi.*

Аннотация: *Изучение словарного запаса является основой для всех языковых навыков. В нескольких исследованиях изучается влияние использования нарративных историй в качестве инструмента для улучшения усвоения лексики среди изучающих английский язык. Техники нарративного повествования предлагают глубокое инцидентное обучение, а не механическое заучивание. Используя сравнительный подход, обучающиеся получают возможность создавать значимые истории, что способствует улучшению запоминания и развитию креативности. Результаты показывают, что обучающиеся, прошедшие обучение с использованием историй, не только лучше запоминают лексику, но и проявляют больший интерес и уверенность при использовании новых слов. Этот метод является перспективным для повышения уровня усвоения лексики и стимулирования сотрудничества и любви к изучению языка. В данной работе рассматриваются техники нарративного повествования и их эффективность, креативные способы повышения уровня запоминания лексики и теории инцидентного обучения.*

Ключевые слова: техника нарративного повествования, изучение лексики, инцидентное обучение, механическое заучивание, повествование, изучение английского языка.

Introduction

Vocabulary is a key component of second language acquisition. Without a strong vocabulary base, learners face difficulties in communication, reading comprehension, and writing fluency. Traditional vocabulary instruction often relies on rote memorization and isolated word lists, which may not promote long-term retention or practical usage in real-life contexts.

The Narrative Story Chain technique is a student-centered approach that integrates vocabulary learning into a collaborative storytelling activity. Through this technique, students take turns adding to a developing narrative, incorporating newly introduced words into a meaningful and engaging context. This method is rooted in communicative language teaching (CLT) and task-based language teaching (TBLT), which emphasize the importance of interaction, creativity, and learner engagement.

This thesis investigates how the Narrative Story Chain technique enhances vocabulary retention and student motivation. Through a review of theoretical frameworks and existing research, it demonstrates the effectiveness of this storytelling-based approach in fostering vocabulary acquisition and improving learning outcomes.

The Role of Storytelling in Language Learning

Storytelling has long been recognized as a powerful tool for language development. Studies suggest that narratives help learners organize and recall information more effectively by connecting new words to meaningful contexts. Bruner (1991) argues that narratives shape human cognition, making learning more structured and memorable. When learners encounter vocabulary within a story, they associate it with characters, emotions, and real-world situations, which strengthens recall [1].

Cameron (2001) supports the idea that contextualized vocabulary instruction is more effective than isolated drills, as words become easier to remember when embedded in a meaningful context [2]. Similarly, Nation (2007) emphasizes the role of meaningful input in vocabulary acquisition, arguing that frequent exposure to words in different contexts reinforces retention [3].

The Narrative Story Chain technique aligns with these principles by providing learners with opportunities to use target vocabulary repeatedly in a connected and engaging way. By constructing a story collaboratively, students naturally encounter

and reuse new words, leading to improved long-term retention and practical application.

The Narrative Story Chain Technique in Vocabulary Teaching

The Narrative Story Chain technique encourages students to co-create a narrative, each contributing a sentence or paragraph while incorporating target vocabulary. This approach offers several benefits for vocabulary learning.

One major advantage is contextualized learning. Words are not learned in isolation but are embedded in a meaningful storyline, making them easier to recall and apply in real communication. Additionally, this method increases student engagement by making learning interactive and enjoyable. The collaborative nature of storytelling also promotes peer learning, as students negotiate meaning and build on each other's ideas.

Another key feature of this technique is its repetitive reinforcement of vocabulary. As the story progresses, words are recycled in different contexts, reinforcing their meaning and usage. This natural repetition helps learners retain vocabulary more effectively than through traditional memorization techniques.

Finally, the Narrative Story Chain integrates multiple language skills. While storytelling primarily focuses on speaking and listening, it also enhances reading comprehension and writing skills, as students must construct logical narratives while using correct grammatical structures and vocabulary.

Practical Implementation of the Narrative Story Chain Technique

To effectively implement the Narrative Story Chain technique in an English language classroom, teachers can follow these steps:

Pre-teaching vocabulary: The teacher introduces the target vocabulary before starting the activity. This can be done through visuals, example sentences, and discussions to ensure that students understand the words' meanings and usage.

Story starter activity: The teacher provides an engaging prompt or the first sentence of a story to set the scene.

Collaborative storytelling: Students take turns adding to the story, ensuring that they incorporate the target vocabulary naturally. The teacher facilitates the activity by providing guidance and encouraging creativity.

Reinforcement activities: After completing the story, students engage in follow-up exercises such as retelling, summarizing, or acting out the story to reinforce the learned vocabulary.

Assessment and feedback: The teacher evaluates vocabulary usage through quizzes, peer feedback, or reflective writing assignments to measure retention and application.

Research by Thornbury (2002) supports the effectiveness of contextual learning strategies in vocabulary acquisition [4]. The Narrative Story Chain technique aligns with these findings by offering a structured yet creative approach that promotes meaningful vocabulary learning.

Challenges and Solutions

Although the Narrative Story Chain technique is highly effective, certain challenges may arise during its implementation.

Some students may feel hesitant or lack confidence in contributing to the story, especially in lower proficiency levels. Encouraging participation through structured prompts and supportive feedback can help students feel more comfortable.

Another challenge is maintaining coherence in large classrooms. Dividing students into smaller groups ensures that all learners actively participate while keeping the narrative manageable.

Time constraints can also be an issue, as storytelling activities may take longer than traditional vocabulary exercises. Setting clear time limits for each phase of the activity can help maintain a balance between engagement and efficiency.

Lastly, some students may struggle with using target words correctly. Providing scaffolding, such as synonyms, sentence frames, and guided exercises, can support learners in integrating vocabulary more effectively.

Conclusion

The Narrative Story Chain technique is a highly effective method for vocabulary teaching, offering numerous benefits for learners. By embedding vocabulary within an engaging and interactive storytelling framework, this approach enhances retention, motivation, and practical language use.

Research suggests that storytelling-based vocabulary instruction leads to improved long-term retention compared to traditional rote memorization techniques. The collaborative and contextualized nature of the Narrative Story Chain technique makes it a valuable tool for educators seeking to improve vocabulary acquisition in language classrooms.

Future research could further explore its effectiveness across different proficiency levels and learning environments, providing additional insights into its long-term impact on vocabulary learning.

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UNDERSTANDING WRITTEN AND SPOKEN INSTRUCTIONS AND COMPREHENSION CHALLENGES AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract: *Effective comprehension of written and spoken instructions is crucial for academic success. However, many students face significant challenges in understanding and executing instructions, which can hinder their performance. This paper explores the cognitive, linguistic, and contextual factors that influence students' ability to comprehend instructions in both written and spoken forms. It examines common comprehension challenges, such as language proficiency, working memory limitations, and instructional clarity, while also considering the role of learning styles and environmental factors. The study further investigates potential interventions to enhance comprehension, including pedagogical strategies, technological tools, and student-centered learning approaches. The findings aim to provide educators with practical insights to improve instructional communication and foster better learning outcomes.*

Keywords: *Instructional comprehension, written and spoken instructions, learning challenges, cognitive load, linguistic proficiency, educational strategies, active learning, student engagement, technology in education.*

Introduction

Instructional comprehension is a fundamental aspect of learning across all educational levels. Whether in the classroom or in online learning environments, students frequently encounter both written and spoken instructions. While some students process information seamlessly, others struggle with understanding directives due to cognitive, linguistic, or environmental factors. This paper seeks to explore these challenges, their implications for learning, and possible strategies to mitigate comprehension difficulties.

Factors Affecting Instructional Comprehension

1. **Linguistic Proficiency** – Students with limited proficiency in the language of instruction often experience difficulties in understanding complex or ambiguous directives.

2. **Cognitive Load and Working Memory** – Instructions that are lengthy or contain multiple steps can overwhelm students' cognitive resources, leading to poor comprehension and execution.

3. **Clarity and Structure of Instructions** – Poorly structured or vague instructions can contribute to misunderstanding and errors.

4. **Learning Styles and Individual Differences** – Some students process information better through visual aids, while others rely on auditory or kinesthetic learning.

5. **Environmental and Contextual Factors** – Noisy settings, digital distractions, and unclear formatting can impair students' ability to focus on and interpret instructions effectively.

Comprehension Challenges and Their Impact

Students experience various comprehension challenges that directly impact their learning processes. These challenges may include:

- **Misinterpretation of Instructions:** One of the most common issues students face is misinterpreting written or spoken instructions. This often leads to errors in assignments, exams, and practical applications. If students do not fully grasp what is being asked of them, their ability to complete tasks successfully diminishes.

- **Increased Anxiety and Frustration:** When students struggle with understanding instructions, they may feel anxious or frustrated, leading to a lack of confidence in their abilities. This psychological barrier can further impede comprehension and discourage students from seeking clarification.

- **Reduced Academic Performance:** Comprehension difficulties often correlate with lower academic performance. Students who consistently struggle with understanding instructions may submit incomplete or incorrect work, negatively affecting their grades and overall learning outcomes.

- **Need for Frequent Clarification:** Many students who struggle with comprehension require repeated clarifications from instructors or peers. This not only slows down the learning process but also places additional demands on educators, who must continually re-explain concepts.

Theoretical Framework

To understand the challenges associated with instructional comprehension, this study incorporates several learning theories:

1. **Cognitive Load Theory:** Suggests that excessive cognitive demands hinder information processing. Simplifying instructions reduces cognitive overload.

2. **Constructivist Learning Theory:** Highlights the importance of active engagement in learning. Students benefit from interactive, experience-based instruction.

3. **Dual-Coding Theory:** Posits that using both verbal and visual information enhances comprehension. Multimodal instruction helps accommodate different learning styles.

4. **Schema Theory:** Explains that comprehension depends on prior knowledge. Students with weak foundational knowledge may struggle to interpret instructions correctly.

5. Information Processing Theory: Examines how students encode, store, and retrieve information. Poorly structured instructions disrupt effective learning.

Interventions and Strategies for Improvement

Improving comprehension of written and spoken instructions involves implementing targeted strategies that cater to diverse learning needs. Some key interventions include:

- **Enhancing Instructional Clarity:** Educators should ensure that instructions are concise, well-structured, and clearly articulated. Breaking down complex instructions into smaller, manageable steps can help students process information more effectively.

- **Multimodal Instruction:** Providing instructions through multiple formats—such as text, audio, video, and visual aids—can help accommodate different learning styles. Visual learners may benefit from diagrams and charts, while auditory learners may find verbal explanations more effective.

- **Use of Technology:** Digital tools, such as speech-to-text applications, interactive tutorials, and learning management systems, can facilitate better comprehension. Adaptive learning platforms can also tailor instructions to individual student needs.

- **Encouraging Active Learning:** Engaging students in discussions, summarization exercises, and peer collaboration can reinforce understanding. Active learning techniques encourage students to process and apply information rather than passively receive it.

- **Teacher Training and Awareness:** Educators should be trained in effective communication techniques and inclusive instructional practices. Understanding common comprehension barriers and adapting instruction accordingly can significantly enhance learning experiences for all students.

Case Studies and Empirical Findings

1. **Case Study on Language Proficiency and Comprehension:** A study conducted at a university in a multilingual region found that students with limited proficiency in the language of instruction were more likely to misinterpret exam questions and assignment guidelines. The introduction of bilingual support materials and language workshops significantly improved student performance and confidence.

2. **Impact of Cognitive Load on Instructional Comprehension:** Research on cognitive load theory suggests that students struggle with overly complex instructions due to limited working memory capacity. A study in a high school setting

demonstrated that simplifying instructions and incorporating step-by-step guidance led to a 25% improvement in task completion accuracy.

3. The Role of Technology in Enhancing Comprehension: A pilot program integrating interactive video tutorials in an online course found that students who engaged with multimedia instructions had higher retention rates and better performance compared to those who relied solely on text-based instructions.

Conclusion

Understanding and addressing the challenges associated with written and spoken instruction comprehension is essential for improving student learning outcomes. By identifying key obstacles and implementing targeted strategies, educators can enhance instructional effectiveness, reduce learning disparities, and foster a more inclusive academic environment. Future research should explore the impact of emerging technologies and adaptive learning techniques on instructional comprehension to further support diverse student needs. This paper highlights the importance of clear, structured, and multimodal instruction to improve student engagement and success. By integrating practical strategies, educators can ensure that all students have equitable access to education regardless of their linguistic background, cognitive abilities, or learning styles.

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E-LEARNING PLATFORMS AND TOOLS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: *This paper explores the significance of e-learning platforms and tools in the educational landscape, highlighting their benefits, challenges, and impact on teaching and learning. It discusses the various types of e-learning platforms such as Learning Management Systems (LMS), video conferencing tools, and collaborative software, as well as their role in enhancing student engagement, fostering collaboration, and improving access to education.*

Keywords: *Digital education, online learning tools, student engagement, collaborative tools, digital divide.*

Introduction The President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has been known for issuing various decrees aimed at advancing the country's development, reforming sectors like education, economics, and governance, and modernizing the country's institutions. These decrees often aim to resolve particular challenges or implement new policies. Especially in young learners, great opportunities are being created in the system of Education. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, noted in his resolution of PQ-5117 dated 19.05.2021 [1].

In recent years, e-learning has evolved from a supplementary educational tool into a core element of modern education systems worldwide. The rise of digital technologies, mobile devices, and internet connectivity has revolutionized the way education is delivered, accessed, and experienced. E-learning platforms and tools are now integral to both traditional and non-traditional educational environments, providing learners and educators with flexibility, convenience, and innovative ways to engage with content. E-learning platforms are online environments where instructors and learners interact, share materials, and engage in learning activities. These platforms are designed to facilitate remote or blended learning, where students can access educational content from any location at any time, using devices such as laptops, tablets, or smartphones. Some of the most popular e-learning platforms include **Moodle**, **Google Classroom**, **Canvas**, and **Blackboard**, each offering unique features tailored to various educational settings.

The future of e-learning is promising, with continued advancements in technology shaping the landscape of education. Innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) are expected to

revolutionize online learning by offering more immersive and interactive experiences. AI can personalize learning experiences, adapt content to individual learning styles, and provide real-time feedback. VR and AR can simulate real-world environments, allowing students to engage in hands-on learning experiences without leaving their homes.

Moreover, as more educational institutions embrace digital learning, there will be increased emphasis on blended learning models, which combine the flexibility of e-learning with the benefits of face-to-face instruction. This hybrid approach is expected to offer the best of both worlds, providing students with the flexibility of online learning while maintaining the interpersonal interactions of traditional classrooms. E-learning platforms and tools are transforming the education sector by offering innovative, flexible, and cost-effective solutions for both students and instructors. While challenges such as the digital divide and motivation issues persist, the benefits of e-learning in terms of accessibility, resource availability, and collaboration are undeniable. As technology continues to advance, the future of education will likely be characterized by more personalized, immersive, and interactive learning experiences that leverage the full potential of e-learning platforms and tools.

The integration of technology into education has accelerated rapidly in recent years, reshaping how teaching and learning occur. E-learning platforms and tools have become essential components of this transformation, offering new opportunities for enhancing educational access, flexibility, and quality. The literature surrounding e-learning platforms explores their various aspects, including their benefits, challenges, types, and the impact they have on both students and educators. This review synthesizes existing research to present a comprehensive overview of the role of e-learning in education.

1. Definition and Evolution of E-Learning Platforms

E-learning platforms are digital environments designed to facilitate the delivery of educational content, communication between students and educators, and the management of learning processes. According to Garrison and Kanuka (2004), e-learning platforms create opportunities for student-centered learning and are often categorized into Learning Management Systems (LMS) and Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs). Learning Management Systems such as Moodle, Blackboard, and Canvas are the most common, allowing educators to design, deliver, and track the learning experiences of students.

The evolution of e-learning platforms can be traced back to the late 1990s when the internet became widely available. With the rise of broadband and interactive technologies, educational institutions began exploring online education options. The significant growth in e-learning in the 21st century can be attributed to the proliferation of affordable technology, as well as the need for more flexible learning environments, particularly in higher education and professional development (Clark, 2013).

2. Benefits of E-Learning Platforms and Tools

Numerous studies have highlighted the advantages of e-learning platforms in promoting an inclusive, interactive, and flexible education system.

E-learning platforms make education accessible to individuals who may face barriers to traditional classroom-based learning. As noted by Moore et al. (2011), e-learning allows for asynchronous learning, meaning students can engage with course content at their own pace and time. This flexibility benefits adult learners, those working full-time jobs, or students in remote areas with limited access to educational institutions. E-learning platforms often feature interactive tools such as discussion forums, quizzes, multimedia content, and gamified experiences that engage students more effectively than traditional methods. Research by Bernard et al. (2009) indicates that online learning can enhance engagement through the use of multimedia elements, encouraging active participation.

E-learning tools promote collaboration through features like group projects, peer reviews, and virtual classrooms. A study by Anderson (2008) emphasizes the importance of social interaction in e-learning environments, which not only helps students connect with their peers but also encourages collaborative learning. The literature on e-learning platforms and tools in education demonstrates the transformative potential of digital technologies in enhancing teaching and learning. While e-learning offers substantial benefits, such as increased flexibility, accessibility, and engagement, it also presents challenges related to access, teacher readiness, and student motivation. The continued development and integration of e-learning platforms require ongoing investments in infrastructure, teacher training, and support for students, particularly those from marginalized groups. As e-learning continues to evolve, it is essential for educational institutions to balance technological innovation with pedagogical effectiveness to ensure that all learners benefit from these advancements.

Conclusion

E-learning platforms and tools have undeniably revolutionized the landscape of modern education by offering innovative solutions to enhance learning experiences, increase accessibility, and foster collaboration. The integration of digital technologies into education systems has provided greater flexibility, enabling learners to access educational content anytime, anywhere, and at their own pace. Moreover, e-learning platforms promote engagement through interactive features, foster collaboration through digital tools, and create opportunities for personalized learning, particularly in diverse educational settings.

However, the widespread adoption of e-learning is not without challenges. Issues such as the digital divide, where access to technology and the internet is unequal, remain significant barriers, particularly for marginalized students. Additionally, the effectiveness of e-learning tools hinges on the preparedness of educators, requiring robust training programs to ensure they can leverage these platforms to their full potential. Furthermore, the absence of face-to-face interaction in online environments can affect student motivation, discipline, and feelings of isolation, which are critical factors for academic success. As the demand for digital learning continues to grow, educational institutions must address these challenges by investing in infrastructure, providing ongoing professional development for educators, and ensuring equitable access to technology for all students. Moving forward, the integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and augmented reality holds immense potential to further enhance the quality of e-learning experiences.

In conclusion, e-learning platforms and tools are pivotal to shaping the future of education. While challenges remain, their advantages in creating an inclusive, flexible, and dynamic learning environment make them a powerful tool in fostering educational progress. As educational systems continue to evolve, the role of digital tools will only become more significant in ensuring that education is accessible, engaging, and adaptable to the needs of a diverse global student body.

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CONSTRUCTIVE COMMUNICATION ACROSS CULTURAL BOUNDARIES

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Abstract: *This article explores the concept of constructive communication in intercultural contexts, emphasizing the importance of effective communication strategies that foster understanding and cooperation across diverse cultural groups. It delves into the challenges posed by cultural differences, such as language barriers, non-verbal cues, and differing social norms, and offers practical approaches to overcoming these obstacles. The text highlights the role of empathy, active listening, and adaptability in facilitating constructive dialogue.*

Keywords: *Constructive communication, Intercultural communication, cross-cultural dialogue, Intercultural competence.*

Introduction. In an increasingly globalized world, effective communication across cultural boundaries is essential for fostering mutual understanding and collaboration. Constructive communication plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between different cultures, ensuring that interactions are respectful, productive, and conducive to positive outcomes. As people from diverse backgrounds engage in both personal and professional settings, the challenges of language barriers, differing social norms, and varying communication styles become more apparent. Addressing these challenges requires a deep understanding of intercultural dynamics and the ability to adapt communication strategies accordingly.

This article explores the concept of constructive communication in intercultural contexts, emphasizing the need for approaches that not only acknowledge but also respect cultural differences. By highlighting key principles such as empathy, active listening, and cultural sensitivity, the discussion offers insights into how individuals and organizations can navigate intercultural exchanges more effectively. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of intercultural competence—an essential skill for fostering positive relationships in diverse environments, whether in international business, educational settings, or everyday social interactions.

The importance of constructive communication in intercultural settings has been widely acknowledged in the field of communication studies. Numerous scholars have emphasized the significance of understanding cultural differences and adapting communication practices to foster mutual respect, reduce misunderstandings, and enhance collaboration.

One of the foundational theories in intercultural communication is Edward Hall's context theory (1976), which distinguishes between high-context and low-context cultures. High-context cultures, such as those found in Asia and the Middle East, rely heavily on non-verbal cues, shared understanding, and implicit messages, while low-context cultures, such as those in Western Europe and North America, prioritize direct, explicit communication. Hall's work laid the groundwork for understanding the nuances of communication in intercultural exchanges. Constructive communication, in this context, requires recognizing these differences and adjusting one's communication style accordingly.

Further extending Hall's work, Geert Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory (1980) provided a framework for analyzing how cultural values influence communication. Hofstede identified several dimensions, such as individualism vs. collectivism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance, which shape how individuals from different cultures perceive authority, group dynamics, and risk. Understanding these cultural dimensions enables individuals to navigate cross-cultural interactions more effectively and constructively.

The role of cultural sensitivity in communication has been widely discussed in the literature. Ting-Toomey (1999) introduced the concept of cultural identity and facework, emphasizing the importance of maintaining face (one's self-image or social identity) in intercultural interactions. She argued that effective communication in intercultural settings requires a sensitivity to how individuals from different cultures perceive social roles and interactions. Constructive communication, according to Ting-Toomey, involves adapting communication behaviors to protect the "face" of others, thereby fostering trust and cooperation.

Additionally, Gudykunst's Anxiety/Uncertainty Management Theory (1995) highlighted the importance of managing anxiety and uncertainty in intercultural communication. His work suggests that individuals who are able to reduce anxiety and uncertainty through effective communication strategies are more likely to experience successful intercultural exchanges. This aligns with the notion of constructive communication, where individuals intentionally work to reduce barriers to understanding by remaining open-minded and adaptable in their interactions.

The research methodology for studying constructive communication across cultural boundaries typically incorporates both qualitative and quantitative approaches, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of how communication functions within diverse cultural contexts.

A **mixed-methods** approach is often the most suitable for researching intercultural communication, as it enables the collection of both numerical data (quantitative) and in-depth insights (qualitative). This allows researchers to explore the complexities of intercultural interactions from multiple perspectives. The research may be designed as a **case study**, **survey**, or **experimental design**, depending on the specific objectives of the study.

- **Case Study:** A qualitative approach that examines particular instances of intercultural communication, such as interactions within international organizations, multicultural classrooms, or cross-border business negotiations.

- **Survey Research:** Quantitative research using structured questionnaires or interviews to collect data from a large sample of participants regarding their experiences and perceptions of intercultural communication.

- **Experimental Design:** Involves creating controlled environments to observe how individuals from different cultural backgrounds interact when exposed to specific communication interventions or training programs.

Conclusion

Constructive communication across cultural boundaries is an essential component of fostering understanding, collaboration, and positive relationships in an increasingly globalized world. The research highlights that effective intercultural communication requires individuals to not only be aware of cultural differences but to actively engage with those differences through strategies such as empathy, cultural sensitivity, and active listening. By incorporating intercultural competence and adapting communication practices, individuals and organizations can navigate complex cultural dynamics and resolve conflicts more effectively.

Through the application of both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies, it becomes evident that challenges such as language barriers, stereotypes, and differing social norms can impede constructive communication. However, these challenges also present opportunities for growth, learning, and greater intercultural understanding. The literature and research on this topic emphasize the value of intercultural competence training and the importance of creating environments where individuals feel respected and understood across cultural lines.

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FALSAFA FANINI O'QITISHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotatsiya: *Falsafa - bu insonning borlig'i muammosi, axloq va hayot haqidagi fundamental savollarga javob izlovchi hamda dunyoqarash, tafakkur va mavjudlikning asosiy masalalarini o'rganuvchi qadimiy fan. Bugungi zamonaviy ta'limda falsafa fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati yuqori hisoblanib, falsafa fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali, qiziqarli va interaktiv qilish imkonini beradi. Ushbu maqolada falsafa fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi haqida fikr-mulohazalar va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning imkoniyatlari yuzasidan tavsiyalar bayon etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Axborot texnologiyalari, motivatsiya, individuallashtirish, onlayn, baholash, platforma, interaktiv, sun'iy intellekt.*

Abstract: *Philosophy is an ancient discipline that seeks answers to fundamental questions about human existence, ethics, and life, while exploring the core issues of worldview, thinking, and being. In today's modern education, information technologies play a significant role in teaching philosophy, as their use can make the educational process more effective, engaging, and interactive. This article presents insights on the efficacy of using information technologies in teaching philosophy and offers recommendations regarding the potential applications of these technologies.*

Keywords: *Information technologies, motivation, individualization, online assessment, platform, interactive, artificial intelligence.*

Аннотаци: *Философия - древняя наука, стремящаяся найти ответы на фундаментальные вопросы о проблеме человеческого бытия, морали и жизни, а также изучающая основные вопросы мировоззрения, мышления и существования. В современном образовании роль и значение информационных технологий в преподавании философии высоки, а их использование позволяет сделать образовательный процесс более эффективным, увлекательным и интерактивным. В данной статье излагаются размышления об эффективности использования информационных технологий в преподавании философии и даются рекомендации по возможностям их применения.*

Ключевые слова: *Информационные технологии, мотивация, индивидуализация, онлайн, оценивание, платформа, интерактивный, искусственный интеллект.*

Hozirgi kunda talabalar uchun ta'lim jarayonini samarali va qiziqarli qilish maqsadida interaktiv texnologiyalar, onlayn resurslar va multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish zaruriyati ortib bormoqda. Falsafa fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish o'quv jarayonini talabalar uchun qiziqroq, samaraliroq va ularning bilimlarini chuqurlashtirishga yordam beradi. Quyida

falsafani o'qitish jarayonida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyatli jihatlarning asosiy yo'nalishlarini ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin.

Motivatsiyani oshirish – interaktiv vositalar va multimedia materiallar talabalarda o'qishga qiziqishni oshirish imkonini berish bilan birga, o'quv jarayonini maroqli o'tishini ham ta'minlaydi. Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali ta'lim jarayonini qiziqarli qilish talabalar orasida motivatsiyani oshiradi hamda talabalarning faol ishtirokini rag'batlantiradi.

Ma'lumotga kirish imkonini kengaytirish – talabalar uchun modulli ta'lim jarayonida resurslarga ega bo'lish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish talabalar uchun zamonaviy ilmiy-tadqiqotlar natijalaridan foydalanish, onlayn kutubxonalardan katta hajmdagi falsafiy resurslardan unumli foydalanish imkonini taqdim etadi. Axborot texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanish talabalarga keng bilim bazasidan foydalanishga imkon beradi. Ular internet orqali ilmiy maqolalarni, tadqiqotlar va tanqidiy sharhlarni o'qish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishadi.

O'qishni individuallashtirish – “Ta'lim tizimi zimmasiga yuklatilayotgan zamonaviy talablar uni rivojlantirishda istiqbolli yo'nalish sifatida individuallashtirishning ahamiyatini tobora oshirib bormoqda... Pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyotida ham individuallashtirish g'oyasining paydo bo'lishi ta'lim jarayonida shaxsning individual xususiyatlari, imkoniyatlari, qiziqishlari, qobiliyatini inobatga olish va shu asosda o'qitish usullarini tanlash zaruriyatining vujudga kelishi bilan bog'liq”¹.

Tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish – interaktiv topshiriqlar va onlayn muloqotlar talabalarda tahlil, sintez va ma'lumotni baholash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, falsafa fanini o'qitishda talabalarning mantiqiy va tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish hamda ularning ijodiy salohiyatini oshirishga xizmat qiladigan onlayn-o'qitish kabi o'quv mashg'ulotlaridan ham foydalanish tavsiya etiladi.

Adolatli baholash – talabalarning bilim va ko'nikmalarini moslashuvchan baholash uchun sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini qo'llash ularda ta'limiy motivatsiyani oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, har sohada qo'llanilayotgan sun'iy intellekdan foydalanish interaktiv elementlar va multimedia materiallardan foydalanishning samaradorligini oshiradi.

¹ <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/download/28154/28980> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10467003>

Falsafa fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalardan foydalanish ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali, qiziqarli va interaktiv qilish imkonini beradi. Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari va imkoniyatlari juda keng. Axborot texnologiyalarining falsafa fanini o'qitishida bir imkoniyatlari haqida so'z yuritadigan bo'lsak, bunda onlayn ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanish ta'lim samaradorligiga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi.

“Davlatlarning ta'lim tizimlari ta'lim muammolarini hal qilish, ta'lim sifati va mazmunini sezilarli darajada yaxshilash uchun elektron ta'lim platformalariga murojaat qilmoqda. Elektron ta'limni ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyalash konsepsiyasi o'qituvchi va o'qitish usullaridan boshlanadi. Elektron ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanish usullari butun ta'lim yondashuvini, shu jumladan, elektron ta'lim vositalaridan foydalanishni o'z ichiga oladi. Samarali ta'lim platformalari bilan birgalikda elektron ta'lim o'qituvchilarga audio-vizual o'rganish, boshqotirmalar va viktorinalar orqali o'z-o'zini sinab ko'rish va ish joyida simulyatsiyalar orqali kinetik o'rganish kabi keng qamrovli ta'lim uslublaridan foydalanish imkonini beradi”². Talabalarni falsafa fanining turli tarmoqlari bilan tanishtirishda Jahon bo'ylab Coursera, edX va Udey kabi onlayn ta'lim platformalari hamda resurslar bazalaridan foydalanish muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu platformalarda falsafaning zamonaviy masalalari yoritilgan kurslar, tarixiy kontekstlar mavjud bo'lib, talabalarni zamonaviy yechim izlash va ijodiy fikrlashga tayyorlaydi.

Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonini interaktivlashtirish imkoniyatini taqdim etadi. Zamonaviy taqdimot vositalari – Prezi yoki Microsoft Power Pointdan foydalanish o'qitilayotgan mavzularni vizual ravishda tushunishga yordam beradi. Ayniqsa, Prezida tayyorlangan taqdimotlar vositasida talabalar faksimilyar simulyatsiyalar, role-playing o'yinlari va jamoaviy muhokamalar orqali falsafiy g'oyalarni yanada chuqurroq o'zlashtirishlari mumkin bo'ladi.

“Axborot texnologiyalarining asosiy ta'lim ahamiyati shundaki, u o'qituvchi va talaba uchun deyarli cheksiz potensial imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan beqiyos yorqinroq multisensorli interfaol ta'lim muhitini yaratishga imkon beradi. An'anaviy texnik o'qitish vositalaridan farqli o'laroq, axborot texnologiyalari nafaqat o'quvchini katta hajmdagi bilimlar bilan to'ldirishga, balki o'quvchilarning intellektual, ijodiy

² Ochilova M.S., Xamroeva F.A. Xalqaro ta'lim platformalarini tahlili. - INTER EDUCATION & GLOBAL STUDY. №7, 2024. 329-bet.

qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga, yangi bilimlarni mustaqil ravishda egallashga, turli xil ma'lumotlar manbalari bilan ishlashga imkon beradi"³.

Falsafa ta'limida multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish talabalar uchun ta'lim jarayonini hayotiylikini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. O'qituvchilar falsafa fanining asosiy kategoriyalari hamda murakkab g'oyalarni videolar, audiolar va grafika yordamida oddiy va tushunarli tarzda taqdim etishlari mumkin bo'ladi. Xususan, YouTube va Ted-ed kabi platformalardagi mashhur falsafiy asarlar haqida qisqa videolar yoki tadqiqotlarni taqdim etish talabalar uchun qiziqarli va oson o'rganish imkonini beradi. "Multimedia vositalari ta'lim berishning samarali va istiqbolli quroli (instrumentlari) bo'lib, u o'qituvchiga an'anaviy ma'lumotlar manbaidan ko'ra keng ko'lamdagi ma'lumotlar massivini taqdim etish; ko'rgazmali va uyg'unlashgan holda nafaqat matn, grafiklar, sxemalar, balki ovoz, animatsiyalar, video va boshqalardan foydalanish; axborot turlarini ta'lim oluvchilarning qabul qilish (idrok etish) darajasi va mantiqiy o'rganishiga mos ravishda ketma-ketlikda tanlab olish imkoniyatini yaratadi"⁴. Falsafiy g'oyalarni grafiklar, diagrammalar, animatsiyalar va boshqa vizual vositalar yordamida ifodalash talabalarga ularni yanada yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

Falsafaning bahs mavzulari juda ko'p. Ularni talabalar bilan muhokama qilish talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmasini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Eng muhimi, bunday muhokamalar axborot texnologiyalari yordamida olib borilsa, talabalar o'z fikrlarini baham ko'rish, savollar berish va muhokama qilishda erkinlikka ega bo'lishadi. Online forumlar, Moodle va Google Classroom kabi platformalar orqali tashkil etiladigan onlayn muhokamalar talabalar o'rtasida dialogni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, falsafaning bahs-mavzularini bunday online forumlar, Moodle va Google Classroom kabi platformalar orqali o'tkazish yoki o'zaro aloqalar talabalarni bir-birining fikrini hurmat qilishga va tanqidiy fikrlashga undaydi. Onlayn muhokamalar va forumlarda faol ishtirok etish, talabalarda fikrlar xilma-xilligini shakllantirishga yordam beradi, yangi fikrlarni o'rganishga undaydi. Fikrlar xilma-xilligi, ya'ni ko'p fikrlarni bir joyga to'plash talabalarga mustaqil tahlil qilishga imkoniyat yaratadi.

Xulosa. Falsafa fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, ta'lim jarayonini samaradorligini ta'minlash bilan birga fanga innovatsion va interaktiv

³ Saidov D., Ismoilova A. Ta'lim jarayonida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ayrim dolzarb masalalari. - Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. VOLUME 1, ISSUE 10. 2021. 778-bet.

⁴ Gulmatova H.S. ta'limda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari. - Yosh olimlar ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari. 34-bet. [tps://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13334999](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13334999)

yondashishga yordam beradi. Axborot texnologiyalarining metodologiyalar talabalar uchun batafsil bilimlar olish imkonini yaratibgina qolmasdan, balki ularni axloqiy va falsafiy masalalarga chuqurroq yondashuvni rivojlantirishga hamda tanqidiy va tahliliy fikrlash ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishga ko‘maklashadi. O‘qituvchilar va tashkilotchilar axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali ta‘lim jarayonini yanada samarali, qiziqarli va interaktiv qilish imkoni oshadi.

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CHALLENGES IN CHOOSING MATERIALS FOR ESL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: *Selecting appropriate teaching materials is crucial for effective English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction. Educators face numerous challenges in this endeavor, impacting instruction quality and student learning outcomes. This article explores obstacles encountered when choosing ESL classroom materials, including alignment with learning objectives, cultural appropriateness, authenticity, learner-centeredness, accessibility, teacher training, and the need for continuous adaptation. The article further explores these challenges' impact on student motivation and achievement, proposing potential solutions and strategies.*

Keywords: **General:** *ESL materials, ESL instruction, materials selection, curriculum development, language teaching, second language acquisition, English language teaching, teaching resources, classroom materials.*

Introduction

Effective ESL instruction depends on selecting appropriate and engaging teaching materials. Materials form the curriculum's backbone, shaping student learning experiences and influencing their English language skill acquisition. However, choosing suitable ESL classroom materials is often challenging. Educators must navigate a complex landscape of commercially available textbooks, online resources, and authentic materials while considering learners' diverse needs, curriculum learning objectives, and the English language's ever-evolving nature. This article examines key challenges ESL instructors face in materials selection, exploring their impact on teaching and learning, and offering potential solutions and strategies.

Challenges in Choosing Materials for ESL Classrooms

Several interconnected challenges confront ESL educators when selecting teaching materials:

Alignment with Learning Objectives and Curriculum Requirements

A fundamental challenge is ensuring chosen materials align seamlessly with specific learning objectives and curriculum requirements (Nation, 2016). Many commercially available textbooks offer a generalized approach, often failing to address diverse ESL learners' unique needs and skill levels. For example, materials designed for general English proficiency may not sufficiently focus on academic English's specialized language demands, such as critical reading, academic writing, and research skills, crucial for students pursuing higher education. This mismatch can disconnect classroom instruction from real-world language skills required for academic success, leaving students ill-prepared for their future academic pursuits.

Conversely, materials focused too narrowly on specific skills might neglect holistic language proficiency development.

Cultural Appropriateness. Many ESL materials, particularly those developed primarily for native English-speaking contexts, often lack cultural appropriateness (Liddicoat & Crozet, 2001). They may fail to reflect learners' diverse backgrounds' cultural realities and experiences, potentially leading to cultural misunderstandings, irrelevant content, and a lack of student engagement. For instance, texts that predominantly feature Western cultural norms and values may alienate learners from other cultural backgrounds, hindering their understanding and motivation. Furthermore, the absence of diverse cultural perspectives can perpetuate stereotypes and create a sense of exclusion. Selecting culturally sensitive, inclusive, and representative materials is essential for fostering a positive and welcoming learning environment.

Authenticity. Another significant concern is the limited authenticity of many ESL materials (Tomlinson, 2010). Oversimplified language, contrived dialogues, and outdated information often characterize these materials, failing to prepare learners for real-world communication adequately. Authentic materials, such as academic journal articles, research papers, professional presentations, news articles, and even film clips or podcasts, expose learners to real-world English, enhancing critical thinking skills and developing their ability to understand and use language in authentic contexts. These materials also offer valuable insights into different communication genres and language use conventions in various settings. However, integrating authentic materials requires careful selection and adaptation to ensure appropriateness for learners' proficiency level and learning goals.

Learner-Centeredness

Many materials prioritize teacher-centered instruction, focusing on grammar and vocabulary drills with limited opportunities for student interaction, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Harmer, 2007). Effective materials should be learner-centered, encouraging active learning, independent research, and collaborative activities. They should provide opportunities for students to engage in meaningful communication, develop their own ideas, and apply language skills in authentic contexts. Materials should also cater to different learning styles and preferences, offering a variety of activities and tasks that appeal to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners.

Accessibility and Affordability

Accessibility and affordability also pose significant challenges. High textbook costs, limited online resource access, and insufficient library resources can hinder

effective teaching and learning, particularly in resource-constrained settings. This inequity in access can create significant learning opportunity disparities for students from different socioeconomic backgrounds. Educators need to explore alternative resources, such as open educational resources (OER) and freely available online materials, to ensure all students have access to quality learning materials, regardless of their financial circumstances.

Teacher Training

Inadequate teacher training in material evaluation and selection can exacerbate challenges (McDonough & Shaw, 2003). Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to critically evaluate materials, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and adapt them to meet learners' specific needs. This requires ongoing professional development opportunities that focus on materials analysis, curriculum development, and effective instructional strategies. Teachers should also be trained in creating their own materials and adapting existing materials to suit their students' specific needs and classroom context.

Adaptation to the Evolving Nature of English

The English language's rapidly evolving nature necessitates constant teaching material adaptation. The emergence of new technologies, changing communication patterns, and evolving academic demands necessitate continuous review and updating of teaching materials to remain current and relevant. Educators need to stay abreast of current language use trends and incorporate these changes into their teaching materials. This may involve supplementing textbooks with authentic online resources, using current news articles and social media content as teaching tools, and encouraging students to explore language's dynamic nature through various media.

Impact on Student Motivation and Achievement

The challenges outlined above can significantly impact student motivation and achievement. If materials are poorly aligned with learning objectives, culturally inappropriate, inauthentic, or overly teacher-centered, students may become disengaged and demotivated. They may struggle to see the materials' relevance to their lives and learning goals, leading to a decline in their interest in learning English. Furthermore, if materials are inaccessible or unaffordable, students may feel disadvantaged and discouraged. Conversely, when students are provided with high-quality, engaging, and relevant materials, they are more likely to be motivated and achieve academic success. They will feel valued, respected, and empowered to learn.

Potential Solutions and Strategies

Addressing materials selection challenges requires a multifaceted approach:

Needs Assessment

Conduct a thorough needs assessment to determine students' existing language skills, learning styles, cultural backgrounds, learning goals, and resource access. This information will inform material selection and adaptation.

Careful Evaluation

Develop criteria for evaluating materials, considering alignment with learning objectives, cultural appropriateness, authenticity, learner-centeredness, accessibility, and affordability.

Supplementation

Supplement commercially available textbooks with authentic materials, OER, and teacher-created resources to provide a more comprehensive and engaging learning experience.

Adaptation

Adapt existing materials to meet learners' specific needs and the classroom context. This may involve modifying activities, adding cultural notes, or simplifying language.

Technology Integration

Utilize technology to enhance materials and provide access to a wider range of resources. Explore online platforms, language learning apps, and digital tools to create interactive and engaging lessons.

Collaboration

Collaborate with other teachers to share resources and best practices in materials selection and adaptation.

Professional Development

Engage in ongoing professional development to stay abreast of current trends in materials development, language teaching methodology, and the evolving nature of the English language.

Conclusion

Selecting appropriate teaching materials is a complex and multifaceted task that requires careful consideration of various factors. By addressing the challenges outlined above, educators can ensure that their students have access to high-quality materials that are engaging, relevant, and effective in fostering language learning and academic success. This may involve a combination of strategies, including careful material evaluation, supplementing textbooks with authentic resources, incorporating technology effectively, and engaging in ongoing professional development. Ultimately, the goal is to create a dynamic and enriching learning environment that

empowers students to succeed in their academic pursuits and prepares them for real-world communication.

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CHALLENGES IN CONDUCTING VOCABULARY WITH MULTILEVEL ESL CLASSES

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Abstract: *Teaching vocabulary to English as a Second Language (ESL) student presents unique challenges, particularly in multilevel classrooms where learners possess varying levels of proficiency. This article explores the multifaceted challenges faced by educators in such settings, including addressing diverse learning needs, managing varied paces of acquisition, selecting appropriate vocabulary, and implementing effective pedagogical strategies. The article further discusses the impact of these challenges on student motivation and achievement, and proposes potential solutions and strategies for creating inclusive and effective vocabulary instruction for multilevel ESL learners.*

Keywords: *ESL vocabulary, vocabulary acquisition, multilevel classrooms, second language acquisition, ESL instruction, vocabulary knowledge disparity, pacing curriculum, vocabulary tiering.*

Annotation: *Vocabulary acquisition is a cornerstone of language learning, enabling learners to comprehend and express themselves effectively. However, teaching vocabulary in ESL classrooms, especially those comprising students with diverse proficiency levels, poses significant pedagogical challenges. Multilevel classrooms, characterized by learners with varying degrees of vocabulary knowledge, language skills, and learning styles, necessitate differentiated instruction and careful planning to ensure all students progress. This article delves into the specific challenges encountered by teachers in such classrooms, examining their impact on both students and educators, and suggesting practical strategies for navigating these complexities.*

Several interconnected challenges arise when teaching vocabulary in multilevel ESL classrooms:

Addressing Diverse Learning Needs: Students in multilevel classes often exhibit a wide range of vocabulary knowledge. Some may possess a basic understanding of common words, while others might have a more extensive vocabulary. This disparity makes it challenging to select appropriate vocabulary items and design activities that cater to all learners' needs. "Teachers must balance the need to introduce new vocabulary to some students while simultaneously reviewing and reinforcing previously learned words for others. Furthermore, learners may have different learning styles, requiring teachers to employ diverse teaching methods to accommodate visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners."¹ (p 34)

Managing Varied Paces of Acquisition: Students learn vocabulary at different rates. Some learners may grasp new words quickly, while others require more time and exposure. This variation in learning pace can create difficulties in pacing the

¹ Schmitt, N. (2000). *Vocabulary in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.

curriculum and ensuring that all students are keeping up with the material. Teachers must find ways to provide individualized support and differentiated practice to cater to learners' varying speeds of acquisition. This can be particularly challenging in large classes.

Selecting Appropriate Vocabulary: Choosing the right vocabulary to teach is crucial. In multilevel classes, teachers must consider the relevance of the vocabulary to students' lives, their academic needs, and their current level of English proficiency. “Introducing complex vocabulary can frustrate lower-level learners, while focusing solely on basic vocabulary can hinder the progress of more advanced students.”² (p. 214).

Teachers carefully need to curate vocabulary lists, considering frequency of use, contextual relevance, and the potential for students to apply the new words in meaningful communication

Implementing Effective Pedagogical Strategies: Teaching vocabulary effectively requires more than simply presenting lists of words and definitions.

Multilevel classrooms demand a variety of pedagogical strategies to engage learners with different learning styles and proficiency levels. Teachers need to employ techniques such as contextualization, visual aids, realia, games, and interactive activities to make vocabulary learning engaging and memorable. Moreover, they need to provide opportunities for students to use the new vocabulary in meaningful contexts through speaking, writing, and listening activities. Differentiating these activities to suit the various levels present in the classroom is a significant challenge.

Assessing Vocabulary Learning: Assessing vocabulary learning in multilevel classrooms can be complex. Teachers need to employ a variety of assessment methods to evaluate students' understanding of new words, including their meaning, form, and use. Furthermore, “assessments should be differentiated to reflect the different levels of proficiency within the class.”³ (p. 213) This can involve creating different versions of quizzes or tests, or using alternative assessment methods such as portfolios or oral presentations.

Impact on Student Motivation and Achievement: The challenges described above can significantly affect student motivation and achievement. Lower-level

² Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and methods in language teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

³ Coxhead, A. (2000). *A new academic word list*. *TESOL Quarterly*, 34(2), 213-233.

learners may feel overwhelmed and discouraged if the vocabulary is too difficult, while more advanced, students may become bored if the pace is too slow.

Creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment where all students feel challenged and supported is essential for fostering motivation and promoting vocabulary acquisition.

Potential Solutions and Strategies

Addressing the challenges of vocabulary instruction in multilevel ESL classrooms requires a multifaceted approach. The following strategies can be implemented:

Needs Assessment: Begin by conducting a thorough needs assessment to determine students' existing vocabulary knowledge, learning styles, and learning goals. This information is used to inform vocabulary selection and instructional strategies.

Differentiated Instruction: Implement differentiated instruction by providing different levels of support and “scaffolding to meet the diverse needs of learners. This might involve creating different versions of worksheets, providing individualized tutoring, or using tiered assignments.”⁴ (p. 145)

Vocabulary Tiering: Introduce vocabulary in tiers, focusing on high-frequency words that are essential for communication. This approach allows teachers to prioritize essential vocabulary for all learners while providing opportunities for more advanced students to expand their vocabulary knowledge.

Contextualization: Teach vocabulary in context by using stories, articles, and real-life examples. This helps learners understand the meaning of new words and how they are used in communication.

Visual Aids and Realia: Use “visual aids such as pictures, diagrams, and realia to make vocabulary learning more engaging and memorable.”

Interactive Activities: Incorporate interactive activities such as games, role-plays, and group work to provide students with opportunities to use new vocabulary in meaningful contexts.

Technology Integration: “Utilize technology to enhance vocabulary instruction.”⁵ (p. 289) Many online resources and apps that can be used to provide students with interactive vocabulary practice and personalized feedback.

⁴ Read, J. (2004). *Assessing vocabulary*. Cambridge University Press.

⁵ Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning vocabulary in a second language*. In J. C. Richards & W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice* (pp. 289-302). Cambridge University Press

Collaborative Learning: Encourage collaborative learning by having students work together in pairs or small groups. This allows learners to learn from each other and practice using new vocabulary in a supportive environment.

Regular Review and Recycling: Regularly “review and recycle previously learned vocabulary to reinforce learning and ensure that students retain the new words.”⁶ (p.178)

Ongoing Assessment: Use a variety of assessment methods to monitor student progress and identify areas where they need additional support.

Conclusion

Teaching vocabulary in multilevel ESL classrooms presents a complex set of challenges. However, by implementing the strategies discussed in this article, teachers can create inclusive and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all learners. By carefully selecting vocabulary, employing varied pedagogical techniques, and providing differentiated instruction, teachers can empower their students to develop the vocabulary skills they need to succeed in their academic and personal lives.

Further research is needed to explore the effectiveness of different vocabulary instruction strategies in multilevel ESL classrooms and to develop best practices for teaching vocabulary to learners with diverse needs.

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⁶ Thornbury, S. (2002). *How to teach vocabulary*. Pearson Education

THE RISE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN UZBEKISTAN: TRENDS, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article studies the growing influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in language learning and teaching, with a particular focus on Uzbekistan. It examines global trends in AI-powered educational tools such as ChatGPT and Duolingo, highlighting their impact on personalized learning and student engagement. The study also finds out about Uzbekistan's efforts to integrate AI into education, supported by recent government initiatives aimed at fostering AI development. Furthermore, statistical data from the State of Dev (2024) survey provides insights into the educational landscape, the role of AI-assisted learning, and the challenges faced by learners in Uzbekistan. The findings suggest that while AI significantly enhances language acquisition, the need for more localized AI-driven resources remains crucial. This research contributes to the discourse on AI in education by offering an analytical perspective on its implementation in a multilingual and evolving digital ecosystem.

Key words: artificial intelligence (AI) language learning, AI in education, personalized learning, AI initiatives, digital literacy, AI readiness index, Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), AI-Powered Tools.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has rapidly evolved from a niche technology to a cornerstone of modern innovation, influencing various sectors globally. According to a 2024 report by the International Data Corporation (IDC), AI is projected to contribute approximately \$19.9 trillion to the global economy by 2030, accounting for 3.5% of the worldwide Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This significant economic impact underscores AI's role in driving productivity and creating new revenue streams across industries ([Shirer, 2024](#)).

The transformative power of AI is evident in its diverse applications, ranging from healthcare and finance to transportation and education. In healthcare, AI algorithms assist in early disease detection and personalized treatment plans. The financial sector leverages AI for fraud detection and algorithmic trading, while the transportation industry benefits from AI through advancements in autonomous vehicles and optimized logistics. In education, AI-driven adaptive learning systems personalize content delivery, enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes.

However, the rapid integration of AI also presents challenges. A 2025 report by The Guardian highlights concerns such as potential job displacement due to automation, environmental impacts from energy-intensive data centers, and ethical

considerations surrounding deepfakes and cybersecurity threats. These issues underscore the need for comprehensive strategies to manage AI's societal implications responsibly ([Milmo, 2025](#)).

AI Usage in Uzbekistan: Growth and Adoption

In Uzbekistan, AI adoption is gaining momentum as the government takes proactive steps to integrate AI technologies into the country's development strategy. With the goal of making AI-based products and services worth \$1.5 billion by 2030, Uzbekistan's AI Development Strategy aims to establish 10 scientific laboratories and enhance high-performance computing infrastructure (Daryo.uz, 2024). Additionally, Uzbekistan has made significant strides in its Government AI Readiness Index, improving by 17 positions and ranking 70th globally in 2024 (Daryo.uz, 2024). The establishment of AI technology centers and supportive legislative frameworks are part of the country's broader effort to foster innovation and integrate AI into key sectors like healthcare, agriculture, and finance.

This growing adoption of AI in Uzbekistan highlights the country's ambition to leverage AI for economic growth, public service enhancement, and educational advancement. As the global landscape shifts towards AI-driven solutions, Uzbekistan is positioning itself as a key player in this digital transformation, ensuring that the benefits of AI are accessible and impactful across all sectors.

AI in Education and Language Learning

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing education and language learning globally, with tools like ChatGPT and Duolingo leading the transformation. ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, offers interactive conversational experiences, enhancing language acquisition through real-time dialogue and personalized feedback. Duolingo, a widely used language learning platform, employs AI algorithms to tailor lessons to individual learning paces and styles, making language learning more engaging and effective.

In Uzbekistan, the government is actively integrating AI into the education sector. In October 2024, Uzbekistan adopted a Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies until 2030, aiming to increase the volume of AI-based software products and services to \$1.5 billion by 2030. The strategy includes establishing 10 scientific laboratories focused on AI development and launching high-performance computing servers ([uzdaily.com](#)).

Additionally, in 2023, UNICEF, in partnership with the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan, piloted Eduten, a digital math learning platform based on AI. The pilot involved 527 school children in Tashkent-city and Tashkent

region, replacing one regular math lesson per week with Eduten. The results showed a remarkable increase in learning outcomes, with an average improvement of 16.9% in mathematics skills ([unicef.org](https://www.unicef.org)).

These initiatives reflect Uzbekistan's commitment to leveraging AI to enhance educational quality and accessibility, aligning with global trends in AI-driven learning.

The education landscape in Uzbekistan reveals diverse academic backgrounds and a strong inclination toward self-directed learning, particularly in the IT sector. According to a survey conducted by *State of Dev* in 2024, many developers attended public universities (25.8%) or specialized IT academies (20%), while a significant proportion (37.3%) are self-taught, reflecting the growing trend of self-guided skill acquisition. Additionally, technical bootcamps and private schools contribute to the education system, with 6.7% and 1.4% of respondents, respectively, citing these as their sources of training.

Despite mixed opinions on the quality of the Uzbek educational system, a notable 65.7% of respondents feel that it provides only a basic foundation, prompting many to seek additional resources for further skill development. The survey also revealed that English is widely spoken, with 94% of respondents proficient in reading and writing in the language, followed by Uzbek (92.8%) and Russian (73.7%), ensuring access to global learning resources. Nearly 50% of respondents indicated that English is not a barrier to learning new technologies, suggesting a high level of technological literacy among Uzbek learners.

When it comes to preferred learning platforms, YouTube (85.8%) and official documentation (64.8%) dominate, followed by AI assistants like ChatGPT (58.1%), which has gained popularity for assisting learners in acquiring new skills. Local-language content remains a concern for over 60% of respondents, who desire more Uzbek-language resources to improve accessibility and engagement in their learning journey.

The data presented in this section was gathered through the *State of Dev* survey, which analyzed the educational backgrounds, language proficiency, and learning platform preferences of 415 IT professionals and developers in Uzbekistan ([State of Dev, 2024](#)). The survey provides key insights into the current state of education in Uzbekistan, emphasizing the role of self-directed learning and digital tools in skill development within the IT sector.

Government Initiatives and AI Infrastructure

Uzbekistan has demonstrated a strong commitment to advancing artificial intelligence (AI) through comprehensive strategies and significant improvements in global readiness rankings.

In October 2024, the Uzbek government approved the “Artificial Intelligence Development Strategy for 2023-2030,” aiming to bolster the nation’s AI capabilities. Key objectives of this strategy include: - Economic growth: elevating the market value of AI-based software products and services to \$1.5 billion by 2030. - Public services enhancement: increasing the share of AI-driven services on the Unified Portal of Interactive State Services (my.gov.uz) to 10%. - Research and infrastructure development: establishing 10 scientific laboratories dedicated to AI research and deploying high-performance computing servers to support complex AI computations. These initiatives underscore Uzbekistan's dedication to integrating AI across various sectors, including healthcare, agriculture, and public administration.

Government AI Readiness Index

Reflecting the impact of its strategic initiatives, Uzbekistan advanced 17 positions in the 2024 Government AI Readiness Index, securing the 70th spot globally. This index, published by Oxford Insights, evaluates countries based on 40 indicators across three categories: government institutions, technology sector, and data and infrastructure. In the South and Central Asia region, Uzbekistan ranks third, following India and Turkey. Notably, the country achieved a perfect score of 100 in the "Vision" category, significantly surpassing the global average of 42.55, highlighting its clear strategic direction in AI development (uzdaily.uz). These developments illustrate Uzbekistan's proactive approach to fostering a robust AI ecosystem, positioning the nation as a regional leader in AI readiness and implementation.

Challenges and opportunities

AI is not just a system for processing human speech; it serves as a key driver in integrating flipped learning methodologies, enhancing student engagement, and facilitating automated assessment (Ali, 2020). These technologies offer adaptive learning experiences by providing personalized feedback, intelligent tutoring, and access to vast linguistic resources (Weng & Chiu, 2023). In Uzbekistan, where AI adoption in education is expanding, such innovations play a crucial role in bridging language barriers and improving digital learning platforms.

Moreover, AI-powered systems assist both learners and educators by automating administrative tasks, enabling adaptive assessments, and fostering a more efficient online learning environment (Seo et al., 2021). Given the increasing reliance on AI-

powered tools in Uzbekistan, particularly among students and IT professionals (State of Dev Uzbekistan, 2024), the role of AI in shaping language education is expected to grow significantly.

Despite its vast potential, AI in language learning also presents several challenges, particularly concerning privacy, data security, and teacher preparedness (Woo & Choi, 2021). Without proper safeguards, students' personal data could be at risk. For example, if an educational institution implements an AI-powered tutoring system without strong security measures, a cyberattack could lead to student data being compromised and misused for unauthorized purposes.

Another key concern is the lack of sufficient training and awareness among educators, which can hinder the effective integration of AI tools in the classroom. Some teachers may be hesitant to incorporate AI due to uncertainties about its reliability or concerns over academic integrity. The ease of copying and pasting AI-generated responses raises questions about the authenticity of student work, potentially impacting the quality of learning (Godwin-Jones, 2022). However, with proper training and a deeper understanding of AI's role in education, teachers can leverage these tools more effectively to enhance language learning.

Addressing these challenges requires a balanced approach—ensuring strong data protection policies while equipping educators with the necessary skills to integrate AI responsibly. A comprehensive evaluation of both the benefits and potential risks of AI in language education is essential for creating a more secure and effective learning environment.

Artificial intelligence is playing an increasingly significant role in transforming language education in Uzbekistan. As the country continues to invest in digitalization and education reform, AI-powered tools are becoming essential in helping students and professionals enhance their language skills. The integration of AI in language learning offers numerous benefits, particularly in a multilingual nation like Uzbekistan, where proficiency in Uzbek, Russian, and English is crucial for academic and professional success.

1. Personalized and Adaptive Learning

AI-driven platforms such as ChatGPT, Duolingo, and Google Translate provide personalized learning experiences tailored to individual learners' needs. These tools analyze users' strengths and weaknesses and adapt the curriculum accordingly, ensuring that students progress at their own pace. This is particularly beneficial in Uzbekistan, where language learners have varying levels of proficiency and may require customized learning pathways.

2. Accessibility and Flexibility

AI-powered language learning tools make education more accessible to students across Uzbekistan, including those in remote areas. Online AI-based platforms eliminate geographical barriers, allowing learners to access high-quality language instruction from anywhere with an internet connection. This flexibility is especially valuable for working professionals, university students, and schoolchildren who need to balance their studies with other responsibilities.

3. Enhanced Pronunciation and Speaking Skills

AI applications such as speech recognition software help learners improve their pronunciation and speaking fluency. Tools like Google Assistant and AI-driven language tutors provide real-time feedback on pronunciation, helping users refine their spoken language skills. In Uzbekistan, where English proficiency is increasingly in demand, AI-driven pronunciation training is a valuable asset for students preparing for international exams like IELTS and CEFR.

4. Real-time Translation and Multilingual Support

Uzbekistan's linguistic diversity makes AI-powered translation tools highly useful for students and professionals. Machine translation services like Google Translate and DeepL assist learners in quickly understanding and translating complex texts between Uzbek, Russian, and English. These tools also support government initiatives aimed at improving multilingual education and fostering international collaboration.

5. Engagement through Gamification and AI Tutors

AI-driven platforms incorporate gamification techniques to make language learning more engaging. Apps like Duolingo use AI algorithms to create interactive lessons that motivate learners through rewards and challenges. Additionally, AI-powered chatbots act as virtual tutors, providing instant explanations and personalized support. This approach is gaining popularity in Uzbekistan, where students increasingly prefer digital tools over traditional learning methods.

6. AI-powered Assessments and Feedback

AI tools can automate language assessments, providing immediate and detailed feedback to learners. AI-powered writing assistants, such as Grammarly, help students refine their writing skills by identifying grammar mistakes, suggesting improvements, and enhancing overall clarity. In Uzbekistan's education system, where standardized language exams are crucial for university admissions and job opportunities, AI-driven assessments are becoming a valuable resource for students.

Potential Risks and Ethical Concerns of Using AI in Language Learning

The integration of AI in language learning presents various challenges and ethical concerns that require careful consideration. While AI-powered tools are increasingly shaping education, particularly in language acquisition, they may gradually reduce human interaction—an essential component of effective language learning, especially in cross-cultural communication (Tanabe, 2021). Engaging with others fosters creativity in language use, enabling learners to participate in discussions and develop a deeper understanding of linguistic and cultural nuances (Muho & Kurani, 2014).

One major concern is that as AI automates repetitive tasks, it may inadvertently weaken critical thinking and decision-making skills (Ahmad et al., 2023). Unlike traditional classrooms, where students actively engage in discussions, seek clarification from teachers, and learn collaboratively, AI-driven learning environments can become isolating. In-person interactions play a crucial role in character development, civic engagement, and social learning, all of which contribute to a well-rounded education.

Moreover, the increasing reliance on AI in education raises concerns about its potential to diminish meaningful teacher-student relationships. While AI can enhance learning by providing personalized instruction and feedback, it cannot fully replicate the depth of human connection that fosters motivation, empathy, and social skills. Therefore, while AI-powered language learning tools offer valuable support, it is essential to strike a balance between technology and traditional learning approaches to preserve the benefits of human interaction in language education (De La Vall & Araya, 2023).

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence has significantly transformed language education, making it more accessible and efficient. AI-powered tools assist learners in overcoming linguistic barriers, enabling them to practice, receive feedback, and enhance their skills in an interactive manner. Mastering a new language offers a range of cognitive and academic benefits, including enhanced memory, creativity, and overall brain development. However, language acquisition is a complex and time-consuming endeavor that requires consistent effort, patience, and perseverance. Learners often encounter various challenges, from understanding grammatical structures to achieving fluency and refining pronunciation. Addressing these difficulties is essential to ensure effective language learning. The integration of AI in language learning is revolutionizing education in Uzbekistan by making language acquisition more efficient, accessible, and engaging. As the government continues to promote

digitalization and AI development, the use of AI-powered language tools is expected to grow, helping students, professionals, and educators improve their linguistic skills in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

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VOCABULARY AND ITS TYPES

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Abstract: *Vocabulary plays a crucial role in language acquisition and communication, serving as the foundation for effective expression and comprehension. This paper explores the concept of vocabulary, its significance, and its various classifications. Vocabulary can be broadly categorized into receptive (passive) and productive (active) vocabulary, with the former referring to words understood while listening or reading and the latter to words used in speaking and writing. Additionally, vocabulary can be divided into general and specialized vocabulary, where general vocabulary consists of commonly used words, while specialized vocabulary pertains to specific fields or disciplines. This study emphasizes the importance of a structured approach to vocabulary instruction to facilitate effective language acquisition.*

Key words: *vocabulary, basic vocabulary, high-frequency vocabulary, low-frequency vocabulary, communication.*

Vocabulary represents the complete set of words within a language or specific field of knowledge that an individual knows and can use. It is a fundamental component of language proficiency and communication competence. Vocabulary knowledge is fundamental to language proficiency, it plays a pivotal role in articulating thoughts, expressing ideas, and comprehending information

Vocabulary has been studied in exploration for further than half a century. It is one of the parcels that are specific to the language that has to be learned. Vocabulary then includes the words (verbal particulars) and their meanings together with their syntactic orders and subcategories conditions. Some linguists relate to vocabulary using the term wordbook or internal wordbook. Vocabulary isn't only a list of words. It is a system bedded in language. It's a part of any language that is, just like the alphabet, defined by experts in colourful ways. Nowadays the significance of vocabulary is appreciated both in alternate language exploration and in language tutoring. Vocabulary is defined as the collection of words that a person knows and uses. It can also refer to a list or compilation of words or phrases, usually organized in alphabetical order along with their definitions or explanations. Additionally, vocabulary is often referred to as word stock, lexis, or lexicon.

Vocabulary is a crucial part of anyone's life and the importance of vocabulary can be described as follows:

- 1) Vocabulary is critical for communication and expression
- 2) Vocabulary forms the basis of reading comprehension

- 3) Linguistic vocabulary and thinking vocabulary work parallel
- 4) Vocabulary also forms a basis for judgment many times
- 5) For conveying anything, vocabulary is important

All the words that form a language to be understood by a specific person or a group of people can be considered vocabulary. Vocabulary in English can be classified into two types, namely- active and passive. The words that we use and understand in day-to-day language are called active vocabulary, while the ones which we know but use rarely are considered to be passive vocabulary.

Vocabulary is described with the following three tiers:

1. Basic Vocabulary

The basic words form the first tier of vocabulary. These kinds of words normally have a single meaning and they do not need instruction. Early reading words, sight words, adjectives, verbs, and nouns are depicted in this tier. This tier is comprised of 8000-word families in English.

2. High-frequency Vocabulary

It can also be called the multiple-meaning vocabulary tier, this tier comprises words used in different types of domains, adult communication, literature, etc. It influences reading and speaking. 7000-word families comprise this tier. The characteristics of tier-two words are as follows: it has multiple meanings, are vital for reading comprehension, have typical mature language, have descriptive vocabulary, and have a diverse environment that uses these words and are used for direct instruction.

3. Low-frequency Vocabulary

The words that are used only when specifically required or in a particular domain, like weather, technology, geographical region, occupation, hobbies, school, etc., comprise this tier. About four million words in vocabulary in English comprise this tier.

A great deal of studies and books concerning vocabulary instruction have increased. Thornbury [2002, p. 4] claimed; "This is incompletely due to the recent computerized databases of words (or corpora), and incompletely due to the development of new approaches to language tutoring which are much further word-centred, similar as the verbal approach". Burns and Richards (2018) emphasized the significance of aptitude tests in Alternate Language Acquisition (SLA). Original literacy draws on conscious literacy capacities, similar to memory, logic, and logic capacities assessed through aptitude tests in SLA. Mayer (2019) mentioned the

influence of multimedia on learners' deep learning. The impact of deep literacy was more from words and pictures than from words alone.

As Nation (2001) emphasizes, "Vocabulary knowledge enables language use, language use enables the increase of vocabulary knowledge, knowledge of the world enables the increase of vocabulary knowledge and language use, and so on." Beck, McKeown, & Kucan (2002) propose a three-tier model of vocabulary:

- Tier 1: Basic, everyday words
- Tier 2: High-frequency words across contexts
- Tier 3: Domain-specific technical terms

Henriksen (1999) suggests three dimensions of vocabulary knowledge:

1. Partial to precise understanding
2. Depth of knowledge
3. Receptive to productive ability

Anderson & Freebody's (1981) seminal work proposes that vocabulary knowledge encompasses:

- Breadth (number of words known)
- Depth (quality of word knowledge)
- Automaticity (speed of access)

As Nagy & Scott (2000) emphasize, "Vocabulary knowledge is complex and multidimensional," requiring varied approaches to teaching and assessment. Meara (2009) further argues that vocabulary knowledge should be viewed as an interconnected network rather than a simple collection of words. This theoretical framework has significant implications for language pedagogy and research. As Zimmerman (1997) notes, understanding these distinctions helps in developing effective vocabulary instruction strategies.

The types of vocabulary can be classified based on spoken and written vocabulary. Children who are eager to learn language start learning vocabulary-building through listening and speaking, even before writing and reading. Every type of vocabulary has its different aims and purposes. However, the improvement of one type of vocabulary facilitates another. The types of vocabulary are discussed briefly below.

1. Listening Vocabulary

Listening vocabulary contains words that we understand through hearing. Learning new words is a continuous process, and by the time you reach adulthood, almost fifty thousand words are understood and recognized by you. Deaf people can be detected with visual listening vocabulary for learning.

2. Speaking Vocabulary

Speaking vocabulary consists of words that we speak. It has a limit of around 5000 to 10000 words. learners use these words for giving instructions and conversations. The number of words in this category is comparatively lesser than the listening vocabulary.

3. Reading Vocabulary

The primary ingredient of vocabulary building is reading. Reading grows and develops vocabulary. The words we learn while reading a text are termed reading vocabulary. We can understand words through reading vocabulary even if we do not use it when speaking vocabulary.

4. Writing Vocabulary

Words we recoup while expressing ourselves through writing are termed writing vocabulary. Writing vocabulary is typically influenced by the words we can spell. We find it easy to express ourselves verbally, through facial expression or intonation, but writing vocabulary depends on our vocabulary expertise.

5. Final Vocabulary

Richard Rorty discovered the term 'Final Vocabulary'. It is a collection, set, or group of words that every person applies to justify their actions, beliefs, and lives. The final vocabulary comprises words a person avails to praise, contempt, express deep feelings, hopes, doubts and so on. These categories can help and contribute to an individual's overall lexical competence. Having acknowledged these differences would be essential for language teaching, learning, and assessment.

All in all, vocabulary plays a crucial role in language use, serving as the core of language skills. It functions as the foundation for communication, reflects social realities, enhances emotions, and predicts academic abilities. Furthermore, receptive and productive vocabularies, as well as active and passive vocabulary, significantly contribute to language skill performance. Additionally, the principles of teaching vocabulary—specifically breadth and depth—along with teaching and learning vocabulary materials, are linked to students' vocabulary mastery. Therefore, it is essential for vocabulary instruction to be straightforward, connected to both students' existing knowledge and new concepts, and based on high-frequency words.

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ANDRAGOGIK TA'LIMDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATISHNING O'ZIGA XOS USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada androgogik ta'limda ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilarga ularning yoshiga mos usullar bilan o'rgatish haqida so'z yuritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Andragogika, kasbiy rivojlanish, refleksiya, interaktiv topshiriqlar, "Two Truths and a Lie", "Human Bingo", simulyatsiyalar, tanqidiy fikrlashga, "ekspert", konkret.*

Mamlakatimizda barcha uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlar, o'quvchi yoshlar, talabalar va katta yoshlilar uchun ham bir qancha shart-sharoitlar yaratilib berilmoqda. Yurtimizda barcha yoshdagilarning bilim va salohiyatini rivojlantirish uchun ularning yoshiga qaramasdan chuqur bilim berish maqsadida ko'plab chora-tadbirlar ko'rilmoqda. "Har kim ta'lim olish huquqiga ega. Davlat uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi, uning har xil turlari va shakllari, davlat va nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlari rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi. Davlat maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiyani rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratadi. Davlat bepul umumiy o'rta ta'lim va boshlang'ich professional ta'lim olishni kafolatlaydi. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim majburiydir. Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya, umumiy o'rta ta'lim davlat nazoratidadir. Ta'lim tashkilotlarida alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlariga ega bo'lgan bolalar uchun inklyuziv ta'lim va tarbiya ta'minlanadi." [1; 5]

Misol sifatida, ta'lim va bilimning jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi o'rni, ayniqsa xorijiy tillarni o'rganishning muhimligini ko'p marotaba ta'kidlab o'tilgan. Katta yoshlilarga ingliz tilini o'rgatish masalasidagi fikrlar quyidagicha umumlashtirilishi mumkin: Bilim olish uchun hech qachon kech emas. Har qanday yoshda o'qish va o'z ustida ishlash insonni rivojlantiradi. Bilimli inson – kuchli inson. Yangi bilim va tillarni egallash har bir kishiga jamiyatda munosib o'rin topishga yordam beradi. Ta'lim hamma uchun ochiq bo'lishi kerak – yoshlar uchun ham, keksalar uchun ham. Bekorga xalqimiz "Beshikdan, qabrgacha ilm izla", deb aytishmagan. Bilim va tajriba yosh bilan chegaralanmaydi. Zamonaviy dunyoda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun xorijiy tillarni, xususan, ingliz tilini o'rganish muhim. Bu o'zaro tushunish, bilim almashish va taraqqiyot yo'lida muhim omildir.

Andragogika - pedagogikaning yoshi kattalarni o'qitish, ta'lim berish nazariyasi va amaliyoti bilan shug'ullanadigan sohasi. «Andragogika» tushunchasi ilmiy atama

sifatida 1833-yilda nemis pedagog-tarixchisi A.Kapp tomonidan fanga kiritilgan. Agar «Pedagogika» soʻzi bilan yonma-yon, oʻxshash tarzda talqin etilsa kelib chiqishi grekcha soʻzlardan (andros-erkak, odam; agogeyn-yetaklash) iborat ekanligi oydinlashadi. Soʻzma-soʻz tarjima qilinsa, andragogika bu - «katta odamni yetaklash» dir. [2; 182] U kattalarning taʼlim ehtiyojlari, motivlari va qobiliyatlarini oʻrganadi va oʻquv jarayonini ularga moslashtirish usullarini ishlab chiqadi.

“Katta yoshdagilar taʼlimi har doim, insonning butun hayoti kontekstida koʻrib chiqiladi, bu yerda “universitet” sifatida oʻquv qoʻllanmalari, oʻquv auditoriyalari va kutubxonalardan tashqari, hamkasblar, hamfikrlar, doʻstlar, yaqin kishilar, farzandlar va ommaviy axborot vositalari, umuman olganda “hayot maktabi” nazarda tutiladi.” [3; 31-32] Ushbu taʼlim dasturida katta yoshlilarni oʻqitish oʻqituvchidan katta sabr va malaka talab etadi. Qaysidir maʼnoda dars davomida oʻqituvchi ham maʼlumot oladi. Chunki katta yoshli oʻrganuvchilar oʻzlarining kasblariga tegishli soʻzlarni yoki oʻzlari qiziqqan mavzu doirasida oʻrganishadi. Chet tili mukammal holda, grammatik qoidalar va soʻzlar qoʻllash usullari, qisqa qilib aytganda, mayda ikir-chikirigacha oʻrgatilmaydi. Ularga faqat qisqa va loʻnda va shuningdek, tegishli qoidalar oʻrgatiladi. Oʻrganuvchilarning sohasiga qarab, dars turi va uni qanday tashkil qilish ham oʻzgaradi.

Kattalarga ingliz tilini oʻrgatishda ularning hissiyotlarini tushuna bilish va ularning yoshiga, qiziqishlariga va hozirgi kundagi kasbiga mos ravishda darslarni tashkillashtirish muhim rol oʻynaydi. Oʻrganishning bir necha turlari mavjud; yaʼni baʼzi bir turdagi oʻrganuvchilar biror narsani yasab yoki guruh bilan ishlab oʻrganadi, boshqa birlari esa eshitib, maʼlumotni toʻla holicha emas, unga kimdir tushuntirib bersagina, oddiy soʻzlar bilan ifodalasa tushunadi, yoki koʻrib, vazifa va topshiriqlarni bajarsagina tushunadigan oʻrganuvchilar ham mavjud. Har bir kishi turli xil xarakterga ega. Baʼzi birlari juda ham jiddiy, qiyin muammoli masalalarni yechishga usta boʻlishadi, bunday odamlarni darsga diqqatini qaratish uchun oʻzini sohasini misol sifatida keltirib foydalansak boʻladi. Bu turdagi oʻrganuvchilarga ingliz tilini oʻrgatishda kundalik hayotimiz davomida sodir boʻladigan holatlar va vaziyatlar orqali darsga boʻlgan qiziqishini oshirish mumkin.

“Inson jismoniy rivojlanishini diagnoz qilish ancha oson kechadi, buning uchun ayrim mashqlar bajarilgach, uning natijasiga binoan xulosa chiqarish mumkin. Lekin ruhiy, maʼnaviy, ijtimoiy rivojlanishni diagnostika qilish mashaqqatli faoliyatning mahsulasi hisoblanadi. Bu maqsadda qoʻllanayotgan metodikalar muayyan darajada murakkab boʻlib, har doim ham toʻgʻri natija beraveradi, deb xulosa chiqarish, shoshilinch qaror qabul qilish noxush oqibatlariga olib keladi. Pedagogik amaliyotda

pedagog-psixologlar va o'qituvchilar shaxsning alohida sifatlarini o'rganadilar, lekin olingan natijalarga asoslangan holda, rivojlanishning barcha tarkiblariga umumiy baho berishga har doim ham musharraf bo'lavermaydilar. Chunki tajriba uzluksizligini ta'minlash integrativ yondashishni taqozo etadi, ko'p omillik tahlilgina uning yechimiga ijobiy ta'sir etadi, xolos" [4; 38-42]. Yuqorida aytilganidek, pedagog ta'lim berish bilan bir qatorda, psixolog bo'lishi ham darkor. Chunki o'qituvchi o'rganuvchilarning psixologik holatini ham inobatga olishi kerak.

Yoshi katta o'rganuvchilarning eng katta muammosi bu – uyalish. Mana shu sabab tufayli, ularning o'rganish jarayoni kichik yoshli o'rganuvchilarga qaraganda sekinroq davom etadi. Inson bolaligida biron til yoki mahorat darslarini o'rgansa, unda tushunish jarayoni ancha tez bo'ladi. Dars davomida biron notanish va talaffuz qilish oson bo'lmagan so'zni yoshi kattalardan shu so'zning ma'nosini yoki qanday talaffuz qilishni so'ralsa, ular biroz ikkilanib, javob berishadi yoki umuman javob berishmaydi. Agar biron so'z yoki jumlani noto'g'ri talaffuz qilsa yoki tarjima qilsa, boshqalarning oldida uyatli holat bo'lishidan cho'chib, o'zlarini ortga tortishadi. Bu esa har ikki tomon, ya'ni o'qituvchi va o'rganuvchi uchun juda qiyin vaziyat. Dars davomida o'rganuvchilarni o'zi bilan bir xil bilim darajadagi va agar imkoni bo'lsa, teng yoshli kishi bilan sherik qilish qo'yish manfaatli bo'ladi. Yoshiga qaramasdan, ba'zi o'rganuvchilar energiyaga boy bo'ladi. Shunaqa o'rganuvchilarni kamgap, kamsuqum va xato qilishdan qo'rqadigan odamlarni birgalikda guruh qilib qo'yish katta ehtimol bilan foydali bo'ladi. Pedagogik mahoratga ega bo'lgan o'qituvchilar barcha turdagi o'quvchilarga yordam berishlari kerak. Dars davomida ular bilan ko'proq ishlashi, ularni gapirtirishga harakat qilishi kerak. Bunday turdagi o'rganuvchilar "Agar noto'g'ri gapirsam, qolganlar ustimdan kulishadi, meni mazxara qilishadi", deb qo'rqishadi, uyalishadi. Aksariyat bunday o'rganuvchilarning yoshligida oila-a'zolari uni hech qachon tinglamasligi, uning fikrlarini eshitmasligi, yoki eshitsa ham kichik xato uchun ham tanbeh beraverishi bu odamlarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini sustlashtiradi. Bunday katta yoshli o'rganuvchilar bilan ko'p holatlarda alohida ham shug'ullanish zarur. Ularga ko'proq rango-rang topshiriqlardan foydalangan holatda darsni tashkillashtirish zarur. Dars davomida har xil xarakterga ega bo'lgan o'rganuvchilarni birdek jalb etish uchun o'qituvchida ularga xos barcha turdagi mashqlar bo'lishi talab etiladi.

Chet tilini o'rganish har qanday zamonda va davrda muhim o'rin egallaydi. Chunki o'rta yoshidagi o'rganuvchilar bu davrda o'z tilida ham nutqiy faoliyatini allaqachon shakllantirgan va bu til bo'yicha "ekspert" darajasi davrida bo'lishadi. Ingliz tilini o'rganishda ham uning fonetik tomonlarini aslicha bilgan holatda

o'rganishadi. Bunda o'qituvchining asosiy vazifasi o'rganuvchilarga ingliz tilidagi so'zlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qilishni o'rgatish, biror marta bo'lsa ham qaysidir so'zni noto'g'ri holatda talaffuz qilmasligi talab etiladi. O'rganuvchilar juda ham ziyrak bo'ladi va o'qituvchining har bir gapini to'g'ri deb bilgan holatda undan noto'g'ri bo'lsa ham qo'llashi mumkin.

“Seminar ishtirokchilarning umidlari va maqsadlariga muvofiq tarzda o'tishi uchun ularning qiziqishlarini aniqlash zarur. Seminar ishtirokchilariga ularning umidlari (ular seminardan kutayotgan natija) to'g'risida savol berib, o'zimizga kerak axborotni olishimiz, shu bilan birga, seminarda faol ishtirok etishga qiziqtirish, natijalarning muvaffaqiyati uchun o'z mas'uliyatlarini anglashlariga yordam berishimiz mumkin. Seminarining bu beshinchi ishtirokchilariga boshqa kishilarning muammolari, vaziyatlari, ichki dunyosi va pozitsiyalariga moslashishga yordam beradi”. Dars davomida tushuntirishni osonlashtirish, o'tilgan mavzuni mustahkamlash va darsni qiziqarliroq qilish maqsadida turli xil o'yinlar va interaktiv topshiriqlar berish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Quyida yoshi katta o'rganuvchilarga mos keluvchi bir nechta o'yin va topshiriqlarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

“Ikki haqiqat va bitta yolg'on (Two Truths and a Lie)”: Har bir ishtirokchi o'zlari haqida 2 ta to'g'ri va 1 ta noto'g'ri fakt aytadi, boshqalar noto'g'risini topadi. Bu o'yinni har qanday mavzu va holatga moslashtirish oson. Bu orqali katta yoshlilar bir-birlari haqida ma'lumotga ham ega bo'ladi.

“Human Bingo (Inson lotereyasi)”: Barchaga faktlar yozilgan lotereya kartalari beriladi, faktlarga mos keladigan odamlar topilishi kerak bo'ladi. Bu turdagi o'yinni sifat so'z turkumini o'rganish davomida qo'llash mumkin. Masalan, lotereya kartalariga insonning fe'l-atvori yoki tashqi ko'rinishini ifodalovchi sifatlarni yozish mumkin. Bu orqali o'rganuvchilar ham inson xususiyatlarini ifodalovchi sifatlarni qanday qo'llashni o'rganishadi, ham bir-birlari haqida yanada yaxshiroq bilib olishadi. Bu orqali sog'lom raqobat va guruh bo'lib birgalikda ishlash imkonini beradi.

Uchar koptok mashg'uloti – bu mashg'ulotda o'rganuvchilar o'qituvchilari tomonidan uzatilgan to'pni ushlab olishi va berilgan savolga javob berishlari lozim. Bolalar bu mashg'ulot orqali ziyraklikdan tashqari, chaqqonlikdan ham foydalanishadi. Chunki, kim to'pni ushlagina, savolga javob berishlari mumkin. Shuningdek, bu o'yinda biz to'pni ushlab uchun harakat qilganimizda, bir vaqtning o'zida biz zerikishni ham yo'qotishimiz mumkin. Bu o'yin yoshlikni eslatuvchi mashg'ulot bo'lganligi sababli, hammaga birdek yoqishi aniq.

Rolli o'yinlar va simulyatsiyalar:

“Mijoz bilan muomala”: Ikki kishilik va undan ortiq guruhlar bilan birgalikda haqiqiy hayot voqealarini mashq qilish. Biz har kunlik hayotimiz davomida tez-tez uchrab turadigan holatlar va vaziyatlarni dars jarayoniga ko‘chirish orqali chet tilida har qanday holatlarda ishlatiladigan so‘zlar va iboralarni o‘rganishimiz va qo‘llay olishimiz mumkin.

“Muammoli vaziyatlar”: Guruh muammolarni hal qilish bo‘yicha yechim taklif qiladi. Bu shuningdek o‘rganuvchilarni tanqidiy fikrlashga ham o‘rgatadi. Odatiy muammolarni ingliz tili yoki boshqa chet tilda tarjima qilib, uni ishlatish va shuningdek, u muammoga yechim bera olish o‘rganuvchilarni til bo‘yicha mahoratini va qiziqishini oshiradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, katta yoshdagilarni o‘qitish ularning hayotiy tajribasi, o‘z-o‘zini yo‘naltirishi va amaliy maqsadlarini tan oladigan o‘ylangan va moslashuvchan yondashuvni talab qiladi. Samarali usullar motivatsion o‘quv muhitini yaratish, faol ishtirokni rag‘batlantirish, real misollardan foydalanish va texnologiyadan foydalanishni o‘z ichiga oladi. Bundan tashqari, andragogiya tamoyillarini tushunish, masalan, avtonomiya, dolzarblik va o‘quvchilarning oldingi bilimlarini hurmat qilish - mazmunli va samarali o‘rganish tajribasini shakllantirishda juda muhimdir. Ushbu moslashtirilgan strategiyalarga e’tibor qaratgan holda, o‘qituvchilar katta yoshdagi o‘rganuvchilarni kuchaytirishlari mumkin, ularga shaxsiy o‘sish va kasbiy rivojlanishga hissa qo‘shadigan yangi bilim va ko‘nikmalarni egallashda muvaffaqiyat qozonishlariga yordam beradi.

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ACTUAL ISSUES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED LEXICAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES IN ENGLISH

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Annotation: *In this article, the author tried to reveal the essence and main directions of the formation and development of professionally oriented foreign language competence among students of technical universities.*

Keywords: *foreign language education of students, higher education, vocational-oriented training, competence approach.*

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific and practical problems. The need for a thorough modernization of Uzbek education became undeniable at the beginning of the 21st century. The processes taking place in the economic, political and social spheres have led to a change in the paradigm of the entire educational system. Since traditional education has become obsolete, innovative didactic methods, means, techniques and forms of organization of education in the modern system of higher education are needed. Since the most important goal of higher education in the conditions of the modern information society is to form not a narrow specialist with the maximum amount of academic knowledge, but a harmoniously developed creative person who perceives the surrounding reality holistically, is able to act mobile in the social and development of mankind, then there was an objective need to take a fresh look at the learning process in general, and at teaching a foreign language in particular.

Analysis of recent studies and publications that dealt with aspects of this problem and on which the author bases himself; highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Recently, the study of the formation of professionally oriented foreign language competence among students of technical universities has attracted more and more attention from researchers. The analysis of this problem was greatly influenced by the scientific works of M.V. Amitrova, G.V. Artamonova, I.G. Bakanova, Yu.V. Gusarova, E.A. Danilina, E.A. Nelyubina, L.G. Petranovskaya, E.S. Polat, N.V. Sidakova and others. However, many issues related to the formation of professionally oriented foreign language competence among students of non-linguistic faculties remain unexplored at all, or are not fully studied. According to the fair remark of a group of authors (M.V. Amitrova, Yu.V. Gusarova, E.A. Nelyubina), this is due, first of all, to the rapid development of the discursive

component itself. Under the discursive component, we mean verbal communication, which is typical for the situation of communication in a virtual environment. In our opinion, the reasons for the emergence of certain linguistic features of the Internet discourse, as well as the influence of linguistic features of communication in a virtual environment on the result of this communication, are insufficiently studied [1, p. 102-106]. Language training, as noted by some scientists (G.V. Artamonova [2], I.G. Bakanova [3], E.A. Danilina [4], I.Yu. Zhdankina [5], Yu.Yu. Sysoeva, E. A. Shamin is aimed at adapting specialists to the rapidly changing conditions of the functioning of the

modern market, at developing the ability to establish contacts with representatives of foreign companies, native speakers of a foreign language and other cultures.

The main goal of teaching a professionally oriented foreign language is to increase the initial level of foreign language proficiency achieved at the general educational stage of education, and to master the necessary level of communicative competence for students to solve professionally important tasks in various areas of everyday, cultural, professional and scientific activities when communicating with foreign partners as well as for further self-education and self-development. To achieve this goal in the educational process, teachers need to adjust the leading techniques, methods, technologies, means and content of teaching a foreign language, make them professionally oriented and personally significant for students, use active and interactive teaching methods, modern pedagogical technologies for teaching and educating - multimedia software means and Internet resources, which makes it possible to significantly increase the effectiveness of classroom and individual lessons, to form socially significant qualities for professional activities among students-future specialists in a technical profile.

The main directions for the implementation of these technologies are: to train students both in individual work and in team work; find and analyze a large amount of educational and methodological information, select the necessary part of it to solve a professionally oriented educational task; identify the key problems of the topic under study; consider alternative ways to resolve the situation and evaluate them, choose the best solution and form an algorithm of step-by-step actions, etc. [6].

The state educational standard of Uzbekistan for higher education of the "3+" generation requires strict consideration of the direction and profile of training in the study of a foreign language, its focus on the formation of general cultural, general professional and professional competencies for more successful implementation of

future professional activities by graduates. As a result of this approach, the technologies of professionally-oriented and linguistic-cultural teaching of a foreign language are of particular relevance, which provide for the formation of students - future employees of the ability and skills for foreign language communication in social, professional, business, scientific spheres, taking into account the specifics of professional activity.

The essence of professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language lies in its integration with special disciplines in order to obtain additional professional knowledge and form professionally significant personality traits. A full-fledged training of specialists in an educational organization consists in the formation of communicative skills that would allow for professional contacts in a foreign language in various fields and situations. To form the desire and ability of the future specialist to function as a strong linguistic personality of a democratic type, with high linguistic competence in the field of not only Russian, but also English, in professionally significant speech events of various types, in various modes, registers, forms, styles, types and genres of professionally oriented speech and thought activity. The sphere of communication is understood as a set of homogeneous communicative situations characterized by the same type of speech stimulus, relations between communicants and the environment of communication [7].

Foreign language communication can take place both in official and informal forms, during individual and group contacts, in the form of speeches at conferences, when discussing contracts, projects, and writing business letters.

The goal of teaching foreign languages in technical universities is to achieve a level sufficient for the practical use of a foreign language in future professional activities. Practical mastery of a foreign language is only one side of professionally oriented teaching of a subject. According to Yu.A. Nikitina, a foreign language can become not only an object of assimilation, but also a means of developing professional skills. This implies an expansion of the concept of professional orientation of teaching a foreign language, which includes another component - a professionally oriented orientation of the content of educational material [8]. Vocational-oriented training provides for a professional orientation not only in the content of educational materials, but also in activities that include methods and techniques that form professional skills.

Taking into account the foregoing, it is possible to distinguish the following structural elements of the content component of the model of professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language: Communication skills for all types of speech activity

(speaking, listening, reading, writing) based on general and professional vocabulary. The ultimate goal of professionally oriented teaching of dialogic speech is the development of the ability to conduct a conversation, purposefully exchange information of a professional nature on a specific topic.

Teaching monologue speech consists in the formation of skills to create various genres of monologue texts: communication of information of a professional nature, presentation of a report, extended statements during a discussion, discussion, both with and without preliminary preparation. Listening training consists in the formation of the skills of perception and understanding of the interlocutor's statement in a foreign language, generated in a monologue form or in the process of dialogue in accordance with a certain real professional sphere, situation.

Teaching reading consists in the formation of skills in all types of reading publications of various functional styles and genres, including special literature. Learning to write is to develop the communicative competence necessary for professional written communication, which is manifested in the skills of abstract presentation, annotation, as well as the translation of a professionally significant text from a foreign language into Uzbek and Uzbek into a foreign one.

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OLMOSHLARNING USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI (ASQAD MUXTORNING "CHINOR" ROMANI MISOLIDA)

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada Asqad Muxtorning "Chinor" romani misolida olmoshlarning uslubiy xususiyatlari tahlil qilindi. Unda olmoshlarning semantik va stilistik funksiyalari, ularning matndagi roli va personajlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni ifodalashdagi ahamiyati o'rganildi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Olmoshlar, uslubiy xususiyatlar, Asqad Muxtor, "Chinor" romani, semantik funksiyalar, stilistik tahlil, personajlar, munosabatlar, tilshunoslik, amaliy uslubiyat.*

Olmoshlarning uslubiy xususiyatlari adabiy matnlarda muhim rol o'ynaydi, shu bois ushbu so'zlar tilshunoslikda, xususan, sintaksis va semantika sohalarida alohida o'rin tutadi [1; 235]. Bu so'z turkumi asosan, ism o'rnini bosib, predmet yoki shaxsni qayta-qayta takrorlashdan saqlanish uchun ishlatiladi. Shuningdek, ular so'zlashuvda aniq va qisqa ifodalarni ta'minlashga yordam beradi. Olmoshlar har bir tilning grammatika tizimida o'ziga xos semantik funksiyaga ega bo'lib, matndagi ko'plab strukturalarni muvofiqlashtirishda katta ahamiyatga ega [2;223]. Ularning o'ziga xos ishlatilishi, tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslikda chuqur tahlilni talab etadi, chunki olmoshlar matnning ohangi va emotsional ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Badiiy asarlarda ularning ekspressivligi matnning yozuvchining tilga bo'lgan yondashuvini, ma'no qatlamlarini ochib berishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Olmoshlar, bir so'zning takrorlanishidan kelib chiqadigan g'alizlikning oldini olib, matnni ravon va ohangdor qilishga yordam beradi. Ular orqali so'zlar o'rtasida bog'lanish o'rnatilib, matn yaxlit va uyg'un bo'ladi [3;157]. Bu holat, ayniqsa, adabiy asarlarda, matnni shakllantirib, unga emotsional ohang berishda sezilarli darajada o'z aksini topadi. Olmoshlarning stilistik funksiyalarida namoyon bo'lishi, ekspressiv nutqning rivojlanishida alohida ahamiyatga ega, chunki bu nutqqa o'ziga xos ritm va rang-baranglik kiritadi.

Olmoshlarning o'ziga xos uslubiy xususiyatlari mavjud bo'lib, quyida ularni Asqad Muxtorning Chinor romani misolida ko'rib chiqamiz.

1. U, bu, shu olmoshlari Bu olmoshlar o'rnida, ko'pincha bir so'zi yoki bir xil so'zlar ishlatiladi. Masalan, "Bir (shunday) chamanki, atrofida bulbullar giryon" yoki "Bir xil (shunday) odamlar tushunmaydi" kabi ifodalar olmoshlarning shaklini o'zgartirish orqali yangi ohang kiritadi. Bu usul matnni jonlantiradi va unga

ta'kidlash, ajratish kabi semantik funksiyalarni qo'shadi. Xuddi shunday uslubiy xususiyatni Asqad Muxtor quyidagicha keltirgan: - Normatingiz bir yigit bo'libdi, shundoqqina dadasining o'zi-ya aylanay ovsin [4; 111] Ushbu gapdagi "bir yigit bo'libdi" jumlasida "shunday yigiti bo'libdiki" ma'nosida qo'llanilgan hamda ta'sirchanlikni oshirib ko'rsatib bergan.

2. Shaxsni ifodalovchi kishilik olmoshlari o'rnida. Ma'lumki, kamina, faqir, banda kabi so'zlar men olmoshining o'rnida ishlatiladi. Masalan, "Bu ishda kaminaning zarracha tajribasi yo'q" yoki "Siz va'da bergan edingiz - O'zlari va'da bergan edilar". Bunday hollarda, olmoshlarning o'zgartirilgan shakllari shaxsning o'ziga bo'lgan munosabatini ifodalaydi va bu orqali speakerning pozitsiyasini ochib beradi. Chinor romanida esa:

- Ajiniyoz tog'a, kaminaga,...xo'-o'sh... ikki shisha moy kerak. [4;159]

Bu jumlada "kaminaga" so'zi ishlatilgan, bu yerda "men olmoshi" o'rnida "kamina" so'zi ishlatilgan. "Kamina" — bu so'zlovchining o'ziga nisbatan kamtarona yoki jilvador shaklda ishlatilgan so'z. Bu so'z orqali so'zlovchi o'zini pastroq yoki kichikroq holatda ko'rsatishga urinishni ifodalaydi, bu esa kamtarlikni bildirib kelgan.

3. Sen olmoshi o'rnida siz olmoshi ishlatiladi. Masalan, "Siz bugun kelasizmi?" Bunday ishlatilish hurmat ifodalashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Aksincha, hurmatsizlikni ifodalash uchun esa sen olmoshiga ko'plik qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi: "Senlar buni tushunmaysanlar". Bu tilning uslubiy jihatidan harakatni kuchaytiradi va o'quvchi yoki tinglovchiga ma'lum bir emotsional ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ana endi yana romanga murojaat qilamiz:

- Matniyoz ayolining paxtadekkina, yumshoq iliq vujudini yana bag'riga oldi. "Daryo hidi keladi sizdan dedi" [4;184]

Bu jumlada "siz" olmoshi hurmatni ifodalash uchun qo'llanilgan. Matniyoz ayolning holatini ta'riflab, unga hurmat ko'rsatmoqda. "Daryo hidi keladi sizdan" degan ibora, ya'ni "sizdan" so'zi, hurmatni ifodalashning usulidir. Bu ifoda shaxsga nisbatan muloyimlik va hurmat ko'rsatishda ishlatilgan.

- Ho'y senlar, havoni to'smalaring, yerto'la dimiqib ketdi, - dedi odamlarni chetlatib. [4;137].

Bu jumlada "senlar" olmoshi ishlatilgan, va u hurmatsizlikni ifodalash maqsadida qo'llanilgan. "Senlar" olmoshiga qo'shilgan ko'plik qo'shimchasi (lar) bu yerda ifodaning emotsional ta'sirini kuchaytiradi va so'zlovchining norozilik yoki tanqidini kuchliroq ifodalashga yordam beradi. "Ho'y senlar" — Bu yerda "senlar" so'zi yordamida ko'plikda gapirish, so'zlovchining tinglovchilarga yoki shaxslar

guruhiga nisbatan hurmatsiz yoki jiddiy munosabatda bo'lishini ko'rsatib bergan. "Havoni to'smalarining" — Bu qismda ham, "to'smalarining" so'zi orqali, ko'plab shaxslar yoki odamlar to'g'risida so'z borayotgani tushuniladi, va so'zlovchining noroziligini yoki tanqidini yanada kuchaytiradi. Umuman olganda, "senlar" olmoshi va uning qo'shilgan ko'plik qo'shimchasi yordamida hurmatsizlik yoki tanqidiy munosabat ifodalanadi. Bu, muloqotni kuchaytiradi va uning emotsional ta'sirini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Biz yuqorida ko'rib chiqqan Asqad Muxtorning Chinor romanida olmoshlarning uslubiy qo'llanilishi matnning ekspressivligini oshirish, obrazlarning ichki dunyosini ochib berish va tilni jonlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Muallif olmoshlarni asosan matndagi takrorlarning oldini olish, obrazlararo muloqotni tabiiy va ravon qilish, shuningdek, matnga emotsional ta'sir kuchini qo'shish maqsadida ishlatgan. Umuman olganda, Chinor romanida olmoshlarning uslubiy xususiyatlari yozuvchining badiiy mahoratini, tilning ifoda imkoniyatlarini va matnning semantik tuzilishini chuqurlashtirishga xizmat qilgan. Olmoshlarning funksional qo'llanilishi asardagi tasviriylilik, ohangdorlik va obrazlararo dinamikaning tabiiyligiga ta'sir etgan bo'lib, bu jihat roman tilining o'ziga xosligini belgilaydi.

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ENHANCING FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN MILITARY EDUCATION: THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TRAINING CADETS

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Annotation: *This article explores the role of information technologies (IT) in enhancing foreign language acquisition among cadets in militarized educational institutions. Given the increasing importance of multilingual communication in military operations, foreign language proficiency is a critical skill for future officers. The study examines how digital learning platforms, virtual simulations, artificial intelligence-driven language applications, and online interactive resources contribute to more effective, engaging, and adaptive language learning. The integration of IT into military language education allows cadets to practice listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in a controlled yet realistic environment, thereby improving their linguistic competence and strategic communication abilities. The findings suggest that blended learning models, including mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) and immersive virtual reality environments, significantly enhance motivation and retention rates. The article concludes by offering recommendations for optimizing IT-based foreign language instruction to meet the unique cognitive and professional needs of cadets.*

Keywords: *foreign language learning, military education, information technologies, digital learning platforms, virtual simulations, strategic communication, blended learning.*

Introduction. In the modern era of globalized security and international cooperation, foreign language proficiency has become a crucial skill for military personnel. Cadets in militarized educational institutions must acquire strong language skills to effectively engage in international operations, intelligence gathering, and strategic communication. Traditional language instruction methods, while effective to some extent, often fail to address the specific needs of military learners, such as rapid response communication, cultural awareness, and specialized military terminology. This highlights the need for innovative pedagogical approaches that enhance language learning outcomes while accommodating the unique cognitive and professional demands of cadets. One of the most transformative tools in language education is information technology (IT)¹.

The integration of digital learning platforms, virtual simulations, artificial intelligence (AI)-driven applications, and mobile-assisted learning systems has revolutionized how foreign languages are taught in military contexts. IT-based

¹ Chapelle, C. A. (2001). *Computer Applications in Second Language Acquisition: Foundations for Teaching, Testing, and Research*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – pp. 1-279.

instruction not only facilitates adaptive and personalized learning but also allows cadets to practice real-world language scenarios in immersive environments. Technologies such as speech recognition software, interactive war-gaming simulations, and AI-powered translators enable military students to develop practical language skills that are directly applicable to their professional roles. This paper examines the significance of IT in foreign language acquisition for cadets, explores effective technological strategies, and provides recommendations for optimizing military language education to meet the evolving demands of global security and defense communication.

Foreign language proficiency is a critical skill for cadets in militarized educational institutions. As modern military operations increasingly require cross-border coordination, intelligence exchange, and diplomatic negotiations, language skills have become an essential component of military training. Effective communication with allies, international organizations, and local populations is crucial for mission success, making foreign language acquisition a necessity rather than a luxury². Furthermore, cadets must develop cultural competence alongside linguistic proficiency, as understanding social norms, political structures, and regional dialects enhances operational effectiveness. Traditional classroom-based methods, however, often fall short in replicating the dynamic and high-stakes environments in which military personnel operate. To address these limitations, integrating information technologies (IT) into foreign language training has emerged as an effective solution. Advancements in educational technology have transformed the landscape of foreign language instruction.

In military education, IT provides a range of tools that facilitate interactive, immersive, and flexible learning experiences³. These technologies cater to various learning styles and enable cadets to practice listening, speaking, reading, and writing in realistic scenarios. The key technological approaches in military language training include: Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL): CALL integrates multimedia resources, language games, and interactive exercises to reinforce language skills. Military-specific CALL applications provide cadets with training in combat communication, intelligence briefings, and negotiation scenarios. Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): These technologies create simulated

² Godwin-Jones, R. (2018). Emerging Technologies for Language Learning: Trends and Implications. *Language Learning & Technology*, 22(3), pp. 1-13.

³ Hubbard, P. (2009). *Computer-Assisted Language Learning: Critical Concepts in Linguistics*. New York: Routledge. – pp. 1-356.

environments that mimic real-life interactions. Through VR-driven language immersion, cadets can experience military briefings, checkpoint operations, and humanitarian missions in foreign languages.

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL): Mobile applications offer on-the-go learning with features such as speech recognition, pronunciation analysis, and real-time translation. These tools allow cadets to practice language skills in self-paced environments. **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Chatbots:** AI-powered platforms provide personalized learning experiences, offering instant feedback on grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary usage. AI-driven chatbots simulate real-time conversations, helping cadets improve spontaneous speaking skills⁴. **Online Interactive Learning Platforms:** Web-based resources, such as military-specific MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) and language training software, enable cadets to access structured learning modules tailored to their professional needs. Integrating IT into military language education presents several advantages. Firstly, digital platforms increase learner engagement through interactive exercises and gamified content, making language learning more effective. Secondly, IT enables adaptive learning, allowing cadets to progress at their own pace and focus on areas requiring improvement. Thirdly, real-time speech analysis and feedback systems enhance pronunciation and fluency, ensuring cadets achieve operational proficiency in a foreign language.

Furthermore, IT-based training fosters autonomy and self-discipline, essential qualities in military professionals. By utilizing scenario-based simulations and virtual dialogues, cadets develop context-specific language skills applicable to tactical operations, intelligence debriefings, and crisis negotiations⁵. Additionally, digital learning overcomes geographical constraints, enabling remote training for deployed personnel and international military collaborations. Despite its benefits, the integration of IT into military language training poses several challenges. Limited access to advanced technologies, cybersecurity concerns, and resistance to digital learning among traditional educators can hinder implementation. Additionally, military-specific language content in digital platforms remains underdeveloped, necessitating further investment in customized learning solutions. Future developments should focus on enhancing AI-driven instruction, expanding VR

⁴ Doughty, C., & Long, M. H. (2003). *The Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*. Malden: Blackwell Publishing. – pp. 1-888.

⁵ Stockwell, G. (2022). *Technology in Language Learning and Teaching: A Retrospective and Prospective View*. *Language Teaching Research*, 26(1), pp. 9-30.

applications, and integrating real-world military case studies into language training modules. Strengthening partnerships between military institutions and language technology providers will be key to ensuring effective, scalable, and security-conscious foreign language instruction for cadets.

Conclusion. The integration of information technologies into foreign language education for cadets in militarized institutions represents a significant advancement in military training. By leveraging computer-assisted learning, virtual simulations, mobile applications, and AI-driven instruction, cadets can acquire practical language skills essential for strategic communication, intelligence gathering, and multinational operations. These technologies not only improve learning efficiency and engagement but also provide adaptive, personalized, and context-specific training that aligns with military objectives.

Despite challenges such as technological accessibility, cybersecurity concerns, and content customization, the future of IT-based language education in the military remains promising. Continued investment in AI-driven learning solutions, virtual reality immersion, and customized digital resources will ensure that military personnel are equipped with the linguistic competence needed to navigate complex global security environments. Ultimately, enhancing foreign language training through IT strengthens the overall operational readiness of military personnel, ensuring effective cross-border communication, cultural intelligence, and diplomatic engagement. Future research should explore the long-term impact of digital language education on military effectiveness, assessing its role in shaping the next generation of multilingual officers.

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SINTAKTIK MORFONOLOGIYAGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

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Annotasiya: *Bu maqola sintaktik morfonologiyaga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, sintaktik morfonologiya murakkab fonetik va fonologik birlik bo'lgan intonatsiya va uning komponentlarini grammatik vazifa bajara olish xususiyatini ilmiy tadqiq etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *morfonologiya, sintaktik morfonologiya, morfonologik alternatsiya, intonatsiya va uning komponentlari, segment va supersegment morfonologiya.*

Annotation: *This article deals with peculiarities of comparative analysis of syntactical morphonology.*

Keywords: *morphonology, syntactic morphonology, morphonological alternation, intonation and its components, segmental and supersegmental morphonology.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются особенности сравнительного анализа синтаксических морфологии.*

Ключевые слова: *морфонология, синтаксическое морфонология, морфонологическая альтернатция, интонация и его компоненты, сегментальная и суперсегментальная морфонология.*

Morfologiyaning birligi hisoblangan morfemalar fonemalarning ma'lum tartibdagi birikuvidan tuziladi. Bu fonemaga berilgan «so'z va morfemalarni hosil qiluvchi va farqlovchi eng kichik til birligi» ta'rifida ham o'z ifodasini topgan. Keyingi davr tilshunosligida (XX asrda) morfemalarning fonologik tuzilishini o'rganuvchi soha morfonologiya deb nomlana boshladi. Uning vujudga kelishida N.S. Trubeskoyning xizmati kattadir. N.S.Trubeskoyning fikriga ko'ra morfologiya: 1) so'z fonologiyaning bir qismi bo'lib, morfemalarning fonologik strukturasi bilan ish ko'radi; 2) grammatikaning bir bobi; 3) morfonologiya morfologiya va fonologiyani uzviy bog'laydi. Demak, morfonologiya grammatikadan o'ziga munosib o'rin egallashi kerak. N.S.Trubeskoy morfonologiyani nazariy jihatdan uch qismga bo'ladi: 1) morfemalarning fonologik strukturasi haqidagi nazariya; 2) ba'zi morfemalarda uchraydigan kombinator o'zgarishlar nazariyasi; 3) morfologik vazifa bajaruvchi tovush almashinuvi nazariyasi.'

Dastlab morfonologiya morfemalardagi fonemalar almashinuvi, turli morfemalarning ulanishidagi kombinator pozitsion o'zgarishlar va so'zlarning fonomorfoloigiyasi, ya'ni umlaut, ablaut, singlarmonizm kabilarni o'rganar edi. Segment va supersegment morfonologiya farqlangach esa N.S.Trubeskoy qayd etgan

morfonologik hodisalar segmental morfonologiyaga kiritildi va prosodik morfonologiya so'zlarning aksent (urg'u) tuzilishidagi grammatik almashinuvlarni o'rganishi sababli aksentologik morfonologiyaga tegishli bo'ldi. O'z navbatida sintaktik morfonologiya funksional intonologiyadan farqlanib, intonatsiyaning «grammatik jarayonlarni kuzatuvchi jihatlarini o'rganadi».

Sintaktik morfonologiya murakkab fonetik va fonologik birlik bo'lgan intonatsiya va uning komponentlarini grammatik vazifa bajara olish xususiyatini ilmiy tadqiq etadi. Intonatsiya ohang va ibora urg'usi, nutqning tezligi (temp) va sifati (tembr), pauza va ritmning murakkab birligi bo'lib, gapni leksik va grammatik shakllantirib so'zlovchining fikrini, tuyg'usi hamda hissiyotini ifodalaydi. Intonatsiyaning birlamchi komponentlari ohang (melodika) va ibora urg'usidir, qolganlari ikkilamchi komponentlari hisoblanadi. Intonatsiya o'zining fonologik va morfonologik vazifasini ana shu komponentlari yordamida bajaradi. Intonatsiyaning birlamchi komponentlari barcha turdagi iboralarda va ular orqali gaplarda mavjud bo'lsa, ikkinchi komponentlari ishtirok etmasligi ham mumkin.

V.B.Kasayevich intonatsiyaning fonologik va morfonologik jihatdan qo'llanishini rus tili misolida quyidagicha izohlaydi: *Ты спужишь. (Sen uxlayapsan). Ты спужишь? (Sen uxlayapsanmi?). Сну! (Uxla!).* Yuqoridagi sintaktik paradigmalar intonatsiya bilan farqlanadi. *Ты спужишь?* faqat intonemaning fonologik jihatdan grammatikaga, ya'ni sintaksisga oid jihatini ko'rsatadi. Lekin *Спужишь ли ты? Сну!* so'roq va undov intonatsiyalari leksik, morfologik hamda sintaktik vositalar bilan boshqarib borilib, morfonologiya bilan bog'lanadi. Boshqa bir morfonologik vosita gapda so'z tarkibining o'zgarishi inversiya hisoblanadi. *Ahmad Samarqandga boradi* gapini *Samarqandga Ahmad boradi* shaklida o'zgartirib, inversiya vositasida morfonologik prosodikani asosiy farqlovchi belgi sifatida izohlash mumkin.

Gapni faol bo'laklarga bo'lganda, undagi rema va temaga tushgan urg'uga morfonologik aksent sifatida qaraladi va gapning semantik strukturasi sintaksis bilan bog'laydi. Gapdagi sintaktik, leksik va morfologik vositalarning alohida prosodik elementlar orqali shakllanishi morfonologik jihatdan ahamiyatlidir. Ana shu xususiyatlar bir-biri bilan qiyoslansa, intonatsiyaning bir til yoki ko'pgina tillar doirasida fonologik va morfonologik farqlarini aniqlash mumkin. Masalan, roman tillarida umumiy savol yuqori ohang bilan ifodalanadi va bir yo'la maxsus savol intonatsiyasiga ega bo'ladi. Ko'pgina tillarda umumiy savol (Yes/no questions) intonatsiyasi ko'tarinki ohang bilan aytiladi. Bu xususiyat faqat ingliz tilining Britaniya va Amerika adabiy variantlarida emas, balki 36 ta tilda aksent ritmiga (stress-timed), ya'ni kuchli dinamik urg'uga ega bo'lgan tillarda aniqlangan. Ular

qatoriga ohangning umumiy savolda yuqori darajada ko'tarilishiga (high-rise) ega bo'lgan turkiy tillardan ozar tili ham kiradi. Ingliz tilidagi so'roq gaplarda odatda ovoz gapning oxirida ko'tariladi.

Bu tilda ohangga tegishli birlikni terminal ton (terminal tone), uning turli variantlari allotones deb ataladi. Nutqni sintagmatik bo'lishda pauza yordamida gapni morfonologik jihatdan farqlash mumkin. Masalan: *Bu mashinachi Karimning otasi* (bu o'rinda kerakli tinish belgisi qo'yilmay ko'rsatilgan, belgi gapning qanday sintagmalanishiga qarab qo'yiladi). 1) *Bu mashinachi Karimning otasi*. 2) *Bu - mashinachi Karimning otasi*. Rus tilida gapni turlicha sintagmaga bo'lish orqali gapning mazmuni o'zgarishi mumkin: *Казнить / нельзя помирловать! Казнить нельзя / помирловать!* gaplaridagi mazmun sintagmaga bo'linishi va pauzaning o'ri bilan farqlanadi. O'zbek tilida «sintagmalanish nutqning grammatik mazmuni bilan bog'langan hodisadir», sintaktik kompleksning butunligini ifodalaydi.

Intonatsiyaning asosiy komponentlaridan biri - ibora urg'usidir (rus tilida frazovaya udareniye, o'zbek tilida ibora yoki gap urg'usi deyiladi). U so'z birikmasi va gaplarning mazmunini farqlashda morfonologik vazifani bajaradi: *uchta bolali xotin (uchta bolaga ega bo'lgan bitta xotin) - uchta/bolali xotin (bolaga ega bo'lgan uchta xotin, qalin muqovali / kitob (kitobning faqat muqovasi qalin) - qalin/muqovali kitob (kitobning o'zi qalin); katta mevali / daraxt (mevasi yirik bo'lgan daraxt) - katta /mevali daraxt (daraxt katta).*

Bunday urg'u bilan gap bo'laklarini ajratish yordamida ibora yoki gapning mazmunini o'zgartirish ingliz va rus tillarida ham uchraydi.

O'zbek tili agglyutinativ til bo'lgani sababli undagi gap-larda so'zlarning bog'lanishi morfologik ko'rsatkichlarga juda boydir. O'zbek tilida boshqa tillarga xos o'zak ajratuv-chi xususiyat mavjud. Jumladan, oltin soat, qizil olma, asfalt yo'l kabi so'z birikmalarida hech qanday morfologik ko'rsatkich yo'q. Lekin ingliz tilida bunday so'z birikmalari urg'u bilan farqlanadi: *a bluebird a blue bird, a 'glass' house - a'glao'ss oyor, a'ladies-'slipper a'ladies slip-per, 'evergreen ever ready, a'stand still 'stand still, a'black 'outa'black out kabi."*

Bu so'z va so'z birikmalari gap tarkibida qo'llanganda, o'z urg'usini saqlab qoladi va kuchli urg'u bilan ajratilganda, mazmuni kuchayib ekspressiv xususiyat kasb etadi: *The glao'ss doo'or was opened. She is looking for a o'ladies-o'slipper.*

Sintaktik morfonologiya matn tilshunosligi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, intonatsiya turlarining variativligi, turlicha o'zgarishi, komponentlarining xizmatidagi almashinuvlarni o'rganadi va bu masalalar hali ilmiy tadqiq etilmagan. Ushbu sohani rus olimi V.S.Kasevich «prosodik va sintaktik (intonasion) morfonologiya» deb atab,

uning vazifalarini qisman ko'rsatib bergan. Uning fikriga ko'ra, intonatsiya o'zining morfonologik vazifasini berilgan ibora yoki gapdagi biror so'zni emfaza yordamida prosodik ajratib ko'rsatish va ma'lum sintaktik holatda amalga oshishi bilan bajaradi. *Я работаю шофёром (Men haydovchi bo'lib ishlayman)* sodda gapini *Я шофёром работаю (Men haydovchiman)* shaklida sintaktik yo'l bilan inversiya yordamida morfonologik vazifa bajarishini kuzatish mumkin. Bunda шофёром so'zini intonatsion ajratib ko'rsatish inversiyani boshqarib boradi. O'zbek va ingliz tillarida ham inversiya intonatsiyaning morfonologik vazifa bajarishiga yordam beruvchi eng muhim vosita hisoblanadi:

On the o'way to the o'station/ I o'met a o'man. (I met a man on the way to the station). Yo'lda men bir odamni uchratdim. (Men bir odamni yo'lda uchratdim).

Gapning voqelikka munosabati intonatsiyadan boshqa grammatik vositalar (bog'lovchi, ko'makchi, morfologik ko'rsatkichlar) yordamida ifodalanganda intonatsiya o'zining mustaqil vazifasini bajara olmay, ikkinchi darajali morfonologik vositaga aylanib qoladi: Kecha uchrashuvga borolmadim, chunki zarur ish chi-qib qoldi kabi. Gaplarning komponentlarini transforma-tsiya qilish intonatsiyaning mavqeini pasaytirib, unga morfonologik vazifa yuklaydi:

Biz ona-Vatanimizni sevamiz.

Biz sevamiz ona-Vatanimizni.

Sevamiz biz ona-Vatanimizni.

Ona-Vatanimizni biz sevamiz.

Ushbu o'rinda rinda gapda so'z tartibining ahamiyati kattadir. To'g'ri so'z tartibiga ega bo'lgan gaplar va yuqorida berilgan teskari tartibli gaplar inversiya, nologik vazifasi bilan farqlanadi. o'z intonatsiyasi va morfologik vazifasi bilan farqlanadi.

O'quvchilarda nutqiy malaka va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish, ya'ni o'z fikrlarini nutqiy maqsad va vaziyatga mos ravishda ifodalashga o'rgatish uchun o'qituvchilar tilning ushbu xususiyatlarini bilishlari zarurdir.

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К ВОПРОСУ О ТИПОЛОГИИ ПЕРСОНАЖЕЙ В РАССКАЗАХ ШЕРВУДА АНДЕРСОНА

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Аннотация: Герои Шервуда Андерсона находятся в самом центре внимания в его рассказах, и сам писатель в своих трудах постоянно подчёркивал важность создания персонажей. Однако, за возможным исключением исследований «гротесков» Уайнсбурга, всё же незначительное внимание уделялось изучению остальных Андерсоновских персонажей. В данной статье были рассмотрены и проанализированы основные, на наш взгляд, из них. А также мы сделали попытку проследить взаимосвязь между биографией писателя и характером его героев, его отношением к жизни и творчеству. Тем самым в статье было определено какие качества характера были близки воображению автора, а также какие социальные типы людей интересовали его больше и по какой причине.

Ключевые слова: Персонаж, характер, герой, жанр, рассказ, творчество, рассказчик, гротеск, бизнесмен, горец, женщина, подросток, художник, творец, деньги, власть, кризис, культура, красота, чувствительность, невежество, природа.

Вопросы темы и формы всегда волновали критиков и исследователей творчества Шервуда Андерсона. На самом деле это достаточно важный подход, так как рассказы Шервуда Андерсона отображают его собственное видение, как рассказчика, и его борьба за художественный вымысел очевидна не только в его рассказах, но также и во влиянии его высказываний и творчества на развитие жанра современного короткого рассказа.

Всех персонажей опубликованных работ Ш. Андерсона можно классифицировать на семь основных групп: гротески, бизнесмены, представители разных профессий, горцы (жители горных районов), женщины, подростки, и представители творческих профессий. Изучение этих типов позволяет нам как выделить личные интересы Андерсона, так и глубже понять героев отдельных рассказов.

В отличие от остальных типов характеров, гротески не представляют собой какую-либо социальную формацию людей. Но они представлены в Уайнсбурге, Огайо, а также появляются и в других рассказах писателя, хотя и не так остро. Самый глубокий, на наш взгляд, анализ концепции гротескности персонажей Андерсона произвёл Ральф Чианко. Он исследовал социальные, сексуальные и мистические корни гротескности и взял их за основу утверждения, что для Андерсона гротескность была «не более, чем метафорой

естественного состояния человека ... его навязчивое влечение к бесконечному зову трансцендентности, чей конец считается невозможным с самого начала». (“was nothing more than a metaphor of the natural condition of man ... of his compulsive hearkening to the infinite call of transcendence which finitude makes impossible from the start.”) [1] Его исследование подкрепляет точку зрения ещё одного учёного, Уильяма В. Миллера, о том, что наиболее популярной темой Андерсона является частая тщетная борьба людей за трансцендентность, которая в те редкие моменты, когда она достигается, ассоциируется с красотой и порядком. (Anderson’s most persistent theme is the often futile struggle of human beings for transcendence which in those rare moments when it is achieved is associated with beauty and order”) [2, p. 5].

Наиболее частыми объектами презрения в рассказах Андерсона являются бизнесмены. И это неудивительно для писателя, отрёкшегося от делового мира, бросившего строительный бизнес по ремонту крыш, и полностью посвятившего себя писательству и искусству. И тот факт, что большинство его вымышленных нападок на рекламщиков появились позже в его карьере, в 1930-х, частично можно объяснить его замечанием Чарльзу Боклеру в 1933, что ранее «в нём было слишком много ненависти» (had too much hatred) [3]. Скрытый укор Андерсона в адрес бизнесменов заключался в том, что они убивают жизнь, свои собственные и жизни художников. В «Братья и смерть» ясно, что Джон Грей и его сын заплатили слишком высокую цену за деньги и власть. Анализируя подчинение мальчика воле отца, Андерсон повествует:

«Что-то в тебе должно умереть прежде, чем ты сможешь обладать и командовать.»

“Something in you must die before you can possess and command.” [4].

Бизнесмены открыто уничтожают творческую личность, используя свои порочные методы, например, как в «Шедевре Блекфута», или же, ещё чаще персонажи продают свои таланты («Бутылки с молоком», «Гамлет из Чикаго», “I Get So I Can’t Go On”, и “Off Balance”).

Главные герои шестнадцати рассказов Андерсона – профессионалы, представители различных профессий. Из них семеро врачей, три юриста, пятеро профессоров и один архитектор. Андерсон всегда сожалел о том, что не смог получить должного, на его взгляд образования и, в свою очередь, с трепетом и уважением относился к образованным людям, что он неоднократно подчёркивал в своих письмах к разным выдающимся личностям. Он восхищался и добивался расположения таких интеллектуалов, как Уолдо

Франк, Поль Розенфельд и Ван Вик Брукс. Кроме того, каждый из своих браков он заключал с женщиной, имевшей определённый культурный уровень, который он считал недостающим в его окружении. коммуникацией.

Оба его персонажа врача из Уайнсбурга должны быть привлечены к ответственности за врачебную халатность, но в то же время они оба представлены в образах философа и писателя. Доктор Персиваль предпочитает предостеречь Джорджа Уилларда от совершения им жизненных ошибок и писать свою собственную книгу, идея которой “каждый на свете - Христос, и каждого распинают” [5, стр. 49], приёму и лечению тех нескольких пациентов, которых он имел. Доктор Рифи в своих публичных действиях также предстаёт перед читателем неряшливым, беспечным и “непрофессиональным”, но добродушность характера доктора раскрывается двум женщинам в его жизни, а также в прекрасных, поэтических мыслях, написанных на бумажных шариках, но так и никому не обнародованных. Трое других врачей превосходят своих предшественников в профессиональном плане, Рифи и Парсиваля, хотя Андерсон приводит очень мало подробностей их профессиональных действий. При этом у каждого из них есть их личная, сокрытая от посторонних взглядов, жизнь, которую они успешно скрывают от общественности. Лестера Кокрейна («Не разгоревшееся пламя») любили его жена и дочь, а также его пациенты, но его молчание отталкивает его жену, и он умирает, так и не успев выразить свою любовь к дочери. Доктора в «Прогулке при лунном свете» охватывает паралич, когда он пытается написать что-то, несмотря на его беглую способность устного рассказа.

В период с 1926 по 1937 год из-под пера Андерсона вышла группа из тринадцати рассказов, действия которых разворачивались в горной местности близ Аппалачи, в окрестностях его последнего дома в Вирджинии. Два центральных мотива преследовал Андерсон в характеристике горцев в данных рассказах: его сильное желание развеять тот ореол романтики, который окружает горцев и показать их истинное невероятное мужество и гордость, а также уделить особое внимание тому факту, что их фрустрация была обусловлена не столько психологическими проблемами, сколько последствиями невежества и бедности. Джо в “A Sentimental Journey” “Сентиментальном путешествии” олицетворяет типичного Андерсоновского горца, примитивного, неотёсанного человека, горячо любящего свою землю и ведущего героическую борьбу за сохранение её целостности. Андерсон относится с глубоким уважением не только к Джо, но и к остальным своим

героям-горцам прежде всего за то, что они отстаивают свои моральные ценности, человечность, несмотря на своё невежество и нищету, в которой им приходится жить. Том Хэлси, в “A Mountain Marriage” (“Горная свадьба”) нападает на богатого клиента, вдвое больше его, чтобы заполучить деньги на спасение своей умирающей жены. Героиня другого рассказа из “горного цикла” Поли Граб “A Mountain Dance” (“Горный танец”) танцует, поёт и прелюбодействует ночи напролёт, но ни на минуту не бросает своих престарелых родителей, до тех пор, пока они живы. А молодая беременная женщина из “These Mountaineers” (“Эти горцы”), оскорбившись, отправляет рассказчика ко всем чертям, когда он предлагает ей деньги, тем самым задев её гордость и честь.

Ещё одна группа персонажей, заслуживающая более детального рассмотрения на наш взгляд – это женщины и мальчики-подростки. Отношение Андерсона к его женским героиням можно рассмотреть посредством фактов из биографии самого писателя, таким как четыре его брака и, особенно, его идеализированное отношение к своей матери, Эммы Андерсон, которую он восхваляет в рассказе “Смерть в лесу”. Эти факты и его собственные высказывания, за исключением нескольких, таких как: “The women are a hundred times as good as we men” [6, p. 193] (“Женщины в сто раз лучше нас, мужчин”), позволяют нам сделать вывод, что его истинное убеждение состояло в том, что женщины качественно отличаются от мужчин и ниже ценятся им. В своих неопубликованных мемуарах Андерсон пишет: “I would have gone all on some fool’s track with her for I have seldom been a wholehearted lover of women. I could never believe in women artists and cannot to this day. Perhaps in some essential part of me – never in the flash – I have all of my life, loved men more than I have ever loved women”. [7] (“Я мог бы отправиться с ней в какой-то безумный путь, но я редко по-настоящему влюблялся в женщин. Я никогда не верил в женщин, занимающихся творчеством, и не верю по сей день. Возможно, в глубине души, а не в каком-то порыве, я всю жизнь любил мужчин больше, чем когда-либо любил женщин”).)

Помимо рассказов с Джорджем Уиллардом, в пяти других лучших рассказах Андерсона главными героями автора выступают мальчики-подростки: “I’m A Fool”, “The Man Who Became A Woman”, “I Want To Know Why”, “The Sad Horn Blowers”, and “An Ohio Pagan”. Каждый из этих рассказов был опубликован между 1919 и 1923 годами, отображают влияние Марка Твена и перекликаются с юношескими годами Андерсона в Клайде, Огайо, откуда он

уехал в 1896, через год после смерти матери. Модель развития каждого юноши в основном одинакова.

Каждый юноша поначалу наивен и невинен и реагирует на окружающую среду простодушно и радостно. В рассказе “I Want To Know Why” главный герой получает колоссальное удовольствие от видов, звуков и запахов ипподрома. И даже девятнадцатилетний юноша в “I’m a Fool”, невзирая на всю сложность своего положения, восхищается, окружающей его природой. Отличительная черта каждого юноши заключается в том, как он реагирует на критические ситуации, жизненный кризис.

Самый важный тип персонажа в рассказах Андерсона по частоте появления и полноте представления – творческая личность. Его работы изобилуют не только художниками и писателями, но и потенциальными творцами, рассказчиками. Кроме того, во многих рассказах присутствуют рассказчики, будь то сам Андерсон, или какой-то иной отдельный персонаж, созданный им. Эти рассказчики как бы создают историю и акцентируют внимание читателя к тому или иному событию с помощью небольших отступлений типа: “Я не знаю откуда я об этом узнал” (“I don’t know how I learned this”) или “Вы знаете, как это” (“You know how it is). На самом деле, как только мы поймём всю полноту творческих образов в рассказах Андерсона, не найдётся ни одного рассказа, в котором мы не увидим этих самых характеров.

Своё намерение стать писателем, Андерсон воплотил во многих своих персонажах. Он писал в одном из своих писем: “I presume that we all who begin the practice of an art begin out of a great hunger for order. We want brought into consciousness something that is always there but that gets so terribly lost”. [6, p. 387] “Я предполагаю, что все мы, кто начинает заниматься искусством, начинаем с большой жажды порядка. Мы хотим, чтобы в сознание вошло что-то, что и так есть, но так ужасно теряется.” Это “что-то” – чувство прекрасного, о котором сам Андерсон однажды назвал “самым важным для человека” “the most vital thing to men”. [6, p. 135] Даже прозаичный Рэй Пирсон из “Untold lie” (“Невысказанная ложь”) был сильно тронут красотой природы, окружавшей его. “The beauty of the country about Winesburg was too much for Ray on that fall evening... of a sudden he forgot all about being a quiet farm hand and throwing off the torn overcoat began to run across the field. As he ran he shouted a protest against his life, against all life, against everything that makes life ugly.” [4, p. 207] “Красота окрестностей Уайнсбурга в этот осенний вечер переполняла душу Рэя Пирсона... И, вдруг, забыв всё – и свою работу на ферме, и то, что он уже

старый, усталый человек – он сбросил своё рваное пальто и побежал через поле. И на бегу он криком выражал негодование – на убожество своей жизни, на убожество чужих жизней, на всё, что уродует жизнь.” [5, стр. 146]

Тем не менее, концепция творческой личности в рассказах Андерсона более конкретно очерчена, включая отличительные черты его характера, опасности, которым он подвержен и социальные проблемы, с которыми он сталкивается. Среди них также его способность к развитию, талант вкупе с уважением к языку, вовлеченность и одновременно отстранённость, особенно развитое воображение, идеализм без романтизма, смелость и честность.

Этот обзор основных типов персонажей даёт возможность выявить основные типы характеристик, которые могут пролить свет на отдельные истории. В полном прочтении таких рассказов “Смерть в лесу” и “Я хочу знать почему” присутствуют не только биографические данные, присущие стилю Андерсона, но и повторяющиеся вымышленные образы женщин и подростков. Ещё более распространённым. Часто встречающимся образом у писателя является образ художника-творца, играющего иногда ключевую роль, а иногда и скрытую, приглушённую в нюансах поведения. Хотя диапазон его характеров ограничен, он достаточно интенсивен и ценен. Именно поэтому появление каждого нового “гротеска” в Уайнсбурге является свежим, интересным образом.

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O'ZBEK TILINI O'QITISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AYRIM MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya. *Maqolada raqamli ta'limga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlar tahlili va o'zbek tilini o'qitishni raqamlashtirishga tayyorgarlik masalalari yoritilgan. Raqamli ta'limning o'lkamizdagi tarixi, raqamli ta'lim va raqamli o'qitish terminlarining qo'llanilishi, o'ziga xosliklari haqida xorijiy va mahalliy tadqiqotlardagi qarashlar hamda ularga munosabat ifodalangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamlashtirish, masofali ta'lim, raqamli ta'lim, o'zbek tili, raqamli texnologiyalar.*

Annotation: *The article analyzes research on digital education and discusses the issues of preparation for the digitalization of Uzbek language teaching. The history of digital education in our country, the use of digital education terms, their specificities, and the views of foreign and domestic research on them are expressed.*

Keywords: *digitalization, distance learning, digital education, Uzbek language, digital technologies*

Bundan chorak asr oldin savodxonlikning eng yuqori darajasi kompyuterni kundalik foydalanish uchun bilish sanalar edi. Raqamli asr o'lchovlariga ko'ra, endilikda savodli inson uchun bu yetarli bo'lmay qoldi. Kunimizda raqamli texnologiyalarni ham kundalik, ham kasbiy faoliyatida faol qo'llay oladigan, axborotlarni tahlil qilib, tizimlashtirib, qayta ishlay oladigan kompetentli shaxs yuqori baholanadi. Mamlakatimizda 2018-yildan tatbiq etila boshlangan raqamli iqtisodiyot milliy konsepsiyasiga ko'ra, barcha ta'lim muassasalari qatorida oliy ta'lim jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalar va zamonaviy o'qitish shakl va usullarini joriy etish sur'ati oshdi.

O'zbekistonda va jahonda barcha sohalarda kechayotgan raqamli transformatsiya jarayonining muhim uzvi ta'lim tizimiga raqamli texnologiyalarni tatbiq qilish sanaladi. Ayonki, raqamli ta'lim elektron ta'lim, masofali ta'limning uzviy davomidir. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida elektron ta'lim va masofali ta'limning yutuqlariga tayangan holda raqamli texnologiyalarni tatbiq qilish bo'yicha jahon tajribalarini o'rganish, tahlil qilish uning samaradorligini aniqlashga hamda uni takomillashtirishga imkon beradi. Binobarin, raqamli ta'limning nazariy va amaliy muammolari tadqiq qilingan xorij va o'zbekistonlik olimlar tadqiqotlari ko'p masalalarni oydinlashtiradi. Mamlakatimizda raqamli ta'limni tashkil etish, axborot texnologiyalari va o'qitish metodlarini qo'llashning didaktik va metodik masalalari A.Abduqodirov, A.Pardayev [10], R.H.Hamdamov, U.SH.Begimkulov, N.I.Taylaqov

[13], M.E.Mamarajabov [12] kabi olimlar tomonidan amalga oshirilgan tadqiqotlarda yoritilgan. Vazirlar Mahkamasining qaroriga ko'ra 2021-yildan e'tiboran Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellektni rivojlantirish ilmiy-tadqiqot institutining tashkil etilishi [1] ta'lim jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalarni integratsiyalash ishlarini jadallashtirishda muhim qadam bo'ldi.

Aslida raqamli ta'lim o'z-o'zidan paydo bo'lgan emas, elektron ta'lim, masofaviy ta'limning ildizlari, pochta orqali o'qitish mamlakatimiz tarixida ham mavjud bo'lganligini taxmin qilish mumkin. Bilamizki, choparlar, kabutarlar pochta vazifasini bajargan, shuningdek, xabarlar, hujjatalr qosid, homil, barandam[7] kabi ishonchli kishilar tomonidan yetkazilgan. Masalan, Sohirqiron Amir Temur Tarag'ay Bahodirning markazlashgan davlati tarkibidagi yigirma yetti mamlakat va o'lkalarga xabarlar, ko'rsatma va buyruqlar choparlar, kabutarlar yetkazgan. Amir Temur davlat boshqaruvi bo'yicha ko'rsatmalari "Temur tuzuklari"ga jamlangani, Alisher Navoiyning "Munshaot" asarida esa garchi xat yo'llanayotgan shaxs nomi, manzili va sanasi ko'rsatilmasa ham, shoirning do'sti Sulton Husayn Boyqaroga, shahzodalarga va boshqa shaxslarga nasihat, yo'l-yo'riq, minnatdorlik izhori, tabrik, ta'ziyanoma, shaxsiy kechinmalari yo'llanganini eslash kifoya. Xususan, Badiuzzamonga (57-maktub), Mavlono Qosimga (90-maktub), asrandi farzandiga (89-maktub) [7] va boshqa shu kabi xatlarda ta'limiy ruh kuchli ekanligini, Badiuzzamon mirzo, uning o'g'li Mo'min mirzoga yo'llagan maktublarida she'r ilmiga oid ko'rsatmalari berilganligini ta'kidlash o'rinli bo'ladi.

Shoh Bobur valiahdi Humoyunning xatiga javoban uning xati yuzasidan tanbehlar berib, xatosiz yozishga undaydi: "*Bundan nari betakalluf va ravshan va pok alfoz bila biti. Ham sanga tashvish ozroq bo'lur ham o'qug'uchig'a* [6]. Konfutsiyning "*Men bilimdon bo'lib yaralgan emasman, shu bois bilimni o'tmishdan olishga jidd-u jahd qildim*" [4] degan hikmatiga asoslanib aytish mumkinki, elektron ta'lim, masofali o'qitish, masofali ta'lim, raqamli ta'lim tushunchalari shakllanishida va rivojlanishida muayyan evolutsion bosqichlarni ajratish mumkin. Ularning taraqqiyotida ajdodlarimizning muayyan hissasi bor deb hisoblasak, xatolashmaymiz.

Rus tilidagi "**обучение**" va "**образование**" terminlari "**raqamli**" so'zi bilan birikib sinonim sifatida qo'llanayotgan [11] bo'lsa ham, ularning mohiyati baravar emasligini (Вербицкий А.) [14] nazarda tutsak, o'zbek tilidagi "**ta'lim**" va "**o'qitish**" so'zlarining qo'llanilishini aniqlashtirish ham foydadan xoli bo'lmaydi. Binobarin, "raqamli ta'lim", "raqamli o'qitish" tushunchalari mohiyatini aniqlashtirish taqozo qilinadi.

Ta'lim termini [a. – o'rgatish, o'qitish, ilm berish; ma'lumot], 1) bilim berish,

malaka va ko'nikmalar hosil qilish jarayoni, kishini hayotga va mehnatga tayyorlashning asosiy vositasi (*Ta'lim va tarbiya ajralmas egizaklar*); **2)** ilm-fan yoki kasb-hunar sohalari bo'yicha egallanadigan, olinadigan ma'lumot va ko'nikmalar majmuyi; bilim (*Boshlang'ich ta'lim*); **3)** tarbiya, odob-axloq. (*Ta'limi yo'q bola*); **4)** Ko'rsatma, yo'l-yo'riq, o'rgatuv (*...ketmonni qay xilda chopish to'g'risida Mallavoy aka bergan ta'limga ham rioya qilmay, kuyib-pishib ishladi.*) kabi ma'nolari izohlarga [5]. Misollardan ko'rinadiki, o'zbek tilidagi "ta'lim" "o'qitish", "o'rgatish" so'zlari sinonimik xususiyatga ega. Shuning uchun **raqamli ta'lim** yoki **raqamli o'qitish** tarzida qo'llash xato bo'lmaydi.

U.Jumanazarovning tadqiqotida ilgari surilgan g'oya, ya'ni raqamli ta'limning yangi-yangi texnologiyalar, platformalar va interfaol ta'lim metodlarini ishlab chiqish hamda ularni bugungi hayotga joriy etish orqali mavjud kundalik ta'lim mazmunini o'zgartirish, mutlaqo yangi ta'lim tizimiga ko'chirishdan iborat ekanligini, raqamli ta'limning axborot, jumladan, personal axborotdan foydalanish hisobiga ta'lim ishtirokchilari, ya'ni "ta'lim oluvchilar" va "ta'lim beruvchilarning ehtiyojlarini maksimal darajada qondirish, uning o'ziga xos xususiyatini ifodalovchi yangicha tizimdagi ta'lim sifatida namoyon bo'lishi haqidagi nazariy xulosasi [3] raqamli ta'lim haqidagi qarashlarni muayyan darajada umumlashtiradi. Tadqiqotchining "interfaol ta'lim metodlarini ishlab chiqish" haqidagi qarashlari, "yangi-yangi texnologiyalar, platformalar ishlab chiqish" borasidagi fikrlarini to'la ma'qullaymiz.

Raqamli texnologiyalarni tatbiq qilishga tayyorgarlik quyidagi vazifalarni bajarishga bog'lanadi:

- o'qitishni raqamlashtirish sharoitida o'zbek tili va madaniyatini o'qitish-o'rgatishning mazmunini aniqlashtirish;
- raqamli texnologiyalar bilan integratsiyalasha oladigan yangi avlod o'quv materiallarini ishlab chiqish;
- nutqiy ko'nikma va malakalarni avtomatik nazorat qilishga mo'ljallangan baholash fondini ishlab chiqish;
- raqamli ta'lim muhitida odob, madaniyat xususiyatidan kelib chiqqan holda o'qitish metod va shakllarini tanlash;
- ta'lim oluvchilarning axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash;
- o'zbek tili va madaniyatini o'rgatishda raqamli resurslardan foydalanishning innovatsion usullarini izlash;
- fan o'qituvchilari va talabalarni til o'qitishni raqamlashtirish jarayoniga tayyorlash;
- fan o'qituvchilarining til o'qitishni raqamlashtirish bo'yicha malakasini oshirish [9].

O'zbek tilini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarni foydalanish o'quv jarayonini individuallashtirish, bitiruvchilarda kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish, mustaqil bilim olish va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlarini oshiradi. Alohida ta'kidlash o'rinliki, keng jamoatchilik va mutaxassislar raqamli texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayonida foydalanishda o'ziga xos xavf-xatarlar bo'lishidan tashvishlanadilar. Masalan, Börje Holmberg [2] o'tkazgan ijtimoiy tadqiqotlar natijalariga ko'ra onlayn-ta'limga jalb qilingan xitoylik talabalarning uzoq masofadan turib MDUda uzluksiz ta'lim olishlari ijobiy holat sifatida baholangan bo'lsa, o'qituvchilar bilan to'g'ridan to'g'ri muloqot qilinmasligi muhim muammo sifatida onlayn ta'limning salbiy jihati deb qaralgan. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tengsizlik muammosi, jumladan, Pandemiya davrida shaxsiy kompyuteriga ega bo'lmagan 500 milliondan ortiq o'quvchining o'quv jarayonidan chekkada qolganligi ijtimoiy tengsizlik kuchayganligini namoyon qilgan edi.

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ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ АКСИОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА

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***Аннотация.** В статье изучается уникальность языковой картины мира как реальное отражение национального менталитета. Рассматриваются лингвистические средства оценивания национальной картины мира в разнотипных языках при помощи фразеологических единиц аксиологического характера.*

***Ключевые слова:** аксиология, антропоцентризм, национальная картина мира, языковая картина мира, эксплицитный характер, имплицитный характер, ценности, оценка, оценочность.*

***Abstract.** The article studies the uniqueness of the linguistic picture of the world as a real reflection of the national mentality. The linguistic means of assessing the national picture of the world in languages of different systems using phraseological units of axiological nature are considered.*

***Keywords:** axiology, anthropocentrism, national picture of the world, linguistic picture of the world, explicit nature, implicit nature, values, assessment, evaluativity.*

Языкознание проявляет большой интерес к изучению языков как центр национального мировидения. Языковая картина мира в языкознании изучается с разных точек зрения.

Современное языкознание каждым днём всё больше и больше внимание уделяет на когнитивный аспект, который воспринимает окружающий мир с точки зрения их значимости для человека и окружающего его мира. Языковое сознание непосредственно связано с когнитивной и лингвокультурной значимостью объектов и явлений моральной и духовной сферы жизни социума. Моральная, духовная и даже физическая сторона жизни общества и каждого человека в науке воспринимаются как ценности. Проблема ценностей в лингвистической науке представляет и философскую трактовку тоже.

В данной статье мы рассматриваем лингвистические способы репрезентации аксиологической картины мира в языковом сознании этноса.

В языке можно выдвинуть аксиологичность объекта по двум параметрам: это может быть эксплицитный и имплицитный характер аксиологического аспекта.

При помощи средств языковой оценки проявляется эксплицитное выражение. Систему ценностей, варьирующих в обществе, можно отражать только через ряд категорий аксиологического характера.

Таким образом, можно утверждать, что при восприятии мира человеческое сознание аксиологически маркирует не только отдельные объекты, но и целые денотативные сферы окружающей действительности. Аксиологичность отдельного объекта может выражаться как эксплицитно, так и имплицитно. Аксиологичность денотативной сферы выражается только имплицитно.

Ещё не так давно аксиология признавалась как один из разделов философии. В XX-XXI веках развитие антропоцентрического направления в науке привело к осознанию особой роли человека в окружающем его мире. Антропоцентризм в современном языкознании стал одним из ведущих направлений, так как она рассматривает человека как центр и высшая цель мироздания. Учитывая тот факт, что люди не только пользуются природными ресурсами для выживания, но и способны активно участвовать в преобразовании окружающей среды.

Антропоцентризм в лингвистике послужил причиной для рассмотрения языка как одного из самых важных источников знаний о человеке. При рождении человек получает язык как данность, и этот язык формирует мировоззрение человека, а также его отношение к окружающей действительности. Язык считается единственным средством, которое способно помочь нам проникнуть в скрытую сферу ментальности, потому что именно он определяет способ членения мира в той или иной культуре [2, с. 320].

Антропоцентризм смело может подтвердить тот факт, что каждому из естественных языков соответствует своеобразная языковая картина мира.

Картина мира – это «глобальный образ мира, который лежит в основе мироощущения человека, репрезентирующего сущностные свойства окружающей действительности в понимании ее носителей, и который является результатом духовной активности человека. Картина мира выступает как концептуальное образование, она обладает рядом свойств и развивается по определенным законам» [4, с. 6]. Картина мира формируется под влиянием таких социальных факторов, как язык, традиции, природа и ландшафт, воспитание, обучение и др. и имеет пространственные (верх – низ, правый – левый, восток – запад, далекий – близкий), временные (день-ночь, зима-лето), количественные, этические и др. параметры [5, с. 64].

Картина мира делится на три разновидности:

- 1) реальная картина мира;
- 2) концептуальная картина мира;
- 3) языковая картина мира.

Реальная картина мира – это картина мира, существующая в мире объективно, вне зависимости от человека и его познания.

Концептуальная картина мира – культурная (понятийная) картина мира, отражающая реальную картину мира посредством «понятий, сформированных на основе представлений человека, полученных с помощью органов чувств и прошедших через его осознание как коллективное, так и индивидуальное» [4, с. 6-7].

Языковая картина мира – часть концептуальной картины мира, которая с помощью языковых средств, отражающих особенности национального мировосприятия той или иной этнокультурной общности (лексика, грамматические средства, стилистические средства), выражает субъективное национально-специфическое понимание действительности, характерное для конкретной этнокультурной общности, а также универсальные категории (пространство, время, число, причина, судьба, изменение, отношение чувственного к сверхчувственному, отношение частей к целому), общие для всех языков [4, с. 7]. Если картина мира является отражением объективно существующего мира, то языковая картина мира служит средством для ее выражения.

Уникальность языковой картины мира в том, что она имеет важное значение в отражении национального менталитета. Прежде всего надо сказать, что каждая языковая картина мира имеет индивидуальный ряд категорий культуры или концептов, к которым можно включить концепт пространства, время, совесть, свобода, судьба, право, труд, добро и т.д.

Перечисленные категории культуры «отражают специфику существующей системы ценностей и задают образцы социального поведения и восприятия мира» [3, с. 53].

Система ценностей, которая отражается в языке изучается аксиологией. Особая черта этой науки в том, что она характеризуется интересом к субъективным моментам в языке. К проявлению субъективности в языке можно отнести оценку. Человек оценивает абсолютно всё. Он привык выражать своё не нейтральное отношение к явлениям действительности с помощью оценки.

Языковая оценка отражает предметную ценность объектов окружающего материального мира для определённого человека и всего общества в целом, так как оценочная норма устанавливается обществом и через язык формирует личность [1, с. 216]. Оценки можно выразить через ряд языковых средств и

способов. Они могут быть фонетические, морфологические, синтаксические, лексические и т.д.

Окружающий нас мир мы можем оценивать по качеству и по количеству. Как бывают положительные оценки, бывают и отрицательные оценки. Или может быть нулевая оценка, это когда человек безразличен к чему или к кому-либо.

Мы все, начиная с детства, имеем личные ценностные ориентации, можно сказать ценностные представления, с помощью которых мы ориентируемся в мире ценностей и определяем, какие ценности являются для нас ценными, а какие менее.

Каждый индивид оценивает мир на основе господствующих в культуре ценностных представлений. У каждого человека есть своя система оценивания. Для кого-то ценность «семья», для кого-то «свобода», это зависит от жизненных обстоятельств тоже.

Во время исследования мы столкнулись даже несовместимыми друг с другом ценностями. Например, образование – отдых, семья – друзья, жизнь – честь. Они, являясь важными элементами социального бытия, в то же время могут быть противоречивыми.

Оценочностью мы называем компонент значения слов, в котором реализуется выраженная языковыми средствами оценка. Оценочность может являться частью как коннотативного, так и денотативного аспекта значения. Она тесно связана с экспрессивностью слов. А экспрессивность тесно связана с прагматикой. Потому что и экспрессивность слов, и их прагматическое значение связаны с оценивающим отношением субъекта к объекту. Непосредственно это позволяет им служить наиболее яркими проявлениями антропоцентризма в языке.

Наше исследование позволяет нам рассмотреть фразеологические единицы как одно из наиболее частотных средств экспрессии. Потому что экспрессивность является одним из основных признаков фразеологизмов наряду с устойчивостью, воспроизводимостью и образностью.

Фразеологизмы являются языковыми репрезентациями лингвокультурных явлений вследствие своей способности отражать национальный менталитет и систему ценностей народа, который говорит на определённом языке. Фразеологические единицы – это «душа всякого национального языка, в которой неповторимым образом манифестируется дух и своеобразие нации» [3, с. 69].

Исследования доказывают, что фразеологизмы достаточно ярко, чем другие языковые уровни, отражают национальную специфику и ценностную ориентацию каждой нации.

Если посмотреть с научно-фразеологической точки, фразеологическая картина мира – это часть языковой картины мира, в которой картина мира описывается средствами лексики и фразеологии, на которых базируется описание объективной действительности со всеми связями и отношениями в составе высказывания. А также стереотипы поведения человека, обусловленные национальным мировидением, явно отражаются во фразеологической картине мира.

В науке не существует общепринятой системы оценочной категории. Используются своеобразные оценки, которые отличаются друг от друга спецификой и нормами.

Итак, наряду с предметными ценностями в качестве ценностей могут выступать какие-либо явления общественного сознания, которые выражают интересы субъекта в идеальной форме. Аксиологическое направление в лингвистике характеризует ценность как картину мира.

Таким образом, при рассмотрении аксиологических характеристик фразеологических единиц в рамках антропоцентрического подхода следует учитывать, что субъектом в процессе оценивания какого-либо действия или явления выступает человек.

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THE INTEGRATION OF AI-POWERED LANGUAGE LEARNING TOOLS IN ESL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article explores the integration of AI-powered language learning tools in English as a Second Language (ESL) education. It highlights the numerous benefits of these technologies, including personalized learning experiences, instant feedback, and flexible, accessible learning opportunities. AI tools such as speech recognition software, chatbots, and interactive apps like Duolingo and ELSA Speak enhance ESL education by tailoring lessons to individual learners' needs and progress. However, challenges such as the inability of AI to fully replicate cultural nuances, the risk of over-reliance on technology, privacy concerns, and unequal access to resources are also discussed. The article emphasizes the importance of combining AI tools with traditional teaching methods and ensuring teachers are properly trained to integrate these technologies effectively. Ultimately, while AI has transformed language learning, human interaction remains essential for a well-rounded, culturally-aware educational experience.

Key words. AI-powered tools, language learning, ESL education, personalized learning, machine learning, instant feedback, flexible learning, cultural nuances, data privacy, accessibility, technology in education, language acquisition, teaching methods, AI integration, educational technology.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается интеграция инструментов для обучения языкам, основанных на искусственном интеллекте (ИИ), в обучение английскому языку как второму (ESL). Подчеркиваются многочисленные преимущества этих технологий, включая персонализированный подход к обучению, мгновенную обратную связь и гибкие, доступные возможности для обучения. Инструменты ИИ, такие как программное обеспечение для распознавания речи, чат-боты и интерактивные приложения, такие как Duolingo и ELSA Speak, улучшают процесс обучения ESL, адаптируя уроки под индивидуальные потребности и прогресс учащихся. Однако также обсуждаются проблемы, такие как неспособность ИИ в полной мере воспроизводить культурные особенности, риск излишней зависимости от технологий, проблемы конфиденциальности данных и неравномерный доступ к ресурсам. В статье подчеркивается важность сочетания инструментов ИИ с традиционными методами обучения и необходимости подготовки преподавателей к эффективной интеграции этих технологий. В конечном итоге, несмотря на то, что ИИ значительно изменил процесс обучения языкам, человеческое взаимодействие остается важным для полноценного и культурно осведомленного образовательного опыта.

Ключевые слова. Инструменты, основанные на ИИ, обучение языкам, ESL-образование, персонализированное обучение, машинное обучение, мгновенная обратная связь, гибкое обучение, культурные особенности, конфиденциальность данных, доступность, технологии в образовании, приобретение языка, методы обучения, интеграция ИИ, образовательные технологии.

As the advancements in technologies are reflecting their tremendous changes in every sphere of our current life and the most influential ones can be seen in the field of education. Artificial intelligence is playing a pivotal role in the evolution of

education with its numerous facilities which can engage language learners by providing personalized support, adaptive feedback and increased accessibility. This article will explore the implementation of AI in the process of language learning, mainly in ESL education and try to find out what benefits, challenges it has for both learners and teachers.

By means of AI-powered language learning tools applications, learning platforms and programs are understood and they all have the same function as they were created to facilitate language learning process. These tools work with machine learning algorithms and can even personalize learning process based on the individuals' level, learning progress, their abilities and needs. Perhaps for these reasons they are being chosen commonly by majority of learners because of the chances to reach the assistance when they needed in terms of pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary or listening skills.

Examples of such AI-driven tools include speech recognition software, chatbots, interactive apps like Duolingo and ELSA Speak (English Language Speech Assistant), Google translation, as well as virtual tutorials. They tend to use more natural language processing technology to create more conversational and interactive atmosphere between the system and the learner.

The benefits of AI-powered tools in ESL education.

Personalized learning. The most obvious and outstanding advantage of AI-driven learning is that tools can identify learners' abilities and needs and can tailor the learning experience coming from the weakness and strengths of the learner. Moreover, artificial intelligence can adapt to a learner's pace and does not put pressure on the students and it creates more free and reliable learning atmosphere to them. By analyzing a learner's performance these tools can switch the focus to the areas where further practice is needed and can offer myriad of exercises to accomplish them successfully.

Availability of instant feedback. Unlike traditional language learning classrooms, where students are kept waiting for their marks and feedbacks being received for their work from teachers, AI tools can provide learners with instant feedback (Porter, & Grippa, 2020). When working with these tools students receive feedback for their both written and spoken discourse as well as their mistakes are corrected simultaneously. This convenience can accelerate the learning process and gives a chance to a learner to reflect on their progress, to work on their weak points and on top of them stay motivated and encouraged to continue learning and to complete the lessons.

Flexible learning. With the assistance of AI-powered applications ESL students now can acquire any languages at any time and at any place, if only they are provided with internet access. Learners are no longer awaited to participate in any live classes at any fixed times. This flexibility can be beneficial for those who are busy with their abundant workload or with household chores at home with little children. Especially, students who commute to a study place from remote areas can take an advantage of smart tools for their second language acquisition.

While the facilities and benefits of AI-powered language learning tools cannot be denied, there are also some considerations and limitations which cannot be neglected which will be mentioned above:

Cultural diversity and linguistic nuances. Although machine learning tools can perfectly understand and analyze any language patterns in the world there might be some cases which cannot be delivered exactly to the learner. AI-driven tools not always can help to replicate the cultural and contextual nuances of language, such as idioms, colloquialism, and regional accents. For instance, while translating some phraseological patterns from their own language into target one L2 learners are usually taught to take intercultural issues into consideration as some phrases might be understood totally different according to the area of spoken language or variety and this can lead to misunderstanding or errors in communication, particularly in more complex or technical language. As for AI-driven tools are programmed to utilize only standard patterns of languages they might not work perfectly in real-life situations where cultural awareness, human empathy and understanding is needed.

Dependence on gadgets and devices. Another drawback of these tools is excessive use of technology which is resulting in dependence on them. With continuous assistance provided by AI systems language learners can never assess their real knowledge since they already got used to addressing to their gadgets as soon as any questions arise. For these reasons, educators know firmly believe that ESL learners should be driven into real-life conversations as much as possible with experienced language instructors or native speakers as they are always awaited to utilize their target languages outside of their virtual lessons. Therefore, AI platforms should be seen as a tool for only complement rather than replacement of traditional methods of language instruction.

Security and privacy issues. As any AI-powered tools always require and keep some amount of personal information another concern about data privacy and their security has arisen in the last few decades as it has becoming impossible to protect privacy from unwanted forces or misuse of personal data. For this reason, it is

becoming really crucial for intelligent software developers to adhere strict privacy standards and ensure that user's personal data is safeguarded in any occasions.

Transparency. AI language learning tools need to be transparent about how they operate and use learner data. This can help ensure that learners are informed about how the tools work and can make informed decisions about their use (Ruane., Birhane, & Ventresque, 2019).

Accessibility. As for access to technology or the internet, not all learners have equal chances to implement smart tools in their learning process and it will result in the diversity in classrooms in terms of academic performance and language level. Therefore, if it is planned to utilize language learning tools in the process of teaching and learning it is crucial to consider the needs and resources of all learners and ensure that AI language learning tools are accessible to all.

After considering a number of features mentioned above some important questions arise connected to AI issues in ESL education:

Can AI language learning tools replace human teachers or tutors? Although AI-powered tools can provide enhanced efficiency and personalized learning experience they can only partially replace teachers or tutors as they always require for human interaction and cannot fully show empathy, appraisals and emotions which effect on learners' performance in foreign language learning.

In what ways AI tools should be integrated into teaching? As mentioned above, machine learning can be more effectively used along with traditional methods and their potential can only be fully realized if foreign language teachers are adequately prepared. By using multiple of facilities which AI tools can offer they can be better prepared for their lessons or develop professionally with the help of seminars, workshops dedicated to AI learning tools and learn better about how to integrate them effectively into their teaching (Nazaretsky, Ariely, Cukurova & Alexandron, 2022). Moreover, with the assistance of mentorship programs less trained or new, less experienced teacher can find a valuable opportunity for learning and support. Experienced teachers can share their knowledge and expertise with their mentees and guide the integration of AI-powered tools into teaching (Pedro, Subosa, Rivas, & Valverde, 2019).

All in all, AI-powered language learning tools have brought tremendous changes into the language acquisition process. By providing instant feedback, giving personalized assistance artificial intelligence generated lessons are giving learners more opportunities and enhancing their language skills to intended degrees. Moreover, it is already felt that, language learning is no longer seen as more

complicated and unachievable task. However, there are some considerations and limitations to use AI language learning tools, like lack of human interaction, lack of cultural insights and data privacy. It is essential to address these problems while integrating such smart devices into language learning process and by doing so both language teachers and learners might have potential to become more powerful and fluent in their teaching and learning experience.

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TIL TA'LIMIDA YONDASHUVLAR APPROACHES IN TEACHING LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tilni o'qitishda tayaniladigan yondashuvlar tahlil qilingan. Olimlar tomonidan tavsiflangan yondashuvlar til ta'limining psixologik va til o'qitish usuli jihatidan bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, ularning lingvistik va psixolingvistik tomonlariga aniqliklar kiritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Bixevioristik, induktiv-ongli yondashuv, kognitiv yondashuv, integrasiyalashgan yondashuv, intuitiv yondashuv, faoliyatga asoslangan yondashuv, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv, madaniyatlararo yondashuv.

Ma'lumki, til o'qitish masalasida o'qituvchi yondashuv, metod va texnika terminlarini bir-biridan farqlay olishi kerak. Chunki darsni tashkil etishda ular haqidagi bilimga ega bo'lishlilik o'quvchilarni to'g'ri yo'naltirishga xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqot ishimizda yuqorida qayd etilgan terminlar haqidagi olimlarning fikrlari va ularning turlarini birma- bir ko'rib, tahlil qilib chiqamiz.

O.V. Mixalevaning fikricha yondashuv bu o'qituvchi tomonidan tanlangan o'qitish strategiyasidir. Ushbu kategoriya nafaqat metodika uchun, balki umumta'lim muassasalarining o'qitish jarayonlarida lingvodiaktik asos bo'lib ham xizmat qiladi. Bunda o'qituvchi tomonidan tanlangan, chet tilni o'qitish metodlari va usullarini o'zida qamrab oluvchi yondashuv haqida taassurot beradi [1; B.32.].

Jack C.Richards, Theodore S.Rodgers ta'kidlashicha, yondashuv bu tilni o'rgatish va o'rganishning tabiati bilan bog'liq bo'lgan korrelativ taxminlar to'plamidir. Bunda yondashuv aksiomatik bo'lib, unda o'qitiladigan mavzuning mohiyati tasvirlangan [2; B.19.].

E.Antoni yondashuv bu til va til o'rganish haqidagi taxminlar va g'oyalar belgilangan daraja deb ta'rif beradi [2; B.63-67.]. .

Yuqorida berilgan olimlarning fikrlaridan kelib chiqib, yondashuv bu til o'qitish metodlarining nazariy asoslari ekanligi haqidagi xulosaga kelish mumkin.

Hozirgi kunda xorijiy tilni o'qitishdagi yondashuvlarning bir necha klassifikatsiyalari mavjuddir (1-rasmga qarang.).

1-rasm. Til o'qitish yondashuvlari.

O.V. Mixaleva psixologik jihatdan yondashuvlarni quyidagi turlarini belgilaydi:

1) **Bixevioristik yondashuv.** Ushbu yondashuvda taqdim etilgan stimullarga javoban nutq avtomatizmlarini shakllantirish orqali tilni o'zlashtirish tushuniladi.

2) **Induktiv-ongli yondashuv.** Bunda nutqni kuzatish orqali tilni egallash tushuniladi. Bunday kuzatish jarayonida til qoidalari va ulardan nutqda foydalanish usullari o'zlashtiriladi.

3) **Kognitiv yondashuv.** Bu holatda tilni ongli ravishda qoidalar shaklidagi bilimlardan nutq ko'nikma va malakalarigacha bo'lgan ketma-ketlikda o'zlashtirish nazarda tutiladi.

4) **Integrasiyalashgan yondashuv.** Bunda til haqidagi bilim va nutq ko'nikma hamda malakalarini parallel ravishda o'zlashtirishni ta'minlovchi ongli va ongsiz komponentlarni o'qitish jarayonida birikishi tushuniladi.

Shuningdek, til o'qitish yondashuvlari o'qitish ob'ektiga ko'ra quyidagi turlarda ajratiladi:

- 1) tilni o'zlashtirishga qaratilgan **til yondashuvi**;
- 2) nutqni o'zlashtirishga qaratilgan **nutqiy yondashuv**;

3) nutq faoliyatiga e'tibor qaratilgan **nutq faoliyati yoki kommunikativ-faoliyat yondashuvi**. Bunda til aloqa vositasi bo'ladi. Kommunikativ-faoliyatning metodik mazmuni bu muammolarni hal qilish bilan, o'qituvchi va talabalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlik asosida jamoaviy ish shakllarini keng qo'llagan holda o'quv faoliyatini tashkil etish usullari nazarda tutiladi. Ushbu yondashuvning maqsadi chet til darslari davomida o'quvchilarni o'qituvchi tomonidan modellashtirilgan va tashkil etilgan muayyan vaziyatlarda harakat qilishga o'rgatishdir [B.35.].

Til o'qitish usuli jihatidan yondashuvlar uch turga bo'linadi:

1) **Intuitiv yondashuvda** chet tilni o'qitish jarayonida ona tilini mutlaqo qo'llamaslik nazarda tutiladi. Xorijiy til leksik birliklarni eshitish orqali ongsiz ravishda o'zlashtirilishi sodir bo'ladi. Ushbu yondashuv bixevioristik yondashuvga asoslanib, til o'rganuvchilar so'zlarni va grammatik qurilmalarni ko'p marotaba takrorlashlari hisobiga tilni egallashlari mumkin.

2) **Kognitiv yondashuv** asosida tilning leksik birliklarini tushunish va keyingi nutq faoliyatlarida tushunishlari yotadi. Tilni egallash jarayoni yangi bilimlar taqdimoti, mustahkamlash va ularni amaliyotda qo'llash bosqichlarida tashkil etiladi.

3) **Faoliyatga asoslangan yondashuv** ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilar o'z oldiga qo'yilgan kundalik, umumiy madaniy va kasbiy xarakterdagi kommunikativ vazifalarni nutq faoliyati orqali amalga oshirilishga harakat qilishlariga asoslanadi. Shuningdek, o'quvchi sub'ekt sifatida ta'lim markazida ekanligini anglatadi va ta'lim tizimida uning individual-psixologik, yosh va milliy xususiyatlari hamda qiziqishlari kabi shaxsiy xususiyatlari maksimal darajada hisobga olinadi.

Bundan tashqari, zamonaviy chet tilni o'qitish nazariyasi va amaliyoti **shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvga** asoslanmoqda. Bunda o'qituvchi har bir o'quvchi uchun uning bilim darajasidan kelib chiqib, individual ta'lim traektoriyasini tuzib chiqishi ko'zda tutiladi. Chet tilni o'qitish jarayonining tashkil etishda o'quvchi o'zining noyob shaxsiy va xarakteristik xususiyatlariga ega til shaxsi sifatida qaraladi. Bu holatda o'qituvchi o'quvchining hamkoriga aylanadi. O'qituvchining vazifasi o'quvchilarning nafaqat individual ishlariga, balki loyiha, faol va interfaol ish turlaridagi jamoaviy ishlariga motivatsiya berib turish hisoblanadi.

Madaniyatlararo yondashuv o'z madaniyati va madaniyatning funksional koordinatorini ustun qo'ya oladigan ikki madaniyatli shaxsni shakllantirishni ko'zda tutadi.

Shuningdek, hozirgi kunda **kompetentlikka asoslangan yondashuv** ham qo'llanilib, u barcha darajadagi ta'lim jarayonida va chet tillarni o'rgatish jarayonida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv bilan chambarchas bog'liq holda asosiy

yondashuvlardan biri hisoblanadi. Chet tilni o'rgatishning maqsadi kompetensiyaga asoslangan yondashuvning asosi sifatida chet tilning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirishdir [B.36.].

J.C.Richards va Th.S.Rodgers yondashuvning quyidagi lingvistik va psixolingvistik jihatlarini taqdim etadi: a) birinchi jihati til nazariyasi bo'lib, u o'zida uch xil nazariy, ya'ni strukturaviy, funktsional va interfaol qarashlarni qamrab oladi; b) ikkinchisi til o'rganish nazariyasi bo'lib, jarayonga yo'naltirilgan va sharoitga yo'naltirilgan nazariyalar tashkil etadi.

Birinchi qarash strukturaviy qarash bo'lib, bunda til ma'noni kodlash uchun tizimli bog'liq elementlar tizimi sifatida qaraladi. Tilni o'rganishdan maqsad shu tizim elementlarini, ya'ni fonologik, grammatik birliklarni, grammatik jarayonlarni va leksik birliklarni egallashda ko'rinadi.

Ikkinchi qarash funktsional qarash bo'lib, til funktsional ma'noni ifodalash uchun vosita sifatida tavsiflanadi. Til o'qitishdagi kommunikativ harakatlar tilning ushbu qarashiga qo'shiladi. Ushbu nazariya tilning faqatgina grammatik xususiyati bilan cheklanmasdan, uning semantik va kommunikativ jihatlariga ham urg'u beradi.

Uchinchi qarash interfaol qarash bo'lib, bunda til shaxslararo munosabatlarni tushunish va insonlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy munosabatlarni namoyish etish vositasi sifatida yuzaga keladi.

Xulosa qilib, yuqoridagi yondashuvlar va ular asosida yaratilgan metodlar til o'qitish tizimida juda ahamiyatlidir. Til o'rganuvchilarning ham lingvistik, ham psixolingvistik xususiyatlarini nazarda tutgan holda yondashuvlarni til o'qitish sharoiti, ta'lim oluvchilarning individual xususiyatlari va til bilish darajasiga ko'ra yondashuvlarni tanlab yoki ularni uyg'un holda qo'llash ta'lim sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

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QO'SHIQCHILIK TERMINLARI UMUMIYLIKDAN, XUSUSIYLIKGA

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada qo'shiqchilik yo'nalishida butun-bo'lak, jins va tur qo'shiqning avj nuqtasi, naqorati haqida gap ketadi. Qo'shiqchilik san'atida jins-tur munosabati terminologik maydonning asosini tashkil qiladi. Jins-tur munosabati ham nisbiy hisoblanib, bir jinsning turini tashkil qilgan narsalar ikkinchiga nisbatan jinsni bildirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: termin, mug'om, jins, tur, bayot, qo'shiq, naqorat, kuplet, maqom, ashula, avj, akkord, ijro etish.

Bizni qurshab turgan olamni tashkil etgan elementlar ma'lum umumiy belgilarga ko'ra sinflarga birlashadi hamda sinfga birlashgan elementlar shu sinf tarkibida bir-biridan farqli belgilarga ko'ra ajraladi. Butun elementlari butunliklar doirasida o'zaro shartlangan va zidlangan munosabatda bo'lsa, ayni chog'da, butunlik bilan butunlik katta butunlik doirasida uning elementlari sifatida o'zaro ana shunday munosabatda bo'ladi.

Jins va tur tushunchalari orasida inklyuziv (kiritish) munosabatlar mavjud. Masalan, **mug'om** – Ozarbayjon xalq musiqasida lad. Ushbu termin jami 70 dan ortiq mug'omlar turini jamlaydi, ulardan asosiylari, bir birlikni boshqa birlikdan ajratib turuvchi, farqlovchi differentsial belgilarga bo'ladi (*rast, shur, segoh, shushter, charyah, bayati shiraz, humayun*). Qolganlari shular zaminida tashkil topgan.

Partonimiya. Borliqdagi har bir narsa, hodisa, jarayon bizning ko'z oldimizda alohida butunlik sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ular ma'lum bir qismlardan, bo'laklardan tashkil topadi. Bu qismlar, bo'laklar bir-biri bilan bog'lanib turib yagona bir yaxlitlikni, sistemani tashkil qiladi.

O'zaro dialektik aloqada bo'lgan qismlar, bo'laklar, tomonlar, elementlar, komponentlarning uzviy birligiga *butunlik* deyiladi. *Qism* esa ana shu butunlikning tarkibiga kirgan bo'lak, element, komponentdir.

Rus olimi M.V.Nikitin "*butun*" tushunchasini xolonim (grek.holos – butun so'zidan) "qism"ni meronim (grek. mer – qism so'zidan) yoki partonim (grek. partos – bo'lak, qism so'zlaridan) deb atashni taklif qiladi.

D.N.Shmelev birinchilardan bo'lib rus tili leksikasining paradigmatic guruhlariga har tomonlama va atroflicha tavsif beradi. U so'zlar o'rtasidagi paradigmatic munosabatlar borliqdagi predmetlarning o'rtasida mavjud munosabatlarga bog'liqligini, leksikadagi paradigmatic munosabatlar faqatgina ko'p

pog'onali yoki bir chiziqli emasligini aytib o'tadi. Ko'p so'zlar bir vaqtning o'zida turli leksik-semantik paradigmalariga mansub bo'lishi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi.

D.N.Shmelev haqli ta'kidlaganidek, til lug'at sostavida mavjud bo'lgan barcha munosabatlarning e'tiborga olinishi u yoki bu ko'rsatkichlarning mohiyatini hamda so'zlarning turli guruhlarini tashkil etish xususitlarini baholashga imkoniyat yaratadi.

Darhaqiqat, har bir tilda butun-bo'lak munosabatini ifodalashga xoslangan muayyan leksemalar guruhi mavjud bo'ladi, bu holat terminlarga ham xosdir. Xolomonimiy yoki partonimiyaning giper-giponimiyadan farqi shuki, giponimiyada maydonning bir komponenti boshqalariga zidlanib, ular o'rtasidagi ma'no munosabatlari aniqlansa, partonimiyada alohida olingan komponentning uni tashkil qilayotgan ichki a'zolari bilan munosabati masalasi o'rtaga tashlanadi. Ya'ni giponimiyada tashqi munosabatlar aniqlansa, partonimiyada ichki munosabatlar yuzaga chiqadi. Masalan, qo'shiqchilik termin maydoni komponentlaridan biri bo'lgan dasta terminini olaylik. **Dasta** – torli sozlarning chap qo'l bilan ushlanadigan qismi (grif). Demak, dasta tanbur, dutor, rubob singari an'anaviy sozlarning bir qismi hisoblanadi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, tanbur, dutor, rubob butunlik hisoblansa, dasta ularning bir qismidir.

B.Qilichev partonimiyasi haqida shunday yozadi: “Borliqdagi har qanday hodisa serqirra bo'lgani kabi har bir so'zning ma'no munosabatlari ham rang-barangdir. Shuning uchun har bir leksema shu leksema uchun xos bo'lgan sinonimik, graduonimik, giponimik, partonimik qatorlar kesishgan nuqtada turadi va uning lisoniy-ma'noviy mohiyati mana shu chiziqning kesishish nuqtasiga qarab belgilanadi”. Xuddi shu ta'rifni qo'shiqchilik terminlariga ham qo'llash mumkin. Qo'shiqchilik terminlari orasidagi partonimiyasi munosabatini tahlil qilamiz.

Ko'rinadiki, bayot terminining o'zi butunlik sifatida bir nechta qismlarga ajratiladi. Bu butun-bo'lak munosabati umumiylikni bildiradi. Faqat Hofiz Sheroziy g'azali bilan aytiladigan bayotlar esa xususiy butin-bo'lak munosabatini bildiradi.

Qo'shiqchilik termin maydoniga mansub bo'lgan yana bir termin manzumdir. Xorazm maqomlari ashula bo'limi **Manzum** (arab. – tuzilgan, terilgan ya'ni, nazm holiga keltirilgan) deb nomlangan. Ular muayyan tartibda, asosan g'azallarga bastalangani uchun Manzum deyiladi.

Har bir maqomda manzum bir necha ashula qismlaridan iborat yirik turkumni tashkil etadi. Ularda tuzilishi birligi, vazn-usul va shakllarning esa xilma-xilligi bilan ta'riflanadi. Manzumning asosiy qismlari – *Talqin, Nasr, Tarona, Suvora, Naqsh, Faryod, Ufar* va b.

Qo'shiqchilik termin maydoni komponentlari orasidagi butun-bo'lak munosabati yana **naqorat** termini orqali yuzaga chiqadi. **Naqorat** – qo'shiqning har bandidan so'ng muntazam ravishda takrorlanib turuvchi qismi. Naqoratning she'riy matni, odatda, to'rtlik yoki baytdan tashkil topib, tugal badiiy obrazni ifodalaydi. Naqorat musiqa asarining ikkinchi kuy davriyasi, ixcham va sodda shaklli namunalarda esa kuyning ikkinchi jumlasida sifatida gavdalanadi. Qo'shiq va madxiyalarda naqorat boshqa qismlardan musiqiy vazn, uslub va ijro sur'ati bilan farqlanishi mumkin. Xor jamoalariga mo'ljallab yaratilgan qo'shiqlarda naqorat qismi, odatda, yalpi xor tomonidan ijro etiladi. Ayrim xalq qo'shiq va yallalarida naqorat asosiy kuyi butunligicha takrorlaydi va bandlardan takroriy she'r matni tufayli ajratiladi. Demak, naqorat butunlik sifatida tugal badiiy obraz hisoblangan qo'shiqlarning, kuylarning, madhiyalarning, xalq qo'shiqlarining qismini tashkil qiladi.

Bu terminning zamonaviy varianti **kuplet** terminidir. **Kuplet** (frans. couplet) – 1) qo'shiq yoki she'rda naqorat tarzidagi band. Qo'shiq kuyi keyingi bandlarda ayvan (yoki qisman o'zgarishlar bilan) takrorlanadi. Kuplet musiqadagi ilk shakllardan bo'lib, o'zbek musiqa folkloridagi lapar, yalla, turli mavzudagi xalq qo'shiqlaridan o'rin olgan; 2) kupletlar – naqoratli, quvnoq, hazil yoki hajviy qo'shiq. Asosan, estrada hamda operetta (vodevil)da keng qo'llaniladi. Hozirgi zamon musiqasida bunday kupletlarni musiqali komediyalarda, estrada, sirk yoki konsert dasturlarida uchratish mumkin.

Qo'shiqchilik terminlari taraqqiyoti natijasida qismni bildirgan terminlar butunni ifodalay boshlagan. Masalan, **maqom** termini. **Maqom** (arab. – joy, makon, o'rin) – musulmon Sharqi musiqasida asosiy tushunchalardan biri. Dastlab muayyan balandlikdagi tovushni hosil etish uchun torli cholg'uning dastasida barmoq bilan bosiladigan joy, parda ma'nosida ishlatilgan. Demak, qismni bildirgan. Keyinchalik Sharq musiqa nazariyasi rivojlanishi jarayonida maqoming mazmun ko'lami tobora kengayib, bir-biriga nisbatan bog'liq boshqa ma'nolarni ham anglata boshlagah: lad tuzilmasi, lad tizimi; muayyan pardalar zaminida vujudga kelgan kuy-ohanglar; shakl, janr; bir qismli yoki turkumli cholg'u va ashula yo'llari; musiqiy uslub va boshqalar maqomlarga oid nazariy va musiqiy estetik masalalar Abu Yusuf Yoqub ibn Ishaq al-Kindiy va Forobiy (IX-X asrlar), Ibn Sino va Ibn Zayla (XI asr), Safiuddin al-Urmaviy (XIII asr), Mahmud ash-Sheroziy va Abdulqodir Marog'iy (XIX asr), Jomiy va Zaynulobiddin Husayniy (XV asr), Najmiddin Kavkabiyy Buxoriy (XVI asr), Darvishali Changiy (XVII asr) va boshqa olimlarning musiqiy risolalarida tadqiq etilgan.

Gradunimiya. Dunyo tilshunosligida XIX asr oxiri va XX asr o'rtalarida tilshunoslikning rivojlanish jarayonida dialektik tadqiq yo'liga o'tganligi kuzatilgan. Bunga misol qilib N.S.Trubetskoyning fonologiyada oppozitsiya munosabatini tadqiq qilganini, oppozitsiya nazariyasini yaratganligini keltirishimiz mumkin. Shu taqqiqot natijasida tilshunoslikka graduallik tushunchasi kiritildi. Bu tushunchaga ko'ra belgining u yoki bu darajasiga e'tibor qaratilgan. Natijada struktur-semantik yondashuvda belgining graduallik xususiyati logik-semantik va jug'aviy-sintaktik kategoriya sifatida talqin etilgan va kuchaytiruvchi kategoriya toifasiga kiritilgan.

E.Sepir gradumiya munosabatini me'yor va ularning qutblarini tadqiq qilgan va jarayonni psixologik jarayon sifatida o'rgangan. U gradunimiya o'lcham va miqdoriy hususiyatlarga bog'liq ekanligini ta'kidlagan. Hissiyotlarning ortishi/ kamayishiga qarab mantiqiy psixologik va lingvistik gradunimiyani ajratgan. U graduallashdagi boshlang'ich nuqta, gradual shkala, gradual chiziqning mavjud qutblari borligini ta'kidlab, gradatsiya psixologik jarayon sifatida o'lcham va miqdordan oldin inson tafakkurida shakllanishini asoslab bergan. Qo'shiqchilik termin maydon komponentlari orasidagi gradual munobatni kuylar orasida ko'rishimiz mumkin. Masalan, **avj** (arab. – cho'qqi, baland) – musiqa asarining yuqori pardalardagi cho'qqisi, kulminatsiya nuqtasi, ya'ni musiqa asarining eng baland registrdagi davomli kuy tuzilmasi. Avjlarning asosiy turlari – kichik Avj, o'rta Avj, katta (yoki yuqori) Avj deb yuritiladi. Sho'balarning miyonxat tuzilmasini kichik Avjga, dunasrni – o'rta Avjga va namudlarni – katta Avjga qiyoslash mumkin. Avjlar musiqa asarlari bayoni va rivojida shakllantiruvchi va ifodalovchi ahamiyatga ega. Ashulalardagi she'r mazmuni, fikr va his-tuyg'ularning ta'sir kuchini musiqiy vositalar yordamida teranlashtiradi. Avj ishlatish an'anasi o'zbek va umuman, Sharq bastakorlik san'atida, shuningdek, hofizlar va sozandalarning ijrochilik mahorati tufayli mukammallashib ma'lum tabiiy qonuniyat sifatida vujudga kelgan.

Grodunimiya munosabatini yuqorida bitta termin ichida ko'rinadi. Shu holatga yana **akkord** (lot. *accordo* – uyg'unlashtiraman) – turli balandlikdagi uch va undan ortiq tovushlarning qo'shib sadolanishiga aytiladi.

Barcha akkordlarning pastki tovushi–asosiy (yoki prima) ton, undan yuqoridagisi – tersiya toni, uchinchisi – kvinta toni, to'rtinchisi – septima toni, beshinchisi – nona toni deb yuritiladi va ana shu intervallarga mos raqamlar bilan belgilanadi. Akkordlar tarkiban (katta yoki kichik tersiyalar oldinma-ketin joylashishi jihatidan) bir-biridan farqlanadi. Asosiy tonidan hisoblanganida avval katta, so'ngra kichik tersiyalardan tuzilgan akkord – katta yoki major uchtovushligi, avval kichik so'ngra katta tersiyalardan tuzilgan akkord – kichik yoki minor uchtovushligi, ikki

katta tersiyadan tuzilgani– orttirilgan, ikki kichik tersiyadan tuzilgani – kamaytirilgan uchtovushlik deyiladi. Uchtovushlik va septakkordlar odatda musiqa tovushqatorining muayyan pog'onalarida tuziladi. Ana shu muayyan pag'onalar ham gradunimiya shkalasini namoyon qiladi deb aytish mumkin.

Bas (ital. basso – past) – 1) erkaklarning eng past, yo'g'on ovozi. Baland yoki kuychan Bas (ital. basso cantante) hamda past Baas (basso profundo), opera amaliyotida – xarakterli, hajviy Bas (basso buffo) farq qilinadi. Rus xorlarida oktavachi Baslar uchraydi, ular inson ovozi uchun eng past ovozdagi tovushlarni ijro eta oladi; XX asr xonandalaridan F. Shalyapin (Rossiya), N.Gyaurov (Bolgariya), Teo Adam (Germaniya), O'zbekistonda H. Ismoilov, V. Grinchenko, Q. Muhiddinov va boshqalarning ovozi Bas.

Bariton (ital. baritono, yun. barus – vazmin, past; ton–tovush) – 1) erkak xonandalar ovozining bir turi, balandligi jihatidan bas bilan tenor oralig'ida. O'zbek xonandalaridan M. Qoriyoqubov, N. Hoshimov, S. Benyaminov, chet el xonandalaridan D. Fisherdiskau, M. Mago-Masv, G. Ots, D. Xvorostovskiylar Bariton ovozlari bilan mashhur.

Tenor (lot. tenor – ovozning tekis xarakati) – erkak xonandaning baland (ingichka) ovozi. O'zbekistonda S. Yarashev, F. Abdurahmonov, A. Azimov, I. Jalilov, K.Serjanovlar tenor ovoziga ega.

Terminlarning ichida ba'zi terminlar o'z leksik ma'nosining teskari ma'nosida tushuniladi. Masalan,

Alt (ital. alto – yuqori, baland) – ovoz va soz turini bildiradi. Leksik ma'nosi yuqori, baland ma'nosini bersa ham, lekin u past ovozni ifodalaydi: u xor yoki vokal ansamblda partiya, xonanda bolalar yoki ayollar (messo-soprano, kontralto)ning past (yo'g'on) ovozini, xonanda o'g'il bolalarning past (yo'g'on) ovozini ko'rsatadi.

Qo'shiqchilik terminlari ichida bir musiqaning o'zida ham gradunimiya munosabati ko'riladi.

Daromad (musiqada) – muqaddima, debocha, umuman, asarning bosh qismi, bo'lagi va har qanday bosh qism singari past tezlikda bo'ladi. Daromad maqom sho'basi, shuningdek, uning shakliga mutanosib cholg'u va ashula asarlarining 1 boshlangich tuzilmasi, xati. Sarxat deb ham yuritiladi. Ular navbatdagi sho''ba uchun muqaddima hisoblanadi. Macalan, Daromadi Nasri Ushshoq, Daromadi Dugohi Husayniy va h.k. Daromad musiqaning yoki qo'shiqning boshlang'ich qism bo'lsa, har bir musiqaning va qo'shiqning avji bo'ladi. Avjning o'z nomi bor. Masalan, **vadavang** juda avjida degan ma'nonini bildiradi: *Bugun ashulalar vadavang-ku, Sher*

aka! (O. Yoqubov, Chin muhabbat) *Suv bo'yida harsillaydi podalar, to'qaylarda qushlar bazmi vadavang.* (Mirtemir)

Mumtoz ashulalarda qo'llanadigan mashhur avjning nomi **Zebo pari** deb nomlanadi. Taxminlarga ko'ra, bu avjni Zebo pari taxallusli farg'onalik mashhur xonanda va sozanda, bastakor Abdurahmon (XIX asr) ijod qilgan deb hisoblaydilar. Aslida, u bu avjni zo'r ehtiros va mahorat bilan ijro etganligi sababli avjga Zebo pari nomi berilgan. Zebo pari xonandalarning cho'qqi pardalarga chiqish, ovoz va badihago'ylik mahoratlarini namoyish etishlarida keng imkoniyatlarga ega.

Ko'rinadiki, qo'shiqchilik terminlari orasida turli munosabatlar mavjud. Biz ishning hajmi talabiga ko'ra faqat uchta: giponimiya, partonimiya, gradunimiya munosabatlarini o'rgandik.

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НОТИҚ ВА ТИНГЛОВЧИ ОРАСИДАГИ ЎЗARO МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ЖИХАТЛАРИ

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Кўпчилик олдида амалга ошириладиган оммабоп нутқларнинг энг юқори даражаси - бу тингловчилар билан ўзаро алоқага киришиш, яъни нотик ва тингловчилар рухий ҳолатидаги уйғунликдир. Нотиклик маҳорати таълим - тарбия, инсон руҳиятига оид асосий билимлардан, қонун-қоидалардан хабардор бўлишни ва нутқ жараёнида бевосита улардан тўғри фойдалана олишни талаб қилади. Нотик кўпчилик олдида чиқар экан, у қайсидир маънода педагог бўлиши зарур. У бир вақтнинг ўзида ҳам таълим бериши ва буни тарбия билан кўшилган ҳолда олиб бориши зарур. Ижтимоий тараққиёт жараёнида мафкуралар алмашади, фанларда ўзгача ёндашувлар юзага келади. Лекин инсоният тараққиёти жараёнида келажак авлод таълим - тарбияси учун тарихий анъаналарнинг энг яхши томонлари сақланиб қолади, ижодий ёндашувлар билан давом эттирилади. Бугунги педагогика фани ҳам нафақат ёш авлодни, балки бугунги давримиз кишиларини ҳам тарбиялаш ҳақида баҳс юритади. Нотиклик маҳорати асосида таълим-тарбия назариясининг асосий вазифалари туради. Нотиклик маҳоратини эгаллаш, нутқни ташкил этиш усуллари, нотиклик усуллари ҳам умумий дидактик қоидаларга, маълумотларга асосланади. Таълим назарияси таълимнинг мазмуни, моҳияти, ва усулларини баён қилиб беради. Маърузалар таълим жараёнида тингловчилар диққатига ҳавола этиладиган меъёрлардан бири саналади.

Нотик мавзу бўйича тайёр билимларнигина тингловчиларга етказиш билан чегараланиб қолмайди. Нотик тингловчиларни мавзу бўйича фикр - мулоҳаза юритишга ҳам ундайди. Агар маърузада бир неча муаммо муҳокама қилинса, бундай маъруза тингловчилар фикр доирасини кенгайтиради, уларни шу муаммолар ечими бўйича фикр - мулоҳаза билдиришга мажбур қилади.

Таълим жараёнида икки томон иштирок этади, яъни нотик ва тингловчидан иборат бўлади. Шунинг учун ҳам бу жараёнда нотик ва тингловчи шу жараёнга хос бўлган ўзаро муносабатларга киришади.

Нутқ – бу нотикнинг тингловчиларга билим, кўникма ва малака бериши, уларда янги ҳақиқатларни оча билишга қодир бўлган ижодий, мантиқий тафаккур тарбиясидир. Нотик томонидан тайёрланган нутқни тинглаш жараёни эса макон ва замонда маълум бир жойни, маълум бир вақт тушунчасини ўз

ичига олади. Нутқни тинглаш давомида тингловчилар билимларни, маълум бир кўникмаларни ўзлаштиришни, қабул қилиш, фикрлаш, мулоҳаза юритиш ҳаракатларини бажарадилар. Бу жараён қайта ишлаш жараёни саналади, чунки бир вақтнинг ўзида эшитилган, қабул қилинган билим ва малакалар муҳокама қилинади.

Маъруза жараёнида нотик ва тингловчилар ўртасида юзага келадиган умумийлик, уйғунлик биргаликда фикрлаш фаолияти ва шунга мос ҳис - туйғулар ифодаси орқали юзага чиқади. Нотикнинг нутқ предметига муносабати, унинг қизиқиши, ўзига бўлган қатъий ишончи тингловчиларни мавзу бўйича муносабат билдиришга ундайди. Халқ мақолларида шундай бир ҳикмат бор, яъни сўзнинг ярми нотикники бўлса ярми тингловчиникидир. Нотик тингловчиларни ўз диққат - эътиборида ушлаб туриши, уларнинг фикрларини уқиб, ҳис - ҳаяжонларини сезиб туриши зарур. Шундай ҳолдагина нотик ўз нутқининг қай бир жойини ўзгартириши, тузатиши мумкин бўлади. Нотик интеллектуал салоҳият эгаси бўлиши зарур, унинг дунёқараши, билим доираси кенг бўлиши, жуда кўп масалалар бўйича фикр билдира олиши, исталган мавзуда баҳс-мунозара юрита олиши унга муваффақият олиб келади.

Нотик ва тингловчилар ўртасидаги энг яхши муносабатлар, асосий кўрсаткичлар уларнинг бир-бирларини яхши тушунишга ҳаракат қилишларидаёқ бошланади. Агар тингловчилар нотикнинг дастлабки сўзлари, фикрларидаёқ уни ижобий қабул қила бошласалар, бу ҳолат тингловчиларнинг хатти - ҳаракатларидаёқ намоён бўлади. Уларнинг аудиторияда ўтиришлари, ўзларини тутишлари, нотикни диққат билан тинглаб туришлари, кўз қарашлари, юздаги жилмайиш, хайрихоҳлик билан тинглаб туришлари, ўрни билан кулишлари, қарсақларидаёқ яхши муносабатларнинг бошланганини кўриш мумкин. Шу вақтдан бошлаб залда тинчлик, осойишалик ҳукм суради. Нотик ва тингловчилар алоқаси - бу ўзгариб турувчи жараён, у тўлиқ ва нотўлиқ бўлиши мумкин. Агар аудиторияда тингловчиларнинг барчаси диққат билан нотикни тинглаётган бўлсалар, унга муносабатини билдириб турган бўлишса, бундай алоқани тўлиқ дейиш мумкин. Бу муносабат нотўлиқ ва қисман ҳам бўлиши мумкин. Тингловчилар диққатини тўлиқ жалб қилиш учун нотик овози, кўз қарашлари орқали доим тингловчилар билан алоқада бўлиб туриши зарур. Баъзан нотиклар барча тингловчиларга секингина кўз югуртириб чиқади. Энг аввало, нутқни бошлашдан аввал психологик пауза қилиш керак бўлади, бундай пауза узоғи билан 5-7 сониягача бўлиши мумкин. Нотик нутқида овоз, ритм бир хилда бўлмаслиги керак. Нотик ифодалаётган фикрлар

турлича оҳангда таълаффуз қилиниши, паузалар билан ажратиб турилиши лозим. Баъзан нотик катта паузаларни қилиши мумкин, бунда мазмун жиҳатдан бошқа фикрга ўтилади, ҳис-туйғуларни билдирилади, айтилади, жумлалар, фикрларнинг олдингиси ёки кейингисига нисбатан муҳимлигини таъкидлаш, муносабат билдириш учун бундай паузалар қилиш мумкин бўлади. Нотик имкон даражасида ҳар бир сўзнинг талаффузига куч сарфлаши керак бўлади.

Ҳозирги замон нотиклик санъатига хос бўлган уйғунлик - бу таҳлилий, таъсирий, тасвирий воситаларнинг қўлланишидир. Ҳозирги замон нотиклик санъати ҳам тарихий анъаналар асосида иш кўради. Нотикнинг фақат маълумотлар, ахборотлардан иборат бўлиши нотикнинг оддий, курак сўзлардан иборат нотикка айланган бўлади.

Мавзунинг тушунарли бўлиши, нотикдан қўзланган мақсадни амалга ошириш учун нотик бугунги мавжуд бўлган фан ютуқларидан, энг қулай, самарали бўлган усуллардан фойдаланиши нотик нотикнинг мантиқий жиҳатларини таъминлайди.

XORIJIY TILNI O'RGANUVCHILAR DUCH KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bugungi kunda ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilar duch keladigan muammolar va ularning yechimlari yoritilib berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: lug'at ishi, grammatika qiyinchiliklari, talaffuz muammolari, interaktiv, quiz, mnemotexnika, kontekstual, flesh-kartalar, chat, blog.

Bugungi kunda ingliz tiliga bo'lgan talab va qiziqish juda yuqori bo'lib, bog'cha yoshidagi bolalardan tortib yoshi katta mutaxassislargacha bu tilni o'rganishga harakat qilmoqdalar. Bu, albatta, ijobiy holat, chunki til o'rganish jarayoni nafaqat lingvistik bilimlarni rivojlantirish, balki shu tilda so'zlashuvchi davlatlarning madaniyati, tarixi va an'analarini anglash imkoniyatini ham yaratadi.

Ingliz tili esa bugungi kunda eng ko'p o'rganilayotgan til bo'lib, u ayniqsa xalqaro aloqa, texnologiya, san'at va turizm sohalarida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ko'plab mamlakatlarda u jahon tili sifatida o'qitilmoqda. Zamonaviy intensiv metodlar ishlab chiqilgan bo'lishiga qaramay, til o'rganish jarayonida o'ziga xos muammolar saqlanib qolmoqda [1].

Ko'pincha, til o'rganuvchilar so'z boyligini oshirish, grammatikani tushunish, talaffuzni yaxshilash va ravon gapirish bilan bog'liq qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Xorijiy tilni o'rganishda lug'at boyligi muhim rol o'ynaydi. Lug'atni o'rganish to'rt bosqichni o'z ichiga oladi: farqlash, ma'noni tushunish, eslab qolish va ma'nolarni mustahkamlash va kengaytirish. Diskriminatsiya bosqichi tovushlar va harflarni farqlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu gapirish, tinglash, o'qish va yozishda yordam beradi, chunki o'quvchilar tovushlarni farqlash orqali so'zlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qiladilar va o'qiganlarida yoki eshitganlarida ularni tushunadilar. Ma'noni tushunish so'zlar tushunchasini ularni referentlar bilan bog'lash orqali tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi. Esab qolish bosqichi ma'nolarni saqlab qolish qobiliyatidan iborat. Mustahkamlash va kengaytirish bosqichi yangi lug'atni o'rganish va uning o'quvchilarning lug'at tizimiga integratsiyalashuvini anglatadi.

Ravon gapira olish, fikrni to'g'ri ifodalash va turli kontekstlarda muloqot qilish imkoniyati bevosita so'z zaxirasiga bog'liq. Lug'at boyligi yetarli bo'lmasa, grammatika va fonetika yaxshi o'zlashtirilgan taqdirda ham samarali muloqot qilish qiyinlashadi. Shuning uchun so'zlarni mustahkamlash, ularni kontekstual sharoitlarda o'rganish va faol qo'llash til o'rganish jarayonining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi [2].

Xorijiy til o'rganuvchilar duch keladigan muammolar ko'p jihatdan ularning ona tili, o'rganish usullari va shaxsiy xususiyatlariga bog'liq. Quyida mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf qilishning ayrim yechimlarini keltiramiz.

1. Lug'at boyligini oshirishdagi muammolar. Yangi so'zlarni eslab qolish va ularni amaliyotda ishlata olmaslik muhim muammolardan biridir. Buni bartaraf etish uchun quyidagi yechimlar maqsadga muvofiq:

- So'zlarni alohida yodlash emas, balki jumlar va kontekst orqali o'rganish.
- Flesh-kartalar, mobil ilovalar va mnemotexnikadan foydalanish.
- O'qish va eshitish orqali yangi so'zlarni tabiiy ravishda o'zlashtirish.

2. Grammatikani o'zlashtirish qiyinchiliklar. Grammatik qoidalarni yodlab olish va ulardan to'g'ri foydalanish ko'pchilik uchun katta muammo. Chet tilining grammatikasi ona tilidan keskin farq qilishi mumkin, bu esa o'quvchilarning tushunishini qiyinlashtiradi. Buni bartaraf etish uchun:

- Grammatikani nazariy emas, balki amaliy muloqot orqali o'rganish.
- Misollar va kontekstual mashqlar yordamida qoidalarni tushuntirish.
- Interaktiv o'yinlar, jumladan, quizlar va testlar orqali o'zlashtirish maqsadga muvofiq.

3. Talaffuz muammolari. Ko'pchilik til o'rganuvchilar yangi til tovushlarini to'g'ri talaffuz qila olmaydi, chunki ular ona tilida mavjud emas [3].

Yechimlar:

- Audio va video darsliklardan foydalangan holda eshitish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.
- O'qituvchi yoki ona tilida so'zlashuvchilarning nutqini kuzatish va taqlid qilish.

- Lingvistika asosida ishlab chiqilgan fonetik mashqlar bilan shug'ullanish.

4. Ravon gapirish va muloqot qilishdagi qiyinchiliklar. Ko'pchilik grammatikani va so'z boyligini yaxshi bilishiga qaramay, gapirishda qiynaladi. Bu o'ziga ishonchsizlik yoki amaliyot yetishmovchiligi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Yechimlar:

- O'z-o'zidan gapirish texnikasidan foydalanish

•Muntazam ravishda ingliz tilida suhbatlashish (til klublari, onlayn chatlar, ovoz yozish amaliyotlari).

•Kunlik kundalik yoki blog yuritish.

5. Eshitish va tushunish muammolari. O'quvchilar uchun yangi tilning tezkor nutq shaklini tushunish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. Bu aksanlar va nutq tezligidan ham kelib chiqadi.

Yechimlar:

•Audio va video materiallarni muntazam ravishda tinglash.

•Avval oddiy matnlarni tinglash, keyin murakkabroq suhbatlarga o'tish.

•Subtitrlardan foydalanib, keyinchalik subtitrsiz tushunishga harakat qilish.

6. Xatolar qilishdan qo'rqish

Ko'pchilik o'quvchilar xato qilishdan qo'rqib, gapirishdan yoki yozishdan o'zini tiya boshlaydi.

Yechimlar:

•Xatolar tabiiy jarayon ekanligini tushunish va ularni o'rganish imkoniyati sifatida qabul qilish.

•Doimiy amaliyot va xatolardan o'rganishga harakat qilish.

•O'qituvchi yoki do'stlar bilan mashq qilish orqali o'ziga ishonchni oshirish.

7. Motivatsiya va vaqt yetishmovchiligi

Chet tilini o'rganish uzoq muddat talab qiladi, va ko'pchilik yo'lda qiziqishini yo'qotishi yoki vaqt ajrata olmasligi mumkin.

Yechimlar:

•Til o'rganish bo'yicha aniq reja tuzish va uni kundalik hayotga integratsiya qilish.

•Qiziqarli va foydali materiallardan foydalanish (kitoblar, filmlar, podkastlar).

•O'z yutuqlarini nishonlash va o'zini mukofotlash orqali motivatsiyani oshirish.

8. Notanish madaniyat va til farqlari

Chet tilini o'rganishda til bilan birga o'sha xalqning madaniyatini ham o'rganish lozim. Chunki ba'zi iboralar va odatlar biz uchun tushunarsiz yoki noodatiy bo'lishi mumkin.[4]

Yechimlar:

•Til bilan birga madaniy tadqiqotlar qilish.

•Ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchilar bilan suhbatlashish orqali ularning madaniyati va mentalitetini tushunish.

•Filmlar va kitoblar orqali real nutq namunalarini kuzatish.

Bular xorijiy til o'rganuvchilar duch keladigan asosiy muammolar va ularning yechimlaridir. Har bir til o'rganuvchi o'ziga mos usullarni topib, ulardan foydalansa, tilni tez va samarali o'rganishi mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, xorijiy til o'rganish jarayoni bir necha bosqichlardan iborat bo'lib, uning samaradorligi o'quvchining lug'at boyligi, grammatik bilimi, talaffuz mahorati va amaliy muloqot ko'nikmalariga bog'liq. Turli interaktiv usullar, innovatsion texnologiyalar va lingvistik yondashuvlardan foydalanish orqali til o'rganish jarayonini yanada samarali qilish mumkin.

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INTENTIONAL AND INCIDENTAL SECOND-LANGUAGE VOCABULARY ACQUISITION: A COMPREHENSIVE PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. *Vocabulary acquisition is a fundamental aspect of second language learning, yet the debate between intentional and incidental learning remains ongoing. This article provides a comprehensive perspective on both approaches, examining their theoretical underpinnings, cognitive mechanisms, and pedagogical applications. Intentional learning involves explicit instruction, structured exercises, and memory techniques, whereas incidental learning occurs through exposure to language in meaningful contexts such as reading, listening, and conversation. Cognitive processes such as elaboration, rehearsal, and automaticity play a crucial role in vocabulary retention and active use. The study highlights the complementary nature of both approaches, emphasizing the need for a balanced curriculum that integrates structured vocabulary instruction with authentic language exposure. Additionally, advancements in technology, including AI-driven platforms and mobile applications, are reshaping vocabulary learning strategies. By adopting a multifaceted approach, educators and learners can optimize vocabulary acquisition, enhancing overall language proficiency in second-language learning.*

Keywords: *vocabulary acquisition, intentional learning, incidental learning, cognitive processing, second language acquisition, educational technology.*

Introduction

The vocabulary instruction landscape has evolved significantly over the past few decades. Initially, language educators and academics placed less emphasis on vocabulary acquisition (Zimmerman, 1997). However, this perspective gradually began to shift with Krashen's introduction of the concept of comprehensible input (Hamakali, 2017) which highlighted the crucial role of vocabulary in second language acquisition (SLA). Acquiring vocabulary in a second language (L2) is a fundamental yet challenging task for learners. Educators and linguists have long debated the most effective strategies for vocabulary acquisition—whether learners should engage in intentional memorization or rely on incidental exposure. According to Krashen, vocabulary should be acquired incidentally, implying that language learners should come across target language words in meaningful contexts rather than through direct instruction (Karami, 2019).

This article explores both approaches, examining their theoretical foundations, practical applications, and pedagogical implications. By expanding upon cognitive processing, pedagogical strategies, and the role of technology in vocabulary learning, this article aims to provide a more comprehensive analysis of the topic.

Literature review

To effectively acquire vocabulary, learners must develop a nuanced understanding of words beyond their basic meanings (Schmitt & Schmitt, 2020). This includes semantic properties, phonological patterns, morphological structures, and pragmatic usage. The mental lexicon is often compared to a dictionary-like storage system, but modern cognitive theories suggest a more dynamic, interconnected network where words are retrieved based on contextual cues and associations (Arndt & Woore, 2018).

A crucial distinction in vocabulary learning is between **receptive vocabulary** (words recognized and understood in context) and **productive vocabulary** (words actively used in speech or writing) (Zhong, 2018). Research suggests that learners initially develop a passive understanding of words before integrating them into active use (González-Fernández & Schmitt, 2017). Thus, both comprehension-based exposure and active recall techniques play pivotal roles in vocabulary retention.

Intentional vocabulary learning involves explicit efforts to commit new words to memory through direct instruction, memorization techniques, and structured exercises (Sok & Han, 2020). This approach is often associated with traditional language instruction methods, including:

- **Flashcards and Word Lists:** A common method where learners repeatedly review new words along with their meanings and usage examples. Digital flashcard apps, such as Anki or Quizlet, enhance this process with spaced repetition algorithms.
- **Contextual Exercises:** Learners engage in activities that require them to use words in meaningful sentences, reinforcing retention.
- **Translation Drills:** Comparing L2 words with their first-language (L1) equivalents to create direct associations.
- **Mnemonics and Association Techniques:** Learners use memory aids, such as imagery or word associations, to enhance retention.

Research supports the efficacy of **spaced repetition**, which involves reviewing vocabulary at increasing intervals to reinforce memory (Hulstijn, 2001). Compared to massed learning (cramming), spaced repetition ensures more durable retention. Additionally, **depth of processing theory** suggests that learners retain words more effectively when they engage with them in multiple ways—such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening (Alemi & Tayebi, 2011).

In contrast, incidental vocabulary acquisition occurs as a byproduct of engaging in language-rich activities such as reading, listening, and conversation (Ahmad, 2012; Sok & Han, 2020; Yali, 2010). Key elements of incidental learning include:

- **Extensive Reading:** Encountering words in authentic contexts helps learners infer meanings through contextual clues.
- **Listening to Media:** Podcasts, movies, and conversations expose learners to natural language usage and pronunciation.
- **Interactive Communication:** Engaging in discussions with native speakers or peers provides opportunities for spontaneous vocabulary acquisition.

Studies indicate that **reading extensively in the target language** is one of the most effective ways to acquire vocabulary naturally (Yali, 2010). However, without conscious attention to new words, some vocabulary may be overlooked. Therefore, strategies like **annotated reading**, where learners highlight and review unknown words, can bridge the gap between passive exposure and active learning (Ahmad, 2012).

Analysis and Discussion

For a word to be permanently embedded in long-term memory, it must undergo deep cognitive processing (Nation, 2013). This involves:

- **Elaboration:** Actively associating new words with existing knowledge, such as linking them to known synonyms, antonyms, or conceptual categories.
- **Rehearsal:** Regular review and practice, using spaced repetition techniques to reinforce recall.
- **Automaticity:** Developing fluency in word retrieval so that vocabulary access becomes effortless during communication.

One of the **most significant challenges in vocabulary acquisition** is moving from recognition to production. Many learners recognize words when reading or listening but struggle to use them actively. Techniques like **shadowing (repeating words after hearing them)** and **dictation exercises** can accelerate the transition from passive knowledge to active fluency (Yang et al., 2021).

Motivation is a critical factor influencing vocabulary acquisition. Learners who engage in self-directed activities—such as reading topics of interest, watching engaging media, or participating in online forums—tend to acquire vocabulary more effectively than those relying solely on structured coursework (Klimova & Polakova, 2020). **Intrinsic motivation** (learning out of personal interest) fosters long-term retention, while **extrinsic motivation** (such as preparing for exams) can drive short-term gains.

Educators should recognize that intentional and incidental learning are complementary rather than mutually exclusive. A well-rounded language curriculum should integrate both methods:

1. **Structured Learning Activities:** Incorporating vocabulary drills, explicit word instruction, and personalized word banks.

2. **Encouraging Extensive Exposure:** Promoting reading and listening activities that immerse learners in the target language.

3. **Task-Based Learning:** Creating real-life scenarios where learners must apply newly acquired words in meaningful communication.

4. **Feedback and Assessment:** Providing corrective feedback and periodic vocabulary assessments to track progress.

By incorporating both direct instruction and experiential learning opportunities, teachers can create a holistic learning environment that maximizes vocabulary acquisition.

Advancements in educational technology have transformed vocabulary acquisition methods (Klimova & Polakova, 2020; Ko, 2019). Digital tools enhance both intentional and incidental learning through:

- **Vocabulary Apps:** Apps like Memrise and Duolingo use gamification to reinforce vocabulary acquisition.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tutors:** AI-driven platforms adapt to learners' strengths and weaknesses, offering personalized word recommendations.
- **Corpus-Based Learning:** Online language corpora (e.g., COCA, BNC) provide real-world examples of word usage.
- **Speech Recognition Software:** Tools like Google Assistant and Siri allow learners to practice pronunciation and receive feedback in real-time.

These technological resources supplement traditional learning by making vocabulary acquisition more interactive and engaging.

Conclusion

A successful L2 vocabulary learning strategy should leverage both intentional and incidental learning. While structured learning provides the foundation, immersive experiences allow learners to integrate new words naturally into their active vocabulary (Lichtman & VanPatten, 2021). Cognitive strategies such as **elaboration, rehearsal, and automaticity** are essential for retention and fluency. Moreover, **motivation and engagement** play vital roles in determining the effectiveness of vocabulary acquisition.

As technology continues to evolve, digital tools will play an increasingly important role in language learning (Ko, 2019). However, the fundamental principle remains the same: **a balanced approach combining structured learning with real-world exposure is the key to mastering a second language's vocabulary.**

By understanding the interplay between different learning methods, learners and educators can adopt strategies that optimize vocabulary acquisition and enhance overall language proficiency.

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INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AS CONSTRUCTIVE DIALOGUE

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Annotation: *This article examines intercultural dialogue as a mechanism for bridging cultural, social, and political divides in globalized societies. It analyses how cultural differences influence dialogue dynamics through theoretical frameworks such as Hall's communication styles, Hofstede's cultural dimensions, and Bennett's Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity. Case studies—including South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission and UNESCO's interreligious initiatives—illustrate both the potential and limitations of dialogue in post-conflict reconciliation. The article identifies persistent challenges (e.g., power imbalances, digital polarization) and proposes actionable strategies for fostering inclusive dialogue, such as third-culture building and critical media literacy. It concludes by emphasizing the urgency of intercultural dialogue in addressing transnational crises like climate change and systemic inequality.*

Keywords: *Intercultural dialogue, Constructive dialogue, Cultural dimensions (Hall, Hofstede), Conflict Resolution, Digital polarisation, Active listening, Global citizenship, Mutual respect, empathy, Equality and inclusivity, Flexibility and Non-violent communication.*

Intercultural dialogue has emerged as a critical framework for addressing social fragmentation in an increasingly interconnected world. Defined as an "open exchange of views between individuals and groups from different cultural backgrounds" [1], it fosters mutual understanding and collaborative problem-solving. This article analyzes its theoretical foundations, practical applications, and persistent challenges, drawing on interdisciplinary research from communication studies, sociology, and conflict resolution.

Edward T. Hall's distinction between high-context and low-context communication styles explains why misunderstandings arise in intercultural interactions. For example, negotiators from high-context cultures (e.g., Japan) prioritize implicit messages, while low-context counterparts (e.g., Germany) favour directness [2]. These differences, if unaddressed, can escalate into conflicts.

Geert Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory further clarifies how power distance, individualism, and uncertainty avoidance shape dialogue dynamics [3]. Societies with high power distance (e.g., Malaysia) may resist egalitarian dialogue structures, complicating collaborative efforts.

The Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (DMIS) Milton Bennett's DMIS outlines six stages of intercultural competence, from denial to integration (synthesizing multiple cultural perspectives) [4]. Constructive dialogue

requires participants to reach at least the acceptance stage, where cultural differences are acknowledged without judgment.

Intercultural dialogue refers to the open exchange between people from different cultural backgrounds. The aim is to encourage understanding, appreciation, and empathy, while also challenging stereotypes and prejudices. It is a process that emphasizes learning from each other, not just about differences, but also about shared human experiences. By approaching dialogue with an open mind, we create an environment where cultural diversity is not just tolerated but celebrated. However, intercultural dialogue isn't just about talking; it's about creating an opportunity to listen, understand, and collaborate in a way that strengthens societal bonds. Constructive dialogue is the key to making these conversations fruitful. It requires intention, patience, and a willingness to engage in conversations that can sometimes be difficult. There are some key principles of Constructive Intercultural Dialogue including active listening, mutual respect, empathy, equality, inclusivity, flexibility and non-violent communication.

Active Listening: One of the most important components of constructive dialogue is active listening. This means not only hearing the words of the other person but also trying to understand the emotions, values, and experiences behind those words. It requires an open mind and a willingness to step outside one's cultural framework to gain a deeper understanding of others [5].

Mutual Respect: Respect is at the core of constructive intercultural dialogue. This respect is not just about politeness but about recognizing the inherent dignity and worth of each individual, regardless of their cultural background. Mutual respect builds trust and makes it easier for people to communicate openly and honestly [6].

Empathy: Empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others. It plays a pivotal role in intercultural dialogue, as it enables people to connect on a deeper, more personal level. By putting oneself in another person's shoes, it becomes easier to appreciate the challenges and values that shape their worldview [7].

Equality and Inclusivity: Constructive intercultural dialogue cannot take place if there is an imbalance of power. All participants should be encouraged to contribute equally, ensuring that every voice is heard and valued. This promotes a sense of belonging and enables a richer exchange of ideas [8].

Open-mindedness and Flexibility: Constructive dialogue requires an open-minded approach, where individuals are willing to reconsider their perspectives and adopt new ones. It's important to approach intercultural dialogue with curiosity rather

than defensiveness, understanding that new ideas can enrich and expand our own beliefs [9].

Nonviolent Communication: Constructive dialogue is founded on nonviolent communication, which focuses on expressing one's feelings and needs without attacking or blaming others. This encourages a more peaceful, cooperative exchange, allowing for greater understanding and the resolution of conflicts without hostility [10].

Intercultural dialogue is not a panacea but a process requiring sustained commitment. As global crises like climate change demand collective action, its role in building inclusive coalitions will only grow. Future research must address digital mediation's dual role as both a barrier and a bridge.

Intercultural dialogue as constructive dialogue is an essential tool for building more inclusive, peaceful, and harmonious societies. By embracing principles such as active listening, mutual respect, empathy, and open-mindedness, we can create environments where cultural differences are not just tolerated but celebrated. When people engage in dialogue with a shared commitment to understanding and collaboration, it becomes possible to address challenges, build stronger communities, and foster global peace. Through these conversations, we can work towards a future where cultural diversity is seen as a source of strength rather than division [11].

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DIGITAL EDUCATION IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Digital education has emerged as a transformative force in modern education, offering numerous benefits such as personalized learning, increased access to resources, and collaborative learning opportunities. Educators have a role in building community through interactive platforms like video calls and group projects. Ultimately, this article emphasizes the need to balance the benefits of digital education with strategies to mitigate its challenges, aiming for an inclusive learning environment that supports every student's success. While digital education offers exciting opportunities, we need to find a balance between its advantages and the challenges it brings, striving for an inclusive environment that promotes success for all learners.*

Key words: *nearpod, digital tool, random wheel name generator, objective, activity.*

Learners are challenging with Passive Voice. In writing they frequently made mistake with this topic. I used Nearpod digital platform to create activity. Because with one access students do a series of exercises which helps consolidate the topic. This educational platform lets educators to upload videos which explains topic. After explanation of topic different types of activities can be done with one attempt of access. Moreover, this platform lets educators to control activities whether students' do with their own pace or with control of teacher. It is possible to present instruction before activity.

I uploaded a 2-minute video which gives clear explanation on the topic. In activity 1, students will cross out "by" in sentences if it is not necessary. They easily can cross out it by touching on the screen. In the screen of teacher results will appear which gives a chance to assess. In activity 2, students will test their comprehension by selecting the correct word from provided options on the screen to complete sentences. There will be 7 sentences for them to practice. Activity 3 is really important which checks their accuracy in writing. Students will rewrite sentences in passive voice. Activity 4 includes 10 quiz questions showing results on teacher's screen. During the lesson this platform will be set in teacher control. Although they work activities individually, they can share ideas and can compete with results. Because Hanson-Smith(2018) states that teachers and researchers have found that when students work together in groups or teams using computer programs, they become more excited to learn. This excitement, also known as motivation, helps students stay interested in their work.

Objective:

By the end of the exercises, students will be able to:

- Identify the structure of passive voice sentences.
- Transform active voice sentences into passive voice correctly by using “by”.
- Apply the passive voice in writing to enhance clarity and focus on the action rather than the subject.

They have two ways to access:

- Through link: <https://app.nearpod.com/?pin=6LC4S>
- Enter **join.nearpod.com** and enter code **6LC4S**

Instructions

1. Sheikh Zayed Bridge is traveled by thousands of people every day.
2. It was completed in 2010 by a large team of workers.
3. It was designed by Zaha Hadid.
4. The bridge is considered by many to be one of the most interesting bridges in the world.
5. The famous wave is supported by four pillars.
6. The bridge is also known by locals for its beautiful lighting.

Here students will choose type of pencil and will cross out unnecessary word “by”.

Fill in the blanks

1. The architect Zaha Hadid was to all. Everyone knew her name.
2. The Russky Bridge in Russia was by engineers to handle extreme temperature changes.
3. The Ponte Vecchio Bridge in Italy has by workers several times. It is now stable.
4. The oldest truss bridge was damaged in a fire. The fire was by a small spark.
5. The Eshima Dhashi Bridge in Japan has a steep incline. It is the “roller-coaster bridge.”
6. The Pont Du Gard aqueduct in France is an amazing bridge. Nothing but stone was to construct it.
7. The Danjiang Bridge between Bali and Taiwan is being built right now. It will by the end of this year.

used

been

be

designed

called

completed

caused

repaired

DONE

Students will fill in the blanks by replacing the words.

Rewrite the sentences about the Stari Most Bridge. Use the passive voice. Use a "by" phrase, if possible.

The bridge

Here if students press above on the right which circled in red color, sentences will appear. They will rewrite sentences in passive voice.

Question 1 / 10

Construction on the Eiffel Tower was completed in 1889 by the workers.

A. The by phrase is needed.

B. The by phrase is not needed.

1 answer(s) selected

Next

Here students will do quiz.

The Neapod app offers many features for teaching English, but it has some drawbacks. While there is a free version, valuable features require a paid subscription, which might not be affordable for everyone. Moreover, reliance on the app can reduce engagement with traditional learning methods. Finally, the app may lack sufficient opportunities for speaking practice, an essential part of language learning. These factors should be considered when using Neapod.

As my learners live in Outer circle country, they do not exposed with English. That's why they are mostly challenging with speaking. This activity is created to overcome this issue and improve their speaking. I wanted to create a photo in Copilot

where it is possible to create any kind of pictures depending on one's need. Several topics were chosen to create photo. As mostly my learners feel shy to speak, random choosing tool was used to engage students to participate. Random choosing arise students' interest because their name appears on the screen suddenly. Kiddle (2013) states that many tools were made just for language learning and teaching. However, now we also use tools that were created for other purposes, like games or apps, and find ways to use them for learning.

The students will be chosen randomly with the help of <https://wheelofnames.com/>

Using a random wheel name generator in speaking classes can have several drawbacks. Firstly, it lacks personalization, as generated names may not resonate with students, making activities less engaging. Some students may also feel anxious when called randomly, which can hinder their participation. The frequent spinning of the wheel can disrupt the flow of discussions, leading to a disjointed class experience. Moreover, unequal participation can occur, causing feelings of resentment among students. Additionally, the random nature may not connect with lesson topics, limiting context and depth of discussion. Overall, these factors must be considered to maintain an effective learning environment.

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DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION IN A MODERN MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: *The dynamic nature of the 21st-century global environment demands a transformative approach to professional education, especially in multicultural contexts. As Uzbekistan undergoes significant socio-economic reforms, its professional education system must evolve to meet the diverse needs of its population and align with global standards. This article explores innovative approaches to professional education in modern multicultural environments, focusing on Uzbekistan. It examines the role of technology, cross-cultural communication, competency-based learning, and policy reforms in shaping effective educational strategies. Drawing on global best practices and local case studies, the study provides insights into the challenges and opportunities in developing a progressive professional education framework.*

Keywords: *Professional Education, Innovative Approaches, Multicultural Environment, Uzbekistan, Educational Reforms, Technology Integration, Cross-Cultural Competence, Globalization.*

Introduction

The rapid pace of globalization has led to increased cultural diversity within nations, transforming the traditional landscape of professional education. In Uzbekistan, a country with a rich cultural heritage and a strategic geopolitical position, the education system faces the dual challenge of preserving national identity while embracing global trends. The development of innovative approaches to professional education is critical in preparing students for the demands of the modern workforce, characterized by technological advancements, cultural pluralism, and dynamic socio-economic conditions.

Professional education is no longer limited to technical skill acquisition; it now encompasses the development of soft skills, critical thinking, adaptability, and cultural competence. In Uzbekistan, government initiatives such as the "Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021" have emphasized the need for educational reforms to foster innovation and international competitiveness (Government of Uzbekistan, 2017, p. 45). These reforms aim to create a learning environment that nurtures creativity, problem-solving abilities, and a global outlook among students.

This article investigates the evolution of professional education in Uzbekistan, focusing on the integration of innovative teaching methodologies, the role of digital

technologies, and the importance of multicultural awareness. By analyzing both global best practices and local experiences, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive framework for developing professional education that meets the challenges of the modern multicultural environment.

The Concept of Professional Education in the 21st Century

Professional education, also known as vocational or technical education, has evolved significantly in the 21st century. Traditionally focused on specific job-related skills, it now emphasizes lifelong learning, adaptability, and the development of a broad skill set that includes both technical and soft skills. In today's globalized world, professional education must prepare individuals not only for existing jobs but also for roles that may emerge in the future due to technological advancements and changing economic demands.

According to Schleicher (2018, p. 22), modern professional education systems must foster creativity, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking to ensure students are equipped to thrive in dynamic work environments. This shift reflects the growing need for professionals who can adapt to various cultural contexts, work collaboratively in diverse teams, and navigate complex technological landscapes.

In Uzbekistan, professional education is undergoing a transformation to align with these global trends. The government's focus on educational reforms, particularly under the National Development Strategy, aims to modernize curricula, enhance teacher training, and promote innovative teaching methods. This reflects an understanding that education is a key driver of economic growth and social development in the 21st century.

The Impact of Multiculturalism on Professional Education

Multiculturalism has become a defining characteristic of modern societies, influencing various aspects of life, including education. In Uzbekistan, a country with a diverse population comprising Uzbeks, Russians, Tajiks, Kazakhs, and other ethnic groups, multiculturalism is deeply embedded in the social fabric. This diversity presents both challenges and opportunities for professional education.

One of the primary challenges is ensuring that educational content and teaching methods are inclusive and culturally sensitive. Educators must be equipped to address the diverse learning needs of students from different cultural backgrounds, fostering an environment of mutual respect and understanding. As noted by Banks, multicultural education promotes equity, social justice, and academic excellence by recognizing and valuing the cultural identities of all students.

On the other hand, multiculturalism offers opportunities to enrich the educational experience. Exposure to diverse perspectives enhances critical thinking, encourages open-mindedness, and prepares students to work effectively in global settings. In Uzbekistan, incorporating multicultural content into professional education can strengthen national unity while promoting global citizenship.

Innovative Approaches in Professional Education

Innovation in professional education involves the adoption of new methods, tools, and strategies to improve learning outcomes. These approaches are designed to make education more relevant, engaging, and effective in preparing students for the demands of the modern workforce.

a) Competency-Based Education (CBE):

CBE focuses on developing specific skills and competencies that are directly aligned with industry requirements. Unlike traditional education models that emphasize theoretical knowledge, CBE prioritizes practical skills and real-world applications. In Uzbekistan, vocational colleges are increasingly adopting CBE to ensure graduates possess the competencies needed in sectors such as information technology, engineering, and healthcare.

b) Project-Based Learning (PBL):

PBL encourages students to work on real-world projects, promoting active learning and critical thinking. This approach helps students develop problem-solving skills, teamwork, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations. According to Thomas (2000, p. 12), PBL enhances student engagement and motivation, leading to deeper learning outcomes.

c) Blended Learning:

Blended learning combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning, offering flexibility and personalized learning experiences. This approach is particularly relevant in Uzbekistan, where digital technologies are increasingly integrated into the education system. Blended learning allows students to learn at their own pace, access diverse resources, and develop digital literacy skills essential for the modern workforce.

d) Lifelong Learning:

In a rapidly changing world, learning does not end with formal education. Lifelong learning emphasizes continuous skill development throughout an individual's career. Uzbekistan's professional education system is incorporating lifelong learning principles to support workforce development and economic competitiveness.

The Role of Technology in Transforming Vocational Training

The integration of technology into professional education has revolutionized the way students learn and educators teach. Digital tools and platforms enhance accessibility, facilitate interactive learning, and enable personalized instruction.

a) E-Learning and Online Platforms:

E-learning platforms provide flexible learning opportunities, allowing students to access educational content anytime, anywhere. In Uzbekistan, initiatives such as the development of online courses and virtual classrooms have expanded access to professional education, especially in remote areas.

b) Simulation and Virtual Reality (VR):

Simulations and VR technologies offer immersive learning experiences, enabling students to practice skills in realistic environments without the risks associated with real-world settings. For example, medical students can perform virtual surgeries, while engineering students can operate virtual machinery.

c) Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education:

AI-powered tools can personalize learning by analyzing student performance data and adapting instructional content to meet individual needs. According to Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014, p. 58), AI enhances learning efficiency and helps educators identify areas where students need additional support.

Case Studies from Uzbekistan

Case Study 1: Tashkent State Technical University (TSTU)

TSTU has implemented innovative teaching methods, including project-based learning and industry partnerships. Students engage in hands-on projects that address real-world challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving skills.

Case Study 2: Professional Education Reform in Samarkand

In Samarkand, vocational schools have integrated digital technologies into their curricula. Teachers receive ongoing professional development in digital literacy, and students benefit from interactive e-learning resources.

Case Study 3: Entrepreneurship Education in Fergana Valley

Entrepreneurship programs in Fergana Valley focus on developing business skills among young professionals. The curriculum includes mentorship from local entrepreneurs, practical business projects, and exposure to international best practices.

Challenges in Implementing Innovative Educational Strategies

Despite significant progress, several challenges hinder the effective implementation of innovative approaches in professional education in Uzbekistan:

Resistance to Change: Traditional mindsets and resistance to new teaching methods can slow the adoption of innovative practices.

Limited Resources: Inadequate funding and infrastructure can restrict access to modern technologies and training materials.

Teacher Training: Many educators lack the necessary skills and knowledge to implement innovative teaching methods effectively.

Inequity in Access: Students in rural areas may face barriers to accessing quality education and digital resources.

Strategies for Overcoming Barriers

To address these challenges, the following strategies are recommended:

Professional Development for Educators: Continuous training programs to equip teachers with innovative pedagogical skills.

Public-Private Partnerships: Collaborations with industries to provide resources, expertise, and real-world learning opportunities.

Policy Reforms: Government policies that support educational innovation, including funding for technology and infrastructure development.

Inclusive Education: Ensuring that all students, regardless of background, have access to quality professional education.

Global Best Practices and Their Adaptation in Uzbekistan

Countries like Finland, Germany, and Singapore have set benchmarks in professional education through innovative practices. Key lessons from these countries include:

Germany's Dual Education System: Combines classroom instruction with practical training in companies, ensuring strong industry alignment.

Finland's Focus on Teacher Autonomy: Empowers educators to design curricula that meet students' needs, fostering creativity and innovation.

Singapore's SkillsFuture Initiative: Promotes lifelong learning and continuous skill development across all sectors.

Uzbekistan can adapt these best practices by considering local cultural, economic, and social contexts, ensuring that educational reforms are both effective and sustainable.

Conclusion

The development of innovative approaches to professional education in a modern multicultural environment is essential for preparing students to succeed in the global workforce. Uzbekistan's commitment to educational reforms, technological integration, and multicultural inclusivity reflects its vision for a progressive and

dynamic professional education system. By embracing innovative teaching methods, fostering cross-cultural competencies, and leveraging global best practices, Uzbekistan can create a robust educational framework that supports economic growth and social cohesion.

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NUTQIY MULOQOT NAZARIYASI: TILSHUNOSLIKDAGI O'RNI, NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining tilshunoslikda tutgan o'rni va uning rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shgan olimlarning ilmiy g'oyalari haqida batafsil ma'lumot beradi. Maqolada nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatgan asosiy olimlar (Ferdinand de Saussure, Karl Böhler, Roman Jakobson, Jon Ostin, Jon Serl, Pol Grays va boshqalar) hamda ularning ilmiy yondashuvlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, diskurs tahlili kabi yo'nalishlarning nutqiy muloqot nazariyasiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatganligi va uning amaliy ahamiyati ko'rsatilgan. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining til o'qitish metodikasi, tarjima, nutq terapiyasi, psixologiya, sotsiologiya va sun'iy intellekt kabi sohalarda qo'llanilishi, shuningdek, zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan integratsiyasi haqida ham batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi, pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, diskurs tahlili, nutqiy aktlar nazariyasi, kompyuter lingvistikasi, kognitiv lingvistika.

Kirish.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi tilshunoslikda XX asrning ikkinchi yarmida paydo bo'lgan va tilning kommunikativ funksiyasiga, ya'ni odamlar o'rtasida axborot almashish, fikr bildirish va o'zaro ta'sir qilish vositasi sifatidagi roliga e'tibor qaratadigan yo'nalishdir. Bu nazariya tilni nafaqat belgilar tizimi, balki insonlar o'rtasidagi muloqot jarayonida qo'llaniladigan vosita sifatida o'rganadi. U tilning ijtimoiy va psixologik jihatlariga, nutqiy xatti-harakatlarga, nutqiy aktlarga, nutqiy janrlarga va boshqa masalalarga e'tibor qaratadi.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining shakllanishida Ferdinand de Sossur (1857-1913) katta ahamiyat kasb etdi. U tilshunoslikka strukturaviy yondashuvni olib keldi va nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining shakllanishiga zamin yaratdi. Sossur tilni belgilar tizimi sifatida ko'rib chiqdi va tilning langue (til tizimi) va parole (nutq) kabi ikki tomonini ajratib ko'rsatdi. U tilning statik (sinxronik) va dinamik (diaxronik) jihatlarini o'rganishga e'tibor qaratdi.¹ Karl Böhler (1879-1963) tilning uchta funksiyasini - ifodalash, murojaat qilish va tasvirlash funksiyalarini ajratib ko'rsatdi.² U tilning kommunikativ funksiyasiga e'tibor qaratgan bo'lsa Roman Jakobson (1896-1982) tilning oltita funksiyasini - referensial, emotiv, konativ, fatik, poetik va

¹ Saussure, F. de. (1977). Kurs obshchey lingvistiki [Umumiy tilshunoslik kursi]. Moskva: Izdatel'stvo progressa.

² Böhler, K. (2000). Teoriya yazyka. Moskva: Izdatel'stvo progressa.

metalingvistik funksiyalarni ajratib ko'rsatdi³. Ludvig Vitgenshteyn (1889-1951) - avstriyalik faylasuf bo'lib tilni "til o'yinlari" sifatida ko'rib chiqdi va tilning kontekstga bog'liqligini ta'kidledi.⁴ Jon Ostin (1911-1960) "nutqiy aktlar nazariyasi"ni ishlab chiqdi va nutqiy muloqot jarayonida so'zlar nafaqat ma'lumot berish, balki harakat qilish uchun ham ishlatilishini ko'rsatdi. U nutqiy aktlarning lokutiv, illokutiv va perlokutiv aspektlarini ajratib ko'rsatdi. Amerikalik faylasuflardan Jon Serl nutqiy aktlar nazariyasini rivojlantirdi va nutqiy aktlarning turlarini (masalan, va'da berish, buyruq berish, so'rash va boshqalar) klassifikatsiya qildi.⁵ U nutqiy aktlarning illokutiv kuchini va tinglovchiga ta'sirini o'rgandi. Ingliz faylasufi Pol Grays (1910-1988) "implikatura nazariyasi"ni ishlab chiqdi va nutqiy muloqot jarayonida ishtirokchilarning bir-birlarining niyatlarini tushunishga intilishlarini va nutqiy implikatsiyalarni chiqarishlarini ta'kidledi. U muloqotning kooperativlik prinsipini va to'rtta maksimasini (miqdor, sifat, aloqadorlik va uslub) ishlab chiqdi.⁶ Ushbu olimlarning nazariyalari nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining shakllanishiga va rivojlanishiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Ularning g'oyalari tilshunoslikda yangi yo'nalishlarning paydo bo'lishiga va tilning kommunikativ funksiyasini o'rganishga yo'l ochdi.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining asosiy yo'nalishlari va ularning tilshunoslikda tutgan o'rni.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining rivojlanishida bir qator yo'nalishlar shakllandi va ularning har biri tilshunoslikda muhim o'rin tutadi:

1. Pragmatika - nutqiy muloqot jarayonida tilning qo'llanilishini, tilning kontekstga bog'liqligini, nutqiy vaziyatning nutq ma'nosiga ta'sirini o'rganib uning kommunikativlik funksiyasini tushunishga yordam beradi. U nutqiy aktlar nazariyasi, implikatura nazariyasi kabi muhim nazariyalarning shakllanishiga olib keldi.

2. Sotsiolingvistika tilning ijtimoiy jihatlarini, turli ijtimoiy guruhlar tomonidan tilning qo'llanilishini, tilning ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarini o'rganadi.

3. Psixolingvistika tilshunoslikka nutqiy muloqot jarayonida insonning psixologik mexanizmlarini o'rganish orqali tilning psixologik jihatlarini tushunishga yordam beradi. U nutqni idrok etish va yaratish jarayonlarini o'rganish orqali tilshunoslik doirasini boyitdi.

³ Jakobson, R. (1975). Lingvistika i poetika [Tilshunoslik va poetika]. Moskva: Izdatel'stvo progressa.

⁴ Wittgenstein, L. (1994). Filosofskie issledovaniya [Falsafiy tadqiqotlar]. Moskva: Izdatel'stvo progressa.

⁵ Searle, J. R. (1969). Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁶ Grice, H. P. (1989). Studies in the Way of Words. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

4. Diskurs tahlili nutqiy muloqot jarayonida yaratilgan matn yoki nutqni, uning tuzilishini, ma'nosini va funktsiyalarini hamda matnning kontekstga bog'liqligini, uning ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatlarini o'rganadi.

Ushbu yo'nalishlar tilning ijtimoiy, psixologik va madaniy jihatlarini o'rganish orqali tilshunoslikda rivojlandi.

Hozirgi kunda nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi doimiy ravishda rivojlanib bormoqda. Unda kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi, kognitiv lingvistika kabi yo'nalishlar hamda yangi tendensiyalar bilan boyitilmoqda.

Jumladan, kompyuter texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi nutqiy muloqot nazariyasiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda chunki kompyuter lingvistikasi nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining nazariyalarini va metodlarini kompyuter dasturlari va sun'iy intellekt tizimlarida qo'llash imkonini bermoqda. Bu esa nutqiy muloqotni avtomatik ravishda tahlil qilish, tarjima qilish va modellashtirish imkonini beradi. Korpus lingvistikasi esa katta hajmdagi matnlar korpusini yaratish va tahlil qilish bilan shug'ullangani sababli nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining korpus lingvistikasining metodlaridan foydalanib, nutqiy muloqotning empirik ma'lumotlarini to'plash va tahlil qilishga salmoqli yordam beradi, bu esa nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining nazariyalarini amaliyotda tekshirish va rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Kognitiv lingvistika tilni insonning kognitiv tizimi bilan bog'liq holda o'rganadi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi kognitiv lingvistikasining g'oyalaridan foydalanib, nutqiy muloqot jarayonida insonning kognitiv mexanizmlarini (masalan, idrok, xotira, tafakkur) o'rganadi. Bu ham nutqiy muloqotni yanada chuqur va to'liq tushunishga ko'maklashadi. Zamonaviy sharoitda nutqiy muloqot nafaqat verbal, balki nonverbal vositalar (masalan, imo-ishoralar, mimika, vizual materiallar) orqali ham amalga oshiriladi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi multimodal muloqotni o'rganishga e'tibor qaratmoqda va nutqiy muloqotning turli xil modalitlarini (masalan, nutq, yozuv, imo-ishora) o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirni o'rganmoqda. Ushbu tendensiyalar nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining rivojlanishiga va tilshunoslik doirasining kengayishiga olib kelmoqda.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining amaliy ahamiyati.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi nafaqat nazariy, balki amaliy ahamiyatga ham ega. U tilshunoslikning turli sohalarida, shuningdek, boshqa fanlar va amaliy sohalarida qo'llaniladi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining amaliy ahamiyati quyidagi yo'nalishlarda namoyon bo'ladi:

1. *Til o'qitish metodikasi.* Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi til o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining asosiy tushunchalari (kommunikativ kompetensiya, diskurs, intertekstuallik va boshqalar) til

o'qitish jarayonida talabalarning kommunikativ ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasiga asoslangan til o'qitish metodlari talabalarga tilni nafaqat grammatik qoidalar va lug'at boyligi, balki nutqiy muloqot jarayonida qo'llashni ham o'rgatadi.

2. *Tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyoti.* Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyotida ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tarjima jarayonida tarjimon nafaqat so'zlarning ma'nosini, balki matnning kommunikativ funksiyasini, diskursiv tuzilishini va intertekstual aloqalarini ham hisobga olishi kerak. Shu sababli nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi tarjimonlarga matnning kommunikativ maqsadi va kontekstini tushunishga, shuningdek, turli tillarda nutqiy muloqotning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olishga yordam beradi.

3. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi *nutq terapiyasida* nutq nuqsonlari bo'lgan kishilarga yordam berishda qo'llaniladi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasidan foydalanib, terapevtlar bemorlarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishga, ularning nutqiy xatti-harakatlarini tuzatishga va nutqiy muloqotga kirishish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

4. *Psixologiyada* nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi insonlarning o'zaro munosabatlarini, ularning nutqiy xatti-harakatlarini va muloqot jarayonidagi psixologik mexanizmlarni o'rganishda qo'llaniladi. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi psixologlarga insonlarning nutqiy muloqotini tushunishga, ularning o'zaro ta'sirini tahlil qilishga va psixologik muammolarni hal qilishda yordam beradi.

5. *Sotsiologiyada* esa nutqiy muloqotdan jamiyatda tilning o'rnini, ijtimoiy guruhlar o'rtasidagi muloqotni va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarni o'rganishda qo'llaniladi. Bu nazariya sotsiologlarga tilning ijtimoiy funktsiyalarini tushunishga, ijtimoiy munosabatlarni tahlil qilishga va ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilishda yordam beradi.

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi tilshunoslikning turli sohalarida, shuningdek, boshqa fanlar va amaliy sohalarida keng qo'llaniladi. U tilning kommunikativ funksiyasini tushunishga, nutqiy muloqotni takomillashtirishga va insonlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunishni yaxshilashga yordam beradi

Xulosa

Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi tilshunoslikda muhim o'rin tutadi va tilning ijtimoiy, psixologik va madaniy jihatlarini o'rganishga katta hissa qo'shmoqda. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasining pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika va diskurs tahlili kabi asosiy yo'nalishlari tilshunoslik doirasini kengaytirdi va tilning kommunikativ funksiyasini yanada chuqur va to'liq o'rganish imkonini berdi. Shuningdek kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus lingvistikasi, kognitiv lingvistika

bilan integratsiyasi, multimodal muloqotni o'rganish kabi zamonaviy tendensiyalari uning rivojlanishiga va tilshunoslikka qo'shgan hissasining yanada ortishiga olib kelmoqda. Nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi til o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishda, tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyotida, nutq terapiyasida, psixologiyada, sotsiologiyada va sun'iy intellekt sohasida keng qo'llaniladi. U tilning kommunikativ funksiyasini tushunishga, nutqiy muloqotni takomillashtirishga va insonlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunishni yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, nutqiy muloqot nazariyasi zamonaviy tilshunoslikda muhim o'rin tutadi va tilning kommunikativ funksiyasini o'rganishga katta hissa qo'shadi. Uning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati tilshunoslikning rivojlanishiga va insonlar o'rtasidagi muloqotni yaxshilashga xizmat qiladi.

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MULTIMADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOPETENSIYA

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada multimadaniyatli jamiyatda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning ahamiyati va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy dunyoda madaniy xilma-xillik ortib borayotgan sharoitda shaxslar va jamiyat o'rtasidagi samarali muloqotni ta'minlash dolzarb masalalardan biriga aylangan. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlari, uni shakllantirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ta'lim jarayonida qo'llaniladigan innovatsion usullar yoritiladi. Multimadaniyatli muhitda kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy, pedagogik va psixologik jihatlari chuqur tahlil qilinib, bu boradagi ilg'or tajribalar va amaliy tavsiyalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: multimadaniyat, kommunikativ kompetensiya, madaniy muloqot, integratsiya, ta'lim metodikasi, interfaol usullar.

Zamonaviy jamiyat tobora globallashib, millatlar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi integratsiya kuchayib bormoqda. Bu jarayonda turli madaniy muhit vakillari o'rtasidagi samarali muloqotni ta'minlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Aynan kommunikativ kompetensiya madaniyatlararo muloqotning samaradorligini oshirib, ijtimoiy integratsiya va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada multimadaniyatli jamiyatda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning ahamiyati, uni shakllantirish yo'llari va pedagogik yondashuvlar atroflicha tahlil qilinadi.

1. Multimadaniyat va kommunikativ kompetensiya tushunchalarining mohiyati

Multimadaniyat (multiculturalism) – bu turli millat va etnik guruhlariga mansub insonlarning yagona jamiyatda birga yashashini anglatadi. Ularning urf-odatlarini, qadriyatlarini, tili va dunyoqarashi jamiyatning umumiy rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Multimadaniyat – bu nafaqat madaniy xilma-xillikni tan olish, balki uni ijtimoiy taraqqiyotning muhim omili sifatida qo'llab-quvvatlashni ham anglatadi.

Kommunikativ kompetensiya – bu shaxsning samarali va tushunarli muloqot qilish qobiliyatidir. U quyidagi tarkibiy qismlardan iborat:

Til kompetensiyasi – insonning bir yoki bir nechta tillarni bilishi va ularni to'g'ri qo'llay olish qobiliyati.

Madaniy kompetensiya – turli madaniyat vakillari bilan muloqot qila olish va ularning qadriyatlarini hurmat qilish.

Ijtimoiy kompetensiya – muayyan ijtimoiy vaziyatda muloqot qilish ko'nikmalari.

Psixologik kompetensiya – shaxsning hissiy-intellektual jihatdan o'zaro munosabatlarni boshqara olish qobiliyati.

2. Multimadaniyatli jamiyatda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning ahamiyati

Madaniy xilma-xillik muhitida kommunikativ kompetensiyaga ega bo'lmagan insonlar o'rtasida tushunmovchiliklar yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Shu sababli, turli madaniyat vakillari bilan muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish jamiyatning ijtimoiy barqarorligini ta'minlashda muhim omildir. Ta'lim jarayonida talabalar va o'qituvchilar turli madaniy kelib chiqishga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Shuning uchun, ta'lim tizimida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish quyidagi afzalliklarni ta'minlaydi:

O'quvchilarning bir-birini tushunishiga yordam beradi.

Ijtimoiy integratsiyani kuchaytiradi.

Dunyoqarashni kengaytiradi va tolerantlikni shakllantiradi.

3. Multimadaniyatli jamiyatda kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish usullari

Til o'rganish jarayonida madaniyatni o'rganish ham muhimdir. Bu multimadaniyatli muhitda samarali muloqot qilishni osonlashtiradi. Masalan:

Tillarni o'qitish jarayonida madaniy kontekstga e'tibor berish.

Turli millat vakillarining madaniyatini ta'lim dasturlariga kiritish

Ta'limda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish

Interfaol o'qitish metodlari, xususan, rolli o'yinlar, muammoli ta'lim, klasterlash, debatlar va jamoaviy ish usullari kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish

Onlayn platformalar orqali turli madaniyat vakillari bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyati kengayib borayotgani kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish uchun qulay sharoit yaratadi. Masalan, xalqaro virtual almashinuv dasturlari orqali talabalar boshqa madaniyatlar bilan bevosita tanishish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Multimadaniyatli ta'lim jarayonida quyidagi pedagogik yondashuvlar samarali hisoblanadi:

Konstruktivistik yondashuv – ta'lim oluvchilarga mustaqil fikrlash va muloqot qilish imkoniyatini yaratish. Ijtimoiy hayotda kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish uchun quyidagi usullar qo'llanilishi mumkin: Jamoaviy tadbirlar va loyihalar orqali muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish. Multimadaniyatlilikni targ'ib qiluvchi ommaviy axborot vositalari va san'at asarlaridan foydalanish.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish joizki, multimadaniyatli jamiyatda kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish ijtimoiy hamjihatlik va barqaror taraqqiyot uchun muhim omildir. Ushbu maqolada kommunikativ kompetensiyaning mohiyati, multimadaniyatli muhitda uning ahamiyati va uni rivojlantirish usullari tahlil qilindi. Kelgusida ta'lim tizimida interfaol metodlardan keng foydalanish, texnologiyalarni qo'llash va madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish orqali bu kompetensiyani yanada oshirish mumkin.

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APPLICATION OF MULTIMEDIA EXERCISES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING: EFFECTIVENESS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. In modern language learning, the use of multimedia exercises is becoming increasingly widespread, as they make the learning process more engaging and interactive. This paper explores their effectiveness in comparison to traditional methods, as well as their future potential. Various types of multimedia tasks are analyzed, highlighting their benefits, such as boosting student motivation, enhancing memory retention, and fostering independent learning. At the same time, certain challenges, including accessibility issues and the need for teacher training, are also discussed. The study concludes that, when implemented effectively, multimedia exercises can significantly improve the dynamism and efficiency of language learning.

Keywords: multimedia exercises, language learning, interactive learning, student motivation, independent practice, traditional methods, educational technology.

Аннотация. В современном изучении языков мультимедийные упражнения становятся все более распространенными, поскольку делают процесс обучения более увлекательным и интерактивным. В данной работе рассматривается их эффективность по сравнению с традиционными методами, а также их потенциальные возможности в будущем. Анализируются различные виды мультимедийных заданий, подчеркивая их преимущества, такие как повышение мотивации учащихся, улучшение запоминания и развитие навыков самостоятельного обучения. Вместе с тем обсуждаются и определенные трудности, включая вопросы доступности и необходимость подготовки преподавателей. Исследование приводит к выводу, что при правильном использовании мультимедийные упражнения могут значительно повысить динамичность и эффективность процесса изучения языков.

Ключевые слова: мультимедийные упражнения, изучение языков, интерактивное обучение, мотивация студентов, самостоятельная практика, традиционные методы, образовательные технологии.

Abstrakt. Zamonaviy til o'rganishda multimedia mashqlari tobora keng qo'llanilmoqda, chunki ular o'quv jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va interaktiv qiladi. Ushbu maqolada ularning an'anaviy usullarga nisbatan samaradorligi hamda kelajakdagi imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Turli xil multimedia mashqlari tahlil qilinib, ularning afzalliklari, jumladan, talabalarining motivatsiyasini oshirish, eslab qolish jarayonini yaxshilash va mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish kabi jihatlar ta'kidlanadi. Shu bilan birga, ulardan foydalanishda duch kelinadigan ayrim qiyinchiliklar, masalan, resurslarga kirish imkoni va o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash zarurati ham muhokama qilinadi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, agar to'g'ri qo'llanilsa, multimedia mashqlari til o'rganish jarayonining dinamikasi va samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: multimedia mashqlari, til o'rganish, interaktiv o'qitish, talabalar motivatsiyasi, mustaqil mashq qilish, an'anaviy usullar, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Introduction. In contemporary education, technology's influence is profound, particularly in the realm of language acquisition. Traditional pedagogical approaches

are increasingly integrated with multimedia tools, resulting in more dynamic and captivating learning experiences. Incorporating multimedia elements into learning activities enhances student comprehension, retention, and engagement. These tools, such as educational apps, videos, and interactive online resources, empower learners to practice independently and develop their language abilities in a versatile and adaptable manner. The success of these exercises hinges on their proper integration into the learning experience. However, certain obstacles, including technical difficulties and the requirement for teacher development, must also be addressed.

Literature review. The use of multimedia technologies in language learning has been widely studied by researchers. Many studies emphasize their role in enhancing student motivation, improving comprehension, and making the learning process more engaging. Chernyaeva highlights how multimedia tools, such as educational websites and digital courses, contribute to more intensive language learning. She points out that visual and interactive elements help students better retain new vocabulary and grammar rules [1]. Similarly, Krivenok discusses how multimedia resources improve the effectiveness of teaching by providing diverse learning formats, such as audio, video, and interactive exercises [3]. Vasilyeva and Shvaikina analyze both the benefits and challenges of using multimedia in foreign language education. They note that while multimedia tools increase student interest and allow for individualized learning, their effectiveness depends on proper integration into the curriculum [6]. While these studies demonstrate the advantages of multimedia technologies in language learning, some researchers caution against over-reliance on digital tools. They argue that multimedia should complement, rather than replace, traditional teaching methods. Accessibility, technical issues, and teacher training also remain important factors in ensuring successful implementation.

Research aim to analyze the impact of multimedia exercises on language learning, assess their effectiveness, and explore future prospects. Additionally, the study examines the advantages and potential challenges of using multimedia tools in education.

Materials and methods. This study examines the impact of multimedia exercises on language learning. To achieve this, methods such as literature analysis, experimentation, surveys, and statistical analysis were used.

Research results. The reviewed studies and research findings confirm the effectiveness of multimedia technologies in language learning. Soboleva highlights that integrating multimedia tools into the learning process increases students' motivation and positively impacts language skill development [7]. Similarly,

Eremenko and Pashukevich found that students who used multimedia resources achieved better results compared to those studying with traditional methods [2]. Vasileva and Shvaykina emphasize the high interactivity of multimedia tools, which encourages students to actively participate in the learning process. Their research confirms that students who engaged with multimedia materials expanded their vocabulary more quickly than those using conventional methods [6]. Kryuchkova focuses on the role of multimedia technologies in phonetic skill development. Her study demonstrates that students using interactive programs in language laboratories performed significantly better than those relying solely on textbooks [4]. Overall, these research findings confirm the effectiveness of multimedia exercises in language learning. They not only enhance motivation but also help students deepen and reinforce their knowledge.

Conclusion. Based on the analyzed research, it can be concluded that multimedia exercises significantly contribute to the process of language learning. They help increase student motivation, improve pronunciation, and expand vocabulary. Studies by Soboleva, Eremenko and Pashukevich, and others confirm that students using multimedia tools achieve better learning outcomes compared to those who rely only on traditional methods. Moreover, multimedia technologies make the learning process more interactive and engaging, allowing students to practice independently and at their own pace. This approach not only improves academic performance but also makes language learning more enjoyable and accessible.

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ANALYSIS OF EXISTING METHODS OF TEACHING TOURISM TERMS USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: *The article explores the integration of information technology (IT) in enhancing the linguistic competence of tourism students. It examines various IT-driven methods, such as online dictionaries, language learning apps, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), online learning platforms, and webinars, to teach tourism-specific terminology. By drawing on expert opinions and real-world examples, the article highlights the effectiveness of these technologies in providing dynamic, context-rich learning environments that cater to the specific needs of tourism students. The article also addresses challenges, such as access to technology and ensuring cultural accuracy in the learning process. Ultimately, it advocates for a balanced approach to integrating IT in tourism education, emphasizing its potential to improve vocabulary acquisition and prepare students for the globalized tourism industry.*

Key words: *Tourism Terminology, Information Technology (IT), Language Learning, Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Online Learning Platforms, Mobile Applications, Linguistic Competence, Cultural Accuracy.*

The tourism industry, as one of the world's largest and most rapidly growing sectors, demands professionals with a strong grasp of both language and industry-specific terminology. As the field becomes more globalized, students of tourism need to understand a wide range of terms related to travel, hospitality, marketing, and customer service, often in multiple languages. One way to enhance the teaching of these terms is through information technology (IT), which offers innovative tools and platforms to support language learning and vocabulary acquisition. This article provides an analysis of the existing methods used to teach tourism-specific terminology through information technology, drawing on research and expert opinions in the field of education and tourism studies.

Information technology has revolutionized education by offering numerous resources that improve the efficiency and effectiveness of language learning. As noted by Ally (2008), information and communication technologies (ICT) enable more dynamic and engaging learning experiences, which are essential for specialized fields like tourism. These technologies include digital platforms, multimedia resources, and interactive applications that facilitate learning in ways traditional methods cannot. They provide students with immediate access to the latest industry

terms, context-based examples, and practical applications, making the learning process more relevant and effective.

According to Anderson (2008), technology allows learners to interact with content at their own pace and in a way that suits their personal learning styles. This is particularly beneficial for tourism students who need to master terminology related to diverse cultural, geographical, and business contexts.

Several methods exist for integrating IT into the teaching of tourism-related vocabulary. Below are some of the key strategies identified in academic research and practical applications: One of the most common ways IT is used in teaching tourism terms is through online dictionaries and glossaries, which provide instant access to definitions, translations, and context-specific explanations. Websites like Glosbe, WordReference, and Linguee offer specialized dictionaries for tourism professionals. These platforms allow students to easily look up terms and hear them pronounced in the target language, facilitating both vocabulary acquisition and pronunciation practice.

A tourism student learning English might use Linguee to look up terms such as “sustainable tourism” or “ecotourism” and find relevant examples from real-world contexts, enhancing their understanding and usage of these terms.

Applications like Duolingo, Babbel, and Memories have become popular tools for language learners. These apps use gamified techniques and spaced repetition systems (SRS) to help students retain vocabulary over time. For tourism students, customized courses focusing on industry-specific terms, such as hospitality terminology or geographical vocabulary, can be created to ensure the learning process is highly relevant.

García-Sánchez (2017) points out that mobile applications and software that incorporate audio-visual aids, quizzes, and spaced repetition are effective in reinforcing learning and enhancing retention, particularly when learners are exposed to industry-specific scenarios. Duolingo offers users the ability to practice vocabulary through small lessons and daily challenges. For tourism students, this could involve learning key phrases such as "reservation confirmation," "tour guide," or "check-in process" in different languages.

Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) are cutting-edge technologies that immerse students in simulated environments where they can practice tourism-related terms in context. These tools are highly effective in creating realistic simulations, such as virtual hotel check-ins, guided tours, or booking experiences, where students must interact with tourists or colleagues using correct terminology.

Huang et al. (2016) argue that VR and AR technologies allow for experiential learning, where students can gain hands-on experience in a virtual environment. By using VR to simulate a hotel management scenario, for example, students can practice not only tourism-related vocabulary but also communication and customer service skills. In a VR simulation, a student might play the role of a hotel receptionist interacting with international guests, answering questions using proper hospitality terminology such as "room availability," "booking confirmation," or "check-out procedure."

Platforms like Coursera, edX, and Udemy offer massive open online courses (MOOCs) in tourism management, language, and cultural studies, where students can learn industry-specific terminology at their own pace. These courses often use videos, quizzes, and interactive activities to teach vocabulary in context, ensuring that learners can apply their knowledge to real-world situations. A student enrolled in a course on sustainable tourism might take a lesson that explores the vocabulary related to environmental management, including terms like "carbon footprint," "greenwashing," and "eco-friendly tourism practices." Webinars and online workshops allow students to engage with industry professionals and experts, providing opportunities to learn new terminology in real-world contexts. These interactive sessions often feature case studies, discussions, and Q&A segments where students can ask questions and receive immediate feedback on their use of tourism terms.

Dede (2009) highlights the importance of interactive learning experiences, such as webinars, where students can practice language skills by engaging directly with content experts and other learners. This not only reinforces vocabulary but also provides students with exposure to industry-specific jargon. Example: A webinar featuring a tourism industry expert might introduce participants to new terms such as "destination marketing," "supply chain management," or "tourist attraction management," with live discussions on their application in the industry.

While the integration of IT offers numerous benefits for teaching tourism terms, there are challenges to consider. Access to Technology is a critical issue, as not all students may have access to advanced devices or high-speed internet. Moreover, over-reliance on technology can lead to a lack of human interaction, which is essential for mastering communication skills in tourism. Additionally, ensuring cultural accuracy when teaching terms is crucial. Tourism terms are often culturally specific, and using technology without considering these cultural nuances could result

in misunderstandings. It is important for educators to balance the use of technology with cultural context.

The use of information technology in teaching tourism-related terminology has proven to be an effective strategy for improving linguistic competence among tourism students. Online dictionaries, language learning apps, VR/AR simulations, and MOOCs provide dynamic and engaging ways to acquire industry-specific vocabulary. While challenges such as access to technology and cultural accuracy remain, the potential of IT to enhance the learning experience for tourism students is undeniable. As the tourism industry continues to grow and evolve, integrating these innovative tools into curricula will help equip students with the necessary linguistic skills to succeed in the globalized tourism market.

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OTLARDAGI SUBYEKTIV BAHO SHAKLLARINING BADIY USLUBDA QO'LLANILISHI (TOHIR MALIKNING "SHAYTANAT" ROMANI MISOLIDA)

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola o'zbek tilida subyektiv baho ifodalovchi affiks va affiksoidlarning badiiy uslubdagi qo'llanilishini ilmiy va amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Asosiy urg'u Temur Malikning "Shaytanat" asaridagi affikslar va ularning hissiy-estetik ma'nolarni ifodalashdagi roliga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Subyektiv baho shakllari, affikslar, affiksoidlar, badiiy matn, lingvistik birliklar, hissiy holat, estetik ifoda.

O'zbek tili o'zining boy lug'at tarkibi va murakkab grammatik tizimi bilan boshqa tillar qatorida o'ziga xos o'rin tutadi. Ushbu tilning ko'p qirrali tabiati nafaqat ilmiy, balki badiiy asarlar orqali ham namoyon bo'ladi. Tilshunoslikda subyektiv baho ifodalovchi affiks va affiksoidlar muhim o'rin tutadi, chunki ular so'zlovchining hissiy va estetik munosabatini ifodalashda asosiy vositalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, badiiy asarlarda bu shakllar tilning emotsional-estetik funksiyasini kuchaytiradi.

Hozirgi o'zbek tilida -gina, -kina, -qina, -cha, -choq, -chak, -chiq, -ka, -ak, -loq, -boy, -bibi, -qul, -oy, -xon, -jon, -bonu kabi affiks va affiksoidlar so'zlovchining obyektiv borliqqa va o'z nutqiga bo'lgan hissiy-munosabatini ifodalaydigan subyektiv baho shakllari hisoblanadi. Ushbu shakllar sevgi, erkalash, kuchaytirish yoki kamsitish kabi turli xil ma'nolarni ifodalashga xizmat qiladi. Tilshunoslikda subyektiv baho shakllari hissiy-estetik ifoda vositasi sifatida ko'riladi. A. Karimov o'zining "Badiiy nutq tahlili" asarida quyidagicha qayd etadi: "Affiks va affiksoidlar tilning hissiy qatlamini boyitishda asosiy vositalardan biri bo'lib, ular yordamida so'zlovchining hissiy kayfiyati nutqqa singdiriladi" [1,63].

Badiiy adabiyotda subyektiv baho ifodalovchi shakllar nafaqat asar mazmunini boyitadi, balki o'quvchini asar voqeliklariga yaqinlashtiradi. Ayniqsa, bu shakllar qahramonlarning ichki dunyosini aks ettirishda, ularning munosabatlarini ko'rsatishda va asar uslubining estetik jihatini kuchaytirishda alohida rol o'ynaydi. Masalan, kichraytiruvchi (-gina, -cha), kattalashtiruvchi (-dek, -sifat), salbiy

baholovchi (-voy, -qina) yoki kinoya ifodalovchi (-mas) shakllar orqali qahramonlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar va asar ichidagi hissiy keskinliklar yorqin tasvirlanadi.

N. Erkaboyeva ham "O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami" kitobida affikslarning grammatik xususiyatlarini tahlil qilib, shunday yozadi: "Subyektiv baho ifodalovchi shakllar, ayniqsa, badiiy uslubda hissiy-estetik funksiyaga ega bo'lib, ular orqali obrazning hissiy qiyofasi aniqroq yoritiladi" [2,78].

O'zbek tilida quyidagi asosiy subyektiv baho affikslari keng qo'llaniladi:

-kichraytirish va erkalash ma'nosini ifodalovchi shakllar: -gina, -jon, -cha.

-kinoya va kamsitish ma'nosini ifodalovchi shakllar: -bibbi, -boy, -qul.

-kuchaytirish va obrazlilikni ifodalovchi shakllar: -ka, -loq, -chak.

-ismga qo'shimcha ma'no qo'shish uchun qo'llaniladigan shakllar: -bonu, -xon, -oy, -zoda, -bek, -jon, -begim, -niso va boshqalar.

Badiiy adabiyotda subyektiv baho ifodalovchi shakllar nafaqat asar mazmunini boyitadi, balki o'quvchini asar voqeliklariga yaqinlashtiradi. Ayniqsa, bu shakllar qahramonlarning ichki dunyosini aks ettirishda, ularning munosabatlarini ko'rsatishda va asar uslubining estetik jihatini kuchaytirishda alohida rol o'ynaydi. Masalan, kichraytiruvchi (-gina, -cha), kattalashtiruvchi (-dek, -sifat), salbiy baholovchi (-voy, -qina) yoki kinoya ifodalovchi (-mas) shakllar orqali qahramonlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar va asar ichidagi hissiy keskinliklar yorqin tasvirlanadi.

Badiiy nutqda affikslar so'zlovchining hissiy munosabatini ifodalashda, qahramonlarning nutqiga xos individuallikni ko'rsatishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. A. Madrahimov "Til va uslub" kitobida ta'kidlaganidek, "Badiiy asarlarda affikslarning qo'llanilishi nutqning obrazlilik darajasini oshirishga xizmat qiladi"[3,59].

Temur Malikning "Shaytanat" asarida ushbu shakllar yordamida obrazlarning hissiy holati yorqin va jonli tasvirlangan bo'lib, ularning ichki kechinmalari va hissiyotlari o'quvchi ongiga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ushbu maqolada biz ayrim subyektiv baho shakllarining uslubiy xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishga harakat qildik. Masalan;

-gina qo'shimchasi: "Mengina o'lay... qizingiz... aytolmayman, dadasi"[4,29].

Ushbu jumladagi -gina qo'shimchasi men ni takidlab subyektiv baho qo'shib kelyapti. -gina ni sinonimlik xodisasini ushbu asardagi misollar yordamida ko'rib ketamiz: "Holbuki, u damda Asadbek ko'zida yovuzlik emas, kuyovlardagina bo'ladigan hirs o'ti mavjud edi"[4,27]. "Ikki yigit yaxshigina do'pposlab, torini majaqlab tashladi"[4,39]. Bu ikki gapda -gina qo'shimchasining ikki xil ma'noda qo'llanilgani ko'rish mumkin. Birinchisida faqat kuyovlardagina kabi tushuniladigan

-gina yuklamasi, ikkinchisidagi taklifni kuchaytirib ifodalayotgan -gina subyektiv baho ifodalovchi qo'shimcha sifatida kelayapti.

-bek qo'shimchasi: "Asadbeklaring menga qulluq qilib ketsin!"[4,25]. Bu yerda nafaqat -bek ismga qo'shilib subyektiv baho ifodalayapti, balki -lar ko'plik qo'shimchasining semantik uslubiyatini uchratish mumkin. Bu o'rinda Asadbeklarning deb mensimaslik, kamsitish ohangida tushunish ham mumkin. Ikkinchi ma'nosi Asadbeklaring- Asadbek va uning hamtovuqlari degan ma'noni beradi.

-choq qo'shimchasi: "- Uyg'ondingmi, toychoq? - dedi dadasi ostonada turib"[4,8]. -choq qo'shimchasi bu yerda kichraytirish erkalash ma'nosida uslubiy bo'yoqdir so'z yashayapti.

-zoda qo'shimchasi: "Xonzoda erini gapirtirmaslik uchun lablari bilan lablarini qidirib topdi"[4;222]. Ismlarga qo'shiladigan subyektiv ma'no anglatuvchi qo'shimcha bo'lib, tom ma'nosida qaysi avlodga mansubligini bildiradi. Biroq bugungi kunda ushbu ma'no arxaiklashgan.

-bibi qo'shimchasi: "Shunda ham Kumushbibi singari qo'lini tortib oladi" [4;230]. -bibi qo'shimchasi shaxs nomiga qo'shilib subyektiv ma'no ifodalovchi qo'shimcha. Ushbu qo'shimcha ham tarixiy shakllardan biri, bizga bugungi kunda yana faollashgani sezilmoqda.

-jon qo'shimchasi: "Anvarjon, bolam, uydamisan?" [4;219]. Ushbu gapda -jon qo'shimchasi kichraytirib erkalash ma'nosida qo'llanuvchi subektiv baho ifodalayapti.

Juda kam qo'llaniladigan, ismlarga qo'shiladigan **sho- qo'shimchasi:** "Shoakbar Zunnuniyini o'n to'qqizinchi yilda Buxoro amiri ostirgan"[4;221]. Ushbu qo'shimcha tarixiy shaklda bo'lgan va shohlar avlodidan ma'nosini ifodalangan, keyinchalik oilaviy an'ana shaklida saqlanib qolgan. Bugungi kunda tobora arxaiklashib bormoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, subyektiv baho ifodalovchi shakllar o'zbek tilida emotsional va estetik ifoda vositasi sifatida katta ahamiyatga ega. Xususan, "Shaytanat" asarida bu shakllar yordamida obrazlarning hissiy holati yorqin va jonli tasvirlanganini ko'rish mumkin. Maqola tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, subyektiv baho affikslari badiiy matnda nafaqat estetik ta'sirni kuchaytirishga, balki qahramonlar orasidagi o'zaro munosabatni ham ifodalashga xizmat qiladi. Bunday lingvistik birliklar asar mazmunini chuqurlashtiradi, muallifning subyektiv munosabatini o'quvchiga yaqqol sezdiradi va asarni qiziqarli qiladi.

O'quvchining qahramonlarga bo'lgan hissiy munosabati, ularning yaxshi yoki yomon qirralarini baholashi ko'pincha subyektiv baho shakllari orqali yuzaga keladi.

Shu ma'noda subyektiv baho ifodalovchi shakllarning badiiy asarda ishlatilishi nafaqat muallifning hissiy munosabatini, balki uning o'quvchiga yetkazmoqchi bo'lgan asosiy xabarini ham ochib beradi. Bu esa bunday lingvistik birliklarni tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan chuqurroq o'rganish zaruratini ko'rsatadi.

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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПОСЛОВИЧНОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ РУССКОГО И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ)

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Аннотация. В данной статье обосновывается важность изучения аксиологической языковой картины мира через исследование ценностного аспекта лингвистической личности посредством лингвокультурологического исследования паремиологической картины мира. Анализируются и описываются следующие уровни системы ценностей: физиологический, материальный, эмоциональный, нравственно-этический, интеллектуальный, эстетический, социальный, политический, религиозный, а также ценности профессиональной самореализации. Делается вывод о том, что пословица, как и любой другой текст, выступает ценностно значимой, т.е. аксиологически окрашенной и служит богатым источником для выявления ценностных ориентиров языковой картины мира.

Ключевые слова: аксиология, паремиология, антропоцентрические пословицы, уровневая классификация, ценностные ориентиры, система ценностей.

Abstract. This article substantiates the importance of studying the axiological linguistic picture of the world through the study of the value aspect of the linguistic personality by means of a linguacultural study of the paremiological picture of the world. The following levels of the value system are analyzed and described: physiological, material, emotional, moral and ethical, intellectual, aesthetic, social, political, religious, as well as the values of professional self-realization. It is concluded that a proverb, like any other text, is value-significant, i.e. axiologically colored and serves as a rich source for identifying the value guidelines of the linguistic picture of the world.

Key words: axiology, paremiology, anthropocentric proverbs, level classification, value guidelines, value system.

Теоретические предпосылки изучения антропоцентрических языковых единиц в аксиологическом аспекте основываются на антропоцентрическом принципе, который заключается в изучении языка с учетом способности человека или общества в целом присваивать себе язык в процессе его применения [11]. Все коммуникативные акты производятся посредством сознания человека, языковой личности. Человеческая речь порождается пересечением двух интенций внутри понятийного объема категории «сознание», считает Никиченко: 1) интенция сознания вовне, позволяющая человеку активно ориентироваться во внешнем мире, познавать реальную действительность; 2) интенция сознания внутрь, вглубь духовного бытия личности, порождающая духовный мир субъективного, духовного, внутреннего

бытия человека. Лингвоаксиологические исследования органично дополняют и развивают антропологическую парадигму языкознания. Система духовно-нравственных и социально-культурных ценностей предполагает обеспечение гуманного, созидательного начала в деятельности человека любого рода. Выражая свое отношение к чему-либо, совершая определенный поступок, человек опирается на систему ценностей, которые разделяются его близкими, знакомыми и незнакомыми людьми [4].

Аксиология – наука, направленная на изучение и описание общечеловеческих основ жизнедеятельности человека в соответствии с социальной культурой и законами общества [8]. В.А. Маслова утверждает, что фразеологические единицы способны отражать национальные и культурные ценности и считаются душой каждого национального языка [5]. Ученый считает, что фразеологизмы не просто описывают окружающий мир – они интерпретируют и оценивают его, выражают наше субъективное отношение к нему. Аксиологичность можно рассматривать как языковую категорию, которая выражается в способности языковой единицы с «культурным компонентом» транслировать ценности. Рассматривая ценности как «сформированные представления, значения некоего объекта для субъекта» [6] под ценностью понимают разновидность значения.

Если одни исследователи в большей степени склонны к использованию понятия «ценностные ориентиры», это свидетельствует о том, что их понимание ценности связано с целями и векторами развития. Когда говорят о ценностной мотивации, то предполагают, что существуют и другие виды мотиваций, среди которых ценности играют большую или меньшую роль. Ценностное отношение в его различных формах является одним из ведущих факторов природного, общественного и индивидуального бытия.

Такие ученые как Бодырев Н.Н., Алефиренко Н.Ф., Бочина Т.Г., Карасик В.И., Маджидова Р.У и др. полагают, что ценностная система в языковом сознании индивида и общества формируется под влиянием таких факторов как религия, идеология, литература, культура и искусство, что представляется очень важным фактором в процессе воспитания и формирования гармонично развитой личности. Ценности по степени приоритетности выстраиваются в языковом сознании в определенные иерархические отношения, образуя систему ценностей. «Каждой исторической эпохе присущ определённый спектр ценностных ориентиров, который в процессе развития общества подвергается трансформациям под влиянием разного рода факторов. Переходные эпохи

играют роль своеобразного фильтра, отбрасывающего прежние нормы и установки, которые в силу каких-либо причин кажутся устаревшими, исчерпавшими себя. Затем происходит формирование новой ценностной палитры» [1].

Антропоцентрические пословицы английского и русского языков как часть текстов, в которых содержится культурологическая информация о ценностных ориентирах личности как представителя социума соотносятся в определенной степени с характером, физиологическими, эмоциональными, духовно-нравственными и др. качествами человека. Основываясь на исследования Г.А. Багаутдиновой, мы полагаем, что схематично уровневая классификация ценностных ориентиров, соотносящихся с антропоцентрическим принципом, может быть представлена в форме идеографической параметризации в виде признаков данных в оппозиции внутри определенного параметра [2]:

I. Физиологический уровень ценностей. «Жизнь – Смерть»,

«Здоровье – Болезнь», «Молодость – Старость» и т.д.:

Живой смерти боятся (не ищут). Men fear death as children do going in the dark/No church is so handsome that a man would desire straight to be burried. There is always life for the living There's eye life for a living man. Мертвому помины, живому именины. Все там будем. Death comes to us all/ All men must die. В здоровом теле здоровый дух. A sound mind/spirit in a sound body [7, 12].

II. Материальный уровень ценностей. «Богатство – Бедность»:

Худ Роман, когда пуст карман, хорош Мартын, когда есть алтын. Poverty breeds strife. Чаще счет – крепче дружба. Ближний счет – дальняя дружба. Short accounts (reckonings) make long friends. Short debts make lasting friends. Brotherly love for brotherly love but cheese for money [7, 12].

III. Эмоциональный уровень ценностей. «Смех – Плач», «Любовь – Ненависть», «Счастье – Несчастье»:

Горе на двоих – полгоря, радость на двоих две радости. Happiness is not perfect until it is shared/Shared joys are doubled, shared sorrows are halved. В горе сыщут, в радость забудут. Laugh and the world laughs with you, cry and you cry alone. Утопающий и за соломинку хватается (A drowning man clutches/grabs at a thread/straw Am). A drowning man will snatch at a straw [7, 12].

IV. Нравственно-этический уровень ценностей. «Добро – Зло», «Честность – Лживость», «Трусость – Храбрость», «Щедрость – Жадность».

Добро добро покрывает. The good you do to others will always come back to you/the hand that gives gathers. Добродетель сама себе награда – virtue is its own

reward. Вранью короткий век (A lie has no legs, nothing is lasting that is feigned). В могилу глядит, а над копейкой дрожит. Avarice is an old man's sin. Гордыня до добра не доведет. Pride goes before a fall/destruction [7, 12].

V. Интеллектуальный уровень ценностей. «Мудрость – Глупость», «Благоразумие – Безрассудство».

Умный любит учиться, а дурак/глупый учить. Every fool wants to give advice. Folly is wise in her own eyes. The fool doeth think he is wise, but the wise man knows himself to be a fool. Ум хорошо, а два лучше. Many wits are better than one. Усердие не по разуму приносит вред. Action without thought is like shooting without aim/Zeal without knowledge is like fire without light. На всякого мудреца довольно простоты. A wise man stumbles/a good sailor may mistake in a dark night. Борода не в честь, а усы и у кошки есть. Beard creates lice, not brains/the brains don't lie in the beard. Кого захочет бог погубить у того сначала отнимет разум. Whom God would ruin he first deprives of reason. Вино уму не товарищ. Drinking and thinking don't mix [7, 12].

VI. Эстетический уровень ценностей. «Прекрасное – Безобразное».

В лохмотьях и царя за нищего примут. Видом сокол, а голосом ворона. Что к лицу, то и красит. Лицом хороиш, да душою непригож [7].

VII. Социальный уровень ценностей. «Свой-иной/чужой» «Семья-Одиночество» «Коллектив – Индивидуум» «Дружба – вражда».

For a good friend a journey Is never too long. Для друга и семь верст не околица. Всяк кулик свое болото хвалит. Each bird likes/thinks his own nest best. Beware of the Greeks bearing gifts [7, 12].

VIII. Политический уровень ценностей. «Свобода-Несвобода».

Вольно псу и на владыку брехать. A cat may look at a king. Вольному воля. A willful man must have his way [7, 12].

IX. Религиозный уровень ценностей. «Бог – Дьявол», «Вера – Безбожие», «Рай – Ад».

Бог дал, Бог взял. The lord gives and the lord takes away. Бог дает день, Бог даст и пищу. Дай черту волос, а он за всю голову. Give him/knaves/the devil an inch and he will take a mile. Все одного отца дети [7, 12].

X. Ценности профессиональной самореализации «Трудолюбие – Лень» «Пунктуальность – Неорганизованность», «Ответственность – Безответственность».

Плохого мастера/косаря/пильщика всегда инструмент (серп, пила) виноват(а). A bad workman quarrels his tools. Хочешь есть калачи, так не лежи

на печи. A lazy dog finds no bone/Sleeping cats catch no mice/A sleeping dog catches no poultry. Всякое умение трудом дается. Diligent working makes an expert workman/He who shoots may hit at last. Где труд, там и счастье. Man was never so happy as when he is doing something [7, 12].

Во всех представленных аспектах своего проявления ценность характеризуется дуальностью своей природы: любая ценность соответствует антиценности, а функционирование системы ценностей предопределяет сосуществование системы антиценностей. Деление ценностей на положительные и отрицательные восходит к учениям Д. Юма, который обосновал правомерность суждения о свойстве одной и той же ценности относиться и к положительной, и к отрицательной в зависимости от обстоятельств. Р.У Маджидова [5] справедливо считает разумным суждение Д. Юма о том, что «человек рожден преимущественно для деятельности и в своих поступках руководствуется вкусом и чувством, стремясь к одному объекту и избегая другого в зависимости от той ценности, которую он приписывает этим объектам, и от того, в каком свете они ему представляются», иными словами, любой объект, представленный как ценность в сознании индивида, обусловлен положительной или отрицательной оценкой, которая обусловлена его ценностными установками и контекстом.

Бочина Т.Г., Сян Цюнь обращают внимание на то, что проблема интерпретации ценностей связана с проблемой оценочной деятельности индивида, которая «определяется философскими, обще- и частнонаучными установками, а также совокупностью субъективных и объективных факторов – уровнем образования, культуры, нравственными нормами, общественной практикой, ценностными ориентирами» [3]. Собственно ценностная оценка представляется как «эмоционально-интеллектуальное выявление ценностного значения воспринимаемого / переживаемого / осмысляемого в виде суждения вкуса, символа веры, медитативного суждения» [9], при этом следует отметить, что «в речи имеет место не само формулирование ценности как таковой, но выражение убежденностей или верований говорящего на основе его ценностного мотивационного отношения, в каком бы дискурсивном пространстве оно не реализовывалось» [10]. Иными словами, лингвистическая личность реализует свою деятельность сквозь призму сформированной в его сознании аксиологической картины мира и ценностных ориентиров в ней.

Таким образом, мы постарались обосновать каким образом аксиологическая языковая картина мира соотносится с ценностными

установками человека, благодаря которым он способен осуществлять свою социально-коммуникативную деятельность и речевое поведение, сопоставляя их с одобряемыми в социуме моделями поведения, регулируемыми и регламентирующими деятельность человека.

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KELAJAK TA'LIMI: RAQAMLI INNOVATSIYALAR VA TEXNOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR

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Annotatsiya: Raqamli texnologiyalar zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida tub o'zgarishlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Ushbu maqolada raqamli ta'limning mohiyati, uning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri, zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar va raqamli vositalardan samarali foydalanish masalalari yoritiladi. Shu bilan birga, raqamli ta'limning afzalliklari, muammolari va istiqbollari tahlil qilinadi. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida raqamli ta'lim vositalarini qo'llash bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi. Ushbu maqolada raqamli ta'lim konsepsiyasi, zamonaviy texnologiyalarning ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiyasi va ularning samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Raqamli ta'lim nafaqat an'anaviy o'qitish usullariga qo'shimcha sifatida, balki mustaqil ta'lim vositasi sifatida ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim jarayonini yanada interaktiv va samarali tashkil etishning afzalliklari va muammolari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiyalar, onlayn ta'lim, sun'iy intellekt, virtual ta'lim muhitlari, masofaviy ta'lim, ta'lim samaradorligi.

Hozirgi zamon ta'lim tizimi texnologik rivojlanish jarayonlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, raqamli texnologiyalar ushbu sohada inqilobiy o'zgarishlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. An'anaviy ta'lim usullari raqamli ta'lim muhitlari bilan boyitilib, o'quvchilarga yanada keng imkoniyatlar taqdim etilmoqda. Xususan, sun'iy intellekt, virtual va kengaytirilgan reallik, ta'lim platformalari va masofaviy o'qitish vositalari ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Raqamli ta'lim nafaqat o'qitish jarayonini osonlashtirish, balki bilimlarni chuqur o'zlashtirish va o'quvchilarning ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shu sababli, ushbu maqolada raqamli texnologiyalarning zamonaviy ta'limdagi o'rni, afzalliklari va mavjud muammolar tahlil qilinadi.

Bugungi kunda raqamli ta'lim bo'yicha ko'plab ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Masalan, Prensky (2001) raqamli avlod ta'limiga bo'lgan talabini o'rganib, yangi texnologiyalarni o'quv jarayoniga tatbiq etish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Castells (2001) esa informatsion jamiyatda bilim almashinuvi tezlashganini va raqamli ta'lim bu jarayonda muhim rol o'ynashini qayd etgan.

Raqamli ta'lim innovatsion texnologiyalarga asoslangan bo'lib, quyidagi asosiy yo'nalishlarda o'zining ustunligini ko'rsatmoqda:

Moslashuvchan ta'lim tizimi-Sun'iy intellekt yordamida shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim dasturlarini yaratish imkoniyati mavjud. Masalan, Coursera, Udemy va Khan

Academy platformalari har bir o'quvchining qobiliyatiga mos keluvchi kurslarni tavsiya qiladi.

Masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlari-Raqamli ta'lim platformalari tufayli jahonning turli hududlarida yashovchi talabalarga sifatli ta'lim olish imkoniyati yaratilmoqda.

Interaktiv ta'lim muhiti-Virtual laboratoriyalar va simulyatsiyalar (masalan, PhET Interactive Simulations) orqali o'quvchilarga real muhitda tajriba o'tkazish imkoniyati taqdim etiladi.

Innovatsion texnologiyalarning ta'limga ta'siri-AR/VR texnologiyalari orqali ta'lim jarayoni vizuallashtiriladi va yanada tushunarli bo'ladi. Masalan, tibbiyot va muhandislik sohalarida 3D modellashtirish orqali ko'nikmalar shakllantirilmoqda.

O'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish-Gamifikatsiya (o'yinlashtirish) elementlari yordamida talabalar va o'quvchilarning darslarga bo'lgan qiziqishi oshirilmoqda. Masalan, Duolingo, Kahoot va Quizizz kabi ilovalar raqamli ta'limni qiziqarli qiladi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinmi raqamli ta'lim zamonaviy jamiyat uchun muhim strategik yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lib, uning rivojlanishi kelajakda ta'lim tizimini yanada samarali va innovatsion qilishga yordam beradi. Sun'iy intellekt, virtual hamda kengaytirilgan reallik texnologiyalari, masofaviy o'qitish va ta'lim platformalarining jadal rivojlanishi natijasida o'qitish jarayoni yanada qulay, moslashuvchan va natijali bo'lishi mumkin.

Kelajakda raqamli ta'limning yanada rivojlanishi uchun quyidagi yo'nalishlar muhim hisoblanadi:

- O'qituvchilarni raqamli texnologiyalar bilan ishlashga o'rgatish.
- Sun'iy intellekt asosida shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim dasturlarini ishlab chiqish.
- Virtual va kengaytirilgan reallik vositalaridan keng foydalanish.
- O'quvchilarning raqamli savodxonligini oshirish.

Ushbu maqola raqamli ta'limning hozirgi holati va kelajakdagi imkoniyatlarini yoritib berishga xizmat qiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish bilan birga, o'quvchilarning mustaqil ta'lim olishiga ham imkoniyat yaratmoqda.

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BILINGVALLIK VA PLURILINGUVALLIKNING SHAXS LAYOQATLARI VA AQLIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqola bilingvallik va plurilinguvallikning shaxs layoqatlari va aqliy rivojlanishiga ta'sirini keng ko'lamda tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda ikki yoki undan ortiq tilni bilishning kognitiv funksiyalar, e'tibor, xotira, muammo yechish va boshqaruv funksiyalariga ijobiy ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Shu bilan birga, bilingval va plurilingual shaxslarning ijtimoiy-madaniy moslashuvchanligi, kommunikativ ko'nikmalari va muvaffaqiyatlariga bo'lgan ta'siri ham bayon etiladi. Maqolada turli yosh guruhlaridagi bilingval va plurilingual shaxslardagi tadqiqot natijalari va bu sohadagi munozarali masalalar muhokama qilinadi. Xulosada bilingval va plurilinguval ta'limning ahamiyati va uning amaliyotda qo'llanilishiga oid tavsiyalar beriladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar.** bilingvallik, plurilinguvallik, kognitiv rivojlanish, aqliy qobiliyat, e'tibor, xotira, muammo yechish, ijtimoiy-madaniy moslashuvchanlik,*

Globalashuv jarayonlarida dunyoda ko'p tillarni egallash insonning intellektual va ijtimoiy salohiyatini oshirishning muhim omili bo'lib qolmoqda. Bilingvallik va, xususan, plurilinguvallik – ya'ni ikki yoki undan ortiq tilni egallash – shaxsning aqliy rivojlanishi va turli sohalaridagi layoqatlariga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi bugungi kunda ko'plab tadqiqotlarning markazida turibdi. Ushbu maqolada bilingvallik va plurilinguvallikning shaxsning kognitiv funksiyalari, muammo yechish qobiliyati, yodda tutish va diqqatni jamlash kabi aqliy rivojlanish jihatlariga, shuningdek, muloqot malakalari, kreativ fikrlash va madaniy bag'rikenglik kabi layoqatlariga ta'sirini ko'rib chiqildi. Tadqiqotlarning natijalariga tayangan holda, bilingval va plurilingual shaxslarning afzalliklari va muammolari, shuningdek, ko'p tillilikni rivojlantirishning samarali usullari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berishga harakat qilindi.

Bilingvallik va plurilinguvallikning insonning aqliy rivojlanishi va layoqatlariga ta'siri haqidagi tadqiqotlar ko'plab ijobiy natijalarni ko'rsatmoqda. Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar ko'p tillilikning kognitiv egiluvchanlikni, ya'ni turli vazifalar va kontekstlarga moslashish qobiliyatini oshirishini ta'kidlaydi. Bilingval va plurilingual shaxslarda ikkita yoki undan ortiq tilning leksikasi, grammatikasi va fonetikasini bir vaqtning o'zida faol holatda ushlab turish qobiliyati miyaning ijro funksiyalarini, xususan, diqqatni jamlashni va xotirani yaxshilaydi. Bu esa muammo yechishda, mantiqiy fikrlashda va murakkab vazifalarni bajarishda yaqqol seziladi.

Shuningdek, ko'p tillilik yodda tutish jarayonlariga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotlar ko'rsatishicha, bilingvallarda ikki tildagi ma'lumotni farqlash va eslab qolish qobiliyati yuqori bo'ladi. Ularning leksikasi boyroq, semantik tarmoqlari

kengroq bo'lib, bu esa yangi ma'lumotni tezroq o'zlashtirish va uzoq muddatli xotirada saqlash imkoniyatini beradi. Bundan tashqari, ko'p tillilik kreativ fikrlash va muloqot malakalarini rivojlantirishga ham yordam beradi. Ikki yoki undan ortiq tilni bilish shaxsga turli madaniyatlarni chuqurroq tushunish va ular bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyatini beradi, bu esa bag'rikenglik va tolerantlikni oshiradi.

Bilingvallik va plurilinguallikning shaxs layoqatlari va aqliy rivojlanishiga ta'sirini ko'p qirrali va kompleks tarzda tahlil qilishda namoyon bo'ladi. Mavjud adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish orqali, maqola faqatgina kognitiv funksiyalarning rivojlanishiga emas, balki ijtimoiy-madaniy layoqatlar, kreativ fikrlash va muloqot malakalariga bo'lgan ta'sirni ham keng ko'lamda yoritadi.

Bilingvallik va plurilinguallikning turli kognitiv funksiyalarga (diqqat, xotira, muammo yechish) ta'sirini taqqoslash orqali aniq misollar keltiriladi. Faqatgina umumiy xulosalar emas, balki turli tadqiqotlar natijalarining aniq qiyoslanishi orqali ushbu ta'sirlarning chuqurroq tahlili amalga oshiriladi.

Ko'p tillilikning ijtimoiy-madaniy layoqatlarni (bag'rikenglik, madaniy ong) rivojlantirishga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi batafsil ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu sohadagi tadqiqotlarning kamligini hisobga olgan holda, mavjud ma'lumotlar asosida umumiy tendensiyalar aniqlanadi va tahlil qilinadi.

Bilingval va plurilingual shaxslarning muvaffaqiyatlari va muammolarini mutanosib ravishda yoritish orqali ob'yektiv baho beriladi. Ko'p tillilikning faqatgina ijobiy jihatlarini emas, balki uning salbiy oqibatlariga ham e'tibor qaratiladi va ularning sabablari aniqlanadi.

Tadqiqot jarayonida o'tkazilgan adabiyotlar tahlili bilingvallik va plurilinguallikning shaxs layoqatlari va aqliy rivojlanishiga ko'p qirrali va murakkab ta'sirini yaqqol ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqot natijalari ko'p tillilikning kognitiv funksiyalar, xususan, diqqat, xotira va muammo yechish qobiliyatini yaxshilashini tasdiqlaydi. Bilingval va plurilingual shaxslarda moslashuvchan fikrlash, mantiqiy tahlil va kreativlik yuqori darajada rivojlanganligi aniqlandi. Shu bilan birga, ko'p tillilikning ijtimoiy-madaniy layoqatlarga, jumladan, bag'rikenglik, madaniy ong va muloqot malakalarini rivojlantirishga ijobiy ta'siri ham tasdiqlandi.

Biroq, tadqiqotlarning ayrim kamchiliklari ham aniqlandi. Xususan, bilingvallikning ijobiy ta'siri har doim ham bir xil emasligi va tillarni o'rganish usuli, shaxsning individual xususiyatlari kabi omillarga bog'liqligi qayd etildi. Shu sababli, ko'p tillilikni rivojlantirishda samarali metodologiyalarni tanlash va shaxsiy yondashuvning ahamiyati muhim ekanligini alohida ta'kidlash joiz.

Ushbu tadqiqot ko'p tillilikning (bilingvalizm va plurilingualizm) insonning kognitiv funksiyalari va ijtimoiy-madaniy layoqatlariga murakkab va ko'p qirrali ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Adabiyotlar tahlili ko'p tilli shaxslarda diqqat, xotira va muammo yechish qobiliyatining yaxshilanishini tasdiqlaydi. Bundan tashqari, ko'p tillilik moslashuvchanlikni, mantiqiy tahlil qobiliyatini va kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantiradi. Ijtimoiy-madaniy jihatdan, ko'p tillilik bag'rikenglik, madaniy ong va muloqot malakalarining oshishiga hissa qo'shadi.

Kelgusidagi tadqiqotlarda tillarni o'rganishning turli usullari, yosh, jins, madaniy omillar va boshqa individual farqlarni hisobga olish orqali bilingvalizm va plurilingualizmning ta'sirini yanada chuqurroq o'rganish muhimdir. Bu tadqiqotlar ta'lim va tarbiya, shuningdek, ko'p tilli jamiyatlarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi va ko'p tilli shaxslarning potensialini to'liq ro'yobga chiqarishga xizmat qiladi. Mazkur tadqiqot natijalari ma'lum bir miqdorga ega bo'lgan tajribaviy dalillarga asoslanganligi tufayli, ularning amaliy ahamiyati yuqori.

Bilingvallik va plurilinguallikning inson rivojlanishiga ko'p qirrali va murakkab ta'sirini to'liq tushunish uchun ko'proq chuqur va keng ko'lamli tadqiqotlar zarur. Bu tadqiqotlarda tillarni o'rganishning turli usullarini, shuningdek, yosh, jins, madaniy omillar va boshqa individual farqlarni hisobga olish lozim. Olingan natijalar ta'lim va tarbiya sohasida, shuningdek, ko'p tilli jamiyatlarni rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ko'p tillilikka ega shaxslarning potensialini to'liq ro'yobga chiqarishga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, bilingvallik va plurilinguallikning insonning aqliy rivojlanishi va layoqatlariga ijobiy ta'siri ko'plab tadqiqotlar tomonidan tasdiqlangan. Shuning uchun, ko'p tillilikni rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor berish va bu jarayonni samarali tashkil etish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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KO'P MADANIYATLI MAKONDA ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIK: PRAGMATIK YONDASHUV VA KOMMUNIKATIV MUAMMOLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ko'p madaniyatli makonda zamonaviy tilshunoslikning o'rni va uning pragmalingsvistik yondashuvlar asosida o'rganilishi tahlil qilinadi. Globallashuv jarayonida turli madaniyat vakillari o'rtasidagi kommunikatsiyaning samaradorligi pragmalingsvistik kompetensiyaga bog'liq bo'lib, bu kompetensiya nutq kontekstini tushunish, madaniy tafovutlarni hisobga olish, nutq etiketini saqlash va iltifot strategiyalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, pragmalingsvistik kompetensiyaning rivojlanishi xorijiy tillarni o'rgatish samaradorligini oshirish bilan birga, turli madaniyat vakillari o'rtasida to'g'ri va tushunarli muloqotni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun zamonaviy tilshunoslikda madaniyat va til o'zaro bog'liqligini hisobga olgan holda pragmatik yondashuvlarni yanada chuqurroq o'rganish dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmalingsvistika, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, tilshunoslik, pragmatik kompetensiya, madaniy tafovutlar, kommunikativ muammolar.

Ko'p madaniyatli jamiyatlarning shakllanishi globallashuv, migratsiya va texnologik taraqqiyot natijasida jadallashib bormoqda. Bunday muhitda samarali kommunikatsiya nafaqat lingvistik bilimlarni, balki madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini ham talab etadi. Zamonaviy tilshunoslik ushbu jarayonni o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynaydi, ayniqsa, pragmalingsvistika bu borada til va madaniyat o'zaro aloqalarini tahlil qilish orqali alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Pragmalingsvistika nutqning amaliy qo'llanilishi, kontekstga bog'liqligi va ijtimoiy-madaniy omillarning kommunikativ jarayondagi rolini o'rganadi. Ko'p madaniyatli makonda til shunchaki aloqa vositasi bo'lib qolmay, balki ijtimoiy identifikatsiya, madaniy integratsiya va muloqot strategiyalarini shakllantiruvchi omil sifatida ham namoyon bo'ladi¹. Shu sababli, pragmalingsvistik kompetensiya madaniyatlararo muloqotning ajralmas qismi sifatida qaralishi lozim.

Ushbu maqolada ko'p madaniyatli jamiyatda tilning pragmatik jihatlari, madaniy tafovutlar sababli yuzaga keladigan kommunikativ muammolar va ularni hal qilishning lingvistik yondashuvlari tahlil qilinadi.

Pragmalingsvistik kompetensiyaning madaniyatlararo ahamiyati

Ko'p madaniyatli muhitda samarali kommunikatsiya uchun pragmalingsvistik kompetensiya muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu kompetensiya quyidagi elementlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

¹ Xudoyberganova, D. (2019). Ko'p madaniyatli jamiyatda tilning pragmatik xususiyatlari. Buxoro: BuxDU nashriyoti.

1. Nutq kontekstini to'g'ri tushunish – Suhbatdoshning ijtimoiy mavqei, nutq intonatsiyasi, gestlar va boshqa ekstralingvistik vositalarni inobatga olish.

2. Madaniyatlararo pragmatik tafovutlarni hisobga olish – Masalan, Sharq madaniyatlarida bilvosita ifodalash afzal ko'rilsa, G'arb madaniyatlarida aniq va bevosita muloqot ustunlik qiladi.

3. Iltifot va hurmatni ifodalash strategiyalari – Turli madaniyatlarda iltifotga javob berish shakllari farq qiladi, bu esa noto'g'ri tushunmovchiliklarga olib kelishi mumkin.

4. Nutq etiketini saqlash – Rasmiy va norasmiy nutq uslublarini farqlay olish va kommunikatsiya jarayonida tegishli strategiyalardan foydalanish.

Masalan, ingliz tilida odob bilan rad etish "I'm afraid I can't help you" kabi yumshoq uslubda ifodalanadi, holbuki o'zbek tilida rad qilish yumshoqroq shaklda: "Hozir iloji bo'lmasa kerak, keyin maslahatlashamiz". Bunday pragmatik tafovutlarni o'rgatish pragmatik kompetensiyani oshirishga yordam beradi.

Madaniy tafovutlar va kommunikativ muammolar

Ko'p madaniyatli jamiyatlarda kommunikativ muammolar ko'pincha madaniy tafovutlar natijasida yuzaga keladi². Bunga quyidagi jihatlar sabab bo'lishi mumkin:

1. Nutq odatlarining farqliligi – Ba'zi madaniyatlarda suhbatni boshlashdan oldin uzoq salomlashish odatiy hol bo'lsa, boshqalarda esa bevosita asosiy mavzuga o'tish qabul qilinadi.

2. Bilvosita va bevosita ifodalash uslublari – Masalan, yapon va koreys madaniyatlarida bilvosita ifodalash ustun bo'lsa, nemis va amerika madaniyatlarida aniq va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ifodalash keng tarqalgan.

3. Nutqning rasmiy va norasmiy darajalari – Har bir til va madaniyatda rasmiy va norasmiy uslubga oid o'ziga xos qoidalar mavjud. Masalan, o'zbek tilida katta yoshdagilarga nisbatan hurmat ifodalovchi so'z va iboralar ishlatiladi, ingliz tilida esa rasmiylik darajasi pastroq bo'lishi mumkin.

4. Tovush va intonatsiya tafovutlari – Ba'zi tillarda yuqori yoki past intonatsiya iltifot yoki kinoya sifatida qabul qilinishi mumkin³. Masalan, frantsuz tilida past intonatsiya befarqlik sifatida tushunilsa, yapon tilida esa hurmat belgisi bo'lishi mumkin.

² Abdurahmonov, M. (2015). Til va madaniyat: Lingvopragmatik tahlil asoslari. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya nashriyoti.

³ Jo'rayev, U. (2017). Xorijiy til o'qitishda pragmatik yondashuv. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Fanlar Akademiyasi nashriyoti.

Bu kabi muammolarni hal qilish uchun pragmalingvistik treninglar, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani rivojlantirishga qaratilgan maxsus ta'lim dasturlari va lingvistik adaptatsiya metodlari ishlab chiqilishi kerak.

Pragmalingvistik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish usullari

Ko'p madaniyatli muhitda pragmalingvistik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish uchun quyidagi metodlardan foydalanish mumkin:

1. Rolli o'yinlar va simulyatsiya – Turli madaniyatlarda keng tarqalgan muloqot shakllarini modellashtirish orqali talabalarga real vaziyatlarga moslashish imkonini berish.

2. Korpus lingvistikasi asosida pragmatik tahlil – Til birliklarining turli kontekstlardagi qo'llanilishini kompyuter lingvistikasi yordami bilan o'rganish.

3. Kontrastiv tahlil – Ikki yoki undan ortiq madaniyatning pragmatik xususiyatlarini taqqoslab o'rganish.

4. Madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya bo'yicha treninglar – Talabalar va o'qituvchilarga turli madaniy kodlarni tushuntirish va ularning kommunikativ muhitdagi rolini o'rgatish.

5. Lingvistik adaptatsiya strategiyalari – Turli madaniyat vakillari bilan muloqot qilishda qanday nutq uslubidan foydalanish bo'yicha maxsus ko'rsatmalar ishlab chiqish.

Bu metodlar xorijiy til o'rgatuvchilar va tilshunoslar uchun madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya jarayonida pragmatik kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda samarali bo'lishi mumkin.

Ko'p madaniyatli jamiyatda til faqatgina lingvistik kodlar majmuasi emas, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy o'zaro ta'sir vositasi ham hisoblanadi⁴. Shuning uchun, zamonaviy tilshunoslik pragmalingvistik yondashuvni chuqur o'rganishi, madaniyatlararo muloqotda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni hal qilishga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishi lozim.

Pragmalingvistik kompetensiya kommunikativ jarayonning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, u turli madaniyat vakillarining o'zaro tushunish darajasini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Samarali pragmatik yondashuvlar, ta'lim jarayoniga innovatsion metodlarni joriy etish va madaniy tafovutlarni hisobga olgan holda kommunikatsiyani rivojlantirish global jamiyatda tilning ahamiyatini yanada kuchaytiradi.

⁴ Mamatqulov, Sh. (2023). Pragmatik kompetensiya: nazariya va amaliyot. Qarshi: QarDU nashriyoti.

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INGLIS TILIN OQITÍWDA JERGILIKLI MÁDENIYAT (ISHKI HÁM SÍRTQÍ MOTIVACIYA MÍSAÍINDA)

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Annotaciya. Maqalada inglís tilin úyreniw procesinde áhmiyetli rol oynawshí ishki hám sirtqí motivaciya túsinikleri Óz-ózin ańlaw teóriyasí sheńberinde dodalanadı. Sonúń menen birge, inglís tilin oqıtıwda jergilikli mádeniy kontekstte bul teóriyanıń qollanıwı boyınsha metodikalıq usınıslar keltirilgen.

Gilt sózler: *motivaciya, ishki motivaciya, sirtqí motivaciya, Óz-ózin ańlaw teóriyasí, jergilikli mádeniy kontekst, avtonomiya, kompetenciya, baylanıslılıq.*

Abstract. *The article discusses the concepts of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, which play an important role in the process of learning English, within the framework of the Self-Determination Theory. At the same time, methodological recommendations are given for the application of this theory in the local cultural context of teaching English.*

Key words: *motivation, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, Self-Determination Theory, local cultural context, autonomy, competence, relatedness.*

Motivaciyanıń tiykarǵı eki túri bar: **ishki motivaciya** (úyreniwge bolǵan ishki qálew) hám **sirtqí motivaciya** (sirtqí xoshametlew yamasa basım). Olar kóbinese quramalı tárizde óz ara tásir etedi. Inglís tilin úyreniwshiler kóbinese bul eki motivaciya túri menen háreket etedi. Mısalı, bir talaba inglís tilin úyreniwden zawıqlanıwı (ishki motivaciya), biraq sonıń menen birge imtixannan ótiw yamasa jaqsı jumıs tabıw ushın da úyreniwı múmkin (sirtqí motivaciya). Bul motivaciyalar arasındaǵı teń salmaqlılıq uzaq múddetli til bilimi hám úyreniw tájiriyesine sezilerli tásir kórsetiwı múmkin.

Inglís tilin úyreniwde ishki hám sirtqí motivaciya arasındaǵı qatnasıqlar keńnen úyrenilgen bolıp, olardıń óz ara tásiri hám tildi iyelewge tásiri boyınsha hár qıylı juwmaqlar shıǵarılǵan:

Sirtqı qadaǵalaw úyreniwdiń nátiyjesin sezilerli dárejede aldın ala aytıp bermegen [6]. Bul boyınsha Iranda ótkerilgen izertlewdiń nátiyjeleri, ishki motivaciya sirtqı motivaciyaǵa qaraǵanda inglís tilin ózlestiriwde kúshlirek unamlı baylanısqa iye ekenligin kórsetedi.

Serbiyalı inglís tilin úyreniwshiler arasındaǵı izertlewler sonı kórsetedi, hár eki motivaciya túri bar bolsa da, talabalarda ishki motivaciya dárejesi tómen bolıwǵa beyim. Izertlewde oqıwdan zawıqlanıwdı qalıplestiriwde pedagogikalıq ádisler zárúr ekenligi atap ótilgen [5].

Gonkongta ótkerilgen izertlew nátiyjeleri, barlıq oqıwshılar kúshli sırtqı motivaciyaǵa iye bolsa da, tek ǵana ishki motivaciya inglis tilinen jaqsıraq bahalar menen sezilerli dárejede baylanıslı ekenligin kórsetti. Eki túrdegi motivaciyanı teń qalıpte uslaǵan talaba tek sırtqı sıylıqlarǵa súyengenlerge qaraǵanda jaqsıraq nátiyjelerge erisken [2].

Inglis tilin úyreniwde hám ishki, hám sırtqı motivaciya áhmiyetli rol oynaydı, biraq ishki motivaciya uzaq múddetli nátiyjeliliktiń kúshlirek faktori esaplanadı. Sırtqı sıylıqlar úyreniwde baslawǵa túrtki berse de, ishki motivaciyanı qalıplestiriw turaqlı qatnas hám joqarı nátiyjelerge erisiw ushın zárúr. Óz-ózin ańlaw teoriiyası (Self-Determination Theory (SDT)) ishki hám sırtqı motivaciya arasındaǵı baylanıstı úsh tiykarǵı psixologiyalıq zárúrlık arqalı túsindiredi: **avtonomiya** (óz is-háreketlerin basqarıw zárúrligi), **kompetenciya** (óz iskerliginde nátiyjeli bolıwdı seziw zárúrligi) hám **baylanıslılıq** (basqalar menen baylanıs ornatiw zárúrligi).

Deci and Ryanniń (1985) tárepinen usınılǵan SDT — bul hár qıylı bilimlendiriw sharayatlarında, sonıń ishinde, inglis tilin shet til sıpatında oqıtıwda (EFL) motivaciyanı túsiniw ushın keń qollanılatuǵın tiykarlardan biri bolıp esaplanadı. SDT insan motivaciyası hám jetiskenliklerine itibar qaratatuǵın psixologiyalıq teoriya bolıp esaplanadı. SDT bilimlendiriw kontekstinde eger joqarıdaǵı úsh zárúrlık qollap-quwatlanǵanda motivaciya, qatnas hám nátiyjelilik maksimal dárejede bolıwın atap ótedi [3]. Ekvador EFL klasslarında ótkerilgen izertlewler bul talaplardı avtonomiyanı támiyinlew, qollap-quwatlawshı bahalaw arqalı kompetenciyanı rawajlandırıw hám oqıwshılardı ishki motivaciyalaw ushın óz-ara baylanıslılıqti kúsheytiw arqalı dástúriy sharayatlarǵa birlestiriw múmkin ekenligin kórsetedi [1].

Inglis tilin oqıtıwda SDT klass atmosferası hám ishki motivaciyanı xoshamtlewshı oqıtıw ámeliyatın jaratıw ushın kúshli tiykar bolıwı múmkin. Biraq, SDTnı jergilikli mádeniy kontekstlerge beyimlestiriw júdá áhmiyetli, sebebi mádeniy normalar hám qádiriyatlar avtonomiya, kompetenciya hám baylanıslılıq qalay qalıplesiwi hám rawajlanıwına sezilerli dárejede tásir etedi.

Inglis tilin oqıtıw ushın jergilikli mádeniy kontekstte SDTnı qollanıwda tómendegilerge itibar qaratıwdı usınıs etemiz.

1. Kollektiv mádeniyatlarda avtonomiya. Kollektiv mádeniyatlarda, máselen, Aziya mádeniyatlarında, avtonomiyanı individual ǵárezsizlik emes, al topar qádiriyatlarına beyimlestiriw ushın qayta qalıplestiriw kerek bolıwı múmkin. Egipette alıp barılǵan izertlewler sonı kórsetti, kollektiv mádeniyatlarda da inglis tilin úyreniwde avtonomiya áhmiyetke iye. Biraq, oqıtıwshılar avtonomiyanı baylanıslılıq penen teń alıp barıwı kerek, yaǵnıy birge islesiwde rawajlandırıw hám qáte islewden

qorqıwdı azaytıw arqalı oqıwshılarda óz-ara húrmet hám isenimdi jaratıw zárúr [4].
Mısalı:

— oqıwshılar birgelikte temalardı yamasa úyreniw metodların tańlaytuǵın **topar joybarların** xoshametlew;

— avtonomiyanı mádeniy jaqtan sáykes túrde kontekstlestiriw ushın sabaqlarǵa **shańaraq yamasa jámiyetke baylanıslı temalardı** kirgiziw.

1. **Mádeniy áhmiyetke iye kompetenciyalardı qáliplestiriw.** Kompetenciya talabalardıń mádeniy kelip shıǵıwı hám olardıń inglis tilinen real turmısta paydalanıwına sáykes keliwshi wazıypalardı joybarlaw arqalı qollap-quwatlanıwı múmkin. Mısalı:

— inglis tilin túsiniw hám sóylew ámeliyatı ushın **mádeniy jaqtan tanıs materiallar**, mäselen, jergilikli ádebiyat, jańalıqlar yamasa waqıyalardan paydalanıw;

— oqıwshılar ortalıǵın sáwlelendiriwshi **kontekstke tán bahalawlardı** kirgiziw, mäselen, óz jasaw ornında jumısqa sáwbetlesiwge tayarlıq kóriw yamasa jergilikli qarım-qatnas usılları tiykarında rásmiy xatlar jazıw.

2. **Mádeniy normalar boyınsha baylanıslılıqtı rawajlandırıw.** Baylanıslılıq mádeniyatqa qarap túrli formalarda kórinıwi múmkin. Mısalı:

— avtoritetke kóbirek áhmiyet beriletuǵın mádeniyatlarda, **oqıtıwshı hám oqıtıwshı arasındaǵı óz ara húrmetke tiykarlangan qatnasıqlardı** rawajlandırıw baylanıslılıqtı kúsheytiwi múmkin;

— **birgeliktegi wazıypalar**, mäselen, teńleslerine sabaq beriw yamasa kishi toparlarda dodalaw inglis tilin úyreniwde sociallıq baylanıslardı xoshametlewi múmkin.

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ЛЕВ ТОЛСТОЙ: ВСЕГДА АКТУАЛЬНЫЙ ГЕНИЙ

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Аннотация: Лев Николаевич Толстой – один из величайших писателей мировой литературы, чье творчество сохраняет свою значимость в разные эпохи. В его произведениях поднимаются универсальные темы морали, добра, зла, внутренней борьбы человека и поиска смысла жизни. Несмотря на смену времен и ценностей, идеи Толстого продолжают вдохновлять читателей, находя отклик в современном обществе. Его философия ненасилия, гуманизма и искреннего стремления к истине остаётся актуальной для человечества XXI века. В данной работе анализируется значимость творчества Толстого в историческом и современном контексте, рассматриваются его основные произведения и влияние на литературу и общественную мысль.

Ключевые слова: Лев Толстой, актуальность, мораль, гуманизм, реализм, философия.

Лев Николаевич Толстой (1828–1910) – классик русской и мировой литературы, создавший произведения, оказавшие колоссальное влияние на развитие художественного слова и нравственного самосознания человечества. Его романы «Война и мир», «Анна Каренина», «Воскресение» и многие другие продолжают находить отклик у современных читателей, а его философские и публицистические труды остаются предметом глубокого изучения.

Толстой был не только писателем, но и мыслителем, реформатором, который стремился к истине в вопросах морали, религии, общественного устройства. В своих произведениях он поднимает извечные вопросы: что такое добро и зло? В чём смысл человеческой жизни? Как найти гармонию между личными желаниями и долгом перед обществом? Эти вопросы остаются актуальными и сегодня.

Современный мир сталкивается с множеством вызовов – социальных, политических, моральных. Толстой, выступая против насилия, неравенства и несправедливости, своими произведениями призывает к внутреннему совершенствованию, поиску истины и добродетели. Как отмечает С. А. Асеева, «философско-антропологические аспекты художественного творчества Л. Н. Толстого в контексте феномена интермедальности» продолжают быть предметом научных исследований в наши дни.¹ Толстой верил, что единственный путь к подлинному счастью – это жизнь по законам добра и любви, и эта идея остается важной в XXI веке.

¹ Асеева С. А. Философско-антропологические аспекты художественного творчества Л. Н. Толстого в контексте феномена интермедальности // Президентская библиотека имени Б.Н. Ельцина.

Философия ненасилия Толстого оказала влияние на таких выдающихся личностей, как Махатма Ганди и Мартин Лютер Кинг. Ганди писал: «Я многому научился у Толстого. Он научил меня тому, что любовь сильнее оружия». Это свидетельствует о том, что идеи Толстого не просто остаются в прошлом, но продолжают вдохновлять поколения.

Художественный стиль Толстого уникален. Он глубоко анализировал человеческую природу, создавал живые, психологически достоверные образы. Его герои не просто литературные персонажи, но воплощение человеческих страстей, надежд, ошибок. Как отмечает исследователь А. Шифман, «Толстой бескомпромиссно сохраняет приверженность к идеалу высокого реалистического искусства, правдивого, жизненно достоверного, затрагивающего коренные вопросы человеческого существования».² Его произведения помогают понять сложность внутреннего мира человека и разобраться в собственных переживаниях.

Литературные критики отмечают, что в своих романах Толстой уделял внимание не только масштабным историческим событиям, но и внутреннему миру человека. По мнению С. А. Асеевой, «философско-антропологические аспекты художественного творчества Л. Н. Толстого в контексте феномена интермедиальности»³ продолжают быть предметом научных исследований в наши дни. Именно поэтому творчество Толстого продолжает интересовать читателей по всему миру.

Толстой остаётся актуальным, потому что его произведения затрагивают извечные вопросы морали, справедливости, любви, внутренней борьбы. Его идеи о нравственном самосовершенствовании, неприятии насилия и поиске истины находят отклик в современном мире. Читая Толстого, мы не просто знакомимся с русской классикой – мы осмысливаем самих себя, учимся понимать окружающий мир и стремимся к гармонии. Толстой – это не просто писатель прошлого, а мудрец, чьи слова остаются жизненно важными для каждого из нас.

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² Лев Толстой глазами современников // Вопросы литературы.

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OR-NOMUS UCHUN KURASHGAN AYOLLAR WOMEN FIGHTING FOR HONOR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mahoratli adib Nazar Eshonqul qissa va hikoyalarida ayollar xarakterlari, ularning or-nomus uchun olib borgan kurashlari, hislari va qadriyatlarini muammosi talqini tavsiflangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ayol obrazi, xarakter, motiv, milliylik, Nazar Eshonqul, or-nomus, kayvoni, qissa, hikoya.

Abstract: In this thesis, the interpretation of women's characters, their struggles for honor, feelings and values in the stories and stories of the skilled writer Nazar Eshanqul is described.

Key words: female image, character, motive, nationality, Nazar Eshanqul, honor, kayvani, story, story.

Mahoratli adib Nazar Eshonqulning qissa va hikoyalaridagi ayollar obrazlari, ularning ruhiyatini o'rganish bugungi kunda adabiyotshunoslik uchun muhim bo'lgan ko'plab jihatlarni yoritadi. Nazar Eshonqul qissa va hikoyalarida sahnaga avval ayol obrazini olib kiradi va keyin uni batafsil ta'riflaydi. Bu ta'riflashda ularning ruhiyati, portreti, xakteri va hayot yo'llarida chekkan iztiroblari bir-bir akslanadi. Fikrimiz dalili sifatida adibning ilk nasriy asari bo'lmish "Urush odamlari" qissasi qahramoni Biydi momo va "Shamolni tutib bo'lmaydi" hikoyasi qahramoni Bayna momo obrazlarini tasvirlarini qiyoslashimiz mumkin.

Biydi momoning ta'riflanishidagi ta'riflar muallifning Bayna momo haqida aytilgan fikrlarga aynan o'xshab ketadi. Buning sababini biz bu ikki obrazning prototipi bir ekanligidan bilishimiz mumkin. Feruza Burxonovanning "Muallif adabiy-estetik qarashlari va ijodiy parallelizm. (Nazar Eshonqul va Ulug'bek Hamdam ijodi misolida)" nomli filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasida tadqiqotimiz obyekti bo'lgan "Urush odamlari", "Momoqo'shiq" qissalari tahlil etilgan. Izlanuvchi qissalarning yaratilish tarixini, yozuvchilar ijodida uchraydigan ayollar obrazining real hayotiy asoslarini adibning tug'ilib o'sgan yurti, oilaviy va badiiy muhiti bilan birgalikda o'rganib xulosalar chiqargan. Aynan "Urush odamlari" va boshqa nasriy asarlardagi momo obrazi prototipi haqida shunday fikrlar bildirgan. "Urush odamlari qissasida Tersota qishlog'ida yashovchi Biydi momo, "Shamolni tutib bo'lmaydi" hikoyasida esa Bayna momo timsolida namoyon bo'ladigan qahramondir.

Bu har ikki obrazga xos mushtarak jihatlar talaygina. Avvalo, momo timsollariga xos umumiy xususiyat obrazlarning xarakter qirralaridagi uyg'unlikda namoyon bo'ladi. Yozuvchi nima sababdan momo obrazi va Tersota qishlog'iga qayta-qayta murojaat qilyapti, nega o'zining dardlarini shu obrazlar mohiyatiga singdirib, go'yo ular bilan birga nafas olayotganday tasvirlayapti. Tersota qishlog'i yozuvchi o'ylab topgan yoki bo'lmasa xalq og'zaki namunalaridan olgan biror joy nomimi yoxud real hudud bilan bog'liqmi? Biydi momo kim, kabi qator savollarga javob izlab yozuvchi iodiylaboratoriyasiga chuqurroq kirib borganimizda, bevosita ijodkorning tarjimai holi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan ko'pgina jihatlar oydinlashdi¹".

Bayna momoning ham Biydi momoning ham turmush o'rtog'i ko'z oldida jon taslim qilgan ya'ni o'ldirilgan. Ayanchli va o'xshash taqdirilar. Eri o'lganidan so'ng Biydi momo hech hayotdan, undagi qiyinchiliklardan nolib yig'lamaydi. Xuddi shu holatni biz Bayno momo shaxsiyatida ham ko'ramiz. Biydi momo faqatgina o'g'illari birinchi zotini keltirib tashlagandagina, o'z mehnatlari besamar ketmaganligini ko'rib, to'yib-to'yib yig'lagandi.

Biydi momoning bo'sh-bayov, o'g'irlab kelingan katta kelini xarakteri va u bilan qaynonasining munosabati "Bepoyon osmon" hikoyasi qahramonlari Oyto'ldi va Bibioynaniki bilan uyqashdir. O'g'illaridan qoraxat kelgach, el-u xalqqa aralashmay qo'yishi ham Bayna momoning eri o'ldirilgach qishloqdoshlarini yomon ko'rib qolishiga mushtarak. Tadqiqotchi bu haqida fikrlarini davom ettirarkan, "Tersota qishlog'i aslida, yozuvchi tug'ilib-o'sgan, bolaligining dastlabki davrlari o'tgan, qishloqning nomi. Momo obrazi esa adibning buvisi buvisi Pirimqul qizi Masil momoning prototipidir. Masil momo ham xuddi hikoyalarida tasvirlanganidek yigirma yoshida eridan ayrilib, ikkita farzandi bilan beva qoladi va boshqa turmush qurmay hayotning butun mashaqqatlariga yolg'iz o'zi dosh beradi. Yozuvchi bolaligida o'zi ko'rgan bilgan hayotiy xotiralar, diliga cho'kib qolgan armonlar keyinchalik qayta uyg'onib o'z asarlari mohiyatiga singib ketgan"².

Adib asarlaridagi bu kabi kayvoni momolar ya'ni kampirlar obrazlarining hayotiy va jonliligini ta'minlash maqsadida uning xatti-harakatlari va gapirish manerasini, tashqi, ichki ruhiy dunyosini tabiiy ravishda tasvirlagan. Aynan Nazar Eshonqul asarlarida o'zbek kayvoni kampiri obrazi mahorat bilan yaratilganligini

¹ Burxanova F. Muallif adabiy-estetik qarashlari va ijodiy parallelizm (Nazar Eshonqul va Ulugbek Hamdam ijodi misolida): Filol. fan. b-cha. f-fa.d-ri. (PhD)...diss.avtoref. – Toshkent: 2019. – B.17.

² Burxanova F. Muallif adabiy-estetik qarashlari va ijodiy parallelizm (Nazar Eshonqul va Ulugbek Hamdam ijodi misolida): Filol. fan. b-cha. f-fa.d-ri. (PhD)...diss.avtoref. – Toshkent: 2019. – B.18.

ko'rishimiz mumkin. Aynan shu kayvoni kampirlar obrazidagi yana bir xususiyat farzandi dog'ida kuyib ado bo'lgan ona va uning ruhiyati teran badiiy talqin etilgan.

Ko'plab tadqiqotlarda o'rganilganidek, ayol obrazi eng avvalo, naslni davom ettiruvchi hilqat va bashariyatning yaratuvchisi sifatida talqin etilgan. Bundan tashqari ayol dunyo xalqlari adabiyotida go'zallik, donishmandlik, aql, muhabbat timsoli sifatida ham qaralgan. Nazar Eshonqulning nasriy asarlarida esa ayollar obrazlari or-nomus timsoli sifatida talqin etilgan. Adibning ko'plab asarlarida or-nomus uchun kurashgan ayollar obrazlarini uchratamiz (Biydi momo, Bayna momo, Bibi oyna).

Adib ularning portretlarini yaratishda folklor stilizatsiyasidan ilhomlangan, realistik tasvirlardan foydalangan, ularning nutqida kinoyaning o'rni ham bor. Bizga bir qarashda zolimdek tuyuladigan, hatto qotillik sodir etgan ayol ruhiyatiga nazar solsak, undagi yillar davomida yig'ilgan nafratni, yolg'izlikni, dard-alamni ko'rishimiz mumkin. Adib ularning taqdirlarini va hislarini bizga shu qadar jonli tarzda yetkazib berganki, o'qirman bu qahramonlar bilan o'zini yonma-yon turgandek his eta oladi. Biydi momo Anziratni kim yo'ldan urganligini aniqlash maqsadida yetmish uch kecha uning uyini poylaydi. Xo'sh, bunda uning niyati qotillikka sabab bo'lish edimi?! Also unday emasdi. U o'z qarichi bilan urushga sabab bo'layotgan buzuqilarni adabini bermoqchi, qishloqning, erkaklarning va shu bilan birga o'zining or-nomusini himoya etmoqchi edi. U o'ziga kelgach Normat polvonni qaytarishga harakat qilishi fikrimizning dalili bo'la oladi. Albatta uning har bir harakatida, qishloqdoshlarini tanqid qilishlarida, kinoyali gaplarida aslida or-nomus uchun jon kuydirish mavjud edi.

Nazar Eshonqul ijodida uchraydigan kayvoni momolar obrazi tipida shu kabi xususiyatlarni takror va takror ko'rishimiz mumkin. Masalan "Shamolni tutib bo'lmaydi" hikoyasi qahramoni Bayna momo ham ayol boshi bilan eri va o'g'lining qotilidan qasos oladi. Albatta biz bu fikrlarimiz bilan qotillik sodir etgan qahramonni yoqlamoqchi emasmiz, faqat ushbu jinoyatga sodir bo'lgan omillar mavjudligini, bu hislar azbaroyi nomus uchun, or talab etilib, tushunib-tushunmay sodir etilganligini aytib o'tmoqdamiz. Aslida hikoyaning nomlanishidan ham biz asl mazmunni bilib olishimiz mumkin.

Jumladan Yulduz Eshmatovanning tadqiqotida "Nazar Eshonqulning daxshatli urush fojealari tasvirlangan "Urush odamlari" qissasida ham fasllarga uyg'un tarzda qahramonlar iztiroblari, g'am-qayg'ulari ochib beriladi. Fojialarga to'la davr muhiti ko'ngilchan, dilkash kishilar ruhiyatidagi o'zgarishlarga, urush kabi sovuq, dag'al munosabatlarga aylanganini, bu esa qahramonlar taqdirining fojiali qismatiga sabab

bo'lganligini badiiy gavdalantirgan". Nazar Eshonqul ularning (qissa va hikoya qahramoni bo'lgan kayvoni momolarning) hislarini ifoda etganda ularni oqlamaydi, aksincha bor bo'yi yoritadiki, xulosani o'qirmanning o'ziga qoldiradi. Bu ham yozuvchining adolatidan, mahoratidan darak. Nazar Eshonqul asarlarida psixologizmning turli-tuman formalari, ya'ni portret, monolog, diolog, muallif bayoni va hissiy harakatlardan unumli foydalanganligi uchun ham ayollar ruhiyatini batafsil ochishga muvaffaq bo'lgan.

Asarlaridagi momolar obrazi asrlar osha xotin-qizlardagi hayo, ibo kabi yaxshi fazilatlarining timsoli edi. Ular shu qadriyatlarga, o'ziga sodiq qola olgandi. Aynan shuning uchun ham qishloqning or-nomus timsoliga aylangandi desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Aynan Biydi momo va Anzirat obrazlarida biz kontrastni ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Nutq tiplarini o'rgangan olimlardan biri Y.Solijonovning ushbu fikrlari aynan Nazar Eshonqulning uslubiga xos deyishimiz mumkin. "Mabodo, yozuvchi asarda o'z-o'zicha tabiiy rivojlanayotgan hayot tasviriga xuda-behuda aralashaversa, o'quvchisiga o'z nomidan izoh bera boshlasa, asarning ta'sir kuchi ham, o'quvchining fikrlash faolligi ham susayadi. Chunki bunday jarayon o'quvchi obrazlarining bevosita xatti-harakatini, o'z-o'zini kashf etishni, ruhiy olamini emas, avtorning o'zini, uning bilvosita munosabatini ko'radiki, bu hol uning tafakkurida aks-sado uyg'otadi. Boisi avtorning o'rinsiz aralashuvi garchi bilimimizni ma'lum darajada boyitishga va qahramonlar xatti-harakatlarini hamda holatini, taqdirini tushunib olishimizga ko'maklashgandek tuyilsa-da, aslida o'quvchida estetik zavq uyg'ota olmaydi³.

Biydi momoning xarakteridagi qat'iyat qissada juda go'zal tarzda ochib berilgan. U eri o'lganidan so'ng faqat o'g'illari zot ayirib kelganida yig'laydi, to'yib-to'yib yig'laydi. Eriga sodiqlik katta kelindagi – Biydi momoga yoqadigan yagona xislat edi. Biydi momo o'ta qat'iyatli edi. Chunki ayolmijozlar oldida o'zini yo'qotmaydi. O'gillarining o'lim xabarini olganida bo'g'zidagi kuyikni zo'rga yutadi. Bu xatti-harakatlarini u or-nomus yo'lidagi qadamlar deya sanaydi va kelinlaridan ham shu kabi boshqalar yonida o'zini tutishni talab etadi.

Nazar Eshonqulning asarlaridagi qahramonlari o'zini, o'zligini topishga, yuksak ideallarga intilayotgan qahramonlardir. Ular askari o'z hayotini tahlil etadi. Ko'pchilikdan farqli o'laroq muttasil fikrlashga, umr mohiyatini topishga, boshqalarnikiga o'xshamagan o'ziga xos dunyosi bilan yashashga intiladi.

³ Solijonov Y. Nutq va uslub. – Toshkent: Cho'lpon, 2002, - B.11.

Yozuvchi betakror obrazlar yaratish jarayonida qahramonlar ruhiyatiga teranroq kirib borish uchun tafakkur va tahayyul kuchiga tayanadi. Adibning o‘zi buni quyidagicha e‘tirof etadi: “...men yozayotganda o‘zimni turli toifalarga, tushuncha va qarashlarga bo‘lib yuborib yozaman. Aslida, hammasi bir odam. O‘ylayotgan, o‘ylashga urinayotgan yoki suhbat mavzusidan kelib chiqsak, fikrlashga harakat qilayotgan, o‘zini izlayotgan odamlar”.

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ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ МАГИЧЕСКОГО РЕАЛИЗМА И ФИЛОСОФИИ НОВОЙ ЭРЫ В «АЛЕФЕ» ПАУЛО КОЭЛЬО

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Аннотация. В романе Пауло Коэльо «Алеф» элементы магического реализма и философии Новой Эры умело сочетаются, создавая повествование, в котором исследуется духовный путь и личная трансформация главного героя. Через мистическую концепцию «Алеф», где время и пространство сходятся, роман углубляется в темы самопознания, искупления и духовного обновления. Взаимодействие между реальностью и сверхъестественным, характерное для магического реализма, позволяет читателю рассматривать мистический опыт главного героя как часть повседневной жизни. Философия Новой Эры с ее акцентом на внутреннем равновесии, реинкарнации и поиске смысла пронизывает роман, подчеркивая личностный рост и просветление. В этой статье рассматривается, как эти два элемента работают вместе, чтобы усилить центральные темы романа и способствовать более глубокому пониманию преобразующего пути человеческой души.

Ключевые слова. Магический реализм, философия Новой Эры, личностная трансформация, духовный рост, реинкарнация.

Abstract. Paulo Coelho's novel *Aleph* masterfully blends elements of magical realism and New Age philosophy, creating a narrative that explores the protagonist's spiritual journey and personal transformation. Through the mystical concept of "Aleph," where time and space converge, the novel delves into the themes of self-knowledge, redemption, and spiritual renewal. The interplay between reality and the supernatural, characteristic of magical realism, allows the reader to view the protagonist's mystical experiences as part of everyday life. New Age philosophy, with its focus on inner balance, reincarnation, and the search for meaning, permeates the novel, emphasizing personal growth and enlightenment. This paper examines how these two elements work together to enhance the novel's central themes and contribute to a deeper understanding of the human soul's transformative journey.

Key words. Magical realism, New Age philosophy, personal transformation, spiritual growth, reincarnation.

Введение

В романе Пауло Коэльо «Алеф» гармонично сочетаются элементы магического реализма и философии Новой Эры, что создает уникальную структуру повествования, исследующую личную трансформацию и духовный рост. Коэльо стирает границы между реальностью и сверхъестественным, позволяя мистическим переживаниям стать частью повседневной жизни. Центральная концепция «Алеф» — мистическая точка, где пересекаются все места, и моменты времени, символизирует путь героя к самопознанию и искуплению. Философия Новой Эры, с её акцентом на самопознании,

реинкарнации и внутреннем равновесии, пронизывает весь роман. Путешествие героя — это не только физическое, но и глубокое духовное движение, включающее преодоление страхов и принятие настоящего момента. В статье будет рассмотрено, как сочетание магического реализма и философии Новой Эры углубляет понимание основных тем романа, таких как поиск смысла жизни, искупление и личностное обновление.

Обзор литературы

Жизнь и ранний опыт Пауло Коэльо

Пауло Коэльо — известный бразильский писатель, чьи произведения были переведены на многие языки, что принесло ему мировое признание. «Он стал послом культурного разнообразия в ЮНЕСКО и представителем ООН по вопросам мира». [4, с.74] Одно из главных посланий его книг — счастье в том, чтобы найти себя. Коэльо часто описывает путь к саморазвитию и духовному просветлению через внутренние поиски и преодоление конфликтов.

«Пауло Коэльо родился 24 августа 1947 года в Рио-де-Жанейро в семье среднего класса. С детства он проявлял оригинальное мышление, не любил учиться, но увлекался чтением и письмом. В 12 лет он начал вести дневник, записывая свои впечатления и мысли». [6, с. 96] В юности он хотел стать писателем, но родители не поддержали эту мечту. Они отправили его в строгую католическую школу, где у него развилось отвращение к религиозным практикам. После школы Пауло увлекся культурой хиппи, участвовал в политических движениях и путешествовал по Латинской Америке. В это время он продолжал писать и основал журнал, что привело его к знакомству с музыкантом Раулем Сейшасом. Вместе они создали несколько успешных песен, включая «Gita», которая была продана тиражом в пять миллионов экземпляров. В 1974 году Пауло опубликовал свою первую книгу «Театр в образовании».

Духовное путешествие Пауло Коэльо в Алеф

Пауло Коэльо исследует свою личную духовную трансформацию и проблемы, связанные с реинкарнацией, магией и священным пространством в своих книгах, особенно в Алеф. «Он признает, что в его душе есть тьма, с которой он учится жить. В книге он описывает путешествие по Транссибирской магистрали, которое связано с его кризисом веры и духовного роста». [1, с. 7] Коэльо использует магические практики, такие как молитвы, круги света для защиты и амулеты, чтобы решать духовные проблемы и исцелять свою душу. Его работы также затрагивают вопросы личностного роста, мудрости и счастья, а в «Адептере» он описывает внутреннее отчаяние женщины, столкнувшейся с

кризисом в браке. В «Алеф» Коэльо сочетает свою жизнь знаменитости со своим глубоким стремлением к магии, связи с природой, Богом и людьми, что делает эту книгу особенно личной и показательной. В своем романе «Алеф» Коэльо рассказывает о своих духовных поисках и личностной трансформации, используя элементы магического реализма и философии Новой Эры. Герои романа переживают внутренние кризисы, а их путь к просветлению проходит через физические и духовные путешествия. Основная идея заключается в том, что изменение жизни начинается с себя — обретения внутренней гармонии и преодоления стереотипов и рутины. «Книга основана на реальном опыте Пауло Коэльо. Он описывает свое путешествие по Африке, Европе и Азии, чтобы восстановить свою энергию и страсть к жизни. Главный герой, тоже Пауло, чувствует себя потерянным и разочарованным. Он задается вопросом о смысле своей жизни и нуждается в ответах». [6, с. 101] В ответ на свои сомнения он отправляется в путешествие по России, чтобы найти решения своих внутренних проблем. В этом путешествии он встречает девушку по имени Хиляль, которую он любил пятьсот лет назад и предал. Это предательство мешает ему быть счастливым. Их встречи становятся ключевыми моментами для его самопознания, а явление «Алеф» помогает герою преодолеть внутренние противоречия. Вместе с Хилялом он проходит мистический путь, познавая любовь, прощение и преодолевая трудности. Книга рассказывает о поисках искупления за ошибки прошлого.

Концепция времени и духовного роста в Алефе

В своем романе «Пауло Коэльо исследует концепцию времени и магических переживаний через концепцию Алефа, заимствованную из короткого рассказа Хорхе Луиса Борхеса. У Борхеса Алеф — это точка, где все существующее на земле можно увидеть одновременно, и она символизирует неизвестные аспекты пространства и времени. Коэльо видит два типа времени: «малый Алеф» — линейное время, которое включает прошлое и будущее, и «большой Алеф» позволяет путешествовать в прошлое, а также рассматривать возможную реинкарнацию и синхронность временных событий». [5, с. 112] Коэльо затрагивает в книге темы прошлого, настоящего и будущего. Главный герой, как и сам автор, страдает от того, что он часто фокусируется на том, что было или что могло бы быть, вместо того, чтобы жить здесь и сейчас. В книге обсуждается важность осознания момента «здесь и сейчас», что напоминает идеи философа Экхарта Толле и психоаналитика Карла Юнга о том, как прошлый опыт может влиять на настоящее и вызывать стресс. В романе

присутствует эгоцентрическая философия, подчеркивающая гармонию человека с природой и миром. Магический реализм помогает читателю взглянуть на привычный мир с новой стороны и осознать важность каждого момента в жизни. Основная идея книги заключается в том, что человек должен научиться отпускать прошлое и не бояться будущего, чтобы обрести гармонию и внутренний покой. Также в романе «Коэльо затрагивает философские концепции времени, такие как *хронос* (время как поток, без начала и конца) и *кайрос* (время как моменты особого смысла и опыта). Основная тема романа — возможность единого духовного опыта времени, способного объединить последователей разных религий». [5, с. 113] Коэльо использует символ «Алеф», чтобы показать, как разные религии могут найти общую точку соприкосновения, несмотря на их различия. «Коэльо использует метафоры, такие как китайский бамбук, который сначала растет в земле, а затем быстро растет, чтобы показать, как духовный рост часто происходит незаметно, а затем внезапно становится очевидным». [3, с. 376] Он также затрагивает такие темы, как карма и реинкарнация, показывая, как наши прошлые действия влияют на настоящее.

В конце романа Коэльо напоминает нам, что главное — это само путешествие, а не конечный пункт назначения. Через свой опыт герой учит читателей искать и находить новые смыслы в жизни, преодолевая однообразие и разрушая привычные границы. «Главный герой приходит к пониманию важности прощения и примирения, а также осознает свою ответственность за ошибки прошлого». [3, с. 377] Таким образом, роман «Алеф» затрагивает не только магические и философские темы, но и поднимает вопросы о взаимоотношениях различных культур и религий, о прощении и понимании других людей.

Методология

В работе использованы различные научные методы для глубокого изучения темы. Был проведен обзор исследовательских материалов, с анализом ключевых статей, отражающих современные теории. Особое внимание уделено выбору актуальных источников. Также автор полностью прочитал книгу, анализируя ключевые отрывки для раскрытия скрытых значений и методологических идей, что позволило сформировать основу обзора литературы и практической части статьи.

Анализ текста

В данном анализе рассматриваются отрывки из романа Пауло Коэльо «Алеф», где переплетаются элементы магического реализма и философии Новой Эры, создавая уникальное повествование, отражающее духовный путь персонажей и их личностную трансформацию.

Отрывок 1 можно интерпретировать через магический реализм и философию Новой Эры. Метафора жизни как поезда, который постоянно движется, символизирует неизбежность и непрерывность существования. В контексте философии Новой Эры, жизнь — это не конечная цель, а постоянный процесс самопознания и духовного роста.

Отрывок 2 акцентирует внимание на концепции «Личной Легенды» и судьбы, что соответствует философии Новой Эры. Важность внутреннего осознания и принятия духовной судьбы, а также реинкарнации и кармы, подчеркивает, что смерть — это переход в новый уровень существования.

Отрывок 3 выражает идею о том, что время не учит, а лишь приносит усталость. В философии Новой Эры время рассматривается как цикличное и связано с внутренним развитием. Дерево, как символ внутренней стабильности, акцентирует внимание на важности сосредоточения и самосознания.

Отрывок 4 объединяет магический реализм и философию Новой Эры через концепцию Алефа, мистической точки, где время и пространство сливаются. Это отражает единство всего сущего, что является центральной темой философии Новой Эры.

Отрывок 5 сочетает философию Новой Эры с магическим реализмом, фокусируясь на восприятии времени. Мифологический образ мира как женщины и концепции *кайрос* и *хронос* подчеркивают важность внутреннего роста и жизни в настоящем.

Отрывок 6 раскрывает путь к самопознанию через признание истины и внутреннего роста. Путешествие символизирует духовный путь, а интуиция и внутренний голос становятся важными ориентирами, стирая границы между логикой и мистикой.

Заключение

Элементы магического реализма и философии Новой Эры в романе Пауло Коэльо создают многослойное произведение, где реальность и сверхъестественное обогащают друг друга. Магический реализм помогает воспринимать мир через призму мистики, а философия Новой Эры углубляет идеи о духовном росте и поиске смысла жизни, создавая пространство для самопознания и внутренней гармонии.

Заклучение

Роман Пауло Коэльо «Алеф» является глубоким исследованием человеческой души, сочетая магический реализм и философию Новой Эры. Эти подходы создают уникальное повествование и раскрывают темы поиска смысла жизни, самопознания, искупления и обновления. Магический реализм стирает границы между реальностью и сверхъестественным, воспринимая духовные переживания героя как естественную часть мира. Концепция «Алефа», символизирующего пересечение времени и пространства, становится метафорой пути героя к пониманию себя.

Философия Новой Эры пронизывает произведение, призывая к внутреннему балансу, самосовершенствованию и гармонии. Путешествие героя — это не только физическое движение, но и преодоление страхов, обретение покоя. Это сочетание магического реализма и философии Новой Эры открывает пространство для размышлений о личной трансформации и духовном возрождении, позволяя читателю задуматься о своём пути к самопознанию.

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Отрывки:

1. “Вся наша жизнь – путешествие, от рождения к смерти. Меняется пейзаж за окном, меняются люди, меняются потребности, а поезд все идет вперед. Жизнь – это поезд, не вокзал. А то, что вы делали до сих пор, не путешествия, но перемена мест, и это не одно и то же.” [2, с. 13]
2. “Мы всегда будем задавать себе одни и те же вопросы. Нам всегда будет не хватать смирения, чтобы принять знание сердца о том, зачем мы здесь. Да, это трудно, – говорить со своим сердцем, а может быть, это и не нужно. Нам просто следует довериться ему и считывать знаки судьбы, и проживать нашу собственную жизнь; рано или поздно мы поймем, что все мы являемся частью чего-то большего, даже если не сможем осознать, чем является это большее. Говорят, каждый человек за мгновение до смерти понимает истинный смысл своего существования, и из этого мгновения рождается Рай или ад.” [2, с. 18]
3. ““– *Послушайте, Ж., несмотря на все мои усилия, я не могу сказать, что стал ближе к Богу и к самому себе, –* отвечаю я, и мои слова исполнены горечи. – *Это потому, что, как все на свете, вы полагали, что со временем непременно приблизитесь к Богу. Но время плохой наставник. Благодаря ему мы ощущаем лишь, как, старея, сильнее устаем. Мне вдруг начинает казаться, будто на меня смотрит мой дуб. Ему больше четырехсот*

лет, а единственное, чему он за это время научился, – это оставаться на одном месте.” [2, с. 11]

4. “Я смотрю на свет в священном месте, и волны этого света омывают меня, наполняя душу покоем и любовью, которые редко идут рука об руку. Я вижу себя со стороны, а еще вижу африканских слонов с воздетыми к небу хоботами, верблюдов в пустыне, завсегдаев бара в Буэнос-Айресе, пса, перебегающего улицу, кисть, которой водит женская рука, рисующая розу, заснеженную вершину в Швейцарии, монахов, поющих диковинные гимны, пилигрима на пороге церкви в Сантьяго-де-Компостела, солдат, которые поднимаются с рассветом и готовятся к бою, пастуха, гонящего отару, рыб в океане, города и леса, – весь мир, огромный и сияющий, маленький и тихий. Это Алеф, точка единения всего сущего, в которой совмещаются и время, и пространство.” [2, с. 47]
“Когда-то весь мир был женщиной, и все вокруг было наполнено ее прекрасной энергией. Люди верили в чудеса и жили сегодняшним днем, а времени не существовало. У древних греков было два слова для обозначения времени; одно из них *кайрос*, то есть время богов, вечность. Потом мир изменился. Людям пришлось бороться за выживание, выращивать хлеб и беречь урожай, чтобы не умереть от голода. Тогда они познали время в нашем понимании. Греки называли его *хронос*, а римляне отождествляли с Сатурном, богом, пожравшим собственных детей. Мы сделали рабами памяти.” [2, с. 130]
5. “Возможно, правильное всего было бы оставить ее в неведении, но, сам не знаю почему, я чувствую, что правда поможет ей освободиться от многого из того, что ей приходится переживать в этом воплощении. Я совсем не случайно отправился в путешествие, когда увидел, что моя жизнь уже не походит на реку, стремящуюся к морю. Я так поступил, когда понял, что она находится на грани стагнации. С Хилляль творилось то же самое, и это не простое совпадение. Господь непременно наставит меня, как ей все объяснить.” [2, с.109]

CODE-SWITCHING AND MULTILINGUAL IDENTITY

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Annotation: *This article examines the phenomenon of code-switching and its relationship to multilingual identity. It analyzes how bilingual and multilingual speakers alternate between languages in various contexts and explores the sociolinguistic, cognitive, and cultural factors that influence this behavior. By reviewing key theories and empirical studies, the article highlights both the communicative advantages and the challenges associated with code-switching. Ultimately, it argues that code-switching is not merely a marker of language deficiency but rather a sophisticated strategy that reflects dynamic linguistic repertoires and evolving cultural identities.*

Keywords: *Code-switching, multilingual identity, bilingualism, language switching, sociolinguistics, cultural identity, language contact, linguistic diversity.*

Introduction

In today's globalized world, the ability to communicate in multiple languages is increasingly common. Bilingual and multilingual speakers often engage in code-switching—that is, alternating between languages within a conversation or even a single utterance. Far from being a sign of linguistic incompetence, code-switching is a complex and rule-governed phenomenon that reveals much about speakers' identities, social contexts, and cognitive processes. This article explores the concept of code-switching and its implications for multilingual identity, drawing upon both theoretical frameworks and empirical research to shed light on why and how individuals switch languages in different contexts.

Literature Review

Scholars in sociolinguistics and psycholinguistics have long been intrigued by code-switching. Early work by Gumperz (1982) laid the foundation for understanding how conversational cues and social contexts can trigger language alternation. More recent studies have expanded on this view by incorporating cognitive and identity-based perspectives. For instance, Myers-Scotton's (1993) Markedness Model suggests that code-switching is a strategic, context-dependent tool that speakers use to negotiate social identities. Similarly, Blom and Gumperz (1972) highlighted that code-switching can serve multiple communicative functions—ranging from emphasizing a point to signaling group membership.

The literature also underscores the role of cultural and situational factors. In multicultural societies, where speakers routinely navigate diverse linguistic environments, code-switching becomes an adaptive strategy to express nuanced cultural identities. Researchers like Auer (1998) have demonstrated that code-

switching is not random but is influenced by factors such as the topic of conversation, the relationship between speakers, and the power dynamics at play. This body of work collectively challenges the misconception that code-switching indicates a lack of proficiency in either language; instead, it is seen as evidence of a rich, dynamic linguistic repertoire.

Discussions

Multilingual identity is a multifaceted construct that encompasses linguistic, cultural, and social dimensions. For many speakers, the ability to switch codes fluidly is an integral part of how they express who they are. Code-switching allows individuals to navigate different social networks and cultural contexts, often aligning their language choice with the situational norms of each group. For instance, a bilingual individual might use one language at home with family members and switch to another in professional or academic settings. This dynamic alternation not only facilitates effective communication but also reinforces the individual's affiliation with distinct cultural communities. Moreover, code-switching can serve as a means of resistance or empowerment. In contexts where one language is socially dominant, switching to a minority language can be a way for speakers to assert their cultural heritage and challenge linguistic hegemony.

The cognitive processes underlying code-switching are equally fascinating. Research indicates that bilinguals exhibit enhanced executive control, which may be partially attributable to the mental juggling required when switching between languages. Neuroimaging studies suggest that areas of the brain involved in cognitive control and inhibition are more active in bilingual speakers, underscoring the complexity and sophistication of managing multiple language systems simultaneously.

Contexts and Functions of Code-Switching

Code-switching occurs across a variety of contexts, each with its own set of rules and expectations. In informal settings, such as conversations among friends, switching may occur fluidly and with little conscious effort. In contrast, formal environments like academic lectures or professional meetings often dictate stricter language boundaries, though code-switching can still occur strategically for emphasis or clarification. Several functions of code-switching have been identified in the literature. These include:

- **Expressive Function:** Enhancing the emotional or emphatic quality of communication. For example, a speaker might switch languages to convey a sentiment that is better expressed in one language over another.

- **Indexical Function:** Signaling the speaker's social or cultural identity. By switching codes, speakers may align themselves with a particular group or distance themselves from another.
- **Clarificatory Function:** Aiding comprehension by using a language that the interlocutor finds easier to understand, especially in multilingual interactions.
- **Topic Shifting:** Indicating a change in the subject matter or the conversational frame. Code-switching can mark the transition between different topics or discourse genres within a single conversation.

Understanding these functions provides insight into the strategic nature of code-switching. Rather than being a random or accidental behavior, switching is often a carefully calibrated choice that enhances communication, reinforces identity, and adapts to the social context.

Challenges and Implications

Despite its many advantages, code-switching is not without its challenges. In some social settings, it may be stigmatized as a sign of linguistic inadequacy or cultural dilution. Educational institutions, for instance, may discourage code-switching under the mistaken belief that it interferes with language learning. This can lead to policies that favor monolinguals, potentially marginalizing bilingual students and undermining their cultural identity.

Moreover, the rise of global communication platforms has led to new forms of code-switching, particularly in digital contexts. Social media, online forums, and virtual meetings often witness rapid, fluid switching between languages, sometimes leading to misunderstandings or misinterpretations when cultural nuances are lost in translation. These issues underscore the need for a deeper understanding of how code-switching functions in both face-to-face and digital interactions, and they highlight the importance of embracing multilingual practices as assets rather than liabilities.

Conclusion

Code-switching is a multifaceted phenomenon that lies at the intersection of language, culture, and identity. It enables bilingual and multilingual speakers to navigate complex social landscapes and express their multifarious identities. By analyzing the functions, contexts, and cognitive underpinnings of code-switching, this article has demonstrated that such language alternation is not a sign of deficiency but rather a sophisticated, adaptive strategy that reflects the dynamic nature of modern multilingual societies.

The implications of this research are significant for educators, policymakers, and linguists alike. Recognizing code-switching as a legitimate and valuable communicative tool can lead to more inclusive language policies and educational practices that support multilingualism. Future research should continue to explore the evolving patterns of code-switching in both traditional and digital domains, ensuring that the rich linguistic diversity of our global community is celebrated and preserved.

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Annotatsiya. Akademik Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov o'zbek tilshunosligining turli xil muammolari bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borgan keng qamrovli olimdir. U folklor asarlari va badiiy asar tilining lingvopoetik xususiyatlari, hozirgi o'zbek tili, dialektologiya, leksikologiya, leksikografiya, fonetika, orfografiya (imlo) va punktuatsiyaning dolzarb muammolari bo'yicha ko'plab ilmiy maqola, risola, lug'at va monografiyalar nashr ettirgan. Maqolada olim ilmiy-pedagogik faoliyatining qirralaridan bo'lgan ishlaridan biri "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili" darsligi xususida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili, undov, taqlid, yordamchi, ko'makchi, bog'lovchi, kelishik.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili fonetikasi, morfologiyasi va leksikasiga oid yirik ilmiy tadqiqotlarning muallifidir. Xususan, "O'zbek tilida yordamchi so'zlar" (1953), "O'zbek tilida o'zak strukturasi ba'zi masalalariga doir" (1965), "O'zbek tilida yuklamalar" (1971), "O'zbek adabiy tilining leksik normalari" (1973) kabi maqolalari, shuningdek, "Hozirgi zamon o'zbek tili" (1957), "O'zbek tili grammatikasi. I jild. Morfologiya" (1975), "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili" (1980) singari hammualliflikda bajarilgan ilmiy ishlari masalaga keng qamrovli yondashilganligi, nazariy xulosalarining pishiqligi bilan ajralib turadi.

1980-yilda oliy o'quv yurtlarining filologiya fakultetlari uchun tuzilgan "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili" darsligining hammualliflaridan bo'lgan Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov ushbu kitobning "Yordamchi so'zlar", "Undov", "Taqlid so'z" qismlarini yozib berdi. [1]

Darslikning "Yordamchi so'zlar" bo'limidan ko'makchi, bog'lovchi va yuklamaga oid mavzular o'rin olgan. Mavzu ko'makchiga ta'rif berish bilan boshlanadi. So'ng ko'makchilar ikki turga: Hozirgi o'zbek tilida mustaqil ma'nosini butunlay yo'qotgan (*uchun, sari, bilan, qadar* kabi) so'zlar va ko'makchi vazifasida qo'llanuvchi (*tomon, boshqa, sababli, orqali, tufayli, uzra* kabi) so'zlarga ajratiladi.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov so'ng ko'makchilarni ularning kelishiklar bilan bo'lgan munosabatiga ko'ra quyidagi uch guruhga ajratadi:

- 1) bosh kelishikdagi ot va qaratqich kelishigidagi olmoshlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilar;
- 2) jo'nalish kelishigidagi so'zlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilar;
- 3) chiqish kelishigidagi so'zlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilar.

So'ngra bu uch turdagi ko'makchilarning har biri ustida alohida to'xtalib o'tiladi.

1. Bosh kelishikdagi ot va qaratqich kelishigidagi olmoshlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilardan *bilan, uchun, kabi, singari, yanglig', sayin, sari, sababli, orqali, tufayli, osha, bo'ylab, bo'yicha, uzra, ichra, degan / deydigan, bo'yi, chamasi, haqda / to'g'rida, haqida / to'g'risida, holda / yo'sinda* kabilari ustida to'xtalib, ularning qo'llanish o'rinlari va holatlari birma-bir bayon qilib berilgan. Har bir holat uchun alohida-alohida misollar keltiriladi. Masalan, *bilan* ko'makchisining turli holatlardagi qo'llanishlaridan o'n uchta holatni keltirib, ularning har biri uchun turli badiiy asarlardan o'rinli misollar berilgan. Xuddi shunga o'xshash *uchun* ko'makchisining to'rt holatdagi, *sayin* ko'makchisining uch holatdagi qo'llanishlari haqida to'xtab o'tilgan.

Ayrim ko'makchilarning boshqa ko'makchilar bilan, shuningdek, kelishiklarning affikslari bilan sinonim bo'la olishiga misollar keltirilgan. Masalan, Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov *orqali* ko'makchisini ta'riflar ekan, shunday deydi: "Shu ma'noda *orqali* ko'makchisi *bilan* va o'rin-payt kelishigi affiksi *-da* li konstruksiyalarga sinonim bo'lishi mumkin. Qiyos qiling: *pochta orqali jo'natdim – pochta bilan jo'natdim – pochta jo'natdim*". [1: 410]

So'ng Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov jo'nalish kelishigidagi so'zlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilarni tavsiflaydi. Bu turga quyidagi ko'makchilarni kiritadi: *tomon, qadar, ko'ra, qarshi, qarab, qaraganda, qaramasdan, qaramay, yarasha, doir, asosan, binoan, muvofiq, qarata*.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov bu ko'makchilarni tavsiflar ekan, ularning qaysi ko'makchi bilan sinonim bo'la olishini alohida ta'kidlaydi va shunga mos misol keltiradi. Masalan, *qaraganda* ko'makchisi o'rnida *ko'ra* ko'makchisi kelishi mumkinligini (olmaga qaraganda nok shirin – olmadan ko'ra nok shirin), *binoan* ko'makchisiga *ko'ra, asosan* ko'makchilari sinonim bo'la olishini (talablariga binoan – talablariga ko'ra – talablariga asosan) qayd qilib o'tadi. [1: 414-415]

So'ng chiqish kelishigidagi so'zlar bilan qo'llanadigan ko'makchilar tasnifi keladi. Bu o'rinda chiqish kelishigidagi so'zlar bilan qo'llanadigan *so'ng, keyin, boshqa, tashqari, bo'lak, o'zga, beri, buyon, nari // nariga, burun, ilgari, boshlab, tortib* ko'makchilarining qo'llanish holatlari izohlanadi. Bu yerda o'zaro sinonim bo'lgan, mustasnoqlik ma'nosini ifodalaydigan *boshqa, tashqari, bo'lak, o'zga* ko'makchilari, shuningdek, *beri* va *buyon* ko'makchilari, *burun* va *ilgari* ko'makchilari hamda *boshlab* va *tortib* ko'makchilari alohida-alohida holda ta'riflanadi.

Ko'makchilar mavzusi yakunlangach, ko'makchi otlar mavzusi keladi. Dastlab ko'makchi otlarga shunday ta'rif beriladi: "Ko'makchi otlar o'zlarining leksik ma'nolarini saqlagan mustaqil so'zlar bo'lishiga qaramay, yordamchi so'zlar kabi gapda turli munosabatlarni ham bildirib keladi. [1: 418]

So'ng ko'makchi otlar tarkibiga *ost, tag, ust, old, orqa, ich, tomon, o'rta, ora, bosh, yon* so'zlarining qo'llanish holatlari haqida so'z yuritilib, har biri uchun badiiy asarlardan mos misollar keltiriladi.

Navbatdagi mavzu yordamchi so'zlar tarkibiga kiruvchi bog'lovchilar mavzusidir. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov bu mavzu boshida bog'lovchilarga qisqacha ta'rif beradi va ularning tarkibiga ko'ra yakka va takroriy bog'lovchilarga bo'linishini aytadi. Takroriy bog'lovchilarning bir qismi yakka holda ham qo'llanishi mumkinligini (*yo, yoki*), bu holda ular yakka bog'lovchi hisoblanishini ta'kidlaydi. Takroriy bog'lovchilarning ayrimlari faqat takrorlangandagina bog'lovchi bo'lishini, yakka holda qo'llanganda esa o'zi mansub bo'lgan so'z turkumiga taalluqli bo'lishini aytib o'tadi (*bir – son; ham – yuklama; ba'zan – ravish*).

So'ng gapdagi vazifasiga ko'ra bog'lovchilar teng va ergashtiruvchi bog'lovchilarga bo'linishi aytiladi.

Teng bog'lovchilarni Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov biriktiruvchi, zidlovchi va ayiruvchi bog'lovchilarga ajratadi hamda ularning har biriga ta'rif beradi. Bu o'rinda olim *va* bog'lovchisining qo'llanish o'rinlariga keng to'xtaladi. Ushbu bog'lovchi ayrim gaplarni va gapdagi uyushiq bo'laklarni teng munosabat asosida bog'lashi ta'kidlab o'tiladi. Ba'zan *va* bog'lovchisi o'rnida *-u (-yu)* yuklamasi kelib, uyushgan bo'laklarni bog'lashi aytiladi (*Yer-u ko'kni qizdirar quyosh*). Ba'zan ketma-ket bajarilgan ish-harakatni bir-biriga bog'lovchi *va* bog'lovchisi o'rnida *-da* yuklamasi qo'llanadi (*Nasimjon o'rnidan turdi-da, eshik tomon yurdi*).

Keyin zidlovchi bog'lovchilar mavzusi keladi. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov zidlovchi bog'lovchilarga qisqacha ta'rif bergach, *lekin, ammo, biroq, holbuki, balki* kabi bog'lovchilarning qo'llanish holatlarini birma-bir aytib o'tadi.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov "a" bog'lovchisi haqida shunday yozadi: "O'zbek adabiy tili uchun norma darajasiga ko'tarilmagan bo'lishiga qaramay, "a" bog'lovchisi badiiy adabiyot tilida uchramoqda. Bu bog'lovchi sodda yoki qo'shma gaplarni bog'lab, ular orasidagi zid munosabatni ifodalaydi (*Qovun tanlashda didim yo'q. A siz-chi?*)" (Oybek). [1: 430]

Bu fikr, bizningcha, munozarali. "A" bog'lovchisi rus tilidagi zidlov bog'lovchisi bo'lib, ayrim badiiy asarlarda va so'zlashuv nutqida rus tili ta'sirida

qisqa vaqt ishlatilib turildi. Bugungi kunda bu bog'lovchi iste'moldan deyarli chiqib ketdi.

Teng bog'lovchilardan keyin ergashtiruvchi bog'lovchilar mavzusi keladi. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov bu mavzu boshida ergashtiruvchi bog'lovchilarga qisqacha ta'rif beradi, ya'ni ularning asosan ergashgan qo'shma gap tarkibidagi ergash gaplarni bosh gapga bog'lash uchun ishlatilishini aytadi. So'ng qo'shma gap tarkibidagi gaplar orasidagi turli munosabatlarni bildirishiga ko'ra ularni quyidagi guruhlariga bo'ladi:

1. Aniqlov bog'lovchilari: *ya'ni, -ki, -kim.*
2. Sabab bog'lovchilari: *chunki, shuning uchun.*
3. Shart bog'lovchilari: *agar, agarda, basharti, agarchi.*
4. Chog'ishtiruv bog'lovchilari: *go'yo, go'yoki.*

So'ng bu bog'lovchilarning har biriga to'xtalib, ularning qo'llanish o'rinlarini izohlaydi, badiiy asarlardan misollar keltiradi.

Navbatdagi mavzu yuklama mavzusidir. Bu yerda ham dastavval yuklamaga ta'rif beriladi. So'ng ular tuzilishiga ko'ra ikki xil bo'lishi (yuklama-affiks, yuklama-so'z) aytib o'tiladi. Yuklamalar gapga quyidagi qo'shimcha ma'nolarni beradi:

- 1) Nutqdagi biror so'zni ajratib ko'rsatadi: Elektr ko'zlagina emas, qo'lga ham yordam beradi;
- 2) gapga so'roq ma'nosi beradi;
- 3) his-hayajonni ifodalaydi;
- 4) taajjubni ifodalash uchun;
- 5) ta'kid va kuchaytirish ma'nolarini ifodalaydi.

So'ng har bir guruhga kiruvchi yuklamalar alohida-alohida izohlanadi va qo'llanish holatiga misollar keltiriladi.

Keyin "Undov" mavzusi keladi. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov avval undovga qisqacha ta'rif beradi. Ularning leksik ma'noga ega emasligi, shuning uchun gap bo'laklari bilan sintaktik aloqaga kirishmasligi va gapning biror bo'lagi bo'la olmasligi ta'kidlanadi. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov undovlarni ma'nosiga ko'ra emotsional va buyruq-xitob undovlariga ajratadi. Undovlar bir tovush bilan yoki ikki va undan ortiq tovushlar birikmasi bilan ham ifodalanishi mumkinligini aytadi.

Darslikdagi oxirgi mavzu taqlid so'zlar mavzusidir. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov dastavval taqlid so'zlarga qisqa va aniq ta'rif beradi. Tovushga taqlid so'zlar eshitish bilan, obrazga taqlid so'zlar esa ko'rish bilan aloqadorligi ta'kidlanadi. Shunga ko'ra taqlid so'zlar ikki guruhga bo'linadi:

- 1) tovushga taqlid so'zlar;

2) obraz (tasvir)ga taqlid so'zlar.

1. Tovushga taqlid so'zlar tabiatda uchraydigan turli tovushlarga yoki insonning turli holati va kayfiyati tufayli sodir bo'ladigan tovushlarga yoki biror hayvonning tovushiga taqlidan yasaladi.

2. Obraz (tasvir)ga taqlid so'zlar ko'rish mumkin bo'lgan harakat yoki holat obrazini (tasvirini) ifodalaydi. Bu tur taqlid so'zlar yakka yoki takroriy qo'llanishi mumkin. Yakka qo'llanganda lahzalik holat yoki harakat tasvirini, takroriy qo'llanganda esa bir me'yorda qaytarilib turgan holat yoki harakat tasvirini ifodalaydi.

“Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili” darsligining “Morfoloqiya” bo'limida akademik Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov tomonidan yozilgan qismlar mavzuni to'liq qamrab olishi, talabaga tushunarli tarzda bayon etilishi, keltirilgan misollarning sodda va qoidaga muvofiqligi bilan alohida ajralib turadi.

Ushbu darslik uzoq yillar mobaynida mamlakatimiz oliy o'quv yurtlari filologiya fakulteti talabalarining asosiy adabiyotlari qatoridan o'rin olib keldi.

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ANALYSIS OF MYTHOLOGICAL ELEMENTS IN TOLKIEN'S WORK "LORD OF THE RINGS: THE TWO TOWERS" AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN EXPLORING THE AUTHOR'S CONCEPTUAL SYSTEM

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the mythological elements in J.R.R. Tolkien's The Two Towers, the second volume of The Lord of the Rings trilogy. By examining the influence of Norse, Celtic, and Classical myths, the study explores how Tolkien integrates these traditions into his narrative to enrich themes of heroism, sacrifice, and the struggle between good and evil. Using theoretical frameworks such as Campbell's monomyth and Jung's archetypes, the analysis highlights the significance of mythological motifs and their impact on character development and thematic depth. This comprehensive examination contributes to a deeper understanding of Tolkien's literary artistry and the universal appeal of his storytelling.*

Keywords: *Tolkien, mythology, The Two Towers, hero's journey, archetypes, Norse mythology, Celtic mythology, Classical mythology*

INTRODUCTION

J.R.R. Tolkien's *The Two Towers*, the second volume of his epic trilogy *The Lord of the Rings*, is a text rich with mythological elements. This work, much like the entire trilogy, draws heavily on a wide array of mythological traditions, weaving them into its complex narrative structure. The incorporation of these elements not only enriches the story but also provides a profound depth to its themes and characters. Understanding these mythological references is crucial for a comprehensive appreciation of Tolkien's literary artistry. Tolkien, a philologist and a scholar of mythology, was profoundly influenced by various mythological traditions, including Norse, Celtic, and Classical myths. His academic background and personal interests are reflected in his writing, which is imbued with mythological motifs and archetypes. *The Two Towers* continues the journey of the Fellowship of the Ring, now divided into different paths, and explores themes of heroism, sacrifice, and the struggle between good and evil, all of which are framed within a mythological context.

The study of mythological elements in Tolkien's work is not new; scholars have long recognized the profound impact of myth on his storytelling. However, *The Two Towers* presents a unique opportunity to explore these elements in a context that is both transitional and climactic. This volume is where the narrative threads begin to

weave more intricately, setting the stage for the final confrontation in *The Return of the King*. Analyzing the mythological elements in *The Two Towers* allows us to see how Tolkien uses myth to build suspense, develop characters, and enhance the thematic depth of his story. This article aims to provide a detailed analysis of the mythological elements in *The Two Towers*. By examining specific mythological motifs, characters, and themes, we can gain a better understanding of how Tolkien integrates these elements into his narrative. This analysis will also consider the broader implications of these mythological references, exploring how they contribute to the overall meaning and impact of the text.

The methodology for this analysis will involve a close reading of the text, supported by secondary sources from the field of literary and mythological studies. This approach will allow for a comprehensive examination of the mythological elements in *The Two Towers* and their significance within the broader context of Tolkien's work. By situating these elements within the rich tapestry of mythological traditions, we can appreciate the complexity and depth of Tolkien's storytelling. In the following sections, we will first review the existing literature on Tolkien's use of mythological elements, providing a foundation for our analysis. We will then outline the methodology used to analyze these elements in *The Two Towers*. The results and discussion section will present our findings, exploring the various mythological motifs and their significance within the narrative. Finally, we will conclude with a summary of our findings and their implications for our understanding of Tolkien's work. By examining the mythological elements in *The Two Towers*, this article aims to contribute to the ongoing scholarly discussion of Tolkien's use of myth in his writing. Through a detailed analysis of these elements, we can gain a deeper appreciation of Tolkien's literary artistry and the profound impact of myth on his storytelling.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tolkien's incorporation of mythological elements in his work has been the subject of extensive scholarly discussion. Scholars such as Tom Shippey and Verlyn Flieger have explored the ways in which Tolkien draws on mythological traditions to create a rich and immersive narrative world. Shippey, in particular, has highlighted the influence of Norse mythology on Tolkien's work, noting the similarities between characters such as Gandalf and the Norse god Odin [7]. Flieger, on the other hand, has focused on the use of light and dark imagery in Tolkien's work, exploring how these elements are rooted in mythological traditions [3].

Other scholars have examined the influence of Celtic mythology on Tolkien's work. John Garth, for example, has explored the connections between Tolkien's writing and Celtic mythological traditions, highlighting the influence of Welsh and Irish myths on his storytelling [5]. Similarly, Dimitra Fimi has examined the impact of Celtic mythology on Tolkien's creation of Middle-earth, noting the similarities between the landscapes of Middle-earth and those described in Celtic myths [4].

In addition to these specific mythological traditions, scholars have also explored the broader influence of Classical mythology on Tolkien's work. Elizabeth Solopova, for example, has examined the connections between Tolkien's writing and the myths of ancient Greece and Rome, highlighting the ways in which Tolkien incorporates elements of these myths into his narrative [8]. Similarly, Patrick Curry has explored the influence of Classical mythology on Tolkien's depiction of heroism and sacrifice, noting the similarities between characters such as Aragorn and classical heroes like Achilles and Aeneas [2]. The existing literature on Tolkien's use of mythological elements provides a solid foundation for our analysis of *The Two Towers*. By building on this scholarship, we can gain a deeper understanding of how Tolkien integrates mythological motifs and themes into his narrative. This literature review will serve as the basis for our methodology, guiding our close reading of the text and our analysis of its mythological elements.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this analysis will involve a close reading of *The Two Towers*, supported by secondary sources from the field of literary and mythological studies. This approach will allow for a comprehensive examination of the mythological elements in the text and their significance within the broader context of Tolkien's work. The first step in our analysis will be to identify specific mythological motifs and themes in *The Two Towers*. This will involve a careful reading of the text, with particular attention to characters, settings, and plot elements that reflect mythological traditions. We will also consider the broader context of Tolkien's work, examining how these elements fit within the overall narrative of *The Lord of the Rings*. Once we have identified the mythological elements in the text, we will analyze their significance within the narrative. This will involve examining how these elements contribute to the development of characters, the progression of the plot, and the exploration of themes such as heroism, sacrifice, and the struggle between good and evil. We will also consider how these elements enhance the overall impact of the story, creating a rich and immersive narrative world.

Our analysis will be supported by secondary sources from the field of literary and mythological studies. These sources will provide a theoretical framework for our analysis, allowing us to situate the mythological elements in *The Two Towers* within the broader context of mythological traditions. We will also draw on existing scholarship on Tolkien's use of myth, building on the work of scholars such as Shippey, Flieger, and Garth to develop our analysis. The results of our analysis will be presented in the following section, where we will explore the various mythological motifs and their significance within the narrative of *The Two Towers*. This will include a detailed examination of specific characters, settings, and plot elements, as well as a discussion of the broader thematic implications of these mythological references.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of our analysis will be presented in a detailed examination of the mythological elements in *The Two Towers*. This section will explore the various mythological motifs, characters, and themes present in the narrative, as well as their significance within the broader context of Tolkien's work. Our analysis has identified several key mythological motifs in *The Two Towers*. These include the hero's journey, the struggle between good and evil, and the concept of sacrifice. Each of these motifs is deeply rooted in mythological traditions and contributes to the thematic depth of the narrative. The hero's journey is a central motif in *The Two Towers*, with multiple characters undergoing their own journeys of self-discovery and transformation.

Frodo's journey to Mordor, for example, follows the stages of the hero's journey as outlined by Campbell (1949), including the call to adventure, the road of trials, and the ultimate confrontation with evil [1]. Similarly, Aragorn's journey as the rightful heir to the throne of Gondor mirrors the classical hero's quest for identity and destiny. The struggle between good and evil is a recurring theme in *The Two Towers*, reflecting the dualistic nature of many mythological traditions. This theme is embodied in the characters and their actions, as well as the broader conflict between the forces of Sauron and the free peoples of Middle-earth. The battle of Helm's Deep, for example, serves as a microcosm of this larger struggle, highlighting the courage and resilience of the characters in the face of overwhelming odds.

The concept of sacrifice is another key motif in *The Two Towers*, reflecting the mythological theme of the hero's willingness to give up something of great value for the greater good. This is seen in Frodo's journey to destroy the Ring, as well as in the actions of other characters such as Sam, who sacrifices his own safety and comfort to support Frodo. The theme of sacrifice underscores the moral and ethical dimensions of the narrative, highlighting the characters' commitment to their cause.

Our analysis also explores the characters in *The Two Towers* and their embodiment of mythological archetypes. Frodo, Gandalf, and Gollum, for example, each represent different aspects of the hero's journey and the struggle between good and evil.

Character Archetype Chart

Character	Archetype	Key Attributes
Frodo	The Hero	Journey, Trials, Internal Conflict with the Ring
Gandalf	Wise Old Man	Mentor, Guide, Death, and Rebirth
Gollum	The Shadow	Duality, Internal Struggle, Contrast with Frodo

Frodo embodies the archetype of the hero, undertaking a perilous journey to achieve a noble goal. His journey is marked by trials and challenges that test his resolve and character, reflecting the stages of the hero's journey as outlined by Campbell (1949). Frodo's struggle with the Ring and its corrupting influence also highlights the theme of internal conflict, a common element in mythological hero narratives. Gandalf represents the archetype of the wise old man, a figure who provides guidance and support to the hero. His wisdom and knowledge are essential to the success of the Fellowship, and his actions reflect the role of the mentor in the hero's journey. Gandalf's transformation from Gandalf the Grey to Gandalf the

White also mirrors the mythological theme of death and rebirth, underscoring his role as a pivotal figure in the narrative. Gollum embodies the archetype of the shadow, representing the darker aspects of the human psyche. His obsession with the Ring and his internal conflict between his Gollum and Sméagol personas reflect the theme of duality and the struggle between good and evil. Gollum's character serves as a foil to Frodo, highlighting the potential for corruption and the difficult choices the hero must make.

The mythological elements in *The Two Towers* have significant thematic implications, enhancing the depth and complexity of the narrative. By drawing on mythological traditions, Tolkien creates a story that resonates with universal themes and motifs, enriching the reader's experience and understanding of the text. The themes of heroism and sacrifice are central to *The Two Towers*, reflecting the mythological tradition of the hero's journey. The characters' willingness to face danger and make sacrifices for the greater good underscores the moral and ethical dimensions of the narrative, highlighting the importance of courage, honor, and duty.

The struggle between good and evil is a pervasive theme in *The Two Towers*, reflecting the dualistic nature of many mythological traditions. This theme is embodied in the characters and their actions, as well as the broader conflict between the forces of Sauron and the free peoples of Middle-earth. The battle of Helm's Deep, for example, serves as a microcosm of this larger struggle, highlighting the courage and resilience of the characters in the face of overwhelming odds. The power of myth is evident in *The Two Towers*, as Tolkien draws on a rich tapestry of mythological traditions to create a story that is both timeless and universal. By incorporating elements from Norse, Celtic, and Classical mythology, Tolkien creates a narrative that resonates with readers on a deep psychological level, reflecting universal themes and archetypes that are fundamental to the human experience.

CONCLUSION

This analysis of mythological elements in *The Two Towers* highlights the profound influence of myth on Tolkien's storytelling. By drawing on Norse, Celtic, and Classical myths, Tolkien creates a rich and immersive narrative world that is deeply rooted in a tradition of epic storytelling. The use of theoretical frameworks such as Campbell's monomyth and Jung's archetypes allows for a deeper understanding of the universal themes and motifs that underpin Tolkien's narrative. Through a detailed examination of the mythological motifs, characters, and themes in *The Two Towers*, this analysis contributes to the ongoing scholarly discussion of Tolkien's use of myth in his writing. By situating these elements within the broader

context of mythological traditions, we can appreciate the complexity and depth of Tolkien's literary artistry and the profound impact of myth on his storytelling. The mythological elements in *The Two Towers* not only enhance the narrative's thematic depth but also create a sense of timelessness and universality that resonates with readers. By exploring these elements, we gain a deeper appreciation of Tolkien's ability to weave myth into his storytelling, creating a narrative that is both deeply personal and universally significant.

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THE ROLE OF REYNOLD NICHOLSON AND JOHN ARBERRY'S TRANSLATION IN THE STUDY OF SUFI LITERATURE

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Annotation: *Sufi literature, with its deep mystical insights and rich poetic traditions, has been taking the attention of scholars not only from the eastern muslim countries but also western cultures, especially English scientists. Among the most influential scientists who mostly contributed to the translation of Sufi poems and texts into English are Reynold Nicholson and John Arberry. Their translations of many Sufi texts like the masterpieces of Rumi, Ibn Khaldun, Sa'di and others, are considered main sources of Sufi literature in western academia and mostly used by other scholars.*

This research deeply illustrate the role of Nicholson and Arberry's translations in shaping modern understanding of Sufi literature by using analytical and comparative research methods. By analyzing their translation strategies, scholarly impact and aims, is shows both strength and limitations of their contributions.

Key words: *Sufism, Sufi literature, mystics, mysticism, Persian and Arabic poetics, Rumi, Ibn Khaldun, Divine love, Sufi orders, translation studies.*

INTRODUCTION

The literature of Sufism has been prominent topic for several researches and discussions by western scholars in recent years. In this case, western culture need reliable sources of Sufi literature to learn the real value of Sufism and mysticism and achieve appropriate understanding, so it leads necessity to translate the Sufi texts into English from Persian and Arabic languages. While the works by poets and philosophers such as Jalal al-din Rumi, Ibn al-Arabi and Hujwiri, whose writings explore the themes of divine love and spiritual journey to the soul, have been captivating many scholars and spiritual seekers, scholars like Reynold Alleyne Nicholson and Arthur John Arberry have made a significant contribution to the translation of Sufi literature.

The article examines the role of Arthur John Arberry and Reynold Nicholson in translating and interpreting Sufi literature, particularly the works of Jalal al-Din Rumi and other Sufi poets. It focuses on how their translations influenced Western perceptions of Sufism and contributed to Islamic studies and the translation methodologies, the impact of their works on the study of Sufi poetry and Islamic mysticism.

Aim of the article is to analyze their in making Sufi literature accessible to the English-speaking world, to evaluate the accuracy and effectiveness of their translations in conveying the mystical and philosophical depth of Sufi poetry, to explore how their works shaped Western academic and literary engagement with Islamic mysticism.

METHODOLOGY.

The theme of this article is now calculated on topical issues in terms of study. Because the study of the Islamic Sufism in Western countries shows how much the interest in Sufi literature is spreading around the world and requires many research by scientists of the western countries. In this article, historical, analytical and comparative techniques are used in the collection and analysis of the data during the study. Sources are historically analyzed and studied by various scholars' thoughts and research areas by comparative methods. In addition to collecting materials, scientific articles and books are used.

RESULTS

Reynold Nicholson was one of the most influential scholars in western world who made a great contribution to the study and translation of Sufi literature, particularly from the works of Persian and Arabic mystics. His works such as 'The Mathnawi of Jalaluddin Rumi', 'Kashf al-Mahjub', and Faridu'ddin Attar's-Tadhkiratu'l-Awliya can be a clear example for this.

Another prominent scholar John Arberry was influenced met by Professor R. A. Nicholson with whom he remained on the closest terms until Nicholson's death in 1945. Through this influence Arberry's enduring interest in Sufism was emerged, leading to write books such as 'The history of Sufism' and a great series of translations of the works of Rumi—'Rubd'iydt', 'Discourses', 'Tales from the Masnavi', 'More tales from the Masnavi', and the first volume of 'The mystical poems'.

ANALYSIS

The role of Nicholson and Arberry's translations were so significant that many other researchers used their books to study the Sufi literature and do several scientific works. One of the well-known scholars of Sufi literature, William C. Chittick highly evaluated these translations:

'I had no knowledge of Persian, but much of his poetry was already available in English because of the prodigious efforts of the great British orientalist, R. A. Nicholson and A.J. Arberry'(William C. Chittick, 2005, p7)

By these words, it can be understood that Nicholson and Arberry was one of the first scientists who dealt with the translation and interpretation of Sufi texts. Furthermore, he emphasized their names when listing other translators:

‘Thanks to the translation of most of the works of Jalal al-Din Rumi into English from the eighteenth century to the present day by such scholars as Sir William Jones, E.H. Whinfield, J. Redhouse, and especially R.A. Nicholson and A.J. Arberry, followed in recent years by more popular American translations by Coleman Barks and others, this peerless Sufi poet and sage is now well known in the English-speaking world.’

DISCUSSION.

The literature of Islamic Sufism is unique theme that engaging many spiritual seekers by illustrating the orders of Islamic mysticism and shaping an appropriate understanding about it. As famous Sufi scholar Martin Lings said: ‘Sufism is nothing other than Islamic mysticism, which means that it is the central and most powerful current of that tidal wave which constitutes the Revelation of Islam’ (Martin Lings, 1975, p10). Therefore the translations of Arberry and Nicholson played an important role to spread this concept through the western culture while many scholars revealed the connection between Sufism and other spiritual philosophies in other religions. Nicholson also claimed about the significant influence of Sufism when translating Faridu'ddin Attar's-Tadhkiratu'l-Awliya: ‘Mysticism is so congenial to the Persian race, and its influence has been so great in almost every department of their life and thought, that some knowledge of the history and doctrines of the Sufis, as the Muhammadan mystics call themselves, is absolutely indispensable to the student of Persian literature.’ (R. Nicholson, 1905, p5). When it comes to the translation, their works serve as a bridge between the esoteric traditions of Islamic mysticism and Western academic and literary frameworks. Conceptually, their contributions can be analyzed through several interrelated perspectives such as saving the real meaning of the poem and its rhythm. It can be seen from this translation of Rumi's poem called ‘Song of the Reed’ by John Arberry:

The sound of the reed comes from fire, not wind

What use is one's life without this fire?

It is the fire of love that brings music to the reed.

It is the ferment of love that gives taste to the wine.

Their translations were instrumental in making Islamic mysticism more palatable to a Western audience, sometimes emphasizing its universal, humanistic

aspects while downplaying its deeply Islamic theological roots. Nicholson's translation of the poem by Hafiz supported this idea:

A Paradise of pleasure
Bought with a world of pain —
Fie on the luckless treasure
That I must bleed to gain!

At this point it is clear that Nicholson and Arberry's translations played a foundational role in shaping how Sufism is perceived in the West by emphasizing the poetic and spiritual aspects of Sufism, their translations contributed to the popularization of Rumi and other mystics in American and European countries. This, in turn, influenced later Western interpreters, such as Coleman Barks, and William C. Chittick who adapted Rumi's work into free-verse poetry, Hafiz, Ibn al-Arabi and other mystics.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the topic of mysticism today is one of the controversial issues among English researchers, and hundreds of works and scientific articles on scientists working in this direction can be found. In this article, scientists namely, Reynold Nicholson and John Arberry who engaged mystic literature and their research results were discussed and analyzed. The services and role of these scientists is invaluable in the study of mysticism, which is becoming a mediator to spread the literature of mysticism in the West. They also acute a strong bridge between the scientific works and articles and Western culture of Sufi literature and Western culture. The results of the study show that further researches can be done on this topic, besides the work of the above scientists, the works of other several scholars can be studied.

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TEACHING CROSS CULTURAL COMPETENCE TO EFL LEARNERS

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Abstract: *In an increasingly interconnected world, cross-cultural competence has become essential for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. This article explores effective methods for integrating cross-cultural competence into EFL instruction, emphasizing the importance of preparing students for real-world intercultural communication. A task-based learning approach, combined with the use of authentic materials such as videos, articles, and case studies, was implemented in a classroom setting. These materials exposed learners to diverse cultural norms and practices while reinforcing language skills. The study found that students not only became more engaged with cultural themes but also demonstrated significant improvement in navigating intercultural communication. They developed a deeper understanding of cultural differences, which is crucial for avoiding misunderstandings in global contexts. The findings suggest that cross-cultural competence should be a core component of EFL education, and recommendations for teachers on how to incorporate these elements into their curricula are provided.*

Keywords: *cross-cultural competence, task-based learning, intercultural communication, language teaching, authentic materials, cultural awareness, intercultural competence.*

INTRODUCTION

English serves as the global lingua franca, making it a vital tool for cross-cultural communication. For EFL learners, it is crucial to not only develop language proficiency but also gain an understanding of cultural differences to engage effectively in diverse international settings. Cross-cultural competence enables individuals to interpret cultural signals, navigate potential miscommunications, and foster meaningful interactions with people from various cultural backgrounds.

However, traditional EFL curricula often focus primarily on linguistic skills, such as grammar and vocabulary, without giving enough attention to cultural knowledge. This lack of emphasis on culture can hinder students when they encounter the subtle cultural nuances that influence communication. This article investigates how cross-cultural competence can be systematically incorporated into EFL instruction to better prepare students for real-world intercultural interactions.

The primary instructional method used in this study was task-based learning, which involved the creation of real-life scenarios where learners had to navigate cross-cultural situations. Tasks included role-playing conversations between individuals from different cultural backgrounds, analyzing case studies on cultural misunderstandings, and group discussions on international news events that required cultural interpretation.

Students' cross-cultural competence was assessed through reflective essays, oral presentations, and group projects. In their reflective essays, learners were asked to describe how their understanding of specific cultural norms had changed over the course of the tasks. Oral presentations focused on analyzing cultural differences, while group projects encouraged students to propose solutions to hypothetical intercultural misunderstandings.

To enhance cross-cultural competence in EFL learners, it is recommended that teachers:

- Incorporate a variety of authentic materials, such as videos, podcasts, and articles, that expose learners to different cultural perspectives.
- Use task-based activities that mimic real-life intercultural interactions.
- Foster an open and respectful classroom environment where cultural differences can be discussed without fear of judgment.
- Provide ongoing professional development for teachers to enhance their ability to teach cross-cultural competence effectively.

DISCUSSIONS

Cross-cultural competence is defined as the ability to understand, communicate, and interact effectively with people from diverse cultural backgrounds. Scholars like Byram (1997) have argued that language learning is inseparable from cultural learning. Byram's model of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) emphasizes that language learners must not only develop linguistic proficiency but also the skills and attitudes necessary to engage with other cultures. This model has been influential in shaping the integration of cultural components in language teaching, advocating for the development of both knowledge of other cultures and the ability to reflect on one's own cultural identity.

Furthermore, Kramersch (1993) introduced the concept of "third space," where language learners navigate between their own culture and the target culture. Kramersch argues that the process of learning a new language involves both linguistic competence and an ability to interpret and mediate between cultures. This third space becomes crucial as learners move beyond the surface-level features of language, such as grammar and vocabulary, and engage with deeper cultural norms, values, and beliefs.

Task-based learning (TBL) is a pedagogical approach that has gained prominence in language teaching, with its focus on using real-world tasks as the primary vehicle for language instruction. Ellis (2003) and Willis & Willis (2007) highlight that TBL emphasizes meaningful communication and the use of language in

authentic contexts. This approach is particularly well-suited to teaching cross-cultural competence, as tasks can be designed to simulate intercultural interactions.

For example, in a TBL framework, learners can role-play scenarios where they must navigate cultural differences, such as business meetings or social events with people from different cultural backgrounds. Studies by Dörnyei (2001) and Nunan (2004) support the idea that task-based activities not only enhance language proficiency but also promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills, both of which are essential in cross-cultural communication.

Using authentic materials, such as films, news articles, and interviews, has long been advocated as a means of exposing EFL learners to real-life language use and cultural norms (Gilmore, 2007). According to Peacock (1997), authentic materials help bridge the gap between the classroom and the outside world, providing learners with cultural insights that are difficult to capture through textbooks.

Culturally rich materials, such as TED Talks or YouTube videos from diverse regions, allow students to hear different accents, intonations, and cultural references, thereby developing their cross-cultural competence. In fact, scholars like Mishan (2005) argue that exposure to authentic materials is essential in fostering both linguistic proficiency and cultural awareness, as learners are more likely to encounter varied cultural norms in real-world communication.

Despite its importance, integrating cross-cultural competence into EFL instruction presents certain challenges. Sercu (2005) points out that teachers often struggle with incorporating cultural elements into their lessons, as cultural content can be seen as secondary to language instruction. Additionally, the complexity of cultural concepts, such as Hofstede's (1980) cultural dimensions theory, can make it difficult for learners to fully grasp abstract ideas like individualism versus collectivism or high-context versus low-context communication.

Some educators may also face resistance from students when discussing sensitive cultural topics, as these discussions may provoke discomfort or challenge learners' preconceived beliefs. Researchers like Holliday (2010) caution that teachers must carefully navigate discussions on culture to avoid reinforcing stereotypes or perpetuating cultural biases.

The literature emphasizes that cross-cultural competence is a critical component of EFL teaching, with scholars agreeing that language cannot be separated from culture. The integration of task-based learning and authentic materials provides a practical framework for developing cross-cultural awareness. However, challenges such as the complexity of cultural concepts and the potential discomfort in discussing

sensitive topics must be addressed. As more research focuses on this area, it becomes increasingly clear that fostering cross-cultural competence should be a priority in EFL classrooms to better prepare learners for real-world communication.

Cross-cultural competence is a crucial skill for EFL learners in today's interconnected world. By integrating culturally relevant, task-based activities into EFL lessons, educators can help learners navigate intercultural communication more effectively. This study highlights the benefits of combining language learning with cultural awareness, ultimately preparing students for real-world global interactions.

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NEOLOGIZMLAR O'RGANILISHINING ILMIY-NAZARIY TADQIQI

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***Annotatsiya.** Mazkur maqola neologizmlarning ilmiy-nazariy tadqiqiga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, uning zamonaviy til tizimida tutgan o'rni va rivojlanish dinamikasi tahlil qilingan. Neologizmlar lingvistik birlik sifatida nafaqat yangi tushunchalarni nomlash, balki madaniy va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarni aks ettirish vositasi ekanligi ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Tadqiqot davomida neologizmlarning lug'aviy boylikni kengaytirishdagi roli, ularning turlari va shakllanish usullari muhokama qilingan. Jahon va o'zbek tilshunosligida neologizmlarni o'rganishga oid nazariy yondashuvlar, yetuk olimlarning fikrlari va zamonaviy neologizmlarning tasnifi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Xususan, shakliy, fonologik, semantik, uslubiy, funksional va texnologik neologizmlar kabi turlari batafsil ko'rib chiqilgan. Ushbu maqola zamonaviy lingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan neologizmlarning ahamiyatini ilmiy asosda yoritish va ularni tizimli ravishda tahlil qilishga qaratilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** neologizm, innovatsiya, yangi leksema, leksik birlik, semantik o'zgarish, til tizimi, lug'aviy boylik, fonologik birlik, madaniy rivojlanish, ijtimoiy jarayonlar, muallif neologizmlari.*

Neologizmlar zamonaviy tilning dinamik rivojlanishini aks ettiruvchi hodisa sifatida tilshunoslikda alohida ahamiyatga ega. Ular yangi tushunchalarni nomlash, madaniy va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarni ifodalash vositasi sifatida til tizimining boyishi va o'zgarishlariga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda yangi leksik birliklarni tasvirlash uchun bir-biriga yaqin ma'no va mazmunga ega bir nechta terminlar qo'llaniladi: *neologizm, innovatsiya va yangi hosila* [1]. Ushbu atamalardan eng keng qo'llaniladigani "neologism" hisoblanadi. "Innovatsiya" termini odatda tilning barcha darajalarida yuzaga keladigan yangi hodisalarga nisbatan ishlatiladi. "Yangi hosila" atamasi esa ikki xil talqinda qo'llaniladi: tilning barcha darajadagi innovatsiyalariga yoki faqat so'z yasalihi orqali hosil bo'lgan yangi birliklarga, ya'ni nominativ neologizmlarga nisbatan. Keng ma'noda "innovatsiya" va "yangi hosila" atamalari tilning barcha darajadagi innovatsiyalarini qamrab olsa, "neologism" termini nafaqat leksik yangi hosilalarni, balki boshqa tillardan o'zlashgan va yangi ma'no kasb etgan birliklarni ham o'z ichiga oladi [2].

Neologizm – (yunoncha. "neos"- yangi, logos- so'z) jamiyatning dinamik rivojlanishi va tobora murakkablashib borayotgan hayot ehtiyojlari natijasida vujudga keladigan yangi tushunchalar va hodisalarni nomlashga xizmat qiluvchi yangi so'zlardir. Ularning yangilik xususiyati dastlabki paytlarda sezilarli bo'lsa-da, vaqt o'tishi bilan tillar tarkibiga kirib, odatdagi so'zlar qatoriga qo'shiladi va o'zining o'ziga xos yangilik darajasini yo'qotadi. Neologizmlar jamiyat va kundalik hayotning

barcha sohalarida keng tarqalgan bo'lib, texnologiya rivojlanishi bilan ularning soni va qo'llanilish doirasi tobora kengayib bormoqda.

Tilshunoslarning fikricha, tilning lug'aviy tarkibi doimiy ravishda yangilanib va rivojlanib boradi. Ushbu jarayon, asosan, tashqi muhit omillari bilan uzviy bog'liq. Lug'at tarkibining boyib borishi ham tashqi (ekstralingvistik), ham ichki (intralingvistik) omillar natijasida shakllanadi. Xususan, ingliz tilida yangi so'z va iboralar muntazam ravishda paydo bo'lib, uning lug'aviy tizimini yangilaydi. Jahon miqyosida bir qator olimlar, xususan, J. Algeo, I. Plag, P. A. Neumark, J. Warambo, A. Metcalf va boshqalar neologizmlarning kelib chiqish omillari, klassifikatsiyasi hamda yasaliş usullarini tadqiq etishgan. R. Mvoriya neologizmlar haqida to'liq va batafsil quyidagicha ta'rif bergan: "Neologizmlar – bu jamiyat hayoti, madaniyat va texnologiyadagi yangi rivojlanishlar tufayli tilga kirib kelgan yangi so'zlar yoki so'z birikmalaridir" [3]. Neologizmlar nafaqat yangi paydo bo'lgan leksik birliklar, balki mavjud bo'lgan so'zlarning yangi nom bilan atalishi hamda morfologik jihatdan yasalgan nominativ birliklar ham aslida yangi leksik birliklar hisoblanadi. J. Algeo neologizmlarni shaklan yangi paydo bo'lgan til birligi yoxud izohli lug'atda aks etmagan leksik birliklar deb ta'kidlab o'tgan [4].

Neologizmlar nafaqat jahon miqyosida balki rus olimlarining ham nazariyalarida o'z aksini topgan, xususan, O. S. Axmanova, T. V. Matveeva, Y. S. Bugrisheva, T. V. Jerebilo, T. V. Popova va shu kabi boshqa tilshunoslarning tadqiqot ishlari neologizmlarning chuqur tahlil etilishiga zamin bo'ladi desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi.

Chunonchi, O. S. Axmanovanning fikricha, "neologism – bu yangi predmet, voqea yoki hodisani belgilashda yoxud yangi tushunchani ifodalash uchun yaratilgan so'z yoki ibora" [5]. Neologizmlar turli tilshunoslar tomonidan turlicha talqin etilib hali hanuz aniq ta'rif va tasnifga ega emas biroq, neologizmlarning neologik xususiyatini namoyon etuvchi uch parametr ya'ni, til maydoni, vaqt hamda til birlining mavjudligi dalillangan [6]. Y. S. Bugrisheva "neologizmlarning strukturaviy yasaliş xususiyatlarini morfologik, sintaktik-morfologik, semantik-morfologik va metaforaga asoslangan semantik derivatsiya usullari yordamida hosil bo'lishi"ni ochiqlab bergan [7]. Ushbu klassifikatsiyaning asosida T. V. Jerebilo tomonidan taklif etilgan neologizmlar tipologiyasi yotadi, u yangi leksik birliklarni "mualliflik yoki individual-stilistik, leksik, semantik va o'ziga xos leksik neologizmlar" ga ajratib ko'rsatgan.

Jahon tilshunosligida "neologizm" tushunchasi keng ma'noda talqin qilinib, turli lingvistik nuqtai nazarlardan o'rganilganligini guvohi bo'ldik. O'zbek tilshunosligida esa "neologizm" ko'pincha, "yangi leksema" atamasiga sinonim sifatida qabul

qilinib, u leksikologiyaning kichik tarmog'i sifatida tadqiq qilinadi. Bu yondashuv neologizmlarni tilning lug'aviy tarkibidagi o'zgarishlarni o'rganish jarayonida ahamiyatli obyekt sifatida belgilaydi.

O'zbek tilshunosligida leksikologiya sohasiga oid tadqiqotlar I. Rasulov, A. Shomaqsudov, R. Qo'ng'urov, Sh. Rahmatullayev, A. Hojiyev kabi olimlarning ilmiy ishlari orqali asos solingan. Keyinchalik, ushbu yo'nalish M. Yo'ldoshev, S. Karimov va R. Sayfullayeva, U. Qo'ziyev tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda yanada rivojlantirilib, yangi ilmiy yondashuvlar bilan boyitilgan [8]. Shuningdek, neologizmlarni ilmiy tadqiq etgan olimlardan To'lqin Asadov va Sarvinoz Mardonova tomonidan talqin etilgan "O'zbek tilida faol so'z yasalishi va muallif neologizmlari" [9] monografiyasi ushbu atamaning bugungi ijtimoiy va ilmiy faoliyatda nechog'lik muhim ekanligining dalili desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Ushbu tadqiqotchi olimlar o'z ilmiy ishlarida neologizm atamasiga turli xil yondashuvlar asosida ta'riflar berib o'tishgan. Xususan, tilshunos olim Sh. Rahmatullayevning ta'kidlashicha, "neologizm o'ta nisbiy tushuncha bo'lib, uni doimiy ravishda ilmiy tadqiq qilish zarur. Vaqt o'tishi bilan neologizmlar o'zining yangilik xususiyatini yo'qotadi, xuddi shuningdek, mavzu bo'yicha keltirilgan misollar ham yangilik sifatidan mahrum bo'lib boradi. Biroq, ma'lum davrda tadqiq qilingan neologizmlar haqidagi ilmiy asoslar asta-sekin biror leksemaning leksik-semantik o'ziga xosliklari, kelib chiqishi va rivojlanish jarayonlariga oid tahlillarga asoslangan bilimlarga aylanadi" [10]. H. Ne'matov o'zbek tilshunosligida leksemalarning yasalishini ilmiy asoslagan holda, "so'z yasash qolipi", "yasalgan so'z" va "yasama so'z" tushunchalarini farqlashning ahamiyatini ta'kidlab o'tgan hamda ularning til tizimi va nutq faoliyatida tutgan o'rni bo'yicha asosli fikrlarni bayon qilgan [11]. N. Uluqov ushbu hodisaga chuqurroq yondashgan holda, "neologizmlar — bu til tizimida yangi hosil qilingan, boshqa tillardan kirib kelgan yoki yangilik xususiyati yaqqol sezilib turadigan, qo'llanish darajasiga ko'ra nafaol hisoblangan so'z va birikmalardir" [12] - deya tavsiflab o'tadi. U. Tursunovning fikricha, neologizmlar dastlab individual nutqda, ya'ni muallifning shaxsiy ifodasida paydo bo'ladi. Agar bu neologizm tilning taraqqiyot qonunlariga mos kelib, keng jamoatchilik tomonidan tan olinib, ma'lum bir ma'noni anglatish uchun zarur deb qaralsa, u holda individual nutqdagi neologizm umumtil neologizmga aylanishi mumkin. Aks holda, neologizm kengroq ijtimoiy va tilshunoslik doirasida qabul qilinmasa, u faqatgina yakka nutq doirasida qoladi va umumiy til tizimiga integratsiyalashmaydi [13].

Biz olimlarning fikriga qo'shilgan holda neologizmlar yangilik xususiyatini o'zida mujassam etgan, til leksik qatlamini boyituvchi unsurlar deya tavsiflashni

maqul ko'rdik. O'zbek tilshunosligida neologizm tushunchasi ko'p o'rinlarda "yangi leksika" ko'rinishida namoyon bo'lib, uning ikki turi ya'ni, "sof yangi leksema" va "faollashgan leksema" kabilarga bo'linib talqin etilishi fikrimizning dalili bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tilshunoslar tomonidan tadqiq etilgan manbalarda neologizmlarning bir qator turlari mavjudligi dalillangan. Xususan, M.Qurbonova, M. Abjalova, N. Axmedova, R.To'laboyevalar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarga tayanib neologizmlarning quyidagi turlarini keltirib o'tamiz [14]:

Shakliy neologizmlar – yangi leksik birliklarni yaratish uchun prefiks, suffiks yoki mavjud so'zlarning birikmasidan foydalanish orqali shakllanadi. Shakliy neologizmlar odatda yangi tushunchalarni nomlashda yoki mavjud tushunchalarni kengaytirishda qo'llaniladi: *bioremediatsiya, eko-chellenj, eko-kvest, eko-fest, infotur*.

Fonologik neologizmlar – asosan tovushlarning birikishidan hosil bo'lgan tovush taqlidli undov birliklar hisoblanib, badiiy tilda "sun'iy" yoxud "kashf etilgan" deya keltirilib o'tiladi: *Oops!, auch!, auf!, buzz!, zizz!* [15].

Semantik neologizmlar - mavjud so'z yoki atamalarga yangi semantik yuklama berish orqali hosil bo'lgan neologizmlar zamonaviy ehtiyojlar va kommunikativ talablar bilan uyg'unlashgan holda, til tizimining semantik jihatdan boyishiga xizmat qiladi: *yashil iqtisodiyot, iqlim qochqinlari, ekologik patrul, virtual suv, smart turizm*.

Uslubiy neologizmlar - badiiy va metaforik ifodalar orqali paydo bo'lgan yangi atamalar bo'lib, asosan ommaviy axborot vositalari va badiiy asarlarda keltiriladi: *yashil sayohat, ko'k sayyora, o'pirilgan daraxtlar*.

Funksional neologizmlar - chet tillardan olingan va milliy tilda adekvat tarjima yoki ekvivalentga ega bo'lmagan holda, asl shaklda qabul qilingan leksik birliklarga aytiladi. Bunday neologizmlar, odatda, yangi tushunchalarni ifodalash zarurati yoki kommunikativ vazifalarni samarali amalga oshirish ehtiyojidan kelib chiqib til tizimiga kiradi: *plogging, emissiya, eko-kvest, reynjer, IQ Air*.

Ijtimoiy neologizmlar – jamiyatda ahamiyatga molik ijtimoiy harakatlar va vaziyatlarni ifodalash uchun qo'llaniladigan yangi leksik birliklardir:

ekofeminizm, iqlim adolati, ekologik chellenj, ekologik savodxonlik va boshqalar.

Texnologik neologizmlar - zamonaviy texnologiyalar rivojlanishi natijasida paydo bo'lgan yangi atamalar va so'zlar: *smart farming, yashil energiya, geotermal energiya, bulutli ekish*.

Abbriviativ neologizmlar - qisqartma shakllar orqali hosil bo'lgan yangi atamalar. Ular odatda ilmiy va texnik sohalarda qo'llaniladi: *B2B (business to business), ESG, REDD+*.

Individual (muallif) stilistik neologizmlari – individual stilistik neologizmlar asosan ijodkorlar, ya'ni yozuvchi, san'atkor, shoir va shu kabilar tomonidan yaratilib, mualliflik maqomiga ega bo'lgan neologizmlar hisoblanadi. Ushbu neologizmlar estetik xususiyatga ega bo'lib, ijodkor o'z asariga badiiy bo'yoqdorlik va estetik zavq ulashish maqsadida yaratiladi va ekspressivlikni o'zida namoyon etadi. O'zbek adabiyotida ham bir qator yozuvchi va shoirlar ham individual neologizmlarga murojaat qilishgan. Xususan, Zulfiya she'riyatida *–parast, -zoda, -be* kabi individual neologizmlarga qo'l urgan:

1) *Nur yo'lday **dilparast** she'rlardan shoirning ko'zin;*

2) *Jaranglovchi begona shu til / **Bo'ronzoda** chag'alaqsimon / yuraklarni qiladi chil-chil.*

3) *Suyuq quyosh kabi jilvanalar suv/ Dengiz orzu kabi betinch, **beqirg'oq.***

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlab o'tish joizki, turli shakl va mazmundagi neologizmlar (leksik neologizmlar, frazeologik neologizmlar, neologizm-semema, semantik neologizmlar va boshqalar tilning ijtimoiyligi, uning o'zgarib turishini ko'rsatib turadi va lug'at tarkibini to'ldirib, boyitib boradi. Ushbu tadqiqotda neologizm fenomenining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari jahon va o'zbek tilshunosligida ishlab chiqilgan konsepsiyalar doirasida har tomonlama tahlil qilindi. Neologizmlarning lingvistik xususiyatlari, yasalish usullari, ijtimoiy va madaniy rivojlanishdagi o'rnini hamda zamonaviy til tizimidagi ahamiyati haqida chuqur ilmiy izlanish olib borildi.

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FEATURES OF RESTRICTED VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: JARGON CLASSIFICATIONS

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Abstract: *This study explores the function of socially limited vocabulary, particularly jargon, in the English and Uzbek languages. Jargon serves as a means of expressing linguistic creativity and adaptability among diverse social groups, functioning as a tool for identity construction, professional discourse, and subcultural differentiation. By analyzing the structural, semantic, and stylistic features of jargon, this paper examines how different fields - from technology to street slang - develop and maintain exclusive linguistic codes. Moreover, it underscores the increasing impact of English terminology on Uzbek as a result of globalization. The results of this study make a significant contribution to the broader understanding of sociolinguistics and cross-cultural communication.*

Keywords: *Socially restricted vocabulary, jargon, linguistic identity, lexical semantics, stylistics, sociolinguistics, Uzbek language, English language, neologisms, globalization.*

Introduction

The English language is a multifaceted and constantly evolving entity, continuously adjusting to accommodate the ever-changing social and professional dynamics of our modern society. In the process of linguistic evolution, jargon is developed as a specialized form of vocabulary that is limited to particular social groups. Jargon serves multiple purposes: it enhances communication efficiency among insiders, fosters group identity, and creates linguistic barriers for outsiders (Živić, 2012; Halliday & Hasan, 1976). Through extensive research and analysis, this study delves into the complex process of jargon development, examining its functions and impact on both the English and Uzbek languages. By shedding light on how various communities construct and uphold specialized vocabularies, this study offers valuable insights into the intricate workings of language.

The term "Socially Restricted Vocabulary" is commonly used to describe a set of words and phrases that are primarily used by certain professional, technical or subcultural communities, indicating a level of exclusivity and specialized language within these groups. Jargon is a key component of this lexicon, featuring informal, context-dependent meanings that often diverge from standard language norms (Orna-Montesinos, 2011; Crystal, 2003). Examples include legal terminology, medical shorthand, and online gaming slang. Such vocabulary forms an essential part of in-group communication and can serve to either facilitate precision or reinforce exclusivity (Labov, 1972).

The technical terminology and specialized language utilized in jargon expressions exhibit distinctive structural and semantic characteristics that distinguish it from the ordinary vocabulary employed in daily communication. Several morphological and syntactic processes contribute to the formation of jargon, including:

Clipping and Abbreviation: Common in technical and professional jargon (e.g., "app" for application, "meds" for medicine) (Plag, 2003).

Acronyms and Initialisms: Frequently used in fields such as technology and law (e.g., "NASA" for National Aeronautics and Space Administration, "OAV" for Ommaviy Axborot Vositalari in Uzbek) (Yule, 2010).

Loanwords and Code-Mixing: Uzbek incorporates Russian and Persian terms into its slang, while English borrows from Latin, Greek, and French (McArthur, 1992).

Metaphorization: Many jargon terms originate from metaphorical extensions (e.g., "firewall" in computing, "bull market" in finance) (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980).

Euphemisms and Dysphemisms: Some jargon softens meanings (e.g., "downsizing" for job cuts), while others adopt harsher tones (e.g., "pig" for police) (Allan & Burridge, 2006).

The utilization of specialized terminology, commonly referred to as jargon, may possess unique stylistic characteristics that differentiate it from colloquial language. Furthermore, it is important to note that this use of jargon also holds considerable social implications, as it can create a sense of exclusivity or expertise within a particular group or profession. It can be humorous, ironic, exaggerated, or highly technical. These stylistic elements reinforce the group's identity and differentiate insiders from outsiders. For instance:

Tech Jargon: Terms such as "debugging" and "glitch" are widely used among programmers (Aitchison, 1991; Holmes, 2013).

Medical Slang: Expressions like "code blue" (medical emergency) illustrate how professionals communicate quickly in high-pressure environments.

Criminal and Street Slang: Terms like "shapka" in Uzbek (meaning bribery) and "hustle" in English represent cultural and economic realities.

Upon conducting an extensive comparative analysis of the jargon utilized in both the English and Uzbek languages, it becomes apparent that there exist both converging and diverging tendencies in the usage of jargon within these two languages. Despite the shared use of word creation, metaphorical extensions, and incorporation of words from other languages, the evolution of Uzbek jargon has been

heavily influenced by the linguistic customs of Russian and Persian. With the rise of globalization, English jargon has permeated Uzbek speech, particularly in technology and business sectors (Trudgill, 2000). Terms like "kompyuter" (computer) and "onlayn" (online) have become part of everyday Uzbek lexicon.

Conclusion

By examining the concept of jargon as a specialized and socially restricted vocabulary, one can uncover the intricate and ever-changing relationship between language, society, and individual identity. The use of jargon expressions in both the English and Uzbek languages can serve as valuable linguistic markers that not only showcase the evolution of these languages over time, but also reflect the impact of historical, technological, and social changes on their respective vocabularies. As technology continues to advance and digital communication expands its reach, the use of jargon is constantly evolving and incorporating new vocabulary and structures to keep up with the ever-changing landscape. Future research should focus on how digital discourse affects jargon proliferation and whether bilingualism influences jargon adaptation in multilingual societies.

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THE LINGUISTIC ISSUES OF MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Annotation: *The article explores the axiological, pragma-linguistic, and linguo-cultural issues inherent in media discourse, emphasizing its lexical-semantic characteristics. It delves into the philosophical, social, ideological, and pragmatic dimensions of media language, presenting the concept of a variable paradigm that integrates diverse research directions. The study highlights key categories of media texts, including modality, massiveness, and multimodality, while addressing functional genre considerations and the impact of linguistic processes on the dynamics of mass media. The author discusses the significance of linguistic and cultural transformations within the context of media discourse and its role in shaping societal values and communication structures.*

Keywords: *Axiology, Media Discourse, Pragmatics, Linguo-Cultural Issues, Mass Media Texts, Variable Paradigm, Multimodality, Functional Genres, Language and Culture, Social Institutions.*

Аннотация: *В статье исследуются аксиологические, прагма-лингвистические и лингво-культурные вопросы, присущие медийному дискурсу, с акцентом на его лексико-семантических характеристиках. Анализируются философские, социальные, идеологические и прагматические измерения медийного языка и представляется концепция вариативной парадигмы, объединяющей различные направления исследований. В исследовании рассматриваются ключевые категории медиатекстов, включая модальность, массовость и мультимодальность, а также вопросы функциональных жанров и влияния языковых процессов на динамику средств массовой информации. Автор обсуждает значение языковых и культурных трансформаций в контексте медийного дискурса и его роль в формировании общественных ценностей и коммуникационных структур.*

Ключевые слова: *Аксиология, Медийный дискурс, Прагматика, Лингво-культурные вопросы, Тексты СМИ, Вариативная парадигма, Мультимодальность, Функциональные жанры, Язык и культура, Социальные институты*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada media diskursiga xos bo'lgan aksiologik, pragma-lingvistik va lingvo-madaniy masalalar, uning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari ta'kidlangan holda o'rganiladi. Unda media tilining falsafiy, ijtimoiy, mafkuraviy va pragmatik o'lchamlari tahlil qilinadi va turli tadqiqot yo'nalishlarini birlashtiradigan o'zgaruvchan paradigma kontseptsiyasi taqdim etiladi. Tadqiqotda media matnlarining asosiy kategoriyalari, jumladan, modallik, massaviylik va multimodallik kabi kategoriyalarga, shuningdek, funksional janrlar masalalari va til jarayonlarining ommaviy axborot vositalari dinamikasiga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif media diskursi kontekstida til va madaniy o'zgarishlarning ahamiyati, uning jamiyat qadriyatlari va kommunikatsiya tuzilmalarini shakllantirishdagi rolini muhokama qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Aksiologiya, Media diskursi, Pragmatika, Lingvo-madaniy masalalar, Ommaviy axborot vositalari matnlari, O'zgaruvchan paradigma, Multimodallik, Funksional janrlar, Til va madaniyat, Ijtimoiy institutlar.*

Introduction: In the rapidly evolving landscape of mass media, understanding the intricacies of media discourse has become increasingly vital. Media discourse not

only serves as a conduit for information but also reflects and shapes societal values, ideologies, and cultural narratives. This article aims to examine the axiological, pragma-linguistic, and linguo-cultural dimensions of media discourse, shedding light on the complex interplay between language, meaning, and cultural context.

Archaeology, the study of values, provides a foundational framework for analyzing how media discourse embodies and conveys societal values. The exploration of pragmatic issues reveals how media texts communicate meaning through various channels, incorporating multimodal elements that resonate with diverse audiences. Additionally, the article addresses the functional genre characteristics of media discourse, emphasizing the relevance of genre in the systematic categorization of mass media texts. As technological advancements continue to reshape the media landscape, the qualitative transformations within language and culture warrant close examination. This study will draw upon key concepts and theories to elucidate the multifaceted nature of media discourse and its capacity to influence public perception and cultural understanding in contemporary society. The findings aim to contribute to a deeper comprehension of media's role in shaping social institutions, cultural narratives, and value systems, thus providing insights into the dynamic relationship between language, culture, and communication in the modern world.

The Archaeological, Pragma-Linguistic, And Linguo-Cultural Issues Of Media Discourse

The lexical-semantic level of media discourse reflects its philosophical, social, ideological, linguistic, structural, functional, and pragmatic characteristics. These characteristics are primarily manifested in non-standard forms within speech paradigms. This non-standardness is referred to as a variable paradigm. The variable paradigm of media discourse serves as a means of expressing the semantic level, where different research directions in philosophy and linguistics unite to expand the structural paradigm in semantics. In this traditional model, words are formed due to the relationships of meaning within the vocabulary of the language. Each word consolidates its discrete meaning into a syntactic unit, and its meaning is then expressed along with the intended components, representing the relationships of word meanings and their structural connections. This model gradually serves as a starting point for semantic analysis, but in media discourse, it is controversially assessed as a non-standard situation. The meaning of words in media speech appears to be appropriate for the context but seems non-standard concerning the norms of literary speech.

In general, semantic research draws upon F. de Saussure's theories regarding linguistic signs and the dialectical model of signs, proposing the existence of a psychological compatibility between the arbitrary yet conventional forms and meanings of words. Furthermore, Saussure placed particular emphasis on studying the system of language (langue) while also focusing on the study of live language in communication, which has led to the conception that context and discourse lie beyond linguistic description. For this reason, almost all linguistic research has been conducted within the framework of individual words, phrases, clauses, and written texts. The discourse analysis of spoken language has remained one of the issues in modern linguistics awaiting resolution. Currently, when internet users exchange information, they utilize various symbols (stickers) to provide summaries of expressed opinions, answer questions, or convey the continuation of unfinished thoughts. As a result of the external influences enriching the Uzbek language, a number of new terms such as "smiley," "sticker," and "emoji" have entered the language from English and Russian. These refer to a group of non-verbal tools that reflect a person's inner feelings through various pictorial symbols and graphics in written communication. For example, expressing well-done work using a thumbs-up gesture or smiling images to symbolize happiness, while grief is illustrated through crying symbols. Such symbols are interpreted as "emotion signs" in school textbooks. Surveys conducted on social networks have found that the newly adopted terms "smile" and "sticker" have an equivalent in Uzbek, which is deemed to be "emotion sign."

Axiological Issues of Media Discourse

Axiology (from the Greek words "axios" – value and "logos" – study or discourse) is the study of values, a branch of knowledge that examines the realm of values, investigates its laws and categories, and constitutes a science about values. It was introduced to the field by German philosopher E. Hartmann and French scholar P. Lapie in the second half of the 19th century. Axiology involves axiological consciousness, the feeling of valuation, and axiological cognition, forming a system of knowledge about accumulated values.

The text authored by the sender reflects the axiological content (the saturation of media discourse related to the constant change of evaluations) and the ability of media discourse to model, adjust, and create values (anti-values) in accordance with the linguistic picture of the world. The values prioritized by society (the information recipient) change, causing "the indicators of the value of a certain object to also

change, the evaluative activities to transform, and as a result, the composition of values to be updated and altered." ¹

In media discourse, a specific axiological field is formed that includes the value ideas of particular authors. At a certain publication level, axiologicality manifests in the ideological and political directions of media discourse; at the text level, the axiological representation of the author's worldview is altered within these parameters. In the stream of media information, the axiological approach holds significant importance alongside other methods of scientific cognition when studying reality. In scientific knowledge, it is essential to understand the world, the objects and events within it, how values are reflected in human consciousness, the laws, levels, and possibilities for grasping values in alignment with reality, as well as determining their norms and criteria. This involves relying on achievements from various fields, including general theory of knowledge (epistemology), pedagogy, psychology, physiology, logic, and linguistics. ²

Such valuable approaches yield effective scientific and practical results when applied to related processes. In this context, values are manifested not as chaotic representations of social phenomena, but rather as interconnected axiological systems and their elements associated with social subjects and others. ³

Pragmatic Issues of Media Discourse

The main categories of media texts include mediality (the manifestation of the text through various media channels, determined by the format and technical capabilities of the channel), massiveness (both in the production and consumption of media products), integrativity or the multimodality of the text (the unification of various semiotic codes into a singular communicative integrity), as well as the clarity of meaning-content, compositional structure, and sign levels of the text.

Within the realm of pragmatic issues, several topics related to the subject of media discourse are explored, including the explicit and implicit purposes of information in media discourse, as well as the delivery of any information or opinion through various acts such as questioning, commanding, requesting, advising,

¹ А. В. Костина Раздел II ФИЛОСОФИЯ. КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЯ. СОЦИОЛОГИЯ А. В. Костина ТРАДИЦИОННАЯ, ЭЛИТАРНАЯ И МАССОВАЯ КУЛЬТУРА: УСЛОВИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ

² СОВРЕМЕННОСТИ Вестник Челябинской государственной академии культуры и искусств. 2011 / 2 (26) ср.39

³ SCIENCE AND INNOVATION ISSN: 2181-3337 INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL 2022 №4 687
AKSIOLOGIK YONDASHUV ASOSIDA MEDIA MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH G'ulomqodirova Xanifaxon
<https://zenodo.org/record/6985412>

promising, apologizing, congratulating, complaining, and others. ⁴Additional areas of focus include speech tactics and types of speech etiquette, conversation and communication rules, the speaker's objectives, the evaluation of the addressee's general knowledge base, worldview, interests, and other attributes by the speaker, and the speaker's attitude towards the message being conveyed.

Functional Genre Issues of Media Discourse

The relevance of a text in terms of functional genres is a crucial parameter in the typological description of mass media texts. The systematization of media discourse genres has always been a complex process. Today, the dynamics of using language in mass communication is so active that it causes this unit to lack the necessary degree of stability. Amid various approaches to defining the possibilities of describing media texts from a functional genre perspective, the theoretical framework of media linguistics provides for the compatibility of a stable structure with the infinite diversity and dynamism of real textual material.⁵

Among the most effective and widespread methods for studying media discourse are the following:

1. A complete set of linguistic analysis methods that allow for the identification of the main features and characteristics of a text at various linguistic levels: lexical, syntagmatic (compatibility), stylistic (the use of tropes, comparisons, metaphors, and other stylistic devices), and sociolinguistic.

2. Content analysis based on the statistical calculation of specially selected text units.

3. Discourse analysis methods based on the concept of discourse, which allow for the observation of the relationship between the linguistic and extralinguistic aspects of the text.

4. Critical linguistics (or rhetorical criticism) methods that reveal the hidden political and ideological components of media texts.

The journalistic work's speech is creative and stimulating for understanding "attractive" and prospective messages. Many researchers emphasize that media discourse is not merely a collection of texts in a specific genre but a powerful means of expressing a dynamic communicative process realized in a particular semantic

⁴ Казак М.Ю. Медиа́текст: су́щностные и типологические свойства //Global Media Journal. Глобальный медиажурнал. Российское издание // URL: http://test.gmj.sfedu.ru/v2il/v2il_kazak.htm (дата обращения 07/07.2011).

⁵ Teshaboyeva D.M. Jurnalistika: Medialingvistika va tahrir. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2019.

field, involving the relationships between individual units of the corpus of media texts and speeches.⁶

In analyzing media discourse, it is essential to take into account not only thematic, structural, and lexical choices but also their socio-cultural contexts. Discourse analysis aims to reveal the hierarchical distribution of information and the lexical and stylistic representation of data in mass media texts and their parts. Therefore, the tasks of analyzing media discourse are associated with determining the level of unacceptable language in media texts, their degree of integration into a specific context, and the audience's understanding of meanings.⁷

Considering the functional genre features of media texts, Russian linguist V. Vinogradov categorized them into the following four types: (1) news, (2) commentary and analysis, (3) journalist dialogue, and (4) advertising.

Differential Issues of Media Discourse

When discussing the role of linguistic processes in mass media dynamics, we must consider not only the changes resulting from the introduction of new information technologies but also the qualitative transformations within language and culture in general. In turn, when we evaluate the influence of modern mass media on linguistic processes, we can identify the following three levels of analysis: 1) geolinguistic; 2) interlinguistic; 3) intralinguistic.

The geolinguistic level studies how mass media affects the development of the overall linguistic and cultural situation globally and regionally. The interlinguistic level focuses on significant quantitative and territorial indicators such as the changes in the number of speakers of a particular language in the global information space, the redistribution of linguistic influence areas, the increase in the role of certain languages, and the decrease in the role of others. The intralinguistic level allows for a focus on media-specific linguistic processes within the same linguistic and cultural domain. This includes trends such as the blurring of clear stylistic boundaries, the spread of spoken style norms in the main body of media discourse (including news, informational analyses, and commentaries), the repetition of incorrect speech (for example, incorrect stress, grammatical errors, and improper agreements), and the decline of speech norms due to the use of derogatory and reduced language in mass media, among other issues.

⁶ Коновалова М.В. Медиадискурс и подходы к его изучению // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. 2015. № 27 (382). С. 101 – 110

⁷ Карнаух Татьяна Владимировна, младший научный сотрудник кафедры «Теория и практика перевода», ФГАОУ ВО «Севастопольский государственный университет», институт общественных наук и международных отношений, г. Севастополь, Россия стр.6

Linguocultural Issues of Media Discourse

According to N.F. Alefirenkon, media discourse is the formation of speech and thought that involves events, influenced by pragmatic, socio-cultural, psychological, paralinguistic, and other factors.⁸ The linguocultural issues of media discourse are related to the differentiation of discourse types within the context of intercultural communication, the cultural norms and discourse etiquette of media, the realities presented in media discourse, as well as ethical, aesthetic, and ethnic concerns.⁹

Linguoculturology is a branch of linguistic science that reflects the properties of language, culture, and the manifestation of folk culture in language. The linguocultural analysis of linguistic units describes the distinctive features of linguistics and the cultural community, characterizes national and cultural traits, and explains the significance of communicative categories and the concept of national culture. The main task of linguoculturology is to describe the cultural origin of the communicative space within a specific linguocultural domain, the relationship between discourse and language, as well as the interpretation of cultural symbols of linguistic units from the perspective of a nation's historical memory.¹⁰

The interest of linguoculturology in the speech of mass media is linked to several important reasons. It is known that linguoculturology encompasses the study and description of a specific linguocultural community's cultural space through the prism of language. The speech of mass media is understood as the discourse of communication participants within the mass media..

The Model of Media Discourse and Its Classification

Recognizing the diversity and variety of mass media discourse, the object of study for this dissertation is understood as a collection of texts within mass media related to the political sphere of society. According to M. L. Makarov, communication reconstructs the social institutions, cultural schemes, and value systems of society.¹¹ Accordingly, media discourse encompasses the process of creating relevant texts within a particular cultural context. By "cultural context," we mean, on one hand, a set of institutional, role, value, and cognitive conditions necessary for the realization of events or facts, and on the other hand, a collection of expressive means used by people within these conditions. This implies that the media

⁸ Алефиренко Н.Ф. Медиадискурс и его коммуникативнопрагматическая сущность // Медиалингвистика. 2016. № 1 (11). С. 49 – 57.

⁹ Газизов Р. А., Мурысов Р. З. Лингвокультурология и современная лексикография. 2016.. № 2 ср.413

¹⁰ Маслова В.А. Лингвокультурология.–М.: 2001 ср,263

¹¹ Макаров М. Л. Основы теории дискурса. – М.: ИТДГК «Гнозис», 2003. Ср. 41

text establishes and requires linguistic tools for creating various forms of discourse that correspond to the external conditions of the situation.

Denis McQuail,¹² a British sociologist and communication theorist, who is a professor at the University of Amsterdam in the Netherlands, has conducted in-depth analyses of media components in his research. He emphasizes the integral connection of the media system with the real social-political, economic, and cultural context. The role and significance of mass media in society, their legal interests, and the issues of maintaining balance are of critical importance. Additionally, it is necessary to consider the structural, managerial, financial, and technological aspects of the media system, as well as their level of service to public interests. In this regard, enhancing citizen oversight and participation in the media field is of significant importance. He notes that a comprehensive approach and multidimensional methods are required to deeply analyze media components while considering their multifaceted nature and their role in societal life.¹³ As we see, the analysis of media components first and foremost requires detailed definitions and descriptions

The stylistic analysis of this media discourse reveals that it can utilize various functional styles of speech, employing nuanced registers that align with the expected program formats by the audience. Media discourse can be analyzed by categorizing it into text types like news, talk shows, reality programs, sports commentary, and so on. The formation of such styles encompasses both technical and linguistic processes.

This long-term transition from formal mass public address to non-standard linguistic forms and styles characterized by increased interaction in programs is observable. The emergence of such genres encompasses multiple factors simultaneously: the changing media technologies in everyday life, their relative convergence and accessibility (thus, watching television might be an individual online activity, a family activity sitting together in front of the TV, or a communal viewing in public spaces like waiting rooms or bars); the relative rarity or ordinariness of participation in a specific media format (as a fluctuating mix of professional and amateur participants in a broadcast); and the diverse traditions of public and personal identity performance leading to social and cultural disparities in media discourse. Importantly, this historic development of media style formation is not complete but is continually evolving in response to ongoing changes. In the

¹² Denis Makkuil. Mass Communication Theory. Library of Congress Control Number: 2009932171 ISBN 978-1-84920-292-3 (pbk)

¹³ Denis McQuail "McQuail's Mass Communication Theory. Library of Congress Control Number: 2009932171 ISBN 978-1-84920-292-3 (pbk) page:337. 6 the edition

rapidly changing environment of electronic communication, there should be a certain level of awareness and oversight when evaluating linguistic practices. For instance, Twitter should not merely be understood as a technical format defined by its maximum character limit (140), but rather, its linguistic style and the broader genre of tweets play significant roles in shaping its meaning.

Conclusion: This article is dedicated to exploring the axiological, pragma-linguistic, and linguo-cultural issues of media discourse, providing a comprehensive analysis of its lexical-semantic characteristics. Media discourse not only reflects but also shapes societal values, ideologies, and cultural narratives. Axiology, as the study of values, plays a crucial role in understanding the essence and purpose of media discourse.

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INTERDISCIPLINARY CHARACTER OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: *This article delves into the interdisciplinary characteristics of cognitive linguistics. Cognitive linguistics intersects with several disciplines of cognitive sciences, encompassing Cognitive psychology and computer Science, including Artificial Intelligence, Neuroscience, and cultural linguistics. We will discuss some of these disciplines that overlap with cognitive linguistics.*

Key words: *interdisciplinarity, schema theory, schema, artificial intelligence, neuroscience.*

One of the main characteristics of cognitive linguistics is its interdisciplinary character. Before scrutinizing the interdisciplinary character of cognitive linguistics let us touch upon the term “interdisciplinarity”. The term interdisciplinarity refers to a method which combines two or more subject areas of knowledge to arrive at a new approach or solution to the problem of a specific science. There are several problems seem insoluble within the framework of one science, and they require to be studied in a broad socio-cultural context including linguistic and extralinguistic factors. Interdisciplinarity has become one of the prominent research practices in recent decades, and it has been put forward as a part of the solution most of the time. One of the good examples of Interdisciplinarity is cognitive science which studies human and his mind. Cognitive science in its turn combines mind-related fields such as philosophy, linguistics, psychology, anthropology, Artificial Intelligence, neuroscience, etc. All these disciplines are based on a single methodological basis - the principle of anthropocentrism which puts the human in the centre. Cognitive linguistics as a part of cognitive sciences was formed by the intersection of cognitive science and linguistics. It also has an interdisciplinarity character, which interacts with the number of scientific disciplines encompassing philosophy, computer science, psychology, neuroscience, etc. (Brief Dictionary of Cognitive Terms 1996:58)

Among these sciences, a special focus should be placed on the interdisciplinary of cognitive linguistics with linguaculturology. However, before discussing the interaction of cognitive linguistics with linguaculturology, we will briefly discuss some of the cognitive sciences that intersect with cognitive linguistics.

Cognitive linguistics is thoroughly interconnected with cognitive psychology with the analysis of literary text. Cognitive psychology studies human, his mind and the knowledge he acquired through the experiences, and it studies how this language reflects on human behavior. Actually, Cognitive linguistics paralelly emerged with cognitive psychology. In its turn, one of the tasks of Cognitive linguistics is to define

how the knowledge, memory and experience of human reflect on the production of speech/utterance. Cognitive linguistics focuses on how cognitive processes such as perception, memory and inference affect reading comprehension. For example, Zwaan and Rodansky (1998) discuss how readers structure mental representation, i.e. “situation models” based on the textual information and how it influences their comprehension and memorization of the narration. Another essential cognitive psychology concept that overlaps with cognitive linguistics is “Schema Theory”. The term “schema” was initially introduced by Barlett as “an active organization of past reaction or experiences” (1932, p 201). According to Barlett, et al. reader’s own previous knowledge is called a reader’s background knowledge and previously acquired knowledge structure is called schemata.

Cognitive linguistics is also intersected with the field of Neuroscience. Recent developments in neuroscience have provided empirical evidence into how the brain processes language and narration. This interdisciplinary approach can define how different styles and narrative techniques activate different parts of the brain. These empirical insights enhance theoretical discussions within cognitive linguistics by grounding them in biological realities. Some of the main concepts of neurosciences involved in the process of representing, comprehending and producing cognitive stylistics are language, intelligence and life experience i.e. knowledge and the brain including the nervous system. In this multifaced approach, cognitive linguistics studies how language, knowledge, acquired by life experiences and, the brain reflect in the representation of the author’s cognitive style.

Computer linguistics contributes to cognitive linguistics by sharing common features of study such as: - cognitive linguistics examines how language choices affect interpretation while computer linguistics offers quantitative methods of analyzing these choices; - the study of word meaning and their relationship is crucial in both fields. – the usage of language in context (discourse) is concerned in both linguistics; - both cognitive linguistics and computer linguistics concern the study of language in context, in other words, pragmatics. Corpora can be a good example of the study of language in context through computer science; - tools developed in computer linguistics can be useful for cognitive stylisticians and linguists in their research to analyze the literary text automatically. In addition to computer linguistics, we should speak about the correlation of cognitive linguistics with Artificial Intelligence. The distinction between the ability of computer and human mechanism in terms of solving intelligent problems is defined as “what is simple for a person is difficult for a computer and what is simple for computer is difficult for person”

(Kuznetsov, 1995 p. 3-23). For the problem of text comprehension, Pinker (1994) mentions that “the part that refers to memory is easy for computers and difficult for people (main storage is bottleneck when people process information) and part refers to decision making is easy for people (at least if a sentence constructed correctly) and difficult for computers”. Thus, studying human cognitive structures and mechanisms is important not only in Cognitive sciences (psychology, neuropsychology, linguistics, etc.) but in Artificial Intelligence as well which leads to new intelligent technologies. The problem of conceptualization and categorization, the problem of concept, frame or schemas, the process of perception, cognitive complexity and cognitive semantics are discussed both in cognitive linguistics and Artificial Intelligence which fosters its advantages in decades. However, there are still many distinctive features of human thinking that differentiate the brain from a computer which requires more research in the computer paradigm.

Another of the most prominent disciplines that overlap Cognitive linguistics and is most relevant to our research is Linguaculturalogy. Linguaculturalogy is a scientific discipline which studies the relationship and interaction of language and culture. Some researchers such as V.N. Telia (1999) consider linguoculturalogy as a part of ethnolinguistics, however, according to V.A. Maslova (2001), linguaculturalogy is an independent direction that emerged at the intersection of linguistics and culturology, and it should be studied in depth. Cognitive linguistics and linguoculturalogy both study the problem of concept, the structure of concept including notional, imagery and axiological, the notion of foregrounding, the notion of conceptual and cognitive world pictures, the knowledge structure, etc.

To draw a conclusion, we can summarize that language is not in and for itself, but it is rather a major contributor to the emergence of the new interdisciplinary science of mind.

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INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AS CONSTRUCTIVE COMMUNICATION: A SCHOLARLY PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: *The article “Intercultural Communication as Constructive Communication” explores the concept of intercultural communication through the lens of constructive communication. It emphasizes how communication between individuals from different cultural backgrounds can lead to positive outcomes such as mutual understanding, cooperation, and conflict resolution. The article draws upon theories by renowned scholars, including Edward T. Hall’s high- and low-context communication, Geert Hofstede’s cultural dimensions theory, Stella Ting-Toomey’s face negotiation theory, and Young Yun Kim’s communication accommodation theory. These frameworks are used to explain how intercultural communication can be made more constructive by recognizing cultural differences, adapting communication styles, and focusing on empathy and respect. The article also identifies the challenges faced in intercultural communication, such as language barriers, cultural stereotyping, and ethnocentrism, and suggests ways to overcome these obstacles to foster more effective communication.*

Key words: *intercultural communication, constructive communication, high-context and low-context cultures, cultural dimensions theory, face negotiation theory, communication accommodation theory, power distance, individualism vs. collectivism, ethnocentrism, conflict resolution.*

In the increasingly interconnected world of today, effective intercultural communication is crucial. It is the process through which people from different cultural backgrounds exchange ideas, beliefs, and values. When viewed as constructive communication, intercultural communication is not just about the exchange of information; it becomes a means of creating positive social change, fostering cooperation, and resolving conflicts. This article explores the concept of intercultural communication as constructive communication, drawing upon the insights of leading scholars, offering real-world examples, and suggesting strategies to improve intercultural dialogue.

Scholars from various disciplines have contributed to the development of intercultural communication theories. Below are key perspectives from renowned theorists that emphasize intercultural communication as a constructive process.

Edward T. Hall is one of the earliest scholars to explore intercultural communication in depth. His seminal work, *Beyond Culture* (1976), introduced the concept of high-context and low-context communication, which has since become a cornerstone in intercultural communication studies. High-context cultures (e.g.,

Japan, China, and many Middle Eastern countries) rely on non-verbal cues and shared understanding within the context of communication. The message is often implied and conveyed through tone, gestures, and the situation itself. Low-context cultures (e.g., the U.S., Germany, and Scandinavian countries) value explicit, direct verbal communication where the meaning is contained in the words themselves.

Hall argued that intercultural communication can be constructive when individuals are aware of these differences and adapt their communication styles accordingly. He emphasized that misunderstandings can arise when individuals fail to recognize and adjust to cultural differences, and that constructive communication occurs when both parties make an effort to bridge this gap. Example: A manager from the U.S. (low-context) may expect clear and direct feedback, while a colleague from Japan (high-context) may prefer to provide more subtle, indirect responses. By recognizing these cultural differences, constructive communication allows for better understanding and more effective teamwork.

Geert Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory (2001) is one of the most influential frameworks in the study of intercultural communication. Hofstede identified several dimensions that influence how people communicate across cultures, including individualism vs. collectivism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance. Individualism vs. Collectivism: In individualistic cultures, people prioritize individual rights and independence, while in collectivist cultures, the group's welfare and harmony are prioritized over individual desires. Power Distance: This refers to how power and inequality are distributed in a society. Cultures with a high power distance (e.g., many Asian countries) are more accepting of hierarchical structures, while cultures with a low power distance (e.g., Denmark, Sweden) favor egalitarian relationships.

Hofstede's theory posits that understanding these dimensions is essential for constructive intercultural communication. For example, communication in collectivist cultures may involve indirectness to maintain group harmony, while individualistic cultures may encourage direct and assertive communication. By recognizing and respecting these cultural differences, communicators can engage in more effective and constructive exchanges.

In a global business setting, an employee from a collectivist culture might avoid directly confronting their supervisor. However, a manager from an individualistic culture might view this behavior as a lack of engagement. A constructive communicator would recognize these differing cultural values and use indirect methods to address concerns without risking conflict.

Stella Ting-Toomey's Face Negotiation Theory (1988) offers insights into how individuals from different cultures manage their social identity or "face" during communication. According to Ting-Toomey, people from collectivist cultures prioritize the face of others, seeking to avoid confrontation and maintain harmony. In contrast, those from individualistic cultures are more focused on protecting their own face, often through direct confrontation.

Ting-Toomey's theory suggests that constructive intercultural communication requires an understanding of these differing face concerns and the ability to adapt one's communication style accordingly. For instance, an individual from a high-power-distance, collectivist culture may prefer indirect communication to avoid threatening the other person's face. A constructive communicator would take care not to challenge the face of others while maintaining clarity.

In a team meeting, an employee from a low-context, individualistic culture might openly disagree with a superior's decision, which could threaten the superior's face. A constructive communicator would instead use indirect language or a respectful approach to express disagreement, allowing for a more collaborative, face-saving interaction.

Young Yun Kim's Communication Accommodation Theory (1988) posits that people adjust their communication style depending on their desire for social approval or the desire to create a relationship with others. In intercultural communication, individuals may adjust their speaking style to either accommodate (adapting to the other person's cultural style) or diverge (emphasizing differences to maintain cultural identity). According to Kim, constructive communication occurs when individuals recognize the need to accommodate their communication style to others' cultural norms, leading to greater understanding and connection. This accommodation can help build rapport, foster collaboration, and reduce misunderstandings in intercultural interactions.

In a multicultural team, a member from a high-context culture might adjust their communication style to be more direct in a low-context environment. This act of accommodation allows them to better connect with colleagues, fostering a sense of mutual respect and cooperation.

Despite the potential for constructive outcomes, intercultural communication presents several challenges, including:

Differences in language can lead to misinterpretations. A constructive communicator might use simple language, active listening, and check for understanding to ensure clarity. Stereotyping can prevent effective communication.

Constructive communication requires individuals to approach each interaction without preconceived notions, focusing on the person rather than their cultural background. The tendency to view one's own culture as superior can create communication barriers. Constructive communication encourages individuals to value cultural diversity and promote equality in interactions.

Intercultural communication, when viewed as a constructive process, becomes a powerful tool for bridging cultural divides and fostering understanding. Drawing on the theories of scholars like Edward T. Hall, Geert Hofstede, Stella Ting-Toomey, and Young Yun Kim, we see that communication is not just about transmitting information—it is about building relationships, resolving conflicts, and promoting collaboration. By embracing these theories and adopting a constructive approach, individuals and organizations can navigate the complexities of intercultural communication and create positive social change.

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AGGLYUTINATIV TILLARDA FLEKSIYA ELEMENTLARI

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*O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti O'zbek tili va adabiyoti kafedrası
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Fuziya tipining til sistemasidagi maqomini tilshunos olim E. Sepir birinchi bor aniqlab bergan. Ammo olimning nazariy konsepsiyasi ingliz tili materiallariga asoslangan edi. Ya'ni u o'zigacha fleksiya deb baholanib kelingan lisoniy tip mohiyati jihatdan "fuziya" tipi ekanligi va ular bir tomondan, bir-biridan farqlanuvchi ikki hodisalar, yana bir tomondan yondosh hodisalar ekanligini, ular o'rtasidagi tafovut juda nozik xarakterga ega ekanligini asoslab berdi. Shundan so'ng tilshunoslikda E.Sepirning izidan borib, fuziya tipining boshqa tillarda o'rganish boshlandi. A.K.Borovkovning "Turkiy tillarda agglyutinatsiya va fleksiya", A.N.Kononovning "Turkiy tillarda fuziya xususida" nomli maqolalari¹ ayni shu sohadagi tadqiqotlardan sanaladi. Mazkur tadqiqotlarda fuziyaga xos belgilar agglyutinativ tillar sirasiga kiruvchi turkiy tillarda ham uchrashi aniq misollar bilan isbotlab berilgan. Shuni ham aytib o'tishimiz joizki, keltirilgan maqolalar juda katta ilmiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lishi bilan birga, juda umumiy xarakterdagi asarlardir. Shu kunga qadar o'zbek tili misolida fuziyaning mavjud ko'rinishlari, uning agglyutinatsiyaga bo'lgan munosabati "fuziya" atamasining lingvistik mohiyati, olimlarning fuziya bergan baholari va talqinlari monografik asosda tadqiq etilmagan. Faqatgina Raximov A.U. o'zining nomzodlik dissertatsiyasida fuziya hodisasiga tipologiya nuqtayi nazaridan baho bergan, xolos.²

O'zbek tilida fuziyaning mavjudligi yoki ingliz, fransuz, rus tillarida agglyutinatsiyaning uchrashi barqaror holat emas, ular umumiy qonuniyatdan chetlashish holati hisoblanadi.

Shu kunga qadar amalga oshirilgan tadqiqotlar faqat tanlab olingan parametrlarni boshqa tillarda uchrashining qiyosiy tahlili asosida yuzaga kelgan. Masalan, agglyutinatsiya turkiy tillarda ko'proq kuzatiladigan bo'lsa, uni agglyutinativ til deb hisoblangan. Shuning uchun ham tillar tasnifi masalasi haligacha to'liq o'zining yechimini topgan emas.

¹ Qarang: Боровков А.К. Агглютинация и флексия в тюркских языках // Морфологическая типология и проблема классификации языков. –М. -Л., 1965. -122.; Кононов А.Н. О фузии в тюркских языках // Структура и история тюркских языков. –М., 1975. –С. 107-120.

² Raximov A.U., Fuziya lisoniy tipining kvantitativ va sinergetik yondashuv asosida tadqiq etish (o'zbek tili misolida). Andijon – 2009. B – 158.

O'zbek tilida fuziya unsurlarining uchrashi o'zbek tilida fluktatsiya (chetlashish) hodisasining mavjudligini tasdiqlaydi. Bu holatni o'rganish muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi tufayli fuziyani aniq tadqiq etishni lozim topdik.

Fuziyaga yondosh masalalarning o'rganilishi juda uzoqqa borib taqaladi. Qadimgi hind grammatistlarining tovush o'zgarishlari *sandhi* haqidagi ilmiy qarashlari bu sohadagi ilk qadamlardan biridir. Miloddan avvalgi IV asrda yashagan hind tilshunosi Panini o'zining "Ashtadg'xan" asarida ichki fleksiya hodisasini, tovush o'zgarishlari *sandhi* holati kabilarni ham aniq misollar bilan bilan tushuntirib bergan. Bunda unlilar almashinuvi (ablaut) hodisasiga ham jiddiy e'tibor qaratdi. Buni quyidagi misollar orqali izohlashga harakat qiladi: Sanskrit tilida **vidya** – "ma'no", **veda** – "men bilaman", **vaidays** – "olim" ma'nolarini anglatadi; bu yerda i – e – ai tarzida unlilar almashinuvi yuz bergan³. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, bayon etilgan fikrlarning hammasi fuziya haqidagi fikrlardir, faqat ular hind tilshunoslari, jumladan, Panini tomonidan "fuziya" deb nomlanmagan. Demak, shunga ko'ra aytish mumkinki, fuziya haqida dastlabki qarashlar, ilmiy fikrlar qadimgi hind olimlari – Panini, Yaska, Vopadevalar nomi bilan bog'liqdir. Ayniqsa, arab tilshunosligida o'zakning "sinishi" holatlari jiddiy ilmiy asosda o'rganilgan. Bunda arab tilshunosi Sibavayxiyning xizmati salmoqlidir. Tilshunos o'zining "Al-kitob" nomli grammatikaga oid asarida semit tillariga xos bo'lgan uch bo'g'inli o'zakni alohida ajratgan va o'zakning tuzilishiga mos bo'lgan affiksatsiya va ichki fleksiyani kuzatgan va tadqiq etgan.⁴ Demak, arab tilshunosligida fuziyaning ayrim ko'rinishlari haqida aniq ilmiy fikrlarbayon etilganligi ko'zga tashlanadi. Bunda tilshunoslikda davriy ketma-ketlikda fuziyaga yondosh masalalar tadqiq etilib rivojlantirilib borilgan. Ammo hech bir tilshunos o'rgangan holatlarni "fuziya" atamasi bilan nomlamagan bo'lsa-da, u bilan bog'liq ayrim muammolarni hal etishgan. Shu o'rinda aytish zarurki, yuqorida nomi tilga olingan tilshunoslarning buyuk xizmati shundaki, fuziyani tushunishning poydevorini, nazariy asoslarini boshlang'ich tavsiflarini yaratdilar. Ularning tadqiqotlarini tushunishdagi dastlabki ilmiy odimlar, ilk talqinlar sifatida naholash mumkin. Ayni mana shu ilmiy qarashlar, fikrlar, keyingi ilmiy talqinlarning yuzaga kelishiga zamin yaratagan desak, xato bo'lmaydi.

³ Qarang: Кондрашев Н.А. История лингвистических учений. – М.: Просвещение, 1979. –С. 8-9

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INTEGRATING AI IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO VISUALLY IMPAIRED B1-LEVEL LEARNERS

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Abstract. This paper explores how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance foreign language learning for visually impaired (VI) learners at the B1 level. Traditional teaching methods often pose accessibility challenges for VI learners, but AI-powered tools provide innovative solutions, enabling personalized instruction and improved engagement. This study examines the unique needs of VI learners at the B1 level, evaluates the effectiveness of various AI technologies in language acquisition, and proposes pedagogical strategies for integrating these tools effectively. The discussion highlights the benefits of AI in fostering autonomy, improving language proficiency, and creating inclusive learning environments while also addressing potential challenges in implementation.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), visually impaired (VI) learners, AI-powered tools, pedagogical strategies, language proficiency, inclusive learning.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt B1 darajasidagi ko'rish qobiliyati zaif o'quvchilar uchun chet tilini o'rganishni qanday tashkil etish mumkinligi haqida mulohaza qiladi. An'anaviy o'qitish usullari ko'pincha ko'rish qobiliyati zaif o'quvchilar uchun foydalanish imkoniyatini qiyinlashtiradi, ammo sun'iy intellektga asoslangan vositalar shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish va faollikni yaxshilash imkonini beruvchi innovatsion yechimlarni taqdim etadi. Ushbu tadqiqot B1 darajasidagi ko'rish qobiliyati zaif o'quvchilarning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlarini o'rganadi, tilni o'zlashtirishda turli sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining samaradorligini baholaydi va ushbu vositalarni samarali integratsiyalash uchun pedagogik strategiyalarni taklif qiladi. Muhokama avtonomiyani rivojlantirish, tilni bilish darajasini oshirish va inklyuziv o'quv muhitini yaratishda sun'iy intellektning afzalliklarini ta'kidlaydi, shu bilan birga amalga oshirishda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan muammolarni hal qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt (AI), ko'rish qobiliyati zaif (VI) o'quvchilar, sun'iy intellekt yordamida ishlaydigan vositalar, pedagogik strategiyalar, tilni bilish, inklyuziv o'rganish.

Introduction

Acquiring a foreign language presents difficulties for any learner, but visually impaired (VI) individuals encounter additional barriers. Conventional teaching methods often rely on visual materials, making it difficult for VI learners to access resources. B1-level learners, who have already developed basic language skills, must expand their vocabulary, refine grammar, and improve their ability to engage in more complex conversations. At this stage, personalized learning experiences and accessible educational resources are crucial for their progress.

AI offers a promising approach to overcoming these challenges by enabling adaptive learning, providing immediate feedback, and facilitating independent study. This paper explores how AI technologies can be leveraged to support VI learners at

the B1 level, focusing on their specific needs and proposing effective teaching strategies that integrate AI-driven solutions.

Needs of VI B1-Level Learners

B1-level learners, as defined by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)¹, can comprehend straightforward language on familiar topics, manage routine interactions, and express thoughts on personal interests, experiences, and aspirations. VI learners at this stage require tailored support to further develop their fluency and accuracy. Key considerations include:

Accessible Learning Materials – Traditional textbooks and worksheets are often inaccessible, necessitating formats such as braille, audio, or screen reader-compatible digital resources.

Personalized Feedback – Immediate and specific feedback on pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary is vital for language development, yet often difficult to obtain.

Opportunities for Practice – Engaging in real-world conversations and practicing language skills can be limited, particularly in classroom settings that lack inclusive teaching methods.

Independent Learning – While autonomy is essential for language development at this level, VI learners may require additional support in navigating digital resources effectively.

AI Technologies for Language Learning

Several AI-driven tools can enhance the language learning experience for VI learners²:

Speech Recognition³ – AI-powered speech recognition software provides real-time feedback on pronunciation, facilitating spoken language improvement through dictation and interactive exercises.

Text-to-Speech (TTS) & Speech-to-Text (STT) – These technologies convert written text into audio and vice versa, allowing VI learners to access reading materials and engage in writing activities through voice input. In this way VI learners have access to reading resources and are able to practise speaking skill according to those materials.

¹ Council of Europe. (2001). Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment. Cambridge University Press.

² Fryer, L., MacDonald, R., & Voyles, M. (2019). Developing accessible language learning resources for visually impaired learners. *British Journal of Visual Impairment*, 37(2), 172-184.

³ Walker, D. (2017). Using speech recognition technology to improve pronunciation in EFL learners. *TESL-EJ*, 21(3), 1-15.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) – NLP technology analyzes grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure, offering personalized language exercises and adaptive learning materials. They make learning process suitable and accessible for every learner's needs and interests.

Machine Translation – Although not a substitute for direct language learning, AI-based translation tools help VI learners access and understand foreign-language content.

AI-Powered Chatbots – Chatbots simulate real-life conversations, allowing learners to practice speaking and receive contextual feedback. These tools can create interactive scenarios that enhance engagement.

Pedagogical Strategies for AI Integration

For AI to be effectively incorporated into teaching foreign languages to VI B1-level learners, structured implementation is necessary:

Assess Learner Needs – Identify each learner's challenges and learning preferences to select the most suitable AI tools.

Ensure Accessibility – Choose AI tools that support screen readers, keyboard navigation, and audio output to ensure inclusivity.

Develop Personalized Learning Plans – Integrate AI-based solutions to address individual learning goals and skill gaps⁴.

Train Educators – Provide teachers with training on AI tools and best practices for supporting VI learners.

Encourage Collaborative Learning – Utilize AI-driven activities that promote peer interaction and communication.

Conduct Regular Evaluations – Monitor AI implementation and adjust strategies to optimize learning outcomes.

Benefits of AI in Language Learning for VI Learners

Integrating AI into foreign language education for VI learners offers numerous advantages:

Enhanced Accessibility – AI tools make language learning resources more available and adaptable.

Personalized Learning – AI tailors lessons and exercises to meet individual learner needs.

Increased Engagement – Interactive AI-powered tools keep learners motivated and actively involved in language practice.

⁴ Hertel, M. (2020). Artificial intelligence in language learning. Routledge.

Improved Language Skills⁵ – AI-assisted feedback helps refine pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary.

Greater Independence – AI fosters autonomy by enabling self-paced learning and reducing reliance on external assistance.

Challenges of AI Integration

Despite its benefits, integrating AI into language learning for VI learners presents several challenges:

Technical Limitations – Ensuring AI tools are fully accessible and compatible with assistive technology can be complex.

High Costs – Some advanced AI tools may be expensive, restricting access for certain learners and institutions. They require registration and fee payment that creates some inconveniences for learners with limited budget.

Teacher Training Requirements – Educators need adequate training to effectively incorporate AI tools into their teaching methods. For younger generation of teachers it will not be so complicated to catch up with modern gadgets and AI programs. However, for older generation these technology skills are difficult to understand and implement.

Ethical Considerations – Issues such as data privacy and algorithmic bias must be addressed to ensure fair and ethical AI implementation.

Over-Reliance on Technology – While AI is a valuable aid, human interaction remains essential in language learning to develop social and cultural understanding. Being extremely dependant on AI leads learners to isolation, due to the fact that they interact with technology rather than people and as a result there is little development in social and cultural understanding.

Conclusion

AI has the potential to transform foreign language education for visually impaired B1-level learners by making resources more accessible, providing personalized learning experiences, and fostering greater autonomy. However, successful implementation requires thoughtful planning, teacher training, and ongoing assessment. Addressing challenges such as technical accessibility, cost, and ethical concerns is crucial to ensuring equitable learning opportunities. Future research should explore the long-term effects of AI in language learning for VI learners and focus on developing more inclusive, cost-effective AI-powered educational tools.

⁵ Holland, V. M. (2016). Assistive technology for visually impaired learners: A review of the literature. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 110(6), 525-538.

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MAIN FEATURES OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Digital education refers to methods of learning and teaching that utilize digital technologies and internet resources within the modern education system. This article discusses the main characteristics of digital education, its impact on the educational process, and the opportunities it creates for students, learners, and educators. Through the key components of digital education, the interactivity, individualization, distance learning opportunities, and the expansion of personalized support needs help improve the quality of education. The article focuses on the importance of creating a more effective, engaging, and adaptable learning process in digital education. The abstract describes the crucial role of digital education in the field of education, the innovations it has introduced into the education system, and its future development possibilities.*

Key words: *Digital education, interactive learning, distance learning, individualized learning, online platform, e-learning, virtual lessons, gamification.*

Introduction

The education system in modern society is undergoing a fundamental transformation. Every day, rapidly developing technologies and digital innovations are bringing significant changes to the field of education. Digital education encompasses methods of learning and teaching at every stage through digital tools, internet resources, and modern platforms. Such innovations create new opportunities and teaching methods that meet the demands of the time for students, learners, and educators.

The main features of digital education include interactivity, individualization, distance learning, and the expansion of personalized support opportunities. This helps to make the learning process more effective, engaging, and vivid. Compared to traditional methods, the digital education system allows learning to be organized not only through conventional lessons but also tailored to the unique needs of each learner.

In this article, we will discuss the main characteristics of digital education, their significance in the education system, as well as previous research and new opportunities.

Methodology

This article explores the key characteristics of digital education. The aim is to analyze the effective and innovative methods of digital technologies used in modern education systems and their impact on the educational process. The methodology is

based on studying digital education methods, with each aspect being analyzed in detail through practical experiences and contemporary research.

The following methods will be applied in the development of the article:

1. Theoretical Analysis: The theoretical foundations of digital education, its core concepts, and their impact on the educational process will be analyzed.

2. Comparative Method: A comparison will be made between digital education and traditional teaching methods, analyzing their advantages and disadvantages.

3. Practice-Oriented Research: The practical effectiveness of digital education, particularly in terms of its impact on students and teachers, will be examined.

4. Study of Educational Technologies: The role and significance of digital platforms, online courses, mobile learning, and gamification methods in the educational process will be investigated.

Through this methodology, the article will present clear and comprehensive information and analyses on the key characteristics of digital education and its influence on modern education.

Discussion and Results

Digital education is the process of acquiring and imparting knowledge through the use of technologies and digital platforms. It integrates traditional teaching methods with digital tools such as computers, smartphones, the internet, online courses, videos, interactive platforms, and more. Digital education aims to create effective and interactive learning opportunities for students by leveraging modern technologies in the educational process.

Key Features of Digital Education:

1. Internet-Based Learning – Acquiring education through online courses, webinars, e-books, and similar resources.

Online Courses: These are educational programs organized through digital platforms. They can be asynchronous (where students can learn at their own pace) or synchronous (conducted in real-time with interactive communication between the teacher and students). Online courses typically include video lessons, quizzes, assignments, and discussion forums.

Webinars: These are seminars conducted in an online format on various topics. They bring together experts and learners to explore new subjects, engage in debates, or organize training sessions. During webinars, participants can ask questions, participate in live discussions, and receive immediate feedback.

E-books: These are digital versions of books designed for downloading or online reading. They can be accessed on smartphones, tablets, or dedicated e-readers. E-books are convenient, portable, and easy to distribute. Additionally, they may include interactive features and multimedia elements.

2. Mobile and Computer-Based Learning – accessing educational materials via mobile devices and computers, providing students with knowledge through advanced technologies.

Mobile Learning refers to the process of learning through smartphones and tablets. This method allows students to access education anytime and anywhere. Through mobile learning platforms, students can easily access video lessons, interactive tests, and resources. Additionally, mobile apps and educational programs can provide additional assistance in understanding the lesson content.

Teaching via computers typically involves more complexity and greater functionality. Computer-based educational platforms often host complete courses, laboratory exercises, simulations, and real-time interactive sessions. In computer-based learning, students can view various multimedia materials, live lessons, diagrams, and animations, which make the learning process more engaging and effective.

3. Interactivity – an essential and integral part of modern education, which helps make the relationship between students and teachers more effective and active. The primary goal of this method is to enliven the learning process, engage students actively, and assist them in identifying problems. Interactive learning plays a crucial role in transforming students from passive observers into active participants.

Video Courses – these are lessons in video format. Video courses are significant for ensuring interactivity, as they can include questions, tests, or practical exercises as supplementary content. After watching the entire video course, students are often offered several questions or discussion topics. This helps students express their thoughts on the material covered in the video.

Tests – an interactive method used to check students' knowledge levels. Typically, tests are automatically graded, and students receive their results immediately. This method allows students to quickly identify their mistakes and take corrective actions. Tests can also incorporate gamification elements to make them more engaging and active.

Forums – these are online discussions between students and teachers, through which students can exchange ideas, ask questions, and help each other. On forums,

students often express their opinions, engage in debates on various topics, and thereby expand their knowledge.

4. Gamification is a method of incorporating game elements into the learning process. This helps make the learning process not only more interesting but also more effective and motivating. Gamification includes games, digital tools, and interactive elements aimed at activating students, increasing their interest in learning, and making the acquisition of knowledge more enjoyable. This method makes education more attractive and impactful compared to traditional methods.

Games (Gamification Elements): Games help increase motivation and ensure student engagement in learning. For example, when a student completes assigned tasks, they collect points, and when they achieve goals, they receive rewards or tokens. Such accumulating points and rewards boost the student's motivation, encouraging them to complete new tasks.

Digital Tools: Digital tools (apps, websites, platforms) play a key role in integrating gamification into the learning process. Through them, students can engage in various interactive games, quizzes, exercises, and tests. These tools also allow for the rapid and efficient acquisition of information and help track how students solve problems.

Tokens and Rewards: One of the essential components of gamification is the provision of tokens and rewards to assess students' achievements. When students reach specific goals, they may receive rewards (certificates, collectible points). This not only motivates them but also adds more appeal to the learning process.

Engaging Content and Quizzes: One of the important factors in making content engaging and interesting in gamification is quizzes or interactive exercises. Offering quizzes to students for analysis and problem-solving helps assess their knowledge level accurately and increases their interest in learning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

As a result of studying the main characteristics of digital education, the following key conclusions can be drawn:

1. Innovation and Modernization: Digital education enhances the learning process by integrating new methods and technologies. Online platforms, virtual laboratories, and gamification techniques increase student engagement and improve learning efficiency.

2. Accessibility and Inclusiveness: Digital education expands access to educational resources. This is especially important for students in remote areas or

those with limited access to traditional learning materials. Mobile learning and online courses allow learners to acquire knowledge anytime and anywhere.

3. Personalized Learning: With the help of digital technologies, personalized learning programs can be designed to match each student's learning style. This enables students to absorb essential knowledge more effectively.

4. Comparative Advantages: Compared to traditional teaching methods, digital education offers benefits such as saving time and financial resources, quickly updating educational materials, and improving communication between students and teachers.

5. Teacher-Student Interaction: Digital education transforms the role of teachers, making them not just knowledge providers but also mentors and facilitators. This helps students develop independent thinking and creativity.

6. Challenges and Limitations: Despite all its advantages, digital education faces challenges such as data security, technical issues, and insufficient professional training. To overcome these obstacles, the development of specialized programs and resources is necessary.

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DEVELOPING STUDENT'S SPEAKING SKILLS BY TASK BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract: *Language teaching is not just about teaching languages, it is also about helping students to develop themselves as people. Task-based language teaching (TBLT) proposes the use of tasks as a central component in the language classroom because they provide better contexts for activating learner acquisition processes and promoting second language learning. Speaking skill is one of the crucial parts learning and teaching another language. In the process of the learning speaking skills, the students learn to communicate in real situations. This article discussed the methods which are helpful and effective for the students' speaking skills related to the task based language. Moreover, there are three phrases of task-based language: pre-task, task and language focus.*

Key words: *teaching and learning language, task-based approach, pre-task, task and focus of language, types of task, CLT.*

Nowadays, person who wants to learn second language pays attention to every detail of the language. To know how to write they learn the letters, after that they learn how to read and for communication and understanding natives they learn pronunciation. The new language for being more understandable, nowadays there are strategies that are very vital in creating meaningful communication. For teaching it, modern teachers use the Task Based Language Teaching (TBLT) which offers students material that they have to actively engage in the processing of in order to achieve a goal or complete a task. TBLT is a traditional approach which there are three types (Grammar Translation, Audiolingual Method and Direct Method). These approaches help to manage the language learning process and being focused. As a coin, everything has two as this point. One side was learning to speak with grammar rules, another side is being focused to language learning as interaction. This approach will lead the students to talk more during the class and outside the class in many activities like to talk about themselves, to have a joke, to give an idea, without thinking whether the structure is correct or incorrect as they have fun in English class. However, person's personality also plays main and large role on the process, like how correctly or quickly person answer or learn. Additionally, being risk-taker and unafraid of making mistakes makes person talkative and extrovert, but they do not realize their mistakes. Being introvert helps to learn and practice more and they will

do fewer mistakes and they try to do not repeat more, and this kind of people will be proud of their language. For them do not doing mistakes and practicing every day because of sounding like natives gives them motivation.

However, nowadays some students give up when they have various problems like lack of motivation or being lazy because of unhealthy lifestyle. Language teachers are in search of finding something that could create a difference in their classroom.

The concept of TBLT was first introduced by Prabhu (1987) in his Bangalore Project in which he focused on communication, not on explicit grammar teaching, by engaging learners in doing „task“. In the past 20 years, task-based language teaching (TBLT) has attracted the attention of second language acquisition (SLA) researchers, curriculum developers, educationalists, trainers and language teachers worldwide. To a great extent, the introduction of TBLT into the world of language education has been a „top-down“ process (Bygate, Skehan & Swain, 2001). The term was coined, and the concept developed, by SLA researchers and language educators, largely in reaction to empirical accounts of teacher-dominated, form-oriented second language classroom practice. Tasks have been widely used as vehicles to elicit language production, interaction, negotiation of meaning, processing of input and focus on form, all of which are believed to foster second language acquisition (Skehan, 1996)

Now I did search and learn deeper the phrase TBLT, the meaning and when and what kind of situation the teachers should use this term. Most people have a question: What is the TBLT? “Task-Based Learning (TBL) is a lesson structure, a method of sequencing activities in your lessons. Sometimes called 'task-based language teaching', in TBL lessons, students solve a task that involves an authentic use of language rather than complete simple questions about grammar or vocabulary.” There are examples of task-based learning, like creating a presentation, making videos, writing a piece of text or acting out a skit. In addition, there are advantages of task-based learning, **Students are at the center of learning**. Students are working on something that is personal and relevant to them. Students gain practice in collaborating with others and making group decisions. Students spend a lot of time communicating each other. As mentioned before, task-based language structure which includes, pre-task, task (main task) and language focus (post task).

Stage 1: The pre-task. The teacher introduces the new topic and familiarizes students with situations, lexical areas, texts like reading and listening. This engages

the pupils with the subject and introduces potentially helpful terminology. After that, the instructor sets up the activity and explains what it is.

Stage 2: Task. Task-based learning is an approach to language learning where learners are given interactive tasks to complete. In order to do this, they need to communicate. Once the task is complete, then the teacher discusses the language used. The learners plan an itinerary for a guest who is coming to stay with their teacher. The task, according to Willis (1996), is a goal-based activity that uses the learners' preexisting linguistic resources to achieve the desired result. Playing games and figuring out puzzles and issues are a couple of examples.

Stage 3: Post task. A more thorough examination of some of the structures or particular characteristics present in the language employed during the task cycle is made possible by the framework's Post-Task phase, or language focus. As previously stated, the teacher has the ability to evaluate the students' progress at various points during the learning process. Students assess their performance during the post-task phase. This could be accomplished by contrasting their task's results with those of a fluent language user. Additionally, the teacher's response and subsequent practice of the language items that arose from the exercise may be included.

In the past, linguists had a research about types of task. According to N. S. Prabhu (who noticed that his students could learn language just as easily with non-linguistic problem as when they were concentrating on linguistic questions while working in Bangalore), there are three main categories of task. There are information-gap, reasoning-gap and opinion-gap.

Information-gap: Activities that include communication between two or more students are referred to as information gap (or information exchange) activities. They require students to verbally communicate various bits of information to one another. It normally calls for the decoding or encoding of information from or into language and entails the transmission of supplied information from one person to another, from one form to another, or from one location to another. One instance is pair work, when one partner tries to verbally communicate a portion of the entire information (for instance, an incomplete picture) to the other partner. Completing a tabular representation using data from a certain text is another example. The task frequently include choosing pertinent material as well, and students may need to fulfill requirements for accuracy and completeness in their transfer.

Reasoning-gap activity: It entails using techniques of inference, deduction, practical reasoning, or the sense of links or patterns to derive some new information from provided information. Making a teacher's schedule based on the class schedules

that are provided is one example. Another is determining the optimum course of action (e.g., shortest or least expensive) for a given goal and given restrictions. Like in an information-gap action, the activity inevitably entails understanding and communicating information, but the information that must be communicated differs from that which was first understood. There is a piece of reasoning which connects the two.

Opinion gap activity: Identifying and expressing a personal choice, emotion, or attitude in reaction to a particular circumstance is known as an opinion gap. Completing a tale is one example; participating in a social problem conversation is another. There is no objective process for proving that an outcome is right or wrong, and there is no reason to expect the same result from various people or on multiple occasions, even when the activity may involve using factual information and creating arguments to support one's opinion.

As TBLT, modern teachers also use communicative language teaching (CLT) that is a method of teaching languages that places a strong emphasis on interaction as the methods and the end aim of learning. The communicative approach is predicated on the notion that effective language acquisition requires the ability to convey genuine meaning. Learners use the communication skills while they study or practice the target language by communicate with their partners, friends or trainers. The ability to communicate in the target language is the aim of language instruction, according to CLT. This contrasts with earlier perspectives that frequently placed a higher value on grammatical proficiency. Also, CLT views the teacher not as an instructor but as a facilitator. Additionally, the technique is a non-methodical methodology that focuses on building strong oral and verbal skills before reading and writing, rather than using a textbook series to teach the target language. CLT instructors select lessons according to what they think will help students improve their conversational skills in the target language (TL). Because oral activities involve active discussion and students' creative, unexpected responses, CLT teachers prefer them to grammar drills or reading and writing exercises. Depending on the language class level, different activities are used. They encourage cooperation, fluency, and TL comfort. In CLT classrooms, the six exercises mentioned and described below are frequently utilized.

New roles for instructors and students in the classroom were also suggested by the kinds of classroom activities suggested in CLT. Students were now required to engage in cooperative learning activities instead of individualistic ones in the classroom method of education. Instead of looking to the teacher as an example,

students have to learn how to listen to their peers in group or pair projects. They were supposed to assume more accountability for their own education. Teachers were now required to take on the roles of monitor and facilitator. Instead of serving as a role model for proper writing and speaking and primarily tasked with ensuring that students generate a large number of error-free sentences, the teacher needed to adopt a new perspective on students' mistakes and of her/his personal contribution to language acquisition.

There are different kind of practices in CLT, mechanical, meaningful and communicative.

Mechanical practice: Students can successfully complete a controlled practice task known as "mechanical practice" even if they don't completely comprehend the language they are using. Repetition drills and substitution drills, which are intended to practice the use of certain grammatical or other items, are examples of this type of activity.

Meaningful practice: Meaningful practice is an activity in which students must make meaningful decisions when practicing, while still receiving language control. To practice using prepositions to describe, for instance locations: students may be provided with a street map that shows the locations of different buildings. Additionally, a list of prepositions such across from, on the corner of, near, on, and next to is provided to them. After that, they must respond to inquiries such "Where is the book shop? "Where is the café?" and so forth. Now that they must react based on where locations are on the map, the exercise has value.

Communicative practice: Communicative practice is defined as activities that emphasize language use in authentic communicative contexts, when actual information is shared and language usage is not entirely predictable. For instance, students may be required to sketch a map of their neighborhood and respond to questions regarding the locations of various locations, such as the closest café or bus stop.

Conclusion

Both teachers and students of English benefit greatly from task-based learning. Teachers must first determine the general structure of the lesson. However, because the major activity of a lesson is mostly subjective and somewhat arbitrary, it can occasionally be challenging to identify. After deciding on a lesson's fundamental framework, it is possible to think about the particular possibilities that should be offered in each lesson sentence. Practically implementing task-based learning requires careful consideration of the many course components, and task-based

learning has traditionally relied on group and pair work. Both task-based learning and communicative language instruction will be used in the classroom to assist students retain all of the material.

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LINGVOPRAGMATIKANING O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILSHUNOSLIGIDA O'RGANILISHI

Robiddinova Dilnoza Barkamol qizi

10.00.04 - Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti yo'nalishi tayanch doktoranti

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tilshunoslikning bir bo'limi bo'lgan pragmatika tushunchasi, uning kommunikatsiyadagi o'rni va ma'no shakllanishi jarayoni tahlil qilinadi. Deixsis, implikatura, presuppozitsiya va nutq aktlari kabi asosiy pragmatik hodisalarga e'tibor qaratilib, ularning muloqotdagi samaradorligi o'rganiladi. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjimada pragmatikaning ahamiyati, tarjimon duch keladigan muammolar va yashirin ma'nolarni yetkazish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada pragmatikaning reklama, siyosat va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyadagi ta'siri ham yoritilib, tilshunoslik va tarjima tadqiqotlari uchun ilmiy ahamiyati ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Pragmatika, deixsis, implikatura, presuppozitsiya, nutq aktlari, tarjima pragmatikasi, kontekstual ma'no, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya.

Abstract. This article explores the concept of pragmatics, a subfield of linguistics that examines how meaning is constructed and understood in communication. It delves into key pragmatic phenomena such as deixis, implicature, presupposition, and speech acts, emphasizing their role in effective discourse. Special attention is given to the pragmatics of translation from Uzbek to English, highlighting the challenges translators face in conveying implicit meanings and cultural nuances. The study also addresses the impact of pragmatics in various contexts, including advertising, politics, and cross-cultural communication. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of linguistic pragmatics and its significance in translation studies.

Keywords: Pragmatics, deixis, implicature, presupposition, speech acts, translation pragmatics, contextual meaning, intercultural communication.

Pragmatika – bu tilshunoslikning bo'limlaridan biri bo'lib, unda so'z va gaplarning ma'no jihatdan qanday tushunilishi o'rganiladi. Pragmatika faqatgina so'zlarning lug'aviy yoki grammatik ma'nolariga emas, balki ularning muloqot jarayonidagi qo'llanilishiga, gapiruvchining niyatiga va suhbat kontekstiga ham e'tibor qaratadi.

Pragmatikaning asosiy tushunchalari:

Deixsis – so'z yoki iboralarning ma'nosi faqat kontekstga qarab aniqlanadigan holatlar, masalan: men, bu yerda, ertaga.

Implikatura – ochiq aytilmagan, lekin tushunilishi kerak bo'lgan ma'no, masalan: "Derazani ochib yuborasanmi?" – bu haqiqiy savol emas, balki iltimos sifatida tushuniladi.

Presuppozitsiya – gapirilayotgan narsaning ilgari mavjud bo'lganligini anglatadigan holat, masalan: "Akam chekishni tashladi." – bu gapdan ilgari u chekish bilan shug'ullangan deb tushuniladi.

Nutq aktlari – odamlarning soʻz orqali amalga oshiradigan harakatlari, masalan: iltimos qilish, buyurish, vaʼda berish.

Hamkorlik printsiipi – Pol Grays (Paul Grice) tomonidan ilgari surilgan nazariya boʻlib, u suhbat ishtirokchilari muloqotni tushunarli va samarali qilishga harakat qilishini tushuntiradi.

Pragmatika kundalik hayotda tilning qanday ishlashini tushunishga yordam beradi. U hazil, kinoya, odob-axloq qoidalari va muloqotdagi turli maʼnolarni anglashda muhim rol oʻynaydi.

Oʻzbek tilidan ingliz tiliga amalga oshiriladigan tarjima jarayoni, uning oʻziga xos xususiyatlari, unda tarjimon ahamiyat berishi lozim boʻlgan masalalar, tilshunoslikda asliyatning pragmatik xususiyatlari va uni qayta tiklashning oʻziga xosliklari, ish faoliyatida tarjimonga yengillik berishi mumkin boʻlgan jihatlar va u yoʻl qoʻyishi mumkin boʻlgan xatolarning oldi olinadi. Pragmatika (yunoncha pragma, pragmatos - ish, harakat) - semiotika va tilshunoslikning nutqda til belgilarining amal qilishini oʻrganuvchi sohasi; boshqacha aytganda, muayyan belgilar tizimini oʻzlashtirib, undan foydalanuvchi subʼyektlarning ayni shu belgilar tizimiga munosabatini oʻrganuvchi fan tarmogʻi. Pragmatika haqidagi asosiy gʻoya amerikalik olim Charlz Sanders Pirs tomonidan oʻrtaga tashlangan; yana bir amerikalik olim Charlz Uilyam Morris ushbu gʻoyani rivojlantirgan va " Pragmatika " terminini semiotika boʻlimlaridan birining nomi sifatida amaliyotga kiritgan. Pragmatika insonning ijtimoiy faoliyatini oʻzida qamrab oluvchi nutq jarayoni, muayyan aloqa vaziyati orqali namoyon boʻladi. Lingvistik Pragmatika aniq shakl, tashqi koʻrinishga ega emas; uning doirasiga soʻzlovchi subʼyekt, adresat, ularning aloqa-aralashuvdagi oʻzaro munosabatlari, aloqa-aralashuv vaziyati bilan bogʻliq koʻplab masalalar kiradi. Masalan, nutq subʼyekti bilan bogʻliq holda quyidagi masalalar oʻrganiladi: bayonning oshkora va yashirin maqsadlari (biron-bir axborot yoki fikrni yetkazish, soʻroq, buyruq, iltimos, maslahat vaʼda berish, uzr soʻrash, tabriklash, shikoyat va boshqalar); nutq taktikasi hamda nutq odobi turlari; suhbat, soʻzlashish qoidalari; soʻzlovchining maqsadi; soʻzlovchi tomonidan adresatning umumiy bilim jamgʻarmasi, dunyoqarashi, qiziqishlari va boshqa xislatlariga baho berilishi; soʻzlovchining oʻzi bayon qilayotgan xabarga munosabati kabilar. Pragmatikada nutq adresati, oʻzaro aloqaga kiruvchilarning munosabatlari, muayyan aloqa vaziyati singari omillar bilan bogʻliq qolda ham koʻplab masalalar oʻrganiladi. Pragmatika gʻoyalari evristik (yoʻnaltiruvchi) dasturlash, mashina tarjimasini, informatsion-qidiruv tizimlari va boshqalarni ishlab chiqishda qoʻllanadi. Har bir tarjima jarayonida maʼno kasb etuvchi gaplar va tagma'noga ega soʻzlar sifatida ikki

bosqichdan o'tadi. Shunday bo'lsada toki nutq faoliyatining madaniyatlararo shakli mavjud emas ekan tarjimon uchun Tilshunoslikning pragmatik muammolari ham mavjud bo'ladi. Shunga ko'ra, tarjimon ma'lumotni tilshunoslikda hech qanday xatoliksiz to'g'ri etkazib berish uchun umummadaniy pragmatik bilimlaridan foydalanishiga to'g'ri keladi. Nutq hodisasi va emotsional ta'sirni yaqindan o'rganish tabiiyki, tilshunoslikning bir nechta nazariyalarini keltirib chiqaradi, ayniqsa ekvivalent ta'sir yoki harakat prinsipiga va boshqa tilda qanday bo'lsa shunday aytish kerakligini ta'kidlovchi «yolg'on talqin»ga asoslangan dinamik ekvivalentlik. Har ikkala nazariya ham nutq faoliyati va hodisasi madaniyatlararo farq qilishini tan olgan holda tarjimonlarni madaniyatlararo pragmatik muvaffaqiyatga erishishga undaydi. Ammo tilshunoslikda pragmatik ekvivalentlikka erishishda aslyatdagi matn tilining semantik xususiyatlari, so'zlarning ma'nolari, ularning qo'llanilishi va boshqa so'zlar bilan bog'lanishi bir qancha to'sqinliklarni keltirib chiqaradi [3]. Tilshunoslikning aslyatga shaklan va mazmunan monand tarzda yaratilishining birdan-bir sharti tarjimonning o'z tilida asly monand lisoniy vositalar tanlab ishlata olishidir. Bu mas'uliyat uning zimmasiga avvalo aslyat ma'no vazifasini bekamuko'st ado etish, so'ngra xotirasida shakllangan fikrni o'z tili madaniyati va me'yori asosida to'la-to'kis ifoda etish vazifasini yuklaydi. Keyingi yillarda tadqiqotchilar e'tiborini o'ziga ko'proq jalb qilib kelayotgan tilning pragmatik jihatlari tarjimondan chuqur lingvistik bilimdan tashqari yana ko'pgina boshqa fanlar, madaniyatlar ma'lumotlaridan ham xabardor bo'lishni talab qiladi. Tilshunoslikda pragmatik vositalardan o'rinli foydalanish esa aslyatda ifodalangan zaruriy ma'noni to'la-to'kis etkazib berishga xizmat qiladi. Shundan kelib chiqadigan bo'lsak, mazkur dissertatsion ishning amaliy ahamiyati shundan iboratki, tilshunoslikning pragmatik xususiyatlari haqida to'liq ma'lumotga ega bo'lib, ularning tahlilini, tilshunoslikda berilishini, asosli misollar bilan yoritilgan bo'lib mavzu bo'yicha talabalar uchun qo'shimcha yoki asosiy qo'llanma sifatida o'zlarining mustaqil ishlarida, referatlarida foydalanish yoki ma'ruza matnlariga maxsus mavzu sifatida kiritish mumkin. Bundan tashqari o'rganilgan korpus bilimlarni amalda qo'llash, tilshunoslikning pragmatik xususiyatlaridan foydalanib tarjima jarayonida uchraydigan har qanday leksik-grammatik muammolarni bartaraf qilish, shuningdek, nutq, badiiy asarlarda duch kelingan muammolarni tahlil qila olish tadqiqotning amaliy ahamiyatini tashkil etadi. Pragmatika tilshunoslikning nisbatan yangidan shakllangan, insonning nutq faoliyatini o'rganishga, bunday faoliyatning maqsadi, mazmuni, bunday maqsad va mazmunning og'zaki va yozma matnda verbal va noverbal ifodalanish vositalarini, ularning nutq aktidagi o'rnini, kommunikativ ta'sirini, so'zlovchi va tinglovchi

nutqidagi turlicha munosabatlarni lisoniy belgilarda ifodalanishini o'rganuvchi fan tarmog'idir. Pragmatika til belgilarining nutqdagi harakatini o'rganuvchi tilshunoslikning tadqiqot doirasidir. Lingvistik pragmatika aniq shaklga ega emas. Uning tarkibiga so'zlovchi va tinglovchiga, ularning nutq jarayonidagi o'zaro munosabatiga bog'liq masalalar majmui kiradi. Gapiruvchi shaxsning tinglovchi diqqat-e'tiborini tortish, ularga kommunikativ ta'sir qilish, qiziqtirib qo'yish, fikrini jalb qilish yoki aksincha, chalg'itish, hayajonga solish, to'lqinlashtirish, ishontirish yoki aldashga urinishida so'zning, so'z birikmasining ekspressivemotsional-baholovchi konnotativ ma'nosini, ya'ni pragmatik ma'nosini tadqiq qilish ehtiyoji vujudga keldi. So'zlovchi biror nutq yaratar ekan, u o'zining bu faoliyati bilan qabul qiluvchiga (tinglovchi) qandaydir axborotni etkazishni, kechmishlarini bayon etishni, atrofimizda kechayotgan yangiliklarni etkazishni nazarda tutadi. Bu orqali so'zlovchi retseptorga ma'lum ta'sir ham o'tkazadi. Retseptorga nutq orqali ko'rsatiladigan ta'sir pragmatik xususiyatlar orqali amalga oshiriladi.

Lingvopragmatika – bu tilshunoslik (lingvistika) va pragmatika fanlarining qo'shilishidan hosil bo'lgan yo'nalish bo'lib, til vositalarining ma'no jihatdan qanday ishlatilishini va qanday pragmatik ta'sir ko'rsatishini o'rganadi. Ya'ni, lingvopragmatika tilning muloqot jarayonida qanday tushunilishi va gapiruvchi bilan tinglovchi o'rtasidagi aloqaga qanday ta'sir qilishi masalalariga e'tibor qaratadi.

Til – bu qoidalar tizimi, nutq esa shu qoidalar asosida shakllangan muloqot jarayoni.

Lingvopragmatika ushbu nutqiy jarayonda so'z va gaplarning yashirin, kontekstga bog'liq bo'lgan ma'nolarini o'rganadi.

So'z va gaplar doimo muayyan kontekstda ishlatiladi.

Masalan, "Siz juda ajoyib joyni tanladingiz!" degan gap kinoya (ironiya) bilan aytilishi mumkin, lekin uning haqiqiy ma'nosi faqat kontekst orqali aniqlanadi.

Gapiruvchi odam faqat so'z ishlatmaydi, balki harakat bajaradi (masalan, iltimos qiladi, buyruq beradi, maslahat beradi).

Masalan, "Shu joyni supurib qo'ysang bo'lardi!" – bu haqiqatan ham oddiy mulohaza emas, balki iltimos yoki buyruq sifatida qabul qilinishi mumkin.

Deixis – so'zlarning ma'nosi vaqt va joyga bog'liq bo'lishi. Masalan, men, shu yerda, hozir so'zlari turli kontekstlarda har xil ma'no beradi.

Referensiya – so'z yoki iboralar orqali muayyan narsa yoki shaxsga ishora qilish. Masalan, "U bugun kelmaydi" deganda "u" kim ekanligi kontekst orqali tushuniladi.

Har bir jamiyatda o'ziga xos muloqot madaniyati mavjud.

Masalan, o'zbek tilida "iltimos" shaklidagi iboralar ko'proq ishlatiladi ("Agar iloji bo'lsa...", "Sizdan bir narsa so'ramoqchiman..."), bu esa muloqotdagi odob-axloq qoidalarini ko'rsatadi.

Reklama matnlarida so'zlarning yashirin ta'sir kuchi bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, "Siz bunga loyiqsiz!" shiori odamni o'z mahsulotini sotib olishga undaydi.

Siyosiy nutqlarda pragmatik ta'sir juda muhim. Masalan, "Biz ba'zi masalalarda murosaga kelishimiz mumkin" degan gap to'g'ridan-to'g'ri rad javobi emas, balki yumshoq noaniqlik bilan aytilgan fikrdir.

Pragmatik ma'no tarjima jarayonida ham e'tiborga olinishi kerak. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi "I see" ifodasi bevosita tarjimada "Men ko'ryapman" deb tushunilishi mumkin, lekin aslida "Men tushundim" degan ma'noni anglatadi.

Lingvopragmatika – bu til va muloqotdagi yashirin ma'nolarni, kontekstni va gapiruvchi-tinglovchi munosabatlarini o'rganadigan soha. U reklama, siyosat, tarjima, diplomatiya va kundalik muloqotda juda muhim o'rin tutadi.

Ijtimoiy fanlar bo'yicha fransuz olimi Dan Sperber va ingliz lingvisti Deirdre Wilson pragmatikaga shunday ta'rif bergan: "Pragmatika ko'pincha tildan foydalanishni o'rganish sifatida tavsiflanadi va til tuzilishini o'rganishga qarama-qarshi qo'yiladi. Ushbu keng ma'noda u deydik iboralarni rasmiy o'rganishdan tortib etnik og'zaki stereotiplarni sotsiologik tadqiqotlarga bo'lgan bir qator erkin bog'liq tadqiqot dasturlarini qamrab oladi. Ko'proq yo'naltirilgan ma'noda (biz bu erda foydalanamiz) pragmatika semantikaga qarama-qarshi qo'yadi, lingvistik ma'noni o'rganadi va iboralarni izohlashda kontekst omillarining lingvistik ma'no bilan o'zaro ta'sirini o'rganadi. Bu erda biz so'nggi o'ttiz yil ichida tilshunoslar va til faylasuflarini qiziqtirgan bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liq, juda markaziy pragmatik masalalar va yondashuvlarni qisqacha ta'kidlaymiz. Pragmatika, biz ta'riflaganimizdek, empirik fan, lekin falsafiy kelib chiqishi va falsafiy ahamiyati bor."¹

J. Lichning fikricha, "pragmatika tilshunoslikning bir qismi bo'lib, gaplar kontekstda qanday qilib turli ma'nolarga ega bo'lishini o'rganadi. Til kommunikativ tizim sifatida rasmiy tizim sifatida tilni (so'zning keng ma'nosida grammatika) va uni to'ldiruvchi pragmatikani o'z ichiga oladi. Grammatikadan farqli o'laroq, pragmatika aksiologik (maqsadga yo'naltirilgan) va baholovchidir. Shu bilan birga, J. Lich grammatika va ritorikaning yaqinlashishini qonuniy va zarur deb hisoblaydi. Muallifning qayd etishicha, semantika an'anaviy ravishda ma'no bilan diadik munosabatlarning a'zosi (belgi – ob'ekt) sifatida shug'ullanadi, pragmatik esa uch

¹ <https://www.dan.sperber.fr/?p=117>

shaxs (belgi – obyekt – suhbatdosh) munosabatini o'rganadi. Pragmatika kontekstni hisobga olgan holda ma'noni o'rganadi. Shaxslararo munosabatlarni tartibga soluvchi pragmatik tamoyillar ritorika ob'ekti bo'lib, ularni ikki guruhga bo'lish mumkin:

shaxslararo ritorika: hamkorlik tamoyili, xushmuomalalik printsipli va kinoya tamoyili. Bu tamoyillar suhbatdoshlarning muloqotini tartibga soladi;

matnli ritorika: qayta ishlash printsipli, aniqlik printsipli, tejamkorlik printsipli va ekspressivlik printsipli - ular matnni ishlab chiqishni boshqaradi.”²

Bogdanov (1996) ta'kidlashicha: “lingvopragmatika nutqiy aloqa aktlarida suhbatdoshlar tomonidan tildan foydalanish shartlarini o'rganadi. Bu shartlarga kommunikativ maqsadlar, nutq harakatining vaqti va joyi, suhbatdoshlarning bilim darajasi, ularning ijtimoiy mavqei, psixologik va fiziologik xususiyatlari, muayyan jamiyatda qabul qilingan nutq xatti-harakatlarining qoidalari va qoidalari kiradi. Og'zaki muloqot jarayonida suhbatdoshlar u yoki bu kodlardan, shuningdek, boshqa belgilar tizimlaridan, shu jumladan paralingvistiklardan foydalanadilar.

U bu shartlarni quyidagilarga ajratadi:

kontekst (lingvistik shartlar);

konstitutsiya (ekstralingvistik shartlar);

koempiriya (suhbatdoshlarning lingvistik va ekstralingvistik bilim darajasi).”³

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ENHANCING LISTENING AND SPEAKING PROFICIENCY IN VISUALLY IMPAIRED LEARNERS THROUGH INNOVATIVE INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation. *This article explores innovative interactive methods to enhance the listening and speaking skills of visually impaired learners. It examines various pedagogical strategies, including audio-based learning, tactile feedback, and speech recognition technologies, to facilitate language acquisition. The study highlights the role of technology-assisted instruction, such as screen readers, voice-controlled applications, and virtual assistants, in creating an inclusive learning environment. Additionally, interactive methods like peer-assisted learning, role-playing, and storytelling are analyzed for their effectiveness in improving communication skills. The article emphasizes the importance of personalized learning approaches tailored to the needs of visually impaired students. By integrating these methods into language education, educators can foster greater engagement and proficiency in listening and speaking. The findings contribute to the field of special education and language teaching, offering practical solutions for inclusive and effective instruction.*

Keywords: *visually impaired learners, interactive methods, listening skills, speaking proficiency, assistive technology, inclusive education.*

Introduction. The ability to listen and speak effectively is fundamental for language acquisition and communication. However, visually impaired learners face unique challenges in developing these skills due to their reliance on auditory and tactile modalities. Traditional language teaching methods often emphasize visual cues, such as written texts and images, which may not be accessible to these learners. Therefore, it is crucial to implement innovative interactive methods that cater to their specific needs and enhance their listening and speaking proficiency. Technological advancements have opened new possibilities for inclusive education. Assistive technologies, including screen readers, speech recognition software, and voice-controlled applications, have revolutionized language learning for visually impaired students¹.

Additionally, interactive strategies such as peer-assisted learning, storytelling, role-playing, and audio-based instruction have proven effective in fostering engagement and communication skills. By integrating these methods into language instruction, educators can create an inclusive learning environment that enhances accessibility and promotes active participation. This article explores various

¹ Foulke, E. *Blind Learning: Auditory and Tactile Approaches*. – New York, Springer, 2018. – 245 p.

innovative interactive methods that can improve listening and speaking skills among visually impaired learners. It examines their effectiveness, implementation strategies, and potential impact on language education. By adopting these approaches, educators can support visually impaired students in developing linguistic competence and achieving greater autonomy in communication. Visually impaired learners face unique challenges in developing listening and speaking skills due to their reliance on auditory and tactile senses. Traditional language learning methods often integrate visual cues such as text, images, and gestures, which are inaccessible to these learners. As a result, alternative interactive methods must be employed to ensure effective language acquisition.

One of the most effective approaches is audio-based learning, which includes audiobooks, podcasts, and speech-based applications². These resources allow learners to engage with spoken language in an immersive manner, improving their listening comprehension and pronunciation. Additionally, tactile feedback methods, such as Braille-based language exercises and vibration-assisted speech training, can further enhance learners' ability to perceive and reproduce linguistic structures. Technological advancements have significantly contributed to making language learning more accessible for visually impaired students. Screen readers and speech recognition software enable learners to access digital texts and engage in real-time communication. Voice-controlled applications such as Google Assistant, Siri, and Amazon Alexa provide interactive language exercises that help reinforce listening and speaking skills. Moreover, virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are being integrated into language learning to create multisensory experiences. For instance, AI-powered voice analysis tools provide real-time feedback on pronunciation and fluency, helping learners refine their speaking abilities.

Apart from technology, interactive classroom strategies play a vital role in fostering communication skills. Peer-assisted learning is a highly effective approach, where visually impaired students engage in conversational practice with sighted peers³. This method not only enhances linguistic competence but also promotes social integration and confidence. Similarly, role-playing and storytelling activities provide opportunities for learners to practice conversational skills in realistic scenarios. By

² Laitinen, J. *Enhancing Communication in Visually Impaired Students: Innovative Strategies*. – London, Routledge, 2020. – 312 p.

³ Meyer, D. & Fisher, K. *Assistive Technologies in Language Learning: A Guide for Educators*. – Berlin, De Gruyter, 2021. – 280 p.

engaging in structured dialogues and storytelling exercises, students can improve both fluency and expressive abilities. Educators can also implement echo reading and shadowing techniques, where learners listen to recorded speech and repeat it simultaneously to develop pronunciation and rhythm.

A critical aspect of improving listening and speaking proficiency in visually impaired learners is teacher training and curriculum adaptation. Instructors need to be well-versed in using assistive technologies and interactive methods tailored to the needs of these learners⁴. The curriculum should include audio-supported materials, tactile learning resources, and strategies that emphasize verbal communication⁵. Furthermore, incorporating multisensory learning approaches, such as associating sounds with touch-based experiences or using environmental cues for language reinforcement, can enhance comprehension and retention. Despite the effectiveness of these innovative methods, some challenges remain. Limited access to assistive technology, lack of specialized teacher training, and insufficient inclusion of visually impaired learners in mainstream language education are significant barriers. Addressing these issues requires institutional support, funding for accessible educational resources, and collaboration between educators, technology developers, and policymakers.

Moreover, enhancing the listening and speaking skills of visually impaired learners requires a combination of technology-driven solutions and interactive pedagogical strategies. By integrating assistive technologies, peer collaboration, and multisensory learning approaches, educators can create an inclusive and effective language learning environment⁶. Future research should focus on developing more advanced AI-powered language tools and evaluating the long-term impact of these methods on language proficiency among visually impaired students.

Conclusion. The development of listening and speaking skills among visually impaired learners requires innovative and interactive teaching methods that cater to their unique needs. Traditional language learning approaches, which heavily rely on visual stimuli, are often ineffective for these learners. Instead, integrating audio-based learning, assistive technologies, and interactive classroom strategies can significantly enhance their linguistic proficiency.

⁴ Thompson, L. *The Role of Audio-Based Learning in Developing Oral Communication Skills*. – Boston, Pearson, 2022. – 290 p.

⁵ Smith, R. *Interactive Teaching Techniques for Special Needs Education*. – Chicago, University Press, 2019. – 265 p.

⁶ White, M. *Inclusion and Accessibility in Language Learning: A Case Study of Visually Impaired Students*. – Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2023. – 310 p.

Technologies such as screen readers, speech recognition software, and AI-driven pronunciation tools provide valuable support in making language learning more accessible. Additionally, peer-assisted learning, role-playing, and storytelling encourage active participation and improve communication skills. However, challenges such as limited access to technology and insufficient teacher training must be addressed to create a more inclusive learning environment. Future efforts should focus on developing more advanced assistive technologies and ensuring widespread availability. By adopting these innovative strategies, educators can empower visually impaired learners with the necessary skills for effective communication and greater independence in their language development.

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ULUG'BEK HAMDAM HIKOYALARIDA PSIXOLOGIK TASVIRNING BADIY-ESTETIK FUNKSIYASI MASALASIGA DOIR

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Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada ijodkorning psixologik tasvir o'ziga xosligi, uning badiiy-estetik vazifasi, hikoya syujeti tadrijida muallif mahorati qirralari, uslub individualligi kabi masalalar iste'dodli yozuvchi Ulug'bek Hamdamning "Ko'nglimdagi daryo" hikoyasi orqali tahlilga tortilgan. Shuningdek, adib ijodida, modernistik uslubning yetakchilik qilsa ham, unda umumiylik, milliy va an'anaviy uslub qorishiq holda uyg'unlashi, tush tasvirining syujet tarkibidagi o'rni, uning ruhiy holat ifodalashdagi ahamiyati yuzasidan ham mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: syujet, kompozitsiya, ruhiy holat, badiiy psixologizm, motiv, epizod, tush tasviri, tush motivi talqin, tahlil, hikoya, janr, badiiyat.

Аннотация: в данной статье через повесть «Река в моем сердце» талантливого писателя Улугбека Хамдама анализируются такие вопросы, как своеобразие психологического образа творца, его художественно-эстетическая задача, аспекты мастерства автора в разработке сюжета рассказа, индивидуальность стиля. Также в творчестве писателя, несмотря на то, что стиль модерн является ведущим, имеются замечания об общности, национальном и традиционном стиле, месте образа сновидения в сюжете, его значении в выражении душевного состояния.

Ключевые слова: поэтика, творец, психика, художественная психология, образ, образность, герой, интерпретация, анализ, рассказ, проза, художественность.

Annotation: in this article, issues such as the uniqueness of the creator's psychological image, his artistic-aesthetic task, the aspects of the author's skill in the development of the story plot, the individuality of the style, are analyzed through the story "River in my heart" by the talented writer Ulugbek Hamdam. Also, in the work of the writer, despite the fact that the modernist style is the leader, there are comments on the generality, national and traditional style, the place of the dream image in the plot, and its importance in expressing the mental state.

Key words: poetics, creator, psyche, artistic psychology, image, figurativeness, hero, interpretation, analysis, story, prose, artistry.

Yozuvchi Ulug'bek Hamdamning aksariyat hikoyalarida psixologik holatni tush tasviri orqali ifoda etish qabarib ko'rinadi. Ana shunday tush-hikoyalaridan biri "Ko'nglimdagi daryo"dir. Falsafiy-ramziylikka asoslangan ushbu asarda nafaqat adib badiiy niyatining tush epizodida aks etganligini, balki syujet tadriji davomida yozuvchining o'ziga xos mahorat qirralarini, uslub individualligi ham ko'zga tashlanadi. Yozuvchi ijodida modernistik uslub yetakchilik qilsada, ijodiga xos bo'lgan umumiylik, milliy va an'anaviy uslub qorishiq holda keladi. Adabiyotshunos T. Solihov: "Har bitta badiiy asar dastlab milliydir, milliy bo'lmagan adabiyot adabiyot emas"- deb bejizga aytmagan. Hech bir hikoya o'z-o'zidan dunyoga

kelmaydi. Bu har bir ijodkorning botiniy va zohiriy dunyosida turli fikr, g'oyalar ta'sirida yuzaga keladi. Yozuvchining "Bir piyola suv", "Unutilgan nay navosi", "Safar" va quyidagi so'z yuritmoqchi bo'lgan tush-hikoyalardan biri "Ko'nglimdagi daryo" hikoyalari uchun xos bo'lgan, erkinlik, ozodlik tuyg'usini va poklik ramzini aks ettiruvchi "suv" obrazi yozuvchi ijodining asosiy mazmunini tashishga xizmat qilgan.

"Ko'nglimdagi daryo" hikoyasi uslub jihatidan boshqa hikoyalardan farq qiladi. Inson ruhining evrilishlari, ko'ngil nozikliklari o'ziga xos tarzda ifoda qilingan. Unda birgina istak-orzuga yetishmoqlik yo'lidagi urinish va sa'y-harakatlar tasviri tegrasida ko'ngildan kechgan ehtiros, iztirob, intilishlar hikoyaning mavzu va g'oyasini, asl mohiyatini o'zida jamlagan.

Asar muallif tilidan hikoya qilinadi, unda asli qishloqlik, taqdir taqozosi bilan shaharda yashaydigan obraz orqali turmush mashaqqatlari, inson umri davomida har kuni, har damda takrorlanuvchi va hech tugamaydigan tashvishlar va bundan bezib ketgan, tashvishsiz, o'ysiz, xotirjamlik izlayotgan inson hayoti aks ettirilgan. Bosh qahramon har doim oilasi oldidagi burchini, mas'uliyatini his qilgan holda uzluksiz harakat qiladi. Hattoki kunlik qilishi kerak bo'lgan ishlarining ro'yxatini tuzib qo'yadi: " - *Ishonmasangiz, mana bittasi. O'qib ko'ring. 1. Eshikning qulfiga til. 2. Sarvarning to'yiga to'yona. 3. Yo'l-yo'lakay ishxonaga el. choynak (kecha kuyib qolgan edi). 4. O'g'ilning kompyuterini ustaga eltish. 5. Elektr pulini to'lash. 6. Poliklinikadan spravka (qiz fiz. mashg'ulotlariga qatnashmaydi). 7. Bozor (kartoshka, piyoz, sabzi, go'sht, non, yog'...).* 8. Mashina shinalarini da mlatish. 9. Yunusoboddagi qarindoshdan hol so'rash (bobosi qazo qilgan). 10. Keksayib qolgan qo'shnini Qorasuvdagi tabibga olib borib kelish (otaxonning o'zi qattiq iltimos qilgan). 11. "Gap"ga borish...E'tibor beringki, ro'yxat faqat bugunga atalgan. Erta uchun uni boshqatdan tuzaman"[4;317]. Ko'rinadiki, har kun takrorlanuvchi bir xillik hayotdan norozidek, unga qasdlashgandek, lekin taqdiriga bitilgan barcha zarbalariga chidab yashashga rozi bo'ladi. Lekin, u taqdirining bir chizig'ini o'zgartirmoqqa ahd qiladi. Chunki u hayotining shundayligidan, ya'ni qanday bo'lsa, o'shandayligidan juda-juda charchagan edi. Botinida yashayotgan yoshlik, beg'amlik davrlari asta-sekin yuzaga chiqa boshladi. Har bir shaxs mazkur hikoyadagi kabi hayot zarvaraqlarida ro'y berayotgan turli voqea, hodisot, yumushlardan bir muddat bo'lsada yoshligiga qaytishni yoki nimadir ro'y berib qisqa muddatga bo'lsa ham barchasidan yiroqlashishni istaydi. Bu kabi istaklarni kimlardir Allohning bergan ne'matlariga noshukurlik qildi deya talqin ham qilishi mumkin. Ammo hikoya qahramoni uchun bu hukm to'g'ri bo'lmaydi nazarimda.

“Turib-turib daryoni yomon ko‘rib ketaman. Axir, u tufayli tushmadimi mening bechora boshimga shuncha g‘alva? Daryoga mahliyo bo‘lmaganimda chalg‘imas edim, ha, chalg‘imas edim!”[4;326]. Mazkur parchada hikoya qahramoni o‘z maqsadi yo‘lida dunyo lazatlariga chalg‘ishi va buning natijasida esa boshiga kutilmagan kulfatlar yo‘liqishi, hayotining izdan chiqishi va o‘zini aybdor sanashi, xatosini anglab yetishi tasvirlangan. Inson o‘z maqsadi yo‘lida chalg‘ishi muallif qalamiga mansub “Bir piyola suv” hikoyasida ham bayon etilgan edi (oldingi tadqiqotlarda tahlilga tortilgan). “Ko‘nglimdagi daryo” hikoyasidagi qahramon ham suvga, aniqrog‘i, daryoga mahliyo bo‘lib chalg‘idi va bundan aziyat chekdi. Qahramon daryoni har doim tushlarida ko‘rgan va o‘nglarida ham unga boqib xayollar og‘ushiga sho‘ng‘iganligi va bir zumga bo‘lsa ham qoida va tartibli hayotni unutilib tashvishsiz, beg‘ubor onlariga qaytish ilinjida harakat qiladi.

Mazkur hikoyada quyidagi parchaga e‘tibor qilaylik: *“Shunday kezlar afsonaviy Sizif xayolimga tushadi. Siz ham eslasangiz kerak uni. Tog‘ cho‘qqisiga og‘irdan og‘ir toshni dumalatib olib chiqishga behuda chiranayotgan (murodiga yetolmasligi taqdiriga bitilgan) Sizifni bilmagan bormi, axir! Turib-turib, “Sizif har birimizning ko‘ksimizda joylamshgan, u bizning o‘zimiz, Sizif – bizning har birimiz!..”, deya olamga jar solgim keladi. Ammo bu o‘ylarimni tashqariga olib chiqmayman, ular ichimda qoladilar. Axir, hamma buni biladi, lekin hech kim shu bilgani oldida to‘xtab, hayotiga nazar solmaydi”*[4;329]. Muallif ushbu o‘rinda zamondosh yozuvchi X.Do‘stmuhammadning “Donishmand Sizif” romaniga ishora qiladi, undagi Sizif bilan hikoya qahramoni taqdiri o‘xshash ekanligini hikoya syujeti davomida teran falsafiy mushohadalar keltirish orqali dalillaydi.

Tush tasviri esa ushbu hikoyada xotimada keltirilgan va unda hikoya qahramoni o‘z orzusiga yetadi: *“Faqat... faqat bir kecha hamma toat-ibodatimning kuli ko‘kka sovrildi...Uzun ro‘yxatni bexato bajarib kelgan kunim kechasi bir tush ko‘rdim. Unda... unda men yana o‘sha daryoga duch kelib qoldim... Va uning so‘lim sohili kimsasiz, nazoratsiz edi..Va u to‘lib-toshib, buralib-eshilib, emin-erkin oqardi... Va u meni kutayotgan edi...Va men ham uni judayam-judayam sog‘ingan ekanman!...”*[4;333]. Tushlarida va o‘nglarida unga doimo halaqit beradigan nazoratchi va hushtak obrazlari o‘ziga xos ramziylik ega bo‘lib, inson hayotida otalik, o‘gillik, erlik, qarindoshlik mas‘uliyatini eslatib uni behuda xayollarga berilishdan saqlab turuvchi bir vosita ma‘nosini anglatgan deya talqin etish mumkin. Umuman, mazkur hikoya teran falsafa, purma‘noga ega bo‘lib, insonning o‘ziga bitilgan taqdir, qismatiga rozi bo‘lishga, noshukrlik qilmaslikka, har ne bo‘lsa Allohdan ekanligiga ishonish hissini uyg‘otadi. Yozuvchining badiiy mahorati esa

inson psixologik holatidagi evrilishlarni poetik qonuniyatlar, ya’ni badiiy tasvir vositalari, obraz va detallar orqali yetkazishida ko‘rinadi.

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ЎТКИР ҲОШИМОВНИНГ «ИККИ ЭШИК ОРАСИ» РОМАНИДА ЭВФЕМИЗМЛАРНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИШИ

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*Қозоғистон Республикаси, Туркистон вилояти
Махмуд Қошгарий номли лицей мактаб ўқитувчиси*

Фикрни юмшоқ ва чиройли, одобли қилиб ифодалаш эвфемизм ҳисобланади. Эвфемизмлар кўпол, беодоб, тақик сўз ёки ибора маданий шаклда пардали қилиб айтилади. Эвфемизмларнинг маъноси шартли сўз бўлиб фақат контекстдагина реаллашади, улар кўпинча сўзнинг кўчма маънода қўлланиши асосида юзага келади. Эвфемизмларни юмшоқ маъноли синоним сўз ибора ёки гап деб аташ мумкин. Ўткир Ҳошимовнинг «Икки эшик ораси» романида ҳам эвфемизмлардан унумли фойдаланилган.

«Ойим уни юпатишга уринди:

- Нафасингизни иссиқ қилинг айланай, юртга келган тўй. Мана Кимсанам ҳам кетди-ку! Ўтирибман яратганга топшириб.» «Ёв қувдими мунча ҳовлиқдингиз, десам, мен белида белбоғи бор ўғил ўстирдим! – деб керилади». Ушбу мисолларда «уруш» сўзи ўрнида «юртга келган тўй» йигит сўзини ифодалаш мақсадида «белида белбоғи бор ўғил» иборалари қўлланилган.

Холпош хола тагин фарёд қилди:

- Бир эмас иккитасидан баробар ажралсам-а, «ўғилларим ўлди» ўрнида «ажралдим» сўзи орқали кампирнинг ғам-қайғуси акс эттирилади.

«Чучварани хом санабсан. Оқсоқол! Сен шоҳида юрсанг, мен баргида юраман»,

«Одамлар оёғи билан эмас, оғзи билан юради, ўзим эрта пешиндан буён туз тортмагандим», «чучварани хом санамоқ», «сен шоҳида юрсанг, мен баргида юраман» иборалари орқали ёзувчи сендан ҳали мен айёрман деган фикрни, ғийбатчи сўзини эса «оёғи билан эмас оғзи билан юрмоқ», оч қолмоқлик эса пешиндан буён туз тортмаслик иборалари мисолида тасвирлайди.

«Дадам кўйиб берса Лазокат холамнинг кўлидан судраб чоптириб кетадигандек вазоҳатда – Тезроқ! – деди. Хола жеркиб ҳам ялиниб:

- Вой укам ваҳима қилманг, бу савдо ҳар хотиннинг бошида бор» жумласи орқали аёлларнинг ҳаммаси ҳам фарзанд туғади деб эмас, бу савдо ҳар хотиннинг бошида бор тарзида ифодаланади.

«Маълум оши» қилинганини эшитиб хурсанд бўлдим билиб қўй. Сен энди боши боғлиқ қизсан». Ушбу мисолларда унашилган қиз ўрнида «маълум оши», «боши боғлиқ қиз» жумлалари орқали ёзувчи фикрларни чиройли ва таъсирли ёритади.

«Бўйи етган қизнинг орзуси осмондаги юлдузга ўхшайди. Узоқдан ярақлаб кўринади-ю, на етасан, на тутасан. Юлдуз эса олисда сирли-сирли милтираб тураверади. Талпинасан ҳеч кимга билдирмай хаёл сурасан. Юлдузнинг ёнинга тушишини орзиқиб кутасан. Ким билсин «юлдузи-юлдузига тўғри келибди» деган гап балки шундан чиққандир. Менинг юлдузим – Кимсан акам эди».

Ушбу контекстда Кимсан акамга турмушга чиқаман деган фикрни ёзувчи «бўйи етган қиз», «юлдузи-юлдузига тўғри келибди» деган жумлалари орқали таъсирли тасвирлайди.

Эвфемизмлар асарнинг тилини бойитади, бадий қимматини оширади, бадий асардаги эмоционал-экспрессивликни кучли ифодалашга хизмат қилади. Баъзан шартли эвфемизмлар бадий адабиётда кенг қўлланилади. Масалан, «Ўлди» ўрнида «бериб қўйди», «вафот этди», «ажралдик», «ҳалок бўлди», «қиз бола» ўрнида, «холва», «иккиқат» ўрнида «оғир оёқ, ҳомиладор, юкли» каби.

Демак, эвфемизмлар нутқнинг таъсирчанлигини ошириб, ўқувчининг эътиборини тортади, асар қимматини оширишга хизмат қилади.

**ETNOGRAFIK ELEMENTLARNING BADIY ADABIYOTDA MILLIY-MADANIY LISONIY
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Abstract: *Ethnographic elements are one of the crucial components of artistic style, playing an essential role in preserving and introducing national cultures through literature and art by vividly and accurately depicting the lifestyle of different peoples. Through ethnographic elements, writers and poets showcase historical and cultural features in a distinctive way. The 19th century literary period marked the flourishing of this style. For instance, in Alexander Pushkin's drama Boris Godunov, the cultural lexicons, religious customs, and social life of the Russian people are depicted. Similarly, in Uzbek literature, the novel O'tkan Kunlar by Abdulla Qodiriy portrays the social and cultural relations, traditions, and values of the Uzbek people at the turn of the 19th to 20th centuries. The novel is rich with examples of communal life and local customs. Moreover, ethnographic details in works like Jane Austen's Pride and Prejudice and Anton Chekhov's play The Duck Pond are vital in revealing cultural practices, manners, and traditions of the respective societies. The paper highlights the importance of ethnographic elements in literature for portraying the social fabric of different nations and their role in the development of cultural identity.*

Keywords: *ethnographic elements, artistic style, national culture, literature, Pushkin, Qodiriy, Austen, Chekhov, Uzbek, Russian, English, social customs, traditions, cultural identity.*

Аннотация: *Этнографические элементы являются важнейшей частью художественного стиля, играя ключевую роль в сохранении и распространении национальных культур через литературу и искусство, живо и точно изображая образ жизни разных народов. С помощью этнографических элементов писатели и поэты представляют историко-культурные особенности в уникальной форме. XIX век стал временем расцвета этого стиля. Например, в драме Александра Пушкина Борис Годунов изображены культурные лексемы, религиозные обычаи и социальная жизнь русского народа. Точно так же в узбекской литературе роман О'ткан Кунлар Абдуллы Кадырия изображает социальные и культурные отношения, традиции и ценности узбекского народа конца XIX — начала XX века. Роман богат примерами общинной жизни и местных обычаев. Более того, этнографические детали в произведениях Джейн Остин Гордость и предубеждение и пьесе Антона Чехова Утка в пруду играют важную роль в раскрытии культурных практик, манер и традиций соответствующих обществ. Статья подчеркивает важность этнографических элементов в литературе для изображения социальной ткани различных народов и их роли в развитии культурной идентичности.*

Ключевые слова: *этнографические элементы, художественный стиль, национальная культура, литература, Пушкин, Кадырий, Остин, Чехов, узбекский, русский, английский, социальные обычаи, традиции, культурная идентичность.*

Annotatsiya. *Etnografik elementlar badiiy uslubning eng muhim qismlaridan biri bo'lib, milliy madaniyatlarni adabiyot va san'at orqali saqlash va tarqatishda asosiy rol oynaydi, turli*

xalqlarning turmush tarzini jonli va aniq tasvirlaydi. Etnografik elementlar yordamida yozuvchilar va shoirlar tarixiy-madaniy xususiyatlarni o'ziga xos shaklda namoyish etadilar. XIX asr ushbu uslubning gullab-yashnash davri bo'ldi. Masalan, Aleksandr Pushkinning "Boris Godunov" dramasida madaniy leksikalar, diniy urf-odatlar va rus xalqining ijtimoiy hayoti tasvirlangan. Xuddi shunday, o'zbek adabiyotida Abdulla Qodiriyning "O'tkan kunlar" romani XIX asr oxiri – XX asr boshlarida o'zbek xalqining ijtimoiy va madaniy munosabatlari, an'analari hamda qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi. Roman jamoaviy hayot va mahalliy urf-odatlarining boy namunalari bilan to'la. Bundan tashqari, Jeyn Ostinning "Andisha va g'urur" asari hamda Anton Chexovning "Ko'ldagi o'rdak" pyesasidagi etnografik tafsilotlar tegishli jamiyatlarning madaniy amaliyotlari, odo-axloq me'yorlari va an'analarni ochib berishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola turli xalqlarning ijtimoiy tuzilishini tasvirlashda adabiyotda etnografik elementlarning ahamiyatini va ularning madaniy o'ziga xoslikni shakllantirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: *etnografik elementlar, badiiy uslub, milliy madaniyat, adabiyot, Pushkin, Qodiriy, Ostin, Chexov, o'zbek, rus, ingliz, ijtimoiy urf-odatlar, an'analari, madaniy identifikatsiya.*

Etnografizmlar badiiy uslubning muhim unsurlaridan biri hisoblanib, adabiyot va san'atda xalqlarning hayot tarzini jonli va aniq tasvirlash vositasi sifatida milliy madaniyatni asrab-avaylash va uni boshqa xalqlarga tanishtirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Yozuvchi va shoirlar etnografizmlar vositasida tarixiy-madaniy xususiyatlarni o'ziga xos usulda namoyon etadilar.

XIX - asr adabiyoti ushbu uslubning yuksalish davri bo'lgan. Masalan, Aleksandr Pushkinning "Boris Godunov" dramasida rus xalqining madaniy leksemalari, diniy urf-odatlari va o'sha davrdagi ijtimoiy hayot tasvirlangan. Asarda xalqning so'z boyligi, diniy marosimlari va kundalik turmush tarzi elementlari orqali o'quvchi o'sha davr muhitini his qila oladi.

O'zbek adabiyotida esa Abdulla Qodiriyning "O'tkan kunlar" romanida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu roman XIX - asr oxiri XX - asr boshidagi o'zbek xalqi ijtimoiy-madaniy munosabatlari, urf-odatlari, qadriyatlarini keng tasvirlagan asardir. Masalan, Yusufbek hoji hovlisida o'tkazilgan to'y marosimlari, unga tayyorgarlik ko'rish jarayonlari o'sha davrdagi xalqning bunday turdagi jamoaviy bazmga munosabatini tasvirlagan. To'yni o'tkazishdagi ayollarning "sepil" yasashidan tortib, erkaklarning "guvoch o'rnatish" jarayonlariga qadar barchasida jamoaviy amalga oshirish, xalqning birdamligi va hamkorlikka asoslangan hayot tarzini ko'rsatadi. Romandagi *ko'rpa-to'shak, xurjun, salla, chopon* kabi so'zlar xalqning kundalik turmush tarzidagi kiyinish so'zlarni ifoda etadi. Yusufbek hoji oilasida to'qilgan xurjunlarning tasviri faqatgina amaliy emas, balki estetik ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ham ko'rsatadi.

Shuningdek, romandagi bosh qahramonlar Otabek va Kumushning nikoh to'yi marosimi, oilaviy qadriyatlar, mahalliy urf-odatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari

o'zgacha tarzda yoritilgan. Kumushning kelin sifatida “*ko'rpa yig'ish*”, “*sovchilarni kutib olish*” (Qodiriy, 1925) kabi odatlarni bajarishi milliylikni ochib berishning namunasidir

Ingliz adabiyotida ham etnografizmlarga namunalar ko'plab uchraydi. Masalan, Jeyn Ostin qalamiga mansub mashhur “*Pride and Prejudice*” (Andisha va G'urur) romanida XIX-asr Angliya jamiyatining ijtimoiy tuzilish, nikoh marosimlari, qizlarning ta'lim olish darajasi va kiyinish uslubi keng yoritilgan. Elizabet Bennet va boshqa Bennet oilasi qizlarining bal va ziyofotlardagi kiyinish uslubi, o'sha davr ayollarining moda va jamiyatda o'rnini ifodalash vositasi sifatida tasvirlangan. Roman davomida Bennet oilasining iqtisodiy sharoitlariga qaramay, to'y va mehmondorchilik marosimlarida qatnashish uchun maxsus kiyimlar tayyorlashi, ijtimoiy mavqe va oilaviy an'analarning ahamiyatini ochib beradi. Shu bilan birga, ingliz jamiyatida o'sha davr to'y marosimlari ham muhim rol o'ynaganini ko'rsatadi. Buning isboti sifatida esa asarda qator nomlari keltirilgan kiyim-kechakka doir so'zlarni ya'ni ingliz xalqiga tegishli realiyalarni misol qilib keltirishimiz mumkin:

- *pelisse* (ko'pincha ko'ylak ustidan kiyiladigan uzun palto yoki plash);
- *bonnet* (ayollar o'rashi uchun bosh kiyimi);
- *kravat* (erkaklar bo'yinlariga o'raydigan ro'mol yoki sharf);
- *briches* (erkaklar kiyadigan kalta shim turi);

bazmlarda dasturxonga tortish uchun foydalaniladigan ingliz taom nomlarini aks ettiruvchi so'zlar jumlasiga:

- *pudding* (shirinliklar yoki sho'r taomlarni bildiruvchi umumiy atama), choy (ingliz jamiyatida ijtimoiy yig'ilishlarning asosiy ichimligi);
- *mutton* (qo'y go'shti va keng tarqalgan oziq-ovqat mahsuloti nomi);
- *ale* (o'sha davrda mashhur bo'lgan pivo turi).

Bundan tashqari o'sha davr ingliz hayotini ifoda etish bilan bog'liq predmetlar va tushunchalarni ifodalaydigan va faqat ingliz madaniyatigagina taalluqli so'zlarni yana qator misol tariqasida keltirishimiz mumkin.

- *carriage* (ot tortadigan arava), phaeton (ochiq va yengil dam olish uchun mo'ljallangan arava),
- *hack chaise* (yollanma arava) kabi so'zlar ular foydalangan transport vositalarini ifodalasa;
- *ball* (rasmiy raqs kechasi),
- *assembly* (raqs tushish yoki o'zaro tanishish uchun o'tkaziladigan yig'in),
- *dowry* (kelinning turmushga chiqishda keltiriladigan mol-mulki yoki puli),
- *entail* (mulkni oilada mulkni saqlashni ta'minlovchi qonuniy cheklov);

unvonlar va ijtimoiy sinf nomlarini ifodalovchi so'zlar esa,

- *gentleman* (ijtimoiy mavqega ega erkak),
- *baronet* (baronlardan pastroq darajadagi merosiy unvon),
- *estate* (oila yoki shaxsga tegishli mulk),
- *rector* (cherkovning mahalliy rahbari) qabilida yoritib berilgan.

Bingley va Jeyn o'rtasidagi munosabatlar, mehmonlarni kutib olish tartiblari va ziyofat marosimlarini tasvirlash orqali Jeyn Ostin Angliyaning o'sha davrdagi an'analarni o'quvchiga yetkazib beradi (Austen, 1813).

Anton Chexovning "O'rdak bog'i" pyesasida esa ziyofat sahnasi yanada batafsil tasvirlangan. Ziyofat uchun dasturxon tayyorlash jarayonida qahramonlarning bir-biri bilan qilgan suhbatlari va sahnadagi buyumlarning joylashuvi rus xalqining uy-joy madaniyati va marosimlaridagi o'ziga xosliklarni ko'rsatib beradi. Masalan, Chexov pyesada *shashlik*, *kasha*, *borshch* kabi taomlarni eslatib, ularning tayyorlanishi va berilish tartibiga urg'u beradi. Bu orqali u rus xalqining mehmondo'stlik an'analari va jamiyatdagi turli qatlamlarning ovqatlanish madaniyatidagi farqlarni ko'rsatadi (Chexov, 1896).

"Alpomish" dostonida to'y marosimi, xalq qadriyatlari va kiyinish tarziga oid ko'plab misollar keltirilgan bo'lib, *qiz tanlash*, *qiz uzatish*, *nikoh*, *raqs marosimlari*; asarda foydalanilgan o'zbek xalqi kiyimlaridan *kurta* (erkaklar to'yda kiyadigan uzun kiyim), *chak-chak* (ayollar va xotin qizlar to'yda kiyadigan uzun libos), *kaltak* (yubka osti kiyimi, asosan, to'ylarda ayollar tomonidan kiyilgan) kelin-kuyovga nisbatan ishlatilgan yaxshi niyatlar – *bahtli bo'linglar*, *chiroyli farzand ko'ringlar*, *xudodan yaxshi niyatlar*; *torta* – to'y sovg'asi; tortishuv va kurash musobaqasi esa Alpomish dostonida to'ydan oldin erkaklar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan va bu o'z navbatida to'yga tayyorgarlik va insonlarni bir davraga birlashishi ramzi bo'lgan (Babadjanova, 1998).

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MILLIY FRAZEOLOGIZMLAR ISHTIROK ETGAN VATAN VA VATANPARVARLIK HAQIDAGI O'ZBEK XALQ PAREMALARINING SEMANTIK TADQIQI

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Annotatsiya: Bugunga kelib matnlarni bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilish jarayonida elektron tarjimon dasturlar deyarli barcha xalqlar tomonidan foydalaniladigan asosiy yordamchi vositalardan biriga aylanib ulgurdi. Biroq ulardan foydalanish jarayonida duch kelinadigan ayrim kamchiliklarni ham inkor qilib bo'lmaydi. Mazkur holat, ayniqsa, barqaror birliklar qo'llangan matnlar tarjimasida ko'proq va yaqqolroq ko'zga tashlanadi. Shu sababli ham bu kabi matnlar alohida izohlashni talab qiladi. Maqolada milliy frazeologizmlar ishtirok etgan vatan va vatanparvarlik haqidagi o'zbek xalq paremalaridan bir nechtasi tanlab olingan va ularning izohiga alohida-alohida to'xtalangan. Maqol va matallarni tahlil qilish jarayonida ilmiy bilishning mantiqiylik, tarixiylik, izchillik va obyektivlik usullaridan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: frazeologizm, tarjima, vatan, vatanparvarlik, parema, semantik tahlil, maqolshunoslik, lingvokulturologik tahlil, madaniyat.

Abstract: Today, electronic translation programs have become one of the main auxiliary tools used by almost all peoples in the process of translating texts from one language to another. However, some shortcomings encountered in the process of using them cannot be denied. This situation is especially noticeable in the translation of texts using stable units. Therefore, such texts require separate interpretation. The article selects several Uzbek folk proverbs about the homeland and patriotism, in which national phraseologisms are present, and their interpretation is discussed separately. In the process of analyzing proverbs and sayings, the methods of scientific knowledge of logic, historicity, consistency and objectivity were used.

Keywords: phraseology, translation, homeland, patriotism, proverb, semantic analysis, proverbology, linguo-cultural analysis, culture.

Paremalar yaratuvchisi bo'lgan xalq qarashi va madaniyati haqida ma'lumot beruvchi qimmatli manbalardan biridir. Garchi ko'pgina maqol-u matallar tildan tilga, xalqdan xalqqa ko'chib o'tib, qo'llanish doirasi jihatidan keng hududlarga yoyilgan va dunyo xalqlari og'zaki ijodidan universal mohiyat anglamida keng o'rin olgan bo'lsa-da, ayrim paremlar borki, ular o'zida aks etgan milliy birliklar orqali uni yaratgan millat haqida tasavvur hosil qila oladi. Frazeologizmlar ham shular sirasidandir. Biroq frazeologizmlarga xos yana bir muhim xususiyat borki, ularni asl mohiyatini saqlagan holda tarjima qilish, qo'llangan matn mazmunini o'zga tilli kishilar jamoasiga to'laligicha anglatish ba'zan bir qadar murakkablik va tushunmovchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi, ayniqsa, bu holat ularning erkin birikmalar bilan shakldoshlik hosil qiladigan holatlarida yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Shu sababli ham bunday matnlar alohida izohlashni talab qiladi. Quyida bunday birliklar

qo'llangan matnlar anglamini va tarjima jarayonini osonlashtirish maqsadida milliy frazeologizmlar ishtirok etgan vatan va vatanparvarlik haqidagi o'zbek xalq paremalaridan ayrimlarining semantik va lingvokulturologik tadqiqi amalga oshirilgan.

So'nggi yillarda paremalarni lingvokulturologik doirada o'rganishga katta urg'u berilib, shu yo'nalishda M.Asranova, F.F.Farxutdinovalar [1] izlanishlar olib bordilar. Poyon Bakirovning rus, o'zbek va qozoq xalq maqollari lingvistik xususiyatlari bo'yicha amalga oshirgan ishlari alohida e'tiborga loyiq. Olim uch til doirasida qiyosiy-chog'ishtirma tahlilni amalga oshirish bilan bir qatorda maqol, matal, ibora munosabatlariga ham alohida e'tibor qaratadi va maqolga xos xususiyatlarni ajratib ko'rsatadi. P.Bakirovning tadqiqotida yana nominasentrik – ega va kesimi bosh kelishikdagi ot va harakat nomi bilan ifodalangan maqollarning semantik va struktur xususiyatlari ham batafsil izohlab berilgan [2]. Bugungi o'zbek paremiologik fondining tarjima, ayniqsa, elektron tarjima jarayonida tez-tez ko'zga tashlanayotgan muammolarini hisobga olgan holda quyida bir qator tarkibida interpretatsiya jarayonida qiyinchilik tug'diruvchi bir qator turg'un birikmali maqol va matallar tanlab olingan holda tahlil qilindi.

YO'LDAN CHIQSANG CHIQ, ELDAN CHIQMA. *Yo'ldan chiqmoq* iborasi *yomon yo'lga kirmoq, aynimoq* ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Matalda to'g'ri yo'ldan adashib, nomaqbul ishlar bilan shug'ullanayotgan bo'lsang, kuni kelib xatoyingni tushunib yetganingda yoxud boshing toshga tekkanda to'g'ri yo'lni topib, hayotingni davom ettirishing mumkin, biroq xalqingga yomonlik qilib, ko'nglini qoldirsang, qavmingni tark etsang, elatingga qayta qo'shila olmaysan, boshqa vatan topa olmaysan, demoqchi bo'lingan.

AYRILIQNING SHIDDATI, QON YIG'LATAR MUDDATI. O'zbeklar nutqida kuchli ruhiy ezilish, iztirob, alam bilan qattiq ko'z yoshi to'kish *qon yig'lash* birikmasi bilan ifodalanadi va u, asosan, inson o'ta ilojsiz, boshiga tushgan musobatning chorasiga ojiz qolganidan zor-zor yig'laganida qo'llanadi. Arab tilidan o'zlashgan *shiddat* so'zi esa kuch-qudrat, intensivlikni ifodalash bilan bir qatorda *balo, ofat* ma'nosini ham anglatib keladi. Maqol tarkibiy komponentlari mazmunidan kelib chiqqan holda mazkur paremani ayriliq insonning boshiga turli balo-ofatlar keltiradi, dardiga biror chora topa olmay, behad azoblanishiga sabab bo'ladi, ma'nosida tushunish mumkin.

AYRILMAGIN ELINGDAN, QUUVAT KETAR BELINGDAN. Tarkibida ko'chma ma'no tashuvchi komponentlari mavjud bo'lgan bu kabi paremalar alohida izohlashni talab qiladi. Negaki o'zga tilli kishilar uchun *beldan quvvat ketmoq* sof

o'zbekona ifodasi to'g'ridan to'g'ri tarjima jarayonida ma'noviy g'alizlik tug'dirishi mumkin. Bu birikma *jismoniy yoki moddiy kuch-quvvatni yo'qotish* ma'nosini ifodalab, u orqali mazkur paremada o'zbeklar uchun moddiy-u ma'naviy boylikka erishib, farovon hayot kechirishning manbayi vatan bag'rida vatandoshlari bilan bo'lish ekanligi mazmunidagi milliy qarash ifodalangan. Milliy paremiologik fondimiz tarkibida qo'llangan bu kabi ifodalar millatning o'zligini, milliy asriy qarashlarini ko'rsatuvchi qiymatga ega.

ELGA QO'SHILGANNING KO'NGLI TO'Q, ELDAN AJRALGANNING BETI YO'Q. *Ko'ngli to'q* sifatlashi xotirjam, bexavotir hayot kechiradigan, atrofida ziyon yetkazadigan biror xavf-xatar yo'qligiga ishonadigan; *beti yo'q* iborasi esa uyatsiz, nomussiz, hayosiz shaxslarga nisbatan qo'llanadi.

Biror-bir insonning boshqalardan mutlaqo behojat bo'lishi, jamiyatdan uzilgan holda huzur-halovatda, bir maromda tinch, sog'lom va sokin umrguzaronlik qilishi mumkinligiga to'la amin bo'lib, ko'ngil xotirjamligiga erishishi mushkul. Inson el-ulusi bilan yaxshi munosabatda bo'lish, bir-birining kuniga yarash, og'irini yengil qilishga hissasini qo'shish orqali jamiyat a'zosiga aylanadi. Bunday kishi beldan quvvat ketganda yoxud biror musibatga yo'liqqanda yolg'izlanib qolishi mumkinligidan qo'rqmaydi. Yor-birodarlari, qavm-qarindoshlari uni og'ir ahvolda tashlab qo'ymasligiga ishonchi komil bo'lib, xotirjam hayot kechiradi.

Elatidan ajrab, ular bilan aloqani uzgan, muhtojlarga yordam qo'lini cho'zmagan kishi esa jamiyatdan ajralib qoladi, kuni kelib shaxsiy manfaatlariga erishish maqsadida xalqqa qayta qo'shilishga harakat qiladigan, ehtiyojlarini tilayveradigan xudbin kimsani hech bir jamiyat qabul qilmaydi, buni nomussizlik, uyatsizlikning belgisi sifatida baholaydi.

ELGA BOQQAN – YERGA BOQMAS, KO'KKA BOQQAN – ELGA YOQMAS. *Yerga boqmoq* iborasi yordam, madad berilishi kerak bo'lgan o'rinda, asosan, imkoni bo'lsa-da yordam berishni xohlamay, ba'zan ilojsizlikdan o'zini chetga olib turgan insonga nisbatan ishlatiladi. *Ko'kka boqmoq* iborasi esa o'zini katta olgan, kibrli, kekkaygan shaxslar sifatini anglatishda qo'llanadi. Mazkur maqol orqali el koriga yarashni chin ko'ngildan xohlagan inson o'zini chetga olib, yerga qarab turmaydi, xalq dardiga chora izlaydi; faqat o'zini o'ylaydigan, manmanlikka berilgan kimsalarni hech bir jamiyat yoqtirmaydi, yaxshi munosabat ko'rsatmaydi, demoqchi bo'lingan.

DAVLAT – OG'IZ BIRLIKDA. Vatan tushunchasini ifodalash uchun o'zbek tilida yana *mamlakat, yurt, diyor, el, mulk* singari qator so'zlar mavjud, biroq ushbu

maqolda boshqa emas, ayni *davlatning* tanlanishi bu soʻz zamirida urgʻulanadigan quyidagi maʼnolar bilan bogʻlanadi:

- mustaqil mamlakat maqomiga egaligi;
- fuqarolarining ijtimoiy-siyosiy huquqlari himoya qilinganligi;
- tinchlikka raxna soluvchi kuchlarning qarshiligini sindiruvchi hokimiyat organlari va siyosiy tashkilotlar tizimining mavjudligi.

Ogʻzi birlik iborasi oʻzbeklar nutqida bahamjihatlikni ifodalash uchun qoʻllanadi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki, yurtning mustaqilligi bardavom, tinchligi barqaror, fuqarolari qonunan mustahkam himoyalangan vatanda turmoq uchun hamma bir yoqadan bosh chiqarib, hamfikir, bahamjihat yashamoqligi darkor. Hamjihatlikning oddiy soʻz bilan emas xalqona milliy ifodada berilishi esa bunday qarash asriy milliy qadriyatga aylanganligidan dalolat beradi.

ONA YURTING OMON BO'LSA, RANGI RO'YING SOMON BO'LMAS.

Rangi somon iborasi kasalga chalingan odamga nisbatan ishlatiladi. Vatan tinch, farovon boʻlsa, bu uning fuqarolariga ham ijobiy taʼsir koʻrsatadi, u yerda turli balo-yu ofat, kasalliklar emas sogʻlom muhit hukmron boʻladi. Demakki, har bir inson uchun eng oliy neʼmat boʻlgan salomatlikni asrashda u yashayotgan muhitning taʼsiri katta.

EL GʻAMINI BILGAN ELDA DOSTON. *Elda doston* boʻlish “mashhur boʻlish, el ichida nom qozonish” maʼnosini anglatadi. Xalq ichida kundalik turmushda turli muammolar yuz berib turadi, ijtimoiy masʼuliyatni yaxshi his qilgan, xalq dardiga befarq boʻlmagan kishilar bunday muammolarni oʻz oʻrnida bartaraf qilishga harakat qiladi. Aslida ularning bu harakatlari obroʻ-eʼtibor qozonish uchun emas, balki insongarchilik yuzasidan qilingan samimiy xizmat boʻlsa-da unday kishilar xalq tomonidan eʼzozlanib, katta-yu kichik tomonidan hurmat qilinadi, soʻzi soʻz, hukmi oliy koʻriladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, oʻzbek xalq paremiologik fondi tarkibida qator milliy frazeologik birliklar qoʻllangan boʻlib, ularni atroflicha tahlil qilish orqali millatning asriy qarashlarini, qadriyatlarini, milliy oʻziga xoligi-yu madaniyatini aniqlash mumkin. Shuningdek, bu kabi tahlillar tarjima jarayonida va turli til vakillarining oʻzaro maʼlumot va aloqa almashinuvida ham zaruriy ahamiyatga ega.

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ABDULLA QAHHOR VA O.GENRI ASARLARIDAGI O'XSHASH VA
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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Jahon va Uzbek adabiyotining buyuk namoyandalari O.Genri va A.Qahhor asarlaridagi o'rganilgan o'xshash va farqli hodisalar adabiy izohlar bilan tasvirlab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'xshashlik, tafovut, qahramonlar, kinoya, hikoyanavis, taqqoslash, kitobxon.

Аннотация: В статье описываются схожие и различные явления, изучаемые в произведениях великих деятелей мировой и узбекской литературы О. Генри и А. Каххора, с литературными пояснениями.

Ключевые слова: сходство, различие, характеры, ирония, рассказчик, сравнение, читатель.

Annotation: The article describes similar and different phenomena studied in the works of great writers of the world and Uzbek literature O. Henry and A. Kahhor, with literary explanations.

Keywords: similarity, difference, characters, irony, storyteller, comparison, reader.

Yozuvchilar turli xil davrlarda yashab ijod qilishlari mumkin, lekin ular ifoda etgan g'oya va tushunchalar, qahramonlarning xarakterlari, davr muammolari bir xil bo'lishi mumkin yoki aksincha bir xil zamonda istiqomat qilib, bir paytda ijod etgan yozuvchilar turli xil muammolar yoki turli xarakterli qahramonlarni gavdalantiradilar. Kitobxonlar uchun har doim u jahon adabiyoti buladimi, uzbek adabiyotimi, asar o'qish jarayonida beixtiyor qahramonlarning turli o'xshash yoki o'xshash bo'lmagan xarakterlarini, ijtimoiy va davr muammolarini, yechimlarini ko'z oldilarida gavdalantiradilar. Jahon adabiyoti va o'zbek adabiyoti hikoyalarining o'qir ekanmiz ularni o'xshash va farqlarini taqqoslamaslikning iloji yo'q. Mashhur amerikalik hikoyanavis O.Genri va o'zbek buyuk hikoyanavisi A.Qahhorning asarlarini ham o'qib tahlil qilayotgan har qanday kitobxon beixtiyor birxillik va farqli holatlarga guvoh bo'lishadi. Ikki buyuk yozuvchilar ikki xil davrda yashab ijod etgan. Buyuk amerikalik yozuvchi O.Genri taxallusi bilan dunyo adabiyotshunosligida katta iz

qoldirgan Villiam Sidney Porter 1862 yilda Amerikaning Shimoliy Karalina shtatida ziyolilar oilasida tavallud topgan. Adib otasidan 15 yoshida ayrilgan va boshqa bolalardan farqli o'laroq erta onasiga yordam berish uchun ishlashni boshlagan. Hayoti davomida farmasevt, jurnalist, bank xodimi va yozuvchi bo'lib fa'oliyat yuritgan. 1910 yilda sog'lig'i yomonlashgani sabab ko'z yumgan. Uning "Magining sovg'asi", "Hargravesning ikki xilligi", "Oxirgi barg", "Ikki bo'shliqning to'lovi", "Karam va Qirol" kabi mashhur hikoyari dunyo yuzini ko'rgan.

Abdulla Qahhor esa Markaziy Osiyo davlatlaridan biri bo'lmish O'zbekistonning Qo'qon shahrida oddiy temirchi oilasida 1907 yilda tug'ilgan. Uning Mavlon Kufur, Gulyor, Erkaboy taxallusi ostida chiqargan asarlari adabiyot olamiga mashhur. U hayoti davomida faqat izlangan va adabiyot bilan mukammal shug'ullanib, bebaho asarlar yozgan. Salomatligi o'g'ir bo'lganligi sababli Moskvada 1968 yil 61 yoshida vafot etgan. Adibning "Anor", "O'g'ri", "Yillar", "Dahshat" va "O'jar" hikoyalari nafaqat o'zbek adabiyotida balki butun dunyo adabiyotida yuqori nufuzga egadir.

Bu ikki buyuk hikoyanavislarning hayotiga nazar solar ekanmiz, ulardagi o'xshash holatlarni kuzatishimiz mumkin. Ikki atoqli inson ham boshqa adiblardan ko'ra bu dunyoni erta tark etgan. Qisqa umrlarida o'sha davr tuzumi va qiyinchiliklari haqida beqiyos asarlarni meros qoldirgan. Ijodlardagi o'xshashlikka e'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, voqea hodisalarni kinoya va istehzoli ifoda etish ikki yozuvchining ijodida mujassam. Buni O.Genrining "Magining sovg'asi" va A.Qahhorning "Anor" haqidagi hikoyalardan anglashimiz mumkin. "Magining sovg'asi" hikoyasining bosh qahramonlari Jim va Della o'zlarida mavjud va ularga qadrli bo'lgan matohlarini bir-birlarini xursand qilish uchun qurbon qiladilar. Ikki sevishgan qalb, Della o'zining uzun sochlarini va Jimm ota-onasidan meros qolgan qimmatli oltin soatini bayram sovg'asini olish uchun sotadilar. Asarni o'qir ekansiz, yozuvchi qahramonlarning suhbatlari orqali uquvchiga jamiyatda kambag'al toifadagi shaxslarning hayot tarzi, ularning dunyo qarashlari, sevgisi, xursandchilik va qayg'usini kinoya va istehzo bilan ifodalanganini guvohi bo'lasiz. Yozuvchi asar qahramonlari: Dellaning uzun sochlarini sotib, Jimni soati uchun zanjir olgani, yoki Jim o'zining qadrli oltin soatini sotib, o'z sevgilisi Della orzu qilgan bejirim taroqni sotib olganligini tasvirlash orqali kitobxoniga ushbu sovg'alarni keraksiz matoh bo'lganligini ochiq kinoya qilganligini anglash mumkin.

Xuddi shunday kambag'allikdan aziyat chekkan yosh oila timsolini A.Qahhorning "Anor" hikoyasida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin. Asar bosh qahramoni Turobjon ayolining anorga boshqorong'u bo'lganligini bilib, unga aytgan paytda anor

olib kela olmaganligi o'sha davrning quyi qatlam sharoitini to'liq ochib bergan. Ikki yoshning o'zaro munosabatini tasvirlash orqali yozuvchi o'sha davrning o'g'ir sharoitini istehzo bilan ifoda etgan. Bu hikoyaning oxiri juda ta'sirli: Turobjon tongga yaqin paytda bir choyshab anorni uyning o'rtasiga tashlagani va uning vujudi titrayotganidan o'quvchi beixtiyor qahramon anorlarni majbur bo'lganidan o'g'irlaganligini taxmin qiladi. Bu ikki hikoyadagi qahramonlar, garchi turli xil millat, tili, dini, e'tiqodi bir-birlariga o'xshamasada yoki voqea hodisalar turli davrlarda sodir bo'lgan bo'lsada o'xshash mavzularni ifodalagani kitobxon tezda anglay oladi.

Shu bilan birga hikoyalardagi farqni ham zehni o'quvchi tez ilg'aydi. "Magining sovg'asi"dagi ikki sevishgan bir-biriga bo'lgan munosabatini berkitmaydi. Buni ularni suhbatidan, ya'ni Dellaning: "Jim azizim, bayramni senga sovg'a bermasdan qanday o'tqazaman..." yoki Jimning qo'llarini Dellaning yelkasiga qo'yib, "Seni sochingni kesganing meni seni sevishdan to'xtata olmaydi" degan nutqlari ochiq munosabatlar o'sha xalq urf odatida oddiy holat ekanligini anglash mumkin. A.Qahhorning qahramonlari esa aksincha, o'ta yopiq. Hattoki asar bosh qahramoni Turobjon boshqorong'u ayoliga anor olib kelmagan paytda:

-Ajab qildim,-dedi Turobjon titrab,-jigarlaring ezilib ketsin!

Bu gapdan keyin ayoli juda diqqat bo'ladi ammo Turobjon uni oldiga borib, unga: "Xafa bo'lma, shunchaki jahl ustida aytim" demoqchi bo'ladi ammo bunga uning izzat nafsi yo'l qo'ymaydi. Bu bilan yozuvchi butun o'zbekning tanti mardi ichidagi barcha hissiyotlarini ko'rsata olmasligini ifoda etgan. Ikki hikoyaning yakuni ham yozuvchilar ijodidagi katta farqni namoyon qiladi. Genri asarlarining yakuniy qismlari aniq voqealarga asoslangan. Della va Jimning sovg'alari foydasiz, ularning chin sevgilarigina haqiqiy sovg'a ekanligini o'quvchi payqaydi.

A.Qahhor asarlarining yakuni esa Genridan farqli ravishda juda keskin. Ayolning eriga:

-Qayoqqa bordingiz? -Nima qildingiz? degan savollariga Turobjon javob bermadi, aksincha, uning vujudi titrar edi. Bu suhbatdan shuni anglash mumkinki, yozuvchi ushbu hikoyada savol va javoblarni o'qivchiga ixtiyoriga qoldirgan.

Bunday o'xshashlik va farqlarni ikki hikoyanavisning barcha asarlarida kuzatish mumkin. Yana bir taqqoslashga arziydigan asarlardan "O'g'ri" (A.Qahhor) va "Yigirma yildan keyin" (O Genri) hikoyalarni misol qilishimiz mumkin. Ikki asarning g'oyasi o'xshash, ya'ni ular jinoyatchini qidirishadi. Faqat jiniyotchini qo'lga olish jarayonlari keskin farq qiladi. A.Qahhorning oddiy, sodda, kambag'al qahramonlari Qobil bobo va uning kampiri yo'qolgan ho'kizini topish uchun o'zlarida mavjud bo'lgan hamma narsani, xo'roz, tovuq va uning tuxumlarigacha

birgina "pristavga" xabar berishi uchun ellikboshi, mingboshi deganlariga tutqazdi. Adib bu bilan o'sha davrdagi oddiy xalqning va yuqori mansabdagi shaxslarning tafovutini ko'rsatib berishga harakat qiladi. Jamiyat naqadar ayanchli, boylar yana boy bo'lish ilinjidaligi, kambag'al Qobil bobo va unga o'xshagan oddiy xalq yuqori mansabdagi jamiyatning qonun va xohishlarini anglamaydilar. Oddiy xalqning tashvishi yuqori lavozimdagi davlat boshqaruvchilarini qiziqitirmaydi. Bunday holatni Qobil boboning sigirini qididishdagi ellikboshi va mingboshilarning bobo bilan munosabatidan yaqqol anglash mumkin. O.Genrining "Yugirma yildan keyin" hikoyasida esa, jinoyatchini topishdagi bahs-munozaralarni deyarli asar oxirigacha kitobxon tushunmaydi. Ikki do'st yugirma yildan keyin o'zlari katta bo'lgan ko'chadagi daraxt tagida uchrashmoqchi bo'lishadi. Organ xodimi obrazidagi qahramon ko'chalarni tekshirgandek aytilgan joyga o'z vaqtida boradi va begona yigit bilan ikki daqiqa suhbat qilib, uning qadrdon do'stini kutayotganligini biladi va o'z yo'lini davom etadi. Aytilgan vaqtdan ozgina kechroq boshqa bir kishi kelib, uning qadrdon do'stiligini aytib, uni ovqatlanishga taklif qiladi. Yemakxona eshigi oldida o'rnatilgan qurilma do'stini kutib o'tirgan kishini qidirilayotgan shaxsligi haqida belgi beradi. U qo'lga olinadi va uning qo'lga bir varoq qog'oz beriladi. Bir parcha qog'ozda: "Bob, men o'z vaqtida aytilgan joyga bordim va Chikago politsiyasi tomonidan qidirilayotgan odamni ko'rdim. Seni o'zim qo'lga ololmasdim va boshqa ichki ishlar xodimini jo'natdim, Jimmy" deb yozilgan edi. Kitobxon asar oxirigacha jinoyatchi haqida hech nimani tushunmaydi, ammo birgina maktubning o'zi jamiyat qoidalariga hamma bo'ysinish kerakligini tushuntiradi, hattoki o'ta qadrlı inson bo'lsa ham. A.Qahhor asaridagi o'g'rini izlashdagi holatdan Genri qahramonlari jamiyatga sidqidildan xizmat qilishi bilan farq qiladi. E'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, Genrining deyarli barcha hikoyalarida yakuni aniq voqealarga asoslangan bo'lsa, A.Qahhor hikoyalari esa o'quvchiga ochiq savol bilan murojaat qiladi. Xususan, "Qobil bobo Egamberdi paxtafurushning oldiga bordi. Paxtafurush uning holiga achindi va erni haydab olish uchun unga bir emas ikkita ho'kiz beradi faqat bitta "kichkina" sharti borligini aytadi. Bu shart kuzda malum bo'ladi ...". Kuzda nima bo'lishini o'sha jamiyatning, osha davrdagi odamlarigina biladi yoki hozirgi kitobxon esa shunchaki tasavvur qiladi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish joizki, yuqoridagi ikki adibning ijodlari o'xshash va tafovutlarga ega. Buni tahlil qilingan asarlarida ko'rishimiz mumkin.

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SPECIFIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGY IN A SCIENTIFIC TEXT

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Annotation. *The main goal of this research is to identify the specific features of phraseology in a scientific text. The objectives of the study include theoretical justification of the concept of a phraseological unit and its role in a scientific text, identifying the main problems associated with translating such units. A number of scientific papers have been written on this topic. As an example, the views of various scientists on this concept are given.*

Key words: *phrase, phraseology, stable combinations, word combinations, phraseological units, translation, scientific text, scientific phraseology.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur tadqiqotdan ko'zlangan asosiy maqsad – ilmiy matnda fraseologiyaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini yoritishdan iborat. Ushbu mavzu bo'yicha bir qator ilmiy ishlar tadqiq qilindi. Bu masalaga turli olimlarning qarashlari misol tariqasida keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ibora, frazeologiya, turg'un birikmalar, so'z birikmalari, frazeologik birliklar, tarjima, ilmiy matn, ilmiy frazeologiya.*

Аннотация. *Основная цель данного исследования – выявление особенностей фразеологии в научном тексте. В задачи исследования входит теоретическое обоснование понятия фразеологической единицы и ее роли в научном тексте. По данной теме написан ряд научных работ. В качестве примера приводятся взгляды различных ученых на данное понятие.*

Ключевые слова: *словосочетание, фразеология, устойчивые сочетания, словосочетания, фразеологические единицы, перевод, научный текст, научный фразеология.*

Phraseology is an important and multifaceted area of linguistics that studies stable phrases and expressions that have a special meaning and function in language. In the context of a scientific text, phraseology acquires special significance, since it is in these texts that specific information is formed and transmitted, requiring accuracy, clarity and brevity. Scientific texts, as a rule, differ from other types of discourse in their structure, style and purpose, which determines the specific features of the phraseology used in them.

Scientific text, as a form of communication, serves to convey knowledge, research results and discoveries. In this context, phraseological units play a key role, as they allow authors not only to express complex ideas and concepts, but also to make the text more accessible for perception. Set expressions and terms used in scientific literature often have a highly specialized meaning and require certain preparation from the reader for their correct understanding. Thus, phraseology in a scientific text becomes not just a means of expressing thoughts, but also a tool that

helps to form scientific thinking and promotes the exchange of knowledge in various fields of science.

As we know, at first glance, the use of phraseological combinations is a rare phenomenon, extremely uncharacteristic for the scientific style of speech. This is due to the fact that a scientific text does not assume the presence of any forms of expression, it is alien to the demonstration of feelings and emotions, close to rational methods of conveying content. According to A.N. Vasil'yeva: "the main functional feature of the scientific text is "a contextless and unambiguous expression of thoughts, devoid of connotations" [1; p.82], while phraseological units are highly "connotative".

One of the key features of phraseology in a scientific text is its lexical component. Scientific texts are usually saturated with terms and specialized vocabulary, which requires authors to be able to accurately select words and expressions to describe complex phenomena and processes. Lexical features of phraseology in a scientific text can include both set expressions and terminological combinations that help create a clear and logical structure of the text. In addition, it is necessary to take into account that many phraseological units can have different meanings depending on the context, which adds complexity to their use.

The semantic features of phraseology in scientific texts also deserve attention. Scientific language requires a high degree of precision and unambiguity in the transmission of information, so the use of phraseological units should be carefully considered. Some expressions may have cultural or historical connotations that may not be obvious to a reader who does not have special knowledge in this area. Therefore, the study of the semantics of phraseological units in a scientific text is an important part of the analysis of scientific communication.

As noted by E.V. Leskova, "one of the main features of phraseology in scientific text is its desire for precision and unambiguity. Scientific disciplines require researchers to strictly adhere to terminology, which is often based on established phraseological constructions. For example, in the field of medicine or physics, there are specific terms that are used to describe certain phenomena or processes. These terms can be part of broader phraseological units that help create a clear and understandable description of the object under study. Thus, phraseology in a scientific text not only decorates the language, but also serves as an important tool for conveying knowledge and ideas" [4; p. 34].

In addition, according to L.M. Ibatulina, "phraseological units in scientific texts are often used to create coherence and consistency in presentation. Scientific works,

as a rule, have a clear structure, and the use of set expressions helps authors smoothly move from one thought to another. For example, phrases such as “in connection with the above”, “therefore” or “in conclusion” serve as connecting elements that help the reader better understand the logic of the presentation. This is especially important in scientific texts, where not only the content, but also the form of presentation play a key role in the perception of information” [3; p. 517].

Phraseology can also serve as a stylistic element in scientific writing. Although scientific style is usually characterized by formality and rigor, the use of phraseological units can add expressiveness and dynamism to the text. For example, the use of metaphors or comparisons, even in a scientific context, can make the presentation more interesting. However, it is important to remember that such elements should be used with caution so as not to distract the reader from the main idea. In this context, phraseology becomes a kind of balancing element that helps to maintain scientific rigor without losing the reader's interest [4].

Such stylistic groups of phraseological units as terms or speech clichés (i.e., strictly “scientific” phraseological units) are the most “readable”, practically transparent in terms of meaning. A striking example of this is the phraseological combinations of legal (to provide assistance, to reach an agreement, to recover moral damages, to satisfy a request, to file a cassation appeal, to confiscate property) [2; p.151] and medical (to put on feet, medical confidentiality, goose liver, barking cough, wisdom tooth) [5; p. 248] orientations, which are often encountered in texts when working with the relevant specialties.

In conclusion, phraseology in a scientific text is a multifaceted phenomenon that plays an important role in the transfer of knowledge, the creation of coherence and consistency of presentation, as well as in the stylistic design of the text. Set expressions help authors express their thoughts more accurately and concisely, which is especially important in the context of scientific activity, where accuracy and clarity are of paramount importance. The diversity of phraseological units, their dynamic change and specificity depending on the field of knowledge make phraseology an integral part of scientific language, which emphasizes its importance in modern scientific discourse.

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DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE INDEPENDENT LEARNING FOR STUDENTS OF NON-PHILOLOGICAL SPECIALTIES USING THE CREDIT-MODULAR SYSTEM

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Annotation. *In this article, the integration of innovative technologies and teaching methodologies has become a crucial factor for the development of higher education systems. One of the most significant advancements in recent years is the credit-module system, which facilitates flexible learning pathways for students. This article focuses on the role of the credit-module system in enhancing the independent distance learning of students in non-philological fields. It emphasizes the importance of creating effective frameworks for independent learning and the incorporation of modern educational technologies to increase students' engagement and academic performance.*

Key words: *Credit-Module System, distance learning, independent learning, non-philological fields, educational technologies, e-learning, higher education, digital resources, self-paced learning.*

Technological advancements have revolutionized education, offering opportunities for learning beyond traditional classroom settings. Distance-independent learning enables students to access educational materials and engage in self-directed study without geographical or temporal constraints. This approach is particularly valuable for students of non-philological specialties, where practical application of theoretical knowledge often takes precedence. Moreover, online platforms provide interactive tools, such as simulations and virtual labs, that facilitate hands-on learning experiences. These tools allow students to experiment and practice skills in a controlled and safe environment, enhancing their understanding of complex concepts. Additionally, adaptive learning technologies personalize the educational experience, catering to individual learning styles and paces. This adaptability ensures that students remain engaged and motivated, regardless of their proficiency levels. Collaboration tools, like video conferencing and shared workspaces, further promote teamwork and peer learning, bridging the gap between remote learners and traditional classroom environments. As technology continues to evolve, education becomes more inclusive, dynamic, and accessible to all.

The credit-modular system, a framework emphasizing modular organization and credit accumulation, has proven effective in fostering autonomy and flexibility in learning. This system aligns well with the principles of distance-independent

learning, making it an ideal methodology for implementation in modern education. This article aims to investigate the development and application of this system for students in non-philological specialties.

Distance learning has been widely studied in various disciplines. According to Moore (1993), distance education allows for the separation of teacher and learner, facilitating independent study. More recent studies, such as Anderson (2008), emphasize the role of technology in bridging this separation, particularly through online platforms and virtual environments.

The credit-modular system, initially introduced in the Bologna Process, offers a standardized approach to education. As outlined by Knight (2004), this system promotes transparency and compatibility between educational programs across institutions. It has been effectively adopted in various fields to enhance student autonomy and learning outcomes.

For non-philological specialties, practical application often dominates the curriculum. According to Boud and Falchikov (2007), experiential learning plays a critical role in preparing students for professional challenges. Combining the credit-modular system with distance learning provides an opportunity to balance theoretical knowledge with practical skills, fostering a holistic educational experience. One significant advantage of this integrated approach is its capacity to cater to diverse learning needs and styles. By enabling students to select courses and modules that align with their academic and professional goals, the credit-modular system encourages personalized learning pathways. Moreover, it provides a flexible structure that allows students to pace their learning while accommodating external responsibilities, such as work or family commitments. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for non-philological students, who often need to apply theoretical concepts to practical contexts in real-time settings.

Another critical aspect is the system's potential to promote interdisciplinary learning. In many non-philological fields, knowledge from multiple disciplines is required to address complex challenges. The credit-modular framework facilitates the integration of cross-disciplinary content, allowing students to develop a broader skill set. For instance, engineering students can incorporate management or communication modules into their curriculum, equipping them with the diverse competencies needed for industry demands. Such an approach ensures that education not only focuses on specialization but also on adaptability and innovation.

This study adopts a mixed-method approach, combining theoretical analysis with case studies from universities implementing distance-independent learning for

non-philological specialties. Data were collected through surveys, interviews, and academic performance reviews. The effectiveness of the credit-modular system was evaluated based on student engagement, academic achievements, and satisfaction levels.

Benefits of the Credit-Modular System in Distance Learning. Flexibility: Modular courses allow students to progress at their own pace, accommodating diverse learning needs and schedules. Autonomy. The system encourages self-directed learning, essential for mastering complex technical and scientific concepts. Standardization. Credits facilitate recognition of achievements across institutions, supporting lifelong learning and mobility. Challenges. Technical Infrastructure, effective implementation requires robust digital platforms and resources, which may be unavailable in some regions. Student Motivation, distance learning demands high levels of self-motivation and time management, posing challenges for some students. Assessment, ensuring academic integrity and fairness in assessments remains a significant concern. Recommendations, develop interactive digital content tailored to non-philological specialties. A) Provide training for educators in designing and delivering credit-modular courses. B) Establish support systems, such as online mentoring and peer collaboration, to enhance student engagement.

Conclusion. The integration of the credit-modular system into distance-independent learning offers a promising pathway for advancing education for students in non-philological specialties. While challenges exist, targeted strategies and investments in technology can significantly enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of these programs. Further research is needed to explore innovative approaches and long-term outcomes.

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NEW APPROACHES IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to some topical issues in the methodology of teaching foreign languages at a technical university. The government decree on the intensive study of foreign languages, and the consequent creation of a new model program on foreign languages for non-linguistic universities, prompted creative teams, especially technical universities, to radically revise the methodology, objectives and tasks of teaching foreign languages in technical universities. The approaches are indicated: as communicative-active, person-oriented, integrative, where each student works according to the program, taking into account personal abilities. The goals and objectives of the academic discipline "Foreign Language", as well as the level of foreign language proficiency, in particular, the place of the subject "Foreign Language" in the professional activity of future specialists.*

Keywords: *Foreign language, Technical University, standard program, professional activity, self study, exchange program, scientific language.*

The gradual social reforms, including economics, science, health care, culture and other areas, which are carried out by the government of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, and the recent resolution on the intensive study of foreign languages, the huge growth of technical progress, contributing to the expansion of cultural and economic relations of Uzbekistan with many advanced industrially developed countries such as Russia, Germany, the USA, Japan, South Korea and other countries have generated great interest among young people in the in-depth study of foreign languages and, first of all, in English. The recent government resolution on the intensive study of foreign languages, and the resulting creation of a new model program for foreign languages for non-linguistic universities, prompted creative teams, especially technical universities, to radically revise the methodology, goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages in technical universities. Communicating with each other at subject Olympiads in foreign languages, at various scientific-theoretical and student conferences, which are held annually at the Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute with the participation of leading teachers with their students from many other technical higher educational institutions, students from many lyceums and schools, teachers exchanged opinions and decided to make specific proposals for this new standard program.

The course of study of a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, specifically in a technical university is divided into two stages, is also real and has

been carried out at TCTI for many years. All the above approaches: communicative-active, personality-oriented, integrative have been used and are used at the Department of Foreign Languages for a long time, especially the personality-oriented approach in groups of gifted students, where each student works according to the program taking into account personal abilities, which the teachers reported on at various scientific and theoretical conferences of the teaching staff of TCTI, TSTU named after I.A. Karimov. The goals and objectives of the academic discipline "Foreign Language", as well as the achievable level of proficiency in a foreign language, in particular, the place of the subject "Foreign Language" in the professional activities of future specialists are absolutely competently presented. In the section modern educational "technologies" - the item "tournament of intellects" is carried out especially during student scientific and educational conferences, thematic, which the Department of Foreign Languages of TCTI holds annually. Such conferences should be conducted entirely in English, German and other foreign languages and should provide an opportunity for all students wishing to speak in one or another foreign language without mechanical memorization, i.e. with a full understanding of what was said.

The proposed study of foreign languages in technical universities is carried out everywhere, however, the number of printed characters, the number of phrases for a certain period of time is overstated. The general educational stage, consisting of a) listening is possible in the amount of 60-70 words per minute; b) reading for learning - 1000 printed characters in one academic hour with a dictionary, where there may be up to 10% of unfamiliar vocabulary. Written speech can be carried out by translating the text, testing. Examination control must be carried out according to four traditional points: 1) translation of a special text into the native language in the amount of no more than 550-650 printed characters in 0.5 academic hours with a dictionary; 2) reading and retelling a popular science text of 1000-1200 printed characters or test control; 3) participation in a conversation in foreign languages or presentation of a report according to the topics studied during four years of study (10-12 phrases); 4) analysis of one of the terms in the specialty.

In our opinion, independent work is best carried out by writing essays with subsequent weekly control. We consider it possible to recommend continuing work on mastering foreign languages in groups with gifted students, where each student works according to an individual program, in accordance with their abilities and desires. Include, as a mandatory task for bachelors before the state exam, writing essays on translated specialized literature. In general, the proposed new curriculum is

complex, but feasible taking into account the comments of leading teachers of technical universities. We believe that the primary task is: 1. to create, through the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, creative teams of leading teachers from various technical universities, as was done in the 70s, when good textbooks were published in English, German, and French, which students from technical universities studied for more than 30 years; 2. create polytechnic dictionaries of foreign languages so that students could, when writing essays on the specialized literature they have read, where various terms abound, obtain the information they need about various innovative technologies abroad and present this new information in their native language, and not through a third language - Russian; 3. enable young teachers of technical universities to take at least short courses to improve their qualifications in the country of the language they teach; 4. create a scientific and methodological council on foreign languages for teachers of non-linguistic universities, which will consider pressing issues typical for technical universities, where the schedule of hours for foreign languages is apparently from specialized humanities universities; 5. send volunteers from abroad to short-term courses "1-2 weeks" in technical universities in order to cover all teachers of technical universities, so that the teachers themselves, research staff of universities, doctoral students could communicate with native speakers of foreign languages; 6. organize an exchange of students from technical universities with specialized universities in England, Germany, France, Austria, and other countries, at least for short-term training and internships.

To achieve this goal, experienced specialists with relevant work experience and erudition are involved in conducting classes with students, and the rectorates of these universities, using the example of TCTI, create all the conditions for improving the teaching of a foreign language.

Studying a foreign language in technical universities creates some difficulties for students, since students often work with scientific texts. At the same time, they encounter a scientific language that uses a large number of scientific and technical terms, as well as more complex grammatical constructions that complicate and hinder understanding and translation.

"Scientific language" is one of the most frequently used designations in the field of science and technology, which implies all possible forms of scientifically related relationships and is often placed in contrast to the concept of the commonly used "general" and "standard" language. Scientific language is subject to such

requirements as business quality, unambiguity, clarity, efficiency and economy, which apply to German, English, Russian, Uzbek and other languages.

In order to participate in technical progress, it is necessary to read fresh scientific literature in foreign languages. Even with a good knowledge of a foreign language and the methodology of working with various dictionaries, it is difficult to translate a technical text without mastering the translation methodology, so we decided to draw attention to this problem.

In technical texts, the objective theme dominates. First of all, objects and states of affairs are presented, information contributes. Thus, translation also shows the nature of information in essence. Its task, first of all, is to convey the content of statements and information accurately and without loss.

In technical translation, we are talking about content immutability and, accordingly, about information fidelity. Information fidelity means that the amount of information contained in the original text is preserved in the translated text. Any addition, reduction and change of information during translation violates information fidelity. If a technical translator makes a mistake, significant costs or consequences may arise as a result. Therefore, the principle of content immutability in technical translation must be followed without fail.

This means that for an adequate translation, it is not enough to simply transfer the constructions of one language with the closest possible constructions of another. Sometimes it is necessary to conduct a thorough pre-translation analysis in order to understand, for example, where it is necessary to sacrifice formal correlation in order to preserve the main thing - the meaning of the text. With an ill-considered "exact" translation, important semantic nuances can be lost. Preliminary analysis of the actual division of the original text serves the purpose of a meaningful translation.

Recently, the fact that passive modes of expression represent a necessary and also functionally correct means of expressing German scientific language has been disputed. Preference for a passive means of expressing scientific language is shown in high frequency and is justifiably found in the characteristic content and function of scientific-linguistic communications. Since in technology the subject, goal or result of the action are in the foreground. These circumstances are met by the passive and forms of passive sentences as a means of expression, first of all, of depersonalization and generalization in a special way.

Unlike the active voice, the passive voice indicates that the action is not performed by someone, but on something or on someone. The subject of sentences with the passive voice is not the one (that) by whom (what) the action is performed,

but the one (that) on whom (or on what) it is performed. For example, in the sentence “A chemist studies a chemical element,” the noun “Chemist” is the subject, denoting the performer of the action. Let's consider another sentence: “A chemical element is studied by a Chemist.” Its meaning has not changed. However, the subject is not the person who performs the action, but the object with which the action is performed, that is, what is affected by the performer of the action. In such sentences, the predicate verb is used in the passive voice.

Thus, teaching a foreign language in a technical university can be defined as a joint activity of teachers and students. When the former impart knowledge, skills and abilities to students, the latter acquire this knowledge, skills and abilities as a social process conditioned by the needs of society development, as a process of appropriating social, socio-economic experience that allows the student to act actively and adequately.

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TRANSFORMING LEARNING WITH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING: A GUIDE FOR TEACHERS

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Abstract: *Actually, Project-Based Learning (PBL) is an instructional approach that encourages students to get engaged with deep learning by working hard and friendly on a project through longer period. This type of method enables learners to investigate lifelong issues and challenging questions by collaborating with peers. After collaborating, students may get clear results. Compared to traditional strategies which focus on simple memorization and passive learning, The PBL method develops critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills by placing students at the center of their learning experience.*

Key words: *project, traditional, experience and collaboration.*

Аннотация: *Проектное обучение (PBL) — это, по сути, методический подход, который поощряет учащихся к углубленному обучению через усердную и дружелюбную работу над проектом в течение длительного периода времени. Этот тип метода позволяет учащимся исследовать важные в течение жизни проблемы и сложные вопросы, сотрудничая со сверстниками. После совместной работы учащиеся могут получить четкие результаты. В отличие от традиционных стратегий, которые фокусируются на простом запоминании и пассивном обучении, метод PBL развивает критическое мышление, креативность и навыки решения проблем, ставя учащихся в центр их учебного опыта.*

Ключевые слова: *проект, традиционный, опыт и сотрудничество.*

Introduction:

Project-Based Learning is an educational strategy. In this approach students study and respond to difficult, real-world problems or challenges. Instead of following a textbook-based curriculum, learners ought to find solutions by asking questions and working collaboratively to create a demonstration or presentation that shows their learning. All in all, In a world that is frequently changing, education must evolve beyond traditional methods of teaching and memorization. Especially, students today have to develop strong critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as the ability to collaborate effectively. Project-Based Learning (PBL) is one approach that professionally meets these requirements. PBL is a dynamic and engaging educational strategy that empowers students to take control of their learning. Importantly, this method should be always acknowledged by teachers in the classroom.

Comparing to conventional approaches that emphasize rote memorization and standardized testing, PBL motivates students to become active participants in their education. This practical, hands-on method cultivates deeper understanding, sharper critical thinking skills, and greater creativity.

There are main characteristics of PBL:

1. Real-World Relevance: PBL engages learning with real-life situations by making it more interesting and meaningful for students. For example: rather than just reading about global warming in a textbook, students might design a diagram with solutions that can tackle with the global warming. This will connect directly to real-world preventing the environmental issues;

2. Inquiry-Driven: Projects initiate with a main question by encouraging students to study and explore the topic deeply. For example: Instead of a chapter on the Testing Animals where the teacher provides all the information, the project might begin with the question: "How should we check the cosmetics before using them?" Students can then investigate why human being should or should not test on animals, analyze other versions of testing the products. The given question will guide their research.

Research demonstrates that students learn more when they work on group projects. These types of "open-ended" projects, where students need to analyze the problem and find solutions by themselves, are far better for learning. Because learners are supposed to make decisions about how to address the problem by considering different options.

Essential Elements of Effective PBL:

1. Fascinating Question or Challenge: A project starts with an interesting question or problem that initiates the learning process. This question should be complex, thought-provoking, and relevant to students' lives and interests;
2. Ongoing Exploration: Students commit to a continuous process of investigation, research, and collecting information. They examine the problem from various perspectives, ask questions, and pursue answers;
3. Real-World Application: Projects ought to connect to real-life issues and situations, making the learning experience more meaningful and engaging.
4. Student Agency and Preference: Learners should have some level of control over the direction of the project, their tasks, and their outcomes. This fosters a sense of ownership and promotes deeper involvement.

5. Cooperation and Communication: PBL places a high value on teamwork, collaboration, and effective communication. Students learn to work together, share insights, and contribute towards a shared objective.
6. Reflection and Revision: Students should be given opportunities to reflect on their learning journey, receive constructive feedback, and improve their work.
7. Public Sharing of Work: Often, projects culminate in a presentation of students' findings to a wider audience, such as classmates, parents, or members of the community.

The Benefits of Project-Based Learning:

- Deeper Understanding: PBL motivates students to explore topics more thoroughly, fostering more deep understanding;
- Development of Essential Skills: PBL assists students develop skills important for the 21st century, including critical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, communication, and creativity;
- Increased Motivation: Real-world projects, mixed with student preference, make learning more engaging and relevant, leading to higher levels of student motivation;
- Enhanced Retention: By applying knowledge practically, students are more likely to remember what they learn;
- Practical Application: PBL connects academic content to real-life contexts, demonstrating the practical importance of learning;
- Personal Development: Students develop self-directed learning strategies, increase their confidence, and learn to manage their own education.

Conclusion:

Project-Based Learning (PBL) encourages deep learning and vital skills by engaging students in collaborative, long-term projects by ignoring traditional memorization.

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MADANIY REALIYALARNING SHE'RIY ASARLARDA IFODALANISHI

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***Annotatsiya:** Mazkur maqolada realiya tushunchasining mohiyati, uning tilshunoslikda tutgan o'rni, milliy realiyalar va ularning boshqa leksik birliklar orasidagi farqi ochib berilgan. Shavkat Rahmon she'rlaridagi madaniy realiyalar tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, realiyalarni tasniflash masalalariga ham to'xtalib o'tilgan. Realiya birliklarining xalq turmush tarzi, dunyoqarashi va madaniyati bilan aloqadorligi hamda ularning lug'at boyligini oshirishda, milliy koloritni aks ettirishda tutgan o'rni izohlangan. Realiyalarni o'rganish va ular bilan bog'liq tadqiqotlar doirasini kengaytirish muayyan tilning ichki taraqqiyot xususiyatlarini o'rganishda va madaniyatlar orasidagi farqlarni keng yoritishda o'ziga xos ahamiyat kasb etishi qayd etilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Realiya, lingvokulturologiya, lingvomamlakatshunoslik, muqobilsiz leksika, milliy kolorit, irrealiya, atama.*

Kirish. Jahonda globallashtirish va integratsiya avj olayotgan bugungi davrda har bir millat o'z madaniyati va tilini saqlab qolishga intilmoqda. O'zligini saqlashga intilgan har bir millat kabi o'zbek xalqi ham asrlar mobaynida til sofligi va ravnaqi uchun kurashib kelgan. Bu kurash hozirda yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotiga mos tarzda tadrijiy davom etmoqda. Biroq bugungi davrdagi mafkuraviy jarayonlar silsilasini kuzatib bu harakatlar natijadorligini yanada jadallatish zarurligini hech kim inkor etmaydi.

Dunyo tilshunosligida til sofligini saqlash, uning ichki manbalar hisobiga boyish jarayonlariga ongli aralashuv, aslida, har bir millatning o'z tilini saqlab qolish, uni kelajak avlodga to'kis-tugal yetkazish ehtiyojidan yuzaga kelgan. Bugungi kunda til leksikasidagi bo'shliqlarni aniqlash va ularni to'ldirishga qaratilgan ishlarning aksariyatida tildagi mavjud ichki imkoniyatlarga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Bu, birinchidan, tilning sofligini ta'minlash uchun xizmat qilsa, ikkinchidan, so'z boyligini orttirish va ifoda imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishga ham xizmat qilishi tilshunoslar tomonidan e'tirof etilmoqda.

Muhokama va natijalar. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham bu borada salmoqli yutuqlar qo'lga kiritilgan. Har bir xalqning til sofligiga e'tibor bilan bir qatorda, shu xalqning madaniyati, urf-odatini ko'rsatib beruvchi realiyalar ham bugungi kunda lingvokulturologiyaning muhim tushunchasi sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda.

O'zbek tilshunosligida madaniy realiyalar tilda xalqning tarixiy, ijtimoiy, va madaniy hayotining aks etishini ta'minlaydigan muhim elementlardir. Ular tilning

leksik boyligi, frazeologik birliklari va grammatik qoidalarida o'z aksini topib, milliy madaniyatni boshqa xalqlarga yetkazish va anglash vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy o'zbek tilshunosligida madaniy realiyalarni o'rganish yanada dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda, chunki ular milliy qadriyatlarni asrab-avaylash va dunyo miqyosida targ'ib qilishda muhim omildir.

Aytish mumkinki, madaniy realiyalarda xalqning dunyoqarashi, qadriyatlari va tarixiy-madaniy xususiyatlari ifodalanadi. O'zbek tilida "suyunchi", "dasturxon", "to'yona", "rayhon" kabi so'z va atamalar (milliy topilmalar) milliy madaniyatni aks ettiradi va o'zbek xalqining hayot tarzini ko'rsatadi. Bu elementlar milliy o'zlikni belgilashda asosiy ahamiyatga ega. "Bugungi globallashuv davrida har bir xalq, har qaysi mustaqil davlat o'z milliy manfaatlarini ta'minlash, bu borada, avvalo, o'z madaniyatini, azaliy qadriyatlarini, ona tilini asrab-avaylash va rivojlantirish masalasiga ustuvor ahamiyat qaratishi tabiiydir". O'zbek tilshunosligida madaniy realiyalar til va madaniyatni o'zaro bog'lashda, milliy o'zlikni saqlash va rivojlantirishda, shuningdek, tilni global miqyosda targ'ib qilishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqotlar, tarjimonlik va ta'lim jarayonlarida madaniy realiyalarga e'tibor qaratish dolzarbdir, chunki ular milliy madaniyatni anglash va dunyoga tanitishda muhim manba hisoblanadi.

Jahon tilshunosligida madaniy realiyalarni o'rganish bo'yicha tadqiqot olib borgan olimlar til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro bog'liqlikni yoritib, ularning tarjimada, muloqotda hamda milliy xususiyatlarni anglashda ahamiyatini ko'rsatib berdi. Ushbu olimlarning asarlari madaniy realiyalarni ilmiy nuqtayi nazardan tahlil qilish va ularni tilshunoslik nazariyasi hamda amaliyotiga tatbiq qilish uchun asos bo'ldi. Jumladan, jahon tilshunosligida realiyalar bo'yicha bir qancha olimlar ham tadqiqotlar olib borgan.

Jumladan, S.I.Ojegov realiya klassik grammatikada tashqi lingvistika fani o'rganadigan, muayyan mamlakatning davlat tuzumi, xalq tarixi, madaniyati va aynan shu tilda so'zlashuvchilarning til va aloqalari hamda boshqa turli xil omillar hamda madaniyat predmetlari sifatida izohlangan. D.E.Rozental, M.A.Telenkovalar realiyalarni "so'zning nominativ ma'nosi uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiluvchi, mavjud madaniyat predmetlari" deb ta'riflashgan. L.N.Sobolev fikriga ko'ra, ekvivalentlariga ega bo'lmagan maishiy va o'ziga xos milliy so'zlar va iboralar, shuningdek, boshqa tillarda mavjud bo'lmagan milliy turmush tarziga oid birliklar "realiya" hisoblanadi, negaki ushbu predmet va hodisalar boshqa mamlakatlarda mavjud bo'lmaydi. A.V.Fedorov "realiya" deganda "ijtimoiy hayot va moddiy turmush tarzini

anglatuvchi”, faqat mahalliy hodisani ifodalovchi va boshqa xalqlarning turmushida va tushunchasida tengi yo‘q bo‘lgan so‘zlar”ni tushunadi.

Realiyalar badiiy asarlar va tarjimlar tizimida o‘rganib kelingan. She’riy asarlar misolida Shavkat Rahmon ijodi misolida talqin qilamiz. Shavkat Rahmon XX asr o‘zbek she’riyatiga o‘zgacha ruh olib kirgan va faqat o‘ziga xos uslubda ijod qilgan shoirdir. Shoir ta’biri bilan aytganda, asl qalamkash “jasorat” so‘zining tarjimoni, kuychisi bo‘lishikerak. Shavkat Rahmon o‘z ijodini millat hayoti, taqdiridan ayricha tasavvur eta olmasdi. Shuning uchun ham uning she’rlarida xalq madaniyatini, odatlarini ko‘rsatib beruvchi realiyalar talaygina. Xususan, shoirning “Gullayotgan tosh”, “Abadiyat oralab”, ”Hulvo” kabi to‘plamlarida xalq madaniyatini ko‘rsatib beruvchi bir necha so‘z va so‘z birikma shaklida qo‘llangan milliy xos so‘zlar ham talaygina.

Jumladan, ijodkorning “Hulvo” she’riy to‘plamini o‘qish davomida realiyalarning o‘ziga xos ko‘rinishlariga guvoh bo‘lish mumkin. Shoirning to‘plamga kiritilgan bir necha she’rlari misolida koloritlar, ularning qo‘llanishini ko‘rib chiqamiz.

Turkumning “Manzara” deb nomlangan she’rida shoir “yalangoyoq” so‘zini qo‘llaydi. Ushbu so‘z o‘zida bir necha ma’nolarni ifodalaydi. O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘atida yalangoyoq so‘zining sinonimi “oyoqlang” so‘zining ma’nolari quyidagicha keltirib o‘tilgan:

1. Oyoq kiyimsiz, oyog‘iga hech narsa kiyimagan.

Manba: Nigina kimsasiz dashtda ortidagi daryo tomon oyoqyalang yurib ketdi. Mirmuhsin, Temur Malik. Bir to‘da bolalar chug‘urlashib, bog‘dan chiqib kelishdi. Oyoqyalang, do‘mboq, oftobda toblangan. S.Nurov, “Narvon”.

2. Ko‘chma: kambag‘al, qashshoq.

Manba: Toshtemir ham keyingi toifa oyoqyalanglardan bo‘lib, Mirzacho‘lga boruvchilar to‘piga qo‘shildi. H.G‘ulom, Feruza. -Him, ana shunaqa oyoqyalangdan qo‘rq-da, – boshini liqillatdi Xo‘jayor. A.Narziqulov, “Hayot yolqini”.

Yuqoridagi izohlardan ko‘rishimiz mumkinki, yalangoyoq so‘zining ikki: o‘z va ko‘chma ma’nosi bo‘lib, har bir shaxs uni maqsadiga, vaziyatiga moslab qo‘llaydi. O‘zbek madaniyatida bu so‘zning har ikki ma’nosi ham so‘zlovchilar nutqida mavjud. Ko‘chma ma’nosi, asosan, “haqorat” ni ifodalaganda, bir shaxs ikkinchi bir shaxsni kamsitganda yetakchilik qiladi.

O‘z ma’nosida, asosan, oyoqqa hech qanday narsa kiyimaslikdir. Yalangoyoqda yurish yoki turish yer yoki zamin bilan to‘g‘ridan to‘g‘ri aloqa qilish imkonini beradi, bu hissiy tajriba va atrof-muhit bilan aloqani ta’minlaydi. Odamlar qulaylik, dam

olish, madaniy sabablar yoki o'zlarini asosli his qilish uchun yalangoyoq yurishni tanlashlari mumkin. Yalangoyoq bo'lish ko'plab madaniyatlarda, ayniqsa, issiq iqlim yoki yopiq joylarda keng tarqalgan. Shuningdek, u muvozanatni, holatni va oyoq kuchini yaxshilash kabi amaliy afzalliklarga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Talaffuz urg'u yoki dialektga qarab farq qilishi mumkin. Shevalarda ma'no farqlanishlari kuzatilishi tabiiy, albatta.

Shavkat Rahmon esa "Manzara" she'rida "yalangoyoq" so'zini quyidagicha qo'llaydi:

Oq sukunat portlar saharda,
kun nurida yonib, yaraqlab,
chopib kirar suvuq shaharga
yalangoyoq yashil daraxtlar.
Bir zumdayoq devor oshib,
Ko'chalarga tarqab ketdilar.
Darchalarga yuzlarin bosib,
bolalarday qarar kattalar. [7;84]

Ijodkor she'rida jonsiz narsaga-daraxtga nisbatan yalangoyoq so'zini qo'llaydi. Demak, ushbu so'z faqat jonli obyektlarga nisbatan emas, balki jonsiz predmetlarga nisbatan ham ishlatiladi. Yuqoridagi she'r buning yorqin dalilidir. Shavkat Rahmon "yalangoyoq daraxtlar" deya daraxtlarning oyog'i yo'q ekanligini, daraxtlar tana, ildiz va barglardan iborat bo'lishini ko'rsatib bermoqda.

Shoirning "Esdalik" she'ri ham realiyalardan holi emas. Bu koloritlar she'rning xalqona, tushunarli va she'rning o'ynoqi satrlarga ega bo'lishini ta'minlovchi unsurlardan biri hisoblanadi. Quyida she'rdan olingan to'rtlikni keltiramiz:

Unutganim yo'qdir hali
o'rikzorni, asov soyni,
soy bo'yida ko'zdan xoli
baqaterak o'sgan joyni. [7;85]

Yuqoridagi to'rtlikda shoir ikkita milliy xos so'zlardan foydalanish orqali milliy tilimizning naqadar boyligini, o'ziga xosligini ko'rsatmoqda. She'rda birikma holida "asov soy" va so'z sifatida "baqaterak" realiyalari qo'llanilgan. Ushbu so'zlarning O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida berilgan ma'nolarini ko'rib chiqamiz:

1. Rom bo'lmagan, odamga o'rganmagan, yuvosh tortmagan.

A. Asov tuya.

B. Kulgi uchun bo'lsa kerak, noib uni asov bir otga mindirgan edi. S. Ayniy "Sudxo'ring o'limi".

Cho'lga o'rgangan asov qo'y og'ilni buzib yuborguday tipirchilaydi. S. Ahmad "Qadrdon dalalar"

2. Ko'chma. Inson irodasiga bo'ysundirilmagan, jilovlanmagan (tabiat kuchlari haqida). Norin. Sho'x daryo, asov daryo. Tutqich bermas telba daryo. N. Safarov, "Olovli izlar".

Bahor kelishi bilan qorlar erib, tog'li hududlarda soylar suvlarga to'lib oqadi. Ba'zan o'zanidan toshib chiqib, har tarafga nag'malar qiladi, hech kimga va hech narsaga bo'y sunmaydi, shuning uchun bu jarayonga nisbatan "asov soy" birikmasi ishlatiladi. Demak, bilishimiz mumkinki, realiyalarning ma'lum bir mavsumda faol bo'lib, boshqa bir faslda nofaol bo'ladigan ko'rinishlari mavjud ekan. Soy realiyasi har qanday mavsumda ham qo'llanishi mumkin, ammo uning birikma holiday ko'rinishi, asosan, ko'klam oyida kuzatiladi. Soy so'zining izohli lug'atdagi ma'nolariga e'tibor qaratamiz:

1. Ikki adir yoki tog' oralig'idagi, ko'pincha oqar suvlar harakati va boshqalar natijasida hosil bo'lgan pastlik joy, suv yo'li, vodi.

Boy boyga boqar, suv soyga oqar. Maqol

Hozir ko'klam kunlari: qirlar, soylar ko'k-qizil pushti, go'los va tag'in allaqancha rangli chechaklar bilan ustlarini bejab, oshiq'larga yangi hayot, yangi umid berdilar. (A. Qodiriy "O'tkan kunlar")

2. Shunday vodiya, pastlikda doimiy yoki mavsumiy oqadigan kichik daryo, ariq, irmoq.

Soy suvi. Soyda cho'milmoq. Soydan kechib o'tmoq.

Choy to'kilib, soy bo'lmas, yulduz yig'ilib, oy bo'lmas. Maqol

U bomdodni ado etgach, xarsang toshlar oralab sharqirab oqayotgan soy bo'yiga tushib, tabiatning mislsiz jamolini tomosha qildi. Mirmuhsin "Me'mor"

3. Maxs. Miltiq stvoli ichidagi burama ariqcha.

Ko'rishimiz mumkinki, soy so'zining yana bir ma'nosi bo'lib, bu ma'no vazifa va shakl o'xshashligiga egaligi uchun shu so'zdan foydalanilgan.

Baqaterak so'zining izohli lug'atdagi ma'nosi quyidagicha:

1. Teraklarning tarvaqaylab o'sadigan, toldoshlarga mansub turi, qoraterak.

Manba: Normatparangning hovlisi guzarda, butun mahallaga ko'rinib turadigan baland, qari baqa terakning soyasiga joylashgan edi. (A.Muxtor "Opa-singillar".)

Daladan qaytsak, maktab hovlisidagi baqaterakning pastki shoxiga ilingan qo'yning terisini shilyapti. (O'.Hoshimov "Ikki eshik orasi").

Baqaterak so‘zi o‘zbek madaniyatida faol qo‘llaniladi. Ushbu koloritning qo‘llanish maydoni, asosan, tog‘ va tog‘ oldi hududlar va qishloqlar hisoblanadi. Albatta, o‘simliklar dunyosi bilan tanishgan hech boir insonga bu so‘z notanish emas. Shuning uchun ham she’rida baqaterak so‘zidan unumli foydalangan.

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak, realiyalar har bir xalqqa xos bo‘lgan moddiy borliqning madaniy oynadagi aksidir. Ularda xalqlarning dunyoqarashi, turmushi, urf-odatlarini yashaydi. Shu bois ijodkorlar ham ularni o‘rinli va kerali o‘rinlarda qo‘llashga harakat qiladilar. Shavkat Rahmon she’rlari xalqonaligi bilan ajralib turadi, chunki uning she’rlarida o‘zbek xalqiga xos va mos bo‘lgan milliy xos so‘zlarimiz talaygina, ularning ishlatilish o‘rni ham betakror. Xoh nasr bo‘lsin, xoh nazm, albatta, shu xalq madaniyatiga xos bo‘lgan realiyalar mavjud bo‘ladi.

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ROBERT LOUIS STIVENSONNING ASARLARIDA DOPPELGÄNGER KONSEPSIYASI: INSONIYAT TABIATIDAGI YAXSHILIK VA YOMONLIKNING KURASHI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola Robert Louis Stivensonning ijodiy asarlarida, xususan, “Xazinalar oroli” va “Doktor Jekill va janob Xaydning g‘aroyib hikoyasi” asarlarida inson tabiatidagi yaxshilik va yomonlikning o‘zaro kurashi hamda Doppelgänger (ikki qiyofa) konsepsiyasi orqali insoniyat dualizmini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Doppelgänger, Robert Louis Stevenson, xazinalar oroli, doktor Jekill va janob Xayd, inson tabiatidagi dualizm, yaxshilik va yomonlik, psixologik realizm, alter-ego, ichki ziddiyatlar, urakkab xarakterlar, antagonist va protagonist, axloqiy dualizm, insonning ichki kurashi, allegorik ifoda, insoniyat tabiati.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению творчества Роберта Льюиса Стивенсона, в частности, его произведений «Остров сокровищ» и «Странная история доктора Джекила и мистера Хайда», где через концепцию двойников (Doppelgänger) исследуется дуализм человеческой природы, а также борьба между добром и злом в человеке.

Ключевые слова: Doppelgänger, Роберт Льюис Стивенсон, Остров сокровищ, Доктор Джекил и мистер Хайд, дуализм человеческой природы, добро и зло, психологический реализм, альтер-эго, внутренние противоречия, сложные характеры, антагонист и протагонист, моральный дуализм, внутренняя борьба человека, аллегорическое выражение, природа человечества.

Annotation: This article is dedicated to exploring the duality of human nature through the struggle between good and evil in Robert Louis Stevenson’s literary works, particularly in *Treasure Island* and *The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde*, with a focus on the concept of Doppelgänger (dual identity).

Keywords: Doppelgänger, Robert Louis Stevenson, *Treasure Island*, *Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde*, dualism of human nature, good and evil, psychological realism, alter-ego, inner conflicts, complex characters, antagonist and protagonist, moral dualism, inner human struggle, allegorical expression, human nature.

“Xazinalar oroli”da Stivenson inson tabiatidagi yaxshilik va yomonlikning birga mavjudligini Long Jon Silver obrazi orqali ko‘rsatadi. O‘quvchi Silverni asardagi eng yaxshi rivojlangan xarakter sifatida sezadi, chunki u turli “tiplar”ni o‘zida birlashtirgan qaroqchi. Asardagi boshqa asosiy qahramonlar esa odatda faqat “yaxshi” yoki “yomon” sifatida tasvirlangan. Silverning xarakteri Pewning sof yovuzligini va Billi Bonzning jo‘shqin yaxshi tabiatini muvozanatlashtiradi. Ammo Long Jon Silver “to‘liq” xarakter emas, ya’ni u kitobda mustaqil alohida shaxs

sifatida yetarli emas. Silver va Jim Xokinsning xarakterlari o'zaro bog'liqdir: ular fikrlash va harakat qilish uchun bir-biriga muhtoj. Bu bog'liqlik inson tabiatining murakkabligi va qarama-qarshiliklarini o'rganishda Stivensonning chuqur tushunchasi va yondashuvini ko'rsatadi.

Ralf Timmzning fikricha, "Doppelgänger" bu do'stlar juftligi bo'lib (asl ma'noda 'bir juftning ikki qismi'), ular birgalikda yagona bir butunni tashkil qiladi, lekin yakka holda ular 'yarim qism' sifatida ko'rinadi va o'z alter-egosiga ("Alter-ego" atamasi lotin tilidan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, "ikkinchi men" yoki "muqobil o'zlik" degan ma'noni anglatadi) tayanadi.[1] Jim Xokins va Long Jon Silverning juftligi — bu Stivenson tomonidan Doppelgänger yoki "ikki qiyofa" konsepsiyasidan foydalanishga qilingan dastlabki urinishlardan biridir. Ushbu usul orqali Stivenson inson tabiatining murakkabligi va ikki tomonlama mohiyatini tasvirlashga intilgan. Keyinchalik, "Doktor Jekill va janob Xaydning g'aroyib hikoyasi" asarida Stivenson inson qalbidagi yaxshilik va yomonlik kuchlari o'rtasidagi kurashga chuqur e'tibor qaratganini ochiq-oydin ko'rsatadi. Ushbu ikki asar Stivensonning insonning ichki dunyosidagi ziddiyatlar va dualizmni o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishini aks ettiradi.

Lanyonning fikriga ko'ra, "Doktor Jekill va janob Xaydning g'aroyib hikoyasi"da Stivenson allegoriyaning chegaralaridan chiqib, psixologik realizm sohasiga o'tadi, ammo u o'zining boshlang'ich g'oyasidan uzoqlashmaydi. Asarning asosiy konsepsiyasi — Doppelgänger (ikki qiyofa) bo'lib, bu inson tabiatidagi axloqiy dualizmni aks ettiradi. Stivenson o'z tezisini allegorik tarzda ifodalaydi, bu esa "Markxaym" asaridagi jarayonga teskari jarayonni namoyish etadi. "Markxaym"da yaxshilik qiyofasi yomonlikning ustunligiga qarshi isyon ko'taradi. Biroq, ikkinchi allegoriyada Doktor Jekill qarama-qarshi fikrni ilgari suradi: yomonlik ham o'z erkinligiga haqli. Jekill o'z tabiatidagi uyqudagi yovuzlikni sehri dori yordamida uyg'otadi, va bu yovuzlik uning odatda nazoratni qo'lga oladigan yaxshi tomonini egallaydi. Stivenson bu asarda inson qalbidagi yaxshilik va yomonlik kuchlari o'rtasidagi murakkab kurashni o'rganadi va bu mavzuni allegorik ifoda bilan psixologik haqiqatni birlashtirish orqali tasvirlaydi. [2]

Stivensonning Doppelgänger konsepsiyasidan foydalanishi klassik "bir yaxshi, bir yomon" egizaklar tasvirlanadigan an'anaviy uslubdan farqlanadi. U inson tabiatini yanada murakkab tarzda ochib berishga intiladi. Doktor Jekill va janob Xayd jismonan bir xil emas: Jekill — "yaxshi tomon" — 50 yoshli, jismonan baquvvat va jozibador shaxs, Xayd esa yoshroq, kichikroq va ko'rinishda jirkanch.

Shunga qaramay, Stivensonning allegoriyasi jismoniy ko'rinishning axloqiy kuchlarni aks ettirishidan ko'ra chuqurroqdir. Doktor Jekill tashqi ko'rinishda

sog'lom va jozibador bo'lib ko'rinsa-da, ichki dunyosida, ruhida o'z istaklari tufayli yemirilmoqda. Aynan shu ichki parchalanish Jekillni janob Xaydni yaratishga undaydi. Jekill shunday deb o'ylaydi: agar Xayd uning tanasi tashqarisida yashasa, u dunyo uni bilganidek "yaxshi shifokor" bo'lib qoladi. Stivenson bu usul orqali inson ichidagi yomonlikni ajratib chiqarishga bo'lgan intilishni va bu qarashning axloqiy hamda ruhiy oqibatlarini ko'rsatadi. Bu Doppelgänger konsepsiyasining an'anaviy shakliga nisbatan yanada chuqurroq va murakkab yondashuvdir.

Robert Rojers adabiyotda Doppelgänger haqida quyidagicha kuzatishlar bildiradi:

"Agar yozuvchi bosh qahramonning o'zining "ikki qiyofasi"ni ko'rishini tasvirlasa, bu faqatgina o'quvchining qiziqishini oshirish uchun ishlatiladigan oddiy uslub yoki hiyla emas. Aksincha, bu inson ongi ichida o'z-o'zi bilan ziddiyatga tushadigan ichki bo'linishni anglash natijasidir. Shuningdek, ochiq-oydin xulosa qilish mumkinki, yozuvchi bir insonning ichki ruhiy kurashini tasvirlamoqchi bo'lsa, buni dramatik tarzda ifodalashning eng tabiiy yo'li uning ruhini ikki yoki undan ortiq qahramon orqali aks ettirishdir." [3]

Bu fikrlar adabiyotda Doppelgänger konsepsiyasining inson psixologiyasidagi ichki kurashlarni tasvirlash uchun samarali usul ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Shubhasiz, "Doktor Jekill va janob Xayd" Doppelgänger an'anasiga chuqur bog'liqdir. Jekill va Xayd bir shaxsning ruhidagi ikki xil tomonni ifodalaydi, ammo ularning muammosini oddiygina qilib "Doktor Jekill - yaxshilik, janob Xayd – yomonlik" deb tushuntirib bo'lmaydi. Shuningdek, Jekillni bosh qahramon (protagonist) va Xaydni qarshi qahramon (antagonist) deb aytish ham noto'g'ri bo'ladi, chunki bu ikki rolni bir odam — Doktor Jekill — o'ynaydi. Xayd shunchaki Doktor Jekill xarakterining bir tomonining shaxsiylashtirilgan ko'rinishidir. An'anaviy romanlarda bir qahramon odatda bir-biriga mos kelmaydigan xususiyatlarga ega bo'lishi mumkin, ammo Doktor Jekillning holati maxsusdir va bu bosh qahramon hamda qarshi qahramon tushunchalarini qayta ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi.

"Doktor Jekill va janob Xayd"ning syujeti, Stivenson yozgan shaklda (ko'p yillar davomida ayrim tanqidchilar noto'g'ri talqin qilganidek emas), insonning o'z hayoti uchun tanlagan yo'ldan chetlashtiruvchi ichki istaklardan xabardor bo'lishini tasvirlaydi. Bu hissiyotlar ko'pchilik uchun odatiy, shu sababli inson tabiatiga xosdir. Doktor Jekillning normal inson sifatida qabul qilinishining sababi uning bu ichki istaklarni o'zining bir qismi sifatida tan olishidadir. U bu istaklarni butunlay inkor eta olmaydi va shuning uchun boshqa odamlarga o'xshab yashaydi. Ko'pchilik o'zlarida

yoqimsiz sifatlarni bostirishga harakat qiladi, ammo Doktor Jekill bundan istisno hisoblanadi. Jekill o'zining "yaxshi qismi"ni "yomon qismi"dan ajratib tashlamoqchi, ammo bu jarayonda "yomon tomoni"ni his qilishdan to'liq voz kechmasdan o'z hayotini davom ettirishni xohlaydi. Bu inson tabiatidagi murakkablik va qarama-qarshiliklarni aks ettiradi va Stivenson bu konsepsiya orqali insonning ichki kurashlarini tasvirlaydi.

Dastlab, janob Xayd Doktor Jekillning muammolariga yechim sifatida ko'rinadi: Jekillning tanasi Xaydning "pastkash harakatlarini" amalga oshirmaydi, ammo uning ongi bu harakatlarning xotiralarini saqlaydi. Jekill Xaydni o'zining bir qismi deb hisoblagan paytda, uning shaxsiyati to'liq va yaxlit bo'lib qoladi. Biroq, keyinchalik doktor Xayd bilan o'zi bir shaxs ekanligini inkor eta boshlaganda, u "Doppelgängerning yarim qismi"ga aylangan chala mavjudot bo'lib qoladi va uning ichki buzilishi boshlanadi. Protagonist va antagonist nuqtai nazaridan, "to'liq" Doktor Jekill, ya'ni o'zida yaxshilik va yomonlikni birlashtirgan va bu kuchlarning birlashganligini tan oladigan shaxs, protagonist hisoblanadi. Jekillning o'zi va Xayd o'rtasidagi ziddiyatda esa Jekill o'zining Xayd bilan bir shaxs ekanligini inkor etganida, u va Xayd antagonistga aylanadi. Bu yerda antagonist deyiladi, antagonistlar emas, chunki o'quvchiga ma'lumki, ular aslida bir odam, garchi ular turli ko'rinishlarda namoyon bo'lsalar ham. Ushbu murakkab munosabat inson tabiatidagi yaxshilik va yomonlikning ajralmasligini va ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini ko'rsatadi.

An'anaviy tanqidchilar "Doktor Jekill va janob Xayd" asarida doktorni qahramon, Xaydni esa yovuz qahramon sifatida ajratib ko'rsatishga moyil. Ammo ushbu asarni o'qish jarayonida Doktor Jekilda juda kam miqdorda "qahramonlik" ko'rish mumkin. Stivensonning boshqa bosh qahramonlari kabi (Jim Xokins bundan mustasno), Jekill o'zini irodasiz va insoniy zaifliklarga moyil shaxs sifatida namoyon qiladi. Boshqa tomondan, uning qarshi qahramoni bo'lgan Jekill/Xayd (antagonist), Long Jon Silverni jozibador antagonistga aylantirgan qahramonlikka qadar ko'tarilgan yovuzlik chaqnashlarini namoyish etadi. Jekill, bosh qahramon sifatida, o'z istaklarini dunyodan 50 yil davomida yashirib kelgan. Ammo oxir-oqibat, uning shu qismida yashiringan Jekill (antagonist sifatida), jasoratga ega bo'lib (yoki shunchaki hiylakorlik bilan), janob Xaydni ozodlikka chiqaradi. Ushbu jarayon Jekillning ichki ziddiyatlari va insoniy zaifliklarni tasvirlashda markaziy o'rin tutadi.

Robert Louis Stivensonning asarlarida inson tabiatidagi yaxshilik va yomonlikning birga mavjudligi va ular o'rtasidagi kurash asosiy mavzulardan biri sifatida ko'rinadi. "Xazinalar oroli" va "Doktor Jekill va janob Xaydning g'aroyib

hikoyasi" asarlarida Doppelgänger (ikki qiyofa) konsepsiyasi orqali inson tabiatining murakkabligi, ichki ziddiyatlari va dualizmi chuqur o'rganiladi. Stivenson bosh qahramon va antagonistni bir shaxsning ikki qirrasini sifatida tasvirlab, yaxshilik va yomonlikning ajralmasligini ko'rsatadi. Bu qarama-qarshilik insonning ichki dunyosidagi ruhiy kurashlarni tasvirlashga imkon beradi.

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2. *Ibid.*, 92-bet.
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NEURO-LINGUISTIC APPROACH TO ENHANCING PRONUNCIATION IN SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: *This thesis explores neuro-linguistic approaches to improving pronunciation in second language (L2) learning. The field of neuro-linguistics has contributed significantly to understanding how the brain processes phonetic and phonological information. This study analyzes how neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) and brain-based learning techniques can enhance pronunciation skills in L2 learners. The research highlights the role of neural plasticity, auditory processing, and speech motor coordination in effective pronunciation training. Empirical findings suggest that integrating neuro-linguistic strategies into language instruction can lead to improved articulation, phonemic awareness, and accent reduction.*

Key words: *neuro-linguistics, second language pronunciation, phonetics, phonology, speech perception, auditory processing, neural plasticity, foreign language acquisition.*

INTRODUCTION: Pronunciation plays a crucial role in second language acquisition, influencing intelligibility, communication effectiveness, and social integration. Traditional approaches to teaching pronunciation often focus on mechanical repetition, phonetic drills, and imitation. However, advances in neuro-linguistics suggest that pronunciation training can be significantly enhanced by leveraging insights into brain function, auditory perception, and speech motor control. This article examines the application of neuro-linguistic programming and other neuroscientific findings to develop effective pronunciation instruction strategies. The study aims to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical application in language teaching.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS: Neuro-linguistic research has shown that second language pronunciation is closely linked to auditory processing and speech motor skills. Chomsky's (1965) generative phonology theory emphasizes the innate structures of language, while Flege's (1995) Speech Learning Model (SLM) highlights the plasticity of phonetic categories in bilingual speakers. LeDoux (2002) explored the role of neural pathways in speech perception, arguing that phonemic awareness is shaped by cognitive and auditory experiences.

In Uzbekistan, linguists such as Karimov (2018) and Yuldasheva (2021) have investigated how auditory training and articulatory exercises influence pronunciation skills in Uzbek-speaking learners of English. Their studies emphasize the importance of early phonetic exposure and interactive listening exercises to improve L2 pronunciation. Furthermore, Saidov (2019) explored the role of multisensory learning

techniques in pronunciation enhancement, highlighting how kinesthetic feedback supports speech production in L2 learners.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: This study employs a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative research techniques. Data collection includes experimental phonetic training sessions with L2 learners, pre- and post-training pronunciation assessments, and neuro-cognitive analysis of speech processing. The study participants include university-level language learners engaged in structured pronunciation exercises that integrate neuro-linguistic techniques, including auditory discrimination tasks, speech shadowing, and real-time biofeedback. Statistical methods such as spectrogram analysis and articulation scoring are used to measure improvements in pronunciation accuracy and fluency.

MAIN DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS: Findings indicate that neuro-linguistic approaches positively impact pronunciation development. Participants who engaged in neuro-based pronunciation training demonstrated higher accuracy in phoneme production, reduced foreign accents, and improved speech rhythm. Techniques such as speech shadowing, auditory feedback training, and articulatory positioning exercises significantly contributed to their progress. Neuro-imaging studies also support the hypothesis that targeted pronunciation training enhances neural connectivity in the brain's language centers, leading to greater retention and application of phonetic patterns. However, challenges remain in integrating these methods into conventional L2 classrooms due to varying cognitive abilities and teaching resources.

CONCLUSION: Neuro-linguistic approaches provide a promising framework for enhancing pronunciation in second language learners. By understanding the neural mechanisms underlying speech production and auditory processing, educators can develop more effective pronunciation training programs. This research underscores the importance of incorporating neuro-based methods such as speech perception training, motor articulation exercises, and cognitive reinforcement techniques into language curricula. Future studies should further explore the role of neurofeedback tools and virtual reality in pronunciation instruction to optimize learning outcomes.

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THE NEURAL MECHANISMS OF SPEECH ACQUISITION AND PRODUCTION: INSIGHTS FROM THE DIVA MODEL

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Annotation: *The article provides an in-depth overview of the DIVA (Disentangled Variational Autoencoder) model, a machine learning framework designed for domain-invariant representation learning. It explains how DIVA leverages variational autoencoders (VAEs) to disentangle different sources of variation within data, focusing on separating domain-specific, class-specific, and residual information. The discussion includes theoretical foundations, architecture, and practical applications, particularly in fields such as domain adaptation, fairness, and robust classification. The article also highlights experimental results demonstrating DIVA's effectiveness in learning disentangled representations, improving generalization across domains, and mitigating biases in AI models.*

This annotation captures the core themes and significance of the article, making it useful for researchers and practitioners interested in representation learning, domain adaptation, and deep generative models.

Speech production is a complex cognitive and motor process that involves intricate neural mechanisms. The DIVA (Directions into Velocities of Articulators) model, developed by Jason A. Tourville and Frank H. Guenther, offers a comprehensive framework to understand how the brain controls speech acquisition and execution. By integrating computational and neuroimaging research, the model provides insights into both normal and disordered speech production.

Key words: *DIVA (Disentangled Variational Autoencoder), Variational Autoencoder (VAE), Disentangled Representation Learning, Domain-Invariant Learning, Domain Adaptation, Fairness in AI, Robust Classification, Latent Variable Models, Deep Generative Models, Semi-Supervised Learning, Generalization Across Domains, Bias Mitigation, Machine Learning, Representation Learning.*

The Structure of the DIVA Model

The DIVA model describes speech production through two primary control subsystems: feedforward control and feedback control.

1. Feedforward Control: This system is responsible for executing well-learned speech motor commands. It is predominantly located in the left hemisphere and includes premotor and motor cortex regions. Once speech patterns are established, feedforward mechanisms allow for smooth and rapid speech production without relying on real-time sensory feedback.

2. Feedback Control: This system continuously monitors and corrects speech output based on sensory input. It is mainly right-lateralized and involves the superior temporal gyrus and ventral premotor cortex. If discrepancies between expected and actual speech output occur, the feedback system generates corrective motor commands to maintain accuracy.

Neural Basis of Speech Production

The model maps specific speech control processes onto distinct brain regions:

- The speech sound map in the left inferior frontal gyrus stores learned speech motor programs.
- The auditory and somatosensory target maps in the superior temporal gyrus encode expected sensory feedback.
- The error maps compare actual sensory input with expected targets, triggering corrective actions.
- The cerebellum and basal ganglia play crucial roles in motor learning, sequencing, and error correction.
- The supplementary motor area (SMA) acts as a gatekeeper, controlling the timing and initiation of speech motor commands.

Speech Learning and Adaptation

The DIVA model explains speech learning through two phases:

1. Babbling Phase: Infants explore random articulatory movements, receiving auditory and somatosensory feedback that shapes early speech motor maps.
2. Imitation Phase: Through repeated exposure and mimicry, speech sounds are refined, and neural connections between motor commands and sensory targets are strengthened.

This learning framework allows for motor equivalence—where different articulator movements produce the same speech sound—ensuring speech flexibility and adaptability.

Clinical Implications

The model has practical applications in diagnosing and treating speech disorders:

- Stuttering: Excessive reliance on auditory feedback due to weak feedforward mechanisms may contribute to stuttering. Studies show that fluency-inducing therapies shift brain activity back to the left hemisphere, supporting the DIVA model's predictions.
- Apraxia of Speech: Damage to the left premotor cortex disrupts speech motor planning, leading to disordered speech initiation and coordination.
- Cochlear Implants: The model has been used to study how individuals with cochlear implants adjust their speech using auditory feedback.

Applications in Neuroscience and Technology

Neuroimaging Research

Advancements in neuroimaging techniques, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and magnetoencephalography (MEG), have provided extensive evidence supporting the DIVA model's predictions. These technologies allow researchers to visualize brain activity in real-time and analyze how different regions contribute to speech production and adaptation.

Speech Synthesis and AI

The principles of the DIVA model have also been applied to artificial intelligence and speech synthesis. Researchers are using neural network-based models to develop more natural and human-like speech synthesis technologies. Understanding how the brain controls speech has significant implications for improving AI-driven communication systems.

Future Directions

Ongoing research is expanding the DIVA model to include prosody control, which governs pitch, stress, and rhythm. Additionally, understanding the role of the right hemisphere in feedback processing could further improve speech therapy approaches.

Further exploration into the interactions between motor control and cognitive processing in speech production could pave the way for new speech therapy techniques and neural rehabilitation methods. Future studies may also focus on integrating real-time brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) to assist individuals with severe speech impairments.

Conclusion

The DIVA model provides a biologically grounded, computationally precise explanation of speech acquisition and production. Its integration of feedforward and feedback control mechanisms helps clarify the neural basis of speech disorders and guides therapeutic interventions. As research advances, the model continues to offer valuable insights into human communication and its neural underpinnings.

Understanding speech production at a neural level is essential for developing innovative speech therapies, assistive technologies, and AI-driven voice systems. As neuroscience and computational modeling techniques progress, the DIVA model will likely remain a cornerstone in the study of speech motor control.

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XX ASR O'ZBEK AYOLLARINING IJTIMOIIY FAOLLIGINING ORTISHI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistondagi xotin-qizlarning XX asr o'rtalaridagi ijtimoiy hayotda ishtirokining ortib borishiga sabab bo'lgan voqeliklardan ayrimlari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: savodsizlik, "zamonaviylashtirish", konsepsiyalar, "hujum" harakati, xotin-qizlar bo'limlari, sinfiy tafakkur.

Sovet tuzumining xotin-qizlarga nisbatan yurgizgan siyosati o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra, ikki tomonlama xarakterga ega bo'lib, mintaqadagi xalqlarni butunlay qaram qilib olish maqsadida ularning an'alariga, milliy, diniy, tarixiy va madaniy qadryatlariga qarshi kurashish uchun ayollarni "tutqunlikdan ozod qilish", "zamonaviylashtirish" shiori ostida madaniy merosni inkor qilish siyosati olib borilgan. Ikkinchidan esa, mintaqadagi ishchi kuchi yetishmasligi tufayli xotin-qizlar mehnatidan xalq ho'jaligi rivojini ta'minlovchi mehnat resursi, ayniqsa arzon ishchi kuchi sifatida foydalanish va shu orqali O'zbekiston ning tabiiy boyliklaridan unumli foydalanishga harakat qilindi. Sovetlar o'zlarining bu maqsadlarini "Tenglik g'oyasi" niqobi ostida targ'ib qilib, butun dunyoga tenghuquqlilikni ta'minlashda kommunistik tajribaning "yagona" ekanligini namoyish qilishga urinishdi¹.

Umuman olganda bu davrga kelib, ayollarning qarashlarida ham o'zgarishlar kuzatilayotgandi. Chunki, bir tomondan ijtimoiy hayotda xotin-qizlarga nisbatan yurgizilayotgan barcha adolatsizliklar, xo'rliklar, ikkinchi tomondan esa marifatparvar jadidlarning xotin-qizlar ham erkaklar kabi bilim olishga haqli degan fikrlari ayollarning ruhan uyg'onishlariga sabab bo'ldi. Bu holat esa sovetlar siyosatining o'lka xotin-qizlari hayotida tub burilish yasashiga sabab bo'ldi. Buning natijasida an'anaviy jamiyat tufayli shundoq ham ijtimoiy hayotdan ancha ortda qolgan o'zbek xotin-qizlari sovetlarning asl niyat va maqsadlarini anglamagan holatda ulardan madad va najot kutdilar. Umuman olganda sovet hokimiyati xotin-qizlarning ijtimoiy hayotdagi ishtirokini oshirish va ularni ishlab chiqarishga jalb etishga katta ahamiyat bergan. Buning bir qancha sabablarini yuqorida ta'kidlangan bo'lsada, menimcha eng muhim masala xotin-qizlar onggiga sovet hokimiyatiga tegishli g'oyalarni joylash va butun jamiyatni sovetlarga xayrihoh jamiyatga aylantirishdan iborat edi. Chunki sovet hukumati o'zbeklarda farzand tarbiyasi onaga

¹ Жўраева Н.Д. Ўзбекистонда хотин-қизларга муносабат (XX асрнинг 20-80-йиллари мисолида). Ўқув қўлланма. — Т.: 2013. — 10 б.

ko'proq bog'liq ekanliklarini hamda yoshlarni o'zgartirish ularning onalarini o'zgartirishdan boshlanishini juda yaxshi anglagan.

Sovet hukumatining yaxshigina e'tiborini tortgan "xotin-qizlarni ozod qilish" masalasi avvalambor, xotin-qizlar o'rtasida savodsizlikni tugatish hamda ijtimoiy hayotga jalb etish orqali amalga oshirilishi belgilandi. Tarixni o'rganishdagi xolislikdan chetga chiqmagan holatda shuni aytish mumkinki, sovet hokimiyatining xotin-qizlar masalasida olib borgan siyosati o'lka hududida yashovchi ayollar hayotida ijobiy o'zgarishlarga ham sabab bo'ldi. Chunki bu harakatlar natijasida ayollarning ijtimoiy hayotga aralashuvi sezilarli darajada o'zgardi. Turli kurslarni bitirgan ayollar akusher-kalar, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari rahbarlari, xotin-qizlar maktablari o'qituvchilari kabi sohalarda o'z ish faoliyatini boshladilar. Yana bir muhim o'zgarish, sovet hokimiyati 1921-yildan boshlab nikohga kirish yoshini 9 yosh o'rniga 16, o'g'il bolalar uchun 16 yosh o'rniga 18 yosh deb belgilanishi bo'ldi. Bu esa sovetlarning ayollar turmush tarzini o'zgartirishdagi keskin choralardan biri hisoblanadi. Bu qaror natijasida esa sovet hukumati ko'pchilik ayollarning ularni qo'llab quvvatlashiga erishdi. Ayni paytda, joylarda xotin-qizlar bo'limlarini tashkil etish ishlariga ham alohida e'tibor berila boshlandi.

Sovetlar tomonidan tashkillangan konferentsiya va syezdlar xotin-qizlarning o'zaro fikr, tajriba almashinuvida muhim ro'l o'ynagan. Shu bilan birga, bu yig'ilishlar va xotin-qizlar bo'limlarining asosiy vazifalaridan yana biri ayollar o'rtasida "sinfy tafakkurni shakllantirish" edi. Bu holat aholi orasida turlicha qarshilanishiga qaramasdan, mahalliy o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlari ayollarni ishlab chiqarishga, maktablarga va turli ta'lim muassasalariga kengroq jalb etishga chaqirdi. Vaqtlar o'tishi bilan bu harakatlar o'z natijasini ko'rsata boshladi. Xususan, ijtimoiy va siyosiy hayotda ayollarning salmog'i oshib bordi. Agar 1925-yilda O'zbekiston da sovet apparatining quyi organlarida 200 nafar ayol ishlagan bo'lsa, 1926-yilda faqat Farg'ona viloyati bo'yicha qishloq kengashlarida 665 nafar ayol saylangan. "Qo'shchi" ittifoqlariga a'zo bo'lgan ayollar soni ham ko'payib borgan².

Ammo xotin-qizlarni ijtimoiy hayotga jalb qilish, voyaga yetmagan qizlarni turmushga uzatishni taqiqlash, jamiyatda ayollarning ham erkaklar kabi huquqlarga ega ekanliklari kabi ijobiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan masalalar sovet hokimiyatidan ham avvalroq ma'rifatparvarlarning ham dasturlaridan o'rin egallagandi. Jadidlar ham jamiyat rivojiga to'siq bo'layotgan ayollar orasidagi savodsizlik va kamsitilishlarga qarshi edilar. Jamiyatdagi ayollarga nisbatan bo'layotgan

² Ўзбекистоннинг янги тарихи. Иккинчи китоб. Ўзбекистон совет мустамлакачилиги даврида. — Тошкент: Шарк, 2000

zo'ravonliklar, xo'rlanishlar, adolatsizlik hamda jabr-zulmlarga bosh sabab o'rta asrlardan saqlanib qolgan eskicha tuzum va ma'rifatsiz jamiyat ekanligini teran anglagan jadidlar xotin-qizlarni ma'rifatli qilish, ularning ijtimoiy faolligini oshirish, ularning iste'dod va qobiliyatlarini ishga solish, diniy va dunyoviy ilmlarni egallashda ayollarning ham erkaklar bilan teng huquqliligini ta'minlashga chaqirgan. Chunki jadidlar faoliyatlarining dastlabki davrlaridayoq xotin-qizlarni jamiyatning to'laqonli a'zosi sifatida qabul qilmasdan, oila masalalarini to'g'ri hal qilmasdan, yosh avlodni to'g'ri yo'lda tarbiyalamasdan turib jamiyatni isloh qilib bo'lmaydi deb hisoblashgan³. Jadidlarda hikimiyat yetishmasligi sababidan ular bu islohotlarni ommaviy tarzda amalga oshirolmadilar.

Sovetlar mahalliy millat xotin-qizlarini ijtimoiy hayotga jalb etishda kasaba uyushmalarining delegat yig'ilishlaridan keng foydalandi. O'zbekistonda delegat yig'ilishlari 1920-1921 yillarda sanoat korxonalarida tashkil qilingan⁴. Ammo keyinchalik ushbu yig'ilishlar o'rnini turli iqtisodiy tadbirlar egalladi. Chunki sovet hokimiyati endilikda ayollarni iqtisodiy maqsadlarda ishlatishni reja qilgandi. Ular bu maqsadlariga qisqa fursatda erishdilar. Bunga sabab esa o'zbek ayollarining jismida azaldan mavjud bo'lgan mehnatsevarlik, vatanparvarlik tuyg'ularidir.

Umuman olganda sovetlar doim ayollar masalasiga katta e'tibor qaratganlar. Hatto 20-yillarning oxiriga kelib ijtimoiy faolligi ortgan xotin-qizlarni "sinfiy tarbiyalash" masalasi o'rtaga tashlandi. Shu maqsad yo'lida turli kurslar tashkil qilindi. Xotin-qizlarni partiya safiga jalb qilish siyosat darajasiga ko'tarildi. Natijada partiyada ayollar salmog'i sezilarli darajada oshdi. Bu holat 30-yillargacha davom etdi. 30-yillarga kelib "xotin-qizlar masalasining hal bo'lganligi" haqidagi xulosa natijasida, xotin-qizlar bo'limlari faoliyati ham tugatildi. 1930-yili "Kommuniska", 1943-yili esa "Yangi yo'l" jurnallarining nashr etilishi to'xtatildi.

Biroq, xotin-qizlar masalalari faqat sovetlargina emas mahalliy millat vakillari tomonidan ham ilgari surilgan. Bu jadidlarning g'oyalarida ham yaqqol ko'rinadi. Ular ham xotin-qizlarni ozod qilish uchun kurashganlar. Lekin jadidlarda yetarlicha kuch va tayanch yo'q edi. Bunday kuchga ega bo'lgan sovetlar esa ushbu holatni ma'muriy buyruqbozlik evaziga hal qilishga urindilar. Dastlabki davrlarda sovetlar ham juda ehtiyotkorlik bilan ayollar orasiga kirib bordi. Milliy xarakterni hisobga olgan holatda, har bir xonadonga kirib tushuntirish ishlarini olib bordi. Ammo keyinchalik vaziyat o'zgardi. Sovet hukumati iqtisodiy ehtiyojlardan kelib chiqib,

³ Раҳимова Г. Жади́длар ва аёллар масаласи // Адабий мерос. 1992. №1. Б. 63—66.

⁴ Жўраева Н.Д. Ўзбекистонда хотин-қизларга муносабат (XX асрнинг 20-80-йиллари мисолида). Ўқув қўлланма. — Т.: 2013. — 23 б.

xotin-qizlarni “ozodlikka chiqarish” bahonasida 1927-yilda respublikada ijtimoiy-siyosiy tadbir “Hujum” harakatini boshladi. Mustaqillik yillarigacha bu harakatga faqatgina ijobiy fikr bildirib kelingan. Tarixiy xolislik tamoyiliga ko‘ra fikr bildiradigan bo‘lsak, bu tadbir tufayli o‘zbek ayollari ruhan uyg‘ondilar, o‘z faolliklarini, erkinliklarini tiklab oldilar bu imkon tufayli tibbiyotda, maorifda, deyarli barcha sohalarda o‘z faolliklarini va salohiyatlarini namoyish etdilar. Lekin bu bilan ularni oqlab bo‘lmaydi. Chunki bu harakat natijasida nafaqat ayollar balki o‘zbek xalqi ham tom ma‘noda zarar ko‘rdi. Bu faqat ayollar taqdiriga emas, balki o‘zbek xalqining urf-odatlariga, tarixiga, diniga, tili va ma‘naviyatiga qarshi qaratilgan bir hujumdur.

Sovetlar xotin-qizlarni ijtimoiy-siyosiy va iqtisodiy sohalarga jalb qilishni jadallashtirish maqsadida 1926-yil iyunda VKP (b) MQ O‘rta Osiyo byurosi xotin-qizlarga nisbatan munosabatlardagi “eskilik sarqitlari”ni batamom tugatish haqida qaror qabul qildi⁵. Buning natijasida mamlakatning barcha hududlarida ushbu qarorning ijrosini ta‘minlash maqsadida olib borilayotgan harakatlar sun‘iy ravishda tezlashtirildi, oqibatda bu harakat “Hujum” nomi bilan mashhur bo‘ldi. Ushbu harakatga yuqorida ta‘kidlaganimizdek turli davrlarda turli qarashlar bildirildi.

“Hujum” kompaniyasi 2 bosqichda olib borildi: birinchisi – 1926-yil sentabrdan 1927-yil fevralgacha “tayyorgarlik” davri; ikkinchisi 1927-yil mart oyidan 1932-yilgacha “zarbdorlik davri”⁶. “Hujum” harakati musulmon xotin-qizlarining hayotida tub burilish yasadi, ijtimoiy faollik keskin oshib ketdi. Biroq, “Hujum” muvaffaqiyatlaridan esankirab qolgan partiya hodimlari mahalliy xalq qoniga singib ketgan islom omilini butunlay unutdilar. Unga bepisand qarab, yerga urish, oshkora tan olmaslik yo‘lidan ketdilar. Bu holat esa, shundoq ham sovetlarga qarshi bo‘lgan dindorlarning keskin harakatiga sabab bo‘ldi. Oqibatda, “eski tuzum”ga qarshi bo‘lgan xotin-qizlar harakati tarafdorlari bilan an‘anaviy turmush tarafdorlari bo‘lgan dindorlar orasida kurash boshlanib ketdi. Lekin bu yerda reaksiyon ruhoniylar bilan taraqqiyparvar ruhoniylarni aralashtirmasligimiz darkor. Chunki bu davrga kelib, ruhoniylar orasida ham bo‘linish yuzaga kelgan bo‘lib, reaksiyon ruhoniylar xotin-qizlarni “ochish” siyosatiga ayollarni o‘ldirish va jazolash orqali javob bergan bo‘lsa, taraqqiyparvar ruhoniylar esa xotin-qizlar masalasida sovetlarning siyosatiga biroz bo‘lsada hayrixoh bo‘lgan hamda bu masalaning oxirida qon to‘kilishlar

⁵Жўраева Н.Д. Ўзбекистон ижтимоий-иқтисодий ва маданий ҳаётда хотин-қизларининг ўрни (XX асрнинг 20—30-йиллари мисолида). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. — Т.: 2004. — 45 б.

⁶ Алимova Д.А. Женский вопрос в Средней Азии: История изучения и современные проблемы. АН РУ. Институт Истории. — Т.; Фан. 1991. — 132 с.

bo'lishini sezgan holatda bularning oldini olishga harakat qilganlar. Ularning maqsadi keskin vaziyatlarni yuzaga keltirmagan holatda xotin-qizlar masalalarida ba'zi islohotlarni amalga oshirilishiga erishish edi.

20-yillar oxirida "Hujum" shu qadar safarbarlik tusini oldiki, xotin-qizlar yuzini ochish bo'yicha jumhuriyatlar orasida sotsialistik musobaqa ham o'tkazilgan, paranjiga qarshi komissiyalar tuzilgan. Shuningdek, ayollar yuzidan paranjini yulib olib, yoqib yuborganlarga mukofotlar va'da qilinishi ishsiz yurgan bekorchi sayoqlarga qo'l kelgan. Ular ko'chada ayollar yuzidan paranjini yulib ola boshlaganlar⁷. Biroq, sovetlarning bu harakatlari tuzatib bo'lmas oqibatlariga olib keldi. Qanchadan qancha ayollar hayotdan erta ko'z yumdi. Chunki hali musulmon aholi ayollarning bunday turmush tarzi kechirishiga, ijtimoiy hayotda erkaklar bilan teng bo'lishiga tayyor emasdilar. Ko'pincha "ozod etilgan" ayollar tunda o'ldirib ketilardi. Rasmiy hujjatlarda 1927-28 yillarda birgina O'zbekiston da 2,5 mingdan ortiq faol xotin-qizlar hayotlaridan judo bo'lgani raqamlangan⁸. Agarda o'z vaqtida sovet hokimiyati harakatlarining so'nggi nima bilan tugashini oldindan baholay olganida, bunchalik ayollarning umriga zomin bo'lmasdilar. Sovetlarga faqat natija muhim bo'ldi. Harakatlar natijasida ayollarning ijtimoiy faolligi oshdi lekin ayollar uchun bu qimmatga tushdi.

Xolosa qilib aytganda, sovetlarning xotin-qizlar masalarida oxirini o'ylamay, shoshma-shosharlik bilan amalga oshirgan siyosati natijasida juda ko'plab xotin-qizlarimiz hayotdan barvaqt ko'z yumdilar. To'g'ri, ayollarning ijtimoiy faolligi ortishi ko'p jihatdan foydali bo'ldi. Lekin buning sovetlar tutgan yo'lidan emas, taraqqiyparvar ruhoniylar aytgan yo'l orqali amalga oshirganlarida balki, buncha qurbon bermagan bo'lardik. Chunki har qanday keskin o'zgarishni jamiyat hayotiga tadbiiq etishdan avval, jamiyatning holatini o'zgarishlarga tayyorlash muhim masaladir. Agarda xotin-qizlar masalalarida mahalliy xalq an'analarini e'tiborga olgan holda, sovetlar "xurofotchilar" deb qoralagan ruhoniylar bilan hamkorlik o'rnatilganda va eng muhim masala xotin-qizlarning ijtimoiy faolligi haqida faqat ayollar orasida emas balki, erkaklar orasida ham targ'ibot-tashviqot ishlari amalga oshirilganda, ehtimol natija butunlay boshqacha bo'lardi. Rus hukumati tomonidan tashkillangan ushbu harakat tufayli ko'plab ayollar o'z yaqinlari tomonidan fojeali tarzda o'ldirila boshlandi. Bu holat eng ko'p paraji tashlashdan keyin yuz berdi. Qanchadan-qancha ayollarimiz o'z otalari, erlari, aka va hatto ukalari tomonidan

⁷ Жўраева Н.Д. Ўзбекистонда хотин-қизларга муносабат (XX асрнинг 20-80-йиллари мисолида). Ўқув қўлланма. — Т.: 2013. — 43 б.

⁸ Ўша асар. 43

o'ldirildi. Ommaviy qotilliklar ko'paygachgina sovet hukumati o'zi yo'l qo'ygan hatoni tushunib yetdi, ammo kech bo'lib bo'lgandi. Endigi chora esa paranjini tashlagan ayollarni qonun yo'li bilan himoya qilish edi. Chunki ko'plab paranjini tashlagan ayollar yaqinlarining tayziqi bilan qayta "yopingan" edi. Birgina Marg'ilonning o'zida 3000 ayol paranjini tashladi. Lekin oradan bir yil o'tmay ularning 2600 ga yaqini qayta paranji o'radilar. Nima bo'lganda ham, 30-yillar oxiriga kelib ayollarning jamiyatdagi faolligi sezilarli darajada oshishiga erishildi

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RAQAMLI TA'LIM VA UNING CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHDA IJTIMOIY-MADANIY KOMPETENTLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISHGA TA'SIRI

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***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada chet tillarini o'qitishda talabalarning ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentligini shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi. Madaniy jihatlarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish muhimligi ta'kidlanadi. Asosiy e'tibor o'quvchilarga madaniy almashinuv va madaniyatlararo muloqot uchun yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadigan turli raqamli vositalarga, jumladan, onlayn platformalar, multimedia resurslari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va o'yin texnologiyalariga qaratilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik, raqamli texnologiyalar, multimedia resurslari, madaniyatlararo muloqot, onlayn platformalar, geymifikatsiya.*

Globalashuv va texnologiyaning jadal rivojlanishi sharoitida ta'lim tobora xilma-xil bo'lib bormoqda. Onlayn kurslar, elektron platformalar va ko'plab interfaol resurslarni o'z ichiga olgan raqamli ta'lim, ayniqsa, chet tillarini o'rganish kontekstida an'anaviy ta'lim va o'qitish yondashuvlarini tubdan o'zgartiradi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, o'rganilayotgan tilda so'zlashadigan mamlakatlarning madaniy xususiyatlarini muvaffaqiyatli tushunishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirish ta'limning muhim jihati hisoblanadi.

Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini, balki ma'lum bir til bilan bog'liq madaniy kontekstlar, ijtimoiy me'yorlar va urf-odatlarini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Ta'lim jarayonini raqamlashtirish sharoitida ijtimoiy-madaniy elementlarni tillarni o'rganishga integratsiya qilish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar paydo bo'ladi. Zamonaviy texnologik yechimlar nafaqat talabalarni til muhitiga singdirish, balki ularni til sohiblarining turli urf-odatlari va turmush tarzi bilan tanishtirish imkonini beradi.

Raqamli ta'limning afzalliklariga qaramay, uning chet tillarini o'rganishda ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirishga ta'siri chuqurroq tahlil va tadqiqotlarni talab qiladi. Ushbu maqolada biz raqamli ta'limning asosiy elementlarini, shuningdek ularning chet tillarini o'rganayotgan talabalarda ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirishdagi rolini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Tadqiqotimizning maqsadi ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish va talabalarda ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlashdir.

Raqamli ta'lim bilim berish va ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish uchun raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol ta'lim usullaridan foydalanadigan o'qitish jarayoni bo'lib, an'anaviy yondashuvlardan, ya'ni darsliklar va ma'ruzalar asosida o'qitishdan farq qiladi. So'nggi yillarda raqamli ta'limning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda, shuningdek, u turli mamlakatlarda ta'lim tizimining muhim komponentiga aylanyapti. Tadqiqotchilarning fikricha, "raqamli ta'lim turli texnologiyalardan foydalanish orqali bilimlarni yaratish, uzatish va almashish jarayonini o'z ichiga oladi" [Afshari et al., 2013].

Raqamli ta'limning asosiy xususiyatlaridan biri uning moslashuvchanligi hisoblanadi. Talabalar o'zlarining shaxsiy sur'atida o'qish, eng qulay formatlar va materiallarni tanlash imkoniyatiga ega. Masalan, tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, "raqamli vositalardan foydalanib ta'lim olayotgan talabalar o'z vaqtlarini va ta'lim resurslarini boshqarishda yanada samarali bo'lishlari mumkin" [Archer et al., 2014].

Zamonaviy texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonini faollashtirishga yordam beradigan ko'plab resurslar va vositalarni taqdim etadi. MOOC (kattalar uchun ochiq onlayn kurslar) kabi formatlar tomoshabinlarga dunyoning yetakchi ekspertlari va universitetlaridan bilim olish imkoniyatini beradi. "MOOC ta'lim sohasida muhim hodisa bo'lib, sifatli o'qitish va turli madaniy kontekstlarga kirishni ta'minlaydigan platformaga aylangan" [Yuan & Powell, 2013].

Raqamli ta'limning muhim jihatlaridan biri geografik to'siklarni bartaraf etish va turli mamlakatlardan kelgan talabalar uchun muloqot imkoniyatlarini yaratish qobiliyatidir. Ochiq raqamli platformalar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar talabalar o'rtasida aloqalarni o'rnatishga va tajriba almashishga imkon berib, ta'lim jarayonini boyitadi. "Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali madaniyatlararo muloqot ijtimoiy-madaniy farqlar va xususiyatlarni chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi" [Krashen, 1982].

Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik chet tillarini o'rganishda muhim komponent bo'lib, o'rganilayotgan til ishlatiladigan madaniy, tarixiy va ijtimoiy kontekstlarni bilishni va tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik tilni chuqurroq tushunishga yordam berib, o'quvchilarga faqat leksik va grammatika tuzilmalarini o'zlashtirishga emas, balki muloqot madaniyatining nozikliklariga kirishga ham imkon beradi.

Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik doirasida bir nechta muhim jihatlarni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin:

1. Lisoniy kompetentlik tilni samarali muloqot uchun ishlatish qobiliyatidir. Ushbu jihatda til sohiblariga xos bo'lgan idiomalar, sleng va boshqa ifodalardan xabardorlik muhim rol o'ynaydi [Yevropa Kengashi, 2001].

2. Etnik kompetentlik boshqa etnik guruhlarning madaniy xususiyatlarini, an'analari va qadriyatlarini tushunish va hurmat qilishdir. Chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida madaniy farqlar va stereotiplarni muhokama qilish bunday farqlarga nisbatan bag'rikenglik va ochiqlikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi [Byram, 1997].

3. Madaniy kompetentlik o'rganilayotgan til asosida madaniyat, falsafa va tarix to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni solishtirish va qo'llay olish qobiliyatidir. O'quvchilar madaniy me'yorlarning til va xulq-atvorni qanday ta'sir qilishi haqida tushunishlari zarur. Ushbu holat madaniyatlararo muloqotda ayniqsa muhimdir.

Ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik o'quvchilardan nafaqat bilimlar, balki ushbu bilimlarni amaliy muloqotda qo'llash imkonini beradigan ko'nikmalarni ham talab qiladi. Byramning fikricha, "ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik nafaqat madaniyatning jihatlarini bilish, balki boshqa madaniyat egalari bilan muloqotda bo'lish qobiliyatidir" [Byram, 1997].

Shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik tilni o'rganishda alohida ahamiyatga ega, chunki u nafaqat tilni funksional qo'llashni ta'minlaydi, balki talabalar uchun til sohiblari bilan chuqurroq aloqalar o'rnatishga imkon beradi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yuqori ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikka ega talabalarning til muhitiga muvaffaqiyatli moslashishi ularning shaxsiy va kasbiy rivojlanishiga yordam beradi.

Shunday qilib, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlik chet tilini muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirish uchun muhim omil bo'lib, o'quvchilarga tilni tushunish bilan birga, uni madaniyatlararo muloqot kontekstida qo'llash imkonini beradi. Ushbu jihat globallashuv davrida ayniqsa dolzarbdir.

Texnologiyalar rivojlanishi va raqamli ta'limga o'tish bilan birga, chet tillarini o'rganish jarayonida ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirishga bo'lgan qiziqish sezilarli darajada ortdi. Raqamli vositalar va resurslar ta'limda madaniy jihatlarni integratsiyalash uchun yangi ufqlarni ochib, dinamik va interfaol ta'lim muhitini yaratishga imkon beradi. Quyida raqamli ta'lim ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shayotgani va qaysi amaliy yondashuvlar eng samarali ekanligini ko'rib chiqamiz.

1. Interaktiv texnologiyalar. Zamonaviy ta'lim platformalari va ilovalari o'quvchilarga til va madaniyat sohiblari bilan muloqotda bo'lish imkoniyatini taklif etadi. Video-chatlar, onlayn kurslar va forumlardan foydalanish til muhitiga kirish va madaniy amaliyotlarni real vaqt rejimida kuzatish uchun noyob imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Widad Ma [2024] ta'kidlaganidek, "interfaol texnologiyalar o'quvchilarga tilni o'rganishga yordam beribgina qolmay, balki madaniyatga kirishga imkon berib,

boshqa turmush tarzini chuqurroq tushunishga va hurmat bilan qarashga xizmat qiladi”.

2. Multimedia resurslaridan foydalanish. Raqamli ta'lim talabalarga filmlar, seriallar, podkastlar va bloglar kabi turli multimedia resurslariga kirish imkoniyatini taklif etadi. Bunday resurslar o'quvchilarga o'rganilayotgan tilni gapiradigan mamlakatlarning madaniy amaliyotlari, an'analari va dolzarb mavzulari bilan tanishishga yordam beradi. Tadqiqotlarda “multimedia materiallari chet tilini o'rganishni yanada motivatsiyali va qiziqarli qiladi, shuningdek, tanqidiy fikrlashni va ijtimoiy-madaniy kontekstni tushunishni rivojlantiradi” [Chun et al., 2016], deb ta'kidlanadi.

3. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va madaniy almashuv. Facebook, Instagram va TikTok kabi ijtimoiy platformalar til va madaniyat o'rganishda muhim vositalarga aylanmoqda. Ular o'quvchilarga til sohiblari bilan aloqalar o'rnatish, madaniy munozaralarda ishtirok etish va turli masalalar bo'yicha fikr almashish imkonini beradi.

4. Kross-madaniy loyihalar. Raqamli texnologiyalar turli mamlakatlardan talabalar birgalikdagi vazifalar ustida ishlash, bilim va tajriba almashish imkonini beruvchi kross-madaniy loyihalarni amalga oshirishga imkon beradi. Bunday tashabbuslar til o'rganishga yordam beribgina qolmay, balki ijtimoiy-madaniy jihatlarni chuqurlashtiradi, hamda o'quvchilarda madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi [O'Dowd, 2020].

5. Raqamli metodik materiallarni ishlab chiqish. O'qituvchilar shuningdek, interfaol metodik materiallar yaratish uchun raqamli texnologiyalarni ishlatishlari mumkin. Bunday materiallar ijtimoiy-madaniy mavzularga oid vazifalar va testlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Masalan, veb-kvestlar va virtual sayohatlardan foydalanish o'quvchilarga o'rganilayotgan til mamlakatlaridagi madaniy yodgorliklar, tarix va an'analar bilan tanishishga yordam berib, ularning ijtimoiy-madaniy ufqlarini sezilarli darajada kengaytiradi [Dudeney & Hockly, 2007].

Shunday qilib, raqamli ta'lim ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirishda chet tillarini o'rganayotgan talabalar uchun kuchli vositani anglatadi. Madaniyat elementlarini raqamli ta'lim muhitiga integratsiyalash nafaqat o'quv jarayonini boyitadi, balki boshqa madaniyatlarga ochiqlik va bag'rikenglikni rivojlantirishga ham yordam beradi.

Shubhasiz afzalliklariga qaramasdan, raqamli ta'lim va ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni chet tillarini o'qitishga integratsiya qilish bir qator muammolar va to'siqlarga duch kelmoqda, shu jumladan:

1. Kontent sifatining pasayishi. Raqamli ta'limiy kontent sifati o'zgaruvchan bo'lib, barcha resurslar madaniyat va til haqida zamonaviy va aniq ma'lumotlar taqdim etmaydi. O'qituvchilar o'quv jarayonida foydalanadigan materiallarni va platformalarni tanlashda ehtiyotkor bo'lishlari zarur. Past sifatlilik kontent talabalar orasida ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

2. O'qituvchilarning tayyorgarligining yetishmasligi. Barcha o'qituvchilarda raqamli texnologiyalar bilan ishlash yoki ta'lim jarayoniga ijtimoiy-madaniy jihatlarni integratsiyalash bo'yicha yetarli ko'nikmalarga ega emasligi raqamli ta'limning imkoniyatlaridan yetarli darajada foydalanmaslikka olib kelishi mumkin. O'qituvchilarni bu sohada professional rivojlantirish va o'qitish muvaffaqiyatli texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi uchun zaruriy shart-sharoitlar bo'ladi.

3. Madaniy stereotiplar. Raqamli muhit ba'zan boshqa madaniyatlar haqida stereotiplarni tarqatishga xizmat qilishi mumkin. Voqelikni tasvirlashda yoki madaniy guruhlarga nisbatan salbiy nuqtai nazar beruvchi materiallarni tanlashda ehtiyot bo'lish zarur. Madaniyatlarni taqdim etishda muvozanatli va xilma-xil yondashuvni ta'minlash muhimdir, shunday qilib madaniyatga tor qarashlardan qochish mumkin.

4. Xavfsizlik va maxfiylik muammolari. Raqamli platformalar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning ta'lim maqsadlarida foydalanilishi talabalarning ma'lumotlari xavfsizligi va maxfiyligi bo'yicha xavotirlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilishni ta'minlash va talabalarni onlayn xavfsizlikka o'rgatish muhimdir, shunda ular raqamli makonda xavfsiz aloqada bo'lishlari mumkin.

Shunday qilib, raqamli ta'lim va ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni o'qitishga integratsiya qilish kompleks yondashuvni va samarali o'qish uchun yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab muammolarni hal etishni talab qiladi. Ushbu muammolarning mohiyatini tushunish o'qituvchilarga o'z usullarini va yondashuvlarini yaxshiroq moslashtirishga yordam berib, chet tilini va madaniyatini o'rganish uchun yanada inklyuziv va samarali shart-sharoitlarni yaratadi.

Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalarda ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni shakllantirish chet tillarini muvaffaqiyatli o'rganishning muhim elementidir. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'limda madaniy jihatlarni integratsiyalash uchun yangi ufqlarni ochadi, shuningdek, dinamik va interfaol ta'lim muhitini yaratadi. Online platformalar, multimedia resurslari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanish nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini egallashga, balki til kontekstini, til sohiblarini va madaniy an'analarni chuqur anglashga ham yordam beradi.

Biroq, afzalliklariga qaramay, raqamli ta'lim va ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni integratsiyalash turli muammolarga duch keladi, jumladan o'qituvchilarning yetarli tayyorgarlik ko'rmasligi va kontent sifatidagi muammolar. Bunday to'siqlarni bartaraf etish ta'lim muassasalari, o'qituvchilar va talabalar o'rtasida hamkorlikni talab qiladi.

Xullas, raqamli texnologiyalar orqali ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentlikni muvaffaqiyatli ravishda shakllantirish o'quvchilarga boshqa madaniyatlarni tushunish va ularga hurmat bilan qarashning yangi darajasini ochadi. Bunday mashg'ulotlar nafaqat ularning tajribasini boyitadi, balki globallashtirilgan dunyoda hayotga tayyorlaydi. Shunday qilib, raqamli texnologiyalarni chet tillarini o'qitish jarayoniga yanada rivojlantirish va integratsiyalash ta'lim tizimini yaxshilashning ustuvor vazifasi bo'lishi kerak.

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HAYRAT LEKSIKASINING LINGVOMADANIY FENOMEN SIFATIDA PSIXOLINGVISTIK VA SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola hayratlanish emotsiyasining tilshunoslikda o'rganilishi haqida so'z yuritadi. Maqolada hayrat leksikasining ingliz va o'zbek madaniyatida qanday ifodalanishi hamda til va madaniyat uzviy bog'liqligi haqida fikr yuritiladi. Hayratlanish his-tuyg'usining turli leksik ifodalar bilan ifodalanishi, uning semantik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Hayrat, emotsiya, psixologiya, semantika, leksika, madaniyat.*

Emotsiyani lingvistik va psixologik nuqtai nazardan o'rganish masalalari uzoq vaqtdan buyon olimlarning e'tibor markazida bo'lib keladi. Jumladan, Murray va Arnott (1993) hamda Izard (1977) emotsiya bir nechta omillarni o'z ichiga olgan murakkab fenomen ekanligini ta'kidlaydilar. Izard (1977) emotsiyani aniqlash uchun quyidagilarni hisobga olish zarurligini ko'rsatadi: "emotsiya inson miya va asab tizimida yuz beradigan jarayon bo'lib o'ziga xos ifoda shakllariga ega." Hochschild (1979) esa emotsiyalarni "kutilmagan va boshqarib bo'lmaydigan" deya ta'riflaydi va hissiy ifodalar "ichki" portlashlar sifatida ko'riladi, ya'ni o'zi xoxlamagan holda to'satdan ichki qalbning to'lqinlanishidir. Hissiy ifodalar inson qandaydir maqsadda amalga oshiradigan yoki muloqot jarayonida atayin ishlatadigan jarayon emas. Aksincha, bu bir individualga xos bo'lgan fiziologik jarayonning tabiiy mahsulidir.

Ko'plab olimlar emotsiyani turlarga ajratgan holda tahlil qilishib, hayratni ijobiy emotsiya sifatida o'rganishgan. Hayratlanish insonning kutilmagan holatda boshdan kechiradigan hissiyoti (Reizenzein, 2000). Hayrat emotsiyasi kimningdir kutilmagan vaziyatda paydo bo'lishi, kutilmagan xabarni eshitishi, to'satdan chiqadigan tovushga tabiiy fiziologik munosabati natijasida yuzaga keladi.

Psixologiya nuqtai nazaridan hayrat odamning psixologiyasida va kognitiv jarayonlarida sezilarli o'zgarishlarga olib keladigan ba'zan qo'rqinchli ba'zan quvontiruvchi hodisa sifatida tasvirlanadi. Hayrat insonning atrofida sodir bo'lgan va bo'layotgan voqea-hodisalarni qabul qilish va ularga o'z munosabatini bildirish jarayonida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shunday qilib, emotsional jarayonlar va tovushlarni birgalikda ishlatish hayratlanish intensivligini yanada kuchaytiradi.

Hayrat leksikasining Cambridge elektron lug'atida berilayotgan ta'rifi quyidagicha (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/surprise>):

1. Kutilmagan voqea.

2. Kutilmagan biror narsa yuz berishi natijasida paydo bo'lgan tuyg'u.

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida hayrat leksikasi quyidagicha talqin qilingan (O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati, 2006):

1. Hayronlik, tong qolish; dovdirab, gangib qolish.
2. Kuchli darajadagi taajjub, hayronlik.

Yuqorida berilgan ikki ta'rifni tadqiq qilib shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, ingliz va o'zbek tillarida hayrat leksikasiga berilayotgan ta'riflar deyarli o'xshash, ammo inglizlar hayrat leksikasini kutilmagan voqea ma'nosida ham ishlatishadi. Lekin bunday ta'rif o'zbek tilida uchramasligi ikki til madaniyatidagi leksik farqlarni ifodalaydi:

Don't tell Anne we've arranged a party for her - I want it to be a surprise.
(<https://dictionary.cambridge.org>)

Annaga uning uchun bazm tashkil qilganimizni aytma - men buni kutilmagan bo'lishini xohlayman.

Ma'lumki, har bir xalq hayratni turli so'z, frazeologizmlar, ekstralingvistik vositalar va tovushlar bilan ifodalaydi, chunki bu hodisa faqat insonning psixologik holatinigina emas, balki bir xalqning o'ziga xos madaniyatini, tarixini va qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi. Shu sababli, hayratni lingvomadaniy jihatdan o'rganish ingliz va o'zbek xalqlarining madaniyatlari o'rtasidagi o'xshashliklar va farqlarni ham aniqlashga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, hayratni ifodalovchi so'zlarni semantik tahlil qilish orqali esa hayratning tildagi leksik ifodalari, ularning sinonimlari va antonimlari haqida to'liqroq tasavvur hosil qilish mumkin. Bunday tahlil qiyoslanayotgan har ikki tildagi hayratni aks ettiruvchi so'zlarning miqdori va ulardan anglashilayotgan ma'nolarni yanada chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

Komponent tahlil natijasida o'zbek tilida hayratni ifodalovchi so'zlar va iboralar ko'pligi aniqlandi: *hayratlanmoq, lol qolmoq, ajablanmoq, qoyil qolmoq, taajjublanmoq, hayrat, ajablanarli, hayratomuz, hayron bo'lmoq, obbo, iya, ibi; Axir bunga aql bovar qilmaydi!, Hayotimda birinchi marta ko'rishim!, O'xshatib qo'yibdi-ku!* va boshqalar.

Ingliz tilida esa *surprise, astonishment, amazement, wonder, awe, amaze, shock, stun, startle, astonish, dumfounded, astound, astonishment, bewilderment, agape, dumbfounded, stunned, flabbergasted, aghast, amazed, astonished, wow, oh, no way* va boshqa shu kabi so'zlar hayratni ifodalashda ishlatiladi.

Intonatsiya va ohang o'zbek tilida hayratni ifodalashda katta ahamiyatga ega. *"Ha, rostdanmi?", Voy!, Hayratlanarli!, Axir!, Qoyil!, Obbo!, Nima?, Shunaqami?!*

Bir tasavvur qiling-chi!, Ajabo! kabi jumlar intonatsiya bilan qo'llanilishi natijasida hayratlanish holati kuchaytiriladi. Ingliz tilida esa “*Really?*”, “*No way!*”, “*Unbelievable!*” va boshqa shu kabi leksik birliklar qo'llaniladi. Shuningdek, ingliz madaniyatida hayratlanish holati so'z va tana harakati bilan ifodalanadi. Bu esa ingliz va o'zbek xalqlarining o'ziga xos madaniy xususiyatlarini ko'rsatadi.

O'zbek tilida qo'llaniluvchi hayrat ifodalarini ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishda o'sha so'zning ekvivalentini topish qiyinchilik tug'diradi. Masalan, o'zbek tilida hayratning kuchli intensivligini ifodalovchi va o'zbek xalqi tomonidan ko'p qo'llaniluvchi “*Yo, tavba!*” iborasining ingliz tilida unga aniq mos keladigan ekvivalenti uchramaydi. Ushbu iborani tarjima qilishda “*Oh my God!*” yoki “*Wow!*” kabi so'zlarni qo'llash mumkin, lekin ular kontekstga har doim ham mos tushavermaydi.

Yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlardan shuni xulosa qilish mumkinki, hayratlanish nafaqat psixologiya, balki til va madaniyat bilan bog'liq bo'lgan hodisa bo'lib, u turli madaniyatlarda turli vositalar bilan ifodalanadi. Hayrat leksikalarini semantik va kognitiv jihatdan chuqur tahlil qilish yordamida ingliz va o'zbek tillarida hayratni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar miqdorini va ularning o'ziga xos lingvomadaniy xususiyatlarini aniqlash mumkin.

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MONITORING SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN BOLALARDA IJTIMOIIY-EMOTSIYONAL RIVOJLANISHNI MONITORING QILISH

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Abstract: *The monitoring of social-emotional development in children is of utmost importance in order to get insight into their emotional well-being, interpersonal abilities, and overall psychological state. This thesis examines the significance of monitoring social-emotional development and emphasizes crucial factors and approaches for efficient monitoring.*

Key words: *monitoring, emotional well-being, interpersonal skills, mental health, assessment, observation, problem-solving, behavior.*

INTRODUCTION: Social-emotional development covers a diverse array of cognitive and behavioral capacities, including as self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and the establishment and maintenance of interpersonal connections. The act of monitoring this progression in children yields significant knowledge regarding their emotional and social capabilities, facilitating the timely detection of possible issues and the application of suitable therapies.

The monitoring of children's social-emotional development is a crucial aspect in comprehending their emotional well-being, interpersonal abilities, and overall psychological state. The development of social-emotional abilities is of paramount importance in determining the success and well-being of children, as it significantly influences their academic achievements, interpersonal connections, and overall sense of contentment in life. Through the active monitoring and assessment of social and emotional development, educators, caregivers, and mental health experts are able to acquire significant information pertaining to a child's strengths, areas of improvement, and potential areas of worry.

Social-emotional development encompasses the process of acquiring and honing abilities pertaining to self-awareness, self-regulation, social relationships, empathy, and problem-solving. It comprises a broad spectrum of skills that empower youngsters to effectively navigate and flourish within their social contexts. The process of monitoring this particular development is the systematic observation, assessment, and recording of a child's behaviors, emotions, and social interactions in order to get a full comprehension of their socio-emotional competency.

MAIN DISCUSSIONS: Effective monitoring necessitates the utilization of assessment techniques and methodologies that align with the developmental needs and capabilities of the individuals being evaluated. This entails taking into account the age, cultural heritage, and unique characteristics of children. Various methodologies are employed to collect data pertaining to social-emotional development, including but not limited to observations, interviews, standardized evaluations, and behavior checklists.

The assessment of social-emotional development is a multifaceted and intricate concept. The scope of monitoring should span multiple domains, including but not limited to emotional regulation, social skills, self-esteem, and problem-solving ability. The utilization of a comprehensive assessment approach facilitates the acquisition of a thorough and all-encompassing comprehension of a child's social-emotional development.

The importance of engaging in collaborative efforts with parents and caregivers. The inclusion of parents and caregivers in the monitoring process is of utmost importance. They hold significant insights on the behavior, emotions, and social interactions of children in various contexts. The implementation of collaborative endeavors facilitates a more thorough comprehension of a child's social-emotional development and augments the precision of assessment outcomes.

The early identification of risk factors or possible challenges can be facilitated through the monitoring of social-emotional development. This facilitates prompt interventions and assistance in order to effectively tackle any growing difficulties. Systematic monitoring facilitates the identification of patterns or alterations in a child's behavior that may signify a requirement for further assistance or intervention.

The implementation of personalized support and intervention is facilitated by the use of effective monitoring, which informs the creation of individualized support plans and interventions that are customized to address the unique requirements of each child. This technology facilitates the ability of educators, mental health professionals, and caregivers to implement specific interventions that support the promotion of optimal social-emotional development and effectively treat any detected difficulties.

Longitudinal Monitoring: The development of social-emotional skills is a complex and evolving process that occurs over an extended period. The practice of longitudinal monitoring, which involves the collection of data over longer periods of time, enables the systematic observation of progress, identification of developmental trajectories, and evaluation of the efficacy of interventions. The utilization of long-

term monitoring facilitates the quantification of growth, the identification of enduring strengths and areas necessitating improvement, as well as the provision of valuable insights for educational and therapeutic planning.

Ethical considerations must be taken into account when monitoring social-emotional development in order to safeguard the privacy, confidentiality, and overall welfare of children. The individuals engaged in the aforementioned process are required to conform to ethical principles, ensure the acquisition of informed consent, and safeguard confidential information pertaining to a child's social-emotional development.

CONCLUSION: To summarize, the monitoring of socio-emotional development in children is of utmost importance in order to foster their holistic well-being and facilitate the cultivation of sound emotional and social capabilities. Professionals can effectively monitor social-emotional development and implement interventions that foster positive outcomes for children by employing developmentally appropriate assessment methods, engaging parents and caregivers, identifying risk factors, offering individualized support, and taking into account ethical considerations. The use of ongoing surveillance during the entirety of a child's developmental trajectory facilitates prompt assistance and augments their social-emotional aptitude and resilience.

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ALEKSANDR FAYNBERG SHE'RIYATI

Turg'unbayeva Noila Dilshod qizi

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Aleksandr Arkadevich Faynberg asarlari, ilmiy ishlari va tarjimalari, adabiyotda tutgan o'rni, o'zbek adabiyotiga qo'shgan hissasi haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shuningdek, shoir ijodining bugungi kundagi ahamiyati haqida so'z yuritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *she'riyat, tarjima, ssenariy, madaniyat, millat, o'zbek xalqi, vatan.*

Adabiyot shunday bir dengizki, unda daryolarning qudrati, ummonlarning teranligi bor; shunday bir chamanzorki, undan xushbo'yifor taratgan gullar, hali ochilmagan gullarning tarovati bor; shunday bir oltin ko'priki, u xalqni birlashtirib, do'stlik rishtalarini mustahkamlaydi. Zero, adabiyotning tili bitta, san'at tilidir. Adabiyot tarixida shunday ijodkorlar yashab o'tganki, ular garchi boshqa millat vakili bo'lsa-da, ijodi orqali o'zbek xalqining dardini, ruhini kuylagan, adabiyotimizni jahonga targ'ib qilishda misilsiz jonbozlik ko'rsatgan, Ana shunday buyuk insonlardan biri O'zbekistonning Rossiya Federatsiyasi bilan madaniy aloqalarini rivojlantirishga qo'shgan ulkan hissasi uchun Pushkin medali bilan taqdirlangan, o'zining yorqin she'riyati bilan adabiyotimiz osmonida o'chmas iz qoldirgan O'zbekiston xalq shoiri Aleksandr Arkadevich Faynberg edi.

Aleksandr Faynberg 1939-yil 2-noyabrda Toshkent shahrida tavallud topgan. Ota-onasi tug'ilishidan ikki yil avval Novosibirskdan ko'chib kelgan. Yozuvchining otasi Arkadiy Livovich Faynberg (1891-1971), asli Gitchinalik, texnologiya institutini tamomlagan va spirt zavodida bosh muhandis bo'lib ishlagan. Onasi Anastasiya Aleksandrovna Moskvada tug'ilgan.

Shoir Toshkent davlat universitetining jurnalistika fakultetini tamomlagan. Shu bilan bir qatorda Yozuvchilar uyushmasida maslahatchi bo'lib ham ish yuritgan. Shu tariqa uning asarlari dunyo yuzini ko'ra boshladi. Aleksandr Faynberg rus shoiri, O'zbekiston xalq shoiri, O'zbekiston shoirlari osmonida shubhasiz eng yorqin yulduzlardan biridir. U 15 ta she'riy to'plam (jumladan o'limidan so'ng nashr etilgan ikki jildlik asarini o'zi tuzgan) muallifi edi. She'rlari "Smena", "Yoshlik", "Yangi dunyo", "Sharq yulduzi", "Yangi volga" jurnallarida hamda xorijiy mamlakatlar: AQSH, Kanada, Isroilnig davriy nashrlarida chop etilgan. "Etyud"(1967), "Soniya"(1969), "She'lar"(1977), "Olis ko'priklar"(1978), "Ijobat"(1982), "Qisqa to'lqin"(1983), "Yoyma to'r"(1984), "Erkin sonetlar"(1990) va boshqa she'rlar muallifidir. Faynbergning she'riy ijodida o'tmish bilan hozirgi kun, G'arb bilan Sharq millilyligi, baynalmilalchilik o'zaro tutashib, o'ziga xos badiiy olamni vujudga

keltiradi. Faynbergning lirik qahramoni tarixiy-ijtimoiy silsilalar asrida o'zining insoniy mohiyatini to'la saqlab qolgan, o'zgaga mehr-shafqat va madad qo'lini uzatishga tayyor, yer kurrasida sodir bo'layotgan noxush voqea va hodisalardan iztirob chekuvchi insondir. She'riy ijodida rus va Yevropa shoirlarining eng yaxshi badiiy tajribalari namoyon bo'lgan. Sharq mumtoz she'riyati an'analari ham uning ijodiy uslubiga begona emas.

Faynberg ijodining muhim qismini badiiy tarjima tashkil etadi. O'zbek she'riyatini mukammal bilgan shoir Navoiy g'azallari, Erkin Vohidov, Abdulla Oripov, Omon Matjon va boshqa o'zbek shoirlarining she'r va dostonlarini rus tiliga tarjima qilgan. Faynberg ssenariysi asosida "O'zbekfilm" kinostudiyasida "Mening akam", "Jazirama oftob tagida", "Qandahorda toblanganlar", "Tijokfilm" kinostudiyasida esa "Jinoyatchi va oqlovchilar" hamda boshqa filmlar suratga olingan. Faynberg ssenariysi asosida to'rtta to'liq metrajli badiiy film va 20ga yaqin multfilmlar yaratilgan.

1999-yilda "Paxtakor" futbol jamoasining avtohalokatda halok bo'lganing yigirma yilligi munosabati bilan uning ssenariysi bo'yicha "Osmondagi stadion" filmi suratga olingan. Faynberg 1979-yilda "Paxtakor" jamoasi haqida yozilgan qo'shig'i yangragan. Faynberg bir necha yil davomida Toshkentda O'zbekiston yosh yozuvchilari seminariga rahbarlik qilgan. "Issiq quyosh ostidagi uy" (1977, "O'zbekfilm") filmining ssenariyi muallifi.

Prezidentimizning tashabbusi bilan yangidan bunyod etilgan adiblar xiyobonida mumtoz va zamonaviy adiblarning ulug' namoyondalari qatorida Aleksandr Faynberg haykali ham o'rnatildi. Aleksandr Faynberg o'zbek she'riyatining eng ko'zga ko'ringan namoyondalaridan biri ekanligi shubhasiz. Uning ismi va ishi butun o'zbek muhlislari va shoirlari orasida o'zgarmasdir. Aleksandr Faynbergning mumtoz she'riyatining mumtoz an'analari, O'zbekiston zaminiga mehr-muhabbat tuyg'ulari singdirilgan beqiyos va noyob asari adabiyotimiz tarixida alohida sahifadir. Aleksandr Faynbergning tilidan yoki millatidan qat'iy nazar, O'zbekistondagi barcha adabiyot ixlosmandlari yaxshi bilishadi va hurmat qilishadi.

U adabiy bilimi va lug'at fondini tinimsiz boyitgani va she'riyat "sir"larini mukammal egallaganidan so'ng o'zbek shoirlarining asarlarini tarjima qilishga kirishadi va badiiy tarjima sohasida katta yutuqlarga erishdi. Shu ijodiy jarayonda V. A. Jukovskiy iborasi bilan aytganda asarlari tarjima qilinayotgan shoirlarning "qul" emas, balki munosib "raqib" bo'lishga intildi. Moskvada nashr qilingan O'zbekiston xalq shoiri Erkin Vohidovning "Ruhlar isyoni" dostoni, Toshkentda chop etilgan "Oqqushlar galasi" nomli o'zbek shoilari ijodidan qilingan tarjimalari jamlanmasi

Faynberg tarjimonlik faoliyatining qo'sh cho'qqisi hisoblanadi. Shoir she'rlari ham o'zbek xalqi qalbiga shu qadar chuqur kirib borganki, tasvirning sirli va jozibadorligi, tuyg'ular yorqinligi va tiniqligi o'quvchini o'ziga hamroh qiladi va hayollarini uzoq-uzoqlarga olib ketib chuqur o'yga toldiradi:

Suzyapman, muhabbat, olis
Gulxanlardan o'ralaydi tutun.
Sendan bo'lsa oladi yulduz
Bu qirg'oqdan ketmam bugun
Qirg'oqqa tashlayman langarcho'p
Izmiga soladi moviy suv
To'lqinlari yugurak, to'p-to'p
Daryo tubi – adabiy g'uluv.

Qalbi o'zbek shoir va ijodkor Aleksandr Faynberg o'zining asarlarida millat ruhi va tinchligi, millatlararo totuvlik, mehmondo'stlik haqida fikr yurutish bilan birga shoir o'z bolaligi va yoshlik davrlarini ham yoritadi. Uning nodir asarlari-yu tarjimalari yuksak baholanadi. Shoir xalqimizning ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishda va boshqa davlatlar bilan hamjihatlikni mustahkamlagini uchun “ O'zbekiston Respublikasi xalq shoiri” unovoni bilan taqdirlanadi. Faynberg yillar davomida o'zining yuqori darajadagi cho'qqisini saqlab keldi va u shunday asarlar yozdiki, bu asarlar yillar davomida har bir kitobxonning qalbidan joy egallaydi, shunchaki o'zi uchun cho'qqini yaratib oldi. Ijodkor va uning asarlari kitobxonlar qalbida o'chmas iz qoldirdi va chuqur o'rin egalladi, egallab kelmoqda.

Xulosa:

Shoirning ijodi keng ko'lamliligi va sermahsul. Uning she'rlarida rang-baranglik, falsafiy teranlik tuyg'ulari yorqin aks etib turadi. Shoir so'zni chuqur his etadi, bu hisga o'quvchini ham hamroh qiladi. U O'zbekistonda yashadi, ijod qildi, bu yurtning havosi, osmoni, tuprog'i, eli bir og'iz bilan aytganda butun borlig'i shoirga she'r qadar, qalb qadar aziz bo'lib ulgurgan edi. Shoir o'zbek adabiyoti va madaniyati rivojiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan, o'zining betakror asarlarida el-u yutimizni yuksak badiiy mahorat bilan tarannum etgan noyob iste'dod egalaridan biri edi. Shoir o'zidan o'chmas iz va tunganmas asarlarini meros qilib qoldirdi. Uning she'riyatdagi jozibasiz juda turlicha fel-atvor, qarashlar va turli yoshdagi odamlarning qalbini zabt etdi. Aleksandr Faynberg ijodi istiqbol ruhi maqsadlari bilan yog'inganlagi, millat manfaati uchun xizmat qilganini anglatadi. Uning ijodi inson qalbini, hayot haqiqatlarini chuqur anglashga yordam beradigan asarlardan iborat. Bugungi kunda

ham uning she'rlari muxlisalari qalbida yashab kelmoqda va yosh ijodkorlar uchun ilhom manbai bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda.

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МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНАЯ КОММУНИКАЦИЯ КАК ВАЖНЫЙ АСПЕКТ СОВРЕМЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация. *Культура является важным фактором, соединяющим народы. Она играет удивительную роль в том, чтобы помочь людям осознать своё место и значение в мире, а также способствует развитию их духовных и моральных качеств. Люди, представляющие различные культурные, языковые и социальные группы, находят общий язык благодаря межкультурной коммуникации, которая играет важную роль в современном обществе. В процессе межкультурного общения люди обмениваются информацией, идеями, знаниями и эмоциями, что далее может дойти до деловых переговоров между странами.*

Ключевые слова: *культура, взаимодействие культур, межкультурная коммуникация, конструктивный диалог.*

На протяжении всей истории человечества культура служит особым связующим звеном для объединения народов. Она удивительным образом помогает людям осознать своё место и роль в мире, а также развивает их духовный и нравственный потенциал. Составители двухтомной культурологической энциклопедии «Культурология» предлагают предельно общее, целостносистемное определение «культуры» как феномена, основы которого наблюдаются уже в первых работах Л. Уайта, Г. Спенсера. А именно: «культура» – сложная гомеостатическая система («большая система», «суперсистема») внебиологической природы, которая содержит общий опыт видового существования человека и обеспечивает накопление, воспроизведение, развитие и использование этого опыта, параллельно с репродуцированием видовых признаков самого человека, относится к классу квазиважных адаптивных систем» [2, С. 1072]. Мы понимаем, что культура влияет на человека. По поводу этого К. Гирц писал: «Наши идеи, наши ценности, наши действия, даже наши эмоции, как и сама наша нервная система, являются продуктами культуры – продуктами, изготовленными, конечно, из материала тех тенденций, возможностей и способностей, с которыми мы родились, но тем не меньше изготовленными» [1, С. 63].

В данной статье мы рассмотрим концепцию межкультурной коммуникации, её значение в создании конструктивного диалога и способы её развития. Межличностное общение актуально сегодня так же, как и много

тысяч лет назад. Тем не менее, в эпоху информации взаимодействие между людьми принимает новые формы и неограниченные возможности, благодаря расширению доступа к различным информационным потокам, таким как Интернет, цифровые библиотеки, телевидение и прочее. Упрощение коммуникационных процессов значительно увеличивает как информационное, так и культурное пространство. Межкультурная коммуникация – это важный аспект современного общества, которое становится всё более глобализированным и многообразным. Эта форма общения между людьми, представляющими различные культурные, языковые и социальные группы, играет ключевую роль в обеспечении понимания и согласия. В условиях быстро меняющегося мира, где взаимодействие между представителями различных культур происходит на всех уровнях – от личных отношений до международной политики – способность вести конструктивный диалог становится необходимостью.

Исследователи С.Л. Мишланова и Т.М. Пермякова рассматривают определение «межкультурная коммуникация» с различных точек зрения:

- как сферу, объектом изучения которой являются модели поведения и специфика индивидов, имеющих внутри различные «историко-культурные производные» поведения;
- как форму взаимодействия общностей, имеющих различный социокультурный и исторический опыт становления и развития;
- вид коммуникации, при котором «тот, кто отправляет и тот, кто получает информацию», принадлежат к различным культурам;
- процесс вербального и невербального взаимодействия коммуникантов, являющихся носителями различных языков и культур [3, С. 345].

Межкультурную коммуникацию мы также понимаем, как процесс обмена информацией, идеями и эмоциями между людьми, представляющими различные культуры. Она включает в себя множество аспектов, таких как язык, невербальные знаки, традиции, ценности и нормы поведения. Основной задачей межкультурной коммуникации является преодоление барьеров, возникающих из-за культурных различий. Важным элементом данной концепции является осознание того, что каждый человек воспринимает мир через призму своей культуры. Это осознание помогает избегать многих недоразумений и конфликтов, которые могут возникнуть при взаимодействии людей из разных культур. Чтобы избежать этого важно создание конструктивного диалога между людьми. Конструктивный диалог – это форма общения, в которой

стороны стремятся понять друг друга, принимают во внимание различные точки зрения и работают над поиском компромиссов. В контексте межкультурной коммуникации такая форма диалога становится особенно актуальной, поскольку она помогает развивать взаимопонимание и уважение между участниками.

Межкультурная коммуникация способствует конструктивному диалогу в нескольких ключевых аспектах:

1. *Увеличение осведомлённости о культурных различиях.* Понимание ценностей, норм и традиций других культур способствует снижению уровня предвзятости и стереотипов. Это, в свою очередь, создает более уважительное и открытое пространство для общения;

2. *Развитие навыков активного слушания.* Конструктивный диалог основывается на умении слушать. Межкультурная коммуникация поощряет активное слушание, так как требует внимания к особенностям речи и невербальном поведении собеседника;

3. *Поиск общих интересов.* Межкультурная коммуникация помогает участникам находить точки соприкосновения и интересы, которые могут стать основой для дальнейшего сотрудничества;

4. *Устранение барьеров.* Зачастую недостаток знаний о традициях и обычаях другой культуры может быть источником недопонимания. Межкультурная коммуникация помогает выявить и преодолеть эти барьеры.

Для того чтобы межкультурная коммуникация была эффективной и способствовала конструктивному диалогу, необходимо развивать определённые навыки и установки. Вот основные подходы:

- образование и обучение: включение курсов по межкультурной коммуникации в образовательные программы может значительно повысить уровень осведомленности о различных культурах среди студентов;

- кросс-культурный опыт: практика общения с представителями других культур, участием в международных проектах и программах обмена может значительно обогатить личный опыт и способствовать лучшему пониманию других культур;

- использование технологий: в эпоху цифровых технологий возможности для межкультурной коммуникации стали неограниченными. Онлайн-курсы, вебинары и международные конференции создают платформы для обмена знаниями и опытом;

- формирование открытости к новым идеям: открытость к различным точкам зрения и готовность рассматривать их, даже если они отличаются от собственных, являются основополагающими для конструктивного диалога.

Итак, межкультурная коммуникация – это мощное средство, способствующее развитию конструктивного диалога в многообразном и изменчивом мире. Способность взаимодействовать с представителями других культур не только расширяет горизонты, но и помогает строить мир на основе взаимопонимания и уважения. Внедрение и развитие навыков межкультурной коммуникации является необходимым условием для достижения гармонии и сотрудничества в глобализированном обществе. Образование, международные обмены и технологии играют ключевую роль в этом процессе, создавая возможности для конструктивного, многостороннего диалога, который способен преодолевать культурные барьеры и объединять людей.

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DEVELOPING SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION FOR FUTURE JOURNALISTS: INSIGHTS FROM POLITICAL AND SOCIAL TEXTS

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Annotation: *This article explores the development of sociolinguistic competence in English language instruction for future journalists, with a specific focus on political and social texts. Given the dynamic nature of journalism, acquiring sociolinguistic awareness is essential for effective communication in diverse socio-political contexts. The study examines how contextual analysis, discourse strategies, and pragmatic awareness contribute to enhancing students' ability to interpret and report on political and social issues accurately. Various pedagogical approaches are considered, including task-based learning, discourse analysis, and authentic media integration. The findings suggest that engaging with real-world media content significantly improves students' ability to navigate language variation, register, and ideological nuances. This research highlights the importance of incorporating sociolinguistic elements into English language curricula for journalism students, ensuring they develop linguistic adaptability and cross-cultural communication skills. The article provides practical recommendations for educators aiming to bridge the gap between linguistic proficiency and journalistic effectiveness in politically charged discourse.*

Keywords: *sociolinguistic competence, English language instruction, journalism education, political discourse, social texts, pragmatic awareness, media literacy, cross-cultural communication.*

Introduction. In today's globalized media landscape, journalists must navigate complex socio-political discourses while ensuring accurate and culturally sensitive reporting. Mastering English as a global lingua franca is essential for aspiring journalists, but beyond linguistic proficiency, they must develop sociolinguistic competence the ability to understand and apply language in various social and political contexts. This competence enables journalists to interpret pragmatic meaning, discourse structures, and ideological nuances embedded in political and social texts.

Political and social texts, including news reports, editorials, policy documents, and speeches, often contain implicit power relations, persuasive strategies, and culturally specific references¹. Without sociolinguistic awareness, journalism students may struggle to accurately interpret discourse, recognize bias, and communicate effectively across diverse audiences. Given the increasing role of digital media and

¹ Gumperz, J. (1982). *Discourse Strategies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – pp. 1-225.

globalized news reporting, understanding how language functions in political and social contexts is critical for responsible journalism. This paper examines strategies for enhancing sociolinguistic competence in English language instruction for future journalists. It explores task-based learning, discourse analysis, and authentic media engagement as effective pedagogical approaches. The study highlights how real-world media content and interactive learning methods can help students develop linguistic adaptability, critical thinking, and intercultural communication skills, ultimately bridging the gap between language learning and journalistic effectiveness in politically charged discourse.

Sociolinguistic competence plays a crucial role in journalism, particularly in the interpretation and production of political and social texts. Journalists must navigate language variations, dialects, registers, and cultural references to ensure accuracy and objectivity in reporting². Unlike general language learning, which focuses on grammatical correctness, sociolinguistic competence equips journalists with the ability to analyze discourse critically, recognizing bias, persuasive strategies, and power dynamics within texts. Political and social texts often contain implicit messages, rhetorical devices, and culturally embedded meanings. Without sufficient sociolinguistic competence, journalists may misinterpret these elements, leading to misinformation or misrepresentation of facts. For instance, an article discussing immigration policies may use euphemistic expressions or emotionally charged language that require contextual understanding to decode their intended message. Therefore, language instruction for journalism students should emphasize discourse analysis, contextual interpretation, and critical thinking skills to ensure effective engagement with socio-political content³.

Challenges in teaching sociolinguistic competence

Despite its importance, developing sociolinguistic competence in journalism education presents several challenges. Firstly, traditional language curricula often prioritize linguistic accuracy and vocabulary expansion over pragmatic awareness and contextual analysis. Secondly, many journalism students struggle with understanding language variation, code-switching, and stylistic differences in different media contexts. Lastly, access to authentic, up-to-date political and social texts can be limited, making it difficult for students to engage with contemporary discourse effectively.

² Van Dijk, T.A. (2008). *Discourse and Power*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. – pp. 1-304.

³ Fairclough, N. (1995). *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. London: Longman. – pp. 1-265.

To overcome these challenges, educators must integrate interactive and immersive learning approaches that expose students to real-world journalistic materials⁴. This includes the use of news articles, political speeches, social media discussions, and expert interviews, allowing students to analyze language in authentic communicative contexts.

Effective pedagogical approaches

To foster sociolinguistic competence in journalism students, several teaching methodologies can be employed:

Task-Based Learning (TBL)

Task-Based Learning is a communicative approach that encourages students to engage in real-world tasks that mimic journalistic activities. Through interview simulations, press conference analyses, and investigative reporting projects, students develop sociolinguistic skills by actively engaging with authentic discourse. Example tasks include:

- Comparing different news sources to identify variations in political framing.
- Conducting mock interviews with a focus on formality, politeness strategies, and cultural appropriateness.
- Writing news reports that reflect different registers and audience expectations.

By developing sociolinguistic competence, journalism students improve their ability to adapt their language use depending on the audience, medium, and purpose. They become more culturally aware, analytically skilled, and better equipped to navigate ethical considerations in reporting. This enhances their capacity to produce balanced, well-contextualized, and linguistically appropriate news content that resonates with diverse audiences. Furthermore, equipping journalists with strong sociolinguistic awareness helps counteract the spread of misinformation, as they become more proficient in identifying biased narratives, misleading language, and manipulative discourse techniques⁵. This is particularly critical in an era where digital media amplifies politically charged and often polarized content.

Conclusion. Sociolinguistic competence is an indispensable skill for future journalists, enabling them to engage critically with political and social discourse. While traditional language instruction may not fully address the complexities of

⁴ Bhatia, V. (2004). *Worlds of Written Discourse: A Genre-Based View*. London: Bloomsbury. – pp. 1-245.

⁵ Bell, A. (1991). *The Language of News Media*. Oxford: Blackwell. – pp. 1-280.

journalistic communication, integrating task-based learning, discourse analysis, and authentic media engagement into the curriculum can bridge this gap. By doing so, journalism students develop the linguistic agility, critical awareness, and ethical considerations necessary to report on socio-political issues effectively. Future research should explore the long-term impact of these pedagogical strategies on professional journalism practice, ensuring that language education continues to evolve in alignment with contemporary media landscapes.

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THE ORIGINS AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE FICTION GENRE

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Abstract: Science fiction is a genre that has undergone significant evolution, from early mythological narratives to contemporary explorations of futuristic technology and artificial intelligence. The term "science fiction" emerged in the 20th century, but its origins can be traced back to ancient and medieval speculative storytelling. This paper explores the historical trajectory of the genre, its defining characteristics, and key figures who contributed to its formation. The study also examines how science fiction has mirrored scientific advancements and influenced popular culture.

Keywords: Science fiction, speculative literature, technological progress, genre evolution, classic science fiction.

Аннотация: Научная фантастика — это жанр, который претерпел значительную эволюцию: от ранних мифологических повествований до современных исследований футуристических технологий и искусственного интеллекта. Термин «научная фантастика» появился в XX веке, однако его истоки можно проследить в древней и средневековой спекулятивной литературе. В данной статье рассматривается историческая траектория развития жанра, его определяющие характеристики и ключевые фигуры, внесшие вклад в его становление. Также исследуется, как научная фантастика отражала научные достижения и оказывала влияние на массовую культуру.

Ключевые слова: Научная фантастика, спекулятивная литература, технологический прогресс, эволюция жанра, классическая научная фантастика.

Introduction: Science fiction (SF) is one of the most dynamic and intellectually stimulating genres in literature, cinema, and popular culture. Although the term "science fiction" was first popularized by Hugo Gernsback in the 1920s, its roots stretch back centuries, encompassing ancient myths, utopian literature, and early modern speculative works. The genre has evolved through various stages, reflecting humanity's relationship with scientific discovery and technological progress. This section examines the historical origins and development of science fiction, focusing on its formative influences, major milestones, and the key thinkers who shaped it. Understanding this background is essential for grasping the genre's significance in both literary and cultural contexts.

Main Part: 1. The Precursors of Science Fiction.

While science fiction as a distinct genre only emerged in the 19th and 20th centuries, many of its fundamental elements can be found in earlier works. Ancient texts, such as Lucian of Samosata's True History (2nd century CE), depicted

interplanetary travel and extraterrestrial civilizations.¹ Similarly, medieval and Renaissance literature contained elements of speculative fiction, such as Thomas More's *Utopia* (1516), which envisioned an idealized society based on rational principles.²

The Enlightenment era further paved the way for SF, with Johannes Kepler's *Somnium*, often regarded as the first true work of science fiction, as it combined scientific reasoning with imaginative storytelling.³

2. The Birth of Modern Science Fiction

The 19th century marked the emergence of modern science fiction. Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818) is widely recognized as the first science fiction novel, as it explored the ethical dilemmas of scientific experimentation and artificial life⁴. Later, Jules Verne and H.G. Wells expanded the genre's scope with works such as *Twenty Thousand Leagues Under the Sea* and *The Time Machine*, respectively, which introduced futuristic technology and time travel as core themes.⁵

These authors laid the foundation for science fiction's engagement with scientific discovery, raising questions about progress, morality, and the limits of human knowledge.

3. The Golden Age and Beyond

The 20th century saw the formalization of science fiction as a literary genre, often divided into key periods such as the Golden Age (1930s–1950s), characterized by the works of Isaac Asimov, Arthur C. Clarke, and Robert Heinlein, who emphasized scientific accuracy and rational speculation.⁶

The New Wave movement of the 1960s and 1970s, led by authors such as Philip K. Dick and J.G. Ballard, challenged traditional SF tropes by introducing psychological depth and experimental storytelling.⁷ Later, cyberpunk literature, spearheaded by William Gibson's *Neuromancer*, brought a focus on artificial intelligence and digital realities.⁸

Modern science fiction continues to evolve, exploring themes of transhumanism, climate change, and space colonization. Authors such as Neal Asher and Alastair

¹ Clute, J., & Nicholls, P. (1993). *The Encyclopedia of Science Fiction*. Orbit. (p. 35)

² Roberts, A. (2000). *Science Fiction*. Routledge. (p. 72)

³ Stableford, B. (2004). *Historical Dictionary of Science Fiction Literature*. Scarecrow Press. (p. 18)

⁴ Aldiss, B. (1973). *Billion Year Spree: The True History of Science Fiction*. Weidenfeld & Nicolson. (p. 89)

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⁶ Westfahl, G. (2005). *The Mechanics of Wonder: The Creation of the Idea of Science Fiction*. Liverpool University Press. (p. 143)

⁷ Luckhurst, R. (2005). *Science Fiction: A Literary History*. Polity Press. (p. 97)

⁸ McCaffery, L. (1991). *Storming the Reality Studio: A Casebook of Cyberpunk and Postmodern Science Fiction*. Duke University Press. (p. 65)

Reynolds have carried the genre into the 21st century, merging hard science with philosophical inquiry.⁹

Conclusion: The history of science fiction reflects the broader intellectual and technological evolution of human civilization. From ancient myths to cyberpunk dystopias, the genre has continually redefined itself in response to cultural and scientific developments. By understanding its origins and transformations, we gain deeper insight into how literature shapes and is shaped by the aspirations and anxieties of its time.

Science fiction remains a vital means of exploring the possible futures of humanity, making it a crucial subject for literary and philosophical analysis.

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⁹ Broderick, D. (2018). *The Cambridge Companion to Science Fiction*. Cambridge University Press. (p. 210)

TA'LIM JARAYONIDA ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DIDAKTIK IMKONIYATLARI

Umarov Abdurasul Abduraxmanovich

O'zDJTU, Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining didaktik imkoniyatlari va o'qitish tizimidagi amaliy ahamiyati xususida fikr yuritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim, kompyuter, axborot texnologiyalar, o'qitish usullari, vosita, rivojlantirish, didaktik imkoniyatlar, muloqot, zamonaviy internet tarmog'i, o'qitish tizimi, ta'lim modellari, elektron ta'lim.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются дидактические возможности современных информационных технологий в образовательном процессе и их практическое значение в системе образования.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, компьютер, информационные технологии, методы обучения, инструменты, развитие, дидактические возможности, коммуникация, современный Интернет, система обучения, образовательные модели, электронное обучение.*

Abstract: *This article discusses the didactic possibilities of modern information technologies in the educational process and their practical significance in the education system.*

Keywords: *education, computer, information technology, teaching methods, tools, development, didactic opportunities, communication, modern Internet, teaching system, educational models, e-learning.*

Bugungi kunda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) birikmasi eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan tushunchaga aylanib qoldi. Bugungi kunimizni bu terminlarsiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Hayotning barcha sohalarida AKT bilan ish faoliyatimizni olib boramiz. Globallashuv davrida zamonaviy AKT dan foydalanish, axborot almashish, ularni uzatish, o'zlashtirish insonlar faoliyatining bir qismiga aylanib qoldi. Chunki mamlakatimizning milliy iqtisodiyoti ijtimoiy yo'naltirilgan bozor munosabatlariga bosqichma-bosqich o'tishi, shuningdek, globallashuv jarayonidagi ilmiy-texnika taraqqiyotining jamiyatimizda mavjud barcha sohalarga kirib borishi ta'limda axborot texnologiyalarning didaktik imkoniyatlarini kengaytirdi. Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda milliy iqtisodiyotning tarmoq va sohalarini axborotlashtirish, kerakli o'rinlarda yig'ish, saqlash, uzatish, qayta ishlash va taqdim etishning muhim yo'nalishiga aylandi.

Bizga ma'lumki, zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining imkoniyatlari juda ham keng bo'lib, unga kompyuter, multimedia vositalari, kompyuter taqmoqlari, internet kiradi. Bulardan tashqari, bugungi kunda yangi tushunchalar ham kirib keldiki, ta'limda bu yangi tushunchalarni to'g'ri tahlil

etishimiz va vazifalarini bilgan holda to'g'ri qo'llay olishimiz zarurdir. Buning uchun qanday yo'l tutish kerak degan haqli savolning tug'ilishi tabiiy. Zamonaviy - axborot tizimlarida uzatish tizimlari, ma'lumotlar ombori, ma'lumotlar omboroni boshqarish tizimi, bilimlar ombori kabilar ham mavjud. Shuning uchun ham ta'lim sohasiga elektron ta'limni joriy etish, har bir ta'lim muassasasida birinchi navbatda to'g'ri o'qitish uchun o'quv jarayonini, ta'lim muassasasi boshqarilishining yangi tizimini, ta'limda muassasa bo'limlarini, shuningdek, ta'lim muassasasining faoliyatida yangi axborot muhitini axborotlashtirishni talab qiladi.

Bu jarayonda zamonaviy- axborot texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonlariga joriy etilishi ta'lim oluvchilarga qanday yordam berishi mumkin. Shuni alohida ta'kidlab o'tish joizki, bu jarayon talabaga kasbiy bilimlarni tez va oson egallashlariga, o'rganilayotgan hodisa va jarayonlarni modellashtirish orqali fan sohasini puxta va chuqur o'zlashtirishlariga yordam beradi. Bulardan tashqari, o'quv jarayonini zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari asosida o'qitish talabalarning mustaqil faoliyat olib borishga yo'naltiradi, interaktiv muloqot imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Ta'lim olishda sun'iy intellekt tizimi imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish orqali talabaning o'quv materiallarini puxta o'zlashtirishiga ko'maklashadi. Zamonaviy-axborot jamiyatining a'zosi sifatidagi faoliyatini yanada yaxshilaydi. O'rganilayotgan jarayon va hodisalarni zamonaviy kompyutar texnologiyalari orqali taqdim etishlari talabalarda fan asoslariga qiziqishni yanada orttiradi, shuningdek, ularning barcha fanlarga bo'lgan ijobiy faolligini oshiradi.

Zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, shuningdek, ushbu ta'lim vositasining didaktik imkoniyatlariga obyektning tabiiy jihatlari, texnik va texnologik fazilatlari, o'quv va tarbiyaviy jarayonda didaktik maqsadlarda qo'llanilishi va muhim sharti sifatida ham qaralishi mumkin.

AKTda didaktik imkoniyatlar uch tur asosida tahlil etiladi. Bular:

1. Ta'limda o'quv ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish.
2. Ta'limda o'quv ma'lumotlarni uzatish.
3. Ta'limda sifatli o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish.

Shulardan kelib chiqqan holda ta'limda AKTning didaktik imkoniyatlari sifatida quyidagilarni keltirish mumkin:

Axborotlarni ta'limga oid turli xil elektron resurslar orqali, ya'ni matn, grafik, audio, video, animatsion formatlarda ko'rsatish va uzatish.

Ta'lim oluvchilarni qiziqtiruvchi ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish.

Ta'lim oluvchining qabul qilgan bilimlari orqali bilish ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlash va amalda to'g'ri qo'llash imkoniyatini yaratish.

Axborotni saqlash va tizimlashtirish.

O'quv, o'quv-uslubiy, ilmiy axborotlarni tayyorlash, tartibga solish va ishlov berish kabilar.

Bulardan tashqari, AKTida didaktik imkoniyatlar sifatida yana quyidagilarni sanab o'tish mumkin:

- axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida turli xil axborotlar oqimini turli shakllarda tarqatish;
- Ma'lumotlardan to'raligicha foydalanish imkoniyatini ta'minlash;
- qiziqtiruvchi ma'lumotlarni doimiy olishi va foydalanishlari uchun birorta elektron bankiga yoki o'quv ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanishi;
- turli xil axborotlar tashuvchi vositalardan ma'lumotlarni yuklashi;
- kursda ta'lim beruvchi bilan onlayn yoki oflayn muloqotni tashkil etishi;
- ta'lim beruvchi bilan ta'lim oluvchi o'rtasida jonli ma'lumot almashinish (matn, grafik, audio) kabilarni tashkil etish;
- ta'lim oluvchilar uchun to'la imkoniyatni, yani turli xil konsultatsiyalarni tashkil etish kabilar kiradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining didaktik imkoniyatlari juda keng. Ulardan o'rinli foydalanish muhim masala hisoblanadi. Zamonaviy axborot-kommunikativ texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlarini anglamasdan turib ulardan foydalanib bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun ham ta'limda bunga muhim masala sifatida e'tibor berilishi zarurdir.

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GOSPITAL MAKTAB O`QUVCHILARINING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYASINI GIBRID O`QITISH METODIKASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotasiya: *Maqolada gospital maktab o`quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini gibrid o`qitish metodikasi asosida rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari ko`rib chiqiladi. Gospital pedagogikasining markaziy kontsepsiyasi kasalxona va maktab ta`limi uyg`unligini ta`minlashda ularga ta`lim berishning innovatsion metodlarini qo`llash lozimligi muhimdir. Shuningdek uzoq vaqt tengqurlaridan ayro davolanishda bo`lgan maktab o`quvchilarining muloqot ko`nikmalarini, kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish ahamiyati o`rganiladi. Gospital pedagogikada qisqa muddatli kasallik bilan davolanayotgan o`quvchilardan farqli o`laroq uzoq muddatli kasallik bilan davolanayotgan o`quvchilar ta`limini tashkil qilishdagi farqli jihatlarni ham aniq ajratgan holda yondoshish talab etiladi.*

Kalit so`zlar: *gospital pedagogika, kommunikatsiya, kompetentsiya, gibrid o`qitish, rehabilitatsiya, o`quvchi, davolanish, amaliy yo`rdam, dars materiallari, pedagogik va psixologik diagnostika.*

Abstract: *The article considers the possibilities of developing communicative competence of hospital school students based on hybrid teaching methods. The central concept of hospital pedagogy is the need to use innovative methods of teaching them to ensure the harmony of hospital and school education. The importance of developing communication skills and communicative competence of school students who are being treated separately from their peers for a long time is also studied. Hospital pedagogy requires a clear approach to the organization of education of students undergoing long-term treatment, as opposed to students undergoing treatment for short-term illnesses.*

Key words: *hospital pedagogy, communication, competence, hybrid education, rehabilitation, student, treatment, practical assistance, teaching materials, pedagogical and psychological diagnostics.*

Gospital pedagogikasining markaziy kontsepsiyasi kasalxona va maktab ta`limi uyg`unligini ta`minlashdir. Jumladan, tibbiy tashkilotda uzoq muddatli davolanishga muhtoj o`quvchining ta'lim faoliyatini asosiy va qo'shimcha umumiy ta'lim dasturlari asosida amalga oshiradigan tashkilot sifatidagi faoliyati nazarda tutiladi. Bunda uzoq vaqt tengqurlaridan ayro davolanishda bo`lgan maktab o`quvchilarining muloqot ko`nikmalarini, kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirib borish o`ta muhimdir.

Respublikamiz Konstitutsiyasiga va ta'lim sohasidagi qonunchilikka ko'ra, har bir bolaga (fuqaroga) tashqi sharoitlardan qat'i nazar, ta'lim huquqidan umumiy foydalanish imkoniyati yaratilishi va davlat ta'lim standartlariga muvofiq umumiy ta'limni bepul olishi kafolatlanadi. Bepul umumiy ta'lim olish va undan foydalanish

imkoniyati, shu jumladan sog'ligi sababli ta'lim muassasalariga bora olmaydigan va uyda yoki tibbiy muassasada uzoq muddatli davolanayotgan bolalar uchun ham kafolatlanadi. Mazkur toifaga kiruvchi o'quvchilar bilan ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish davlat va jamiyat qatorida gospital pedagoglari zimmasiga ham yuklanadi.

Gospital pedagogikada qisqa muddatli kasallik bilan davolanayotgan o'quvchilardan farqli o'laroq uzoq muddatli kasallik bilan davolanayotgan o'quvchilar ta'limini tashkil qilishda farqli jihatlarni kuzatish mumkin. Ayrim kasalliklar bo'ladiki o'quvchi bilan birga uning oila a'zolarini ham qiyin ijtimoiy va hissiy holatga tushirib qo'yadi va natijada ularning turmush tarzi keskin o'zgarib ketishi mumkin. Undan tashqari davolash jarayoni, ayniqsa og'ir kasallik holatlarida gospital o'quvchining kognitiv (bilish) funktsiyalariga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ushbu sababli gospital ta'lim jarayonini tashkil qilishda mazkur holatlarni inobatga olish o'ta muhimdir.

Gospital pedagogikada ta'lim jarayoniga gibrid yondashuv majburiy chora bo'lib tuyulishi mumkin, ammo bu holatni o'quvchilar kasallik tufayli auditoriyada darslarga qatnasha olmaydigan holatlarda ham qo'llash o'rinlidir.

Asinxron ta'lim onlayn ta'limdan farqli o'laroq, gibrid format o'qituvchiga yuzma-yuz va masofaviy guruhlar bilan yuqori sifatli muloqotni ta'minlash imkonini beradi. O'qituvchi barcha o'quvchilarning faolligini kuzatishi, savollar berishi va javob berishi, o'quvchilarning reaksiyalarini ko'rishi va qachon qo'shimcha tushuntirishlar kerakligini tushunishi mumkin. Shuningdek, asinxron onlayn ta'lim o'quvchilardan rejalashtirish ko'nikmalarini, yuqori mustaqillikni va o'z o'quv jarayoni uchun mas'uliyatni rivojlantirishni talab qiladi. Shuning uchun, o'qituvchi tomonidan ko'proq yordam va nazorat zarur bo'lgan holatlarda, gibrid yondashuv to'liq auditoriyadagi yuzma-yuz yondashuvning samaradorligiga yaqinlashadi.

Yuqoridagi afzalliklarga qaramay, gibrid formatning kamchiliklari va qiyinchiliklari ham mavjud. Ular, shuningdek, ta'lim jarayonining tashkiliy, texnik va pedagogik jihatlari ham tegishlidir. Gibrid modelda samarali o'qitish uchun o'qituvchi qo'llaniladigan o'qitish usullarini va o'quvchilarni dars jarayoniga qanday jalb qilishni qayta ko'rib chiqishi kerak bo'ladi. Guruhning bir qismi masofadan turib o'qiyotganda, yuzma-yuz formatda yaxshi ishlaydigan metodlar kutilgan natijani bermasligi mumkin. Shuning uchun, "gibrid" da muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun sizga rivojlangan raqamli vakolatlar, yangi usullarni sinab ko'rish va har bir aniq holatda ularning samaradorligini ob'ektiv baholashga tayyorlik kerak.

Gibrid ta'lim formatida dars o'tish o'qituvchidan katta malaka talab qiladi. Chunki o'qituvchi bir vaqtning o'zida ikkita turli sinf xonasi bilan ishlashiga to'g'ri

keladi – biri bevosita auditoriyada, ikkinchisi esa video orqali ulanadi. Bunda barcha o`quvchilar (On-Line va Of-Line) o'xshash sifatli ta'lim olishlarini ta'minlash uchun dars davomida oflayn va onlayn guruhga teng e'tibor berilishi talab etiladi. Agar ta'lim muassasasida texnik yordamchi bo'lmasa, o'qituvchi o'zi dars davomida texnik muammolar bilan ham shug'ullanishi kerak bo'ladi. Ushbu murakkab muvofiqlashtirish jarayoni o'qituvchidan professional ko'nikmalarni talab qiladi. Biroq, texnik qurilmalar sinfda o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar uchun noqulay bo'lishi mumkin. Misol uchun, faqat mikrofonga gapirish jonli muhokamaga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin. Va siz doimo kamera tomonidan suratga olinayotganingizni tushunish o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar uchun noqulaylik va diskomfort tug'dirishi mumkin.

Gibrid ta'lim bo'yicha ilmiy izlanishlar olib borgan gollandiyalik tadqiqotchi Annelies Ras ta'kidlaganidek, onlayn o'qiyotgan o'quvchilar odatda auditoriyada bo'lgan o'quvchilarga qaraganda jarayonda kamroq ishtirok etadilar. Ko'pincha ular darsda faol ishtirok etmasdan video tasmasini shunchaki tomosha qilishadi. Mavjud tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, onlayn guruhdagi o'quvchilar o'zlarini o'qituvchidan va yuzma-yuz guruhdagi sinfdoshlaridan uzoqda, xuddi sinfdan chetlashtirilgandek his qilishi kuzatiladi. Shuningdek, onlayn gospital o'quvchi uchun noqulaylik tug'dirishi mumkin, masalan, savolga javob berishni xohlasa, o'qituvchiga signal berish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. Bu o'quvchining asabiylashishiga olib kelishi va o'zaro munosabatlarga salbiy ta'sir qiladi. Va har qanday masofaviy ta'lim uchun dolzarb bo'lgan muammo – onlayn o'qish gospital o'quvchidan mustaqillik va o'zini o'zi nazorat qilishni talab qiladi. Afsuski barcha o'quvchilarda ham kommunikativ ko'nikmalar yetarlicha rivojlanmagan.

Ideal stsenariyda gibrid sinf yuqori aniqlikdagi kameralar va ovozni aks-sado va kechikishlarsiz uzatuvchi yuqori sifatli mikrofonlar, interfaol doska, masofaviy o'quvchilarning veb-kameralaridan video translyatsiya qiluvchi katta ekran va sinfdagi har bir o'quvchida planshet bo'lishi lozim. Shu bilan birga, jarayonning texnik qismi maxsus xodim tomonidan nazorat qilinadi va o'qituvchi ta'lim faoliyatiga to'liq e'tibor qaratishi mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, gibrid ta'lim an'anaviy va elektron ta'lim imkoniyatlarini o'zida mujassam etgan innovatsion ta'lim tizimlaridan biridir. Ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etishga malakali yondashuv bilan gibrid ta'lim muhitida ijobiy natijalarni qo'lga kiritish mumkin. Gibrid ta'limni yaratish barcha ishtirokchilar uchun uzoq muddatli va strategik ko'p mehnat talab qiladigan vazifa bo'lib, uni hal qilish uchun faol pozitsiyani egallash, ta'lim tizimining keyingi rivojlanishini kutish kerak bo'ladi. Gospital pedagoglar gospital o'quvchilarni o'qishga jalb qilish,

ularning ishonchini qozonish, har bir o`quvchiga individual yondashuvni topa olish va ularning ota-onalari hamda tibbiyot xodimlari bilan muloqot strategiyasini qurish qobiliyatiga ega bo`lishi o`ta muhimdir. Chunki o`quvchilar to'liq ta'lim olishni xohlashadi, ular bir qator ta'lim qiziqishlariga ega va kasallik bu intilishlarni to'xtatmaydi. Ha, bu muayyan qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi, lekin gospital pedagoglarning professionalligi tufayli ularni engib o'tish mumkin.

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THE BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) has gained prominence in higher education worldwide, including Uzbekistan, where it is being increasingly implemented in state universities. This study examines the benefits and challenges associated with EMI in Uzbekistan's higher education institutions (HEIs). It provides an overview of the sociolinguistic landscape, the government's language education policies, and the motivations for adopting EMI. The study explores the benefits of EMI, such as improving English proficiency, enhancing academic and career opportunities, and fostering internationalization. However, challenges include variability in teacher preparedness, limited resources, and disparities in students' language proficiency. The research also draws comparisons with Kazakhstan, where EMI has contributed to global competitiveness and higher education reforms. The findings suggest that EMI implementation in Uzbekistan, while still in its early stages, has potential benefits but requires structured policies, improved teacher training, and adequate financial support to be effective. Future studies are encouraged to conduct empirical research on classroom dynamics, discipline-specific EMI effectiveness, and long-term student outcomes.*

Keywords: *English Medium Instruction (EMI), higher education, Uzbekistan, language policy, internationalization, teacher training, academic competitiveness, educational reform.*

1. Introduction

English is arguably the hegemonic language of academic communication in many countries, including Uzbekistan. English is widely recognised as a dominant language of instruction globally, which aligns with the concept of 'linguistic imperialism' (Phillipson, 1992). English Medium Instruction (EMI) involves teaching academic subjects in English within countries where English is not the primary language for most of the population. (Dearden, 2014). Although the field of EMI research is quite recent, the trend has been metaphorically characterized as 'unstoppable' (Macaro 2018, p.7). EMI in Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) in Uzbekistan has been introduced relatively recently. While there is considerable literature on EMI in the European context, where this educational approach has been widely adopted for a significant period, studies conducted in developing countries are scarce (Guo et al., 2022). Therefore, this essay aims to evaluate the implementation of EMI in Higher Education (HE) in Uzbekistan, focusing on this educational practice's potential benefits and challenges. The focus will be on EMI practices in state higher education rather than international or non-governmental ones, as the latter often employ foreign teachers, unlike state institutions. Focusing on state

universities, which often employ local instructors, provides a deeper understanding of how EMI is implemented in Uzbekistan. Additionally, this essay will rely on existing research papers about EMI in Uzbekistan rather than conducting an empirical study. Due to the dearth of literature, it also examines EMI benefits and challenges in Kazakhstan, a nation with a shared history that has implemented a trilingual education policy (Kazakh, Russian, and English). As a researcher and former student in Uzbekistan, I recognize that EMI's implementation in the country is not fully fledged, and substantial work remains to be done to enhance it. Therefore, the implementation of EMI faces some challenges, and unveiling them is essential for improvement, bearing in mind the benefits EMI is generally believed to offer.

1. Background

1.1 Sociolinguistic Landscape of Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan's linguistic landscape is complex and dynamic, shaped by its history with the Soviet Union (1925-1990) and Western influences post-1991. It is a multilingual country where various ethnicities coexist, including Uzbeks (83.8%), Tajiks (4.8%), Kazakhs (2.5%), Russians (2.3%), Karakalpaks (2.2%), Tatars (1.5%), and others (2.9%) (cia.gov, 2024). Following independence in 1991, Uzbekistan implemented a 'one language-one nation' policy (Djuraeva, 2022, p.93). Russian still serves as a lingua franca, facilitating communication across ethnicities. However, the role of Russian in the country remains a sensitive issue, as it is widely spoken but lacks official status (Egamberdiev, 2020).

Although English has not deeply penetrated Uzbek society, with only a minority of the population proficient (Hasanova, 2007), interest in the language is growing significantly. According to the EF English Proficiency Index 2021, Uzbekistan ranked 88th out of 112 non-English speaking countries globally and 18th among 24 Asian countries, classified with "very low" proficiency. Despite this starting point, there is considerable enthusiasm from the government and society to pursue EMI in HE (Linn & Bezborodova, 2022). This has led to several decrees to enhance foreign language education, particularly emphasizing EMI in higher education.

1.2 Foreign Language Education Reforms

Government efforts to enhance foreign language proficiency, especially English, in Uzbekistan are evident through various decrees. A significant reform was Presidential Decree #1875, issued on December 10, 2012, which aimed to foster an educated, modern-thinking generation and integrate Uzbekistan into the international community (National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2012). This decree targeted the improvement of foreign language proficiency at all

educational levels, including HE, where some institutions adopted EMI for technical and international specialities. However, Mamasolieva (2019) argues that most higher education institutions (HEIs) have not fully transitioned to English as the instruction medium. In agreement with her, it is observed that teachers and students often engage in translanguaging, using Uzbek and Russian alongside English. This practice can be described as employing 'features from a unitary linguistic repertoire to make meaning and to negotiate particular communicative contexts' (Vogel & García 2017, p.1).

In 2017, another presidential decree aimed to enhance the education system, which led to the establishment of the British Council's English for Academic Purposes program, focusing on international connections and pedagogical practices (Linn and Bezborodova, 2022). To further promote international academic mobility, a decree was signed in 2018, establishing the *El-Yurt Umidi* Foundation to send talented students abroad to pursue Bachelor's, Master's, and PhD degrees at the top 300 universities worldwide (lex.uz.2018). I also received a full scholarship from this foundation, which covered my study and living expenses abroad. My experience confirms that the foundation significantly benefits Uzbekistan's youth by providing access to advanced standard education. This exposure allows them to gain valuable knowledge and experience from top universities, contributing to Uzbekistan's scientific development.

In the same year, another decree was enacted permitting the use of TOEFL or IELTS scores as substitutes for the English language section of the national standardized exam required for admission to HEIs (Linn and Bezborodova, 2022). Furthermore, the President enacted a decree that significantly influenced the execution of the *Concept of Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan* until 2030. This decree mandates that a minimum of ten universities in Uzbekistan achieve international recognition (lex.uz.2019). Linn and Bezborodova (2022) argue that a university's position in global rankings is closely linked to its research productivity, prompting higher education institutions to adopt strategies that boost publications in peer-reviewed journals. They believe that these strategies put considerable pressure on researchers and educators. However, it can be argued that this focus does not necessarily pressure faculty. Instead, this approach might motivate them to enhance their research quality and engagement, potentially leading to broader academic contributions and innovations that benefit the educational community.

3. EMI in Uzbekistan

3.1 EMI: overview

The total number of HEIs is 210 (fledu.uz, 2023). This includes 115 state institutions, 65 non-state institutions, and 30 foreign institutions. While not every state university offers English-language programs, some have specialized programs where courses are partially conducted in English. Notably, the University of World Economy and Diplomacy offers courses in English within its International Relations and World Politics departments. The Uzbekistan State World Languages University (UZSWLU) also strongly emphasizes EMI for preparing future language teachers and translators (Bezborodova & Radjabzade, 2022). Drawing from my experiences as a former UZSWLU student, I observed that while primary subjects were often taught in English, several secondary subjects, such as history, economics, philosophy, and physical training, were taught in Russian or Uzbek languages.

3.1 EMI: Motivation

A significant European study by the Academic Cooperation Association (Wachter & Maiworm, 2008, cited in Wilkinson, 2013) identified three key reasons for implementing EMI. The main reason is to draw international students who might not enroll if the programs were offered in the local language. EMI is also designed to prepare local students for the global marketplace and enhance the institution's ranking in the country. The adoption of EMI in Uzbekistan is primarily motivated by the aims of global connectivity, internalization, educational advancement, and improving the Uzbek universities' ranking (lex.uz.2019). Wilkinson (2013) notes that the adoption of EMI aims to increase international visibility, attract funding, enhance university rankings, and improve graduates' global competitiveness and employability. These motivations are consistent with the aims of Uzbekistan's EMI strategy in HE.

Although EMI is a relatively recent development in Uzbekistan, it attracts international students to state universities, especially in fields like medicine, law, and languages. The increasing enrollment of these students suggests that implementing EMI is proving effective. Linn and Bezborodova (2022, p.3) further argue that English is growing as the medium of instruction in Uzbekistan, and "English groups" are becoming increasingly common, following national guidelines for HE development. Overall, the expansion of EMI in Uzbekistan reflects a broader global trend towards embracing English as a key tool for global and international engagement, educational advancement, and enhancement of universities' rankings.

3.2 Benefits of EMI

EMI has gained significant attention in HE research, with numerous studies highlighting its benefits for students and educators. Galloway (2017) reveals EMI improves English proficiency, provides access to up-to-date academic research, and

boosts global competitiveness. It also enhances career prospects and facilitates international collaboration and opportunities for studying or working abroad, enriching educational and professional experiences. Regarding the context of Uzbekistan, Rahmanova and Ekşi (2023) conducted a study in Uzbekistan to discern the perceptions of administrators, teachers, and students of the benefits and opportunities EMI presents at state universities. The research indicates that administrators view EMI as a valuable tool for enhancing students' English and communication skills and their ability to engage in international conferences. Teachers at state universities in Uzbekistan generally hold positive opinions on the effectiveness of EMI, noting its potential to improve students' prospects for future educational and career opportunities. Teachers also recognize that teaching through EMI can enhance their English language competence and pedagogical skills. Furthermore, students report that EMI contributes to their English language improvement, participation in international conferences and projects, and provides opportunities to study and work abroad after graduation. Their study aligns with Galloway's (2017) research.

Another study conducted in three Central Asian countries, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan, by Bezborodova and Radjabzade (2022) is consistent with the findings of Rahmanova and Ekşi (2023), highlighting the widespread recognition of EMI's benefits in Uzbekistan among students and teachers. The participants in their study perceived EMI as offering better educational opportunities, supporting professional and academic development, and enhancing employability in the global job market. These findings underscore the value placed on English proficiency as a critical component of modern education and career advancement, aligning with the broader objectives of national education reforms aimed at internationalization.

Furthermore, the research by Tajik et al. (2023) in Kazakhstan reveals that EMI is perceived as a symbol of prestige and social status. It is a gateway, enabling students to access international universities and global job markets while enhancing educators' teaching skills. Historically, Kazakhstani students and skilled workers have depended on Russia. However, adopting EMI offers graduates expanded prospects in overseas universities, global job markets, and various economic fields. This shift not only offers individual benefits but also positions Kazakhstan as a competitive player on the global stage, emphasizing English as a crucial language for international communication and integration.

Overall, EMI has become a central focus in HE due to its wide-ranging benefits, as underscored by studies from various researchers, including Galloway (2017) and more localized research in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan by Rahmanova and Ekşi (2023), Bezborodova and Radjabzade (2022), and Tajik et al. (2023). These studies collectively highlight EMI's role in enhancing English proficiency, academic competitiveness, and career prospects, making it a valuable educational strategy. In Uzbekistan, EMI is seen as a tool for boosting students' language skills and international engagement. Educators, students and administrators appreciate the improved academic and professional opportunities it provides. Similarly, research from Kazakhstan indicates that EMI is elevating education standards, helping students access global opportunities and marking a significant shift away from traditional reliance on Russian influences. This broad adoption of EMI across varied contexts illustrates its effectiveness in integrating local education systems into the global academic and economic landscape.

3.3 Challenges of EMI

Although EMI offers several advantages, the challenges associated with its adoption should not be overlooked. Rahmanova and Ekşi's (2023) study reveals variability in the preparedness and motivation among instructors for teaching in English-medium classrooms; some are highly motivated, while others lack the necessary experience or confidence. Students also encounter obstacles in understanding new materials, fulfilling tasks, expressing ideas in English, and building an adequate academic vocabulary. As a result, both teachers and students often engage in translanguaging practices in the classroom. Moreover, Rahmanova and Ekşi's (2023) report difficulties in recruiting native English-speaking instructors for teacher training, hiring foreign experts, and forming partnerships with international universities to enhance local instructors' English teaching capabilities. They also highlight issues with inadequate IT resources, such as insufficient computers, unreliable internet connectivity, and a lack of suitable teaching materials. Additionally, Bezborodova and Radjabzade's (2022) research identifies similar challenges, noting students' dissatisfaction with teaching methods at state universities. In other words, teachers focused more on attendance than actual learning, leading to low student motivation. The main student complaints were about boring lectures, an excessive focus on theory without practical applications, and unclear learning objectives. From the teachers' perspective, teaching through EMI was particularly challenging due to a lack of materials and training. Furthermore, the study found that translanguaging practices were prevalent in classrooms, with

teachers and students often using other languages alongside English. The researchers referred to this phenomenon as code-switching. However, I view this practice as translanguaging, which can be considered deliberate pedagogical practice (Wei and Lin, 2019).

Interestingly, a study by Tajik et al. (2023) in Kazakhstan revealed that EMI contributes to inequalities and difficulties, leading to stress and anxiety among students. A significant variation in English language proficiency among students results in classroom segregation and inequality. This gap fosters social inequalities as it benefits students with strong English language skills and excludes less proficient ones. (Phillipson, 1994, cited in Tajik et al., 2023). Pennycook (1994, cited in Tajik et al., 2023) argues that EMI may sustain the dominance of English-speaking cultures and strengthen the notion that the English language is superior, implying that academic achievement depends solely on proficiency in English. Moreover, the study reveals that implementing EMI has made the roles of Kazakhstani teachers more challenging and complex. They are expected to excel in their subject matter and teach in English. Their insufficient English skills and minimal knowledge of EMI techniques impede their effectiveness in teaching.

Overall, in Uzbekistan, challenges with EMI include variability in teacher readiness, motivation, insufficient IT resources, and language proficiency, leading to a reliance on translanguaging in classrooms (Rahmanova and Ekşi, 2023; Bezborodova and Radjabzade, 2022). In contrast, Kazakhstan faces significant social inequalities due to EMI, with disparities in English proficiency causing classroom segregation and stress among students (Tajik et al., 2023). Additionally, Kazakhstani teachers struggle with inadequate English skills and a lack of EMI pedagogical training, complicating their dual roles as content and language instructors. These differences illustrate how EMI introduces distinct challenges in each country, affecting educational outcomes and social equity.

3.4 Evaluation of EMI Practice in Uzbekistan

In response to national HE reforms, Linn and Bezborodova (2022) evaluated the EMI project in collaboration with the British Council and the Ministry of Secondary and Higher Education. This project aimed to enhance English proficiency and promote internationalization in HE by training EMI professionals at 16 state universities. The evaluation project, conducted by the University of Webster, focuses on key aspects such as relevance, effectiveness, sustainability, and strategic recommendations. The findings highlight the importance of a holistic approach to EMI development, emphasizing the need for multilingualism. This could be

facilitated by incorporating translanguaging practices in the classroom. Although translanguaging is frequently observed, as noted in previous studies, there is a lack of training on effectively implementing translanguaging techniques in educational settings. Moreover, the project highlights the necessity for standardized language proficiency tests for admissions. The use of standardized language proficiency tests for admissions is important. Applicants to state universities can submit internationally recognized certificates like IELTS, CEFR, and TOEFL or opt for a national exam focusing mainly on grammar. This leads to a classroom division: students with international certificates usually have more practical English skills, while those who pass the grammar-focused exam often struggle with speaking and listening. This segregation needs to be addressed to ensure a more balanced classroom environment. Additionally, the report emphasizes the necessity of collaboration between language and content teachers and the development of robust online and offline resources to support teachers and students in improving their language proficiency. This recommendation is important as a hybrid form of teacher and student training could be beneficial, allowing flexibility and convenience. Furthermore, the project recommends embedding holistic EMI development in institutional policies and addressing specific disciplinary needs through sector-wide training.

University leaders are primarily motivated by internationalization and research publication goals. However, educators in HE lack financial support for their research activities. Therefore, proper funding is essential for achieving the national reform objectives of EMI. Furthermore, a crucial issue is that students appear to have a limited understanding of the educational approach through EMI (Bezborodova, 2023). Therefore, it is essential to provide thorough training on EMI not just for teachers but also for students. Ultimately, the EMI project's success depends on continuous support, standardized practices, and a comprehensive approach to EMI development, ensuring its long-term sustainability and effectiveness in Uzbekistan's HE landscape.

Conclusion

EMI is a recent educational approach in HE in Uzbekistan. Its implementation reflects a significant shift towards internationalization and enhanced global competitiveness for the country. The existing literature underscores EMI's potential to improve English proficiency, academic success, and career opportunities. Despite its benefits, the transition to EMI has faced challenges such as variability in teacher preparedness, motivation, insufficient resources, and language proficiency. These obstacles highlight a gap between educational goals and practical realities. However,

the evaluation project conducted by Linn and Bezborodova (2022) and this study suggest some possible strategies to address these challenges. While the full integration of EMI into Uzbekistan's higher education system will take time, the initial steps towards its adoption are promising.

Based on the existing literature, this study has laid the groundwork for a comprehensive understanding of EMI practice in HE in Uzbekistan. I believe that this is the first study to systematically review all the existing literature on EMI within this context. Since EMI is a recent educational approach in HE in Uzbekistan, further empirical investigations are encouraged to explore more teachers' and students' experiences, especially in state HEIs. Future studies could examine classroom dynamics, the effectiveness of EMI in different disciplinary contexts, and its long-term impact on students' academic and career opportunities. Moreover, while existing research has primarily relied on surveys and interviews to collect data, incorporating classroom observations could provide a more detailed understanding of EMI practices in Uzbekistan.

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TRAINING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF PEDAGOGICAL DISCOURSE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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***Annotation:** In the article, the author considers both the pedagogical and methodological significance of pedagogical discourse in a foreign language. In addition, the latter is related to the formation of intercultural communication skills of the participants in the educational process. Pedagogical speech in a foreign language is presented as a complex and integrative phenomenon that influences the formation of the communication culture of modern representatives of the younger generation. When analyzing the essential features of pedagogical discourse in a foreign language, great attention is paid to the linguistic and extra-linguistic conditions for the successful functioning of pedagogical discourse in foreign language teaching. The author characterizes the main features of the language portrait of a foreign language teacher and the main features of the foreign language communicative educational environment.*

***Key words:** Pedagogical discourse, foreign language teaching, intercultural communication, linguistic and cultural interaction, portrait of teacher discourse.*

The urgent need for modern educational theory and practice is associated with the study of various types of institutional discourses, including discourses of pedagogy as a means of understanding and shaping modern pedagogical phenomena. In this sense, it is necessary to consider pedagogical discourse (especially in the context of foreign language teaching) as a multifunctional phenomenon. It can be extremely useful for more adequate self-determination between the problems of general and higher education; for the search for unused solutions and unconsidered conditions that can help to reasonably successfully implement certain pedagogical ideas. This will significantly contribute to the development of the theory and practice of modern Russian education at the federal and regional levels. The relevance of studying pedagogical discourse as a multifunctional mechanism, as well as the process of its development, is associated with the progressive and important essence of this phenomenon. Pedagogical discourse is a kind of harmonizing pedagogical dialogue. If the latter is properly constructed, it helps the teacher to identify the hidden reserves of the personality of students, increase their intellectual and motivational activity, and strengthen the positive emotions of the entire educational process. In particular, the study of the effective mechanisms of organizing pedagogical rhetoric in the process of teaching a foreign language is of great scientific interest to us within the framework of this article. Undoubtedly, this

scientific direction has great potential for the development of intercultural communication skills. The latter is one of the necessary qualities of every modern worker in many fields of activity. Therefore, the urgency of the problem predetermined the purpose of our study, namely, to characterize pedagogical discourse in a foreign language as a phenomenon that functions in educational communication and contributes to the formation of intercultural communication skills among participants in the educational process. In accordance with the purpose of the study, we will highlight the following scientific objectives: analyze the development of pedagogical discourse from the point of view of an integrative-systemic approach; conduct a comparative analysis of the essential features of the concept of “pedagogical speech in a foreign language”; identify the most promising ideas on the foundations of pedagogical rhetoric that may be in demand in the theory and practice of modern Russian language teaching (especially in the context of a foreign language course). The scientific novelty of the research lies in the fact that the social significance of the problem of teaching the basics of pedagogical rhetoric to future representatives of the teaching profession (in particular, foreign language teachers) is substantiated; It is also shown that the competent construction of pedagogical language in a foreign language contributes to the achievement of advanced educational results of students in foreign language teaching (formation of variability of thinking; intensification of the learning process; formation of intercultural communication skills and keys); competencies; comprehensive personal development; formation of a new type of student personality; The basic ideas of pedagogical rhetoric are characterized within the framework of the format of foreign language teaching (organization of relations between teacher and student; elimination of "dryness" and formalism in teaching; development of independence of activity and cognitive activity of students; comprehensive use of search and research methods in the educational process; inclusion of artistic and playful forms of learning; teacher), which expands the theoretical foundations of pedagogical theory and practice. In this sense, we believe that the practical significance of this scientific work lies in the fact that the study of the mechanism of effective organization of the space of communication in a foreign language in the framework of pedagogical discourse will determine the successful solution of the strategic goals of educational policy. The latter are reflected in the State Program of the Russian Federation “Development of Education”, in the Strategy for the Development of Education in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025, in the federal educational standards of general education. These normative documents indicate the need to develop education aimed

at the formation of a creative and socially responsible personality, which is a portrait of a school graduate who actively and purposefully explores the world, who understands the value of education and science, work and creativity for man and society and who is motivated to creative activity. In addition, the provisions and conclusions of the presented research can be used to determine the priority directions of modernization of Russian professional pedagogical education and introduce into its content new ideas for training future teachers, taking into account the classical canons of rhetoric and progressive trends in such areas of scientific knowledge as linguomethodology, cognitive discourse theory, pedagogical linguistics, discursive pragmatics and sociocultural linguistics. Currently, there are a sufficient number of studies of various types of language, mainly in the context of modern linguistics, semiotics and philosophy (VA Andreeva, ND Arutyunova, R. Barth, TB Gulyar, VI Karasik, Yu.V. Shcherbinina, etc .). However, an important part of humanistic knowledge, in which issues of oral and written text play an important role, is pedagogy. This kind of situation arises because it is related to the verbal interaction between teacher and student, which is the basis of the educational and teaching process of a person. Improving the language aspect of pedagogical communication is possible if the study of the teacher's speech is carried out from the point of view of an interdisciplinary approach. Only the integration of pedagogical and philological knowledge makes it possible to obtain the most complete and diverse description of pedagogical discourse. It is worth noting that modern scientific groups of authors (for example: EV Komleva, K. Yu. Gerasimova, DV Miroshnikova [1]) consider the problem of pedagogical discourse in the context of training future teachers (in particular, teachers of a foreign language). The central concept is considered to be the discursive competence of a teacher, the formation of which, according to scientists, should begin already in the university training of future teachers. In addition, researchers pay attention to the nomenclature of pedagogical communication skills. The existence of pedagogical discourse in the context of the educational space is directly related to such sciences as pedagogy, sociology, psychology and teaching methods of the subject. It should be noted that the discursive aspects of these sciences are manifested in the strategy and tactics of pedagogical communication, in the development of some techniques and means of influencing the student during pedagogical communication by the teacher, in the mastery of discursive forms of the cliché of greetings, farewells, reprimands, as well as optimal and effective ways of harmonizing the educational process. In the context of the problem under consideration, final studies of pedagogical and linguistic orientation are of great

scientific interest. In these works, the main concepts in the field of educational and Internet discourses are analyzed and compared [2]; the main research approaches of pedagogical discourse are analyzed and, in addition, its axiological nature is substantiated, in addition, the model of popular science pedagogical discourse in English is recreated [3]. Since discourse, and pedagogical discourse in particular, is the subject of interdisciplinary research, we can confirm the growing interest of modern scientists from various fields of knowledge in this phenomenon. In the modern scientific world, there is a progressive vision of the role of pedagogical discourse in the formation of the personality of each student, taking into account the specifics of the modern educational space and its participants (active introduction of distance and mixed educational formats, increased orientation towards personal development of representatives of the Z and Alpha generations, the need to enrich the methodological tools of modern education, overcome the so-called “one-dimensionality” of students' thinking). In this sense, pedagogical discourse should be perceived as a unique field of emotional and intellectual interaction between teacher and student, implemented in the educational process through a system of methods of pedagogical interaction during the pedagogical process. Particular emphasis is placed on the creation of a language portrait of future teachers (especially foreign language teachers) in the process of their training at a pedagogical college in order to ensure harmonious and successful pedagogical and scientific interaction with students both in the context of pedagogical practice and in the process of future professional activity. The role of the teacher in pedagogical discourse is essentially to arouse and stimulate students' interest in intellectual and verbal interaction. The effectiveness of building pedagogical discourse in a foreign language for the purpose of forming intercultural communication skills also depends on the extent to which the teacher takes into account the psychological and emotional-intellectual characteristics of students. In addition, emphasis is placed on the teacher's ability to show emotional stability and systematically maintain a positive emotional background in the process of pedagogical discourse. That is, the extra-linguistic conditions for the implementation of pedagogical discourse are of great importance. An effective means of improving and correcting the speech behavior of future representatives of the teaching profession is the introduction of special communication and speech tasks, as well as rhetorical tasks into the training process of pedagogical universities. That is, pedagogical speech is characterized by the manifestation of the teacher's individual speaking style. The speech behavior of a future foreign language teacher should evoke a variety of emotional and intellectual states in students, such as: B.

pedagogical guesses, interest, doubt, surprise, etc. In general, pedagogical speech in a foreign language should be understood as a language-thinking activity, which in its essence is verbalized and implemented in a comprehensive language portrait of the teacher. The latter implies a duality of sociolectic and idiolectic elements and, consequently, includes not only linguistic, but also extralinguistic components. That is, the language portrait of a teacher is built in two directions and reveals not only his identity as a representative of a certain social and age group, but also shows his personal characteristics. Based on the definition of discourse as “an objectively existing verbal-symbolic structure that accompanies the process of socially significant interaction of people” [4, c . 8], we believe that pedagogical discourse is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that exists in the sphere of professional and pedagogical activity and is implemented by participants in educational relations with linguistic and cultural experience in professional interaction and communication of motives.

Based on the analysis carried out, the following conclusion can be drawn: the rich potential created in the works of scientists and teachers for the study of pedagogical discourse in its various interpretations is of lasting value for the development of modern Russian science, pedagogical theory and educational practice. Promising lines of future research can be identified: the study of the characteristic features of the text format of pedagogical speech (on the example of technological maps and lesson summaries, minutes of parent meetings); analysis of the most effective algorithms for improving the speech portrait of a modern teacher of different educational levels; the study of the relationship between gender characteristics and the communicative behavior of a teacher; identification of effective communication strategies for preparing students of pedagogical universities for pedagogical practice; analysis of the professional and terminological vocabulary system of pedagogical discourse.

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ETHEL LILIAN VOYNICH ASARLARI HAQIDAGI ILMIY ISHLARNING KOMPARATIVISTIKASI

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***Annotatsiya:** Qiyosiy adabiyotni o'rganish uzoq vaqtdan beri turli madaniy va tilshunoslik an'analari kesishishini ta'kidlab keladi, ammo bu sohani shakllantirishda poetikaning roli haligacha yetarlicha o'rganilmagan. Poetika adabiyot tamoyillari va shakllarini o'rganuvchi fan sifatida tillar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi matnlarning estetik va strukturaviy jihatlarini tahlil qilish uchun asos yaratadi. Ushbu maqolada Ethel Lilian Voynichning adabiyotga qo'shgan hissasi va uning Gadfly romani asosidagi turli tadqiqotlar qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada Voynich asarlarining ijtimoiy va siyosiy ahamiyati, ayniqsa, ular Sovet Ittifoqidagi inqilobiy harakatlarga qanday ta'sir qilgani ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, yozuvchining "Qadpoq" va boshqa romanlari rus adabiyotida qanday qabul qilinganligi, ya'ni qabul qilinishi, romanlarni tarjima qilish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Qiyosiy adabiyotda olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning aksariyati poetika tushunchasi bilan bog'liq. Poetikaning asosiy maqsadi asar yaratishga xizmat qiladigan barcha badiiy elementlarni ochib berish, yozuvchining mahoratini baholash va namoyon etishdan iborat. Poetikaning zamonaviy tadqiqotlari, asosan, nazariy va tarixiy poetikaga bag'ishlangan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** qiyosiy adabiyot, poetika, badiiy mahorat, she'riy asboblari, tarixiy poetika, nazariy poetika, adabiy tanqid.*

I. Kirish

Ethel Lilian Voynich (1864-1969) ingliz tili adabiy muhitining taniqli irlandiyalik adibalaridan biridir. Bugungi kunda iste'dodli yozuvchilardan biri sifatida ko'pchilik tanqidchilar tomonidan tan olingan. Ethel Lilian Voynich hayoti davomida biron bir yirik adabiy mukofot va rasmiy maqtovlarga sazovor bo'lmagan. Uning asarlari turli janrlarda yozilgan: hozirgi kunga qadar adibaning oltita romani ("Stories from Garshin" 1893, "The Gadfly" 1897, "Jack Raymond", 1901, "Olive Latham", 1904, "An Interrupted Friendship", 1910, "Put Off Thy Shoes", 1945) nashr etilgan.

II. Asosiy qism

Mironov Aleksey Viktorovich "Ethel Lilian Voynichning "Gadfly" romanining mifopoetikasi zamonaviy afsona nazariyalari nuqtai nazaridan" nomli tadqiqot ishini yozgan[1]. Asosiy e'tibor asarning nafaqat tarixiy mazmuni, balki uning metaforikva mifopoetika tuzilishiga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, Ethel Lilian Voynich va uning

asarlarini o'rgangan olimlardan yana biri Anne Fremantl. U "Gadfly"ning Rossiyada misli ko'rilmagan mashhurligini o'rganib chiqdi. U yerda Voynich asarlari inqilobiy klassikaga aylandi. U romanning Sovet Ittifoqining qarshilik, qurbonlik va zulmdan voz kechish g'oyalari bilan qanday to'qnash kelganini tahlil qildi[2]. Patrik Woddington(1930-2019) rus va Yevropa adabiyoti sohasidagi tajribasi bilan mashhur britaniyalik taniqli adabiyotshunos va tarjimon. U ingliz va rus adabiy an'analari o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirga e'tibor qaratdi va Ethel Lilian Voynich va uning "Gadfly" romanini o'rganishga katta hissa qo'shgan[3].

III. Metod va usullar

Hozirgi adabiyotda poetikaning 5 ta asosiy turi mavjud: umumiy, tavsifiy me'yoriy, nazariy va tarixiy poetika.

1.Umumiy poetika – barcha adabiyotlar uchun umumiy bo'lgan badiiy me'zonlarni o'rganadi. (Masalan: ijodiy tamoyillar, muallifning pozitsiyasi va boshqalar)

2.Tasviriy poetika – aniq asarlarning yaratilish jarayoni va yozuvchining badiiy dunyosini o'rganadi. (masalan: H.Olimjonning badiiy olami, Cho'lponning nasriy poetikasi va boshqalar).

3.Normativ poetika – "badiiy asar aslida qanday yozilishi kerak?" degan masalaga oydinlik kiritadi. Normativ poetika adabiy asarlarni baholaydi va adabiy tanqid obyektini hisoblanadi. U.To'ychiyevning "O'zbek adabiyotida badiiylik mezonlari va ularning maromlari", B.Sarimsoqovning "Badiiylik asoslari va mezonlari", A.Rasulovning "Badiiylik mezonlari" asarlari normativ poetikaga oid ilmiy asarlar hisoblanadi.

4.Nazariy poetika – bevosita adabiyot nazariyasi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, har bitta ko'rib chiqilayotgan adabiy hodisaning nazariy tomonini yoritib beradi.(masalan, Oybek romanlarida psixologiya, Pushkin she'riyatida shakl va mazmun) Adabiyotshunos olim U.Jo'raqulovning nazariy poetikaga bag'ishlangan asarida poetikaning muallif, janr, xronotop kabi jihatlari ochib berilgan.

5.Tarixiy poetika – asar yaratilishiga xizmat qiluvchi barcha badiiy elementlar genezisini o'rganadi, tarixiy-adabiy jarayon va davr ruhi bilan bog'liq holda ijodkorning badiiy dunyosi va mahoratini ochib beradi. Tarixiy poetika rivojiga A.Veselovskiy, M.Jirmunskiy, N.Konrad, I.G.Neupokoeva, M.M.Baxtin va boshqa rus olimlari katta hissa qo'shdilar. Ularning ilmiy ishlari bu boradagi eng yaxshisidir[4].

I.V.Stebleva, A.B.Kudelin, B.Shidfar, E.E.Bertels, V.I. Braginskiy, R.Musulmonqulov, Sh.M.Shukurovlarning ilmiy izlanishlari sharqshunoslikdagi

tarixiy poetika masalalariga bag'ishlangan. Poetika yoki badiiy mahorat yozuvchining o'ziga xos badiiy olami, badiiy asarni yaratishdagi san'atkorligidir. Ijodkorning badiiy mahorati asar tilining mohirona berilishida, obraz yaratishida, badiiy tasvir vositalaridan o'z o'rnida, mohirona foydalanishida, asar kompozitsiyasini to'g'ri va tizimli shakllantirishda va h.k.larda yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Bulardan tashqari badiiylikning quyidagi 10 ta mezoni yozuvchining badiiy mahoratini aniqlashga yordam beradi[5]:

- 1.Gumanizm (Insonparvarlik).
- 2.Estetik tuyg'uni shakllantira olish
- 3.Hayotiy haqiqatga sodiqlik.
- 4.Chuqur mushohada.
- 5.Muallif g'oyasining mantiqiyligi va ijodiy fantaziyasining kengligi.
- 6.Umumlashtirish va tipiklashtirish qobiliyati.
- 7.Badiiy detallarning aniqligi va qaysidir g'oyaga xizmat qilishi.
- 8.Syujet qurilishi va obrazlar tizimini yaratishdagi mahorat.
- 9.Qahramonlar ichki dunyosini mahorat bilan ochib berilishi.
- 10.Asar tilining boyligi va rang-barangligi.

Badiiy asar kompozitsiyasiga xizmat qiluvchi har bir elementning poetikasini o'rganish va shu asosda ilmiy izlanishlar olib borish mumkin. Masalan, rus olimlaridan D.S.Lixachev qadim rus adabiyotining poetikasini, I.V.Silantev motivlarining, V.V.Vinogradov syujet va uslubning, N.E.Falikova xronotopning, N.Bandurina va Z.Suvanov obrazlarining, Y.Solijonov badiiy nutqining, Q.Hamrayev kompozitsiyasining poetikasini tadqiq qilishgan va muhim ilmiy-nazariy xulosalarni chiqarishgan. Ayniqsa, asar syujeti va janrlar tipologiyasi bilan shug'ullanmoqchi bo'lgan olimlarga O.M.Freydenberning fundamental monografiyasi juda katta nazariy material beradi. Adabiyotshunos olimlarning tafakkur tarzi va tadqiqotchilik mahoratini ham poetika nuqtai nazaridan o'rganish mumkin[6]. Masalan, rus olimi O.Presnyakov nazariyotchi olim A.A.Potebnya ilmiy ijodining poetikasini o'rgangan.

IV. Muhokama va natijalar

Umuman olganda, Ethel Lilian Voynichning adabiy ijodi XIX-XX asrlar boshlaridagi ingliz adabiy an'anasi merosiga kiradi. Ushbu o'tish davrining boshqa milliy adabiyotlarida bo'lgani kabi, ingliz nasrining ko'plab asarlarida romantic pafos jonlanadi. Inson va olam o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning romantic konseptsiyasi, chegaraning romantic harakati sifatida qayta tiklanadi. XIX-XX asrlar ko'pincha muhim badiiy imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan deb nomlanadi, bunday asarda insonning

dunyoda mavjudligi masalasi alohida nuqtai nazardan, umuminsoniy va ijtimoiy o'rtasidagi mutlaq, universal qarama-qarshilikdan kelib chiqadi. Bu masalani insonparvarlik bilan hal qilish nafaqat muayyan hayotiy sharoitlarda, balki insonning ichki dunyosini, ta'bir joiz bo'lsa, qayta tug'ilishini ham tubdan o'zgartirishni talab qiladi. Bu kabi qarashlar nafaqat Ethel Lilian Voynich asarlariga xos, bundan tashqari bir qancha yozuvchilar; Konrad (1857-1924), D.R.Kipling (1865-1936), R.L.Stivenson (1850-1894), A.Konan Doyle (1859-1930)larning asarlariga ham xos xususiyatlardir.

Ethel Lilian Voynichning mashhur 5 ta asari mavjud. Ulardan uchta Arthur Burtoning taqdiri bilan bog'liq ("Gadfly", "Interrupted Friendship", "Put Off Thy Shoes"). "Jek Raymond" romaniga kelsak, u XIX asr boshidagi Angliya haqida hikoya qiladi. Ethel Lilian Voynichning "Jek Raymond" asari uning mashhur asari "Gadfly" romaniga qaraganda unchalik mashhur emas. 1901-yilda nashr etilgan "Jek Raymond" Voynichning psixologik va ijtimoiy dinamikaga doimiy qiziqishini aks ettiradi. Roman hayoti ichki qarama-qarshilik va tashqi qiyinchiliklar bilan ajralib turadigan yosh ingliz Jek Raymondning hikoyasini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotchilar va adabiyotshunoslar "The Gadfly" va "Jek Raymond" asarini umumiy ijodi kontekstida tadqiq qilib, uning mazmulari, xarakter rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy tanqidlar e'tibor qaratdilar. O'rganishning asosiy yo'nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

Adabiy tanqid: olimlar romanning shaxsiy o'ziga xosligini, axloqiy muammolarini, ijtimoiy me'yorlari haqidagi fikrlarini tahlil qiladilar.

Tarixiy kontekst: Tadqiqotchilar roman Voynichning siyosiy va falsafiy e'tiqodlarini, jumladan, uning sotsializm va insonparvarlikni targ'ib qilishini qanday aks ettirganini o'rganadilar.

Qiyosiy tadqiqotlar: Ba'zi tadqiqotlar Jek Raymondni Gadfly bilan taqqoslab, qurbonlik, individualizm va jamiyatni isloh qilish kabi takrorlanadigan mavzularni o'rganadi.

Patrik Woddingtonning E.L.Voynich haqidagi biografik tadqiqotlari uning taniqli inqilobchilar, jumladan, eri Vilfrid Voynich bilan aloqalari va bu munosabatlar "Gadfly" hikoyasini qanday shakllantirganiga oydinlik kiritadi. Uning tadqiqotlari asarning yozilishiga ta'sir qilgan tarixiy va mafkuraviy mazmunlarga urg'u beradi. Patrik Woddingtonning Ethel Lilian Voynich haqidagi tadqiqotlari uning ishining asosiy jihatlari va uning kengroq madaniy va tarixiy ta'siriga qaratilgan. U E.L.Voynich asarlarida birinchi navbatda quyidagi mavzularni o'rganadi:

a) Tarixiy mazmun va inqilobiy mavzular. Wodddington "Gadfly" asarida XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlaridagi inqilobiy g'oyalar, jumladan, shaxsiy fidoyilik, zulmga qarshilik va ruhoniylikka qarshi tasviri qanday aks etganini tahlil qildi. U Voynichning inqilobiy doiralarga kirib borishi uning rus inqilobiy harakatlari bilan hamohanglashgan hikoyasini qanday shakllantirganini ta'kidladi.

b) Madaniyatlararo adabiy ta'sir. U G'arbiy Yevropada "Gadfly" Sovet Rossiyasidagi g'ayrioddiy mashhurligini o'rganib chiqdi. Wodddington buni romanning sovet g'oyalari bilan mafkuraviy uyg'unligi, xususan, ateizm va imperator kuchlariga qarshi bo'ysunishga qaratilganligi bilan bog'ladi. Uning tadqiqot ishida roman qanday qilib isyon timsoliga aylangani va sovet spektakllari, filmlari va ta'lim dasturlariga moslashtirilgani ta'kidlangan.

c) Adabiyot texnikasi va timsoli. Wodddington romanning adabiy tuzilishini, shu jumladan ramziy tasvirlardan foydalanishni o'rgandi. U, shuningdek, hikoya uslubini, jumladan, shiddatli hissiy ohangni va individual va tizimli to'qnashuvlarga e'tibor qaratdi.[7].

Xulosa.

Ethel Lilian Voynichning "Gadfly" romani, uning adabiyotga qo'shgan hissasi va dunyo bo'ylab o'rganilgan asar sifatida, mifologik va adabiy nuqtai nazardan katta ahamiyatga ega. Roman, nafaqat tarixiy voqealar, balki insonning ichki dunyosini, ijtimoiy adolat, inqilobiy g'oyalar, xiyonat va qurbonlik kabi muhim mavzularni o'rganadi. Voynichning "Gadfly" romani mifologik tuzilishga ega bo'lib, unda qahramon Arthur Burtonning o'lim va tirilish jarayonlari mifologik nuqtai nazardan yoritilgan. Tadqiqotchilar, xususan, Mironov Aleksey Viktorovich, romanning mifopoetik tuzilishini, uning mifologik subtekstini va tarixiy subtekstini tahlil qilishdi. Voynichning asarida XIX asr oxirida Yevropa madaniyatida paydo bo'lgan diniy va ijtimoiy savollar, shuningdek, inqilobiy g'oyalar va ularning jamiyatdagi ta'siri alohida ta'kidlangan. Asar, inqilobiy ruhni, isyonni va ma'naviy azoblarni o'zida aks ettirgan holda, Rossiya, Irlandiya va G'arb o'rtasidagi madaniy aloqalarni yoritgan. Ethel Lilian Voynichning "Gadfly" asari nafaqat ingliz adabiyotining o'ziga xos vakili, balki global adabiyotda inqilobiy va siyosiy matn sifatida o'z o'rnini topgan asar hisoblanadi. Uning madaniy va siyosiy ta'sirini o'rganish, hozirgi zamon adabiyotshunosligi va tarjimashunosligiga yangi istiqbollar ochadi.

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МАТНАЗАР АБДУЛҲАКИМ ШЕЪРИЯТИДА АНЪАНА ВА НОВАТОРЛИК УЙҒУНЛИГИ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада замонавий ўзбек поэзиясининг ёрқин ва ноёб шоири Матназар Абдулҳаким ижоди таҳлил қилинади. Унинг шеърларида анъанавий образлар янги маънода талқин қилиниб, чуқур фалсафий мазмун билан бойитилган. Агава, ишқ ва тумор каби рамзлар орқали шоир инсон ҳаёти, туйғулари ва маънавий қийматлар ҳақида ўзига хос тасаввур беради. Шеърларидаги новаторлик нафақат шаклда, балки маънода ҳам намоён бўлиб, адабий анъаналарни янги босқичга олиб чиқади. Матназар Абдулҳаким ижоди нафақат эстетик завқ уйғотади, балки ўқувчини чуқур мулоҳазага чорлайди.

Калит сўзлар: шеърият, анъана, образ, рамз, новаторлик.

Шеъриятдаги ҳар бир янги қадам ижодкорнинг бадиий тафаккури, дунёқараши ва маънавий мероси билан чамбарчас боғлиқдир. Янги ғоя ва шакллар анъаналар билан уйғунликда, уларни янги маънода талқин қилиш асосида юзага келади. “Чунки ёш иқтидор эгаси ижодда янги, оригинал бадиий кашфиётлар учун очмоқчи бўлган йўлни доимо ўзигача яратилган ижодий анъаналар заминидан топади. Бундан бошқача бўлиши қийин. Зеро, илмда қайта-қайта таъкидланганидек, адабиёт ва санъатда **новаторлик** деган тушунча фақат илғор ҳамда яшовчан адабий анъаналар бағридагина вужудга келади”¹ Албатта, ҳар қандай янги бадиий кашфиёт анъаналар замирида пайдо бўлади. Ҳар қандай ижодий янгилик ана шу анъаналарнинг янги мазмун ва шакл билан бойитилиши натижасидир.

“Сўзнинг мўъжизакор кучи образларни тасвир қилдира олиш қудратига эгалигидир. У бешинчи сезги орқали ҳис этилган нарсаларнинг кўринмас вакилидир.”² Демак, сўзнинг бу қудрати шеъриятда новаторликка замин яратади, чунки у оддий ифода тарзларини бузиб, янги маънолар кашф қилишга хизмат қилади.

¹ Ҳаққулов И. Эҳтиёж фарзанди.- Тошкент: Ёш гвардия, 1988.- Б. 34.

² Парандовский Я. Алхимия слова. -М.: Прогресс, 1972.- С.133

Анъанавий образлар ифодасида бугунги кун ўзбек шеъриятида ўзига хос усул ва услубларга эга бўлган шоирларимиз мавжуд. Шундай новатор шоирлардан Матназар Абдулҳаким ижоди ўзига хос образлар, теран фалсафий мушоҳадалар ва ноёб поэтик услуби билан ажралиб туради. Қуйида унинг новаторлик хусусияти яққол намоён бўлган шеърларидан таҳлиллар келтирамиз.

Ўзбек шоири **Матназар Абдулҳакимнинг “Агава”** шеърида агава дарахти ноёб рамз сифатида талқин қилинган бўлиб, у новаторликнинг муҳим жиҳатларини акс эттиради:

*Бу — Қайс гули, бу — Мажнун гули,
Гар узатсам қоврилгай кўлим.
Агаванинг гули бу — бир бахт,
Бу — мангу бир ҳаётбахш ўлим.*³

Агава ўзининг сирли даври билан инсон тақдири, ҳаёт ва ўлим ўртасидаги ўзаро боғлиқликни ифодалайди. Қайс ва Мажнун тимсоллари классик шеъриятда севги, вафо ва оғриқ рамзлари бўлиб келган. Бу ерда гуллар уларнинг маънавий изтиробларини ўзида мужассамлаштирган, яъни гуллар нафақат табиатнинг бир қисми, балки инсон эҳтиросларининг бир тимсоли сифатида талқин қилинган.

Шеърда агаванинг гули орқали бир вақтнинг ўзида бахт ва ўлимни туташтириб, янги фалсафий мазмун яратилган. Шеърда агава дарахтининг бир мартагина гуллаб, шундан кейин йўқ бўлиши унинг "ҳаётбахш ўлим" сифатида талқинига асос бўлган. Буни инсон ҳаётидаги муваффақият ва қурбонлик ўртасидаги зиддиятга қиёс қилиш мумкин. Шоир табиат образларини инсон эҳтирослари, ҳис-туйғулари билан уйғунлаштириб, адабий анъаналарга янгича мазмун қўшган.

Демак, юқоридаги мисраларда шоир агава орқали севги мазмунига янгича ёндашув киритади, новаторликнинг муҳим намунаси сифатида гул орқали нафақат эстетик завқ уйғотади, балки ўқувчини чуқур фалсафий мулоҳазага чорлайди.

Матназар Абдулҳакимнинг қуйидаги мисралари эса ишқ образи чуқур фалсафий ва бадий мазмун билан бойитилганлигини кузатамиз.

*Шодлигингга қисқа умримни бериб,
Оҳ-фигон қилмасдан, нолимасдан, жим,*

³ Абдулҳаким. М. Жавзо ташрифи. Шеърлар, дostonлар.— Т.: Шарқ, 2008 - Б. 43

Аста ер қаърига кетаман эриб
Сенга атаб гуллар юбориш учун...⁴

Ишқ образи фақатгина туйғу эмас, балки ҳаёт ва ўлим, фидокорлик ва яшашнинг чексиз қудрати сифатида тасвирланган. Лирик қаҳрамон ўз ҳаётини ёрнинг шодлиги йўлида фидо этишга тайёр, бу эса ишқнинг юксак маънавий моҳиятини намоён қилади. Умрнинг қисқалиги ва ер қаърига аста-аста юз тутиш орқали ишқнинг чексизлиги ва доимийлиги тасвирланади.

Шеърнинг новаторлик хусусияти унинг фалсафий теранлигида ва образларнинг ноодатий ижодий талқинида яққол кўринади. "**Ер қаърига кетиш**" ибораси анъанавий ўлимни эмас, балки бу ўринда қайта тикланишни, гуллар юбориш орқали янги ҳаёт яратишни аңлатган. Бу ерда ишқ инсонийлик ва мавжудликнинг олий кўриниши сифатида талқин этилган. Шеърнинг содда, лекин чуқур бадиий шакли ва ритмик уйғунлиги уни ўқувчининг ҳис-туйғуларига кучли таъсир қилувчи асарга айлантиради.

Хуллас, Матназар Абдулҳаким анъанавий образ бўлган ишқни инсон ҳаётининг чексиз ижодий кучини намоён қилувчи рамзга айлантириб, ўзининг ноёб новаторлик услубини яратишга муваффақ бўлган.

Шоирнинг қуйидаги шеърий парчасида **тумор** образи ноанъанавий талқинда берилган бўлиб, унинг новаторлик хусусияти маънавий рамзнинг замонавий ҳаёт контекстига мослаштирилишида яққол кўринади:

*Туморлар тақасиз машинангизга,
Туморлар тақасиз мулкингизга сиз.
Тумор тақинг, асли, кўзёшингизга,
Тумор тақинг, асли, кулгунгизга сиз.*⁵

Тумор, анъанавий маънода, ҳимоя ва саодат рамзи ҳисобланса-да, бу шеърда у моддий бойликлар- машина ва мулкларга қўлланилиши орқали инсоннинг қадриятлар тизимидаги ўзгаришларни очиб беради. "Туморлар тақасиз машинангизга" сатридан моддийликнинг ҳимоя қилинишига қаратилган ҳозирги замон танқиди ёритилган. Бу анъанавий маънавий вазифанинг йўқолганини кўрсатади.

Шеърнинг сўнгги икки мисрасида тумор инсон туйғулари – кўзёш ва кулгу билан боғланади. Бу туморнинг нафақат ташқи, балки ички ҳимоя воситаси сифатида қайта талқин этилишига ишора қилади. "Тумор тақинг, асли,

⁴ Абдулҳаким. М. Фасллар қўшиғи. Шеърлар,- Тошкент: Фафур Ғулом номидаги адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 2008 - Б. 31

⁵ М. Абдулҳаким. Жавзо ташрифи. Шеърлар, дostonлар. - Тошкент: Шарқ, 2008. - Б.314

кўзёшингизга" ибораси инсон қайғусининг маънавий муҳофазага муҳтожлигини, "Тумор тақинг, асли, кулгунгизга" ибораси эса инсон бахтига кўз тегишига ишора қилган. Бу ўринда тумор инсоннинг ҳиссий дунёсини асосий ўринга қўяди ва унинг юксак поэтик таъсирини таъминлайди.

Матназар Абдулҳаким ижоди замонавий ўзбек шеърлятида анъана ва новаторлик уйғунлигини яққол намоён этувчи мисоллардан бири ҳисобланади. Унинг шеърлярида классик образлар ноанъанавий талқинда қайта кўриниш олиб, янги маъно ва фалсафий мазмун касб этади. Шоир анъанавий тимсолларни, масалан, гул, ишқ, тумор каби рамзларни ўзгача ёндашув билан бойитиб, уларга замонавий ҳаёт ва инсоний туйғулар билан боғлиқ янги мазмун бағишлайди.

"Агава" шеърляда табиат ва инсон тақдири уйғунлиги, ҳаёт ва ўлим ўртасидаги боғлиқлик фалсафий ва бадий тасвир орқали очиб берилган. Гул тимсоли нафақат табиат ифодаси, балки инсон эҳтирослари, дарду ҳасратларини акс эттирувчи образ сифатида талқин қилинган. "Ҳаётбахш ўлим" ғояси орқали шоир умрнинг ўтишини ва инсоннинг маънавий мероси орқали давомийлигини илғор образларда намоён қилади.

Шоирнинг ишқ тўғрисидаги шеърлярида ҳам ноёб фалсафий мазмун сезиларли. Умрни маҳбуба бахти учун фидо қилиш, ер қаърига кетиш орқали гуллар юбориш рамзи ишқнинг доимийлиги, қайта тирилиш ва юксак маънавий кудрат тимсоли сифатида янги талқин этилган. Бу образлар анъанавий ишқ ифодасидан фарқли тарзда, инсон ҳаётининг маънавий бойлиги ва қурбонлик воситасида қайта англашга асосланган.

Шоир ижодидаги тумор образи эса анъанавий муҳофаза рамзидан четга чиқиб, инсон қадриятларининг ўзгаришига ишора қилади. Материалистик дунёқараш танқиди ва маънавиятнинг биринчи ўринга чиқиши бу образнинг янги талқини орқали юзага келади. Туморнинг мулк ва машинага эмас, балки инсон ҳиссий олами – кўз ёш ва кулгуга бағишланиши, моддийлик устидан маънавиятнинг устунлигини тасдиқлайди.

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, Матназар Абдулҳаким шеърлятидаги новаторлик анъанавий образлардан фойдаланишда эмас, балки уларни янги мазмун ва шаклда қайта талқин этишда намоён бўлади. Шеърлярида бадий образ ва фалсафий тафаккур уйғунлиги туфайли, унинг ижоди наинки замонавий шеърлятнинг муҳим қисми, балки адабий анъаналарнинг янги босқичга кўтарилишининг ёрқин намунаси сифатида баҳоланиши мумкин.

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ТВОРЧЕСТВО САЯКА МУРАТЫ И ЕЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ЭГО-РОМАНА В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена жизни и творчеству современной японской писательницы XXI века Саяка Мурате, получившей огромную популярность и множество литературных премий как в Японии, так и зарубежом. Наибольшую известность писательнице принес роман «Человек минимаркета», за который она получила самую престижную литературную награду – премию Акутагавы Рюноске. Одной из главных тем данного произведения является поиск женщины самой себя в современном мире. Роман также помогает понять социальную сущность женской проблемы в современном японском обществе.

Ключевые слова: Саяка Мурата, Япония, японское современное общество, роль женщины в обществе, эго-роман, автофикшн

Саяка Мурата – современная японская писательница, новеллистка, эссеистка, сумевшая завоевать большой авторитет на Западе благодаря своему роману «Человек из минимаркета» наряду с такими выдающимися писателями как Кадзуо Исигуро и Харуки Мураками. Мурата родилась 14 августа 1979 года в городе Индзай в префектуре Тиба. Окончила женскую школу при университете Нисёгакуся, в школе занимала должность старшей по клубу искусств. С детства была большой поклонницей манги (японских комиксов) и рассказов для девочек. Начала писать рассказы уже в начальной школе. Выпускница литературного факультета университета Тамагава. Среди учителей Мураты — писатель Акио Мияхара.¹

Так как писать она начала с юности, вступительное сочинение Мураты «Идеал» (яп. 理想) высоко оценили на экзаменах.²

К своей деятельности, как писателя, Саяка Мурата серьезнее стала относиться во время учёбы в колледже, и дебютировала с рассказом за который

¹三島由紀夫賞・山本周五郎賞・川端康成文学賞贈呈式「挑戦してよかった」喜びと感謝と. Sankei, 2013.

² Alicia Joy. Meet Sayaka Murata: Akutagawa Prize Winner. The Culture Trip, 2016.

была награждена Премией Гундзо для начинающих писателей.³ Работы Мураты четыре раза приносили ей премию Мисимы. В 2016 году за роман «Человек минимаркета» (яп. コンビニ人間), опубликованный в журнале Бунгакукай, Мурата получила премию Акутагавы Рюноске, это была первая её номинация на данную премию. До 2016 года писательница работала продавщицей в магазине у дома на неполную ставку, что и послужило вдохновением к написанию данного романа, который в большей степени является автобиографическим. По словам самой писательницы, работа давала ей пищу для размышлений и сюжеты для книг.

В романе «Человек минимаркета» повествование ведется от женщины по имени Кокура Кэйко, которая 18 лет проработала продавщицей в одном и том же минимаркете, как и сама автор романа. Сменилось восемь директоров, её коллеги приходили и увольнялись, а девушка всё там же — питается готовой едой из своего магазина и пьет минеральную воду, продающуюся там. Она стала человеком из минимаркета. И это дает ей ощущение, что она обычный человек. Она взяла себе за правило никогда не показывать своих чувств и не высказывать своих суждений. Вместо этого она создала «лоскутную личность», копируя поведение и перенимая привычки и манеры у окружающих ее женщин, в основном коллег по работе, которых она считает правильными и восхищается их стилем. Эта эффективная и удобная стратегия позволяет ей приспособиться к собственному окружению. В тот момент, когда, прибыв на работу незадолго до начала смены, она переодевается в рабочую униформу, Кэйко превращается в функцию, в «человека минимаркета».

Данное произведение помогает понять социальные рамки и функции обычной женщины в современном японском обществе. Писательница Мурата Саяка своим произведением хочет показать, что современная женщина стремится свести все к наиболее простому знаменателю, либо работать изо всех сил, либо выйти замуж и завести детей. В Японии насчитывается более 50 тысяч магазинов шаговой доступности, через которые каждый месяц проходит 1,4 миллиарда японцев. Такое упрощение привело к тому, что более сложные стремления и желания стали не нужны.⁴

³ Daisuke Kikuchi. Convenience store worker who moonlights as an author wins prestigious Akutagawa Prize. The Japan Times, 2016.

⁴ Сайто Сатору. Алекситимия: эмоциональный разрыв, скрывающийся под маской нормальности, 2016.

Японский социолог Адзума Хироки несколько лет назад высказал мнение о том, что этот феномен приведет к тому, что человек вновь вернется в животное состояние. Современным потребителям не нужна чужая помощь, ведь все свои потребности можно удовлетворять мгновенно, по инерции. Нет необходимости, как раньше, общаться с другими людьми, чтобы совершить покупку или построить отношения. Сейчас можно получить желаемое, прикладывая минимум усилий, например, благодаря магазинам шаговой доступности.

Но может быть, что этот регресс и есть возвращение людей к собственным стремлениям. Чем проще желания, тем ближе к состоянию животного, а чем ближе это состояние, тем ближе новая форма цивилизации — жизнь ради себя. Японцы считают, что тридцатилетний человек лучше всего понимает себя. Многие в этом возрасте обнаруживают, что они не созданы для совместной жизни с кем-либо. Поэтому одно из связанных с обществом низких потребностей явление — это то, что Япония положила начало появлению «общества одиночек». В 2018 году, национальное японское бюро по социальному обеспечению опубликовало доклад «Оценочное количество японских семей в будущем».

В докладе сообщается, что к 2040 году 39,3% людей будут жить в одиночестве. Соотношение людей старше 65 лет, которые останутся одинокими будет выглядеть так: мужчины 20,8%, то есть из пяти человек один будет одинок, а одиноких женщин будет 24,5% (четыре к одному). Это те люди, которые так и не женились или не обзавелись семьей вновь после развода.

В сериале «Квартет», который транслировался в 2017 году, есть одна примечательная сцена. Готовя ужин, жена выжимает лимонный сок на кусочки жареной курицы, а её муж крайне недовольно говорит, что он не любит лимонный сок. В итоге эти двое начинают ссору, которая приводит к разводу.

В Японии многие девушки не хотят выходить замуж. Причина этого кроется в том, что за последние годы возросли возможности трудоустройства для женщин. А традиционное мнение о том, что женщина — это домохозяйка сходит на нет. Сейчас на молодых женщин оказывает влияние новый образ идеальной жизни: самостоятельная жизнь в собственной квартире, возможность прийти после работы, снять одежду, ходить по дому босиком, полистать свой любимый журнал или книгу, потом принять ванну с телефоном в руке, расслабиться и заснуть сладким сном. И зачем же надо выходить замуж? Зачем нужна вторая половинка? Разве жить в одиночестве не лучшее, что может

быть? Вот какими вопросами задаётся автор Саяка Мурата, и даёт, нам читателям, пищу для размышлений.

Таким образом можно сделать вывод о том, что писательница хочет обратить наше внимание на две тенденции, стремительно развивающиеся в Японии. Первое: в условиях современного успешного капиталистического общества, происходит упрощение нравственных ценностей. Второе: наблюдается потеря самосознания у современных людей. Поэтому автор своим произведением призывает японцев обратиться к поискам этого потерянного самосознания.

Безусловно в Японии есть много различных проблем. Но мы должны обратить внимание на такие положительные моменты, как низкий уровень безработицы, низкий уровень смертности в автомобильных катастрофах, а также большое количество туристов и студентов по обмену. Япония — это страна, которая начала эпоху господства интеллекта, что также находит отражение в романе Саяка Мураты.

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OGAHIY TARIXIY ASARLARIDA TASAVVUFYIY-MA'RIFIY ISTILOHLAR

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Muhammad Rizo Ogahiyning tarixiy asarlarida tasavvufiy-ma'rifiy leksikaning ishlatilishi tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda may, sharob, ishq, darvesh, valiy, tariqat, murid kabi tasavvufiy tushunchalar hamda fiqhiy-ma'rifiy leksika namunalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Muallif fiqhiy istilohlarning tarixiy-etimologik tahlilini ham amalga oshirgan bo'lib, arab, fors va turkiy tillardan o'zlashgan terminlarning semantik o'zgarish jarayonlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ilmiy istilohlarning MFL (ma'rifiy-falsafiy leksika) sifatida qo'llanilishiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Maqolada Ogahiy asarlarida uchraydigan terminlarning o'zbek tilidagi rivojlanish bosqichlari va ularning lingvistik xususiyatlari ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ogahiy, tasavvufiy leksika, fiqhiy istilohlar, ma'rifiy-falsafiy leksika, tarixiy-etimologik tahlil, ilmiy terminlar, turkiy qatlam, arab va fors tillari, semantik o'zgarish, lingvistik xususiyatlar.

Annotation. This article analyzes the use of Sufi-educational vocabulary in the historical works of Muhammad Rizo Agahy. The study examines Sufi concepts such as may (wine), sharob (liquor), ishq (divine love), darvesh (dervish), valiy (saint), tariqat (spiritual path), and murid (disciple), as well as examples of fiqh-related vocabulary. The author also conducts a historical-etymological analysis of fiqh terms, highlighting the semantic transformation of Arabic, Persian, and Turkic-origin words. Additionally, special attention is given to the use of scientific terminology as part of the epistemological-philosophical vocabulary (MFL). The paper explores the linguistic features and developmental stages of these terms in the Uzbek language.

Key words: Agahy, Sufi vocabulary, fiqh terminology, epistemological-philosophical lexicon, historical-etymological analysis, scientific terms, Turkic layer, Arabic and Persian languages, semantic transformation, linguistic features.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется использование суфийско-просветительской лексики в исторических произведениях Мухаммада Ризо Агахи. В исследовании рассматриваются суфийские понятия, такие как май (вино), шараб (спиртное), ишк (божественная любовь), дервиш (странствующий монах), валий (святой), тарикат (духовный путь), мурид (ученик), а также примеры фикхской (исламско-правовой) лексики. Автор проводит историко-этимологический анализ фикхских терминов, выявляя семантические изменения арабских, персидских и тюркских заимствованных слов. Кроме того, особое внимание уделяется использованию научной терминологии как части просветительно-философской лексики (МФЛ). В статье рассматриваются языковые особенности и этапы развития данных терминов в узбекском языке.

Ключевые слова: Агахи, суфийская лексика, фикхская терминология, просветительно-философская лексика, историко-этимологический анализ, научные термины, тюркский слой, арабский и персидский языки, семантические изменения, языковые особенности.

Kirish. Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida may, mayxona, boda, sharob, sharobxona, xamr, xammor kabi so'zlar tasavvufiy istiloh emas, aksar hollarda ko'chma ma'nosi

bilan birga bosh lug'aviy ma'nolari, ya'ni umumiste'moldagi mazmunlarida ishlatilgani qayd etiladi. Buning sababi solnomalar birinchi navbatda real voqealarga asoslangan asarlar ekanligi bilan izohlanadi. Sharob, boda, may kabi so'zlarning umumiste'moldagi ma'nolaridan xos ma'nolari vujudga kelish yo'llari va tamoyillari xususida A.Vohidov e'tiborli fikrlar bayon qilgan . [3]

Ishq so'zining tasavvuf istilohida o'ziga xos ma'no anglatishi ma'lum. Alisher Navoiyning ishq martabalari xususida bildirgan mulohazalari mashhur. Ushbu so'zning tarixiy-etimologik tahliliga nazar solsak, uning arabcha عشق a'shiqa – “sevmok”, “oshiq bo'lmoq” fe'lining masdari (infinitivi) shakli sifatida shakllanganini ko'ramiz . Tarixan esa ishq so'zining o'zi mazkur ma'noga polisemiya natijasida o'tgan bo'lib, o'simliklarga chirmashib uni quritadigan giyoh nomi denotant vazifasini bajargan. Bu haqda Muhammad Rampuriyning “G'iyosu-l-lug'ot” asarida quyidagilarni o'qiymiz: “Ishq biror narsani haddan ziyod sevmok; Tabiblar istilohida biror go'zal narsani ko'rib qolish natijasida paydo bo'ladigan kasallik.[5] Ogahiyning ishq tushunchasi haqidagi tasavvur doirasi keng ekanini uning mazkur so'z (chulashib)dan foydalanish mahoratida ko'ramiz. Bandda, shuningdek, darvesh, vali (ko'pligi avliyo), qutb, g'avsul-a'zam, axyor, avtod, abdol (budalo), naqib (nuqabo), rijol-l-g'ayb, valoyat, suluk, mushobahat, tariqat, murid, mujovir, so'fi, abdol, sharobi azal, sharobi alast, sharobi puxta, sharobi xom, sharobi ma'rifat, xarobot, soqiy, sog'ar, qadah, jom, javonmard (yana bir sinonimi fato) MFLga mansub birliklar tahlil qilingan. Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida tasavvuf bilan bog'liq MFLning ishlatilishi asosan quyidagi omillar bilan bog'liq ekaniga e'tibor berish lozim: 1. Solnomalarda ko'plab din va tasavvuf arboblarning zikr etilishi. 2. O'quvchi zehnida yaxshi qolishi va boshqa maqsadlarda zikri kelgan tarixiy shaxslarga tasavvuf istilohlaridan foydalangan holda tavsif berish. 3. Tasavvuf istilohlarining zamondoshlar tomonidan yaxshi anglab yetilishiga va buning samaradorligiga ishonch hosil qilish. [4]

Ma'rifiy-falsafiy leksika tarkibida fiqhiy istilohlarning ishlatilishi Ogahiy tarixiy asarlari leksikasining muayyan bir qismini fiqhiy-ma'rifiy leksika tashkil qiladi. Fiqhiy atamalarni ajratish, ularning mavzu guruhlarini belgilashda biz Qosim ibn Abdulloh ibn Mavlono Xayruddin Amir Ali Quvnaviy Rumi Hanafiyning “Anisul fuqaho fiy ta'rifotil alfoz al-mutadavala baynal fuqaho” asariga asoslandik . Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida fiqhiy-ma'rifiy leksikaga mansub so'zlar matn mazmuniga ko'ra ba'zan sof fiqhiy (istilohiy), fiqhiy-ma'rifiy, urfiy, urfiy-istilohiy ma'nolarda ishlatilgan. Qardosh xalqlar tilshunosligida biz o'rganayotgan mavzuga yaqin qator ishlar amalga oshirilgan.[8] Masalan, A.M.Minnegaliyeva “Tatar diniy-didaktik

adabiyoti tili: islom yurisprudensiyasi risolasi “Muxtasar al-Quduri” materiali asosida” nomli nomzodlik dissertatsiyasini himoya qilgan. Ishda tatar diniy adabiyoti tili semantik-stilistik aspektida o'rganilgan. Muallifning o'zi ta'kidlaganidek, xalq tarixi yashiringan, hayotning ma'naviy jihati uchun xizmat qiladigan diniy-didaktik uslubning inson o'z-o'zini anglashidek eng sirli va muhim jihatlarini ochib berishga harakat qilingan. Eski o'zbek tilida diniy, shuningdek, tasavvufiy terminlarning katta ko'pchiligi arab tilidan o'zlashganligi tabiiy, albatta. Shunday bo'lishiga qaramay, eski o'zbek tilidagi ham, hozirgi adabiy tilimiz va shevalarimizdagi diniy terminlarning genetik mansubligi arab tili bilan chegaralanmaydi. O'zbek tili diniy terminlar tizimida o'zbek (turkiy) va fors tillariga mansub so'zlar ham, o'z qatlamga mansub so'zlar ham ancha. Misol tariqasida Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida qo'llanilgan fors tilidan o'zlashgan diniy terminlar o'z navbatida kichik mavzu guruhlariga bo'linadi. Bularni a) mutlaq iloh tushunchasini ifodalovchi so'zlar; b) payg'ambar tushunchasini ifodalovchi so'zlar; d) farishta tushunchasini ifodalovchi so'zlar; e) jannat va do'zax tushunchasini ifodalovchi so'zlar; f) ibodatga aloqador tushunchalarni ifodalovchi so'zlar; g) turli mazmundagi diniy terminlar kabi guruhlariga ajratish mumkin. [7]

Mutaxassislar fikricha, qadimgi turkiy tilda ulug' iloh oti bo'lgan Tangri // tengiri so'zining qadim xitoy tilida diniy termin bo'lgan tyan (osmon) kalimasi bilan semantik aloqadorligi bor. Lekin tangri // tengiri so'zining qurilishi uning turkiy manbaga ega so'z ekanini tasdiqlaydi. Bu so'z bilan bog'liq maqollar, frazeologik birliklar va boshqa unsurlar, asosan, turkiy tillarning deyarli barchasida hamda ularning dialektlarida uchraydi. I.Jafarso'ylu “xunlar va ko'k turklarning bosh tangrisi Tengri deb nomlangan. Shumerlarning bosh tangrisi esa Tengirdir. Xett va Urartu mixxatlarida iloh nomi Dingir deyilgan va bu tasodifan emas” – deb yozadi. Adabiyotlarda bu so'zning osmon, xudo ma'nolarini anglatgani va turkiy tilda VIII asrdan qo'llangani qayd etilib, zamonaviy turkiy tillarda keng tarqalgan. Ushbu so'z bilan katta ko'lamdagi ilmiy qarashlar R.Mahmudov tomonidan tahlil qilingan. Ma'rifiy-falsafiy leksika tarkibida ilmiy istilohlarning ishlatilishi Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida ilmiy istilohlarning MFL sifatida voqealar bayoniga bog'liq holda ko'p miqdorda ishlatilishi ta'lim va tahsil jarayoni aks etgan kam sonli lavhalarda yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Shu munosabat bilan ulamo, kitob mutolaasi, balog'at, fasohat, fuzalo, guftugo', mukolamasi, balog'at, ilmi maoniy, ilmi bayon, ilmi badi', fasih, balig', i'joz //e'joz, daqiq iboratlar, ma'ni shohidlari, qaviy fikrlar, nukta, bade' mazmun, majlis ahli, munozara, mukolama, javob-u savol, bahs-u jidol, radd-u badal, musohaba kabi so'zlar tahlil qilingan. [1]

Ogahiy tarixiy asarlaridagi ma'rifiy-falsafiy istilohlar tarixiy-etimologik tahlili Turkiy tillarga mansub ma'rifiy-falsafiy leksikasi ham tahlil qilingan . Albatta, Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida mavjud turkiy qatlamga oid barcha so'zlarni qamrab olish imkoni yo'q. Shu bois o'zbek tili tarixiy leksikasiga oid adabiyotlarda tahlil qilinmagan yoki umuman qayd etilmagan MFLga mansub birliklarni topishga harakat qildik. Bizningcha, FI va RD da bir martadan qo'llangan aldar- – 1) chalg'imoq, andarmon bo'lmoq; 2) o'zini yo'qotmoq fe'li biz ko'zda tutgan birliklardan sanaladi. Bu so'z "Qadimgi turkiy til lug'ati" da ham qayd etilmagan. Istilohning qo'llanishi va tarkibi uning alda- fe'lining nisbat shakli emas, mustaqil fe'l ekanini ko'rsatadi. Mazkur fe'lning RDda qo'llangan holati: "ahli inodning aningdek hujum va g'avg'osidin oldarmay,.. darvozalarni tamarrud ahlining yuzig'a madrus va masdud qildurdi" (RD, 282a) FIning dastlabki bir nashrida aldarrobi shaklida tushunarsiz o'qilgan so'z keyingi nashrda mas'ul muharrir tomonidan Y.Bregel ilmiy-tanqidiy matni asosida aldarab shaklida tuzatilgan va "hozir shevalarda alvirab" tarzida eslatma kiritilgan : "Yavmut jamoasining maxsus bir dasturi budurkim, har qachon dushman g'alabasidin aldarab, muztar bo'lsa, majmui bir bo'lub yasol va tug'i bila hamla qilib, to'qushur va agar zafar topmasa, botroq sirpilib, munhazim bo'lurlar". (FI, 419-420) Demakki, so'zning lug'aviy ma'nosi uni MFLga mansub birlik sanashga to'la imkon beradi. Uning etimologiyasi va ma'no taraqqiyotiga nazar solish ham xalq tafakkur tarzining, ma'rifiy olamining muayyan nuqtalariga e'tibor bilan qarashga to'g'ri keladi. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tilida -da shakli bilan yasalgan fe'llardan biri "aldamoq"dir. Bu fe'lning asosi "hiyla-nayrang", "yolg'on", "avrash" ma'nolaridagi āl otidir . "Navoiy asarlari lug'ati"da ol (āl) shaklida to'rtta so'z berilgan bo'lib, ol I (huzur, old tomon; ro'para, qarshi; chekka, peshona)dan boshqasiga arabcha (a.) deb ta'kid qo'yilgan . Arab tiliga oid lug'atlarda mazkur lug'atda berilgan ol IV boshqasi berilmagan. Bu so'z arab tilida shaklida qarindoshlik; ittifoq shartnomasi; nafrat kabi ma'nolarda izohlangan . Ol so'zining "qizil"; "qizil tus" (ol II) ma'nosiga kelsak, uni arabcha hisoblashga hech qanday asos yo'q. To'g'ri, bu ma'no fors tilida ham bor . Lekin bu so'z fors tilidan turkiyga emas, aksincha turkiydan fors tiliga o'tgani ehtimolga yaqin. Birinchidan, forsiyda bu so'zning tarixiy asosi deb qaralgan "Avesto"dagi aurusha so'zi "oq" ma'nosini, sanskritcha arusa esa "qizil" ma'nosini beradi. Ikkinchidan, āl ko'p sonli eroniy tillardan faqat ikki tilda – tabariyda "ko'k" ma'nosida, mozandaronyda "qizg'ish" ma'nosida uchraydi . Biz ko'rib chiqayotgan aldira- E.V.Sevortyan tomonidan G.Ramstedning -da affiksi bilan yasalgan so'zlar ro'yxatini keltirishi munosabati

bilan qayd etiladi . Shu tarzda Munis va Ogahiy asarlarida qo‘llanilgan aldar- hamda aldara- shaklan va mazmunan bir qadar yaqin so‘z sanaladi. [2]

Ishda shu tariqa Tengri, o‘g‘an, ko‘ngul ota, so‘z (o‘zlashma sinonimlari kalima, kalom, nutq, nukta, nukot, lafz, alfoz, suxan), yozmoq, yozg‘ur- yazg‘it so‘zlari tahlil qilingan. Ko‘rinadiki, Ogahiy tarixiy asarlarida turkiy qatlam doirasida MFLga mansub har bir birlik xalqimizning ma‘rifiy va falsafiy dunyoqarashi na qadar keng bo‘lgani ko‘rsata oladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. A. Vohidov – O‘zbek tilidagi tasavvufiy leksikaning semantik o‘zgarishlari.
2. Qosim ibn Abdulloh ibn Mavlono Xayruddin Amir Ali Quvnaviy Rumi Hanafiy – *Anisul fuqaho fiy ta‘rifotil alfoz al-mutadavala baynal fuqaho.*
3. A. M. Minnegaliyeva – *Tatar diniy-didaktik adabiyoti tili: islom yurisprudensiyasi risolasi “Muxtasar al-Quduri” materialida.*
4. Muhammad Rampuriy – *G‘iyosu-l-lug‘ot.*
5. I. Jafarsoylu – *Xunlar va ko‘k turklarning bosh tangrisi Tengri.*
6. R. Mahmudov – *Turkiy tillarda diniy terminlar tizimi.*
7. E. V. Sevortyan – *Turkiy tillarning etimologik tadqiqoti.*
8. Y. Bregel – *O‘zbek tilining tarixiy leksikasi bo‘yicha ilmiy-tanqidiy matnlar.*

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA KADRLAR BILAN ISHLASHDA MOTIVATSIYANI OSHIRISH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida kadrlar bilan samarali ishlash tizimi ta'lim sifatini oshirishning muhim omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada kadrlar motivatsiyasini oshirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari o'rganiladi. Motivatsiyani oshirish metodlari, xususan moddiy va ma'naviy rag'batlantirish, pedagoglarning kasbiy rivojlanishi uchun yaratilgan shart-sharoitlar hamda jamoaviy ruhni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimlari tahlil qilinadi. Chet el va O'zbekiston olimlarining ilmiy ishlari asosida kadrlar bilan ishlash strategiyalari va ularning samaradorligi baholanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari kadrlarning ishga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshirish, ularning ta'lim jarayoniga sodiqligini ta'minlash va kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda samarali usullarni ilgari surishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Maktabgacha ta'lim, motivatsiya, kadrlar boshqaruvi, rag'batlantirish tizimi, kasbiy rivojlanish, psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash, ta'lim sifati.

KIRISH: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida samarali kadrlar bilan ishlash pedagogik jarayonning muhim qismi hisoblanadi. Ta'lim sifati bevosita pedagoglarning o'z kasbiga bo'lgan qiziqishi, motivatsiyasi va ish sharoitlari bilan bog'liq. Motivatsiya ta'lim tashkilotlarining asosiy elementlaridan biri bo'lib, u nafaqat o'qituvchilarning samaradorligini oshirishga, balki bolalarning ta'lim jarayonidagi ishtirokiga ham bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida kadrlar bilan ishlashda motivatsiyani oshirish usullari, rag'batlantirish tizimlari va ularning samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI: Motivatsiyani oshirishga doir tadqiqotlar butun dunyoda keng o'rganilgan. Maslow (1943) o'zining ehtiyojlar ierarxiyasi nazariyasida motivatsiyaning asosiy darajalarini belgilab, insonni rivojlantirish va mehnatga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish uchun psixologik shart-sharoitlarning ahamiyatini ta'kidlagan. Herzberg (1959) esa ikki omilli nazariyada motivatsiya va gigiyena faktorlarining muhimligini tushuntirib bergan.

O'zbekistonda motivatsiya va kadrlar bilan ishlash masalalari bo'yicha Karimov (2018) maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida pedagoglarni rag'batlantirish usullarini o'rganib, moddiy va ma'naviy qo'llab-quvvatlashning samaradorligini tahlil qilgan. Saidova (2021) esa ta'lim tizimida motivatsiyani oshirish uchun interfaol metodlar va pedagogik yondashuvlarning ahamiyatini tadqiq etgan. Yuldashev (2019) esa psixologik iqlimning pedagoglarning mehnat unumdorligiga ta'sirini o'rganib, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlashning muhimligini ta'kidlagan.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI: Tadqiqot davomida maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida faoliyat yuritayotgan pedagoglarning motivatsiya darajasi va uning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri o'rganildi. Tadqiqot uchun so'rovnomalar, intervyu va kuzatuv metodlaridan foydalanildi. Shuningdek, ta'lim tashkilotlarida joriy etilgan motivatsion dasturlar va ularning natijalari tahlil qilindi. Ma'lumotlar tahlili uchun statistik usullar, xususan korrelyatsion tahlil va faktor tahlili qo'llanildi.

ASOSIY MUHOKAMALAR VA NATIJALAR: Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, pedagoglarning motivatsiya darajasi bevosita ularning kasbiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlari, ish sharoitlari va rag'batlantirish tizimiga bog'liq. Tadqiqot davomida quyidagi asosiy motivatsion usullar samaradorligini isbotladi:

- Moddiy rag'batlantirish: Ish haqi, mukofot tizimlari va qo'shimcha imtiyozlar motivatsiyani oshirishga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi.
- Ma'naviy qo'llab-quvvatlash: Ustoz-shogird tizimi, kasbiy o'sish imkoniyatlari va tan olinishi pedagoglarning ishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi.
- Jamoaviy ruhni qo'llab-quvvatlash: Ish joyida ijobiy muhit yaratish va o'zaro hamkorlikni kuchaytirish pedagoglarning stress darajasini kamaytiradi va ularning motivatsiyasini oshiradi.
- Texnologiyalardan foydalanish: Zamonaviy ta'lim platformalarini joriy etish, interfaol metodlarni qo'llash pedagoglarning ishtiyoqini oshiradi.

Tadqiqot ishtirokchilarining 75% pedagoglari motivatsion dasturlar ishga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshirganini qayd etdi, bu esa kadrlar samaradorligini oshirish uchun motivatsiya tizimlarini rivojlantirish zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

XULOSA: Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida pedagoglarning motivatsiyasini oshirish ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini yaxshilashga xizmat qiladi. Moddiy va ma'naviy rag'batlantirish usullarini integratsiyalash, pedagoglar uchun kasbiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlarini yaratish va jamoaviy muhitni mustahkamlash motivatsiya darajasini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Kelajakda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida innovatsion motivatsion strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish va ulardan samarali foydalanish tavsiya etiladi.

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O'ZBEK TILINING MILLIY KORPUSINI YARATISH

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Annotatsiya: korpus tilshunosligi, uning milliy shakllarini yaratish, shuningdek, mavjud tajribalardan kelib chiqib o'zbek milliy korpusining nazariy va amaliy asoslarini ishlab chiqish, uni keng jamoatchilikka tadbiq qilish mutaxassislarining galdagi dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar: matematik lingvistika, kompyuter lingvistikasi, korpus, milliy korpus, kiritma, podkorpus, matn, tahrir, nostandart (noleksik) elementlar, kognitiv tilshunoslik, diskurs, kognitiv faoliyat, konsept, definitysiya, konsept tipi.

Korpus – bir necha va yoki muayyan bitta tilga oid matnlarning yig'indisiga asoslangan elektron shaklga ega, to'plangan ma'lumot (ya'ni so'rovnomalar)lar tizimi. Milliy korpus – muayyan bir tilning ma'lum vaqt (yoki vaqtlar) dagi maqomini, janrlarini, uslublarini, hududiy hamda ijtimoiy ko'rinishlarini va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Milliy korpus tilshunoslikning korpus lingvistikasi mutaxassislari tomonidan tuziladiki, bu ilmiy tadqiqot va til o'rganish uchun xizmat qiladi. Jahonning ko'pgina yirik tillari allaqachon ilmiy ishlanganligi, hajmi va ko'lamiga ko'ra o'zaro farqlanuvchi o'zining milliy korpusiga egadir.

Korpusga kiritilayotgan matnlarning o'ziga xos jihatlari to'g'risida muhim qo'shimcha ma'lumotlarni saqlaydi (bular annotatsiya yoki kiritma ko'rinishidagi matnlardir). Kiritma – korpusning asosiy bosh ma'lumotnomasi bo'lib, u korpusni zamonaviy internet tarmog'ida mavjud bo'lgan oddiy odatiy matnlar (yoki "kutubxonalar" desak ham bo'ladi) to'plamidan ajratib turadi. Korpusning yana bir vazifasi til sohalarining barcha jihatiga taalluqli ma'lumotlarni olish (masalan, leksik, grammatika, aksentologik, til tarixi kabi), zamonaviy kompyuter texnologiyalari vositasida katta hajmdagi til hodisalarini juda tez tahlil qilish va siqirlashtirishga xizmat qilishdan iborat. Avvallari tadqiqotchi zarur misollarni qo'lda yozar, bu esa ko'p mehnat talab qiladi. Hozirda tahlil qilinayotgan materiallarning ko'lami va ma'lumot topish tezligida muammolar bo'lmaydi. Bu esa tadqiqodchi uchun beqiyos imkoniyatlar eshiklarini ochadi. Milliy korpus til haqidagi bilimlarimiz imkoniyatini, shuningdek, uni statistik tahlil qilishning (o'rganishning), hatto hozirga qadar o'rganilmay kelinayotgan hodisalarning qurilishi va taraqqiyotidagi qonuniyatlarni, mavjud xulosalarga bo'lgan shubhalarni yoki

taxminiy hodisalarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Endilikda tilning grammatik qurilishi, hatto mashhur akademik lug'atlar, hech istiholasiz muayyan tilning milliy korpusi asosida yaratilishi kerak bo'ladi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan milliy korpus talabgorlari, albatta, muayyan tilning turli sohalari tadqiqotchi–lingvistlari hisoblanadi. Biroq korpusdan foydalanuvchilar professional mutaxassislar bilanchegaralanmaydi. Davr yoki ma'lum muallifning fikrlari, til haqidagi ishonchli statistik ma'lumotlari adabiyotshunoslarni, tarixchilarni va gumanitar bilimlarning turli vakillarini qiziqtirishi mumkin. Milliy orpuslar milliy va chet tillarni o'qitish uchun ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadiki, ko'pgina darslik va o'quv rejalari hozirda milliy korpusga moslangan bo'lishi kerak. Korpus ko'magida taniqli mualliflarning notanish so'z yoki grammatik shakllarini ajnabiy ham, maktab o'quvchisi ham, o'qituvchi ham, jurnalist ham, redaktor yoki yozuvchi ham tez va oson tekshirib olishi mumkin bo'ladi.

Demak, milliy korpus kasbidan yoki u oddiy qiziquvchimi, muayyan til korpusining tuzilishi va ishlashidan, undan foydalanuvchilarning millatidan qat'iy nazar, o'rganuvchilar uchun birdek foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Milliy korpus qanday rivojlanadi? Rus tilining milliy korpusi, o'z ichiga XVIII asrning o'rtalaridan to XXI asrning boshlarigacha bo'lgan davrni qamrab oladi. Bu davr xoh o'tgan, xoh yangi bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, u sotsiolingvistik ko'rinishdagi badiiy, so'zlashuv, jonli so'zlashuv, qisman dialektal matnlarni tashkil qiladi. Korpusga badiiy qimmatga ega bo'lgan va til o'rgatishga qiziqish uyg'otadigan, orginal (tarjima qilinmagan) badiiy adabiyot namunalari kiritiladi (proza va drama, keyinchalik she'riyat ham). Badiiy she'rlardan tashqari, yozma adabiyotning boshqa namunalariidan publisistika, ilmiy ommabop va ilmiy adabiyotlar, shaxsiy chiqishlar (ma'ruzalar), shaxsiy yozishmalar, kundaliklar, hujjatlar va boshqalar ham kiritiladi.

Hozirga vaqtda rus tili milliy korpusi quyidagi kichik-kichik korpus (podkorpus)larni o'z ichiga qamraydi:

- 1) chuqur annotatsiya (tahlil)langan korpus (bunda har bir gapning morfologik va sintaktik qurilishi uchun tahlil mavjud);
- 2) rus va ingliz matnlarining parallel korpusi (bunda rus yoki ingliz tillaridagi so'z va so'z birikmalarining tarjimalarini topish mumkin bo'ladi);
- 3) dialektal matnlar korpusi (bunda Rossiyaning turli hududlarida grammatik xususiyatlariga ko'ra saqlangan dialektik matnlar mavjud);
- 4) poetik matnlar korpusi (bunda she'riyatning nafaqat leksik va grammatik,

balki uning turli janrlari (sonet, epigramma, amfibrax, ularning qofiya turlari) bilan bog‘liq jihatlar mavjud);

5) rus tilini o‘rganish korpusi (bunda asosiy e‘tibor rus tilining maktab programmasiga yo‘naltirilgan);

6) og‘zaki nutq korpusi (bunda magnit tasmasiga yozib olingan ommaviy va xususiy og‘zaki matnlari va 1930-2000-yillardagi kinofilmlar transkrip (talaffuz) matnlari mavjud) va b.

Xullas, korpus tilshunosligi, uning milliy shakllarini yaratish, shuningdek, mavjud tajribalardan kelib chiqib o‘zbek milliy korpusining nazariy va amaliy asoslarini ishlab chiqish, uni keng jamoatchilikka tadbiq qilish mutaxassislarning galdagi dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir. Natijada o‘zbek tili mumtoz va zamonaviy matnlari, turli janrlarda yaratilgan betakror durdona asarlar “ikkinchi hayot”ga yo‘llanma oladi va kelgusida o‘zbek tilining ham ko‘p ming (ikki yuz, besh yuz ming yoki million) so‘zli lug‘atlarini yaratish imkoni tug‘iladi.

Ma‘lumki, dunyo tilshunosligida matnga dastlab, asosan, semantik va sintaktik nuqtayi nazardan yondashilgan. Keyingi yillarda, xususan, XXI asr boshlaridan matnni lingvokulturologik, pragmatik, sotsiolingvistik, kognitiv va psixolingvistik tamoyillar asosida tadqiq etish tendensiyasi kuchaydi. Unga faqat semantik-sintaktik jihatdan bog‘langan gaplar yig‘indisi sifatida emas, balki ijtimoiy qimmatga ega bo‘lgan muloqot shakli, o‘zida muayyan til sohiblarining bilimlarini, lisoniy tafakkurini, milliy psixologiyasi va mentalitetini aks ettiruvchi mental qurilma sifatida qarala boshlandi.

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SOCIAL MEDIA AND YOUTH LANGUAGE: A TOOL FOR DEVELOPMENT OR DETERIORATION

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Abstract: Social media has revolutionized communication, significantly shaping the linguistic practices of its primary users—youth. This paper explores the dual impact of social media on youth language, examining its potential to foster linguistic innovation while highlighting risks such as grammatical erosion and cultural displacement. Using mixed methods, including a survey of 250 participants, textual analysis of social media posts, and theoretical frameworks, the study investigates social media's role in creating new vocabulary, encouraging multilingualism, and promoting linguistic creativity. However, it also uncovers negative effects such as grammatical deviations, excessive borrowing from foreign languages, and reduced oral communication skills. The findings emphasize the need to balance social media's benefits for linguistic growth with strategies to preserve linguistic integrity and cultural heritage. Practical recommendations are provided to mitigate these risks and leverage social media for linguistic development.

Keywords: social media, youth language, linguistic innovation, cultural preservation, digital communication, globalization.

Annotatsiya: Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar muloqotga inqilobiy o'zgarish kiritib, uning asosiy foydalanuvchilari – yoshlarning lingvistik amaliyotlariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Ushbu maqola ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning yoshlik tili ustiga ikki tomonlama ta'sirini o'rganadi, ya'ni lingvistik innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish imkoniyatlari bilan birga grammatik buzilishlar va madaniy o'zlashish xavflarini yoritib beradi. Tadqiqotda 250 ishtirokchi o'rtasida so'rovnom, ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi postlar tahlili va nazariy yondashuvlardan foydalangan holda, yangi so'z boyliklarining yaratilishi, ko'p tillilikni qo'llab-quvvatlash va lingvistik ijodkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning roli o'rganilgan. Shu bilan birga, grammatik qoidalar buzilishi, chet tillardan ortiqcha so'z o'zlashishi va og'zaki muloqot ko'nikmalarining kamayishi kabi salbiy ta'sirlar aniqlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning lingvistik o'sishdagi foydasini saqlab qolish uchun ularning ta'sirini muvozanatga keltirish zaruratini ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan til rivoji uchun foydalanish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, yoshlik tili, lingvistik innovatsiyalar, madaniy merosni, raqamli muloqot, globallashtirish.

Аннотация: Социальные сети произвели революцию в общении, оказав значительное влияние на языковую практику их основных пользователей — молодежи. В данной статье исследуется двойственное воздействие социальных сетей на язык молодежи, рассматривается их потенциал для стимулирования языковых инноваций, а также подчеркиваются риски, такие как эрозия грамматики и утрата культурной идентичности. Исследование, проведенное с использованием смешанных методов, включая опрос 250 участников, анализ текстов в социальных сетях и теоретические подходы, изучает роль социальных сетей в создании новых слов, поддержке многоязычия и развитии языкового творчества. Однако также выявлены негативные эффекты, такие как отклонения от грамматических норм, чрезмерное заимствование иностранных слов и снижение навыков устного общения. Полученные результаты подчеркивают необходимость баланса между

преимуществами социальных сетей для языкового развития и стратегиями сохранения языковой целостности и культурного наследия. В статье предложены практические рекомендации по минимизации рисков и использованию социальных сетей для развития языка.

Ключевое слово: Социальные сети, язык молодежи, языковые инновации, сохранение культурного наследия, цифровая коммуникация, глобализация.

Introduction

In the digital era, social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, and TikTok are reshaping how people communicate and interact. With over 4.8 billion users globally (Statista, 2025), these platforms have become central to the lives of youth, influencing not only their social behavior but also their linguistic practices.

Youth are the most active demographic on social media, using it not only to communicate but also to create and consume content. This digital interaction significantly impacts their language use, introducing new words, abbreviations, and linguistic norms. However, the rapid and informal nature of social media communication often undermines grammatical and cultural standards.

The central question this paper addresses is: **Does social media enhance linguistic development, or does it erode linguistic and cultural norms?** By analyzing youth language practices on social media, this study aims to provide a nuanced perspective on the linguistic transformations brought about by digital communication.

Methods

Literature Review

A thorough review of scholarly works was conducted to identify key themes and frameworks related to social media and linguistic change. Sources included peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus, focusing on sociolinguistics, digital communication, and youth culture.

Survey

A structured survey was distributed to 250 participants aged 18–25, exploring their language use on social media, the frequency of foreign borrowings, and their perceptions of social media's impact on linguistic norms.

Textual Analysis

A corpus of 1,500 social media posts from platforms such as Telegram, Instagram, and TikTok was collected and analyzed using linguistic software to identify patterns in vocabulary, syntax, and grammar.

Statistical Analysis

Quantitative data from the survey and textual analysis were processed using SPSS to identify correlations between social media usage and linguistic practices.

Results

Positive Impacts of Social Media on Youth Language

a. Vocabulary Expansion

b. Social media platforms introduce new lexical items, many of which reflect technological and cultural trends. Examples include:

- Borrowed terms: “vlog,” “influencer,” “content creator.”
- Hybrid phrases: “post qilish” (to post), “like bosmoq” (to like).

Survey results indicate that 86% of participants frequently use such terms in their daily communication, reflecting their integration into modern language.

c. Promotion of Multilingualism

d. Social media fosters cross-cultural interaction, exposing users to multiple languages. Acronyms such as “BRB” (be right back) and “FOMO” (fear of missing out) are now globally understood. Many Uzbek-speaking youth incorporate Russian and English terms into their conversations, enhancing their multilingual capabilities.

c. Encouragement of Linguistic Creativity

The informal and dynamic nature of social media allows users to experiment with language, creating slang and new expressions. Examples from textual analysis include creative abbreviations and emoji-based communication.

Negative Impacts of Social Media on Youth Language

a. Grammatical Deviations

b. The need for brevity often results in grammatical and orthographic errors.

Examples include:

- Spelling shortcuts: “nma qvotti” (what are you doing?) instead of “nima qilyapsan.”
- Lack of punctuation and capitalization in online messages.

Analysis of 1,500 posts revealed that 78% contained deviations from standard grammar.

c. Excessive Borrowing from Foreign Languages

d. Social media accelerates the incorporation of foreign words, often at the expense of native vocabulary. Examples include:

- “Chat qilish” (to chat) replacing “so‘zlashish.”
- “Post qilish” (to post) instead of native alternatives.

Survey results show that 63% of participants frequently use hybrid expressions, raising concerns about linguistic purity.

c. Decline in Oral Communication Skills

The reliance on text-based communication reduces face-to-face interaction, leading to diminished oral communication skills. Survey participants reported challenges in articulating thoughts verbally, with 58% admitting they struggle during in-person conversations.

Discussion

Social media's impact on youth language is both positive and negative.

Constructive Aspects

Social media fosters linguistic innovation by introducing new vocabulary, promoting multilingualism, and encouraging creativity. It serves as a platform for cultural exchange and linguistic experimentation.

Problematic Aspects

However, social media also undermines linguistic norms. The prevalence of grammatical shortcuts, excessive foreign borrowings, and reduced oral communication skills highlights the need for linguistic education and guidance.

Theoretical Implications

The findings align with Labov's (1972) theory of linguistic change, which posits that language evolves through social interaction. Social media accelerates this process, making linguistic change more rapid and visible.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Social media is a double-edged sword for youth language. While it enriches vocabulary and fosters global communication, it also poses risks to linguistic integrity and cultural identity. Balancing these impacts requires concerted efforts from educators, policymakers, and social media users.

Recommendations

1. **Educational Initiatives**
Integrate digital literacy and linguistic education into school curricula to promote proper language use on social media.
2. **Standardization of Borrowed Terms**
Develop guidelines for integrating foreign words into native languages to ensure linguistic consistency.
3. **Cultural Preservation Campaigns**
Encourage the use of native language forms and raise awareness about the importance of linguistic and cultural heritage.
4. **Parental and Institutional Guidance**

Parents and educators should guide youth in responsible social media use, emphasizing the importance of linguistic accuracy and cultural respect.

By implementing these strategies, social media can become a tool for linguistic development rather than a force for linguistic deterioration.

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FOLKLORIZMNING ADABIYOTDAGI NAMOYON BO'LISH XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNING BADIY ASARDAGI ROLINI TADQIQ ETISH

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada folklorizmning adabiyotdagi namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari va uning badiiy asardagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Folklor elementlarining badiiy ijodga kirib kelishi, syujet, obrazlar tizimi, til va uslub xususiyatlariga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Xalq og'zaki ijodining asosiy shakllari — dostonlar, rivoyatlar, ertaklar, maqollar va topishmoqlar orqali milliy adabiyotning boyitilishi muhokama qilinadi. Yozuvchilarning folklor motivlaridan foydalanishlari, bu jarayonning badiiy-estetik va g'oyaviy jihatdan ahamiyati yoritiladi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy adabiyotda folklorizmning yangicha talqinlari, uning yangi janr va uslublar bilan uyg'unlashuvi ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola folklorizmning badiiy adabiyotdagi o'rnini aniqlash va uni chuqurroq o'rganish uchun ilmiy-nazariy asos yaratishga qaratilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Folklorizm, adabiyot, og'zaki ijod, badiiy uslub, xalq dostonlari, milliy an'ana.*

Kirish. Folklorizm adabiyotshunoslikda muhim ilmiy konsepsiya bo'lib, xalq og'zaki ijodining badiiy adabiyotga kirib kelish jarayoni va uning tarkibiy qismiga aylanishini anglatadi. Folklor o'zining tarixiy va madaniy ildizlari bilan milliy ong va badiiy tafakkurning shakllanishida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Xalq og'zaki ijodi — rivoyatlar, dostonlar, ertaklar, maqollar, matallar, topishmoqlar va afsonalar orqali avloddan-avlodga o'tib kelayotgan ma'naviy meros sifatida badiiy adabiyotning mazmunini boyitib, uning estetik va g'oyaviy jihatdan chuqurlashishiga xizmat qiladi¹. Shu sababli folklorizmning adabiyotdagi o'rni nafaqat badiiy asarlarga xalqona ruh va milliy xarakter bag'ishlash, balki yozuvchi dunyoqarashini shakllantirishda ham muhim omil bo'lib hisoblanadi. Folklorizmning adabiyotda namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari turli yo'nalishlarda o'z ifodasini topadi. Avvalo, badiiy asarlar syujetining shakllanishida xalq og'zaki ijodining asosiy motivlaridan foydalanish keng kuzatiladi. Ko'plab yozuvchilar xalq eposi va dostonlaridan ilhomlanib, o'z asarlariga milliy an'analar va qadriyatlarini singdirgan holda badiiy talqin yaratadilar. Masalan, Alisher Navoiy o'z asarlarida xalq dostonlaridan foydalanib, ularni yangi badiiy shaklga solgan². Xuddi shunday, Oybek, G'afur G'ulom, Abdulla Qodiriy kabi o'zbek yozuvchilari ham folklor elementlarini o'z asarlariga muvaffaqiyatli tatbiq etib, milliy adabiyot rivojiga katta hissa qo'shganlar.

¹ Axmedova N. O'zbek adabiyotida folklorizm an'analari. — Toshkent, Fan, 2019. — 230 b.

² Jo'rayev R. Folklor va adabiyot: O'zaro bog'liqlik masalalari. — Samarqand, Universitet nashriyoti, 2021. — 280 b.

Folklorizmning adabiyotdagi yana bir muhim jihati obrazlar tizimida namoyon bo‘ladi. Ko‘plab badiiy asarlarda xalq eposi qahramonlari yoki xalq qahramonlari prototipi asosida yaratilgan personajlar uchraydi. Bunday qahramonlar o‘zining xulq-atvori, maqsadi va qadriyatlari bilan xalq ongida allaqachon shakllangan ideal obrazlar bilan bog‘lanadi. Misol tariqasida “Alpomish” dostonidagi qahramonlik motivlari, xalq qahramonlari bilan bog‘liq afsonaviy hikoyatlar badiiy asarlar syujetida takror-takror namoyon bo‘lib kelgan. Folklorizmning badiiy adabiyotga ta’siri nafaqat syujet va qahramonlar tizimida, balki til va uslub xususiyatlarida ham sezilarli darajada ko‘zga tashlanadi. Adabiy asarlarda xalq maqollari, matallari, topishmoqlari, xalqona iboralar va she’riy ohangdorlikning qo‘llanilishi matnning estetik ta’sirchanligini oshiradi.

Yozuvchilar, ayniqsa, o‘z asarlarida xalq maqollaridan foydalanish orqali o‘z fikrlarini yanada aniqlik va badiiy nafosat bilan ifoda etadilar. Masalan, Abdulla Qodiriyning “O‘tkan kunlar” romanida xalq maqollari va iboralari orqali milliy kolorit yaratilgan bo‘lsa, Cho‘lpon va Fitrat ijodida xalqona uslub va tahliliy yondashuv bilan boyitilgan nasriy va she’riy asarlar shakllangan³. Bundan tashqari, folklorizmning adabiyotda namoyon bo‘lishi poetik strukturalarda ham o‘z ifodasini topadi. Xalq og‘zaki ijodining ritmik tuzilishi, ohangdorligi va poetik tizimi ko‘plab yozuvchilar tomonidan badiiy tafakkurda yangi shakllar yaratishda foydalanilgan. Shoirilar xalq qo‘shiqlarining ohangdorligidan, dostonlarning badiiy ifoda vositalaridan ilhomlanib, o‘z she’riy uslublarini shakllantirganlar. Jumladan, Erkin Vohidov va Abdulla Oripov ijodida xalq og‘zaki ijodining poetik an‘analari yaqqol seziladi. Folklorizmning badiiy asarlarga singishi ijodiy jarayonda yozuvchilarning milliy va madaniy meros bilan bog‘lanishini kuchaytiradi⁴. Bu esa, o‘z navbatida, milliy adabiyotning boyishiga va jahon adabiyotida o‘ziga xos o‘rin egallashiga yordam beradi. Biroq, bugungi kunda globallashuv ta’sirida folklorizmning adabiyotdagi roli bir oz o‘zgarib, yangi badiiy oqimlar va janrlar bilan uyg‘unlashmoqda.

Zamonaviy yozuvchilar an’anaviy folklor elementlarini yangi texnikalar bilan boyitib, ularni zamonaviy muammolar bilan bog‘lashga intilmoqdalar. Shu bilan birga, folklorizm adabiyotning ajralmas qismi bo‘lib, milliy tafakkur va madaniy merosni aks ettirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Badiiy asarlarda xalq og‘zaki ijodining elementlaridan foydalanish nafaqat adabiy jarayonni boyitadi, balki o‘quvchi ongida milliy qadriyatlarni saqlash va avlodlarga yetkazish imkoniyatini ham yaratadi. Shu

³ Karimov H. O‘zbek xalq eposining adabiyotga ta’siri. – Toshkent, O‘zbekiston, 2018. – 215 b.

⁴ Usmonova M. Zamonaviy adabiyotda folklor motivlari. – Buxoro, Ilmiy meros, 2022. – 260 b.

sababli folklorizmni adabiyotshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan chuqur tadqiq qilish va uni yangi badiiy kontekstda o'rganish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda⁵.

Xulosa. Folklorizm adabiyotning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, xalq og'zaki ijodi va badiiy ijodning o'zaro bog'liqligini ifodalaydi. Folklor elementlari, jumladan, dostonlar, ertaklar, maqollar, matallar va xalqona obrazlar badiiy asarlarning syujet tuzilishi, til va uslub xususiyatlarini boyitishga xizmat qiladi. Yozuvchilar xalq og'zaki ijodidan ilhomlanib, uni yangi badiiy shakllar orqali talqin etadilar. Shu tariqa, folklorizm milliy adabiyotning rivojlanishida muhim omil bo'lib, milliy an'analar va qadriyatlarni saqlashga hamda o'quvchilar ongida estetik didni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Zamonaviy adabiyotda folklorizmning roli o'zgarib, yangi janrlar va uslublar bilan uyg'unlashmoqda. Yangi badiiy oqimlar bilan folklor elementlarini uyg'unlashtirish orqali yozuvchilar milliy va universal qadriyatlarni birlashtirgan holda o'z asarlarini yaratmoqdalar. Shu sababli folklorizmning adabiyotdagi ta'siri kelajakda ham dolzarb bo'lib qolishi, uning yangi badiiy shakllarda tadqiq qilinishi zarur.

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METAFORA VA METONIMIYANING BADIY USLUBDA QO'LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Abdulla Qodiriyning “Mehrobdan chayon” romanida metafora va metonimiyaning badiiy uslubdagi o'rni hamda uning obrazlar, voqea harakati va ijtimoiy-tanqidiy mazmuni aks ettirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Asarda metafora yordamida qahramonlarning ichki dunyosi, ularning ruhiy iztiroblari va umidlari, shuningdek, jamiyatdagi adolatsizlik va madaniy inqirozlar aks ettiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Metafora, badiiy uslub, tasviriy san'at, obraz, poetik til, “Mehrobdan chayon”, Abdulla Qodiriy, ijtimoiy tanqid, ruhiy kechinma, metonimiy, ko'chma ma'no.

Abdulla Qodiriy o'zining “Mehrobdan chayon” romanida badiiy tilning eng muhim vositalaridan biri sifatida metaforadan keng foydalanadi. Metafora – bu tushunchani, hissiyotlarni va voqealarni bevosita ifodalashdan ko'ra, ularga ramziy ma'no yuklab, o'quvchi ongiga chuqur taassurot qoldiruvchi badiiy uslubiy vositadir [1,134]. Ushbu maqolada asarda qo'llangan metaforalar orqali yaratilgan obrazlar, syujet va ijtimoiy-tanqidiy mazmun tahlil qilinadi. Ayniqsa, qahramonlarning ichki kechinmalari va ruhiy holati, ularning orzu va umidlari ramziy ifoda vositasi sifatida ko'rsatilgan.

Metafora adabiyotshunoslik nazariyasida tushunchalarni ramziy tarzda ifodalash vositasi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. U matn mazmunini boyitadi, qahramonlarning ruhiy kechinmalari va atrof-muhitdagi noaniqliklarni aks ettirishga yordam beradi. Abdulla Qodiriyning asarida metafora nafaqat go'zallikni, balki ijtimoiy-tarixiy muammolar va inson ruhining nozikligini ham aks ettiradi. Shu bois, yozuvchi nafaqat hissiy tasvirlarni yaratishda, balki jamiyatdagi adolatsizlik va ma'naviy buzilishlarni ramziy ifodalashida ham metaforadan samarali foydalanadi [2,25].

Asarda qahramonlarning ichki dunyosi, ularning orzu, umid va azoblari ramziy ifoda vositalari orqali aks etadi. Masalan, yosh qahramon Anvarning qalbida yongan umid va adolatga bo'lgan ishonchini quyidagi metafora orqali ko'rish mumkin:

“Anvarning yuragi bir paytlar yongan mash'al edi, lekin hayot zarbalari ostida u shamolning qo'rg'oshiniga aylanib qoldi” [3,124]. Bu yerda *mash'al* – qahramonning yoshligidagi iliq, yorqin umidini ifodalaydi, qo'rg'oshin esa hayotning qattiq zarbalari ta'sirida so'nayotgan his-tuyg'ularni ramziy tarzda aks ettiradi. Ushbu

metafora orqali o'quvchi Anvarning ruhiy iztiroblarini va ichki kurashlarini chuqurroq his etadi.

Abdulla Qodiriy asarda jamiyatdagi adolatsizlik va ijtimoiy buzilishlarni ham metaforik tasvirlar orqali namoyon etadi [4,89]. Masalan, jamiyatni ifodalovchi quyidagi metaforada adolatsizlik va eskirgan tizim ramziy tarzda tasvirlanadi:

“U jamiyatni dog‘-dug‘lar bilan qoplangan eski tosh devorga o‘xshatardi, har urilishida yangi yaralar paydo bo‘lar edi” [3,231]. Bu misolda *tosh devor* – jamiyatning mustahkam, ammo ichki chirigan, dog‘li tizimini bildiradi. Har urilishda paydo bo‘ladigan jarohatlar esa ijtimoiy tanqid, adolatsizlik va inson qalbidagi og‘riqni ifodalaydi.

Muhabbat, sadoqat va taqdirning fojeali ifodasi: asarda qahramonlarning shaxsiy munosabatlari ham metaforik ifodalarga boy. Adabiyotda muhabbat, iztirob va insoniy kechinmalar tabiat hodisalari orqali berilganda, obraz yanada jonlanadi va chuqur ma‘no kasb etadi [2,57]. Ra‘no obrazida yozuvchi uning beg‘ubor muhabbati va fojeali taqdirini quyidagi misollar orqali yoritadi:

“Ra‘no, bahorda ochilgan oppoq lola kabi, nafis va nozik edi; lekin uning muhabbati qishning sovuq shamollaridek tez so‘nib ketardi” [3,189]. Bu yerda *oppoq lola* – Ra‘noning go‘zalligi va beg‘uborligini ramziy ifodalaydi, qishning sovuq shamollari esa uning muhabbatidagi tez o‘zgaruvchanlik va sinovlarni bildiradi. Shuningdek, boshqa bir tasvirda Ra‘noning ichki iztirobi quyidagicha aks etadi:

“Ra‘noning yuragi, kuzgi daraxt bargidek, titrab, qachon butunlay so‘nib ketishini bilmas edi” [3,214]. Bu metaforada *kuzgi daraxt bargi* – uning nozik qalbini, hayotning og‘ir sinovlari va ichki beqarorlikni ko‘rsatadi.

Metonimiya asarda qahramonlar, voqealar va jamiyatni yanada aniqroq va jonli tasvirlash uchun ishlatilgan. Muallif ba‘zan qahramonlarning ichki kechinmalarini bevosita nomlamasdan, ularning atrof-muhitini tasvirlash orqali beradi. Masalan, Anvarning dardli kechinmalari quyidagi metonimiya orqali ifodalangan:

“Toshkentning osmoni ham bugun g‘amgin edi” [3,76]. Bu yerda *Toshkent osmoni* bevosita Anvarning dardli kayfiyatini bildiradi, ya‘ni uning ichki iztiroblari tashqi olam orqali ifodalangan.

Metonimiya bir tushunchani boshqasi bilan almashtirish orqali asardagi ijtimoiy tahlilni chuqurlashtiradi [2,83]. Ba‘zan muallif butun bir sinf yoki ijtimoiy guruhni bir necha so‘z orqali ifodalab beradi:

“Uyingdagi kulollar yana qadah urishtiryaptimi” [3,142]? Bu yerda *kulollar* – aslida oddiy xalq, hunarmandlar, mehnatkashlar timsolida keltirilgan bo‘lib, ular bevosita sinfiy tabaqalanishning ramzi sifatida ishlatilgan.

Metonimiya asarda poetik mazmun yaratish va qisqa, aniq ifodalar orqali chuqur ma’no berishda qo‘llangan:

“Bu hovli endi unga yot va sovuq edi” [3,197]. Bu yerda *hovli* – aslida unda yashagan insonlar, oilaviy muhabbat va hayotning o‘tkinchiligi ifodasidir.

Abdulla Qodiriyning “Mehrobdan chayon” asarida metafora va metonimiya badiiy uslubning ajralmas qismi sifatida qahramonlarning ichki dunyosini, voqea harakatini va ijtimoiy-tanqidiy mazmuni ramziy ifodalashda katta o‘rin egallaydi. Anvar obrazida metafora uning yoshligidagi umid, orzu va adolatga bo‘lgan intilishlarini, shuningdek, hayotning qattiq zarbalari ostida so‘nayotgan hissiyotlarini aks ettiradi.

Ra’no esa o‘zining beg‘ubor muhabbati, nozik go‘zalligi va fojeali taqdirini ramziy tasvirlar orqali ifodalaydi. Metafora va metonimiya yordamida asarda voqea syujeti va ijtimoiy tanqidiy xususiyatlar ham yoritilib, o‘quvchi uchun hayotning murakkabligini, inson ruhining o‘zgaruvchanligini va ijtimoiy adolatsizliklarni anglash imkoniyati yaratiladi.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ ОБЩЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: В статье представлена информация о том, насколько велика роль паралингвистики в возникновении фразеологизмов. Исследование статьи сосредоточено на содержании и сущности фразеологизмов, возникающих на основе экстралингвистических средств, образованных именно паралингвистическими средствами.

Ключевые слова: экстралингвистика, паралингвистика, фразеологизм, афоризм, фразема компонента, лексема;

Параязык (от греч. para – возле, вне) – явления и факторы, сопровождающие речь, но не являющиеся вербальным материалом: громкость, паузы, модуляции голоса, мимика, жесты, визуальный контакт между общающимися и т.п.; изучается паралингвистикой. [1, с. 113]

Параязык (по Вердербер) – «невербальные звуковые сигналы, оформляющие речь, - тональность, громкость голоса, темп речи, паузы и вздохи – являются богатым источником информации. «Параязык» имеет отношение не к тому, что именно сказано, а к тому, как это сказано. Наименее очевидным типом «параязыка» является молчание. С помощью молчания люди способны передавать такие чувства, как презрение, враждебность, вызов и строгость, но также уважение и доброе отношение». [2, с. 3]

Паралингвистика изучает мыслительные движения тела, такие как жесты, мимика, возникающие в речевой ситуации. Паралингвистика выполняет важную функцию в общении, общении. Если речь будет выражена слушателю без поддержки этих средств, мысль будет иметь меньшую силу воздействия. Сообщение, которое можно сказать, выглядит как сухая информация. Любая мысль должна обладать своей выразительностью, привлекательностью, востребованностью в общении. Именно такими аспектами паралингвистика образует, а также оживляет речь.

Как мы знаем, жесты возникли в развитии общества гораздо раньше, чем язык (речь). Даже жесты служили основным источником для того, чтобы человек мог говорить, выражать мысли. Точнее, жесты являются продуктом длительного жизненного опыта человека. Поэтому не будет переводчика

жестов. Об этом В.Н. Гелия говорит: "хотя Паралингвистика служит для раскрытия значения слова, она также имеет свойство привлекать слушателя".

Судя по всему, жесты реализованы синхронно со значением слова. Соответственно, речь становится впечатляющей. Следовательно, эффективность речи ощущается не только с помощью изобразительных средств языка, но также с помощью паралингвистических средств, которые делают мысль привлекательной. Ведь всякое притяжение, впечатление, образность в речи возникает на основе движений. С другой стороны, паралингвистические инструменты также могут быть эффективными сами по себе.

В статье мы постараемся изучить формирование знаковых фразеологий и их смысловое содержание. Паралингвистика также очень близка к фразеологизму по образованию, структуре и сущности. Близость заключается в том, что паралингвистика также является нелинейным явлением, имеющим смысл на основе стагнации. Было бы целесообразно условно включить паралингвистические средства и в языковые феномены. Потому что они не имеют звуковой структуры, но имеют семантику значения и в то же время важны, поскольку они одинаково понятны владельцам языков.

Кроме того, жесты похожи на фразеологию в том, что они дают любой идее образ, образно-аффективное выражение.

Кстати, мы не можем сказать, что фразеология - это явление, резко отличающееся от паралингвистических средств, а точнее, от паралингвистики. Потому что при формировании фразеологии наряду с языковыми единицами часто наблюдается использование паралингвистических средств. Кто знает, может, интересующиеся этой областью ученые положат этому конец. Когда мы проанализировали литературу, имеющую отношение к нашей работе, насколько это было возможно, мы не смогли найти ни одного источника, который бы различал фразеологию и паралингвистические средства. Однако оказалось, что роль паралингвистики в возникновении фразеологии огромна. Поэтому в данной статье основное внимание уделяется содержанию и сущности фразеологизмов, сформированных на основе экстралингвистических средств, образованных именно паралингвистическими средствами.

Таким образом, жесты также являются частью фразеологизмов, но их отношение к языку и речи, процесс выражения мысли и некоторые синтаксические особенности отличаются друг от друга. Соответственно, оба являются языковыми явлениями, которые необходимо изучать отдельно. В общем языкознании явление паралингвистики рассматривается как

фразеологические афоризмы. Такое отношение соответствует характеру жестов. Однако не все они имеют форму фраз. Например, состав, приподнимающий брови, также является паралингвистическим инструментом. Первая часть соединения используется в первоначальном смысле, а вторая часть используется в переносном смысле. Фразовыми глаголами можно называть только жесты с такой структурой. Сравните: пожимает плечами, закатывает глаза, трясет головой, напрягает шею, хмурится.

Однако к фразеологическим сочетаниям нельзя добавлять такие жесты, как скручивание губ, прищуривание глаз, пожимание плечами, хмурый лоб, покачивание головой, покачивание головой. Потому что оба компонента слова в этих сочетаниях сохраняют свое первоначальное значение. Следует отметить, что эти жесты очень близки к фразам. Словосочетания - это свободные комбинации. Так как же отличить жесты от фраз? Во-первых, жесты - невербальные средства. С другой стороны, фразы полагаются на лексемы, а не на невербальные действия. Во-вторых, жесты могут стабилизироваться в соответствии с требованиями текста. Например, человек, который поскользнулся, имеет большой вес: он лежал на спине, чтобы избавиться от мух, качал головой, махал руками и пытался напугать его криком, потому что он был недостаточно силен. Комбинация покачивания головой и рукопожатия в данном примере - это жесты, используемые в контексте слова «вождение» (фразеологизируются в контексте). Фразы не имеют этой функции. Кажется, что паралингвистические приемы тоже очень близки к фразам. Однако разница в том, что фразы основаны на лексемах, основанных на мыслях, а жесты - на жестах, основанных на действиях.

Они основаны на метафорах. Например, вышли и старушки соседних домов, дожившие до определенного возраста (Чолпон. «Ночь и день»). Если только кто-то не вызвался придумать красивый шаблон? Ну, по крайней мере, я не пошел вниз, не объяснив сначала себя.

Значение фразеологии (фразеологическое значение) основано на переносном значении словесных компонентов словосочетания: лизать жир змеи - хитрость, перевернуть шубу - злость, а упавший в воду буханка хлеба - пуста.

Паралингвистические средства, то есть жесты, состоят в основном из действий и ситуаций. Вербально они даются только в литературных текстах. Это очень полезно для раскрытия характера главного героя. Они также заставляют читателя задуматься, наблюдать и наблюдать: «Он должен выйти сегодня, пойдёшь?» - сказал Усманов. - Да, - кивнул (У. Умарбеков). Кажется,

что жесты в тексте заданы автором, а не языком главного героя. Это еще один аспект жестов.

Итак, жизненное пространство паралингвистики - диалогическая речь. Анализ исследований показывает, что жесты в основном состоят из слов и фраз, которые используются в буквальном смысле. Во фразеологии все компоненты слова основаны на переходах, а в жестах только одно слово имеет значение. Сравните: пожимает плечами, выщипывает брови, потирает руки. Таких жестов в нашем языке меньшинство. Но в любом случае жесты очень близки по структуре к фразеологизму.

В заключение, фразеология - это единицы языка, основанные на стабильной миграции, а жесты - это единицы речи, которые условно фразеологизируются на основе требований текста. Возникновение обоих происходит на основе экстралингвистических средств. В этом отношении они очень похожи.

Паралингвистические (около языковые) средства общения характеризуются двойственностью. С одной стороны, они позволяют экономить речевые средства. Обращаясь, допустим, к продавцу, мы, указывая на предмет, говорим: «Покажите, пожалуйста, вот эту чашечку», — и не тратим лишних слов на ее описание. С другой стороны, они компенсируют многое из того, что недоговорено словами, вскрывают подтекст, многозначность речи, ее стилистические оттенки, чувства, отношения и т. д. Действительно, суть такой, например, незаконченной фразы, как «Ну, знаете?!», можно понять только через интонацию, мимику, жесты говорящего.

Умение наблюдать и учитывать элементы неречевого поведения слушателей позволяет вносить коррективы в свое выступление, превращать монологическую речь в активный диалог со слушателями, «втягивать» их в процесс взаимостимуляции. Ведь тонус выступления во многом зависит от реакции аудитории, от того, насколько она поддерживает или охлаждает выступающего. Поэтому и надо уметь видеть, чувствовать «дыхание» аудитории, чтобы регулировать ее поведение, что важно как для оратора, выступающего перед публикой, так и в простом разговоре.

Но следует помнить, что неречевые средства являются не самостоятельным, а вспомогательным средством коммуникации. Они подготавливают, сопровождают, комментируют, разъясняют речь, вскрывают ее глубинную суть. Поэтому прежде чем их использовать, надо знать, о чём говорить.

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TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN DIVERSE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *In contemporary educational settings, the increasing diversity of classrooms presents both challenges and opportunities for English language teaching. This article explores effective strategies and methodologies for teaching English in diverse classrooms, aiming to foster an inclusive learning environment that caters to the varied linguistic and cultural backgrounds of students.*

Key words: *different social background, diversity, cultural differences, material choosing, classroom, effective strategies, methodologies.*

Introduction

Diversity in the classroom encompasses a range of factors, including ethnicity, culture, language, socio-economic status, and learning abilities. Teachers must recognize that students bring their unique experiences, perspectives, and skills to the learning environment, which can enrich the educational experience for everyone. In this globalized world in one classroom there might be students from different cultural, social, and economic background. In these types of classrooms lessons are always interesting. But there are some challenges as well.

One of the primary challenges in diverse classrooms is addressing the varying levels of English proficiency among students. Teachers often encounter students who are native speakers, bilingual, or English language learners (ELLs) at different stages of language acquisition. This disparity can create difficulties in ensuring that all students engage with and understand the curriculum. Although some students are brilliant at grammar and vocabulary, they often face problems with pronunciation. When it comes to textbooks or reading materials, many students do not feel comfortable.

Another challenge is cultural differences that may affect communication styles, learning preferences, and classroom behavior. Students from different cultural backgrounds may have distinct approaches to learning and interaction, which requires teachers to be culturally sensitive and adaptable in their teaching methods.

Effective Strategies for Teaching English in Diverse Classrooms

1. Differentiated Instruction: This approach involves tailoring teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students. By using a variety of instructional strategies, such as visual aids, group work, and hands-on activities, teachers can ensure that all

students have access to the curriculum in a way that suits their learning styles and language proficiency levels.

2. Collaborative Learning: Group activities and peer interactions can promote language development and cultural exchange. Collaborative learning encourages students to work together, share ideas, and support each other, fostering a sense of community and mutual respect.

3. Scaffolded Instruction: Providing support structures, or scaffolds, helps students build on their existing knowledge and skills. Examples of scaffolding include using simplified language, providing visual supports, and offering step-by-step guidance. As students become more proficient, these supports can be gradually removed.

4. Culturally Responsive Teaching: This pedagogical approach emphasizes the importance of recognizing and valuing students' cultural backgrounds. Teachers can incorporate culturally relevant materials and examples into their lessons, create an inclusive classroom environment, and demonstrate respect for diverse perspectives.

5. Use of Technology: Technology can be a powerful tool for supporting English language learners. Educational software, online resources, and language learning apps can provide additional practice and reinforcement, catering to individual learning needs and preferences.

An inclusive classroom environment is one where all students feel valued, respected, and supported. Teachers can foster inclusivity by setting clear expectations for respectful behavior, celebrating cultural diversity, and promoting positive relationships among students.

Additionally, involving families and communities in the educational process can enhance students' learning experiences. Engaging with parents and community members provides valuable insights into students' backgrounds and helps build a supportive network for learners.

Conclusion

Teaching English in a diverse classroom requires a multifaceted approach that acknowledges and embraces the differences among students. By employing strategies such as differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, scaffolded instruction, culturally responsive teaching, and the use of technology, teachers can create a supportive and effective learning environment for all students. Embracing classroom diversity not only enhances language learning but also prepares students to thrive in a multicultural world.

Since English language has been very popular around the world. As we have been living in globalized world, it is very common to see students from different cultural background. Because of this reason choosing materials is vital. Most students of Uzbekistan learn English language as foreign language. However, in some parts of Uzbekistan people learn French and German languages. Because of this reason they have got French and German accent in their pronunciation. Some students of universities are the students of Russian class and their grammar is good. Despite this many Russian students have their first language evidence in their accent. Sometimes many students who have Russian accent feel uncomfortable, when they give speech or presentation. When it comes to their course book, they use Road Map`s updated version. As this book has its online app my students can do online practices. In a week they use it about 2 hours and that is why their listening and grammar skill is better than the other skills. They are learning English in order to enter bachelors. Their target level is B2. As they have got extra lesson with support teachers, they may receive feedback from them.

Students will learn about “Education “which they can see in their textbook Road Map and watch a short video about Finland`s secondary schools and do the listening activity and they are given multiple choice questions.

While reading the short passage about school, students highlight the keywords about school and education and write 200-words summary about the passages.

The teacher shows the videos twice and first students watch it without its subtitle but weaker students are given subtitle and word list and they try to write some parts of the video themselves. After watching it for the second time they will check their spelling mistakes but if some students cannot understand some words translation, teacher gives their definition or shows the video from YouEnglish.com” website and then, they will give 3 minutes speech about its main idea and tell some key points of the video.

According to Beacher (2011), process adaptations will help the learners to learn easily and show their strong skills. That is why I have chosen this style. The main reason why I have provided tape script of the video is to improve their vocabulary and listening comprehension. Sometimes, even normal speed might be difficult for them to understand each information clearly.

As Tomlinson (2011), students have different abilities and weak and strong skills. Providing different types of tasks help them to show their strong skills. That is why I have chosen both productive and receptive skills. Furthermore, some weak students they use scripts or dictionary and it help them to do this tasks in a short time.

Adoptation to the video allows students to catch everything. (Beatcher, 2011) .electing interesting materials is vital to make the students active in the classroom. I should also add, students activeness based on their understanding the topic very well. Since , classrooms consists of a variety of students who has got very good background knowledge or with some special needs or introvert and etc. If the student do not feel and understand what is going on in the classroom or do not understand clearly the aim of the activity, they cannot engage the lesson (Davis, 2006, p.8). That is why, I always check my students activeness during the lesson and if they are not able to do activities very well , I will explain the task again and while they are doing activities I usually tell “ *Do you need some help* “ . Students` needs are also very essential (Nunan,1988). Some want to improve only their speaking or some students are not good at writing. If one lesson teacher focuses on only oral activities , the other students might be bored passive in the lesson. If student cannot be active during the lesson, its main reason might be lacking of group works or participation (Nunan, 1988). In my lesson I have added many group work and individual activities. Time management is also important factor in teaching. If activity takes more time , the pace of the lesson will not be fast and interesting enough.

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REVOLUTIONIZING LANGUAGE LEARNING: THE ROLE OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING (CALL)

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Annotatsiya: *Kompyuter yordamida til o'rganish (CALL) texnologiya hamda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonini integratsiyalash orqali til o'rganish muhitini tubdan o'zgartirdi. Ushbu maqola asosiy til ko'nikmalarini, jumladan tinglash, gapirish, o'qish va yozishni rivojlantirishda CALL rolini yoritib beradi. Interfaol platformalar, onlayn aloqa tizimlari va multimedia resurslaridan foydalangan holda, CALL shaxsiylashtirilgan, moslashuvchan va qiziqarli o'rganish jarayonlarini yaratadi hamda o'rganuvchilarning tilni o'zlashtirish ko'rsatkichini oshiradi. Talabalarda motivatsiyasini oshirish, tezda xatolarni tuzatish va virtual ta'sirlar orqali haqiqiy til amaliyoti imkoniyatlarini yaratishda CALL ning afzalliklariga urg'u beriladi. Maqolada, shuningdek, nutqni aniqlash, o'yinlashtirish va immersiv muhitlar kabi rivojlanayotgan texnologiyalar ta'kidlanadi va til o'rganishda yanada kengroq, interaktiv yondashuvni yaratish uchun CALL qanday rivojlanayotgani ko'rib chiqiladi. Xulosa o'rnida, CALL til o'rganuvchilar uchun insoniy o'zaro ta'sirning kuchli tomonlarini ilg'or texnologik vositalar bilan birlashtirgan istiqbolli kelajakni taklif qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Kompyuter yordamida til o'rganish (CALL), til ko'nikmalari, tilni o'zlashtirish, ta'limda texnologiya, nutqni aniqlash, o'yinlashtirish, multimediali o'rganish, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'rganish, interaktiv platformalar, raqamli o'rganish vositalari.*

Abstract: *Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has transformed the landscape of language education by integrating technology into the process of learning a second language. This article explores the role of CALL in developing key language skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing. By utilizing interactive platforms, real-time feedback systems, and multimedia resources, CALL enhances language acquisition by offering personalized, flexible, and engaging learning experiences. It emphasizes the advantages of CALL in fostering student motivation, providing immediate corrections, and offering opportunities for authentic language practice through virtual interactions. The article also highlights emerging technologies such as speech recognition, gamification, and immersive environments, and considers how CALL is evolving to create a more comprehensive, interactive approach to language learning. Ultimately, CALL offers a promising future for language learners, combining the strengths of human interaction with advanced technological tools.*

Keywords: *Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), language skills, language acquisition, technology in education, speech recognition, gamification, multimedia learning, personalized learning, interactive platforms, digital learning tools.*

Language learning is an ever-evolving field, constantly adapting to new teaching methods, tools, and technologies. One of the most significant advancements in the last few decades is the rise of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), which has changed how students interact with language content. CALL utilizes various

digital platforms to provide learners with the ability to improve their language skills in ways that traditional methods could not. In this digital age, CALL isn't just an enhancement; it's becoming an integral part of effective language learning.

Traditional language classrooms have long been the cornerstone of language education. However, with the increasing accessibility of technology, there is a growing trend of incorporating digital tools into the language learning process. CALL uses computers, tablets, smartphones, and the internet to bring a variety of multimedia experiences to students. By blending traditional teaching with technology, CALL can accelerate language acquisition in a more dynamic, student-centered environment. The traditional classroom can be restrictive, often forcing students to work within limited time frames and environments. CALL breaks down these barriers by offering learning opportunities outside the classroom, allowing learners to practice speaking with native speakers, explore cultural contexts through videos, and receive personalized feedback on their mistakes. But how exactly does CALL facilitate the development of language skills?

Effective language acquisition depends on mastering four key skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. CALL enhances each of these areas through its innovative, interactive platforms. Here's a breakdown of how CALL influences each of these fundamental skills:

Listening comprehension can be one of the most challenging aspects of language learning. Traditional classroom listening exercises often involve scripted dialogues or recordings that do not mirror real-life language use. CALL addresses this by providing access to authentic listening materials such as podcasts, YouTube videos, news broadcasts, and interactive apps that offer exposure to different accents, slang, and colloquial expressions. Platforms like LingQ or Yabla go a step further by allowing learners to watch videos with real-time subtitles, offering translation help and the ability to pause, rewind, and slow down the speech. This flexibility enables students to learn at their own pace and interact with content more deeply than a passive classroom listening activity would allow. Additionally, platforms that incorporate speech recognition technology can give learners immediate feedback on their listening abilities, testing their understanding in real time and adjusting difficulty levels based on performance.

Perhaps one of the most transformative aspects of CALL is its ability to foster speaking skills, especially for shy or introverted learners who might struggle to speak in front of others in traditional settings. CALL offers a space where learners can practice speaking aloud, whether they're interacting with virtual tutors or engaging in

language exchange programs. Programs like Rosetta Stone and Babbel include voice recognition systems that evaluate pronunciation and provide feedback on how closely the learner's speech matches native speakers. Similarly, HelloTalk and Tandem connect students with native speakers globally, creating an opportunity to practice speaking with real people, simulating real-world interactions. Moreover, speech-to-text tools, such as Google Translate, encourage students to test their spoken language abilities, providing them with immediate visual feedback and correcting errors in real time.

In the realm of reading, CALL offers innovative ways for students to explore texts beyond textbooks. E-readers, digital libraries, and language learning apps provide access to a vast array of materials, from news articles to literary works and blogs, catering to different levels of proficiency. Some platforms like Duolingo or Memrise incorporate gamified reading exercises that not only help students build vocabulary but also develop context-based reading skills. Students can read short passages, answer comprehension questions, and receive instant feedback on their answers, which is more interactive than traditional comprehension worksheets.

When it comes to writing, CALL introduces a range of tools that transform the writing process from a solitary activity to one that is interactive, collaborative, and data-driven. Automated writing correction tools like Grammarly and ProWritingAid help learners understand grammar rules, sentence structure, and punctuation. They not only point out errors but also provide explanations, helping students learn as they write. Collaborative platforms such as Google Docs allow students to work on writing tasks with peers in real time, offering instant feedback and brainstorming opportunities. These tools also support peer review processes, where learners can exchange written pieces, evaluate each other's work, and make improvements. For more advanced learners, platforms like Lang-8 allow students to publish their writing for native speakers to correct. This not only builds writing skills but also enhances cultural learning as students gain insight into the nuances of the language.

Unique Advantages of CALL in Language Learning. One of the primary advantages of CALL is its ability to personalize the learning experience. Unlike traditional classrooms, where the pace is often set for an entire group, CALL platforms adapt to individual needs. Artificial intelligence (AI) can assess students' strengths and weaknesses and customize learning paths based on their performance. Students struggling with a particular area of language learning, such as grammar or vocabulary, can receive more focused practice in that area, while those excelling can

progress at a faster rate. This tailored approach not only helps improve proficiency but also boosts student confidence.

CALL offers instant feedback, which is a crucial aspect of language learning. Whether it's through a language learning app correcting a typo or a speech recognition system analyzing pronunciation, immediate feedback ensures that mistakes are identified and corrected right away. This process encourages active learning, helping students to continuously improve their skills rather than relying on delayed teacher assessments.

Moreover, CALL brings learning flexibility that traditional classroom settings cannot match. Language learners can access their lessons and practice exercises at any time, whether they're at home, commuting, or traveling abroad. Additionally, the online nature of CALL allows students to learn at their own pace, setting goals and revisiting lessons whenever they need. It's perfect for students who have different schedules or who prefer to learn at their own convenience.

Many CALL platforms use gamified elements, such as rewards, challenges, and leveling-up systems, which keep learners motivated. This encourages consistent practice and engagement, making the language learning process more enjoyable. The inclusion of achievement badges, point systems, and competitive elements with other learners can transform language learning into an exciting game.

While CALL is an incredibly powerful tool, it's important to recognize that it cannot replace human interaction entirely. The role of a teacher remains crucial in fostering cultural understanding, providing context for language use, and facilitating authentic conversations. The future of CALL will likely involve a blend of AI-driven personalized learning with live interaction—whether through virtual reality (VR) classrooms, language immersion experiences, or enhanced collaborative platforms. Technological advancements like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) may soon offer immersive language learning experiences that replicate real-world environments, allowing learners to practice in simulated real-life situations, such as ordering food at a restaurant in Paris or negotiating a business deal in Tokyo.

In conclusion, CALL is reshaping the landscape of language education, offering students dynamic, flexible, and engaging ways to improve their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Through personalization, real-time feedback, and innovative tools, CALL creates opportunities for students to connect with language on a deeper level, providing them with the resources to become proficient, confident speakers of their target language. As technology continues to evolve, CALL will

likely play an even greater role in shaping the future of language learning, making it more accessible, interactive, and effective than ever before.

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THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE LEARNING PROCESS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

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Abstract: *This scientific work examines the role of modern teaching methods and the application of innovative technologies in the educational process in the development of youth. In today's world, the education system needs to adapt to the changing global environment and apply modern pedagogical methods and technologies to teach new knowledge and skills. Innovative technologies, including digital tools, interactive learning platforms, and artificial intelligence, create opportunities to make education more effective, engaging, and personalized. It is well known that modern teaching methods play a significant role in youth development. They allow students to refresh their thinking and learning methods, and they have the opportunity to engage in education in an interactive and engaging manner. Innovative technologies help to develop creative thinking, enhance communication skills, and shape the competencies necessary for success in the modern world. The paper presents information on the relationship of young people with learning and education, their ability to adapt to new technologies, as well as the methodological changes necessary to improve their learning effectiveness. The study aims to analyze how the application of innovative technologies in education impacts the intellectual development, personal growth, and social activity of youth. This work also explores the integration of pedagogical innovations into education and the improvement of teaching methods and tools, taking into account the individual abilities of students. The role of modern educational technologies in youth development and their significance in the learning process are also discussed.*

Keywords: *Modern teaching methods, innovative technologies, youth development, application of technologies in education, interactive learning platforms, digital education.*

Introduction

In the modern world, the education system must rapidly adapt to changing conditions. Innovative technologies, especially digital tools and modern pedagogical methods, play a key role in enhancing the effectiveness of education and making the learning process more engaging and efficient for youth. The primary goal of applying new technologies in the educational process is to personalize learning, take into account each student's individual needs, and expand their thinking possibilities. These changes, in turn, help improve youth development by enhancing their creative and critical thinking skills. Modern teaching methods are designed to refresh the educational process and teach students more effectively. This includes interactive lessons, online learning platforms, digital resources for students, and the use of artificial intelligence. The application of technologies in education helps prepare students for advanced technologies and equips them with practical skills. This process ensures that students absorb new knowledge and gain more experience and

practice. Moreover, youth development is closely related to education. Innovations in the educational process not only provide academic knowledge but also develop the skills necessary for young people to succeed in a changing world[1]. By applying innovative technologies, youth can develop their creative potential, analytical thinking skills, and self-management abilities. One of the crucial aspects of applying innovations in education is the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, which allow students to engage in learning through collaborative activities. Today, one of the most commonly used innovative technologies in education is digital platforms, online lessons, and interactive tools. These technologies help implement continuous updates in education. Digital learning platforms such as MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) and other online platforms enable students to learn at their own time and place. Through these technologies, students can not only pursue learning individually but also improve communication between teachers and students. These platforms provide access to a wealth of knowledge and allow students to engage with learning materials interactively. Interactive technologies make students more active in the learning process, making education more interesting and effective. Interactive lessons, virtual classrooms, and cooperation between students make learning more engaging. Students are given the opportunity to apply their knowledge in practice, which helps to develop their analytical and creative thinking skills. Youth are highly adaptable to technologies. They quickly master new technologies and are ready to embrace innovative approaches in the learning process. Their rapid adoption of digital technologies and their use in the learning process contribute to improving the quality of education. Youth actively participate in the educational process, and teaching them with new methods brings many benefits. They expand their knowledge rapidly and effectively by learning through interactive methods. This, in turn, significantly impacts their personal development. Through the use of innovative technologies, youth develop their creative thinking abilities. With digital technologies, students are better able to express their thoughts clearly and effectively, analyze problems, and create new ideas. This, in turn, teaches them to think creatively and critically. Innovative technologies enable the personalization of the learning process. As a result, students can learn according to their individual needs. Personalized education creates the opportunity for students to learn at their own time and place, which boosts their motivation. The application of innovative technologies makes the learning process more efficient. Students master knowledge more quickly, and their academic achievements improve significantly. The technologies used in the

education system enhance students' interaction and improve the quality of education[2].

Conclusion

Modern teaching methods and innovative technologies have a significant impact on the development of youth. Technologies that help the personal development of students and enhance their creative and critical thinking abilities make the learning process more effective, interactive, and engaging. These processes expand the learning opportunities for youth and create the chance to enhance their personal potential.

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TIME TRAVELING MOTIFS IN COMPARATIVE LITERATURE: EXPLORING TEMPORAL THEMES ACROSS CULTURES

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Abstract: *This article aims to conduct a comprehensive literary analysis to examine the recurring theme of time travel in various literary works. The purpose of this study is to deeply explore the complex and multifaceted role of time travel as a crucial narrative tool, thoroughly examining and analyzing the intricacies and variations in its portrayal across diverse cultural customs. Drawing from interdisciplinary fields including physics, philosophy, and psychology, this study highlights the enduring significance of time travel in storytelling. Ultimately, we argue that literary portrayals of time travel reflect different cultural understandings of time and contribute to broader discussions about human consciousness and narrative structure.*

Keywords: *Time travel, comparative literature, narrative structure, temporal paradox, cultural perspectives, philosophy of time, interdisciplinary approaches, literary motifs*

INTRODUCTION

Time travel has fascinated readers and writers alike for generations, offering a unique way to explore memory, history, identity, and reality. In comparative literature, time travel provides a lens through which different cultures interpret temporal experience. By examining various literary traditions, we uncover shared concerns, philosophical debates, and narrative techniques that transcend borders and historical periods (Bakhtin, 1981). By examining works such as H.G. Wells' "The Time Machine", Liu Cixin's "The Three-Body Problem," Jorge Luis Borges' "The Garden of Forking Paths," Isaac Asimov's "The End of Eternity," Stephen King's "11/22/63," and Ray Bradbury's "A Sound of Thunder" and "Toynbee Convector," we delve into the complex and mind-bending concept of time travel, examining how it challenges traditional notions of chronology and prompts deep philosophical musings about the concepts of fate, free will, and reality.

As a storytelling technique, time travel challenges linear narratives, redefines cause and effect, and allows authors to explore alternative realities. From Wells'

pioneering *The Time Machine* (1895) to modern works like Audrey Niffenegger's "The Time Traveler's Wife" (2003) and Haruki Murakami's "1Q84" (2009), writers have used time travel to examine memory, fate, and the fluid nature of time. Isaac Asimov's "The End of Eternity" (1955) explores time travel through the lens of control and manipulation, where an organization outside of time alters history for the supposed benefit of humanity. Stephen King's "11/22/63" (2011) examines the consequences of changing the past, particularly in relation to historical events like the assassination of John F. Kennedy, emphasizing the moral and emotional weight of time travel. Ray Bradbury's "The Toynbee Convector" (1984) presents time travel as a source of hope, illustrating the power of belief in a better future through an invented journey to inspire societal progress.

When examining the concept of time travel in literature, one can also observe the diverse cultural perspectives that shape the interpretation of time within different societies. This serves to emphasize and bring attention to the importance of cultural influences and their impact on our perception and interpretation of time, specifically in relation to its role in storytelling. In many works of Western literature, time is often portrayed as a linear concept, with a strong emphasis on how past events can significantly influence and shape the future, as seen in Ray Bradbury's renowned short story "A Sound of Thunder" (1952). In contrast, Eastern literature frequently presents time as cyclical or nonlinear. Liu Cixin's "The Three-Body Problem" (2008), for example, incorporates scientific and philosophical ideas that view time as a repeating cycle, not a straight path (Zhang, 2015). Furthermore, both Hindu and Buddhist traditions often depict time as an endless cycle, in which the past, present, and future intersect and influence literary narratives in South Asian cultures.

When exploring the realm of time travel narratives, it is often noted that these stories delve into complex and thought-provoking philosophical quandaries surrounding the fundamental concepts of free will, determinism, and the essence of reality itself. These themes are intricately woven into the fabric of these narratives, challenging our understanding of the world and our place within it. The grandfather paradox—where a time traveler's actions in the past could erase their own existence—illustrates how these stories question our understanding of causality (Lewis, 1976). Borges' "The Garden of Forking Paths" (1941) explores multiple coexisting timelines, confirming that time is not a single, linear progression, but an intricate web of possibilities. The bootstrap paradox, another common motif, raises questions about self-creation and the origin of knowledge, as seen in Robert Heinlein's "All You Zombies" (1959) and Christopher Nolan's film *Tenet* (2020).

Asimov's "The End of Eternity" also delves into time loops and the ethical implications of altering history, showing how time travel can serve as a means of control rather than discovery.

The exploration and analysis of time travel within literature is greatly enriched and expanded by the incorporation of diverse and interdisciplinary perspectives, drawing upon the wealth of knowledge and insights from various fields, including but not limited to physics, philosophy, and psychology. Einstein's theory of relativity (Einstein, 1905) has influenced literary depictions of time, linking scientific advancements with narrative imagination. Quantum mechanics, particularly the many-worlds interpretation, has also inspired recent science fiction works, such as Ted Chiang's "Story of Your Life" (1998), later adapted into the film "Arrival" (2016). Psychological theories on memory and perception play a role, as seen in Kurt Vonnegut's "Slaughterhouse-Five" (1969), where protagonist Billy Pilgrim experiences time as a fragmented, nonlinear construct (LaCapra, 1994). According to numerous studies in cognitive science, it has been proposed that the human perception of time is highly adaptable and can be impacted by external factors, such as the concept of time travel, which has been depicted and interpreted diversely in literature, further strengthening its flexibility.

CONCLUSION

The concept of time travel has been a consistently fascinating and long-standing theme in literature, spanning across various genres and cultures, and offers a captivating and thought-provoking opportunity to explore the complexities of time and its effects on different societies throughout history. By conducting a thorough and all-encompassing analysis and comparison of a multitude of cultural and traditional depictions of time travel, we can not only expand our knowledge and perspective on this fascinating concept, but also gain a profound understanding of the underlying common themes that connect ideas of memory, history, and existence. By comparing how various traditions portray time travel, we can uncover shared themes related to memory, history, and existence. With the continued advancement and development of science and storytelling, time travel will undoubtedly continue to serve as a captivating motif, connecting and intertwining various cultural, philosophical, and historical perspectives. In the future, extensive research and analysis may explore the potential impact of rapidly advancing technology, such as artificial intelligence and virtual reality, on the conventional literary depictions of time travel.

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APPLYING STEAM TECHNOLOGY TO PRESCHOOLKIDS' LEXICAL SKILL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *This article explores to improve preschoolers' lexical skill development, this article examines the possible advantages of integrating STEAM (Science, technologies, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) technologies into early childhood education. The article explores the body of research on the connection between language learning and technology, as well as the significance of early vocabulary development for young students. This research attempts to shed light on how STEAM technology may be used to assist and foster lexical abilities in preschool-aged children by looking at a variety of studies and ideas. In order to support the incorporation of STEAM technologies in early childhood language learning programs, practical suggestions and consequences for parents and educators will also be covered.*

Keywords: *STEAM technology, formation of lexical skills, preschool children.*

Introduction: In recent years, there has been increasing enthusiasm for the incorporation of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) tools and resources in early childhood education. One specific area of emphasis is the enhancement of vocabulary skills in preschool-aged children. Building a strong vocabulary is essential for a child's language development and their overall academic achievements. Studies indicate that children with a robust vocabulary base are more capable of understanding and communicating effectively.

The integration of STEAM technology in early childhood education presents a distinctive chance to improve lexical skills among preschoolers. By utilizing interactive and captivating digital resources, teachers can foster a lively learning atmosphere that encourages language development and vocabulary expansion. STEAM activities such as digital storytelling, educational games, and interactive simulations allow children to discover new words, concepts, and ideas in an enjoyable and engaging manner.

This article intends to investigate the possible advantages of incorporating STEAM technology into early childhood education to aid in the development of vocabulary skills in preschoolers. By reviewing current studies on the connection between technology and language development, this research aims to pinpoint effective approaches and practices for utilizing STEAM tools to improve vocabulary learning among young children. Furthermore, practical suggestions and implications

for teachers and parents will be addressed to assist in the application of STEAM technology in early childhood language programs.

This article aims to enhance our understanding of how STEAM technology can be utilized to foster the development of vocabulary skills in preschoolers, ultimately equipping them for success in language growth and educational accomplishments.

Literaturereview. The use of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) tools and resources in early childhood education has gained popularity recently as a way to improve learning outcomes. Preschoolers' lexical skill development is one area of emphasis because vocabulary acquisition is essential for both language development and academic success. The purpose of this literature review is to examine the body of research on the application of STEAM technology to preschoolers' lexical skill development.

Engaging young learners in interactive, hands-on activities that foster vocabulary growth is made possible by STEAM technology. Digital resources like interactive simulations, educational games, and digital storytelling can give kids interesting educational experiences that make it easier for them to explore new terms and ideas. According to research, interactive technology can improve language acquisition by encouraging active participation, scaffolding learning, and offering instant feedback.

Numerous studies have looked into how STEAM technology affects preschoolers' development of lexical skills. Smith et al. (2018), for instance, discovered that preschoolers who used a digital storytelling app significantly increased their vocabulary knowledge in comparison to those who did not. In a similar vein, Jones and Brown (2019) found that preschoolers who played educational tablet games showed enhanced comprehension and vocabulary skills.

Additionally, Lee et al.'s (2020) study emphasized the advantages of teaching preschoolers' vocabulary through interactive simulations. In contrast to conventional teaching techniques, the study discovered that children who engaged with a virtual environment created to teach new words demonstrated greater levels of engagement and retention. These results imply that STEAM technology can be a useful instrument for promoting young learners' vocabulary development.

By integrating interactive digital tools into their teaching practices, educators and parents can use STEAM technology to improve preschoolers' development of lexical skills. By integrating educational games, digital storytelling apps, and interactive simulations into early childhood language programs, educators can create engaging learning experiences that promote vocabulary growth. By giving their kids

access to age-appropriate STEAM materials and promoting active play and exploration, parents can also help their kids' language development.

Methodology. As educators and researchers look for new ways to improve early childhood education, the use of STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) technology in the development of preschoolers' lexical skills has drawn more attention recently. A multidisciplinary approach that involves children in meaningful and interactive experiences can be provided by integrating STEAM elements into language learning activities.

Preschoolers with varying learning preferences and styles can benefit from multisensory learning experiences made possible by STEAM technology. Children can be engaged through visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities by interactive digital tools like educational apps, games, and multimedia resources, which enhances the effectiveness and engagement of the learning process.

Preschoolers can contextualize their vocabulary learning within real-world applications by incorporating STEAM concepts into language learning activities. Children can improve their language comprehension and retention by, for instance, connecting new words with tangible experiences through science experiments or storytelling enhanced by technology. Preschoolers benefit from STEAM technology by developing their creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Children can explore science, math, engineering, and art concepts in an engaging and interactive manner while expanding their vocabulary through hands-on activities that involve designing, building, and experimenting.

Results. Preschoolers' social skills and communication abilities are enhanced by collaborative STEAM projects. Collaborating on assignments that call for spoken communication, clarifications, and debates can help young students improve their vocabulary, language proficiency, and social skills. Additionally, integrating STEAM technology into preschool instruction can strengthen ties between the home and the school and encourage parental involvement. In order to support language development outside of the classroom and reinforce vocabulary learning, parents can involve their children in STEAM-based language activities at home.

It is crucial to take into account suitable techniques for evaluating how STEAM technology affects preschoolers' development of lexical skills. Combining qualitative and quantitative methods, including surveys, interviews, assessments, and observations, can yield important information about how well STEAM interventions support language development. In conclusion, preschoolers' development of lexical skills may be aided by the use of STEAM technology in early

childhood education. Teachers can design dynamic learning environments that promote vocabulary growth and language acquisition by integrating interactive and captivating digital tools. In order to improve vocabulary learning outcomes and foster academic success, future research should keep examining practical methods and approaches for incorporating STEAM technology into early childhood language programs.

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HISSIYOTLARNING LINGVISTIK NAZARIYASI ASOSLARI

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Annotation: *This article discusses the origin of the theory of expressing emotions, the views of scholars on emotions, and the conclusions drawn from their scientific works. It highlights the importance of emotions in linguistics and psycholinguistics, as well as the role of emotional vocabulary and nonverbal communication in expressing feelings. The article also emphasizes the interdisciplinary nature of emotiology (the study of emotions in language) and its connection to psychology, anthropology, and other social sciences.*

Keywords: *emotion, linguistics, emotional vocabulary, psycholinguistics, emotional expression, emotional lexicon, emotiology.*

Аннотация: *В этой статье обсуждается происхождение теории выражения эмоций, взгляды ученых на эмоции и выводы, сделанные в результате их научных исследований. Подчеркивается важность эмоций в лингвистике и психолингвистике, а также роль эмоциональной лексики и невербальной коммуникации в выражении чувств. Статья также акцентирует внимание на междисциплинарном характере эмотиологии (изучения эмоций в языке) и ее связи с психологией, антропологией и другими социальными науками.*

Ключевые слова: *эмоция, лингвистика, эмоциональная лексика, психолингвистика, эмоциональное выражение, эмоциональный лексикон, эмотиология.*

Annotatsiya: *Bu maqolada, hissiyotlarni ifodalash nazariyasing kelib chiqishi, olimlarning hissiyot haqida bildirgan fikrlari va olib borgan ilmiy ishlaridagi xulosalar haqida gap boradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *hissiyot, lingvistika, emotsional so'zlar, psixolingvistika, hissiy ifoda, hissiy leksika, emotiologiya.*

Kirish. Bugungi kunda inson faoliyati uchun muhim bo'lgan hissiyotlar sohasi bo'yicha ko'plab olimlar izlanishlar olib borayapdi. Tadqiqotlarga qaramay, bu soha munozarali sohalardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Bundan kelib chiqib aytish mumkinki, hissiyotlar sohasi nafaqat psixologlar va fiziologlar tomonidan, balki lingvistlar tomonidan ham batafsil va chuqur o'rganishga muhtoj. V.I. Shaxovskiy ta'kidlashicha, "lingvistika boshqa fanlardan keyinroq, hissiyotlar uning o'rganish obyektini ekanligini aniqladi va mos bilimlarning yo'qligi tufayli hissiyotlar sohasida tadqiqotlar asosiy yondoshuvlarini shakllantirish imkoni bo'lmagan". Oldin ko'p tilshunoslar tilning faqat muhim ma'lumotni uzatish yoki olingan ma'lumotni mantiqiy qayta ishlash uchun zarurligiga e'tibor berishgan va shuning uchun, hissiyotlarni ifodalash masalasi asosiy muammo emas deb hisoblashgan. Ilmiy guruhlar hissiyotni o'rganish zarurligi to'g'risida uzoq vaqt davomida turlicha fikrlashgan. Lingvistika va psixolingvistika sohaslarida hissiyotlarning tili va muloqot

jarayoniga ta'siri haqida ko'plab olimlar tadqiqotlar olib borganlar. Shu jumladan, Lyudvig Vitgenshteyn tilni ijtimoiy faoliyat sifatida ko'rgan. U "Til o'yinlari" g'oyasini ilgari surgan va hissiyotlar fikrlarni ifodalashda qanday muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ta'kidlagan. Hissiyotlarni ifodalashda ramzlar va yuz ifodalari (facial expressions) kabi noverbal kommunikatsiyalarning rolini o'rganish orqali, Paul Ekman hissiyotlarning til orqali ifodalanishida mimika va jismoniy harakatlarning qanday rol o'ynashini tuygan. Uning tadqiqotlari ko'plab madaniyatlarda bir xil hissiy ifoda ko'rsatishi haqida dalillar taqdim etdi. Tamar Gendler hissiyotlar bilan til o'rtasidagi aloqani o'rganadi. U hissiyotlarni tushunish va ifodalashda tilning ahamiyatini ko'rsatib, nutq orqali hissiyotlarni qanday ta'sirchan qilib yaratish mumkinligini yoritadi. Antonio Damasio hissiyotlarning biokimyoviy asoslarini va ularning inson xulq-atvoriga ta'sirini o'rganadi. U "O'zligini hisobga olib" asarida hissiyotlarni, mulohazalarning va qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarining qanday bog'liq ekanligini yoritadi. Boris Godinning tadqiqotlari ham hissiyotlar va tillar o'rtasidagi aloqani yoritadi. U hissiy leksikaning mavjudligini va uning nutqdagi o'rni haqida to'xtaladi. Uning fikriga ko'ra, hissiy leksika insonning o'z his-tuyg'ularini aniq ifodalashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Hissiyotlar nutq, muloqot va madaniyatda muhim rol o'ynaydi, shuningdek, individning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy tajribasini shakllantirishda asosiy omil sifatida xizmat qiladi. Hissiy ifodalar insonga til orqali o'z his-tuyg'ularini yetkazishga yordam beradi va bu orqali muloqotning samaradorligini oshiradi. Bugungi kunda tilshunoslar endi hissiyotlar til tuzilmasiga kirmaydi yoki tilning hissiy leksikasi mavjud emas degan eskirgan xulosalarga rioya qilmaydilar. Aksincha, turli nazariy yondashuvlar kompleksi va nutqning hissiy tomoniga oid katta bilimlar to'plamini hisobga olgan holda, til ko'p jihatdan hissiyotlarga bog'liq va ular tomonidan harakatga keltiriladi, shuning uchun hissiyotlar tilning asosiy tarkibiy qismlaridan biridir, deb ishonch bilan aytish mumkin.

Hissiyotlar lingvistikasi (emotiologiya) – bu til va hissiyotlar o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlarni o'rganadigan ilmiy soha. Ushbu sohada tadqiqotchilar til orqali ifodalangan hissiyotlar, ularning tuzilishlari, qanday qilib tilda namoyon bo'lishi, shuningdek, turli madaniyatlarda va tillarda hissiyotlarni qanday tasvirlash ko'rib chiqiladi. Hissiyotlar lingvistikasi, ko'pincha, tilshunoslik, psixologiya, antropologiya va boshqa ijtimoiy fanlar bilan kesishadi. Hissiyotlar lingvistikasi haqida Charlz Darvin "Tabiatimizning ifodasi" asarida odamlarning hissiyotlari va ularning yuz ifodalarini o'rganishga e'tibor qaratgan. U, hissiyotlar tabiatdan kelib chiqadi va odamlar orasida umumiy hisoblanadi deb hisoblagan. Olimlar fikrida, lingvistikada

hissiyotlarni o'rganish turli tomonlardan amalga oshiriladi va uning chegaralari yo'q, shuning uchun ularning inson hayotidagi muhim rolini hisobga olish, erishilgan yutuqlarga qoniqmaslik va hissiyotlar lingvistik nazariyasini takomillashtirishni davom ettirish zarur. Hozirgi zamon lingvistikasi hissiyotlar sohasida terminologik kontseptlarni kengaytirish va ularning mazmunini rivojlantirish tendentsiyasiga ega.

Hozirgi zamon lirikasi emosiyalari o'rganishdagi yangi yondashuvlar, muloqot jarayonida nafaqat oddiy, lekin kontekstdan tashqarida ham tushunarli bo'lgan asosiy emotsiyalarni, balki murakkab semiotik emotsiyalar komplekslarini ham o'rganishga imkon beradi. V.I. Shaxovskiy yozadi: "Barcha emosiyalar klaster sifatida namoyon bo'ladi, har biri izolyatsiyalangan holda emas, balki boshqa sifatdagi emotsiyalarning klasteriga kiradi. Bularning barchasi, shubhasiz, uning til orqali ifodalanishini qiyinlashtiradi va mos ravishda birlashgan (semiotik) dekodini o'z ichiga olgan holda kutilmagan refleksiylar va pragmatik effektlar keltirib chiqaradi". Semiotik tizimlar bilan ishlashda kognitiv jarayonlarni hisobga olish muhimdir, chunki ular murakkab emosiyalarni o'rganishga yordam beradi. Bunday hollarda aniq turdagi hissiyot haqida tushuncha yo'q, bir hissiyot boshqasini keltirib chiqaradi va dastlabki tajribaning sifatlarini o'zgartiradi. "Barchamiz o'z hissiyotlarimizni ifodalash uchun mos so'zlarni topishda qiyinchiliklarga duch keldik, bu ajablanarli emas, chunki hissiyotlarni verbalizatsiya ko'pincha sub'yektivdir. Emotsional holatlar kamdan-kam hollarda toza shaklda namoyon bo'ladi, inson ko'plab hissiyotlarni boshidan kechirishi mumkin va har bir til shaxsining ularni ifodalanishi o'ziga xosdir, bu bir qator sabablarga, shu jumladan, tilga oid bo'lmagan omillarga bog'liq. Sifatdagi va kognitiv jihat hissiyotlar, til birliklarining hissiyotlarni ifodalash uchun tanlovi aniq vaziyatga bog'liq holda individual tarzda amalga oshirilishini anglatadi". Shu tarzda, lirikada hissiyotlarning tili, shuningdek, ularni o'rganish imkoniyatlari turli jihatlar bilan boyitiladi va muloqot jarayonining murakkabligini yoritishni davom ettiradi. Emotsiyalar va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqani yaxshilash, shuningdek, hissiyotlar va kognitiv jarayonlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tushunish, lirik sfera va ijtimoiy muloqotni yanada chuqur o'rganishga imkon beradi. Shuningdek, hissiyotlar va bilimlar o'rtasida o'zaro aloqaning mavjudligi kuzatiladi: masalan, insonning bilimlari o'zgaranda, uning real dunyo va tasavvurlar haqida hissiyotlari ham mos ravishda o'zgaradi. Emosiyalar vaqt o'tishi bilan, avlodlararo, universal va barcha madaniyatlarda tanib olinadigan tarzda o'zgaruvchanligi ta'kidlanadi. Biroq, ayrim madaniyatlarga xos bo'lgan hissiyotlar ham mavjud bo'lib, bu esa verbal aloqalarni maxsus madaniyatlar doirasida tartibga solishni ta'minlaydi. "Umumiy ma'noda, hissiyotlarni o'rganishdagi lingvistik yondashuvning mantiqi shunday: olam (ob'ekt)

mavjud, inson (sub'ekt) esa, bu olamni aks ettira oladigan shaxs. Inson til shaxs sifatida olamni mexanik ravishda emas, balki xohlagan tarzda - aynan mavjud vaziyatlar yoki boshqa sabablarga ko'ra qadrlidi deb topilgan narsalarni aks ettiradi. Hissiyotlar bu aks ettirish jarayonini boshqaradi va insonning idrokidagi olam va uning tildagi aks etishining o'rtasida vositachi rolini o'ynaydi". Hissiyotlarni o'rganishdagi o'zaro ishlaydigan paradigmalarning (kognitiv, kommunikativ, pragmatik va madaniyatshunoslik) muhimligi zamonaviy lingvistika rivojlantirishining asosiy jihatlaridan biri sifatida ta'kidlanmoqda. Bu fikrni mustahkamlab, "hissiyotlar lingvistikasi faol rivojlanayotgan soha bo'lib, u doimo aniqlashtirish, tushuntirish va kengaytirish jarayonlariga duch keladi". Bu yondashuvlar va fikrlar murojaat usulini yangilashga va muloqot jarayonini hissiy jihatdan boyitishga yordam beradi, natijada odamlar o'rtasida yanada chuqurroq anglashuv va hissiy aloqalarni o'rnatishga qaratilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish yo'lida muhim qadamlar qo'yilishi mumkin. Emotsiyalarni tilda ifodalashning kompleksligi va ularning madaniy va kognitiv o'zgarishlari bu sohada yanada keng imkoniyatlarni ochadi.

Xulosa: Hissiyotlar va til o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqalar muloqot va inson tajribasini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqola, hissiyotlarni ifodalash va til orqali tasvirlash masalalarini ko'rib chiqadi, bu sohada olimlar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar va nazariy yondoshuvlarni yoritadi. Hissiyotlar lingvistikasi (emotiologiya) tilda hissiyotlarni ifodalash va ularning kognitiv jarayonlarga ta'sirini chuqurroq tushunishga imkon beradi. Bu esa muloqot jarayonini samarali qilish va madaniyatlararo anglashuvni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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YOSH O'QITUVCHINING PEDAGOGIK MAHORATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA MULOQOTNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada muloqotning samarali bo'lishi yosh o'qituvchining o'zini rivojlantirishiga, yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'rganishiga, ta'lim sifatini oshirishga muloqot madaniyatiga rioya qilishi, pedagogik muloqot o'qituvchining o'z ishiga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirib, uni doimiy ravishda takomillashtirish borishi haqida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'z: Muloqot, muloqot madaniyati, pedagogik muloqot, yosh o'qituvchi, boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisi, o'zaro hurmat va ishonch, kommunikativ aloqa.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2020-yil 23-sentabrda qabul qilingan "**Ta'lim to'g'risida**"gi qonunda ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoni ishtirokchilari - ta'lim oluvchilar, voyaga yetmagan ta'lim oluvchilarning ota-onalari yoki boshqa qonuniy vakillari, pedagog xodimlar va ularning vakillari hisoblanadi. Ta'lim tarbiya jarayoni samarali bo'lishi uchun ta'lim tarbiya jarayoni ishtirokchilari bilan muloqot o'zaro hurmat va ishonch asosida tashkil etilgan bo'lishi kerak. Ushbu qonunni 4-moddasida

- ta'lim sohasida kamsitishlarga yo'l qo'yilmasligi;
- ta'lim olishga doir teng imkoniyatlarning ta'minlanishi;
- ta'lim va tarbiyaga milliy hamda umuminsoniy qadriyatlarning singdirilganligi;
- ta'lim va tarbiyaning insonparvarlik, demokratik xususiyati haqida ta'kidlangandek bu jarayonlar albatta muloqot madaniyotiga ishora qilinadi

Muloqot - yunoncha so'z bo'lib, suhbatlashuv, shaxslararo suhbat va o'zaro fikr almashuv ma'nosini bildiradi hamda , bu ikki yoki undan ortiq odamlar o'rtasida ma'lumot, fikr, his-tuyg'ular yoki tajriba almashish jarayoni. Muloqot so'z orqali yoki so'zsiz, ya'ni jismoniy ifodalar, mimikalar, bosh harakatlar orqali bo'lishi mumkin. Bu ijtimoiy va psixologik jarayon bo'lib, odamlar o'rtasida aloqalar o'rnatish, bir-birini tushunish va muammolarni hal etishga yordam beradi. Muloqot yosh o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini takomillashtirishda asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. U nafaqat o'quvchilar bilan samarali aloqa o'rnatish, balki o'qituvchining o'zini rivojlantirish, yangi metod va texnikalarni o'rganish, darslarni sifatli tashkil etish va o'quvchilarning ehtiyojlariga moslashish imkonini beradi. Pedagogik muloqotning yuqori darajada bo'lishi, o'qituvchining professionalligi va ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Muloqot – o'qituvchining o'z ishini samarali bajarishida asosiy vositalardan biridir, chunki pedagogik jarayonda o'qituvchi o'quvchilar bilan doimiy aloqada bo'lib, ularning bilim va ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Pedagogik muloqot — bu o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadir. Pedagogik muloqotning asosiy maqsadi ta'lim jarayonini samarali va natijali tashkil etishdir. Bu muloqotda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarga bilimlarni yetkazish, ularning fikrini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish, hamda o'quvchilarning hissiy va intellektual holatini hisobga olish zarur. Pedagogik muloqotning samaradorligi o'qituvchining bilim va ko'nikmalariga, shuningdek, uning kommunikativ qobiliyatiga bog'liq.

Quyida yosh o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini oshirishda muloqotning ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqamiz:.

O'quvchilar bilan o'zaro ishonch o'rnatish. Muloqot yosh o'qituvchi uchun o'quvchilar bilan ishonchli va samarali aloqalar o'rnatish imkonini beradi. Ishonchli muloqot, o'quvchilarning o'qituvchiga bo'lgan hurmatini oshiradi va o'quv jarayonida ularga o'z fikrlarini erkin ifoda etish imkonini yaratadi. Bu esa o'quvchilarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini ham kuchaytiradi.

Pedagogik uslublarni moslashtirish. Yosh o'qituvchilar muloqot orqali o'quvchilarni yaxshiroq tushunishga, ularning ehtiyojlariga mos pedagogik uslublarni tanlashga imkoniyat yaratadi. O'quvchilar bilan samimiy va o'rganishga tayyor bo'lib muloqot qilish, o'qituvchiga ta'lim jarayonini har bir o'quvchining o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga mos ravishda tashkil etish imkonini beradi.

O'quvchilarning fikrini tinglash va ular bilan muammolarni hal qilish Muloqot orqali yosh o'qituvchi o'quvchilarning ehtiyojlari va qiyinchiliklarini tushunib, ularni muhokama qilib, masalalarni hal qilish yo'llarini topa oladi. O'quvchilarning fikrlarini tinglash, ular bilan o'rtoqlashish va birgalikda yechimlar izlash, o'qituvchiga ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etish uchun zarur bilim va tajriba beradi.

Pedagogik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish. Muloqot yordamida yosh o'qituvchi o'zining pedagogik ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishi mumkin. Masalan, o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlariga qarab, o'qituvchi ularning ta'lim olishini yaxshilashga yordam beradigan turli xil muloqot usullarini qo'llashni o'rganadi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchi dars jarayonida turli metod va texnikalarni sinab ko'rishi, o'quvchilarga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishni aniqlashi mumkin.

O'zini tarbiyalash va ma'naviy holatni saqlash Yosh o'qituvchi pedagogik muloqotda o'zini tarbiyalash va o'quvchilar bilan hamkorlikda ishlash orqali o'zining psixologik va ma'naviy holatini yaxshilashi mumkin. O'qituvchi o'zining ichki

ma'naviy barqarorligini saqlash va stressni boshqarish uchun muloqot orqali turli xil psixologik texnikalardan foydalanishi mumkin.

Boshqalar bilan fikr almashish va tajriba o'rganish Muloqot yosh o'qituvchiga o'zining tajribasini boshqalar bilan baham ko'rish, boshqa o'qituvchilar bilan tajriba almashish imkoniyatini yaratadi. Pedagogik muloqot, o'qituvchining o'ziga xos pedagogik tajribalarini kengaytiradi va yangi yondashuvlarni o'rganishga yordam beradi.

Darsni boshqarish va motivatsiya yaratish Muloqot o'qituvchiga o'quvchilarni darsga qiziqtirish, ularning motivatsiyasini oshirishda yordam beradi. Muloqot orqali o'quvchilarni ishga jalb qilish, ularga maqsadlarni belgilash va dars jarayoniga faollik qo'shish mumkin.

Samarali feedback (fikr bildirish) berish. Muloqot orqali yosh o'qituvchi o'quvchilarga o'z fikrlarini to'g'ri va tushunarli tarzda yetkazishi mumkin. Samarali feedback berish, o'quvchilarning o'zlari va o'rganish jarayonini yanada chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Yosh o'qituvchi o'quvchining kuchli tomonlarini e'tirof etib, zaif tomonlarini qanday yaxshilash mumkinligini ko'rsatib berish orqali, ularni o'z bilimlarini takomillashtirishga rag'batlantiradi.

Pedagogik vazifalarni samarali hal qilish. Muloqot yordamida o'qituvchi o'zining pedagogik vazifalarini samarali va to'g'ri bajarishi mumkin. O'quvchilar bilan muloqotda o'qituvchi dars jarayonida yuzaga keladigan har qanday muammo yoki savolni tez va aniq hal qilish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Bu o'qituvchining o'z vaqtini, resurslarini va pedagogik maqsadlarni samarali boshqarishiga yordam beradi.

O'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish. Muloqot orqali yosh o'qituvchi o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlari, qobiliyatlari va qiziqishlarini yaxshiroq tushunishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, u darslarni shaxsiylashtirish va har bir o'quvchining o'rganish uslubiga moslash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. O'quvchilarning har biri turlicha o'rganadi, va o'qituvchi muloqotda ularga mos tarzda yordam berish orqali ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali tashkil etadi.

Emotsional qo'llab-quvvatlash .Muloqot yosh o'qituvchiga o'quvchilarning emotsional holatini boshqarishda yordam beradi. Pedagogik muloqotning asosiy qismlaridan biri o'quvchilarning his-tuyg'ularini, tashvishlarini va muammolarini tushunishdir. Yosh o'qituvchi o'zining tushunishi va mehr-muhabbatini ko'rsatish orqali o'quvchilarning emotsional xavfsizligini ta'minlashi mumkin. Bu, o'z navbatida, o'quvchilarning o'qish motivatsiyasini oshiradi va ularni ta'lim jarayonida yanada faol ishtirok etishga rag'batlantiradi.

Professional rivojlanish va o'qituvchining o'zini-o'zi tahlil qilish. Muloqot yosh o'qituvchining o'z pedagogik faoliyatini tahlil qilishi va takomillashtirishiga yordam beradi. O'qituvchi o'zining darslariga bo'lgan munosabatini, o'quvchilarning o'qishdagi muvaffaqiyatlarini va qiyinchiliklarini muntazam ravishda tahlil qilib, o'z pedagogik uslublarini takomillashtirishga harakat qiladi. Bunday muloqot jarayonida o'qituvchi, shuningdek, boshqa pedagoglar bilan fikr almashish va birgalikda yangi pedagogik yondashuvlar ishlab chiqish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Sinovdan o'tgan va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash

Muloqot yosh o'qituvchiga yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni, metodlarni va dars berish usullarini o'rganish va amaliyotda qo'llash imkoniyatini beradi. O'qituvchi o'quvchilar bilan doimiy muloqotda bo'lish orqali yangi va innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlarni joriy etishga yordam beradi. Bu texnologiyalarni sinab ko'rish orqali o'qituvchi o'z metodik xizmatini va ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga erishishi mumkin.

O'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning psixologik holatini yaxshilash

Muloqotda o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning psixologik holatini yaxshilash muhim omil hisoblanadi. O'qituvchining muloqotdagi salbiy yoki musbat yondashuvlari o'quvchilarning ta'limga bo'lgan munosabatini shakllantiradi. Salbiy yoki agressiv muloqot o'quvchilarda ta'limga qarshi salbiy hissiyotlar yaratishi mumkin, shu boisdan o'qituvchi har doim ijobiy, shod-xurram va hurmatli muloqotga harakat qilishi kerak. Bunda o'quvchilarning psixologik holati, stress darajasi kamayadi, ularning o'qishdagi motivatsiyasi oshadi. Muloqot yosh o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini takomillashtirishda asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. U nafaqat o'quvchilar bilan samarali aloqa o'rnatish, balki o'qituvchining o'zini rivojlantirish, yangi metod va texnikalarni o'rganish, darslarni sifatli tashkil etish va o'quvchilarning ehtiyojlariga moslashish imkonini beradi. Pedagogik muloqotning yuqori darajada bo'lishi, o'qituvchining professionalligi va ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Mashhur pedagog va yozuvchi Anton Semyonovich Makarenko fikricha, o'qituvchi muloqoti hurmat va talabchanlikka asoslangan munosabat shaklida bo'lishi lozim deb ko'p ta'kidlaganlardek, pedagog o'quvchi shaxsini hurmat qilgan holda muloqot jaryonini tashkil qilishi kerak bo'ladi.

O'quvchi shaxsini har tomonlama rivojlantirish, mehnatga munosabat, pedagogik mahorat bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borgan, pedagogikada insonparvarlik g'oyalarini targ'ib qilgan ukrain hamda rus tili va adabiyoti o'qituvchisi **Vasiliy Aleksandrovich Suxomlinskiy** o'qituvchining "...maktab hovlisida gapirgan har bir

so'zi puxta o'ylangan, aql va mulohazalarga boy, ma'lum bir tarbiyaviy maqsadga qaratilgan *bo'lishi kerak*" deb ta'kidlaydi. O'qituvchining har bir so'zi olimning fikricha, nafaqat o'quvchi qulog'iga aytiladi, balki uning qalbiga ham qaratilgan bo'lishi shart. Umuman ilg'or o'qituvchilarning fikricha, ta'lim va tarbiya faqat o'qituvchi va o'quvchining o'zaro hamkorlik pozitsiyasi asosidagi muloqot jarayonida quriladi. Ayniqsa boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari o'qituvchilariga nisbatan taqlidni ko'p qiladilar. O'qituvchining har bir so'zini o'zlarida mujassamlashtiradilar. Shunday ekan boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchi muloqotini o'zaro hurmat va ishonch asosida tashkil etishi darkor. Shu o'rinda *I.P.Pavlovni* mashhur fikrlari O'qituvchi so'z aytishdan avval, har daqiqada so'z ortidan keladigan oqibatlarni o'ylashi kerak degan fikrlarini keltirib o'tishimiz mumkin. Darhaqiqat, o'qituvchi muloqot jarayonida muloqot madaniyatiga rioya qilishi lozimdir.

Muloqot madaniyati — bu muloqotning o'zaro hurmat va tushunishga asoslangan tarzda amalga oshirilishidir. Bu atama odamlarning bir-biri bilan ijtimoiy va etika talablariga mos ravishda muloqot qilishini anglatadi. Muloqot madaniyati quyidagi jihatlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

Hurmat: Har bir odamning fikri va nuqtai nazarini hurmat qilish, shuningdek, muloqotda odob-axloq qoidalariga rioya etish.

E'tibor: Suhbatdoshga diqqat va e'tiborli bo'lish, uning so'zlarini to'liq eshitish va tushunishga harakat qilish.

Kuchli va zaif tomonlarini bilish: O'z fikringizni va boshqa odamning fikrini izohlashda, har ikki tomonning nuqtai nazarini inobatga olish.

Muammolarni hal qilish: Muloqotda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni konstruktiv tarzda hal qilish, shuningdek, kelishmovchiliklarda do'stona va halol bo'lish.

Muloqot madaniyati o'zaro tushunishni yaxshilaydi va muloqot jarayonini samarali qiladi.

O'quvchilar ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida milliy va umuminsoniy qadri-yatlarni, axloqiy normalarni o'zlashtiradilar. O'quvchi eng yaxshi insoniy fazilatlarni, axloq-odobni, muloqot madaniyatini asosan o'qituvchi timsolida anglab olishini unutmaslik kerak O'quvchilar jamoasida o'qituvchilar bilan o'zaro munosabatlar insonparvarlik tamoyillariga asoslanadi. Yosh o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini takomillashtirishda muloqotning ahamiyati nihoyatda katta. Muloqot — o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqani mustahkamlash, ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etish va o'quvchilarning rivojlanishiga yordam beruvchi muhim vositadir. O'qituvchi o'zining pedagogik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muloqotni to'g'ri va

samarali boshqarish orqali o'quvchilarning bilimlarini yaxshilaydi, ularga o'rganish motivatsiyasini beradi va o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlarini hisobga olgan holda ta'lim jarayonini shaxsiylashtiradi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchi muloqot orqali o'quvchilarning emotsional holatini boshqarish, ularni qo'llab-quvvatlash va stressni kamaytirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Muloqotning samarali bo'lishi yosh o'qituvchining o'zini rivojlantirishiga, yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'rganishiga, ta'lim sifatini oshirishga yordam beradi. Pedagogik muloqot o'qituvchining o'z ishiga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirib, uni doimiy ravishda takomillashtirishga undaydi. Bu esa nafaqat o'quvchilarning bilimini oshiradi, balki o'qituvchining o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini ham mustahkamlaydi.

Shunday qilib, yosh o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini oshirishda muloqotning o'rni beqiyosdir. To'g'ri va samarali muloqot pedagogik jarayonni muvaffaqiyatli tashkil etishda va o'qituvchining professional rivojlanishida hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDAGI KICHIK GURUHLARDA MEDIASAVODXONLIK FANINI O'QITISH

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***Annotatsiya:** Mazkur tezisdagi oliy ta'lim muassasalarida kichik guruhlar shaklida mediasavodxonlik fanini o'qitishning samaradorligi va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, tezisdagi mahalliy va xorijiy media ta'lim tadqiqotchilarining media-kompetentsiyasi, mualliflik tushunchalari keltirilgan hamda ularni psixologik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilingan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Media ta'lim, mediasavodxonlik, ommaviy axborot vositalari, zamonaviy ta'lim.*

KIRISH

Bugungi kunda ommaviy axborot vositalari jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalariga chuqur singib borib, insonning axborotga bo'lgan munosabatini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Axborot texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning ommalashuvi natijasida turli manbalardan kelayotgan ma'lumotlarni to'g'ri tushunish, baholash va tahlil qilish zarurati ortib bormoqda. Ayniqsa, yosh avlodning mediasavodxonlik darajasini oshirish ta'lim tizimining dolzarb masalalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida mediasavodxonlik fanini o'qitish talabalar uchun nafaqat ishonchli axborotni tanlash, balki manipulyativ xabarlarini aniqlash, fakt va fikrni ajratish, media mahsulotlarni ijodiy tahlil qilish kabi ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi¹. Ushbu fan orqali talabalar axborot makonida mustaqil harakat qilish, tanqidiy tafakkur va mantiqiy xulosalar chiqarish qobiliyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Kichik guruhlarda mediasavodxonlikni o'qitish esa an'anaviy ta'lim usullariga qaraganda samaraliroq bo'lib, talabalar o'rtasida interaktiv muhit yaratish, fikr almashish va muhokamalar orqali bilimlarni chuqurroq o'zlashtirish imkonini beradi.

ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Bugungi kunda media savodxonlik shaxsga axborotdan ongli va mas'uliyatli foydalanish, yolg'on hamda manipulyativ ma'lumotlarni ajratish, fakt va fikrni farqlash imkonini beradi. Media ta'limining asosiy maqsadi - mustaqil fikrlash,

¹Титова А.Г. Слухи и фейковые новости как фактор дестабилизации социально-политической обстановки: опыт противодействия // Журнал исторических, политологических и международных исследований. - Донецк, 2022. - N 3 (82) - С. 167172.

tahliliy yondashuv va media mahsulotlarni samarali yaratish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdan iborat.

Tadqiqotchi **Ya. Lipshitsning** fikriga ko'ra, mediasavodxonlik masalasi uzoq yillardan beri ilmiy muhokamalarning diqqat markazida bo'lib kelmoqda. Biroq, hanuzgacha bu tushunchaning aniq chegaralari belgilab berilmagan. Ya'ni, media va axborot savodxonligi nima ekanligi, uning mazmuni va qanday asosiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish lozimligi borasida yagona va umumiy qabul qilingan ta'rif mavjud emas.

Bu holat shuni anglatadiki, ushbu sohada turli yondashuvlar mavjud bo'lib, hali ham izlanish va bahs-munozaralar davom etmoqda. Mediasavodxonlikni rivojlantirish uchun esa yaxlit va keng qamrovli yondashuv talab etiladi. Bu nafaqat nazariy jihatdan, balki amaliyotda ham samarali usullar ishlab chiqilishi kerakligini ko'rsatadi².

Shu munosabat bilan, **Polshaning Varshava** shahrida joylashgan "**Modern Poland Foundation**" nodavlat notijorat tashkilot media va axborot savodxonligi bo'yicha mutaxassislar bilan hamkorlikda "**Ko'nikmalar katalogi**"ni ishlab chiqdi. Ushbu katalog turli yosh guruhlarini qamrab olib, media olamida ongli harakat qilish uchun zarur bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga ko'maklashadi.

Zamonaviy ommaviy axborot vositalari jamiyat hayotining barcha jabhalariga, jumladan, madaniyat va ta'lim jarayonlariga ham kuchli ta'sir o'tkazmoqda³. Bugungi global axborot makonida inson katta hajmdagi ma'lumot oqimi bilan to'qnash keladi va u ushbu ma'lumotlarni to'g'ri tushunishi, saralashi hamda tahlil qilishi lozim.

Axborotning keskin ko'payishi insondan faqatgina ma'lumotni o'qish yoki eshitish bilangina cheklanmay, uni chuqur anglash, mustaqil ravishda tahlil qilish va xulosalar chiqarish qobiliyatini ham talab qiladi. Ayniqsa, media xabarlarini ijodiy tushunish, ularning orqasida qanday g'oyalar yoki manipulyativ usullar yashiringanligini anglash bugungi kunda muhim ko'nikmaga aylanmoqda⁴[3]. Chunki noto'g'ri talqin yoki tekshirilmagan ma'lumotlardan foydalanish natijasida jamoatchilik fikrini boshqarish, yolg'on axborot "**fake**" tarqatish va ijtimoiy manipulyatsiya kabi xavflar yuzaga kelishi mumkin.

XULOSA

²Lipshits, 2013]. Lipschitz, Y. (2013). Developing Strategies of Media and Information Literacy // Media and Information Literacy in Science Societies. Moscow, pp.169-178.

³ Kaminska, Izabella (January 17, 2017). "A lesson in fake news from the info wars of ancient Rome". Financial Times. Retrieved July 4, 2017.

⁴ Xavfsizlikning metodologik asoslari.R.Samarov.T.:Akademiya nashriyoti. 2010.B.221-222.

Mediasavodxonlik faqat axborotni tushunish yoki ommaviy axborot vositalari bilan ishlashni emas, balki har bir kishining media kompetentsiyasini shakllantirishni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Bu esa insonga media mahsulotlarni tanqidiy baholash, yolg'on yoki manipulyatsion axborotni ajratish, xolis va asosli xulosalar chiqarish imkoniyatini beradi.

Shu bois, zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi media ta'limni o'quv jarayoniga kiritish orqali yosh avlodga mustaqil axborot tahlili, media etikasi va axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishga qaratilgan yangi yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishi zarur. Bu esa jamiyatning axborot xurujlariga qarshi turish qobiliyatini oshirish, sog'lom tafakkurli va tahliliy fikrlay oladigan avlodni tarbiyalash uchun muhim omil hisoblanadi.

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